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Sent: Thu, 29 Mar 2007 14:22:02 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Agenda question
Attachments: Schoen JUro 2006 cost analysis of neoMC.pdf

Hi, all.

I was just about to invite Edgar Schoen to give the talk on cost-effectiveness of neonatal MC, when I realized that the title of that session is *What is the potential impact of male circumcision on HIV transmission in the US?* The data I've seen from Schoen does not relate directly to HIV transmission, so I'm not sure he would fit well in that session. What we're really talking about for that presentation is Stephanie and Angela's lifetime risk study.

Would Schoen perhaps fit better in the slot we've got labeled *Evidence of other health effects of male circumcision?* I imagine he'd be willing to talk more generally about potential "other" benefits of MC, rather than the cost-effectiveness part, per se. Attached is his paper on costs/benefits of neonatal circ from Kaiser Permanente (JUrol 2006), to give you a flavor of what he might be able to discuss.

What are your thoughts?
-Allan

PS – Surprisingly, I have not yet heard from Van Howe. I'm looking for other potential counterpoint speakers and have one or two leads.

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Cost Analysis of Neonatal Circumcision in a Large Health Maintenance Organization

Edgar J. Schoen,* Christopher J. Colby and Trinh T. To

From the Department of Genetics, Kaiser Permanente Medical Center and Division of Research, Kaiser Permanente Medical Care Program (CJC), Oakland, California

Purpose: We studied the costs of newborn circumcision in relation to its health benefits later in life.

Materials and Methods: We conducted a retrospective database analysis using direct internal cost data from Kaiser Permanente Northern California—a large health maintenance organization—and published cost data (including the cost of medically indicated postneonatal circumcision). The study cohort consisted of 14,893 male infants born in 1996. One-way sensitivity analysis was used to demonstrate the impact of selected variables in the model. Monte Carlo analysis was used to determine the 95% confidence intervals.

Results: Postneonatal circumcision was 10 times as expensive as neonatal circumcision (\$1,921 per infant vs \$165 per newborn), and was medically indicated for 9.6% of uncircumcised males. Cost benefits of circumcision resulted from prevention of infant urinary tract infection, balanoposthitis, phimosis, HIV infection and penile cancer. Assuming initial neonatal circumcision cost to be \$200, the future health care cost offset (avoided) was calculated as \$183 (range \$93 to \$303 in 95% of simulations).

Conclusions: Multiple lifetime medical benefits of neonatal circumcision can be achieved at little or no cost. Because postneonatal circumcision is so expensive, its rate is the most important factor determining future cost savings from newborn circumcision.

Key Words: circumcision; costs and cost analysis; health maintenance organizations; infant; infant, newborn

(b)(4)

(4)

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Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: An insurmountable problem?

Peter,

This morning Jennifer informed Allan that the funding for the circumcision consultation is "extramural" which means we have to let a contract in order to pay for hotel meeting space. She checked with the division and there is no way to use extramural funds except by contract. We are required to have a contractor do the meeting arrangements, despite having previously been instructed to have the SBU do it.

Obviously, there is not time enough to let a contract and make the arrangements in time for the currently planned meeting dates.

Advice?

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
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Subject: Another article.

It's not on the e-journal list at CDC so I've ordered a copy from the library and will send around when I have it.

Fine-touch pressure thresholds in the adult penis

Author(s): Sorrells ML, Snyder JL, Reiss MD, et al.

Reference: BJU Int. 2007 Apr;99(4):864-9.

Published Abstract: OBJECTIVE: To map the fine-touch pressure thresholds of the adult penis in circumcised and uncircumcised men, and to compare the two populations. SUBJECTS AND METHODS: Adult male volunteers with no history of penile pathology or diabetes were evaluated with a Semmes-Weinstein monofilament touch-test to map the fine-touch pressure thresholds of the penis. Circumcised and uncircumcised men were compared using mixed models for repeated data, controlling for age, type of underwear worn, time since last ejaculation, ethnicity, country of birth, and level of education. RESULTS: The glans of the uncircumcised men had significantly lower mean (sem) pressure thresholds than that of the circumcised men, at 0.161 (0.078) g ($P = 0.040$) when controlled for age, location of measurement, type of underwear worn, and ethnicity. There were significant differences in pressure thresholds by location on the penis ($P < 0.001$). The most sensitive location on the circumcised penis was the circumcision scar on the ventral surface. Five locations on the uncircumcised penis that are routinely removed at circumcision had lower pressure thresholds than the ventral scar of the circumcised penis. CONCLUSIONS: The glans of the circumcised penis is less sensitive to fine touch than the glans of the uncircumcised penis. The transitional region from the external to the internal prepuce is the most sensitive region of the uncircumcised penis and more sensitive than the most sensitive region of the circumcised penis. Circumcision ablates the most sensitive parts of the penis.

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Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Colleagues,

In addition to the official conference events listed on the agenda we sent earlier, we will plan to gather informally at 6:00 PM on Wednesday 4/26 in the lobby of the Embassy Suites Hotel. The hotel will have

complimentary cocktails for hotel guests, and this gathering will be an opportunity to renew acquaintances and make new ones.

Thank you. We look forward to seeing you.

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Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US
Attachments: MC Consultation Agenda Final.pdf, CDC Fact Sheet.pdf, Sawires Coates Report 2006 opp and challenges.pdf, Circumcision_commentary_for consultation.pdf

Colleagues,

We are looking forward to your participation at the upcoming Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the United States. Attached are several documents for your reference:

1. Consultation Agenda
2. CDC Factsheet on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
3. Two overview papers that review many of the issues to be discussed at the consultation

Thank you, and see you next week.

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Consultation on Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences

Atlanta, GA
April 26-27, 2007

AGENDA

Thursday, April 26

8:30 Welcome Dr. Rob Janssen
8:45 Charge to the Consultants and recent WHO/UNAIDS guidance Dr. Tim Mastro

Why consider increasing male circumcision in the United States?

Moderator: Dr. Tim Mastro

9:00 Overview of international male circumcision and HIV Dr. Helen Weiss
9:25 Results of the South African Trial Dr. Bertran Auvert
9:45 Results of the Uganda Trial Dr. Robert Bailey
10:05 Results of the Rakai Trial Dr. Ron Gray
10:30 Discussion

11:00 Break

11:30 Overview of domestic male circumcision Dr. Peter Kilmarx
11:50 Evidence on male circumcision and HIV in MSM Dr. Susan Buchbinder
12:10 Evidence of adverse outcomes in male circumcision Dr. Robert S. Van Howe
12:30 Discussion

1:00 Lunch

What is the potential cost of male circumcision and impact on HIV transmission in the US?

Moderator: Dr. John Douglas

2:30 Modeling impact and cost-effectiveness Dr. Stephanie Sansom
3:00 Cost of circumcision in US newborns and adults Dr. Edgar Schoen
3:30 Discussion

4:00 Break

4:20 Risk communication and disinhibition Dr. Brad Bartholow
4:40 Ethical, religious, and cultural issues Dr. Bernard Lo
5:00 Discussion and public comment period
5:30 Adjourn

Friday, April 27

8:30 Charge to Breakout Groups

Dr. Dawn K. Smith

8:45 Concurrent Breakout Sessions

1. MSW in the US

Dr. Lee Warner, facilitator

2. MSM in the US

Dr. Gary Marks, facilitator

3. Newborns in the US

Dr. Allan Taylor, facilitator

11:30 Lunch

Moderator:Dr. Naomi Bock

1:00 Report back and discussion - MSW Rapporteur

1:30 Report back and discussion – MSM Rapporteur

2:00 Report back and discussion – newborns Rapporteur

2:30 Summary Comments

Dr. Rob Janssen

3:00 Adjourn

CDC HIV/AIDS Science Facts:

Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States

March 2007

This fact sheet summarizes information in four areas of male circumcision: 1) male circumcision and risk of HIV transmission; 2) male circumcision and other health conditions; 3) risks associated with male circumcision; and 4) status of HIV infection and male circumcision in the United States.

What is Male Circumcision?

Male circumcision is the surgical removal of some or all of the foreskin (or prepuce) from the penis [2].

Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission

Biologic Plausibility

Compared to the dry external skin surface, the inner mucosa of the foreskin has less keratinization (deposition of fibrous protein), a higher density of target cells for HIV infection (Langerhans cells), and is more susceptible to HIV infection in laboratory studies [3]. It has also been argued that the foreskin may have greater susceptibility to traumatic epithelial disruptions (tears) during intercourse, providing a portal of entry for pathogens including HIV [4]. In addition, the micro-environment in the preputial sac between the unretracted foreskin and the glans penis may be conducive to viral survival [2]. Finally, the higher rates of sexually transmitted genital ulcerative disease, such as syphilis,

observed in uncircumcised men may also increase susceptibility to HIV infection [5].

International Observational Studies

Multiple cross-sectional, prospective, and ecologic (population-level) studies have identified lack of male circumcision as a risk factor for HIV infection.

A systematic review and meta-analysis that focused on heterosexual transmission of HIV in Africa was published in 2000 [6]. It included 19 cross-sectional studies, five case-control studies, three cohort studies, and one partner study. A substantial protective effect of male circumcision on risk for HIV infection was noted, along with a reduced risk for genital ulcer disease. After adjusting for confounding factors in the population-based studies, the relative risk for HIV infection was 44% lower in circumcised men. The strongest association was seen in high-risk men, such as patients at sexually transmitted disease (STD) clinics, for whom the adjusted relative risk was 71% lower for circumcised men.

A review that included stringent assessment of 10 potential confounding factors and was stratified by study type or study population was published in 2004 [7]. Most of the studies were from Africa. Of the 35 observational studies included in the review, the 16 in the general population had inconsistent results. The one large prospective cohort study in this group showed a significant protective effect, with the odds of infection being

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42% lower in circumcised men [8]. The remaining nineteen studies were conducted in high-risk populations. These found a consistent, substantial protective effect, which increased with adjustment for confounding. Four of these were cohort studies: all demonstrated a protective effect, with two being statistically significant.

Ecologic studies also indicate a strong association between lack of male circumcision and HIV infection at the population level. Although links between circumcision, culture, religion, and risk behavior may account for some of the differences in HIV infection prevalence, the countries in Africa and Asia with prevalence of male circumcision of less than 20% have HIV-infection prevalences several times higher than countries in those regions where more than 80% of men are circumcised [9].

International Clinical Trials

Three randomized, controlled clinical trials have been undertaken in Africa to determine whether circumcision of adult males will reduce their risk for HIV infection. The study conducted in South Africa [10], was stopped in 2005 and those in Kenya [11] and Uganda [12] were stopped in 2006 after their interim analyses found that medical circumcision reduced male participants' risk of HIV infection.

In these studies, men who had been randomly assigned to the circumcision group had a 60% (South Africa), 53% (Kenya), and 51% (Uganda) lower incidence of HIV infection compared to men assigned to the wait list group to be circumcised at the end of the study. In all three studies, a few men who had been assigned to be circumcised did not undergo the procedure, and vice versa. When the data were reanalyzed to account for these deviations, men who had been circumcised had a 76% (South Africa), 60% (Kenya), and 55% (Uganda) reduction in risk of HIV infection compared to those who were not circumcised. The Uganda study investigators are also examining the following in an ongoing study: 1) safety and

acceptability of male circumcision in HIV-infected men and men of unknown HIV-infection status, 2) safety and acceptability of male circumcision in the men's female sex partners, and 3) effect of male circumcision on male-to-female transmission of HIV and other STDs.

Male Circumcision and Male-to-Female Transmission of HIV

In an earlier study of couples in Uganda in which the male partner was HIV infected and the female partner was initially HIV seronegative, the infection rates of the female partners differed by the circumcision status and viral load of the male partners. If the male blood HIV viral load was <50,000 copies/mL, there was no HIV transmission if the man was circumcised, compared to a rate of 9.6 per 100 person-years if the man was uncircumcised [8]. If viral load was not controlled for, there was a non-statistically significant trend towards a reduction in the male-to-female transmission rate from circumcised men compared to uncircumcised men. Such an effect may be due to decreased viral shedding from circumcised men or to a reduction in ulcerative sexually transmitted infections acquired by female partners of circumcised men [14].

Male Circumcision and Other Health Conditions

Lack of male circumcision has also been associated with sexually transmitted genital ulcer disease, infant urinary tract infections, penile cancer, and cervical cancer in female partners of uncircumcised men [2]. The latter two conditions are related to human papillomavirus (HPV) infection. Transmission of this virus is also associated with lack of male circumcision. A recent meta-analysis included 26 studies that assessed the association between male circumcision and risk of genital ulcer disease. The analysis concluded that there was a significantly lower risk of syphilis and chancroid among circumcised men, while the reduced risk of herpes simplex virus-2 infection had a borderline statistical significance [5].

Risks Associated with Male Circumcision

Reported complication rates depend on the type of study (e.g., chart review vs. prospective study), setting (medical vs. nonmedical facility), person operating (traditional vs. medical practitioner), patient age (infant vs. adult), and surgical technique or instrument used. The most common complications are minor bleeding and local infection. In large studies of infant circumcision in the U.S., complications rates range from 0.2 to 2.0% [2]. In the recently completed South African study of adult circumcision by general medical practitioners in their surgical offices, the overall complication rate was 3.8%. The most commonly reported complications were pain (0.8%), followed by swelling or hematoma, bleeding, and problems with appearance (each 0.6%). Damage to the penis (0.3%), infection (0.2%), and delayed wound healing (0.1%) were uncommon. There were no reported deaths or problems with urination [10].

HIV Infection and Male Circumcision in the United States

In 2004, men who have sex with men (MSM) (47%) and persons exposed through heterosexual contact (33%) accounted for an estimated 80% of all HIV/AIDS cases diagnosed in areas in the U.S. with confidential name-based reporting. Blacks accounted for 49% of cases and Hispanics for 18%. Infection rates in both groups were several-fold higher than that in whites. An overall prevalence of about less than 0.5% was estimated for the general population [15]. Although data on HIV infection rates are available since the beginning of the epidemic, data on circumcision and risk for HIV infection in the U.S. are limited. In one cross-sectional survey of MSM, lack of circumcision was associated with a two-fold increased odds of prevalent HIV infection [16]. In another, prospective study of MSM, lack of circumcision was also associated with a

two-fold increased risk for HIV seroconversion [17]. In both studies, the results were statistically significant and controlled statistically for other possible risk factors. In one prospective study of heterosexual men attending an urban STD clinic, when controlling for other risk factors, uncircumcised men had a 3.5-fold higher risk of HIV infection than men who were circumcised. However, this association was not statistically significant [18].

Status of Male Circumcision in the United States

In a national probability sample of adults in 1992, the National Health and Social Life Survey found that 77% of men reported being circumcised including 81% of white men, 65% of black men, and 54% of Hispanic men [19]. It is important to note that reported circumcision status may be subject to misclassification. In a study of adolescents, only 69% of circumcised and 65% of uncircumcised young men correctly identified their circumcision status as verified by physical exam [20].

According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999 and the overall proportion of newborns circumcised was stable from 1979 to 1999 [21]. Notably, the proportion of black newborns circumcised rose over this reporting period (58% to 64%), while the proportion of white infants circumcised remained stable (66%). In addition, the proportion of newborns who were circumcised in the Midwest increased over the 20-year period from 74% in 1979 to 81% in 1999, while the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased from 64% in 1979 to 37% in 1999. In another survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), circumcision rates increased from 48% during 1988-1991 to 61% during 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black [22].

In 1999, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) changed from routinely recommending circumcision to a neutral stance on circumcision, noting that: "It is legitimate for the parents to take into account cultural, religious, and ethnic traditions, in addition to medical factors, when making this choice." [23] This position was re-affirmed by the Academy in 2005. This change in policy may influence reimbursement for and practice of neonatal circumcision. In a 1995 review, 61% of circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant [24]. Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary [25].

Considerations for the United States

There are a number of important differences that must be considered in the possible role of male circumcision in HIV prevention in the U.S. Notably, the overall risk of HIV infection is considerably lower in the United States, changing risk-benefit and cost-effectiveness considerations. Also, studies to date have focused on heterosexual, penile-vaginal sex, the predominant mode of HIV transmission in Africa, while the predominant mode of sexual HIV transmission in the United States is by penile-anal sex among MSM. In addition, while the prevalence of circumcision may be somewhat lower in racial and ethnic groups with higher rates of HIV infection, most Americans are already circumcised, and it is not known if men at higher risk for HIV infection would be willing to be circumcised, nor if parents would be willing to have their infants circumcised to reduce possible future HIV infection risk. Lastly, whether the effect of male circumcision differs by HIV-1 subtype, predominately subtype B in the U.S. and subtypes A, C, and D in Africa, is also unknown.

Summary

Male circumcision has been associated with a lower risk for HIV infection in international observational studies and in three randomized, controlled clinical trials. Male circumcision could also reduce male-to-female transmission of HIV to a lesser extent. It has also been associated with a number of other health benefits. While there are risks to male circumcision, serious complications are rare. Accordingly, male circumcision, together with other prevention interventions, may play an important role in HIV prevention in settings similar to the clinical trials.

Male circumcision may also have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. With the results of three clinical trials showing that male circumcision decreases the risk for HIV infection, CDC is undertaking additional research and consultation to evaluate the potential value, risks, and feasibility of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention in the U.S.

As CDC proceeds with the development of public health recommendations for the U.S., individual men may wish to consider circumcision as an additional HIV prevention measure, but must recognize that circumcision 1) does carry risks and costs that must be considered in addition to potential benefits; 2) has only proven effective in reducing the risk of infection through insertive vaginal sex; and 3) confers only partial protection and should be considered only in conjunction with other proven prevention measures (abstinence, mutual monogamy, reducing number of sex partners, and correct and consistent condom use).

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***Male Circumcision and HIV/AIDS:
Opportunities and Challenges***

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Preface

This review was commissioned by the Ford Foundation in order to deepen our understanding of the current research on the interfaces between male circumcision and HIV/AIDS. The experience of our grantees in working in the community development, sexuality, sexual health, and human rights fields tells us that many factors would have to be considered before making a decision to implement male circumcision as an HIV/AIDS prevention mechanism. It would need to take into account questions of personal autonomy, bodily integrity, and human rights; of social and cultural dynamics in specific contexts; and of health system capacity to deliver integrated HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment interventions to the majority of the population.

We wanted to understand what the new research tells us about these broader contextual factors, and what kinds of issues would need further exploration in order to ensure that any new preventive intervention would only be implemented after a thorough consideration of the individual, social, and health system implications, as well as the likelihood of success outside of a research environment.

This review aimed to provide us with such information. Since there are many others in the field who are asking similar questions, we asked the authors to make it available to the public as a contribution towards constructive dialogue on the options.

Barbara Klugman and Jacob Gayle,
Ford Foundation

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes available information on male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy, and the policy and prevention implications of its implementation. To this end, the report examines:

1. Summary of HIV prevention science and practice;
2. A review of the currently available data from observational studies and randomized controlled clinical trials;
3. Adult male circumcision, other health benefits, and the implications for women's health;
4. Biological mechanism responsible for reduced susceptibility to HIV infection and other medical benefits among circumcised males;
5. Medical professional group policy statements pertaining to male circumcision;
6. Challenges related to male circumcision;
7. Research priorities;
8. Ethical concerns; and
9. Potential next steps.

While the results of the recently stopped clinical trials demonstrating the protective effect of male circumcision on HIV infection are extremely promising and can have enormous impact on the HIV epidemic, there are numerous implementation challenges, contextual considerations, and ethical concerns that require rigorous attention.

We identify here 15 such challenges, and the list can probably be expanded. Nonetheless, we present these to encourage discussion, and to ensure that these issues are considered as new medical findings are released and implementation plans are drawn up. Furthermore, we hope that these challenges will enrich and add nuance to the discussions as to how male circumcision should be offered as an HIV prevention intervention, and what steps need to be taken to ensure it is implemented in an ethical and effective manner.

We highlight the following:

1. **Acceptability:** Price, pain, and lack of complications seem to be universal concerns and need to be attended to in rollout of male circumcision. Rollout programs will consider these and other issues as plans for scale-up and implementation are considered.
2. **Level of protection:** The benefit from male circumcision is relative, not absolute, and communications strategies will need to be devised to reinforce this point clearly. Further, any rollout must take into account the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. Ideally, discussions of these issues will reinforce the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques will receive a needed boost in attention and funding.
3. **Risk** is typically defined in terms of medical risk; how can conceptions of risk be expanded to include social, psychological, cultural, or sexual factors? Acceptability on a population level, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.
4. **Interventions** using male circumcision (as with other technologies) absolutely require behavior modification and educational components. It will be essential to place male circumcision within a broad prevention context in order to avoid many of the difficulties that may be associated with it. Ideally, the introduction of male circumcision will be used as impetus to gain support for the

wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies. Male circumcision may help to focus attention on *combination prevention* and the need to use multiple prevention strategies in concert.

5. It will be essential to maintain funding for broader commitments in the fight against HIV, especially with regard to fighting gender inequity, stigma, and other issues related to disease spread. The implications of MC can be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.
6. Benefit to women: How can male circumcision benefit women? How can male circumcision not harm women?
7. Religious and cultural practices need to be taken into account. Actual risk reduction, versus that of reduction rates achieved in controlled trials, is likely to have more regional variance and is dependent on local behaviors surrounding sexual practices, local drivers of the epidemic, and current prevalence rates.
8. The questions of when to circumcise—in infancy or adulthood—are hotly debated and will continue for some time. It may be easiest in infancy, but infants will not benefit immediately and cannot make informed choices.
9. Male circumcision and female genital mutilation (FGM): Opportunity to further distinguish the two? This raises at least two questions: a) whether promoting MC will in any way undermine current efforts to eliminate FGM, and b) how to understand the social and cultural discourses about the penis, about sexuality, and about sexual maturation that may all be affected, and potentially have positive or negative impacts on, an ostensibly neutral public health intervention.
10. Assessment and surveillance of safety and complications is essential to ensure that circumcisions are performed safely, that training is adequate, and that oversight is in place.
11. The challenges to health systems are enormous. The fact that health systems in many countries with high or growing HIV incidence are very poor and can not cope with the systemic or human resource requirements of an MC program without major additional short- and long-term investments. The estimated costs per circumcision could be significant when considering a developing country's per person health budget. The global experience with prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV (PMTCT) has already demonstrated the inability of global health systems to deliver on the promise of technical advances.
12. Male circumcision also needs to be considered and evaluated in a broader context of sexual and reproductive health, beyond the constraints of HIV alone.
13. Some have asserted that the trials and the calls for widespread implementation are being fueled by a form of racism. These issues need to be addressed seriously and included in the discussion.
14. It will be essential to determine how to avoid stigma associated with male circumcision or the lack of it.
15. It will also be essential to carry on the discussion around male circumcision to deliberately avoid branding men as perpetrators of infection.

We highlight the following research priorities:

1. What is the effect of male circumcision on female partners—not just related to HIV, but also sexually transmitted infections (STIs), cervical cancer, female pleasure, and female perceptions of sexual viability of the male partner?
2. There are often few ethical guidelines on the social and behavioral effects of biomedical trials—only medical effects and adverse events are examined. Social and behavioral effects need to be defined, and studies need to be carried out on the positive and negative consequences related to study participation.
3. Is penile hygiene as good as MC? Clinical trials that include a penile hygiene study arm should be conducted. These studies should also conduct analyses of feasibility, required resources, and infrastructure requirements.
4. Although much cost analysis, particularly in the United States, has been conducted to project the cost savings from averted HIV infection, STIs, and urinary tract infections (UTIs), there is a lack of data projecting the costs of treating circumcision-related complications. How will complications be addressed in resource-poor settings?
5. The development of models that include cost analysis for training practitioners in resource-poor settings is urgently needed. Modeling should project the cost of equipment and its maintenance, and the treatment of complications. These projections should be comprehensive modeling strategies including PMTCT, condom provision, voluntary counseling and testing (VCT), and treatment.
6. Interventions that combine reproductive health services, HIV VCT, and male circumcision should be explored.
7. Should MC rollout begin, it is essential that surveillance systems be put into place to track who is presenting for services, incidence of adverse events, and disinhibition in circumcised populations.
8. Qualitative studies that shed light on people's understanding of protection afforded by male circumcision—both for males and females—will be essential. It will be important to repeat these over time as events change. The perspective of parents will also need to be included.
9. Prevention models that include male circumcision, but do not focus on it exclusively, are needed to elucidate how male circumcision can be incorporated into a broader prevention framework.
10. Legal research is needed to understand barriers and facilitators of male circumcision, and the protections necessary to maximize benefits and reduce harms.
11. Stigma remains a central impediment in HIV prevention. Understanding how male circumcision reduces or enhances stigma will be essential.

Acronyms

AAP	American Academy of Pediatrics
ABC	Abstinence, be faithful, use condoms
AIDS	Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
ANRS	Agence Nationale de Recherches sur le Sida (France)
ARV	Antiretroviral
BMA	British Medical Association
DFID	Department for International Development (UK)
DSMB	Data and safety monitoring board
FGM	Female genital mutilation
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
HPTN	HIV Prevention Trials Network
HPV	Human papillomavirus
HSPC	Human subjects protections committee
HSV-2	Herpes simplex virus type 2
IDU	Injecting drug user
IRB	Institutional review board
MC	Male circumcision
MSM	Men who have sex with men
NHDS	National Hospital Discharge Survey
NIH	National Institutes of Health (U.S.)
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (U.S.)
NGO	Nongovernmental organization
PLWH/A	Person/people living with HIV/AIDS
PMTCT	Prevention of mother-to-child transmission (of HIV)
PrEP	Pre-exposure prophylaxis
SRH	Sexual and reproductive health
STI	Sexually transmitted infection
TDF	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate
UCLA	University of California, Los Angeles
UNAIDS	Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS
USAID	U.S. Agency for International Development
UTI	Urinary tract infection
VCT	Voluntary counseling and testing
WHO	World Health Organization

Introduction

This report summarizes available information on male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy and the policy and prevention implications of its implementation. To this end, the report examines:

1. Summary of HIV prevention science and practice;
2. A review of the currently available data from observational studies and randomized controlled clinical trials;
3. Adult male circumcision, other health benefits, and the implications for women's health;
4. Biological mechanism responsible for reduced susceptibility to HIV infection and other medical benefits among circumcised males;
5. Medical professional group policy statements pertaining to male circumcision;
6. Challenges related to male circumcision;
7. Research priorities;
8. Ethical concerns; and
9. Potential next steps.

It is urgent that we immediately address the myriad cultural, economic, social, ethical, moral, and political challenges related to male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy. The first randomized controlled clinical trial to report impact of MC on HIV infection, the South African "Orange Farm" trial, released results at the July 2005 International AIDS Society meeting in Rio de Janeiro that demonstrated that MC could provide up to a **60% protective benefit** in 3,274 men aged 18-24 that were enrolled in the study. On December 13, 2006, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) announced the early termination of two additional randomized controlled trials of male circumcision—in Kenya and Uganda—based on interim evidence that MC has a significant protective benefit against HIV infection. The Kenya trial reported a **53% reduction** in HIV incidence among 2,784 enrolled men; the Uganda trial reported a **48% reduction** in HIV incidence among 4,996 enrolled men. The combined results from the three trials provide sufficient evidence that MC does provide protective benefit from HIV acquisition, but many additional questions remain unanswered.

Now that results are available from these three studies, it is urgent that planning for large-scale implementation begins. Plans for implementation of this magnitude need to account not only for the medical risks and benefits, but also social, cultural, economic, sexual, and other risks and benefits. We outline these issues and the associated challenges surrounding them to stimulate discussion about policy and planning.

Background

At the time this report was produced, approximately 39.5 million people globally are infected with HIV, of which, 24.7 million live in sub-Saharan Africa(1). Currently there are no available strategies that provide complete protection from HIV infection (other than complete abstinence, which is difficult to maintain and in the case of couples trying to conceive, unrealistic). Nor is a vaccine providing either full or partial immunity likely to be developed in the short term, and fundamental questions about whether a preventive vaccine is even feasible remain unanswered.

Significant emphasis has been placed on the development of novel prevention technologies and behavioral and social approaches that are intended to work in concert with one another. Currently, there are approximately a dozen such approaches being investigated. Current trials include:

- **Pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP)** is chemoprophylaxis using tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) or a combination of TDF and emtricitabine. Both agents are existing, well-tolerated antiretrovirals licensed in the U.S. and Europe to treat HIV infection.
- **Treatment or suppression of herpes simplex virus 2 (HSV-2).** With chronic or episodic use of acyclovir Infection with HSV-2 has been associated with higher HIV prevalence rates.
- **HIV viral load suppression** uses antiretroviral medications to treat HIV infection, and also has the potential to dramatically lower transmission rates.
- **Diaphragms** might prevent HIV from reaching the cervix and endocervix where most female infections occur, as well as providing women with the potential advantage of being able to protect themselves without the need to negotiate with a partner.
- **Vaginal, rectal, and topical microbicides** are substances that could be placed inside the vagina, inside the rectum, or topically on the penis to prevent infection.
- **New strategies for treating sexually transmitted infections,** a co-factor for HIV acquisition (eg, treatment of bacterial vaginosis); and for improving vaginal health.
- **New behavioral and pharmacologic strategies** for preventing and treating abuse of substances, including opiates, stimulants, and alcohol.
- **New strategies for making voluntary counseling and testing (VCT)** uptake more attractive and available. This has the potential to challenge stigma, reduce risk behavior, and heighten community level discussion about HIV.
- **More effective strategies for reducing mother-to-child transmission,** including reducing transmission of HIV through breast milk, and strategies for women whose HIV is not diagnosed until labor.
- **Treatment of depression,** as this has been related to HIV infection in several different studies.
- **Male circumcision,** the focus of this report, which has a rapidly growing body of literature, and findings from three randomized controlled clinical trials suggest has a substantial protective benefit against HIV-1 acquisition.

Why Do We Need Additional Prevention Strategies?

One might wonder why it is necessary to develop new prevention strategies and technologies when current devices such as the male and female condom are highly effective when used correctly and consistently. There are several reasons. The first is that the prevention literature demonstrates that it can be difficult to motivate certain groups of people to use male or female condoms every time that they are in a high-risk situation (eg, when consuming alcohol or using other psychoactive substances). The second is that it requires consistent effort to ensure that individuals continue to use condoms over time. Most studies show that it might be possible to get an immediate or even short-term (eg, 12 months) increase in condom use, but that this effect wanes over a longer period of time. The third is that there is substantial evidence demonstrating that condoms use drops significantly at the initiation of emotional, intimate, or long-term relationships, as use of condoms often signifies lack of trust. Nonetheless, there is also substantial literature demonstrating that women, especially in resource poor countries, are at risk for HIV and other sexually transmitted infections from their regular, not secondary or casual partners.

The search for other prevention strategies is not intended to replace condoms, but rather to add to the armory of available HIV prevention strategies. We know that having multiple prevention strategies allows more dynamic interventions that are able to respond to locally specific resources, culturally specific issues, as well as structural and geographical limitations. It may be possible that people will choose one strategy in preference to another, or choose one strategy at one time and a second at another time.

The Prevention Science View

The Prevention Science View diagram provides one perspective on HIV prevention and the science behind it. Delaying first intercourse and reducing number of partners can reduce HIV infection. Adults have a more mature reproductive health tract, more capable of resisting infection. Adults might also be more equipped socially and emotionally to take precautions. A greater number of sexual partners increase the likelihood that one will come into contact with someone who has HIV or another sexually transmitted infection. This is especially true because those with more sexual partners are likely to be interacting across sexual networks where more disease is present, thus increasing the likelihood of infection. Stoneburner et al document the impact of partner reduction as a result of the communication about HIV/AIDS through social networks in Uganda(2). Similar effects were noted in Zimbabwe, Kenya and Haiti(3-6).

Psychoactive drugs (eg, opiates, stimulants, alcohol, etc) increase sexual risk. Barrier methods such as male and female condoms protect against infection, but they must be used consistently and correctly. Proponents of the vaginal diaphragm await the results of the efficacy trial in South Africa and Zimbabwe.

Treating bacterial and probably viral sexually transmitted infections reduces both transmission and acquisition of HIV.

Reduced viral load is associated with reduced probability of transmission. This concept has been demonstrated both for sexual transmission and in mother-to-child transmission. Suppression of viral load with antiretroviral medications reduces mother-to-child transmission and may also reduce sexual transmission. The trial to test the hypothesis that reductions in viral load achieved through medications reduces transmission (HPTN 052) is underway (7).

Several Phase III studies are underway to test various vaginal microbicide preparations; rectal microbicides are gaining traction in concept but are still only in preclinical or early human trials. Effective preventive vaccines may not be available for as many as 15 to 20 years in the future. It is possible that a therapeutic vaccine—one that reduces viral load or boosts immune response and therefore reduces infectiousness—may also prevent transmission(8).

As the “Prevention Science View” schema depicted in the figure demonstrates, social, behavioral, and biomedical interventions require work at multiple levels of society, including the individual, the couple and family, the network, the community, and at the level of policy and legal interventions. This also means that any intervention needs to address social inequities related to gender, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, occupation, age, sexual orientation, legal status, immigration status, educational status, or any other variable that drives the epidemic.

Ideally, the use of combination prevention strategies would be encouraged, as none of the available prevention strategies work perfectly all of the time. Alternatively, it might be possible for individuals to choose different prevention strategies in different situations.

The Research Evidence on Male Circumcision

Male circumcision may offer a powerful advantage over other HIV prevention strategies in that it involves a one-time surgery that does not require ongoing behavioral modification in order to work. The protection afforded by MC is temporally separate from the risk behavior. Once it is done safely, it is completed and the person does not need to exert any further actions in order to achieve the protection that circumcision affords. This may have significant implications in resource-poor settings where routine access and distribution of technologies that require ongoing use (condoms, antiretrovirals (ARVs), diaphragms, etc) may present operational hurdles that diminish efficacy.

Nonetheless, MC presents challenges. The cost associated with population-level MC may exceed a country’s financial resources and health care infrastructure capacity. Significant financial commitments would have to come from multilateral and bilateral organizations. Furthermore, people may develop the perception that circumcision provides complete protection, when in fact protection is far less than ideal (based on the recent clinical trials, approximately a 50% protective benefit under ideal circumstances at the time of vaginal intercourse).

Observational Studies

Since the mid 1980s, multiple observational studies have correlated male circumcision with reduced risk for HIV-1 infection. Based on results from these studies, it has been hypothesized that variation in HIV prevalence rates in Africa are associated with differences in circumcision practices. High HIV prevalence rates are associated with low circumcision rates.

In response to the mounting enthusiasm generated from the observational evidence of the potential protective benefits against HIV infection that male circumcision may provide, the Cochrane Collaboration published a comprehensive review of the available studies suggesting that circumcision can be used as an intervention to prevent HIV infection(9). The original findings were reported in July 2003 and were then updated in March 2005(10). The Cochrane review differs from previous reviews in that it attempts to assess the likelihood that circumcision will reduce heterosexual transmission of HIV to men. Previous reviews focused on the correlations between circumcision and HIV prevalence. No studies included in the review reported on medical complications associated with circumcision. It is important to note that the Cochrane Collaboration points out that many of the observational studies were poorly designed.

The updated review included 37 observational studies, 18 conducted among the general population and 19 among high-risk populations. Of the 18 general population studies included, 12 reported circumcision as having a beneficial effect (9 were statistically significant). All of the 19 high-risk population studies demonstrated beneficial effect.

Observational studies, unlike randomized controlled trials, might not have comparable groups of circumcised and non-circumcised participants because people were not assigned at random. Meta-analysis was not conducted because of heterogeneity in the multiple confounding factors present, including viral load, sexual behaviors, penile hygiene, religion, etc. Sigfried et al highlight that circumcision status itself may be a confounder, functioning as a proxy measure of knowledge about sexual practice, monogamy, and penile hygiene(10).

For example, a comparison of sub-Saharan Africans by religious affiliation indicates that circumcised Muslim men have lower HIV incidence than circumcised non-Muslims. Although Muslims almost universally circumcise males, there could be many specific behaviors (eg, washing before and after sex, prohibition against substance use, etc) that might account for the lower HIV acquisition risk in Muslims. It is not possible to exclude the possibility that the apparent protective effects of circumcision may reflect subtle differences in risk behaviors between Muslim and non-Muslim men or their partners. Another example occurs in the Rakai District of Uganda where married Muslim men are predominantly polygamous, and polygamous unions may provide a closed sexual network reducing the risk of HIV infection(11). Lower alcohol consumption among Muslims may also be a factor, as alcohol reduces inhibition and potentially increases high-risk behavior.

Randomized Controlled Trials

Randomized controlled trials are the only way to determine with relative confidence a causal relationship between male circumcision and HIV acquisition. Such studies need to conform to standard ethical practices, especially informed consent, counseling for risk reduction, and the promotion and provision of condoms. Using these standards, three major, African, randomized clinical trials were initiated in South Africa, Uganda, and Kenya. The French and United States governments (through ANRS and NIH, respectively) funded these studies with additional support from The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Public health officials in the United States, Europe, and Canada have been reluctant to make recommendations based on observational data alone, because one cannot rule out alternative explanations as to why the circumcised men might be less likely to become infected than the uncircumcised men. Although there is abundant, positive observational data supporting circumcision as a preventative HIV infection strategy, observational studies alone are insufficient to recommend circumcision as an intervention because extensive confounding variables exist that can mask the true reason as to why an association is found (9, 10).

The first trial to report outcomes, the South African “Orange Farm” study, showed a substantial protective benefit in the circumcised cohort: a 65% reduction in probability of HIV-1 infection(12). The trial was stopped early after interim review by the data and safety monitoring board (DSMB) determined that continuing the trial in light of such overwhelmingly positive results would be unethical. Due to the early termination of the Orange Farm study, it was not possible to continuously monitor participants and therefore will not be able to provide critical information pertaining to how circumcision may or may not change the men’s sexual practices, possible sexual disinhibition leading to riskier behavior, and the effect MC will have on condom use.

In addition to attempting to replicate the Orange Farm study to determine if male circumcision prevents infection, the Ugandan trial (which was designed to involve approximately 6,800 male and female participants) also investigated whether male circumcision will reduce transmission rates from people with HIV to those without HIV. A third randomized controlled trial, the Kenyan study, involved 2,784 previously uncircumcised HIV-negative men, half of whom were circumcised during the trial.

On December 13, 2006, the DSMB of the U.S. NIH announced the early termination of both the Ugandan and Kenyan trials based on evidence that male circumcision in these trials did provide substantial protective benefit against HIV infection. The Kenya trial reported a **53% reduction** in HIV incidence among 2,784 enrolled men, and the Uganda trial reported a **48% reduction** in HIV incidence among 4,996 enrolled men. The HIV prevention community is eagerly awaiting the detailed discussion of the interim results from the Kenyan and Ugandan trials.

South Africa (“Orange Farm”): “Randomized, Controlled Intervention Trial of Male Circumcision for Reduction of HIV Infection Risk: The ANRS 1265 Trial”

Auvert B, Taljaard D, Lagarde E, Sobngwi-Tambekou J, Sitta R, Puren A.

In November 2005, Bertran Auvert et al, reported results from the South African “Orange Farm” trial after the DSMB stopped the trial based on an interim analysis of data collected after all subjects had completed the 12-month clinic visit(12). The results that lead to the early ending of the Orange Farm trial suggested that the risk of HIV infection was reduced by 60% in circumcised men. Important findings that may have implications on future studies and interventions include:

1. The participants were all drawn from the general population with a low lost-to-follow-up rate, suggesting that large circumcision trials can be effectively conducted in resource-limited settings;
2. The study noted that subjects in the male circumcision group had significantly more sexual contacts--an important factor for policy makers to consider as there is growing concern that MC may lead to sexual disinhibition and riskier behavior;
3. Auvert et al concluded that male circumcision provides a degree of protection comparable to what a vaccine with high efficacy would achieve.

With regard to a protective benefit for women, the authors assert; “...MC will indirectly protect women and, therefore, children from HIV infection because if the men are less susceptible to HIV acquisition, women will be less exposed.” This statement needs more rigorous scrutiny, insofar as it assumes that the benefits of MC to female sexual partners will not be counteracted by increased risk behaviors. Among societies where agency over one’s body and imbalances in sexual decision making are heavily weighted towards men, decreasing the susceptibility of men to HIV acquisition without cautious consideration of existing social norms may have a significantly less beneficial impact on HIV acquisition among women.

Uganda: “Trial of Male Circumcision: HIV, STD and Behavioral Effects in Men, Women and the Community”

Serwadda D, Wawer M, Gray R.

The study is being carried out by the Rakai Health Sciences Program, a research collaboration between the Uganda Virus Research Institute/Uganda Ministry of Health, Columbia University Mailman School of Public Health, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, and researchers from Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda.

The study was conducted in Rakai District, Uganda, and was designed to enroll ~800 HIV-positive men. Following a detailed informed consent process, the men were randomized to receive either immediate (within several days or weeks) or delayed (two years) circumcision. The goals were to assess the safety and acceptability of male circumcision among HIV-positive men, and to assess potential effects of male circumcision on the acquisition of STIs such as HSV-2. The investigators hypothesize that male circumcision will be acceptable to and safe in HIV-positive men, will reduce the rate of acquisition of STIs, and will reduce the frequency of STI symptoms, such as genital ulceration.

The study design also included the enrollment of ~1,000 men who, regardless of their HIV status, decline to receive their HIV results, despite encouragement to do so. Hypotheses are that circumcision will be acceptable and safe in men who decline their HIV results, and will reduce the rate of acquisition of HIV and STIs, and the frequency of STI symptoms such as genital ulcers.

The study also planned to enroll up to ~5,000 female partners of the men in groups above, as well as 5,000 HIV-negative men enrolled in a complementary NIH-funded study of male circumcision for HIV prevention (which is being separately registered). Female partners were to be followed annually to assess the acceptability and safety of male circumcision, and potential effects of male circumcision on HIV and STI acquisition. The hypothesis is that male circumcision will be acceptable to and safe in female partners, and will reduce the acquisition of HIV and STIs such as HSV-2 and human papillomavirus (HPV), which causes cervical cancer.

Finally, the study was also designed to follow ~3,000 men and women in the ~50 communities where the circumcision trials are taking place, in order to assess community attitudes towards and knowledge of male circumcision, and to assess whether other preventive behaviors (abstinence, monogamy, numbers of partners, condom use, etc) change in the community once circumcision becomes available. The investigators hypothesize that male circumcision will be acceptable in the community and will not result in behavioral disinhibition (increased rates of high-risk behaviors).

The Gates-funded study is complementary to a separate NIH-funded trial of male circumcision in HIV-negative men who accept their HIV results and is being carried out by the Rakai Health Sciences Program study team. It is expected to report data in 2008. The latter study, which is enrolling 5,000 HIV-negative men, is designed to answer question about whether male circumcision is acceptable and safe in HIV-negative men, and whether the procedure reduces the acquisition of HIV and STIs.

The complementary Gates-funded trial is designed to answer the following question:

- Is male circumcision acceptable to and safe in HIV-infected men, and will it reduce the rates of acquisition of STDs in these men?

This question is of great importance for future circumcision programs:

- Is male circumcision acceptable and safe in men who decline their HIV results, and will it reduce rates of acquisition of HIV and STIS in these men?

Determining potential circumcision risks in these men (such as potentially delayed healing because of their higher risk behaviors) or benefits (such as potentially reduced rates of HIV and STI acquisition) is thus very important for the design of any future large-scale circumcision programs. From the public health viewpoint, it will be important to know whether such programs should include or exclude men who decline HIV results. The Rakai Program strongly recommends and encourages the receipt of HIV test results, and provides the results confidentially and free of charge. The great majority of Rakai Program research participants (85-90%) accept their HIV results, but a minority continues to decline, although the latter group is getting smaller every year. If participants decline their HIV results, the Rakai Program still provides them with detailed HIV prevention education and counseling. Enrollment of men who decline their HIV results is also congruent with Ugandan Ministry of Health Policy, which encourages but does not force individuals and study participants to receive their HIV results.

Enrollment of female partners is designed to answer important questions regarding potential effects of male circumcision on women. Should male circumcision reduce HIV and STI acquisition in women, this

would represent an additional important public health benefit and would increase the cost effectiveness of male circumcision programs. However, if the procedure is associated with increased HIV transmission (for example, due to increased transmission before a circumcision surgical wound is fully healed), it is crucial that such a potential risk be identified rapidly within a trial, in order to prevent the risk within trials and in any potential future circumcision programs.

Following enrollment, men in the circumcision arm are followed post-operatively, at 4-6 weeks, and at 6, 12, and 24 months. Men in the control arm are also followed at 4-6 weeks and at 6, 12 and 24 months. At baseline and follow up, men respond to a detailed sociodemographic, behavioral, and health questionnaire, and provide biological samples (venous blood, urine, sub-preputial swabs [prior to circumcision] and for circumcised men, foreskins are collected at time of surgery.) Samples will allow assessment of multiple infections, including HIV, HSV-2, gonorrhoea, *Chlamydia*, and syphilis.

Female partners are followed annually, through the Rakai Community Cohort Study. Following written informed consent, women are administered a detailed sociodemographic, behavioral and health status questionnaire, and provide venous blood and self-administered vaginal swabs at baseline and study follow-up visits. The samples will allow assessment of multiple infections and conditions, including HIV, syphilis, gonorrhoea, *Chlamydia*, *Trichomonas*, bacterial vaginosis, HSV-2, and HPV. Female partners of HIV-positive men receive an additional visit at 6 months post enrollment, in order to ensure expeditious assessment of potential risks.

Kenya: “Trial of Male Circumcision to Reduce HIV Incidence”

Bailey R, Moses S, Maclean I, Parker C, Ndinya-Achola JO, Agot K, Krieger J.

Uncircumcised men aged 18 to 24 were offered voluntary HIV counseling and testing. HIV-negative men were asked to enroll in the study. All study participants were interviewed to obtain sociodemographic information and assess behavioral risk factors. Participants were examined for significant medical conditions. All men were counseled in strategies to reduce their risk for HIV infection. Consenting men was randomly assigned to either the treatment (circumcised) arm or the control (uncircumcised) arm of the study. After circumcision, men were monitored for complications. They were counseled to abstain from sex until healing is complete. Follow-up visits occurred every 6 months for 2 years. Uncircumcised men were offered circumcision at the end of the follow-up period. The primary study endpoints will be HIV incidence and surgical complications. Additional outcomes will be the incidence of other sexually transmitted diseases and behavioral risks. Additional laboratory studies of foreskin tissue will evaluate the number and density of specialized cells rich in HIV receptors in order to illuminate the biological mechanisms by which presence of foreskin may increase HIV susceptibility.

Male Circumcision, HIV Viral Load, and Male-to-Female Transmission

In addition to reducing the risk of exposure to HPV, recent studies in Uganda suggest that in HIV-infected men, circumcision combined with lower viral loads reduces the risk of male-to-female transmission. The Rakai, Uganda study group recently reported that when HIV viral loads are not controlled, the overall effects of circumcision on HIV transmission from HIV-infected men to their HIV-negative partners was modest(8). However, when circumcised HIV-positive men had viral loads less than 50,000 copies/mL, no transmission occurred whereas in uncircumcised HIV-positive men with viral loads of less than 50,000 copies/mL, the transmission rate was 9.6 per 100 person years. For the Rakai group, circumcision afforded no protection from HIV transmission at viral loads greater than 50,000 copies/mL, suggesting that male circumcision may protect women from HIV transmission at lower, but not at higher, viral loads. This finding could have significant implications in Africa, as the majority of transmissions fueling the epidemic are male-to-female. Furthermore, it suggests that controlling the viral loads of HIV-positive individuals could have significant impact on lowering new infections and that this effect is amplified by

male circumcision. It is important to note that the Rakai group looked at individuals with naturally suppressed viral load; they did not look at individuals with suppressed viral loads due to antiretroviral therapy. Studies monitoring male circumcision combined with antiretroviral-suppressed viral loads in HIV-positive individuals should be conducted.

Other Health Benefits

Since the initial paper suggesting protective effective of MC against HIV infection was published in 1986 and Wiswell et al first reported reduced UTIs in circumcised males over two decades ago, there have been extensive and impassioned debates as to the impact that male circumcision used as a public health measure would have on the reduction of STIs in the adult population(13-15). Many of these arguments have highlighted that insufficient and even contradictory evidence existed. Others have cited that although many prospective cohort studies exist, a lack of longitudinal studies limited the conclusions that could be drawn(16).

Indeed, the American Academy of Pediatrics' (AAP) 1999 decision not to recommend routine neonatal circumcisions partially rested upon this assumption(17). Since the Academy's decision, there has been mounting consistent evidence suggesting reduction of STIs in circumcised males. Fergusson et al recently reported results from a 25-year longitudinal study of a cohort of more than 500 New Zealand males that confirm the considerable reduction of STIs in circumcised males(18). Uncircumcised males were 3.19 times more likely to have STIs than circumcised males. The added power of longitudinal data makes it possible to examine circumcision status and infection risk over an extended period of time rather than at a point in time. The investigators report that if the entire cohort had been circumcised, STIs would have been reduced by approximately 50%.

In addition to the potential protective benefits from HIV-1 infection and UTIs, evidence exists that suggests male circumcision is associated with a number of other health benefits, including the reduced risk of genital ulcer disease and HSV-2. Minimizing HSV-2 infection and genital ulcer disease has the dual benefit of reducing HIV-1 transmission rates, as both significantly increase the probability HIV-1 transmission. Additionally, cervical cancer occurs at a higher rate in the female partners of uncircumcised males. The mechanism thought to be responsible for the increased cervical cancer is a higher transmission rate of HPV, which is associated to a greater extent with uncircumcised males.

Biological Plausibility

The mechanism thought to be responsible for reduced risk of incident HIV-1 infection in circumcised males is the presence of a significantly higher concentration of Langerhans cells, which are target cells for HIV-1 in the mucosal layer of the foreskin(19). Additionally, keratin is believed to provide a protective barrier against HIV-1 infection(20). The penile shaft and outer foreskin surface are well keratinized, while the inner mucosal layer of the foreskin is not(21). It is also argued that the sensitive foreskin may be more susceptible to micro-abrasion during sexual intercourse, which could provides an entry for STIs and HIV(22). Initial HIV target cell concentration studies were conducted among samples from Australian, English, and North American men. Recent results from Donoval et al confirmed that samples from African males (Kisumu, Kenya) were consistent with the previous finding(23). Donoval et al report higher concentrations of Langerhans cells in the foreskin mucosal layer and little or no protective keratin layer on the inner foreskin of the Kenyan study participants.

Potential Benefits to Populations

Herd immunity is defined as the resistance of a group to attack by a disease due to the immunity achieved in a large proportion of the members. The consequences of this process lessen the likelihood that an affected individual will come into contact with a susceptible individual.

The concept of herd immunity depends on achieving a critical breaking point in the spread of disease. For each disease, there exists a percentage of the population (the critical immune threshold) that when achieved will effectively stop or slow further transmission. As with smallpox and tuberculosis, the typical threshold for stopping disease spread is high. In the context of HIV infection, it is unlikely that full herd immunity will be achieved in the short term as no single strategy or combination of strategies are currently available to achieve a high enough protection at the population level. Nevertheless, technologies like male circumcision can significantly retard incidence rates and reduce overall prevalence insofar as the protective benefit for any single circumcised individual translates to decreased risk among sexual partners. It is important to note that epidemiologists and virologists point out that when there is insufficient coverage to thwart disease spread, while overall disease spread may be slowed, unforeseen problems can occur (eg, while overall population incidence may decline, incidence in a particular subgroup may rise).

Williams et al used modeling to project that large-scale implementation of male circumcision has the potential to avert approximately 2 million new HIV infections and 0.3 million deaths over the next ten years(24). Over the subsequent 10 years an additional 3.7 million HIV infections and 2.7 million deaths could be averted, totaling almost 6 million averted infections over 20 years. The greatest impact would be in southern Africa where circumcision rates are low and HIV prevalence is high. Additionally, Williams et al report that combining male circumcision with prevention strategies known to reduce transmission rates, such as the use of antiretrovirals, would further reduce new infections.

Table from Williams, 2006(24)

Region	Time Period	Incident Cases Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Incident Cases (Percent)	Prevalent Cases Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Prevalent Cases (Percent)	Deaths Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Mortality (Percent)
Sub-Saharan	2005–2015	2.0 (1.7–3.8)	8 (4–17)	2.2 (1.2–4.3)	8 (4–17)	0.3 (0.1–0.5)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	3.7 (1.9–9.0)	14 (6–32)	4.1 (2.0–8.7)	13 (6–31)	2.7 (1.5–5.3)	9 (5–19)
	2025–2035	4.4 (2.2–9.0)	13 (6–32)	4.7 (2.4–9.7)	13 (6–30)	4.9 (2.5–9.9)	14 (7–34)
Central	2005–2015	0.7 (0.1–0.3)	8 (4–17)	0.7 (0.1–0.4)	8 (4–17)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	1 (0–2)
	2015–2025	0.4 (0.2–0.8)	15 (7–36)	0.4 (0.2–0.9)	15 (7–37)	0.2 (0.1–0.3)	9 (4–20)
	2025–2035	0.5 (0.3–1.1)	16 (7–39)	0.5 (0.2–1.2)	15 (7–39)	0.5 (0.2–1.1)	16 (7–39)
East	2005–2015	0.5 (0.3–1.0)	9 (4–18)	0.6 (0.3–1.2)	9 (4–18)	0.1 (0.0–0.1)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	14 (7–33)	1.1 (0.5–2.3)	14 (7–34)	0.8 (0.4–1.3)	10 (5–20)
	2025–2035	1.3 (0.6–2.6)	14 (7–35)	1.4 (0.7–2.9)	14 (6–34)	1.4 (0.7–2.8)	15 (7–36)
Southern	2005–2015	1.0 (0.6–1.9)	11 (6–22)	1.2 (0.7–2.1)	11 (6–23)	0.1 (0.1–0.3)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	1.9 (1.0–3.6)	18 (9–43)	1.9 (1.0–3.8)	18 (9–42)	1.4 (0.8–2.6)	12 (7–26)
	2025–2035	2.0 (1.1–4.0)	18 (9–43)	2.0 (1.1–4.1)	16 (8–39)	2.4 (1.3–4.6)	20 (10–48)
West	2005–2015	0.2 (0.1–0.5)	4 (2–9)	0.3 (0.1–0.6)	4 (2–9)	0.0 (0.0–0.1)	0 (0–1)
	2015–2025	0.5 (0.2–1.1)	6 (3–15)	0.5 (0.2–1.2)	6 (3–16)	0.3 (0.2–0.7)	4 (2–10)
	2025–2035	0.6 (0.3–1.3)	6 (3–15)	0.6 (0.3–1.5)	6 (3–15)	0.6 (0.3–1.4)	7 (3–16)
South Africa	2005–2015	0.5 (0.3–1.0)	11 (6–22)	0.6 (0.3–1.0)	11 (6–23)	0.1 (0.0–0.1)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	0.9 (0.5–1.8)	20 (1–48)	1.0 (0.5–1.9)	19 (9–46)	0.7 (0.4–1.3)	13 (7–27)
	2025–2035	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	19 (9–48)	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	17 (8–43)	1.2 (0.6–2.3)	22 (11–53)

Data are as defined for the countries and regions given in Table 1. Data are given separately for each region and for South Africa over the next ten, twenty, and thirty years. Full coverage of MC is reached in 2015. The table gives the reduction in incidence and deaths, over each ten year period, and in prevalent cases at the end of each ten year period. Reductions are relative to the baseline, which assumes no change in MC prevalence. The calculations are done using the expected reduction in female to male transmission from the RCT and using the lower and upper 95% confidence limits of the reduction observed in the RCT [8]. DOI: 10.1171/journal.pmed.0030020

Although these projections are promising, there are several important caveats. First, the modeling analysis was based on the results from a single clinical trial (Orange Farm) and thus additional modeling based on

data from ongoing trials, once it is available, should be conducted. Second, the impact of a circumcision intervention depends on the current prevalence of male circumcision and HIV. Comparing the Williams modeling to the current epidemic in South Africa, a recent article in the *Mail & Guardian Online* reported that fifteen-year-olds in South Africa now have a 56% chance of dying before turning 60, versus ten years ago when they had a 29% chance of not making their 60th birthday(25). The article continues, “A third of women between the ages of 25 and 29 years are infected, while 19% of the country’s working-age (age 20 to 64) population is HIV positive.”

Men Who Have Sex with Men and Penile-Anal Transmission

There is currently limited data available on the rate of HIV transmission for the receptive partner of a circumcised man in penile-anal intercourse. In a study evaluating sexual risk factors conducted among 3,257 MSM in six U.S. cities, Buchbinder et al reported that uncircumcised men were almost twice as likely to seroconvert than circumcised men (26). The effect of male circumcision on reducing the risk of HIV transmission among men who have sex with men has not been studied in a randomized controlled trial. It is also unclear what proportion of men involved in the South African, Ugandan, and Kenyan circumcision trials engaged in MSM or penile-anal intercourse. The protective benefits afforded by MC accrue primarily to the circumcised man. The rectal and vaginal epithelium do not contain traditional receptors for HIV-1 and provide a protective barrier to the underlying target cells. Because the rectal epithelium is a single layer, and mucosal trauma is often associated with anal sex, receptive anal intercourse is significantly higher risk than receptive vaginal intercourse(27, 28). The MSM population will likely not achieve the same prevalence reduction as the heterosexual population. Within the heterosexual population, it is also unclear what percent of men engage in penile-vaginal and penile-anal intercourse. The combination of penile-vaginal and penile-anal intercourse will also likely be a confounding factor in measuring prevalence reduction.

Male Circumcision, Sexual Functioning, and Post-Procedural Satisfaction

There is no current consensus on the role of foreskin on penile sensitivity(29). Limited comprehensive data on sensation loss after male circumcision currently exists. Many early studies conducted to evaluate the effect of MC on sexual function enrolled subjects with preexisting morbidities, which may be confounding factors of the results(30). Fink et al conducted a retrospective chart review of 123 men circumcised after the age of 18, of which 43 responded to a mailed survey. Although the study concluded overall satisfaction¹ rates, it also reported slightly reduced erectile function and decreased penile sensitivity (which bordered on statistical significance, $p = .08$). Senkul et al, responding to the power limitations and pre-existing morbidities of the Fink study, looked at 42 males who were circumcised between ages 19-28, none of whom had pre-existing pathologies(31). Of the participants, 39 were circumcised for religious reasons and 3 were circumcised for cosmetic reasons. Subjects were evaluated before and after using the Brief Male Sexual Function Inventory(32). The study concluded an increase in ejaculatory latency time (which the authors note could be interpreted as a benefit) and that the subjects’ sexual function was not adversely affected.

The fields of reproductive health and sexually transmitted diseases have a long history of balancing prevention technologies as public health measures with diminished sexual sensation. Consistent and correct use of condoms has proven protective benefits against unwanted pregnancies and STIs; yet even in areas where access to condoms is not a barrier and >90% coverage is feasible, condom use is not consistent. One of the major cited barriers has been the diminished sexual sensation for both men and women. Nevertheless, the global campaign for 100% condom coverage is viewed as one of the most

¹ Satisfaction was defined as a more pleasing appearance of the penis to the men and their partners, and less pain experienced with erection.

effective strategies to thwart unplanned pregnancies and STIs. Several of the emerging prevention technologies (eg, topical microbicides, diaphragms) will likely encounter similar concerns regarding diminished sensation. While condoms, microbicides, and diaphragms are not permanent physiological alterations as is MC, there are several advantages to MC: 1) the protective benefits are separate from risk behavior; 2) unlike condoms and diaphragms, the protective benefits of MC do not require behavioral adherence; 3) MC has proven reduction of UTIs, STIs, and HPV transmission; 3) MC will easily work in concert with other prevention strategies.

Official Medical Professional Statements Regarding Male Circumcision

Medical professional groups have addressed male circumcision, especially of infants, and these official positions have changed over time. It is interesting to note that the U.S., European, and Australia/New Zealand groups have interpreted recent evidence in quite different ways. Further, it is important to note the change that has taken place in Botswana.

American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) Circumcision Policy Statement

It is useful to consider U.S. circumcision policy and understand its origins, because many governmental agencies and nongovernmental organizations in the U.S. significantly influence global HIV prevention policy. This is particularly true in regards to ethical considerations of U.S.-funded international research, and interventions targeted primarily at high-prevalence areas in Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia that may result in international policy that is not consistent with that of the United States.

On March 1, 1999, the AAP issued recommendations stating that although evidence demonstrating medical benefits exists, the benefits associated with neonatal circumcision are not sufficient to warrant the recommendation of circumcision as a routine procedure(17). The policy statement, which was reaffirmed in 2005, indicates that in circumstances where a procedure has potential risks and benefits, yet is not essential to well-being of the neonate, the decision as to what is in the best interest of the child should be left to the parents. The statement continues, “To make an informed choice, parents of all male infants should be given accurate and unbiased information and be provided the opportunity to discuss this decision.”

The AAP’s focus on the immediate well being of the neonate, rather than the individual’s well being through their adult life and any public health benefits, is inconsistent with the Academy’s other recommendations. Specifically, the Academy recommends newborn immunization against hepatitis B. Unless in circumstances where a mother is hepatitis B positive, hepatitis B presents primary risk to the adult, sexually active population, not the neonate. This recommendation is clearly based on consideration of the well-being of the adolescent or adult population. It is important to note that the hepatitis B vaccine is relatively safe. This type of inconsistency may suggest that factors other than object assessment of neonatal well being are influencing policy.

Beginning in the Academy’s 1971 manual, *Standards and Recommendations of Hospital Care of Newborn Infants*, and reiterated in the 1975 and 1985 revisions, the AAP concluded that there was no absolute medical indication for routine circumcision. In 1989, in response to research exploring the links between circumcision status and both UTIs and STIs, particularly HIV, the Academy concluded that newborn male circumcision did have potential medical benefits and advantages, as well as risks. In 1997, the AAP redefined nontherapeutic circumcision of the newborn as an elective procedure. Although the current recommendations (1999; reaffirmed in 2005) acknowledge the potential medical benefits and risks, the statement asserts circumcision is an elective procedure that is not necessary for the immediate health of the neonate and as such, defers to the parents’ judgment. The National Hospital Discharge

Survey (NHDS) provides the most comprehensive data set of incidence rates of circumcision over time. The data offers limited sensitivity insofar as only 5% of U.S. hospitals participate. The NHDS divides the country into four census regions and also produces a combined average circumcision rate of all regions. For circumcision, from 1994-2001, rates fluctuate by region, but the combined national average was approximately 60% of male neonates being circumcised. Since 2002, there has been a decline in all four regions.

The British Medical Association (BMA) Position

As of June 2006, the BMA's position was:

Circumcision for medical purposes: Unnecessarily invasive procedures should not be used where alternative, less invasive techniques, are equally efficient and available. It is important that doctors keep up to date and ensure that any decisions to undertake an invasive procedure are based on the best available evidence. Therefore, to circumcise for therapeutic reasons where medical research has shown other techniques to be at least as effective and less invasive would be unethical and inappropriate. Male circumcision in cases where there is a clear clinical need is not normally controversial. Nevertheless, normal anatomical and physiological characteristics of the infant foreskin have in the past been misinterpreted as being abnormal. The British Association of Paediatric Surgeons advises that there is rarely a clinical indication for circumcision. Doctors should be aware of this and reassure parents accordingly.”

Non-therapeutic circumcision: Male circumcision that is performed for any reason other than physical clinical need is termed non-therapeutic (or sometimes “ritual”) circumcision. Some people ask for non-therapeutic circumcision for religious reasons, some to incorporate a child into a community, and some want their sons to be like their fathers. Circumcision is a defining feature of some faiths.

There is a spectrum of views within the BMA's membership about whether non-therapeutic male circumcision is a beneficial, neutral or harmful procedure or whether it is superfluous, and whether it should ever be done on a child who is not capable of deciding for himself. The medical harms or benefits have not been unequivocally proven except to the extent that there are clear risks of harm if the procedure is done inexpertly. The Association has no policy on these issues. Indeed, it would be difficult to formulate a policy in the absence of unambiguously clear and consistent medical data on the implications of the intervention. As a general rule, however, the BMA believes that parents should be entitled to make choices about how best to promote their children's interests, and it is for society to decide what limits should be imposed on parental choices.

Australia and New Zealand

Routine Circumcision of Male Infants and Boys - Summary Statement:

The Pediatrics and Child Health Division. The Royal Australian College of Physicians (RACP) has prepared this statement on routine circumcision of infants and boys to assist parents who are considering having this procedure undertaken on their male children and for doctors who are asked to advise on or undertake it. After extensive review of the literature the RACP reaffirms that there is no medical indication for routine neonatal circumcision.

Circumcision of males has been undertaken for religious and cultural reasons for many thousands of years. It remains an important ritual in some religious and cultural groups. In Australia and

New Zealand, the circumcision rate has fallen considerably in recent years and it is estimated that currently only 10%-20% of male infants are routinely circumcised. Circumcision is now generally performed with local or general anesthesia, and when the procedure is carried out for a medical indication this is usually outside the neonatal period. The best recognized medical indication for circumcision is phimosis.

In recent years there has been evidence of possible health benefits from routine male circumcision. The most important conditions where some benefit may result from circumcision are urinary tract infections, HIV and later cancer of the penis.

Urinary tract infections affect 1%-2% of boys, and may be about 5 times less frequent in circumcised boys, whilst circumcision has a complication rate of 1% to 5%. On current evidence routine neonatal circumcision cannot be supported as a public health measure on this basis.

Whilst there is some evidence, particularly from sub-Saharan Africa, that male circumcision reduces the risk of acquisition of HIV, evidence is conflicting and would not justify an argument in favour of universal neonatal circumcision in countries with a low prevalence of HIV.

Penile cancer is a rare disease with an incidence of around 1 per 100,000 in developed countries. Even though the evidence suggests neonatal circumcision may reduce the risk 10-fold, the rarity of the condition and its other recognized predispositions are such that universal circumcision is not justified on these grounds alone. The complication rate of neonatal circumcision is reported to be around 1% to 5% and includes local infection, bleeding and damage to the penis. Serious complications such as bleeding, septicaemia and meningitis may occasionally cause death. The possibility that routine circumcision may contravene human rights has been raised because circumcision is performed on a minor and is without proven medical benefit. Whether these legal concerns are valid will be known only if the matter is determined in a court of law.

If the operation is to be performed, the medical attendant should ensure this is done by a competent operator, using appropriate anesthesia and in a safe child-friendly environment.

In all cases where parents request a circumcision for their child the medical attendant is obliged to provide accurate information on the risks and benefits of the procedure. Up-to-date, unbiased written material summarizing the evidence should be widely available to parents.

Review of the literature in relation to risks and benefits shows there is no evidence of benefit outweighing harm for circumcision as a routine procedure in the neonate.

South Africa and Botswana

In July 2006, President Thabo Mbeki of South Africa signed into law the Children's Act which contains a clause that no male under the age of 16 may be circumcised except when, "performed for religious purposes in accordance with the practices of the religion concerned", or "for medical reasons on the recommendation of a medical practitioner".

The Government of Botswana also recently mandated that all mothers of newborn boys should be counseled on the potential health benefits of circumcision. The Eastern Cape Province of South Africa recently legislated against traditional circumcision. The law raises concerns regarding parents' ability to choose to circumcise their male infants for future health benefits. The law was passed in attempt to curtail the rising number of circumcisions performed as part of traditional initiation school ceremonies resulting in serious medical complications or death. The provincial department of health says that 243 deaths and

216 genital amputations from circumcisions were recorded between 1995 and 2004. Last year there were more than 20 deaths. Furthermore, traditional surgeons must now be officially registered with the department of health. Many health care practitioners and human rights advocates point out that “medical grounds” allowing circumcision should be clarified.

Challenges

While the results of the clinical trials are extremely promising and can have enormous impact on the HIV epidemic, there are numerous implementation challenges, contextual considerations, and ethical concerns that require rigorous attention. We identify here 15 such challenges, and the list could probably be expanded. Nonetheless, we present these to encourage discussion, and to ensure that these issues are considered as new medical findings get released and implementation plans are drawn up. Furthermore, we hope that these challenges will enrich and add nuance to the discussions as to how MC should be offered as an HIV prevention intervention, and what steps need to be taken to ensure it is implemented in an ethical and effective manner.

We highlight the following:

1. **Acceptability:** Price, pain, and lack of complications seem to be universal concerns and need to be attended to in rollout of male circumcision. Rollout programs will consider these and other issues as plans for scale-up and implementation are considered.
2. **Level of protection:** The benefit from male circumcision is relative, not absolute, and communications strategies will need to be devised to reinforce this point clearly. Further, any rollout must take into account the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. Ideally, discussions of these issues will reinforce the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques will receive a needed boost in attention and funding.
3. **Risk** is typically defined in terms of medical risk; how can conceptions of risk be expanded to include social, psychological, cultural, or sexual factors? Acceptability on a population level, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.
4. Interventions using male circumcision (as with other technologies) absolutely require behavior modification and educational components. It will be essential to place male circumcision within a broad prevention context in order to avoid many of the difficulties that may be associated with it. Ideally, the introduction of male circumcision will be used as impetus to gain support for the wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies. Male circumcision may help to focus attention on *combination prevention* and the need to use multiple prevention strategies in concert.
5. It will be essential to maintain funding for broader commitments in the fight against HIV, especially with regard to fighting gender inequity, stigma, and other issues related to disease spread. The implications of MC can be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.
6. **Benefit to women:** How can male circumcision benefit women? How can male circumcision not harm women?

7. Religious and cultural practices need to be taken into account. Actual risk reduction, versus that of reduction rates achieved in controlled trials, is likely to have more regional variance and is dependent on local behaviors surrounding sexual practices, local drivers of the epidemic, and current prevalence rates.
8. The questions of when to circumcise—in infancy or adulthood—are hotly debated and will continue for some time. It may be easiest in infancy, but infants will not benefit immediately and cannot make informed choices.
9. Male circumcision and female genital mutilation (FGM): Opportunity to further distinguish the two? This raises at least two questions: a) whether promoting MC will in any way undermine current efforts to eliminate FGM, and b) how to understand the social and cultural discourses about the penis, about sexuality, and about sexual maturation that may all be affected, and potentially have positive or negative impacts on, an ostensibly neutral public health intervention.
10. Assessment and surveillance of safety and complications is essential to ensure that circumcisions are performed safely, that training is adequate, and that oversight is in place.
11. The challenges to health systems are enormous. The fact that health systems in many countries with high or growing HIV incidence are very poor and can not cope with the systemic or human resource requirements of an MC program without major additional short- and long-term investments. The estimated costs per circumcision could be significant when considering a developing country's per person health budget. The global experience with prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV (PMTCT) has already demonstrated the inability of global health systems to deliver on the promise of technical advances.
12. Male circumcision also needs to be considered and evaluated in a broader context of sexual and reproductive health, beyond the constraints of HIV alone.
13. Some have asserted that the trials and the calls for widespread implementation are being fueled by a form of racism. These issues need to be addressed seriously and included in the discussion.
14. It will be essential to determine how to avoid stigma associated with male circumcision or the lack of it.
15. It will also be essential to carry on the discussion around male circumcision to deliberately avoid branding men as perpetrators of infection.

Numerous ethical challenges will emerge as researchers define and apply the ethical principles of justice, beneficence, and respect for persons to current and future MC trials and research projects.

Challenge #1: Acceptability

The effectiveness of any circumcision intervention will be dependent on male uptake and community acceptance. In a review conducted by Westercamp et al, 13 acceptability studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa among non-circumcising communities were evaluated(33). Of these studies, 8 were designed to specifically investigate acceptability of MC, of which 4 included women. The median acceptability was 65% among men: 69% of women favored their partners being circumcised, and 81% of both men and women were willing to circumcise their male children. Variance in acceptability ranged from 29% in Uganda to 87% in Swaziland, and is at least partially attributed to how the questions were

posed and in what context. Higher acceptance rates were achieved when participants received information regarding the potential health risks and benefits. One of the highest acceptance rates was achieved by Halperin et al (2006), who asked participants if they would prefer circumcision if it was proven to have protective benefits against HIV(34). While the majority of studies on acceptability of male circumcision demonstrate general favorability, meaningful evaluation of available data requires understanding of diverse ethnic and regional specificities.

The three most common barriers to circumcision are costs associated with the procedure, fear of pain, and safety concerns. This suggests that public health and other bodies responsible for considering implementation of MC will need to ensure that the procedure is affordable, especially to the most vulnerable populations. Further, great care will need to be taken to ensure that the procedure is done as painlessly as possible and that adverse events occur as infrequently as possible.

Concerns related to costs vary from study to study; with some studies reporting that subjects feel that circumcision should be free and offered by government health clinics, other studies showing that participants perceive free or inexpensive circumcisions as being of lower quality. Notably, the cost of traditional circumcisions in some areas was viewed as prohibitive due to the costs associated with ceremony or initiation schools. In one study, 34% of participants initially opting to remain uncircumcised changed their minds when the proposed cost was set at US\$3.00. Similarly, a pilot intervention in Siaya, Kenya reported that men came in large numbers when the cost was set at US\$1.45. Concern for lost salary from missed work due to the healing period was also widely expressed these costs are difficult to quantify in economic projections.

Concerns regarding safety and pain are common. Many non-circumcising groups are familiar with circumcising practices of other groups, and cite the endurance of pain as a key component in the rite of passage. Furthermore, circumcision is widely understood as a surgical procedure with inherent risks. This concern is partially shaped by either personal knowledge or periodic media reports of complications or death. In general, most studies reviewed suggest a preference for circumcision to be provided by trained medical professionals in public health clinics. Given these results, it is likely that if male circumcision proves to have a protective benefit consistent with available results from ongoing clinical trials, acceptability is high enough to have a potentially significant impact on the reduction of HIV incidence. The greatest impact will be dependent on the age of intervention and among mixed- or non-circumcising areas that have high HIV prevalence rates(24).

Westercamp et al note that local regions of ethnically homogeneous non-circumcising groups may present greater resistance to circumcision interventions than ethnically diverse populations, insofar as circumcision may be identified as a break from identifying custom(33), although this may not be a universal trend. For example, Swaziland is a predominately non-circumcising country with high acceptability of circumcision as a protective technology.

The generalizability of any acceptability result may be limited by the context in which the study took place. One of the most important contextual factors is whether the epidemic is generalized or concentrated, and whether or not there is adequate availability of ARVs. In the United States, for example, male circumcision might not be viewed as necessary for the majority of the population because they are not at high risk for HIV, and ARVs are widely available and seemingly effective. African American, Caribbean, and large immigrant populations of males might be more interested, especially if they know that they are at extremely high risk for becoming infected with HIV. The procedure might have more attraction in sub-Saharan Africa, unless ARVs become widespread, inexpensive, and easy to access. Under those conditions, HIV might start to be seen as a more manageable, less lethal disease.

If male circumcision is a common practice, or is practiced by some groups and not others in a heterogeneous society, then individuals may feel more kindly disposed to it. If it is a foreign practice, or seen as something that some other religious or cultural group practices, then it may be less acceptable. The answers people give also depend on how the questions are asked and how well people can understand the concepts. If circumcision is proposed to prevent HIV, it may have greater acceptability than if it is proposed to prevent some other sexually transmitted infection, especially if that infection is quite treatable. If circumcision is proposed to prevent HIV, have people been told that the protection is not perfect, but is perhaps only 50% effective or maybe even less? What is the breaking point? Would it be 50% or 75% or 90%? When that concept is presented, do people understand that the probabilities refer to populations and not to individuals, and that the probability for a given individual in a given act of intercourse is either 0 or 1?

We do not understand enough about what determines acceptability for men and for women. Are men interested in male circumcision because it will render them more attractive to women (who might think that they are not susceptible to HIV)? Are they interested because they think it removes the need to use condoms? Are women interested in men being circumcised because they think it is less likely that the man will have HIV? Is it ethical to promote the intervention on an individual basis when we know the greatest public health impact would require wide scale rollout?

How price sensitive will circumcision be? Would incentives work to increase acceptance in specific situations? If a popular or important leader got circumcised or endorsed it for the population, would the procedure become more acceptable?

All of these questions are raised to reinforce the point that facile interpretations of acceptability studies are hazardous. Acceptability studies may need to use more sophisticated marketing strategies, and probably need to rely heavily on qualitative methods so that we can understand and "unpack" what people might mean when they say that male circumcision might be acceptable. And, acceptability will wax and wane over time. If people are getting circumcised, and the procedure goes well, many more may want it. If it is inexpensive, or even incentivized, many more may want it. If there are reports of serious adverse events, such as occurred in the Eastern Cape of South Africa(35-37), or if there are relevant sociocultural or ethical issues that are not adequately being tended to, then people may mistrust the medical establishment or not be so eager to expose themselves to the risk.

Challenge #2: The Benefit from MC is RELATIVE Not Absolute: How Can This Be Communicated?

Ideally, what might happen is that discussion of these issues reinforces the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques are given a needed boost in attention and funding.

Maintaining clear and nuanced communications about male circumcision will be difficult, when passions for and against the practice are so pronounced. We know from other circumstances, such as for the rollout of ARVs, that such passions cause people either to emphasize the problems or the benefits in ways that are not helpful for public discourse.

No single prevention technology or strategy will work on its own. All currently investigated strategies will require implementation in concert with one another. A vaccine providing 100% immunity is not likely to be developed in the short term, as fundamental questions about whether a highly effective preventive vaccine is even feasible remain unanswered. In the mean time, novel biomedical prevention strategies (such as microbicides, pre-exposure prophylaxis, etc) will be needed to effectively control the epidemic. As with MC, each of these strategies has the potential to lead to increased risk behavior. Caution should be emphasized so that the actual biomedical benefits of any investigational strategy are

not conflated with variables like risk behavior. Unlike other prevention strategies that are only as effective as the individual's ability to adhere to modified behavior or an ARV regimen, the protective benefits of male circumcision are disconnected from the actual risk behavior, making it an even more powerful strategy. The relative infection risk for each coital act remains the same. Increased risk behavior resulting from perceived protection of an intervention must be addressed in any strategy for rollout.

Any rollout must take into consideration the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. The first complicating issue has been the (some would say unnecessary; others will say harmful) debate about abstinence, partner reduction, or condom use. The "abstinence, be faithful, use condoms" (ABC) approach to prevention has sparked debate about whether or not abstinence is better than partner reduction, and whether or not condoms provide sufficient protection against HIV and other STIs. The unfortunate consequence of this debate is that all three contribute to HIV prevention. Obviously, one cannot get HIV or an STI if one is abstinent, and delaying onset of intercourse may also render people less susceptible to HIV and other STIs. Older individuals' reproductive systems have matured to be more resistant to infection, and older individuals may be more capable of taking care of themselves emotionally and behaviorally. Reducing number of partners, especially concurrent partnerships, may reduce exposure to pathogens.

Nonetheless, some have seemed to pit one strategy against another, and disparage condoms in the process. This had lead to unnecessary confusion about the real and beneficial protective effect of condoms. The problem has been exacerbated by religious objections to condoms on the grounds that they might encourage promiscuity in an environment where abstinence and/or faithfulness within marriage should be supported (such discussions do not take into account that most women in sub-Saharan Africa, and perhaps in other regions, are put at risk for HIV and other STIs within the context of a marriage or committed relationship).

The second complicating issue is that the current prevention strategies--male and female condoms, prevention of mother-to-child transmission with ARVs, access to clean syringes and needles, voluntary counseling and testing for HIV, treatment for substance abuse (including substitution and maintenance chemotherapy for opiate abuse--have not been used widely at all. One could conclude that prevention has not worked because it has not been tried. The following chart, drawn from the work of the Global HIV Prevention Working Group and funded by The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, shows that fewer than one in five--just 4% to 16%--of people at high risk for HIV infection have access to effective prevention. The report goes on to state that access is particularly limited to populations known to be at especially high risk for infection, including sex workers, men who have sex with men, and injecting drug users (IDUs).

Percentage of Individuals at Risk with Access to HIV Prevention

Source: UNAIDS, 2006; USAID et al., 2006

The report also cites the fact that the current supply of condoms falls 50% short of the number required, and the number of condoms needed annually is expected to increase significantly as the population of reproductive-age individuals increases by nearly 25% in some countries between 2000 and 2015.

Within this context, it is entirely possible that male circumcision will be hailed as the great new intervention, compensating for the significant failures of prior strategies when in fact those strategies

were never fully implemented. The unfortunate circumstance may be that progress toward implementation of the other strategies falls to the wayside and all hopes are pinned on male circumcision. This would be ethically irresponsible because, as we have reported, the effect of male circumcision will be relative and not absolute.

Challenge #3: Defining Risk, Benefit, and Harm Reduction

Population acceptability, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.

Beneficence is an ethical principle that entails an obligation to protect persons from harm. The principle of beneficence can be expressed in two general rules: 1) do no harm, and 2) protect from harm by maximizing anticipated benefits and minimizing possible risks of harm. Minimal risk for male circumcision is usually understood as minimal medical risk. The common risk/benefit analysis presented in discussions of male circumcision is framed typically in terms of the biological or medical well-being of the individual.

It would appear that the current studies, and those responsible for them, have limited their perspective of risk to “medical risk” and are providing limited consideration to possible negative social or gendered impacts. Placing the risk/benefit calculus in a framework that only considers, or even emphasizes, the medical harm minimizes the social, cultural, or psychological impacts that are a necessary part of any risk/benefit calculation.

Medical risk and adverse consequences require accurate and appropriate surveillance and documentation. It might be possible, for example, that a few sensational adverse consequences will attract media attention and headlines, and cause confusion, much in the way that some toxicities associated with ARVs sometimes are exaggerated both in terms of effects on individuals and the prevalence of those effects. Thus, it will be essential, if rollout occurs, that systems be set up to understand the range and prevalence of adverse effects, and the conditions associated with those effects, and that such information be used to improve the surgery for further use. If, for example, more adverse events are associated with a particular type of medical practitioner, or with traditional practitioners, then that information needs to be used to improve quality of outcomes lest individuals and populations be put at needless risk.

There are also several ethical issues that remain around the balance of expectations concerning local and international standards of care before and after trials—and who determines them. One issue is who should provide the needed treatments and services. Major ethical debates are currently circulating about whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV-infected.

Risk and risk aversion have different meanings to different groups of people. The concept of risk perception is socially constructed and culturally imbedded within groups, and individual risk perception is perceived through this sensibility(38-41). Policy statements pertaining to routine male circumcision are no exception. The social and economic factors that inform risk perception by the American Academy of Pediatrics, the British Medical Society, or any other developed country may not be congruent with those of societies within developing countries in which the risk of morbidity or mortality resulting from HIV infection (or a host of other opportunistic infections) is considerably higher. For example, the AAP may focus on the immediate health of a neonate because the adult risk of HIV is not high in the United States and access to ARV therapy is widespread. In developing countries where there is an incredibly high risk of HIV infection and access to life-saving drugs has not materialized, risk perception may dramatically differ from that of the U.S. Multilateral and bilateral organizations based in the United States and Europe should ensure that, when considering the risk/benefit calculus of interventions targeted to high prevalence

areas, harm reduction is understood in terms of regionally specific health risks. Equally important will be assurances from governments and community members that an MC intervention may have a positive impact; these assurances may play an important role in guiding policy.

Challenge #4: Placing Male Circumcision in a Combination Prevention Strategy Context

Ideally, what could happen is that the introduction of male circumcision can be used as impetus to gain support for the wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies, and that male circumcision causes us to focus on “combination prevention” and the need to evaluate the use of multiple prevention strategies in combination.

Consider the following letter published in *The New York Times* on December 19, 2006.

To the Editor:

Although I am encouraged by the discovery that circumcisions can significantly reduce the chances of transmitting the virus that causes AIDS, I am concerned about how people living in the third world will react to this news.

We do still live in a world where men with AIDS in Cambodia have unprotected sex with virgin girls in the belief that it will “cure” them, as Nicholas D. Kristof noted in his Dec. 12 column.

I’m concerned that more men will be circumcised as a result of these studies, but that they will then live an even more promiscuous life. We ought not lose sight of the importance of condom education.

Edmund DeMarche, Brooklyn, Dec. 14, 2006

And another letter said:

How do you persuade a man to snip off a protective skin on the most sensitive part of his body? Condoms are infinitely safer than circumcision.

Marshall Guerra, Chicago, Dec. 14, 2006

One issue here is that condoms are pitted against male circumcision in a totally unnecessary contest. We need both prevention strategies. A second is the disparaging language (addressed below).

What is needed is a framework that place MC within the context of a broader framework of prevention strategies and that does not isolate the strategy, thereby reinforcing the notion that it has the potential to address the complexities of HIV prevention by itself.

Such a framework was presented by Coates in the December 1, 2006 issue of the *Mail and Guardian* (Johannesburg). This is but one example; we encourage others to be developed:

For every person given antiretrovirals (ARVs) for HIV in South Africa, seven more become infected. If that continues, the health system will be completely overwhelmed. The advances of treatment in South Africa currently are groundbreaking. This must continue, expand and reach every person who needs drugs. Every HIV-infected person should know his or her status and be monitored so that treatment starts when he or she needs it. A good starting point would be a seven-point prevention plan, to counter the seven people that become infected for every ARV treatment. Promote HIV literacy: Received wisdom is that everyone knows about HIV and its transmission. The truth and the facts are muddled for many. That is partly the government's responsibility and partly because widespread information and messaging campaigns are imperceptible.

Goal 1: By 2010, 75% of adults score 100% on Aids literacy tests.

Promote HIV counseling and testing: People cannot plan their futures, take treatment or prevent transmission (including to babies) unless they know whether they have HIV. The biggest barriers to HIV testing are logistics and cost. We have found that bringing HIV testing to people--either through mobile or door-to-door testing--massively increases uptake. Mobile testing draws youth and especially young men.

Goal 2: By 2010, 75% of people have been tested for HIV at least once.

Protect young people: They are the future of South Africa. Access to accurate information, services and condoms are fundamental human rights. Young people vitally need them.

Goal 3: Prevalence of HIV among youth is reduced by 50% by 2010.

Prevent and treat substance use and abuse: Alcohol is probably a major driver of HIV transmission in South Africa, but other drugs such as tick and cat are spreading rapidly and could further fuel the pandemic.

Goal 4: What if every alcoholic beverage sold were accompanied by a condom? It would get the message across and demonstrate commitment to HIV prevention.

Get ready to circumcise: The results from Orange Farm's male circumcision study are the most hopeful we have had in HIV prevention since we found that ARVs can prevent mother-to-child transmission.

Goal 5: Circumcise 50% of men by 2010; advise 100% of parents of baby boys about circumcision and 75% opt for it.

Integrate prevention into treatment for HIV-positives: HIV can only spread from those who have it to those who don't. Treatment for HIV is wonderful, not only because it extends people's lives and brings hope, but also because it gives us the chance to interact with HIV positive people regularly.

Goal 6: By 2008, every HIV-infected patient is advised about safer sex at every clinic visit, every patient is offered a bag of condoms along with ARVs. An annual sexually transmitted infections check is offered to all HIV-infected patients.

Tackle stigma head-on: The popular paradigm is sad: if someone has HIV, they've been sleeping around and they bring shame on themselves and their families.

Goal 7: By 2010, 75% of South Africans regard HIV like any other disease, and that 75% of people with HIV disclose their status.

Challenge #5: Maintaining Broader Funding Commitments to Social and Behavioral Research and to Fighting Gender Inequality

The implications of MC would be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.

There is no vaccine to solve gender inequality or change behaviors, and the potential ethical implications of this larger over-reliance on biomedical solutions at the expense of social justice and human rights missions can't be dismissed. Finally, given the cost of circumcisions, the difficulty for health systems to scale up, and the lack of current attention in the field on the clear interaction between biomedical solutions and social and behavioral effects of interventions, some consider it unethical not to further promote behavioral prevention interventions financially, and in national-level communications at the same time as results and calls for further mass MC may roll out.

Challenge #6: How Will Male Circumcision Benefit Women? How Can Male Circumcision Not Harm Women?

There are two separate issues that must be considered: (1) benefiting women; and (2) shifting the disease burden toward women is a potential problem that may occur because the critical threshold to herd immunity cannot be achieved. Groups that advocate a cautious approach to male circumcision interventions increasingly voice this concern. The issue is that interventions that do not include adequate behavioral/educational components to ensure that the protective benefits of circumcision are not interpreted as allowing increased risk behavior among men, may in fact increase the risk to women. HIV-positive men are almost twice as likely to infect a female partner as an HIV-positive woman is to infect a male partner(42, 43). As a result, reducing the male prevalence rate would indirectly benefit the susceptibility of female partners. Modeling studies by Williams et al suggest that if male circumcision were to reduce female-to-male transmission by 60% as the Orange Farm clinical trial reports, it would have a population-level impact that reduced transmission in both directions by 37%(24).

Although mathematical modeling suggests that lowering the overall incidence of female-to-male transmission will lower prevalence rates for men and women (see *Herd Immunity* discussion above), and other studies suggest that MC combined with controlled viral burden in HIV-positive men will reduce transmission to their female partners, the degree to which MC as a prevention intervention will benefit women--or potentially increase their risk of infection--is uncertain and is a growing concern among social and behavioral scientists and policymakers. Of primary concern is that the sense of protection individuals associate with MC may lead to increased risk behaviors. Such behaviors could both diminish the

protective benefits and effectively shift the disease burden further toward women by increasing their risk. This argument is often framed as comparatively gauging the effective risk reduction for men and women separately. A strategy affording infection reduction to men that is misperceived as allowing more frequent risk behaviors may exacerbate existing gender disparities and further shift the disease burden to women.

Less obvious, but equally important, is addressing the underlying issues of why so much attention is given to the potential disinhibition of sexual behavior for male circumcision as a prevention strategy? Although there is some evidence regarding sexual disinhibition, there are conflicting results in various settings. Addressing behavioral disinhibition will have to accompany all prevention technologies (PrEP; viral load suppression; microbicides; vaccines; and even condom use, as inconsistent/improper use is pervasive). Some behavioral concerns regarding male circumcision may in part be linked to existing power discourses that connote specific gender and reproductive rights issues, (ie, coercive sex). Behavioral disinhibition would not be sufficient grounds to slow a prevention strategy that has such high potential for population impact. Behavioral disinhibition should be addressed in structuring effective messaging as part of rollout; it should not be used to withhold this technology (which in itself is counter to ethical principles of beneficence). While these issues are complex and are intimately related to prevention strategies, caution should be taken in distinguishing and evaluating with equal value the absolute biomedical harm or benefits of any strategy and its social impact.

Challenge #7: MC and Religious and Cultural Practices in the African Context

Historically, circumcision appears to have been practiced at one time or another throughout most of Africa, with the exception of the central inland east extending from southern Sudan to South Africa. Myriad circumcising and non-circumcising ethnic groups exist in both North and sub-equatorial Africa with diverse social histories. The practice, even among currently circumcising groups, was by no means consistently adhered to over time.

For groups that were not circumcising at the time of Colonial contact, there are at least two explanations for abandonment of the practice. The first is a less understood abandonment of circumcision and initiation schools in areas of south Malawi, Mozambique, parts of Zambia and Zimbabwe before arrival of the Europeans(44). The second explanation is better understood and relates to the Zulu wars in southern Zimbabwe and South Africa. The Zulu king Chaka ordered his people to stop the practice due to the difficulty of conducting initiation schools during the continuous period of fighting in the early 1800s. Many other groups that were also drawn into the fighting also abandoned the practice. That some groups readopted circumcision practices after the period of warfare, Jeff Marck explains as "...the general shifting of traditions and adopting other groups' styles and formats after long periods of abandonment"(44). Although the example of abandonment during the Zulu wars can not be generalized to the entire continent of Africa, it does provide an example of how circumcision patterns shifted because of historical factors even prior to Colonial imposition.

Religious beliefs are closely linked to the acceptability of circumcision. Islamic groups universally circumcise males. Many investigators have suggested the link between lower HIV prevalence rates in North Africa and the predominance of Islam and associated circumcising practices. As previously discussed, associating male circumcision in North Africa with lower HIV prevalence rates may be more complicated as sexual behavioral patterns among Muslims may have significant impact on curbing the spread of HIV(11, 44). In Africa, predominantly Christian groups have widely varying beliefs and inconsistent practices regarding male circumcision. In mapping the context of existing practices and strategies for potential interventions, local religious institutions and leaders should be involved, particularly where Christianity is prevalent.

Challenge #8: When to Circumcise: Infants vs. Adolescents vs. Adults?

The age at which circumcision is performed poses multiple challenges. Neonatal circumcision is considerably safer and substantially less expensive than adolescent or adult circumcisions(14, 15, 18, 45-49). If male circumcision proves effective and is only rolled out to neonates, it would take at least a generation before a population-level impact occurs. An adult intervention raises significant questions regarding the capabilities of existing health systems, increased complexity of the procedure, higher complication rates, and expense. Managing complications, and the associated costs, in resource-poor settings also raises significant concerns. Age at which a circumcision intervention is introduced is highly dependent on locally available capacity and training of staff. Surgical techniques that are feasible in resource-limited settings would have to be rapidly developed, as would clear guidelines for practitioners.

Modeling studies suggest that, although male circumcision could have an immediate and dramatic impact on HIV transmission, the full impact on prevalence rates and deaths would only be apparent in 10 to 15 years(24). Complicating the issue are the official statements, such as those cited in this document, regarding the advisability of infant circumcision, especially when such surgeries do not have an immediately beneficial therapeutic effect and/or the preventive impact will not occur for years.

Challenge #9: Taking the Opportunity to Further Distinguish MC from Female Genital Mutilation

The demand for male circumcision might lead to increased demand for female circumcision², especially in places where both practices are being carried out. The human rights reversals that are implied by this situation is one in which decades of work that has been carried out on fighting the harm of FGM to girls and women could be rolled back with implications for gender equity, rights, health, sexuality, and the body. Certainly, the ethical implications of attempting to make parallels between HIV outcomes with male circumcision and female genital mutilation are numerous. We advice caution and call for: a) extreme care around definitions of practices; b) warding off inaccurate parallels between MC and FGM; c) calls for action, advocacy, and media communications that ensure that inappropriate parallels are not made that would undermine long fought battles at the intersection of gender equality, women's rights, and harmful health outcomes on the issue of FGM; and d) consideration of a possible reinvigoration of human rights violations against girls and women if inappropriate parallels are made and actions supporting FGM moved forward.

The World Health Organization (WHO) describes the different types of FGM as follows:

- Type I - excision of the prepuce, with or without excision of part or all of the clitoris;
- Type II - excision of the clitoris with partial or total excision of the labia minora;
- Type III - excision of part or all of the external genitalia and stitching/narrowing of the vaginal opening (infibulations);
- Type IV - pricking, piercing or incising of the clitoris and/or labia; stretching of the clitoris and/or labia; cauterization by burning of the clitoris and surrounding tissue;
- Scraping of tissue surrounding the vaginal orifice (angurya cuts) or cutting of the vagina (gishiri cuts);
- Introduction of corrosive substances or herbs into the vagina to cause bleeding or for the purpose of tightening or narrowing it, and any other procedure that falls under the definition given above.

² Throughout this document we refer to female circumcision as female genital mutilation in compliance with World Health Organization's standard nomenclature.

The WHO reports that up to 80% of FGMs globally involve excision of the clitoris and the labia minora(50). The practice is conducted by several different cultures and religious groups. There are dramatic differences between FGM and male circumcision. FGM is partly structured to control a woman's sexuality and reposition it to focus on the male partner's pleasure. Removal of the clitoris eliminates the woman's ability to orgasm; and stitching the vaginal canal to make it smaller is carried out, in part, to increase male sexual pleasure due to tightening. Although significant medical and psychological morbidity has been documented, the perception of FGM by women in cultures that widely practice it varies. The importance of the practice as a group identifying marker and its cultural significance should be considered thoroughly when developing interventions intended to either eradicate the practice or minimize its severity (51). Comparisons to MC do significant violence to the global movement to eliminate the most severe forms of the practice. Male circumcision as an initiation practice is most often intended to signify either group affiliation or the transition from adolescents to adult status. From a cultural perspective, the intent is not to curtail or control the practice of one's sexuality. From a medical perspective, while circumcision may affect male sexual pleasure to a limited degree, circumcision as a public health measure is, at least in part, intended to keep men's sexual ability intact while providing protective benefits from disease.

Other than an unfortunate similarity in the naming of the procedures, male circumcision and female circumcision/FGM have no common health benefits. Male circumcision has been proven to reduce the risk of several sexually transmitted diseases, penile cancer, UTIs and a host of other diseases. FGM has no medical benefits and, in fact, may promote disease. The most severe forms of FGM are associated with tetanus infection, UTIs, gangrene, uterine infections, and other complications. In regards to HIV, UNAIDS has a clear position that, "There is no evidence or observational data that (female circumcision) would reduce the risk of HIV transmission; biologically, it is more likely to increase the likelihood of HIV transmission." Several recent studies of circumcised Tanzanian women have demonstrated the increased susceptibility to bacterial vaginosis and HSV-2, which are positively linked with HIV infection(52-54). The only biological-based similarity is that both procedures modify or remove sensitive tissues of the sexual organs.

Several possible components could be added to male circumcision interventions to ensure that participants do not believe similar benefits are gained from FGM. One possibility is to introduce joint counseling services for men and their female partners during the consent process. Additionally, male circumcision could be integrated as part of reproductive health services that provide both the circumcision procedure and family planning that distinguishes FGM from MC.

Challenge #10: Assessment and Surveillance of Safety and Complications

In developed countries it is difficult to accurately report complication rates as they vary widely depending on the type of study, setting, person performing the surgery, and most importantly, how complications are defined. This problem is compounded in resource-limited settings where multiple confounding factors may be present and basic sentinel surveillance is often limited. Limited data exists on the safety of male circumcision in resource-poor regions with high HIV prevalence. The procedure, whether conducted by traditional circumcisers or in medical facilities, is often conducted under suboptimal conditions, increasing the risk of immediate and future complications. Nevertheless, there is limited data suggesting that safe procedures utilizing accessible resources could be established in resource-limited settings. In a recent article, Krieger et al working in the Kisumu district of Kenya demonstrated that standard procedures for safe and acceptable MC services could be established in developing countries(55). The study used locally trained staff to conduct the procedures, and all supplies and instruments were locally obtained. In the United States, two large retrospective studies are often cited. The first, conducted by Wiswell et al reviewed the records of 136,086 boys from 1980-1985 for complications over the first month of life and found a 0.19% rate of complications, the majority being relatively minor(49).

The second study conducted by Christakis et al retrospectively reviewed the circumcision status of 354,297 neonates, of which 37% were circumcised, over 9 years (1987-1990) (56). The study reported a 0.20% complication rate, but also advised that although the procedure is relatively safe, “modest medical benefits may be offset by its complications.” The most common complications in both these studies were post-circumcision bleeding and infection. The major limitation to both of these studies is neither monitor or report complications after the newborn is discharged from the hospital. A longitudinal study following 500 New Zealand children from birth to 8 years post-circumcision reported an 11% complication rate (vs. 18.8% for uncircumcised males)(18). Although circumcision appears to provide a lifetime of numerous medical benefits, it is not without risk. The assessment of personal and public health benefit verses relative risk may differ dramatically by regionally specific confounding factors. In regions where high HIV prevalence rates expose the population to risks that have devastating impact on entire societies, the risks associated with MC may be outweighed by the potential lives saved. There is an urgent need to conduct further research on locally specific risks in resource-limited settings and to establish country plans for surveillance of procedures and complications.

Challenge #11: Health Systems Challenges

Implementation of male circumcision will be difficult and will strain the resources of health systems in many countries, especially those that need it the most. Prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) is still accessible to only 9% of mothers who need it, rising from 5% in 2003 to the current figure in 2005. Blood safety remains an important issue in several sub-Saharan African countries, and infection via occupational exposure (because safer devices or even clean needles and syringes are not accessible) also continues to occur.

Several issues emanate from this reality. The first is the need to continue to build and develop health systems in countries that most need it. HIV/AIDS has provided the opportunity to do so, especially given the aggressive targets for getting people onto ARVs.

But the second is the need to do so without distorting or diminishing resources from other critical aspects of the medical care system. The modeling done by Williams et al projecting thousands of new infections averted and overall reduction of prevalence rates were based on the results of the Orange Farm trial(24). With the release of the recent data from the Uganda and Kenya trials confirming the protective benefits found in Orange Farm, the Williams modeling gains further strength. The implications of averted new infections and reduced prevalence rates are that resources currently committed to combating HIV would be freed. While this is true, it will take time, as Williams points out that it would take approximately 10 years to reach the initial threshold of 2 million averted new infections and 20 years to reach approximately 6 million averted new infections (see discussion above, *Potential Benefits to Populations*). Each year would increase averted infections, presumably freeing funds. This means that substantial resources would initially need to be invested from international agencies to accommodate scale up of MC interventions and that funds could be re-allocated to other health systems needs as prevalence drops.

Immediate resource allocation will require comprehensive analysis as reduction in HIV prevalence could have a potential dramatic impact on available health system resources in the future. While achieving high rates of circumcision might be beneficial, it should not be at the cost of other disease prevention strategies such as antenatal care, malaria control, nutrition, etc. Since an internationally agreed-upon public health goal is for all women to give birth in health facilities, offering male circumcision in clinics to babies would at least not divert national resources from current efforts to build systems and might be a strategy that has multiple benefits. It might mean, however, that women have to remain longer in those settings and adequate resources will be essential to ensure that the goals might be met.

A major issue has to do with the need to ensure that there are sufficient personnel available to perform circumcisions, and whether or not the procedure necessarily needs to be performed by a physician, or whether medical officers, nurses or others can perform the surgery. Basic competency levels and certification that personnel are able to meet these standards must be established. An important issue highlighted in several XVI International AIDS Conference (Toronto, 2006) venues was the paucity of skilled health care personnel and the lack of proper medical training, even to perform the current tasks. Skilled, trained health care personnel are desperately needed to accommodate treatment needs in the context of wide-scale distribution of ARVs and appropriate follow-up treatment and care, particularly given the need for more widespread HIV testing scale up. In some contexts, many health workers received their medical training prior to the emergence of HIV, and therefore have little or no knowledge of the diagnosis and treatment of HIV and HIV-related illnesses. For some who received training after the onset of the epidemic, but prior to the availability of ARVs in their region, many still believe that HIV/AIDS is an invariably terminal and unmanageable condition. Those aware of ARVs may lack the knowledge to administer them properly.

In other contexts, community-based workers who may be lacking “formal” health-care training are delivering the highest standard of care. Volunteers have played important roles in counseling and care, but investment is needed to bridge the gap and maintain consistency in quality of care for the long term, since altruism alone may be inadequate in providing sustained motivation for volunteer involvement in long-term health programs, particularly in high-burden settings where volunteers may be subject to many of the same environmental conditions contributing to disease(57).

The South African (Orange Farm), Kenyan, and Ugandan MC randomized clinical trials all employed highly trained medical staff in controlled environments to perform the surgical procedure. As would be expected, complications in these controlled settings are relatively low; Orange Farm, the only trial of the three to report results, reported a 3.8% complication rate. Low complication rates may be significantly higher outside a controlled clinical trial environment. Questions pertaining to safety, human resources, and adequate medical training in resource-poor environments remain a high concern. A recent study in Ibadan, Nigeria reported a 20.2% complication rate among a cohort of 322 circumcised male infants ranging in age from 8 days to 13 months in which circumcisions were performed by nurses (55.9%), doctors (35.1%), and traditional circumcisers (9%)(58). Over eighty percent of these circumcisions were performed in a hospital setting. Other studies in Nigeria and Kenya cite complications rates (of varying severity) ranging from 12-17.5% in hospital settings.

Returning to Williams’ modeling, any initial intervention will take time (nearly a decade) before a dramatic impact is seen on population-level prevalence. It is unlikely that a rapid response that will achieve sufficient coverage to avert millions of new infections over the next decade can be achieved without a scale up that does not solely rely on physicians or nurses.

Health Care Infrastructure. For men who undergo an important initiation into manhood when circumcision is performed by a “traditional” surgeon (as is the case for many men in South Africa), there may be important reasons to provide solid training to those outside of the medical establishment to support important cultural rites of passage and their continuation. It is unethical not to further promote behavioral prevention interventions. What if demand outstrips capacity? Where will men get this done? What are the ethical implications of putting forward a practice and suggesting it *en masse* if families have to eventually decide, due to lack of health care capacity, which person they will or will not circumcise?

Incorporating trained and certified traditional circumcisers and nurses should be considered. It is likely that traditional circumcision practices will continue, regardless of regulatory mandates limiting them(35, 36). It is also conceivable that if circumcision receives the same level of acceptability reported from studies, and health care systems are incapable of meeting demand, unregulated and unsafe circumcisions

may rise dramatically. The ability to incorporate these providers into scale up provides several advantages including the reduced strain on existing health care systems, a more rapid scale up, and the ability to regulate and monitor circumcision conducted in a cultural context. Equally important will be engaging traditional circumcisers and potentially incorporating the complex social dynamics associated with traditional ceremony into a population-level intervention that could avert millions of deaths. Finally, as discussed above (see *Acceptability*), religious and cultural leaders have substantial influence on circumcision practices and, as Westercamp recommends, should be consulted prior to any intervention. They could present significant barriers if they are not engaged in scale up (33).

Challenge #12: Placing Male Circumcision Within a Broader Context of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Beyond the Constraints of HIV Alone

The intensification of linkages between sexual and reproductive health (SRH) and HIV/AIDS is not simply a service issue but is at the core a policy and program issue as well. These linkages are complex and involve family planning, maternal and infant health, management of STIs, and management of other sexual and reproductive health (SRH)-related issues on the one hand, and HIV/AIDS prevention, treatment, care, and support on the other.

Areas where key linkages need to be made include VCT, the promotion of safer sex, STI management, tending to the SRH of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWH/A), tending to the primary health care of PLWH/A, integrating HIV/AIDS prevention and care into maternal and reproductive health, examining SRH and safer sex between discordant couples, and optimizing other connections between HIV/AIDS and SRH (eg, gender-based violence, female condoms). The challenge here is to place the discussion and advancement of male circumcision within this broader context and not restrict the discussion to HIV/AIDS alone.

Male circumcision provides the additional benefit for partners intending to have children. It provides a level of protection against HIV, STIs, and HPV while allowing for pregnancy.

Challenge #13: Perceptions of Inequitable Power Relations between the North and the South and Reinvigoration of Essentialized Notions of Male Sexuality

The power relations implied by the way in which developed countries are carrying out trials in developing countries for a practice that has finally been declared medically unnecessary for babies in the West may be tainted with unfortunate accusations of new forms of colonialism(59). While these accusations are relatively few, and have come from adamant opponents to routine MC, they have the potential to distract from important questions of scale up. Nevertheless, there are significant ethical concerns pertaining to MC randomized trials. Trials are being carried out consistently in Africa, when several other countries, including the inner-city United States, clearly have significant epidemics. While they may not be as severe as many regions in Africa experiencing generalized population-wide epidemics, they are nonetheless local epidemics. What are the ethical issues around “exporting” a rejected practice from the West (eg, AAP, BMA, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, etc) to the South, while not calling for implementation of it in the West too?

The ethical principle of justice asks questions about who ought to receive the benefits of research and bear its burdens. This is an issue of social justice, in the sense of considering fairness in distribution or what is deserved. An injustice occurs when some benefit to which a person is entitled is denied without good reason or when some burden is imposed unduly. Thus, some may argue that the principle of justice would center on whether particular racial and ethnic minorities or individuals in particular regions of the world are being systematically selected for participation in MC trials simply because of their easy availability, their compromised position, or their manipulability, rather than for reasons directly related to

the problem being studied. As the medical, prevention, public health, and advocacy communities are perched to hear the results of upcoming trials, these issues will undoubtedly and increasingly come to the fore.

Thus, the ways in which developed countries are carrying out trials in developing countries for a practice that has been declared medically unnecessary for the West may also invariably reinvigorate racist perceptions of sexuality and African masculinity in regions where the trials are not conducted. Specifically, MC trials have already likely reinvigorated perceptions that the epidemic is largely “heterosexualized”—that men’s sexual behavior is problematic and “excessive”—only to be contained by medical surgery and an essentializing notion of male sexuality. No matter how acceptable MC may be internally to communities in various regions, the gaze of external audiences might stigmatize men in regions not experiencing the severity of the sub-Saharan African generalized epidemic. Perceptions of race are fluid, and racial formation is influenced by both proximal (local) and global factors. Diasporic communities of African men, their descendants, and men whose ancestry is of the global South are influenced and shaped by the gaze of the West on Africa. That is, the assumed relationship that men of color in the Global South have to their own (and others’) bodies and sexuality under a suggested roll out of MC—that some men are more moral and can contain themselves while others need surgery on their genitals so as to not impose damage on the populace—may become part of the public perception and this stigmatizing effect has been left out of studies and commentaries on trials thus far. While individuals in other nations will not bear the ethical brunt of the implications of the science in this way, men in the Global South may not be able to avoid it, and trials might exacerbate erroneous perceptions that men are perpetrators of the disease and responsible for it. Additionally, there is a need to investigate how MC as a HIV prevention strategy may affect social and cultural meanings about the role of the penis in constructing men’s sense of themselves and their sexuality.

Challenge #14: Avoiding Stigma Associated with Male Circumcision or the Lack of It

Remarks at the XVI International AIDS Conference in Toronto in 2006 placed the importance of female-initiated methods of HIV/STI prevention (and especially microbicides) at center stage. The comments were important and useful, and it was refreshing to see major leaders talking about equity, prevention, female-controlled methods, and condoms. The choice of words revived a familiar and important discourse that was not critically examined deeply enough at the conference. The resurgence of an individualist innocence discourse brought to the fore the need to advance rights-based approaches to HIV prevention and care without falling into the trap of morality, judgment, and blame.

This innocence discourse, long used to set apart babies, hemophiliacs, faithful wives, and orphaned children as deserving of protection and health services, might be a way to make condoms (and other prevention strategies) palatable to politicians and others. However, such discourse may perpetuate stigma, minimize structural factors that affect both women’s and men’s HIV risks, and does not deal with issues of marginalized populations (eg, MSM, commercial sex workers, and IDUs).

Lurking just below the surface in many presentations is the belief or perception that people in certain countries or regions are more promiscuous, more callous, less empathic, or less moral. For numerous reasons, some are framed as more damaged from their past and present environments than others. All too quickly, this can slide into discussions of morality, “excessiveness,” or personal responsibility. The ensuing conversations about sexuality may be too individualized (or group-based) and become a justification for racism and inequitable judgments on populations from the Global South (or inner cities of the North). Also lurking below the surface is the attitude and expectation that people living with HIV should abstain or minimize sexual activity and refrain from pursuing a full sex life, including procreation.

In this context, the questions are these: Will those men who choose not to become circumcised be branded as risky? Will they be assumed to have HIV infection? Will they be stigmatized as individuals not willing to do all that they can to reduce the spread of HIV? Will parents of young women want certification of circumcision in the male partners of their daughters?

Further, the need remains to better understand sexual behaviors and sexuality in diverse populations, as well as the needs of sexual minorities, especially in places where discrimination, stigma, and legal sanctions are practiced. Any discussion of male circumcision, and its advisability for specific populations, needs to be placed in this context.

Challenge #15: Avoiding Discourse That Brands Men as Perpetrators of Infection

In the present context, the challenge is this: Will advancement of male circumcision further brand men as perpetrators? Will male circumcision be seen as “the answer” to the need to change conceptions of masculinity in society? Will efforts to modify male social norms and behaviors be given short shrift in the desire to advance male circumcision more generally?

There were new and important emphases at the Toronto AIDS conference placed on structural inequities facing women and how to adequately respond with new interventions at this level (eg, educational and economic interventions, property rights, continued legal reform). But most sessions referred to gender as a women’s issue, and there were few sessions on gender relations, men, and masculinity. Even fewer sessions examined the role of racism in the exacerbation of the epidemic. Some of the discourse and research framed “problems” related to the epidemic as the fault of individual men instead of examining a system of interlocking race, class (or caste), age, and gender relations. Overall, particularly strong vilification of African men occurred throughout the conference.

Improving gender equality will go a long way toward resolving some of the most powerful dynamics of HIV transmission. It will remain important to examine the disenfranchisement that both women and men face, and to develop programs to fight structural inequities. Vigilance will be required in order to avoid the trap of individualizing problems/solutions that pit men and women against one another. A rights-based agenda can advance women’s status and reduce their HIV/AIDS risks, and hence a women’s empowerment agenda needs to be advanced.

However, it also remains vital that discourse and research find a more accurate way to describe men and masculinities, particularly as these intersect with race, class/ caste, sexuality, and nationality, in order to take a comprehensive gender relations agenda forward. One writer for *The Toronto Globe and Mail* said, “...changing the behaviour of African men is probably hopeless.” These kinds of stereotypes of African men serve to entrench both a highly racialized perspective on African males’ sexuality, moral depravity, and common modes of thought about gender, rather than advancing these discussions. African men are being portrayed as vectors, unconcerned about others and spreading disease along with violence and neglect for families.

What Research Needs to Be Conducted?

We provide here a list of ideas, in no particular order, about research initiatives that might be undertaken to address some of the challenges articulated above. We anticipate expanding this list as people reading this and other reports consider these issues and challenges.

1. What is the effect of male circumcision on female partners—not just related to HIV, but also sexually transmitted infections (STIs), cervical cancer, female pleasure, and female perceptions of sexual viability of the male partner?
2. There are often few ethical guidelines on the social and behavioral effects of biomedical trials—only medical effects and adverse events are examined. Social and behavioral effects need to be defined, and studies need to be carried out on the positive and negative consequences related to study participation.
3. Is penile hygiene as good as MC? Clinical trials that include a penile hygiene study arm should be conducted. These studies should also conduct analyses of feasibility, required resources, and infrastructure requirements.
4. Although much cost analysis, particularly in the United States, has been conducted to project the cost savings from averted HIV infection, STIs, and urinary tract infections (UTIs), there is a lack of data projecting the costs of treating circumcision-related complications. How will complications be addressed in resource-poor settings?
5. The development of models that include cost analysis for training practitioners in resource-poor settings is urgently needed. Modeling should project the cost of equipment and its maintenance, and the treatment of complications. These projections should be comprehensive modeling strategies including PMTCT, condom provision, voluntary counseling and testing (VCT), and treatment.
6. Interventions that combine reproductive health services, HIV VCT, and male circumcision should be explored.
7. Should MC rollout begin, it is essential that surveillance systems be put into place to track who is presenting for services, incidence of adverse events, and disinhibition in circumcised populations.
8. Qualitative studies that shed light on people’s understanding of protection afforded by male circumcision—both for males and females—will be essential. It will be important to repeat these over time as events change. The perspective of parents will also need to be included.
9. Prevention models that include male circumcision, but do not focus on it exclusively, are needed to elucidate how male circumcision can be incorporated into a broader prevention framework.
10. Legal research is needed to understand barriers and facilitators of male circumcision, and the protections necessary to maximize benefits and reduce harms.
11. Stigma remains a central impediment in HIV prevention. Understanding how male circumcision reduces or enhances stigma will be essential.

Ethical Issues for Future Research

As human subjects protections committees (HSPCs) or institutional review boards (IRBs) are only beginning to define what the social and behavioral effects of participation in a biomedical trial are (with emphasis only on “adverse events”), the field should attempt to be ethically ahead of the curve on these

issues and not wait for protests that may soon follow (a letter of caution has already been written by many leading thinkers in the field to the WHO asking for immediate consideration of ethical issues such as these to be taken into account).

Ethical Issues Related to Informed Consent

There is anecdotal information that men in several areas of high HIV prevalence are eager to be circumcised. One rather large ethical implication of these trials for future research involves the question of how consent is given by men. In some instances, researchers' may have meetings with community leaders—often including traditional, tribal, and political leaders—who then lead discussions with men, who subsequently volunteer.

But the actual question remains as to whether individuals within a village can maintain the ability to individually refuse participation while the village is being strongly encouraged to participate from its leaders. Additionally, the extent to which full disclosure about the risks and benefits are being offered to men at the group or individual level (particularly given the lack of sociocultural, gendered, tribal, or other cultural factors in the definition of risk/benefit calculation). The extent to which men feel coerced or pressured into volunteering have not been evaluated.

Ethical Implications for Past, Present, and Future Trials

Circumcision does not have a strong history of being systematically and ethically examined prior to claims being made about its ability to resolve health problems. The historical record shows that it has been claimed to prevent hydroencephalitis, persistent masturbation, epilepsy, insanity, tuberculosis, spinal paralysis, hip dysplasia, STIs, penile cancer, cancer of the tongue, and more.

IRB Principles of Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice

Recognized principles that guide the ethical conduct of research are respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. To what extent are these being adequately considered in the current trials?

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that requires that individual autonomy be respected and that persons with diminished autonomy be protected. Here, it is clear that autonomy refers to requirement that subjects, to the degree that they are capable, be given the opportunity to choose what shall or shall not happen to them. This opportunity is provided when adequate standards for informed consent are satisfied.

Some ethical issues linked to respect for persons and autonomy include:

1. Prior comments we have made concerning the way in which researchers seek the consent of participants are relevant here. The process through which consent is being obtained in MC trials is not being critically examined, particularly given the differential relationship that individuals from non-Western countries can have to the medical establishment (eg, individual consent vs. group or village level decision-making processes).
2. If recommendations are made for mass MC for neonates, the medical establishment will be recommending a permanent surgical procedure for a child who does not have the right to decide something about their own body, the consequences of which would not even be relevant until they are sexually active.

3. Full evaluation of risks and benefits is needed in order to say that one responded with informed consent to voluntarily participate. Yet, risks and benefits that we have delineated throughout this document are not currently fleshed out beyond medical risk.
4. Autonomy should also be respected in terms of respecting the fact that individuals who are HIV tested in trials may not want to receive their results. At the same time, researchers should track the behaviors of such individuals, as it is known that such individuals engage in higher risk behavior.
5. Language issues—are consent forms clear? Do people understand what is being said?

Beneficence is an ethical principle that entails an obligation to protect persons from harm. The principle of beneficence can be expressed in two general rules: (1) do no harm; and (2) protect from harm by maximizing anticipated benefits and minimizing possible risks of harm. Some ethical issues related to beneficence:

1. What are the risks—medical risks and beyond—and are they worth the benefits? Furthermore, since we do not know how behavioral factors will interact with medical aspects of risk, how can we accurately ensure protection under the principle?
2. Stigma is an issue related to both beneficence and justice. After all, entire communities may be stigmatized by the mere fact that large, well-publicized HIV/AIDS research is being conducted in them. Previous issues raised in this document about perceptions of male sexuality, masculinity, racism, and beliefs that certain men are responsible for the perpetration of disease while others are not are highly relevant.
3. Are there reductions in sexual pleasure, sexual functioning, and changed self- or sexual-concept for men? Are these, on balance, worth the benefits? How shall this be decided and by whom?
4. Properly weighing risks/benefits not just to men but also to women will remain an important ethical and practice issue.
5. As has been noted, there is no consensus on how to properly balance expectations concerning local and international standards of care before and after trials—and who decides. Who should provide the needed treatments and services is a key issue. Major ethical debates are currently circulating about whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV -infected.

The principle of **justice** asks questions about who ought to receive the benefits of research and bear its burdens. As we have noted, this is an issue of social justice, in the sense of considering fairness in distribution or what is deserved. An injustice occurs when some benefit to which a person is entitled is denied without good reason, or when some burden is imposed unduly.

Some ethical issues related to justice:

1. As we have noted, are men from particular areas of the world—or particular racial and ethnic minorities—being systematically selected for participation in MC trials simply because of their easy availability, their compromised position, or their manipulability, rather than for solid reasons directly related to the problem being studied?
2. Are poor communities able to bear the burdens of research and can they truly benefit from it despite the complexities of poverty or a lack of infrastructure?
3. With the exception of adverse events, inadvertent positive and negative consequences of research participation are not generally tracked. These could be defined and tracked in order to adequately assure adherence to principles of justice—and define new ones if needed.
4. Relatively privileged researchers may feel motivated to contribute to the reduction of social inequality through health research but this may be carried out at the expense of local communities, as Western definitions can exacerbate situations on the ground. Key to the local research experience might be the way in which “risk,” “benefit,” or “acceptable” are defined for communities that may or may not be adequate for the region.
5. Some believe that researchers from rich countries contribute to sustaining poverty in poor countries (eg, through exploitation of cheap labor, unsound trade rules, requiring debt payments that are not payable, histories of colonialism) and thus they have an ethical obligation to transfer resources (and not just public health requirements or suggestions) to reduce gross injustices(60).
6. Studies have elucidated how power relations between developing and developed countries have resulted in the misperception that Western science and its interventions are perceived by study participants as definitively “working”, even when, for example, candidate microbicides may be investigated for acceptability and not efficacy(61). No matter how clear informed consent may be concerning risks/benefits, levels of protection, and the need for behavioral change, individuals might feel that an intervention that comes from Western science is one that unequivocally “works.” True dangers therefore exist that misperceptions will occur regarding the partial protection afforded by MC. Qualitative research needs to be conducted to investigate men’s and women’s perceptions of protection afforded over the long run.

Standards of Care

Determining what the standard of care should be during and after clinical trials can be complex, particularly when examining the differential resources available to resource-rich and resource-poor countries (and middle-income countries). Debates about standards of care required in placebo arms of drug trials initially emerged in 1999, and were modified and rewritten in 2000 due to ethical debates about randomized controlled trials of PMTCT. At the time, placebo-controlled study arms were being used, rather than comparing the experimental regimen to another that was either a) an acceptable standard treatment around the world or b) a local standard treatment. Debates raged about whether control arms should be constituted according to “the highest standard in the world,” “the highest standard of care practically attainable in the country in which research is being carried out,” or “placebo control.” At first, the World Medical Association proposed that placebos should be used in trials by arguing that the standard of care should not be the “highest in the world” but rather “the highest standard of care practically attainable in the country in which research is being carried out.” However, other arguments emerged to underscore that the standard of care that is “practically attainable” might mean anything from state-of-the-art to clearly substandard treatment; on the lower end, this could certainly violate the

principle of beneficence known as “do no harm.” As a result of these debates, in October 2000 in Helsinki, the World Medical Association released a new version of the Declaration to argue that placebo arms were prohibited in “situations of local scarcity” if the “best current method” existed elsewhere. Relevant issues related to standards of care in MC trials involve debates about what will constitute standard of care during and after trials, and who will decide.

Some relevant issues are:

1. There are several ethical issues that remain about local and international standards of care before and after trials and for potential rollout. Who should provide HIV and non-HIV treatment and care services for trial participants in resource-limited health systems is a major issue. Ethical debates are also focusing on whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV-positive. In countries where ARV rollout is incomplete, what if MC trial participants are among the few in their communities who receive ARV treatment?
2. The above relates to the question of how dual standards of care shall be dealt with. In short, it is not uncommon for trial participants to receive more or better access to health care than others in their communities due to their participation in research. This can result in problems within families, communities, and health systems. Some argue that this can lead to “undue inducement” to participate in research and that large payments for trial participation should not be made to participants, as this might further exacerbate undue inducement and interfere with the principle of autonomy.
3. A basic principle of standard of care is that researchers or sponsors of trials should make successful interventions available to the host country after research is completed.
4. Some believe that researchers from resource-rich countries have an ethical obligation to transfer resources to improve the overall standard of care in health systems (and not just offer public health suggestions) to reduce gross injustices in resource-poor countries(60). The argument is that sustainable improvements in health come from improvements in the health care system-- researchers from resource-rich countries are ethically obligated to improve standards of care in the health care system where research occurs. How this would actually happen is not clear.
5. Several opportunities may exist to improve standards of care in health systems. For example, there is the opportunity to integrate male circumcision within broader male sexual, reproductive health, and HIV prevention strategies. Needs assessments and capacity building assistance in various contexts is much needed on this and various other standard-of-care improvements.

Conclusions: Possible Steps Forward

Because the Kenya and Uganda MC trials replicated the results of the already completed Orange Farm study, at least in providing evidence that HIV infection is reduced for males who are circumcised vs. those who are not, immediate steps should be taken to engage stakeholders in formulating assessment of potential MC scale up. It remains an open question as to whether or not the evidence will be similarly strong to support the hypothesis that circumcising HIV-infected men reduces transmission to their partners.

Because all three trials presented similar and convincing data, the pressure will begin mounting for broad implementation of male circumcision, especially in high-prevalence areas such as sub-Saharan Africa,

parts of India, and perhaps Eastern Europe. Questions will arise regarding the benefits of male circumcision for concentrated epidemics—such as are occurring in the United States, many parts of Spanish-speaking Latin America, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, and China—and especially when these epidemics involve primarily men who have sex with men, where the main risk is from receptive anal intercourse. Questions will continue to arise about the benefits of infant vs. adolescent or adult circumcision. Controversies will continue to rage as to whether male circumcision is mutilation, or whether it is justified for health, religious, and cultural reasons.

Because there may be a disconnect between the MC lobbying forces in Europe and the United States and those voices from the areas most impacted by HIV, it is important to ensure comprehensive inclusion of all positions, and that these positions are identified by local origin and are evidence based.

We have presented challenges to ensure comprehensive coverage of medical, social, and structural issues related to MC as a prevention strategy. The challenges are not intended to discourage the use of male circumcision for HIV prevention nor are the challenges intended to slow the development of potential interventions. Indeed, if the effectiveness of male circumcision in real practice approaches the results from the three clinical trials, the practice can potentially avert thousands of new infections and dramatically reduce prevalence of infection in entire populations.

Further, we do not present these challenges as a “social science” reaction to a decidedly medical HIV prevention strategy. All advances in HIV prevention are welcome and encouraged.

Rather, we present these challenges to ensure that the discussion regarding the evolution and rollout of male circumcision reflects the full range of issues that should be considered for individuals and for populations. We believe that there are benefits to this kind of discussion that will strengthen policy and application. We think it essential that laws, policies, and programs reflect the full reality of concerns and issues, especially for a practice as radical and potentially helpful as male circumcision.

Next steps:

- We encourage broad dissemination of this and similar monographs as a way to stimulate discussion of the points made. Articles should also be prepared for the scientific literature, and for general readership, to ensure dissemination and discussion of the ideas.
- Encourage the development of national strategic plans for countries with the highest prevalence rates. These plans should include assessment of current capacity, the development of a single sentinel surveillance and reporting mechanism, clear guidelines on basic standards of care, plans for complication triage, measurable targets, cost analyses, and specific assessment of internal ethnic group practices.
- Engagement of traditional practitioners and religious groups should be paramount. The development of national plans should include them. Ongoing research on the ethnic and cultural dynamics of scale up should be encouraged.
- Additional modeling should be done. The important modeling done by Williams et al relies on only the Orange Farm data and assumes high uptake. Modeling projections that estimate varying degrees of uptake and additional factors such as combination prevention strategies (MC + ARVs or MC + condoms) should be undertaken.
- In preparation for scale up, widespread public information campaigns should be developed that describe the risks and benefits.

- The development of regionally specific “tool kits” for ministries of health that outline standards, triage, and surveillance techniques. These kits would include manuals and modules for training of practitioners as well as “training of trainers.”
- Technical support for country-level scale up should be sought from NGOs and multilaterals.
- One or more think tanks might be beneficial to flesh out ideas, test them with larger groups of people, and to modify the points made here and add to them. Such think tanks should involve key opinion leaders. It might be useful to think of global events, as well as regional or country-level meetings, that could serve as opportunities to stimulate thinking and discussion.
- From these think tanks could emerge briefings for policymakers, program planners, and implementers. Obviously, such efforts should coincide with those of the multilateral and bilateral implementing agencies (WHO, UNAIDS, World Bank, PEPFAR, USAID, DFID, etc), so that people charged with making funding and programmatic decisions are not receiving contradictory advice. Nonetheless, we would hope that briefings would allow for the full range of issues to be raised in these discussions so that programs and policies can be advanced that take into account all of the necessary information and perspectives.
- International standards for MC should be developed that are flexible enough to respond to local need.
- It would be useful to stimulate research on some of the specific topics outlined, and especially to encourage country- and regional-level research that will have applicability for local advocacy, legal and policy issues, sexual and reproductive health, and religious and cultural perspectives.
- Specific focus needs to be given to ethical discussion, studies, and guidelines, as these issues are among the most difficult in the field of HIV prevention, especially regarding male circumcision in the context of research and in practice.
- We also encourage a focus on stigma, as it is possible that male circumcision could have a beneficial effect on HIV/AIDS stigma. It is also possible that male circumcision could result in increased stigma for individuals who do or do not undergo the surgery.
- The feasibility of comprehensive reproductive services targeting both men and women that include the provision of MC and associated counseling and messaging, as well as family planning, STI counseling, the provision of condoms, contraceptive devices, and VCT services should be considered.
- We think it would be useful to track media coverage of the issue. If one searches Google for “male circumcision,” an extremely varied array of viewpoints are found. Many of these take the perspective that male circumcision is genital mutilation. Media coverage of the issue might illuminate the various ways that people are thinking about the issue, and also highlight confusions that might be generated in populations.

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Annotated Bibliography of Key Literature

(Wiswell and Geschke 1989; Moses, Bradley et al. 1990; Christakis, Harvey et al. 2000; Gray, Kiwanuka et al. 2000; Quinn, Wawer et al. 2000; Schoen, Wiswell et al. 2000; Siegfried, Muller et al. 2003; Auvert, Taljaard et al. 2005; Christoffersen-Deb 2005; Cohen 2005; Malone 2005; Schoen 2005; Siegfried, Muller et al. 2005; Wawer, Reynolds et al. 2005; CDC 2006; Donoval, Landay et al. 2006; Fergusson, Boden et al. 2006; Westercamp and Bailey 2006; Williams, Lloyd-Smith et al. 2006)

Auvert, B., D. Taljaard, et al. (2005). "Randomized, controlled intervention trial of male circumcision for reduction of HIV infection risk: the ANRS 1265 Trial." *PLoS Med* 2(11): e298.

BACKGROUND: Observational studies suggest that male circumcision may provide protection against HIV-1 infection. A randomized, controlled intervention trial was conducted in a general population of South Africa to test this hypothesis. **METHODS AND FINDINGS:** A total of 3,274 uncircumcised men, aged 18-24 y, were randomized to a control or an intervention group with follow-up visits at months 3, 12, and 21. Male circumcision was offered to the intervention group immediately after randomization and to the control group at the end of the follow-up. The grouped censored data were analyzed in intention-to-treat, univariate and multivariate, analyses, using piecewise exponential, proportional hazards models. Rate ratios (RR) of HIV incidence were determined with 95% CI. Protection against HIV infection was calculated as $1 - RR$. The trial was stopped at the interim analysis, and the mean (interquartile range) follow-up was 18.1 mo (13.0-21.0) when the data were analyzed. There were 20 HIV infections (incidence rate = 0.85 per 100 person-years) in the intervention group and 49 (2.1 per 100 person-years) in the control group, corresponding to an RR of 0.40 (95% CI: 0.24%-0.68%; $p < 0.001$). This RR corresponds to a protection of 60% (95% CI: 32%-76%). When controlling for behavioural factors, including sexual behaviour that increased slightly in the intervention group, condom use, and health-seeking behaviour, the protection was of 61% (95% CI: 34%-77%). **CONCLUSION:** Male circumcision provides a degree of protection against acquiring HIV infection, equivalent to what a vaccine of high efficacy would have achieved. Male circumcision may provide an important way of reducing the spread of HIV infection in sub-Saharan Africa. (Preliminary and partial results were presented at the International AIDS Society 2005 Conference, on 26 July 2005, in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.).

CDC (2006). Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

This fact sheet summarizes information in 4 areas of male circumcision: (1) male circumcision and risk of HIV transmission; (2) male circumcision and other health benefits; (3) risk associated with male circumcision; and (4) status of HIV infection and male circumcision in the United States

Christakis, D. A., E. Harvey, et al. (2000). "A trade-off analysis of routine newborn circumcision." *Pediatrics* 105(1 Pt 3): 246-9.

BACKGROUND. The risks associated with newborn circumcision have not been as extensively evaluated as the benefits. **OBJECTIVES.** The goals of this study were threefold: 1) to derive a population-based complication rate for newborn circumcision; 2) to calculate the number needed to harm for newborn circumcision based on this rate; and 3) to establish trade-offs based on our complication rates and published estimates of the benefits of circumcision including the prevention of urinary tract infections and penile cancer. **METHODS.** Using the Comprehensive Hospital Abstract Reporting System for Washington State, we retrospectively examined routine newborn circumcisions performed over 9 years (1987-1996). We used International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision codes to identify both circumcisions and complications and limited our analyses to children without other surgical procedures performed during their initial birth hospitalization. **RESULTS.** Of 354, 297 male infants born during the study period, 130,475 (37%) were circumcised during their newborn stay. Overall 287 (.2%) of circumcised children and 33 (.01%) of uncircumcised children had complications potentially associated with circumcision coded as a discharge diagnosis. Based on our findings, a complication can be expected in 1 out every 476 circumcisions. Six urinary tract infections can be prevented for every complication endured and almost 2 complications can be expected for every case of penile cancer prevented. **CONCLUSIONS.** Circumcision remains a relatively safe procedure.

However, for some parents, the risks we report may outweigh the potential benefits. This information may help parents seeking guidance to make an informed decision.

Christoffersen-Deb, A. (2005). "'Taming tradition': medicalized female genital practices in western Kenya." *Med Anthropol Q* 19(4): 402-18.

This article considers the question of female genital practices at the hands of health workers in western Kenya. Recent articles in *Medical Anthropology Quarterly* have critically engaged with the biomedical arguments condemning such practices. This article studies the case of medicalized circumcision in which biomedical concerns over health risks have become incorporated in their vernacular practice. Although some suggest that medicalization may provide a harm-reduction strategy to the abandonment of the practice, research in one region challenges this suggestion. It argues that changing and conflicting ideologies of gender and sexuality have led young women to seek their own meaning through medicalized practice. Moreover, attributing this practice to financial motivations of health workers overlooks the way in which these "moral agents" must be situated within their social and cultural universe. Together, these insights challenge the view that medicine can remain neutral in the mediation of tradition.

Cohen, J. (2005). "HIV/AIDS. Prevention cocktails: combining tools to Stop HIV's spread." *Science* 309(5737): 1002-5.

Donoval, B. A., A. L. Landay, et al. (2006). "HIV-1 target cells in foreskins of African men with varying histories of sexually transmitted infections." *Am J Clin Pathol* 125(3): 386-91.

Numerous epidemiologic studies have found significant associations between lack of circumcision and HIV-1 acquisition in men. To our knowledge, this is the first study of human foreskin tissue that examines biologic mechanisms that increase susceptibility of uncircumcised African men to HIV-1. Foreskin specimens from 20 men with and 19 men with no history of sexually transmitted infections were examined for HIV-1 target cells. Most Langerhans cells were found in the epithelium; most CD4+ T cells and macrophages were in the submucosa. There were no differences in HIV-1 target cells between men with and those without history of sexually transmitted infections. However Langerhans cells and macrophages were more abundant in the group with a history of infection. The densities and positions of HIV-1 target cells in the foreskin tissue of these Kenyan men indicate that the inner mucosal surface of the human foreskin contains cells that make it highly susceptible to HIV infection.

Fergusson, D. M., J. M. Boden, et al. (2006). "Circumcision status and risk of sexually transmitted infection in young adult males: an analysis of a longitudinal birth cohort." *Pediatrics* 118(5): 1971-7.

OBJECTIVES: Previous research suggests that male circumcision may be a protective factor against the acquisition of sexually transmitted infections; however, studies examining this question have produced mixed results. The aim of this study was to examine the association between circumcision status and sexually transmitted infection risk using a longitudinal birth cohort study. **METHODS:** Data were gathered as part of the Christchurch Health and Development Study, a 25-year longitudinal study of a birth cohort of New Zealand children. Information was obtained on: (1) the circumcision status of males in the cohort before 15 years old, (2) measures of self-reported sexually transmitted infection from ages 18 to 25 years, and (3) childhood, family, and related covariate factors. **RESULTS:** Being uncircumcised had a statistically significant bivariate association with self-reported sexually transmitted infection. Adjustment for potentially confounding factors, including number of sexual partners and unprotected sex, as well as background and family factors related to circumcision, did not reduce the association between circumcision status and reports of sexually transmitted infection. Estimates of the population-attributable risk suggested that universal neonatal circumcision would have reduced rates of sexually transmitted infection in this cohort by 48.2%. **CONCLUSIONS:** These findings suggest that uncircumcised males are at greater risk of acquiring sexually transmitted infection than circumcised males. Male circumcision may reduce the risk of sexually transmitted infection acquisition and transmission by up to one half, suggesting substantial benefits accruing from routine neonatal circumcision.

Gray, R. H., N. Kiwanuka, et al. (2000). "Male circumcision and HIV acquisition and transmission: cohort studies in Rakai, Uganda. Rakai Project Team." *Aids* 14(15): 2371-81.

BACKGROUND: Male circumcision is associated with reduced HIV acquisition. **METHODS:** HIV acquisition was determined in a cohort of 5507 HIV-negative Ugandan men, and in 187 HIV-negative men in discordant relationships. Transmission was determined in 223 HIV-positive men with HIV-negative partners. **HIV**

incidence per 100 person years (py) and adjusted rate ratios (RR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were estimated by Poisson regression. HIV-1 serum viral load was determined for the seropositive partners in HIV-discordant couples. RESULTS: The prevalence of circumcision was 16.5% for all men; 99.1% in Muslims and 3.7% in non-Muslims. Circumcision was significantly associated with reduced HIV acquisition in the cohort as a whole (RR 0.53, CI 0.33-0.87), but not among non-Muslim men. Prepubertal circumcision significantly reduced HIV acquisition (RR 0.49, CI 0.26-0.82), but postpubertal circumcision did not. In discordant couples with HIV-negative men, no seroconversions occurred in 50 circumcised men, whereas HIV acquisition was 16.7 per 100 py in uncircumcised men (P = 0.004). In couples with HIV-positive men, HIV transmission was significantly reduced in circumcised men with HIV viral loads less than 50000 copies/ml (P = 0.02). INTERPRETATION: Prepubertal circumcision may reduce male HIV acquisition in a general population, but the protective effects are confounded by cultural and behavioral factors in Muslims. In discordant couples, circumcision reduces HIV acquisition and transmission. The assessment of circumcision for HIV prevention is complex and requires randomized trials.

Malone, P. S. (2005). "Circumcision for preventing urinary tract infection in boys: European view." *Arch Dis Child* 90(8): 773-4.

Moses, S., J. E. Bradley, et al. (1990). "Geographical patterns of male circumcision practices in Africa: association with HIV seroprevalence." *Int J Epidemiol* 19(3): 693-7.

To ascertain whether male circumcision might explain some of the geographical variation in human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) seroprevalence in Africa, we investigated the association between the practice of male circumcision at a societal level and HIV seroprevalence. Male circumcision practices for over 700 African societies were identified, and HIV seroprevalence in general adult populations from 140 distinct locations in 41 countries was obtained. In locations where male circumcision is practised, HIV seroprevalence was considerably lower than in areas where it is not practised. This study supports the hypothesis that lack of circumcision in males is a risk factor for HIV transmission.

Quinn, T. C., M. J. Wawer, et al. (2000). "Viral load and heterosexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus type 1. Rakai Project Study Group." *N Engl J Med* 342(13): 921-9.

BACKGROUND AND METHODS: We examined the influence of viral load in relation to other risk factors for the heterosexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1). In a community-based study of 15,127 persons in a rural district of Uganda, we identified 415 couples in which one partner was HIV-1-positive and one was initially HIV-1-negative and followed them prospectively for up to 30 months. The incidence of HIV-1 infection per 100 person-years among the initially seronegative partners was examined in relation to behavioral and biologic variables. RESULTS: The male partner was HIV-1-positive in 228 couples, and the female partner was HIV-1-positive in 187 couples. Ninety of the 415 initially HIV-1-negative partners seroconverted (incidence, 11.8 per 100 person-years). The rate of male-to-female transmission was not significantly different from the rate of female-to-male transmission (12.0 per 100 person-years vs. 11.6 per 100 person-years). The incidence of seroconversion was highest among the partners who were 15 to 19 years of age (15.3 per 100 person-years). The incidence was 16.7 per 100 person-years among 137 uncircumcised male partners, whereas there were no seroconversions among the 50 circumcised male partners (P<0.001). The mean serum HIV-1 RNA level was significantly higher among HIV-1-positive subjects whose partners seroconverted than among those whose partners did not seroconvert (90,254 copies per milliliter vs. 38,029 copies per milliliter, P=0.01). There were no instances of transmission among the 51 subjects with serum HIV-1 RNA levels of less than 1500 copies per milliliter; there was a significant dose-response relation of increased transmission with increasing viral load. In multivariate analyses of log-transformed HIV-1 RNA levels, each log increment in the viral load was associated with a rate ratio of 2.45 for seroconversion (95 percent confidence interval, 1.85 to 3.26). CONCLUSIONS: The viral load is the chief predictor of the risk of heterosexual transmission of HIV-1, and transmission is rare among persons with levels of less than 1500 copies of HIV-1 RNA per milliliter.

Schoen, E. J. (2005). "Circumcision for preventing urinary tract infections in boys: North American view." *Arch Dis Child* 90(8): 772-3.

Schoen, E. J., T. E. Wiswell, et al. (2000). "New policy on circumcision--cause for concern." *Pediatrics* 105(3 Pt 1): 620-3.

Siegfried, N., M. Muller, et al. (2005). "HIV and male circumcision--a systematic review with assessment of the quality of studies." *Lancet Infect Dis* 5(3): 165-73.

This Cochrane systematic review assesses the evidence for an interventional effect of male circumcision in preventing acquisition of HIV-1 and HIV-2 by men through heterosexual intercourse. The review includes a comprehensive assessment of the quality of all 37 included observational studies. Studies in high-risk populations consisted of four cohort studies, 12 cross-sectional studies, and three case-control studies; general population studies consisted of one cohort study, 16 cross-sectional studies, and one case-control study. There is evidence of methodological heterogeneity between studies, and statistical heterogeneity was highly significant for both general population cross-sectional studies ($\chi^2=132.34$; degrees of freedom [df]=15; $p<0.00001$) and high-risk cross-sectional studies ($\chi^2=29.70$; df=10; $p=0.001$). Study quality was very variable and no studies measured the same set of potential confounding variables. Therefore, conducting a meta-analysis was inappropriate. Detailed quality assessment of observational studies can provide a useful visual aid to interpreting findings. Although most studies show an association between male circumcision and prevention of HIV, these results may be limited by confounding, which is unlikely to be adjusted for.

Siegfried, N., M. Muller, et al. (2003). "Male circumcision for prevention of heterosexual acquisition of HIV in men." *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*(3): CD003362.

BACKGROUND: The findings from observational studies, reviews and meta-analyses, supported by biological theories, that circumcised men appear less likely to acquire human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) has contributed to the recent ground swell of support for considering male circumcision as a strategy for preventing sexually acquired infection. We sought to elucidate and appraise the global evidence from published and unpublished studies that circumcision can be used as an intervention to prevent HIV infection. **OBJECTIVES:** 1) To assess the evidence of an interventional effect of male circumcision for preventing acquisition of HIV-1 and HIV-2 by men through heterosexual intercourse 2) To examine the feasibility and value of performing individual person data (IPD) meta-analysis **SEARCH STRATEGY:** We searched online for published and unpublished studies in The Cochrane Library (issue 2, 2002), MEDLINE (April 2002), EMBASE (February 2002) and AIDSLINE (August 2001). We also searched databases listing conference abstracts, scanned reference lists of articles and contacted authors of included studies. **SELECTION CRITERIA:** We searched for randomized and quasi-randomized controlled trials of male circumcision or, in their absence, observational studies that compare acquisition rates of HIV-1 and HIV-2 infection in circumcised and uncircumcised heterosexual men. **DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS:** Independent reviewers selected studies, assessed study quality and extracted data. We stratified studies based on study design and on whether they included participants from the general population or high-risk groups (such as patients treated for sexually transmitted infections). We expressed findings as crude and adjusted odds ratios (OR) together with their 95% confidence intervals (CI) and conducted a sensitivity analysis to explore the effect of adjustment on study results. We investigated whether the method of circumcision ascertainment influenced study outcomes. **MAIN RESULTS:** We identified no completed randomized controlled trials. Three randomized controlled trials are currently underway or commencing shortly. We found 34 observational studies: 16 conducted in the general population and 18 in high-risk populations. It seems unlikely that potential confounding factors were completely accounted for in any of the included studies. In particular, important risk factors, such as religion and sexual practices, were not adequately accounted for in many of the included studies. **General population study results:** The single cohort study (N = 5516) showed a significant difference in HIV transmission rates between circumcised and uncircumcised men [OR = 0.58; 95% CI: 0.36 to 0.96]. Results for the 14 cross-sectional studies were inconsistent, with point estimates for unadjusted odds ratios varying between 0.28 and 1.73. Six studies had statistically significant results, four in the direction of benefit and two in the direction of harm. The test for heterogeneity between the cross-sectional studies was highly significant ($\chi^2 = 77.59$; df = 13; P-value < 0.00001). Nine studies reported adjusted odds ratios with eight in the direction of benefit, ranging from 0.26 to 0.80. Use of adjusted results tended to show stronger evidence of an association although they remained heterogeneous ($\chi^2 = 75.2$; df = 13; P-value < 0.00001). Only one case-control study was found (N = 51) which had a non-significant result [OR = 1.90; 95% CI: 0.50 to 7.20]. **High-risk group study results:** The four cohort studies identified found a protective effect from circumcision with point estimates for unadjusted odds ratios varying from 0.10 to 0.39. Two of these studies had statistically significant results. Two studies reported adjusted odds ratios, both protective with one being significant. The chi-square test for between-study heterogeneity was not significant ($\chi^2 = 5.21$; df = 3; P-value = 0.16). All eleven cross-sectional studies reporting unadjusted results found benefit from circumcision, eight of which had statistically significant results.

Estimates of effnal studies reporting unadjusted results found benefit from circumcision, eight of which had statistically significant results. Estimates of effect varied from an unadjusted odds ratio of 0.10 to 0.66. Between-study heterogeneity was significant with the chi-square = 29.77; df = 10; P-value = 0.0009. Four of these studies reported adjusted odds ratios ranging from 0.20 to 0.59 and all were significant. One additional cross-sectional study only reported an adjusted odds ratio in the direction of benefit which was statistically significant. All three case-control studies found a protective effect of circumcision on HIV status, two being statistically significant. Point estimates varied from unadjusted odds ratios of 0.37 to 0.88. One reported an adjusted odds ratio showing a significant protective effect. Adverse effects: No studies reported on the adverse effects of circumcision. In most studies, circumcision had taken place during childhood or adolescence before the studies commenced. REVIEWER'S CONCLUSIONS: We found insufficient evidence to support an interventional effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition in heterosexual men. The results from existing observational studies show a strong epidemiological association between male circumcision and prevention of HIV, especially among high-risk groups. However, observational studies are inherently limited by confounding which is unlikely to be fully adjusted for. In the light of forthcoming results from RCTs, the value of IPD analysis of the included studies is doubtful. The results of these trials will need to be carefully considered before circumcision is implemented as a public health intervention for prevention of sexually transmitted HIV.

Wawer, M. J., S. J. Reynolds, et al. (2005). "Might male circumcision be more protective against HIV in the highly exposed? An immunological hypothesis." *Aids* 19(18): 2181-2.

Westercamp, N. and R. C. Bailey (2006). "Acceptability of Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Review." *AIDS Behav.*

Based on epidemiological, clinical and experimental evidence, male circumcision (MC) could have a significant impact on the HIV epidemic in selected areas. We reviewed studies of the acceptability of MC in sub-Saharan Africa to assess factors that will influence uptake of circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising populations. Thirteen studies from nine countries were identified. Across studies, the median proportion of uncircumcised men willing to become circumcised was 65% (range 29-87%). Sixty nine percent (47-79%) of women favored circumcision for their partners, and 71% (50-90%) of men and 81% (70-90%) of women were willing to circumcise their sons. Because the level of acceptability across the nine countries was quite consistent, additional acceptability studies that pose hypothetical questions to participants are unnecessary. We recommend pilot interventions making safe circumcision services available in conjunction with current HIV prevention strategies and evaluating the safety and acceptability of circumcision.

Williams, B. G., J. O. Lloyd-Smith, et al. (2006). "The potential impact of male circumcision on HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa." *PLoS Med* 3(7): e262.

BACKGROUND: A randomized controlled trial (RCT) has shown that male circumcision (MC) reduces sexual transmission of HIV from women to men by 60% (32%-76%; 95% CI) offering an intervention of proven efficacy for reducing the sexual spread of HIV. We explore the implications of this finding for the promotion of MC as a public health intervention to control HIV in sub-Saharan Africa. METHODS AND FINDINGS: Using dynamical simulation models we consider the impact of MC on the relative prevalence of HIV in men and women and in circumcised and uncircumcised men. Using country level data on HIV prevalence and MC, we estimate the impact of increasing MC coverage on HIV incidence, HIV prevalence, and HIV-related deaths over the next ten, twenty, and thirty years in sub-Saharan Africa. Assuming that full coverage of MC is achieved over the next ten years, we consider three scenarios in which the reduction in transmission is given by the best estimate and the upper and lower 95% confidence limits of the reduction in transmission observed in the RCT. MC could avert 2.0 (1.1-3.8) million new HIV infections and 0.3 (0.1-0.5) million deaths over the next ten years in sub-Saharan Africa. In the ten years after that, it could avert a further 3.7 (1.9-7.5) million new HIV infections and 2.7 (1.5-5.3) million deaths, with about one quarter of all the incident cases prevented and the deaths averted occurring in South Africa. We show that a) MC will increase the proportion of infected people who are women from about 52% to 58%; b) where there is homogenous mixing but not all men are circumcised, the prevalence of infection in circumcised men is likely to be about 80% of that in uncircumcised men; c) MC is equivalent to an intervention, such as a vaccine or increased condom use, that reduces transmission in both directions by 37%. CONCLUSIONS: This analysis is based on the result of just one RCT, but if the results of that trial are confirmed we suggest that MC could substantially reduce the burden of HIV in Africa, especially in southern Africa where the prevalence of MC is low and the prevalence of HIV is high. While the protective

benefit to HIV-negative men will be immediate, the full impact of MC on HIV-related illness and death will only be apparent in ten to twenty years.

Wiswell, T. E. and D. W. Geschke (1989). "Risks from circumcision during the first month of life compared with those for uncircumcised boys." *Pediatrics* **83**(6): 1011-5.

The records of 136,086 boys born in US Army hospitals from 1980 to 1985 were reviewed for indexed complications related to circumcision status during the first month of life. For 100,157 circumcised boys, there were 193 complications (0.19%). These included 62 local infections, eight cases of bacteremia, 83 incidences of hemorrhage (31 requiring ligature and three requiring transfusion), 25 instances of surgical trauma, and 20 urinary tract infections. There were no deaths or reported losses of the glans or entire penis. By contrast, the complications in the 35,929 uncircumcised infants were all related to urinary tract infections. Of the 88 boys with such infections (0.24%), 32 had concomitant bacteremia, three had meningitis, two had renal failure, and two died. The frequencies of urinary tract infection (P less than .0001) and bacteremia (P less than .0002) were significantly higher in the uncircumcised boys. Serious complications from routine prepuce removal are rare and relatively minor. Circumcision may be beneficial in reducing the occurrence of urinary tract infections and their associated sequelae.

Maps

Circumcision Prevalence

(Caldwell, 2006) (67)

REGIONS WHERE MOST MEN ARE UNCIRCUMCISED

HIV Prevalence

UNAIDS HIV Prevalence, 2005

2005

Adult prevalence %

**Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV Transmission: What the New Data Mean
for HIV Prevention in the United States**

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Required Disclaimer: The findings and conclusions in this commentary are those of the
authors, and do not necessarily represent the views of the Centers for Disease Control and
Prevention.

Word Count: 2969

Three randomized, controlled clinical trials in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda were recently unblinded early because interim analyses concluded that circumcision of HIV-negative adult males reduced their risk for acquiring HIV infection through penile-vaginal sex.¹⁻³ In each trial, men who had been randomly assigned to an intervention group receiving circumcision had a lower incidence of HIV infection in up to 2 years of follow-up, compared to men who were assigned to a control group not receiving circumcision. The estimated reduction in the risk of HIV infection ranged from 51% to 60%; per-protocol estimates of risk reduction ranged from 55% to 76%.

It is now clear that male circumcision can be efficacious for men in reducing their risk of HIV acquisition through sex with women.⁴ Some experts predict that the impact of male circumcision as a biomedical intervention for HIV prevention in Africa may be large^{5,6}, and preparatory work for male circumcision programs in Africa has been taking place. The implications of African trials of circumcision for HIV prevention programs in the United States are less clear – despite interest of the popular press in the idea.⁷ Here, we consider the differences between the HIV epidemics in Africa and the United States, the current status of male circumcision in the United States, and the knowledge gaps in the United States that will need to be addressed as we consider whether male circumcision should be evaluated or implemented as a biomedical intervention to reduce sexually acquired HIV infection domestically.

Epidemiologic Differences

The results of any trial must be interpreted with the caution that inference not be extended to populations differing from the study participants in important ways. The

HIV epidemics in Africa are substantially different from the US epidemic. In many areas of Africa, generalized HIV epidemics exist, and the population prevalence of HIV among adult Kenyans, Ugandans and South Africans ranges from 6-19%.⁸ The predominant mode of HIV transmission in Africa is through male-female sex. In contrast, the United States has a concentrated epidemic, with most sexual transmission occurring among men who have sex with men (MSM). The general population prevalence of HIV is about 0.4%,⁹ and only 17% of men diagnosed with HIV infection during 2005 were reported to have acquired HIV through male-female sex.¹⁰

Biologic Plausibility of Circumcision to Prevent HIV Acquisition

The association between circumcision and reduced risk for HIV acquisition is biologically plausible: the foreskin contains high concentrations of superficial Langerhans cells, CD4+ T cells, and macrophages¹¹ – target cells for HIV infection – some of which may also be close to the skin surface^{12,13}; the preputial sac may serve as a reservoir for HIV-containing secretions, resulting in prolonged contact time after exposure to secretions; and the foreskin may present less of a physical barrier to HIV entry because of lower keratinization¹² and, potentially, more frequent epithelial disruption. There are also potential indirect mechanisms of association of lack of circumcision and HIV risk; for example, lack of circumcision is associated with increased risk of genital ulcer diseases, which are associated with increased risk of HIV transmission and acquisition.¹⁴

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Vaginal-Penile Sex

Epidemic differences are important because, on a population basis, the impact of circumcision as an intervention to prevent HIV infection among men who have sex with

women will depend on the likelihood of exposure to HIV among US men who have sex with women – and, therefore, on the prevalence of HIV among their female sex partners. A recent analysis of data from sexually transmitted disease clinics in Baltimore evaluated the association of male circumcision and risk of prevalent HIV infection in two ways – first, among all male attendees at the clinics, and second, restricting the analysis to males who were known to have been exposed to HIV heterosexually (e.g., sexual contacts to partners known to be infected with HIV).¹⁵ The results indicated that, while circumcision was not associated with prevalent HIV infection in the whole population of male STD clinic attendees where HIV prevalence was 3%, circumcision was associated with significantly lower HIV prevalence among men with a known infected female sex partner -- where the prevalence of infection was markedly higher at 12% (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 0.46; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.22-0.97). In effect, this analysis illustrated the impact of partner prevalence of HIV on the association of circumcision and HIV infection status and concluded that it was difficult to detect a protective effect from circumcision on HIV infection in the setting of a partner pool with lower HIV prevalence.

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Male-Male Sex

Most sexual transmission of HIV in the United States is by male-male sex¹⁰, and most transmission by male-male sex is to the *receptive* partner in penile-anal intercourse.¹⁶ The fact that the results from the African trials that circumcision was protective for men who were the *insertive* partner in vaginal intercourse suggests that the utility of male circumcision in prevention of HIV transmission among MSM may be limited. Because reducing the concentration of target cells for HIV infection on the penis is a proposed protective mechanism, understanding the relative viral challenge presented

by vaginal versus anal-rectal secretions is relevant to evaluating the plausibility of a protective effect of circumcision for the insertive male partner during anal intercourse. The concentration of HIV-RNA in rectal secretions may be higher than in blood or semen, regardless of use of antiretroviral therapy¹⁷, and may be orders of magnitude higher than the concentrations in vaginal or cervical secretions.^{17,18} Circumcision may change the balance of virus and target cells, but if rectal mucosal secretions contain a higher concentration of infectious virus than vaginal secretions, any potential protective effect of circumcision for the insertive partner may be overwhelmed by excess virus. Also, new data suggest that, for limited periods of time before wound healing is complete, female sex partners of newly circumcised men may be at increased risk of acquiring HIV.⁴ Possible transient increased risk of transmission (before complete wound healing) from recently circumcised MSM to their receptive anal intercourse partners is also of concern.

Few studies provide evidence as to whether circumcision may protect against HIV infection among MSM. In a vaccine-preparedness cohort of MSM followed from 1995 to 1997, circumcision was significantly associated with a decreased risk for HIV seroconversion (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.3-0.9), controlling for number of male sex partners and unprotected sex with an HIV-positive partner.¹⁹ In a cross-sectional survey of gay men in the early 1990s, circumcision was associated with decreased odds of prevalent HIV infection (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.25-1.0).²⁰ While falling short of the quality of data from a randomized intervention trial, these limited data suggest that circumcised MSM in the United States may have decreased risk of HIV infection. However, it is possible that the noted associations in these two observational studies may have been related to

uncontrolled bias. A small cross-sectional study of Australian MSM found no association of circumcision status and risk of HIV infection, when stratifying by insertive and receptive roles.²¹

Virologic Issues

In the African countries where circumcision has been demonstrated to be efficacious, the predominant HIV subtypes are A, C, and D; it is likely that some recombinant strains were also represented in the Kenya and Uganda trials. In the United States, subtype B predominates. Despite the theoretical possibility that subtype differences in either vaginal shedding of HIV or affinity to HIV receptors (especially those natively expressed on the foreskin) could modify the effectiveness of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention, the consistent findings of the African trials argue that this is unlikely. For example, despite differences in vaginal shedding between subtype C and subtypes A and D¹⁸, the efficacy of circumcision in trials where subtypes A, C, or D were prevalent was comparable. One potentially relevant biological difference relates to binding avidity of HIV subtypes for CCR5 receptors, which are important mechanisms for entry into Langerhans cells, and present in high concentrations in the foreskin.¹¹ Subtype C is reported to have lower binding avidity than subtype B for CCR5 receptors²²; it is unclear whether the greater binding avidity of subtype B for CCR5 could represent an escape mechanism to overcome the decreased availability of target cells that results from circumcision.

Status of Circumcision in the United States

Public health recommendations will likely have the largest impact in populations where circumcision has been rare. Non-religious male circumcision was introduced to

the United States in the late 1800s²³, and by the 1940s, an increasing proportion of male children in the United States were born in hospitals, and were circumcised.²⁴ The proportion of newborns that were circumcised annually reached 80% after World War II and peaked in the mid-1960s. The proportion of male babies circumcised subsequently decreased. According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), which documents circumcisions performed in hospitals but would not ascertain circumcisions performed outside of the hospital for religious reasons, 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999. Although the overall proportion of newborns circumcised has been stable from 1979 to 1999²⁵, the proportion of black newborns who were circumcised rose over the period to approximately 65%. Significant discrepancies also exist by region. While the proportion of newborns born in the Midwest who were circumcised increased over the 20-year period to 81% in 1999, the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased over the same period, to 37% in 1999.²⁵

Data from another hospital discharge survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), present a slightly different picture.²⁶ In that survey, newborn circumcision rates increased from 48% in 1988-1991, to 61% in 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black.²⁶

Data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES) from 1999 to 2004 indicated that the overall prevalence of circumcision among adult males in the United States was 79% and varied by race/ethnicity (88% in non-Hispanic whites, 73% in non-Hispanic blacks, 42% in Mexican Americans, and 50% in others). The prevalence of circumcision decreased among US-born men from the 1970s to the

1980s.²⁷ Although causality cannot be implied by these data and many other factors are likely operative, the rates of HIV and AIDS among non-Hispanic blacks and Hispanic men are considerably higher than in non-Hispanic whites in the United States.²⁸

Willingness of adult males to be circumcised

The ability of investigators to fully enroll three trials of adult circumcision¹⁻³ in Africa speaks to the acceptability of circumcision among adult males in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda. A recent systematic review of published literature suggests that adult male circumcision may be acceptable as an HIV prevention intervention in many countries in sub-Saharan Africa.²⁹ In the United States, the overwhelming majority of circumcisions are performed on newborns; adult circumcisions are commonly only done for medical reasons, such as preputial cancer or phimosis. It is not clear whether adult circumcision, were it to be recommended in the United States, would be acceptable as a prevention intervention. Preliminary evidence from interviews with uncircumcised men surveyed at Gay Pride festivals in the United States suggests that the majority of men would consider circumcision as an adult, if circumcision were shown to reduce risk of HIV infection by male-male sex³⁰ – although respondents were not told in the survey that protection would be partial, and condom use would still be recommended after circumcision.

Policy Issues Related to Circumcision of Newborn Boys

In 1999, the American Academy of Pediatrics changed from routinely recommending circumcision (primarily based on benefits with respect to risk for urinary tract infections and sexually transmitted infections) to a neutral stance on circumcision³¹; this position was re-affirmed in 2005 by the Academy after publication of the results of

the South Africa trial.³² In a 1995 US review, 61% of infant circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant.³³ Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary.³⁴

Should Adult Male Circumcision be Recommended for HIV Prevention in the United States?

Circumcision may have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. However, because of the many differences in the underlying HIV epidemics between Africa and the United States, differences in the prevalence of male circumcision in Africa and the United States, and the considerable gaps in knowledge that exist regarding the potential impact of circumcision on HIV transmission by male-male sex, the extent of this role on a population basis is unknown. Further, the already high prevalence of circumcision among US men suggests some limitations in the potential impact of circumcision at a population level.

Based on the data from the three African clinical trials, it is likely that circumcision will decrease the probability of a man acquiring HIV via penile-vaginal sex with an HIV-infected woman in the United States. Until public health recommendations are available for the United States, some sexually active men may consider circumcision as an additional HIV-prevention measure, but should do so only in consultation with their physician or health care provider, and with a clear understanding of the costs and risks of circumcision and the need to continue use of other, proven prevention measures (e.g., reducing the numbers of sex partners and consistent and correct condom use). Men who

choose to be circumcised should also be counseled about the importance of refraining from sexual intercourse following circumcision, until wound healing is complete.⁴

To consider the possible impact of public health recommendations for male circumcision, we must also take into account HIV incidence in high-risk groups, as well as adoption of other protective behaviors, such as condom use. For example, HIV incidence among US MSM recruited in community- and venue-based samples was, on average, about 1.9% annually,³⁵ and 36% of MSM in the US National HIV Behavioral Surveillance System reported having unprotected anal sex with a casual partner in the 12 months before interview.³⁶ There are few data on HIV incidence among high-risk heterosexuals in the United States, but there are limited data on condom use: in 2002, 16% of high-risk heterosexual men and 24% of high-risk heterosexual women never used condoms during penile-vaginal sex with a non-primary partner.³⁷ Currently available data on disparities in rates of prevalent HIV infection and AIDS^{28,38} and the prevalence of circumcision among US men²⁷ suggest that Black and Hispanic men may have particular opportunities for reduction of risk of HIV acquisition through circumcision.

Future research and consultation

In order to understand the potential for male circumcision as an HIV-prevention approach in the United States, we believe that there are important questions that should be answered. These include questions that can be answered by basic science, by modeling, by surveys of acceptability, by considering ethical issues, and, perhaps, by clinical trials in the United States. For example, it is important to understand more fully the differences in shedding of HIV by rectal versus vaginal mucosa. Modeling may provide important information on (1) the impact on the US epidemic from increasing

male circumcision rates, and (2) the cost-benefit of circumcision among newborns, or among adult men with high risk of exposure to HIV through sex. Cost benefit models may be limited by lack of definitive transmission parameters in US populations and should therefore be conducted with appropriate sensitivity analyses. Surveys may increase our understanding of the acceptability of adult male circumcision among groups of uncircumcised adult males in the United States for whom circumcision might be recommended (e.g., men at high risk of acquiring HIV heterosexually and who do not use condoms consistently, and high-risk MSM), and of barriers and facilitators to acceptance of adult male circumcision, were it recommended as an HIV-prevention strategy. In light of recent trial results and international consensus that male circumcision is efficacious, ethical questions about whether equipoise exists for a US MSM trial, and about how to implement trials or programs of male circumcision in light of complex cultural and religious views about circumcision are important to consider.³⁹ Evaluating data from basic science, modeling, and acceptability surveys and addressing ethics questions will be important in deciding whether a clinical trial to determine the efficacy of male circumcision among MSM may be feasible and appropriate in the United States.

Further, recommendations about circumcision in newborns or high-risk adults for the prevention of HIV infection cannot be made without a more comprehensive discussion of other, documented prevention benefits and risks of circumcision. Benefits include reduction in acquisition of sexually transmitted genital ulcer disease, infant urinary tract infections, penile cancer, and cervical cancer in female sex partners.^{14,40-43} Although less clear, circumcision may also be associated with reduced risk of herpes simplex-virus-2 infection.¹⁴ Risks include post-operative infection, damage to the penis,

excessive bleeding, problems with post-operative appearance of the penis, and anesthesia-related problems.^{1-3,40} If it is determined that circumcision has a role in preventing HIV transmission and other adverse health outcomes in the United States, it will be important to consider the extent to which circumcision is included in public and private medical insurance benefits. The cost, medical risks, and potential benefits of circumcision for HIV prevention will need to be considered separately for infants, high-risk heterosexuals and high-risk MSM. Relatively high rates of circumcision have prevailed in the United States, where rates of HIV infection are currently relatively low. To the extent that a high prevalence of circumcision may have hypothetically led to lower HIV rates in the United States, reducing reimbursement and declining rates of the procedure could reverse this beneficial effect.

To address these scientific and policy questions with a broad group of stakeholders, CDC plans to convene a consultation in 2007 to gain diverse input about the public health research agenda and to develop public health recommendations about the role of male circumcision for prevention of HIV in the United States.

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Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Colleagues,

In addition to the official conference events listed on the agenda we sent earlier, we will plan to gather informally at 6:00 PM on Wednesday 4/25 in the lobby of the Embassy Suites Hotel. The hotel will have

complimentary cocktails for hotel guests, and this gathering will be an opportunity to renew acquaintances and make new ones.

Thank you. We look forward to seeing you.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Assistant Secretary for Health Policy and Practice
Assistant Secretary for Health Services and Quality Improvement
Assistant Secretary for Health Equity and Community Engagement
Assistant Secretary for Health Information Systems and Informatics
Assistant Secretary for Health Law, Ethics and Regulation
Assistant Secretary for Health Policy and Practice
Assistant Secretary for Health Services and Quality Improvement
Assistant Secretary for Health Equity and Community Engagement
Assistant Secretary for Health Information Systems and Informatics
Assistant Secretary for Health Law, Ethics and Regulation

PS Apologies for the incorrect date in the last message, for those of you who received it.

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 16 Apr 2007 13:40:28 +0000
To: ilevin@westernu.edu
Cc: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org; Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US
Attachments: Circumcision Consultation Conference Registration Form.doc, MC Consultation ConferenceLogistics Letter 1.doc, MC Consultation Invitation Letter.pdf

Dr. Levin,

We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this conference as detailed in the letter.
- 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.

Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Director, Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Dermatology and STD
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Centers For Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the
United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns
April 26-27, 2007

RETURN BY: April 21, 2007 TO: Leris
Bernard
B L Seamon Corporation
4221 Forbes Boulevard, Suite 245, Lanham,
MD 20706

Registration Information Form

Please check as appropriate:

Mr. Ms. M.D. Ph.D. Other _____

Name: _____ Title: _____

Organization/Affiliation: _____

Department: _____

Address: _____

City: _____ State: _____ ZIP Code: _____

Phone: _____ Fax: _____ E-mail: _____

Assistant Name: _____ Phone: _____ E-mail: _____

Emergency Contact Name: _____ Phone: _____

PLEASE CONFIRM ATTENDANCE:

_____ YES, I will attend.

_____ NO, I will be unable to attend.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

Room Type: Single Double
 Smoking Nonsmoking Handicap No Hotel Needed

Arrival Date: _____ Departure Date: _____

Comments: _____

Your room **MUST** be guaranteed with a credit card.

Type of Card: VISA MC AMEX Other: _____ Expiration Date: _____

Name of Cardholder: _____

Credit Card #: _____

Signature

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS: Please make your travel arrangements through our travel agency, Travel-On, at (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between the hours of 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.) and reference project # **H1248**. **Please indicate your method for arranging your travel:**

_____ I will call Travel-On to arrange my travel.

_____ I will make my own travel arrangements.

_____ Other: _____

Special Requirements

*Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)*

Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

April 26–27, 2007

Atlanta, GA

FROM: Leris Bernard, Conference Planner
B L Seamon Corporation
Phone: (301) 577-0244, ext. 32
Fax: (301) 577-5261

MEETING DATES: **Thursday April 26, 2007 – 8:30 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.**
Tuesday March 27, 2007 – 9:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m.

MEETING AND LODGING SITE: **Embassy Suites Hotel**
Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park
267 Marietta Street
Atlanta, GA 30313
Phone: (404) 223-2300
Fax: (404) 223-0925

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns, sponsored by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). B L Seamon Corporation (BLS), under contract to DHHS, is providing administrative and logistical support for the meeting. Please take a few minutes to review the information below.

REGISTRATION

Please confirm your intent to attend the meeting by filling out the enclosed Registration Form. This form will also be used to reserve your hotel room. If you do not plan to attend, please let us know by returning the registration form.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

A guestroom has been reserved in your name at the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for your arrival on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007. Your confirmation number will be provided under separate cover. **Do not call the hotel directly.**

BLS will cover the cost of your guestroom for a maximum of 2 (two) nights. You will be responsible for settling all incidental charges and additional nights before checking out of the hotel. If you need to cancel your reservation, please do so 72 hours before your scheduled arrival date to avoid a direct credit card charge of 1 night's lodging. If you cancel your reservation, be sure to obtain a cancellation number from the reservationist for your records.

Your reservation must be guaranteed with a major credit card submitted on the attached Registration Information Form. Although the cost of your accommodations will be covered, a major credit card is required to guarantee your room reservation. Your card will be charged if you do not attend the meeting and do not cancel your room reservation by 3:00 p.m., 24 hours prior to the day of arrival. Please provide this information on the attached Travel and Hotel Information Form.

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS

CDC will sponsor travel and lodging support for you to attend the meeting. Please make your travel arrangements as soon as possible through our travel agency, Travel-On, 9000 Virginia Manor Road, Suite 201, Beltsville, MD. Call 1 (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.) and **reference the meeting name and project code #H1248.** Your travel authorization will cover the most economical, round-trip, coach fare between the city listed in your address and the meeting site for arrival in Atlanta, GA, on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007 (unless otherwise authorized).

Federal Travel Regulations require BLS to purchase the most economical airfare for sponsored participants. In most cases, a nonrefundable ticket will be purchased for you. Therefore, it is important that you carefully consider your schedule when requesting travel reservations.

In addition, if you need to fly from an airport other than the one serving your city, notify BLS as soon as possible. Use of an alternate airport requires special authorization if it increases the cost of your ticket, and approval for a rental car must be obtained **prior to the meeting.** If a rental car is approved, reimbursement may be restricted to the cost of a round-trip taxi from the airport.

After your travel arrangements are confirmed, Travel-On will forward a copy of your itinerary to you for approval (most often via e-mail). Upon receipt, please review, approve, and return to Travel-On. Upon receipt of your approved itinerary, a prepaid ticket will be issued.

Ticketing

An electronic ticket (e-ticket) will be issued unless you request a printed ticket. However, please note that in some cases printed tickets cannot be issued. Please discuss your preference with the travel agent, and he/she will advise you of available ticketing methods.

If you request a printed ticket and it is an available option, please confirm your mailing address when speaking with the travel agent. Your ticket will be sent to you via express mail within a few days after confirming your arrangements.

If an e-ticket is issued, please note that your itinerary should be used as confirmation of your arrangements. Upon arrival at the airport, please present your itinerary and photo identification. After you check in, the airline will provide you with a printed boarding pass for your reserved seat.

Making Your Own Travel Arrangements

If you would like to make (or have already made) your own travel arrangements, please check the appropriate box on the attached Travel and Hotel Information Form. **You will be reimbursed for the cost of your ticket if you use an American carrier, reserve coach-class seating, and have your ticket cost approved by BLS *BEFORE* you purchase your ticket.** Submit your travel receipts for reimbursement after the meeting.

Travel by Automobile

If you are traveling by automobile, you will be reimbursed 48.5¢ per mile, not to exceed the cost of air travel. The Federal Government does not authorize BLS to reimburse you for lodging or meals between your departure city and the meeting site or for mileage not related to attending the meeting.

Ground Transportation

From Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport, participants may use the MARTA, Atlanta's subway system to travel to the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for \$1.75 each way. Take any northbound train to Five Points Station. Transfer to the Westbound train. Go one stop to W1/Omni/Dome/GWCC Station. Take the small escalator to the big escalator. Turn left and go to Philips Drive. Turn right and go to International Blvd. Turn right and go to Marietta Street. Embassy Suites Hotel is one block on the left. (Approximately a 5-minute walk from the train station)

In addition, participants can utilize the Atlanta Link, a traditional van service that offers round-trip airport transfer for \$28.00 per person. The *DOWNTOWN* Shuttle is preferred because it handles downtown properties only. Advance reservations can be secured by calling 1 (866) 545-9633.

A taxicab from the Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport should run \$24.00 one way plus \$2 for each additional passenger.

REIMBURSEMENT OF EXPENSES

BLS will reimburse you for ground transportation as well as meals and incidental expenses (M&IE) after the meeting. Ground transportation expense reimbursement covers taxis to/from your home, the airports, and the hotel, as well as parking and tolls. Mileage is reimbursed at 48.5¢ per mile for the use of your personally owned vehicle. The M&IE reimbursement covers meals, tips, telephone calls, and other miscellaneous expenses and is applicable to the geographical location of the site visit. The M&IE allowance for Atlanta, GA is \$49.00 per full day. You will receive three-fourths of the M&IE allowance or \$36.75 for each travel day on

April 25 and April 27.

To claim your expenses following the conference, please submit the Travel Reimbursement Form by May 11, 2007. You will receive this form at the meeting. When submitting your expenses, attach all applicable receipts including your travel ticket stub. All receipts and your travel ticket stub must be submitted in original form. Receipts are not required for meal expenses.

QUESTIONS

Please contact Leris Bernard at lbernard@blscamon.com or (301) 577-0244, ext. 32, if you have questions regarding logistics or if your attendance plans should change.

Questions concerning program content should be directed to Dr. Allan Taylor at (404) 639-6120 e-mail: avt0@cdc.gov.

April 12, 2007

Dear Colleague,

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

Meeting Objectives

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

Space will be available for presentation of posters if participants have data or activities they wish to share. Please contact us in advance if you plan to prepare a poster so that we may ensure adequate space.

CDC will cover the cost of your travel and lodging and will provide a per diem of \$49 per full day for meals and incidentals. The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. The Embassy Suites Hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313, Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925. We have reserved a block of rooms for our participants at the US Government rate. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation. Please contact Allan Taylor, MD, MPH at ataylor2@cdc.gov or at (404) 639-6120 if you have any questions or comments. We are looking forward to your participation and to a productive consultation.

Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 01:26:27 +0000
To: Carn, Rudolph (CDC aol.com)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Bcc: 'melanie.bacon@nih.hhs.gov'; 'sblank@health.nyc.gov';
'Ciesielski_Carol@cdph.org'; 'carl.dieffenbach@nih.hhs.gov'; 'aforsyth@mail.nih.gov'; 'Fuchs-MontgomeryNR@state.gov'; (b)(6); Ryan, Caroline (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP);
'jschilli@health.nyc.gov'; Stanton, David (CDC usaid.gov); 'Ronald.Valdiserri@va.gov'; Wolff,
Tracy (AHRO); (b)(6); 'alonsomon@paho.org';
(b)(6); 'j.gayle@fordfound.org'; 'jsanchez@inmensa.org'; 'Anjie
Emanuel'; 'Council, Lisa (NIH/NIAID) [C]'
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
Attachments: MC Consultation Invitation Letter 2.pdf, CDC Fact Sheet.pdf,
Circumcision_commentary_for consultation.pdf, Sawires Coates Report 2006 opp and
challenges.pdf, MC Consultation Agenda Final.pdf

Mr. Carn,

We would like to extend our formal invitation to the upcoming **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

1. An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
2. Consultation Agenda
3. CDC Factsheet on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
4. Two overview papers that review many of the issues to be discussed at the consultation

In addition to the official conference events listed on the agenda we sent earlier, we will plan to gather informally at 6:00 PM on Wednesday 4/25 in the lobby of the Embassy Suites Hotel. The hotel will have complimentary cocktails for hotel guests, and this gathering will be an opportunity to renew acquaintances and make new ones.

Please do not hesitate to contact me at any time if questions should arise. We look forward to a productive meeting.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP

Director, Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Dermatology and STD
Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, NE
Atlanta, GA 30333
Phone: 404/616-1400
Fax: 404/616-1400
E-mail: ataylor@cdc.gov

April 12, 2007

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CDC is unable to provide for your travel expenses; however we have reserved a block of rooms at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park for our participants at the US Government rate of USD\$124/night. The hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313. Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925). The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter.

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Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

CDC HIV/AIDS Science Facts:

Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States

March 2007

This fact sheet summarizes information in four areas of male circumcision: 1) male circumcision and risk of HIV transmission; 2) male circumcision and other health conditions; 3) risks associated with male circumcision; and 4) status of HIV infection and male circumcision in the United States.

What is Male Circumcision?

Male circumcision is the surgical removal of some or all of the foreskin (or prepuce) from the penis [2].

Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission

Biologic Plausibility

Compared to the dry external skin surface, the inner mucosa of the foreskin has less keratinization (deposition of fibrous protein), a higher density of target cells for HIV infection (Langerhans cells), and is more susceptible to HIV infection in laboratory studies [3]. It has also been argued that the foreskin may have greater susceptibility to traumatic epithelial disruptions (tears) during intercourse, providing a portal of entry for pathogens including HIV [4]. In addition, the micro-environment in the preputial sac between the unretracted foreskin and the glans penis may be conducive to viral survival [2]. Finally, the higher rates of sexually transmitted genital ulcerative disease, such as syphilis,

observed in uncircumcised men may also increase susceptibility to HIV infection [5].

International Observational Studies

Multiple cross-sectional, prospective, and ecologic (population-level) studies have identified lack of male circumcision as a risk factor for HIV infection.

A systematic review and meta-analysis that focused on heterosexual transmission of HIV in Africa was published in 2000 [6]. It included 19 cross-sectional studies, five case-control studies, three cohort studies, and one partner study. A substantial protective effect of male circumcision on risk for HIV infection was noted, along with a reduced risk for genital ulcer disease. After adjusting for confounding factors in the population-based studies, the relative risk for HIV infection was 44% lower in circumcised men. The strongest association was seen in high-risk men, such as patients at sexually transmitted disease (STD) clinics, for whom the adjusted relative risk was 71% lower for circumcised men.

A review that included stringent assessment of 10 potential confounding factors and was stratified by study type or study population was published in 2004 [7]. Most of the studies were from Africa. Of the 35 observational studies included in the review, the 16 in the general population had inconsistent results. The one large prospective cohort study in this group showed a significant protective effect, with the odds of infection being

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In English, en Español
24 Hours/Day
cdcinfo@cdc.gov
<http://www.cdc.gov/hiv>

42% lower in circumcised men [8]. The remaining nineteen studies were conducted in high-risk populations. These found a consistent, substantial protective effect, which increased with adjustment for confounding. Four of these were cohort studies: all demonstrated a protective effect, with two being statistically significant.

Ecologic studies also indicate a strong association between lack of male circumcision and HIV infection at the population level. Although links between circumcision, culture, religion, and risk behavior may account for some of the differences in HIV infection prevalence, the countries in Africa and Asia with prevalence of male circumcision of less than 20% have HIV-infection prevalences several times higher than countries in those regions where more than 80% of men are circumcised [9].

International Clinical Trials

Three randomized, controlled clinical trials have been undertaken in Africa to determine whether circumcision of adult males will reduce their risk for HIV infection. The study conducted in South Africa [10], was stopped in 2005 and those in Kenya [11] and Uganda [12] were stopped in 2006 after their interim analyses found that medical circumcision reduced male participants' risk of HIV infection.

In these studies, men who had been randomly assigned to the circumcision group had a 60% (South Africa), 53% (Kenya), and 51% (Uganda) lower incidence of HIV infection compared to men assigned to the wait list group to be circumcised at the end of the study. In all three studies, a few men who had been assigned to be circumcised did not undergo the procedure, and vice versa. When the data were reanalyzed to account for these deviations, men who had been circumcised had a 76% (South Africa), 60% (Kenya), and 55% (Uganda) reduction in risk of HIV infection compared to those who were not circumcised. The Uganda study investigators are also examining the following in an ongoing study: 1) safety and

acceptability of male circumcision in HIV-infected men and men of unknown HIV-infection status, 2) safety and acceptability of male circumcision in the men's female sex partners, and 3) effect of male circumcision on male-to-female transmission of HIV and other STDs.

Male Circumcision and Male-to-Female Transmission of HIV

In an earlier study of couples in Uganda in which the male partner was HIV infected and the female partner was initially HIV seronegative, the infection rates of the female partners differed by the circumcision status and viral load of the male partners. If the male blood HIV viral load was <50,000 copies/mL, there was no HIV transmission if the man was circumcised, compared to a rate of 9.6 per 100 person-years if the man was uncircumcised [8]. If viral load was not controlled for, there was a non-statistically significant trend towards a reduction in the male-to-female transmission rate from circumcised men compared to uncircumcised men. Such an effect may be due to decreased viral shedding from circumcised men or to a reduction in ulcerative sexually transmitted infections acquired by female partners of circumcised men [14].

Male Circumcision and Other Health Conditions

Lack of male circumcision has also been associated with sexually transmitted genital ulcer disease, infant urinary tract infections, penile cancer, and cervical cancer in female partners of uncircumcised men [2]. The latter two conditions are related to human papillomavirus (HPV) infection. Transmission of this virus is also associated with lack of male circumcision. A recent meta-analysis included 26 studies that assessed the association between male circumcision and risk of genital ulcer disease. The analysis concluded that there was a significantly lower risk of syphilis and chancroid among circumcised men, while the reduced risk of herpes simplex virus-2 infection had a borderline statistical significance [5].

Risks Associated with Male Circumcision

Reported complication rates depend on the type of study (e.g., chart review vs. prospective study), setting (medical vs. nonmedical facility), person operating (traditional vs. medical practitioner), patient age (infant vs. adult), and surgical technique or instrument used. The most common complications are minor bleeding and local infection. In large studies of infant circumcision in the U.S., complications rates range from 0.2 to 2.0% [2]. In the recently completed South African study of adult circumcision by general medical practitioners in their surgical offices, the overall complication rate was 3.8%. The most commonly reported complications were pain (0.8%), followed by swelling or hematoma, bleeding, and problems with appearance (each 0.6%). Damage to the penis (0.3%), infection (0.2%), and delayed wound healing (0.1%) were uncommon. There were no reported deaths or problems with urination [10].

HIV Infection and Male Circumcision in the United States

In 2004, men who have sex with men (MSM) (47%) and persons exposed through heterosexual contact (33%) accounted for an estimated 80% of all HIV/AIDS cases diagnosed in areas in the U.S. with confidential name-based reporting. Blacks accounted for 49% of cases and Hispanics for 18%. Infection rates in both groups were several-fold higher than that in whites. An overall prevalence of about less than 0.5% was estimated for the general population [15]. Although data on HIV infection rates are available since the beginning of the epidemic, data on circumcision and risk for HIV infection in the U.S. are limited. In one cross-sectional survey of MSM, lack of circumcision was associated with a two-fold increased odds of prevalent HIV infection [16]. In another, prospective study of MSM, lack of circumcision was also associated with a

two-fold increased risk for HIV seroconversion [17]. In both studies, the results were statistically significant and controlled statistically for other possible risk factors. In one prospective study of heterosexual men attending an urban STD clinic, when controlling for other risk factors, uncircumcised men had a 3.5-fold higher risk of HIV infection than men who were circumcised. However, this association was not statistically significant [18].

Status of Male Circumcision in the United States

In a national probability sample of adults in 1992, the National Health and Social Life Survey found that 77% of men reported being circumcised including 81% of white men, 65% of black men, and 54% of Hispanic men [19]. It is important to note that reported circumcision status may be subject to misclassification. In a study of adolescents, only 69% of circumcised and 65% of uncircumcised young men correctly identified their circumcision status as verified by physical exam [20].

According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999 and the overall proportion of newborns circumcised was stable from 1979 to 1999 [21]. Notably, the proportion of black newborns circumcised rose over this reporting period (58% to 64%), while the proportion of white infants circumcised remained stable (66%). In addition, the proportion of newborns who were circumcised in the Midwest increased over the 20-year period from 74% in 1979 to 81% in 1999, while the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased from 64% in 1979 to 37% in 1999. In another survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), circumcision rates increased from 48% during 1988-1991 to 61% during 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black [22].

In 1999, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) changed from routinely recommending circumcision to a neutral stance on circumcision, noting that: "It is legitimate for the parents to take into account cultural, religious, and ethnic traditions, in addition to medical factors, when making this choice." [23] This position was re-affirmed by the Academy in 2005. This change in policy may influence reimbursement for and practice of neonatal circumcision. In a 1995 review, 61% of circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant [24]. Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary [25].

Considerations for the United States

There are a number of important differences that must be considered in the possible role of male circumcision in HIV prevention in the U.S. Notably, the overall risk of HIV infection is considerably lower in the United States, changing risk-benefit and cost-effectiveness considerations. Also, studies to date have focused on heterosexual, penile-vaginal sex, the predominant mode of HIV transmission in Africa, while the predominant mode of sexual HIV transmission in the United States is by penile-anal sex among MSM. In addition, while the prevalence of circumcision may be somewhat lower in racial and ethnic groups with higher rates of HIV infection, most Americans are already circumcised, and it is not known if men at higher risk for HIV infection would be willing to be circumcised, nor if parents would be willing to have their infants circumcised to reduce possible future HIV infection risk. Lastly, whether the effect of male circumcision differs by HIV-1 subtype, predominately subtype B in the U.S. and subtypes A, C, and D in Africa, is also unknown.

Summary

Male circumcision has been associated with a lower risk for HIV infection in international observational studies and in three randomized, controlled clinical trials. Male circumcision could also reduce male-to-female transmission of HIV to a lesser extent. It has also been associated with a number of other health benefits. While there are risks to male circumcision, serious complications are rare. Accordingly, male circumcision, together with other prevention interventions, may play an important role in HIV prevention in settings similar to the clinical trials.

Male circumcision may also have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. With the results of three clinical trials showing that male circumcision decreases the risk for HIV infection, CDC is undertaking additional research and consultation to evaluate the potential value, risks, and feasibility of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention in the U.S.

As CDC proceeds with the development of public health recommendations for the U.S., individual men may wish to consider circumcision as an additional HIV prevention measure, but must recognize that circumcision 1) does carry risks and costs that must be considered in addition to potential benefits; 2) has only proven effective in reducing the risk of infection through insertive vaginal sex; and 3) confers only partial protection and should be considered only in conjunction with other proven prevention measures (abstinence, mutual monogamy, reducing number of sex partners, and correct and consistent condom use).

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**Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV Transmission: What the New Data Mean
for HIV Prevention in the United States**

Patrick S Sullivan, Peter H. Kilmarx, Thomas A. Peterman, Allan W. Taylor, Allyn K.
Nakashima, Mary L. Kamb, Lee Warner, Timothy D. Mastro

Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (Sullivan, Kilmarx, Nakashima, Taylor, Mastro),
Division of STD Prevention (Peterman, Kamb), and Division of Reproductive Health
(Warner), Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta Georgia.

Required Disclaimer: The findings and conclusions in this commentary are those of the
authors, and do not necessarily represent the views of the Centers for Disease Control and
Prevention.

Word Count: 2969

Three randomized, controlled clinical trials in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda were recently unblinded early because interim analyses concluded that circumcision of HIV-negative adult males reduced their risk for acquiring HIV infection through penile-vaginal sex.¹⁻³ In each trial, men who had been randomly assigned to an intervention group receiving circumcision had a lower incidence of HIV infection in up to 2 years of follow-up, compared to men who were assigned to a control group not receiving circumcision. The estimated reduction in the risk of HIV infection ranged from 51% to 60%; per-protocol estimates of risk reduction ranged from 55% to 76%.

It is now clear that male circumcision can be efficacious for men in reducing their risk of HIV acquisition through sex with women.⁴ Some experts predict that the impact of male circumcision as a biomedical intervention for HIV prevention in Africa may be large^{5,6}, and preparatory work for male circumcision programs in Africa has been taking place. The implications of African trials of circumcision for HIV prevention programs in the United States are less clear – despite interest of the popular press in the idea.⁷ Here, we consider the differences between the HIV epidemics in Africa and the United States, the current status of male circumcision in the United States, and the knowledge gaps in the United States that will need to be addressed as we consider whether male circumcision should be evaluated or implemented as a biomedical intervention to reduce sexually acquired HIV infection domestically.

Epidemiologic Differences

The results of any trial must be interpreted with the caution that inference not be extended to populations differing from the study participants in important ways. The

HIV epidemics in Africa are substantially different from the US epidemic. In many areas of Africa, generalized HIV epidemics exist, and the population prevalence of HIV among adult Kenyans, Ugandans and South Africans ranges from 6-19%.⁸ The predominant mode of HIV transmission in Africa is through male-female sex. In contrast, the United States has a concentrated epidemic, with most sexual transmission occurring among men who have sex with men (MSM). The general population prevalence of HIV is about 0.4%⁹, and only 17% of men diagnosed with HIV infection during 2005 were reported to have acquired HIV through male-female sex.¹⁰

Biologic Plausibility of Circumcision to Prevent HIV Acquisition

The association between circumcision and reduced risk for HIV acquisition is biologically plausible: the foreskin contains high concentrations of superficial Langerhans cells, CD4+ T cells, and macrophages¹¹ – target cells for HIV infection – some of which may also be close to the skin surface^{12,13}; the preputial sac may serve as a reservoir for HIV-containing secretions, resulting in prolonged contact time after exposure to secretions; and the foreskin may present less of a physical barrier to HIV entry because of lower keratinization¹² and, potentially, more frequent epithelial disruption. There are also potential indirect mechanisms of association of lack of circumcision and HIV risk; for example, lack of circumcision is associated with increased risk of genital ulcer diseases, which are associated with increased risk of HIV transmission and acquisition.¹⁴

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Vaginal-Penile Sex

Epidemic differences are important because, on a population basis, the impact of circumcision as an intervention to prevent HIV infection among men who have sex with

women will depend on the likelihood of exposure to HIV among US men who have sex with women – and, therefore, on the prevalence of HIV among their female sex partners. A recent analysis of data from sexually transmitted disease clinics in Baltimore evaluated the association of male circumcision and risk of prevalent HIV infection in two ways – first, among all male attendees at the clinics, and second, restricting the analysis to males who were known to have been exposed to HIV heterosexually (e.g., sexual contacts to partners known to be infected with HIV).¹⁵ The results indicated that, while circumcision was not associated with prevalent HIV infection in the whole population of male STD clinic attendees where HIV prevalence was 3%, circumcision was associated with significantly lower HIV prevalence among men with a known infected female sex partner -- where the prevalence of infection was markedly higher at 12% (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 0.46; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.22-0.97). In effect, this analysis illustrated the impact of partner prevalence of HIV on the association of circumcision and HIV infection status and concluded that it was difficult to detect a protective effect from circumcision on HIV infection in the setting of a partner pool with lower HIV prevalence.

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Male-Male Sex

Most sexual transmission of HIV in the United States is by male-male sex¹⁰, and most transmission by male-male sex is to the *receptive* partner in penile-anal intercourse.¹⁶ The fact that the results from the African trials that circumcision was protective for men who were the *insertive* partner in vaginal intercourse suggests that the utility of male circumcision in prevention of HIV transmission among MSM may be limited. Because reducing the concentration of target cells for HIV infection on the penis is a proposed protective mechanism, understanding the relative viral challenge presented

by vaginal versus anal-rectal secretions is relevant to evaluating the plausibility of a protective effect of circumcision for the insertive male partner during anal intercourse. The concentration of HIV-RNA in rectal secretions may be higher than in blood or semen, regardless of use of antiretroviral therapy¹⁷, and may be orders of magnitude higher than the concentrations in vaginal or cervical secretions.^{17,18} Circumcision may change the balance of virus and target cells, but if rectal mucosal secretions contain a higher concentration of infectious virus than vaginal secretions, any potential protective effect of circumcision for the insertive partner may be overwhelmed by excess virus. Also, new data suggest that, for limited periods of time before wound healing is complete, female sex partners of newly circumcised men may be at increased risk of acquiring HIV.⁴ Possible transient increased risk of transmission (before complete wound healing) from recently circumcised MSM to their receptive anal intercourse partners is also of concern.

Few studies provide evidence as to whether circumcision may protect against HIV infection among MSM. In a vaccine-preparedness cohort of MSM followed from 1995 to 1997, circumcision was significantly associated with a decreased risk for HIV seroconversion (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.3-0.9), controlling for number of male sex partners and unprotected sex with an HIV-positive partner.¹⁹ In a cross-sectional survey of gay men in the early 1990s, circumcision was associated with decreased odds of prevalent HIV infection (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.25-1.0).²⁰ While falling short of the quality of data from a randomized intervention trial, these limited data suggest that circumcised MSM in the United States may have decreased risk of HIV infection. However, it is possible that the noted associations in these two observational studies may have been related to

uncontrolled bias. A small cross-sectional study of Australian MSM found no association of circumcision status and risk of HIV infection, when stratifying by insertive and receptive roles.²¹

Virologic Issues

In the African countries where circumcision has been demonstrated to be efficacious, the predominant HIV subtypes are A, C, and D; it is likely that some recombinant strains were also represented in the Kenya and Uganda trials. In the United States, subtype B predominates. Despite the theoretical possibility that subtype differences in either vaginal shedding of HIV or affinity to HIV receptors (especially those natively expressed on the foreskin) could modify the effectiveness of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention, the consistent findings of the African trials argue that this is unlikely. For example, despite differences in vaginal shedding between subtype C and subtypes A and D¹⁸, the efficacy of circumcision in trials where subtypes A, C, or D were prevalent was comparable. One potentially relevant biological difference relates to binding avidity of HIV subtypes for CCR5 receptors, which are important mechanisms for entry into Langerhans cells, and present in high concentrations in the foreskin.¹¹ Subtype C is reported to have lower binding avidity than subtype B for CCR5 receptors²²; it is unclear whether the greater binding avidity of subtype B for CCR5 could represent an escape mechanism to overcome the decreased availability of target cells that results from circumcision.

Status of Circumcision in the United States

Public health recommendations will likely have the largest impact in populations where circumcision has been rare. Non-religious male circumcision was introduced to

the United States in the late 1800s²³, and by the 1940s, an increasing proportion of male children in the United States were born in hospitals, and were circumcised.²⁴ The proportion of newborns that were circumcised annually reached 80% after World War II and peaked in the mid-1960s. The proportion of male babies circumcised subsequently decreased. According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), which documents circumcisions performed in hospitals but would not ascertain circumcisions performed outside of the hospital for religious reasons, 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999. Although the overall proportion of newborns circumcised has been stable from 1979 to 1999²⁵, the proportion of black newborns who were circumcised rose over the period to approximately 65%. Significant discrepancies also exist by region. While the proportion of newborns born in the Midwest who were circumcised increased over the 20-year period to 81% in 1999, the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased over the same period, to 37% in 1999.²⁵

Data from another hospital discharge survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), present a slightly different picture.²⁶ In that survey, newborn circumcision rates increased from 48% in 1988-1991, to 61% in 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black.²⁶

Data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES) from 1999 to 2004 indicated that the overall prevalence of circumcision among adult males in the United States was 79% and varied by race/ethnicity (88% in non-Hispanic whites, 73% in non-Hispanic blacks, 42% in Mexican Americans, and 50% in others). The prevalence of circumcision decreased among US-born men from the 1970s to the

1980s.²⁷ Although causality cannot be implied by these data and many other factors are likely operative, the rates of HIV and AIDS among non-Hispanic blacks and Hispanic men are considerably higher than in non-Hispanic whites in the United States.²⁸

Willingness of adult males to be circumcised

The ability of investigators to fully enroll three trials of adult circumcision¹⁻³ in Africa speaks to the acceptability of circumcision among adult males in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda. A recent systematic review of published literature suggests that adult male circumcision may be acceptable as an HIV prevention intervention in many countries in sub-Saharan Africa.²⁹ In the United States, the overwhelming majority of circumcisions are performed on newborns; adult circumcisions are commonly only done for medical reasons, such as preputial cancer or phimosis. It is not clear whether adult circumcision, were it to be recommended in the United States, would be acceptable as a prevention intervention. Preliminary evidence from interviews with uncircumcised men surveyed at Gay Pride festivals in the United States suggests that the majority of men would consider circumcision as an adult, if circumcision were shown to reduce risk of HIV infection by male-male sex³⁰ – although respondents were not told in the survey that protection would be partial, and condom use would still be recommended after circumcision.

Policy Issues Related to Circumcision of Newborn Boys

In 1999, the American Academy of Pediatrics changed from routinely recommending circumcision (primarily based on benefits with respect to risk for urinary tract infections and sexually transmitted infections) to a neutral stance on circumcision³¹; this position was re-affirmed in 2005 by the Academy after publication of the results of

the South Africa trial.³² In a 1995 US review, 61% of infant circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant.³³ Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary.³⁴

Should Adult Male Circumcision be Recommended for HIV Prevention in the United States?

Circumcision may have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. However, because of the many differences in the underlying HIV epidemics between Africa and the United States, differences in the prevalence of male circumcision in Africa and the United States, and the considerable gaps in knowledge that exist regarding the potential impact of circumcision on HIV transmission by male-male sex, the extent of this role on a population basis is unknown. Further, the already high prevalence of circumcision among US men suggests some limitations in the potential impact of circumcision at a population level.

Based on the data from the three African clinical trials, it is likely that circumcision will decrease the probability of a man acquiring HIV via penile-vaginal sex with an HIV-infected woman in the United States. Until public health recommendations are available for the United States, some sexually active men may consider circumcision as an additional HIV-prevention measure, but should do so only in consultation with their physician or health care provider, and with a clear understanding of the costs and risks of circumcision and the need to continue use of other, proven prevention measures (e.g., reducing the numbers of sex partners and consistent and correct condom use). Men who

choose to be circumcised should also be counseled about the importance of refraining from sexual intercourse following circumcision, until wound healing is complete.⁴

To consider the possible impact of public health recommendations for male circumcision, we must also take into account HIV incidence in high-risk groups, as well as adoption of other protective behaviors, such as condom use. For example, HIV incidence among US MSM recruited in community- and venue-based samples was, on average, about 1.9% annually,³⁵ and 36% of MSM in the US National HIV Behavioral Surveillance System reported having unprotected anal sex with a casual partner in the 12 months before interview.³⁶ There are few data on HIV incidence among high-risk heterosexuals in the United States, but there are limited data on condom use: in 2002, 16% of high-risk heterosexual men and 24% of high-risk heterosexual women never used condoms during penile-vaginal sex with a non-primary partner.³⁷ Currently available data on disparities in rates of prevalent HIV infection and AIDS^{28,38} and the prevalence of circumcision among US men²⁷ suggest that Black and Hispanic men may have particular opportunities for reduction of risk of HIV acquisition through circumcision.

Future research and consultation

In order to understand the potential for male circumcision as an HIV-prevention approach in the United States, we believe that there are important questions that should be answered. These include questions that can be answered by basic science, by modeling, by surveys of acceptability, by considering ethical issues, and, perhaps, by clinical trials in the United States. For example, it is important to understand more fully the differences in shedding of HIV by rectal versus vaginal mucosa. Modeling may provide important information on (1) the impact on the US epidemic from increasing

male circumcision rates, and (2) the cost-benefit of circumcision among newborns, or among adult men with high risk of exposure to HIV through sex. Cost benefit models may be limited by lack of definitive transmission parameters in US populations and should therefore be conducted with appropriate sensitivity analyses. Surveys may increase our understanding of the acceptability of adult male circumcision among groups of uncircumcised adult males in the United States for whom circumcision might be recommended (e.g., men at high risk of acquiring HIV heterosexually and who do not use condoms consistently, and high-risk MSM), and of barriers and facilitators to acceptance of adult male circumcision, were it recommended as an HIV-prevention strategy. In light of recent trial results and international consensus that male circumcision is efficacious, ethical questions about whether equipoise exists for a US MSM trial, and about how to implement trials or programs of male circumcision in light of complex cultural and religious views about circumcision are important to consider.³⁹ Evaluating data from basic science, modeling, and acceptability surveys and addressing ethics questions will be important in deciding whether a clinical trial to determine the efficacy of male circumcision among MSM may be feasible and appropriate in the United States.

Further, recommendations about circumcision in newborns or high-risk adults for the prevention of HIV infection cannot be made without a more comprehensive discussion of other, documented prevention benefits and risks of circumcision. Benefits include reduction in acquisition of sexually transmitted genital ulcer disease, infant urinary tract infections, penile cancer, and cervical cancer in female sex partners.^{14,40-43} Although less clear, circumcision may also be associated with reduced risk of herpes simplex-virus-2 infection.¹⁴ Risks include post-operative infection, damage to the penis,

excessive bleeding, problems with post-operative appearance of the penis, and anesthesia-related problems.^{1-3,40} If it is determined that circumcision has a role in preventing HIV transmission and other adverse health outcomes in the United States, it will be important to consider the extent to which circumcision is included in public and private medical insurance benefits. The cost, medical risks, and potential benefits of circumcision for HIV prevention will need to be considered separately for infants, high-risk heterosexuals and high-risk MSM. Relatively high rates of circumcision have prevailed in the United States, where rates of HIV infection are currently relatively low. To the extent that a high prevalence of circumcision may have hypothetically led to lower HIV rates in the United States, reducing reimbursement and declining rates of the procedure could reverse this beneficial effect.

To address these scientific and policy questions with a broad group of stakeholders, CDC plans to convene a consultation in 2007 to gain diverse input about the public health research agenda and to develop public health recommendations about the role of male circumcision for prevention of HIV in the United States.

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***Male Circumcision and HIV/AIDS:
Opportunities and Challenges***

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Preface

This review was commissioned by the Ford Foundation in order to deepen our understanding of the current research on the interfaces between male circumcision and HIV/AIDS. The experience of our grantees in working in the community development, sexuality, sexual health, and human rights fields tells us that many factors would have to be considered before making a decision to implement male circumcision as an HIV/AIDS prevention mechanism. It would need to take into account questions of personal autonomy, bodily integrity, and human rights; of social and cultural dynamics in specific contexts; and of health system capacity to deliver integrated HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment interventions to the majority of the population.

We wanted to understand what the new research tells us about these broader contextual factors, and what kinds of issues would need further exploration in order to ensure that any new preventive intervention would only be implemented after a thorough consideration of the individual, social, and health system implications, as well as the likelihood of success outside of a research environment.

This review aimed to provide us with such information. Since there are many others in the field who are asking similar questions, we asked the authors to make it available to the public as a contribution towards constructive dialogue on the options.

Barbara Klugman and Jacob Gayle,
Ford Foundation

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes available information on male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy, and the policy and prevention implications of its implementation. To this end, the report examines:

1. Summary of HIV prevention science and practice;
2. A review of the currently available data from observational studies and randomized controlled clinical trials;
3. Adult male circumcision, other health benefits, and the implications for women's health;
4. Biological mechanism responsible for reduced susceptibility to HIV infection and other medical benefits among circumcised males;
5. Medical professional group policy statements pertaining to male circumcision;
6. Challenges related to male circumcision;
7. Research priorities;
8. Ethical concerns; and
9. Potential next steps.

While the results of the recently stopped clinical trials demonstrating the protective effect of male circumcision on HIV infection are extremely promising and can have enormous impact on the HIV epidemic, there are numerous implementation challenges, contextual considerations, and ethical concerns that require rigorous attention.

We identify here 15 such challenges, and the list can probably be expanded. Nonetheless, we present these to encourage discussion, and to ensure that these issues are considered as new medical findings are released and implementation plans are drawn up. Furthermore, we hope that these challenges will enrich and add nuance to the discussions as to how male circumcision should be offered as an HIV prevention intervention, and what steps need to be taken to ensure it is implemented in an ethical and effective manner.

We highlight the following:

1. **Acceptability:** Price, pain, and lack of complications seem to be universal concerns and need to be attended to in rollout of male circumcision. Rollout programs will consider these and other issues as plans for scale-up and implementation are considered.
2. **Level of protection:** The benefit from male circumcision is relative, not absolute, and communications strategies will need to be devised to reinforce this point clearly. Further, any rollout must take into account the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. Ideally, discussions of these issues will reinforce the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques will receive a needed boost in attention and funding.
3. **Risk** is typically defined in terms of medical risk; how can conceptions of risk be expanded to include social, psychological, cultural, or sexual factors? Acceptability on a population level, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.
4. **Interventions** using male circumcision (as with other technologies) absolutely require behavior modification and educational components. It will be essential to place male circumcision within a broad prevention context in order to avoid many of the difficulties that may be associated with it. Ideally, the introduction of male circumcision will be used as impetus to gain support for the

wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies. Male circumcision may help to focus attention on *combination prevention* and the need to use multiple prevention strategies in concert.

5. It will be essential to maintain funding for broader commitments in the fight against HIV, especially with regard to fighting gender inequity, stigma, and other issues related to disease spread. The implications of MC can be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.
6. Benefit to women: How can male circumcision benefit women? How can male circumcision not harm women?
7. Religious and cultural practices need to be taken into account. Actual risk reduction, versus that of reduction rates achieved in controlled trials, is likely to have more regional variance and is dependent on local behaviors surrounding sexual practices, local drivers of the epidemic, and current prevalence rates.
8. The questions of when to circumcise—in infancy or adulthood—are hotly debated and will continue for some time. It may be easiest in infancy, but infants will not benefit immediately and cannot make informed choices.
9. Male circumcision and female genital mutilation (FGM): Opportunity to further distinguish the two? This raises at least two questions: a) whether promoting MC will in any way undermine current efforts to eliminate FGM, and b) how to understand the social and cultural discourses about the penis, about sexuality, and about sexual maturation that may all be affected, and potentially have positive or negative impacts on, an ostensibly neutral public health intervention.
10. Assessment and surveillance of safety and complications is essential to ensure that circumcisions are performed safely, that training is adequate, and that oversight is in place.
11. The challenges to health systems are enormous. The fact that health systems in many countries with high or growing HIV incidence are very poor and can not cope with the systemic or human resource requirements of an MC program without major additional short- and long-term investments. The estimated costs per circumcision could be significant when considering a developing country's per person health budget. The global experience with prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV (PMTCT) has already demonstrated the inability of global health systems to deliver on the promise of technical advances.
12. Male circumcision also needs to be considered and evaluated in a broader context of sexual and reproductive health, beyond the constraints of HIV alone.
13. Some have asserted that the trials and the calls for widespread implementation are being fueled by a form of racism. These issues need to be addressed seriously and included in the discussion.
14. It will be essential to determine how to avoid stigma associated with male circumcision or the lack of it.
15. It will also be essential to carry on the discussion around male circumcision to deliberately avoid branding men as perpetrators of infection.

We highlight the following research priorities:

1. What is the effect of male circumcision on female partners—not just related to HIV, but also sexually transmitted infections (STIs), cervical cancer, female pleasure, and female perceptions of sexual viability of the male partner?
2. There are often few ethical guidelines on the social and behavioral effects of biomedical trials—only medical effects and adverse events are examined. Social and behavioral effects need to be defined, and studies need to be carried out on the positive and negative consequences related to study participation.
3. Is penile hygiene as good as MC? Clinical trials that include a penile hygiene study arm should be conducted. These studies should also conduct analyses of feasibility, required resources, and infrastructure requirements.
4. Although much cost analysis, particularly in the United States, has been conducted to project the cost savings from averted HIV infection, STIs, and urinary tract infections (UTIs), there is a lack of data projecting the costs of treating circumcision-related complications. How will complications be addressed in resource-poor settings?
5. The development of models that include cost analysis for training practitioners in resource-poor settings is urgently needed. Modeling should project the cost of equipment and its maintenance, and the treatment of complications. These projections should be comprehensive modeling strategies including PMTCT, condom provision, voluntary counseling and testing (VCT), and treatment.
6. Interventions that combine reproductive health services, HIV VCT, and male circumcision should be explored.
7. Should MC rollout begin, it is essential that surveillance systems be put into place to track who is presenting for services, incidence of adverse events, and disinhibition in circumcised populations.
8. Qualitative studies that shed light on people's understanding of protection afforded by male circumcision—both for males and females—will be essential. It will be important to repeat these over time as events change. The perspective of parents will also need to be included.
9. Prevention models that include male circumcision, but do not focus on it exclusively, are needed to elucidate how male circumcision can be incorporated into a broader prevention framework.
10. Legal research is needed to understand barriers and facilitators of male circumcision, and the protections necessary to maximize benefits and reduce harms.
11. Stigma remains a central impediment in HIV prevention. Understanding how male circumcision reduces or enhances stigma will be essential.

Acronyms

AAP	American Academy of Pediatrics
ABC	Abstinence, be faithful, use condoms
AIDS	Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
ANRS	Agence Nationale de Recherches sur le Sida (France)
ARV	Antiretroviral
BMA	British Medical Association
DFID	Department for International Development (UK)
DSMB	Data and safety monitoring board
FGM	Female genital mutilation
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
HPTN	HIV Prevention Trials Network
HPV	Human papillomavirus
HSPC	Human subjects protections committee
HSV-2	Herpes simplex virus type 2
IDU	Injecting drug user
IRB	Institutional review board
MC	Male circumcision
MSM	Men who have sex with men
NHDS	National Hospital Discharge Survey
NIH	National Institutes of Health (U.S.)
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (U.S.)
NGO	Nongovernmental organization
PLWH/A	Person/people living with HIV/AIDS
PMTCT	Prevention of mother-to-child transmission (of HIV)
PrEP	Pre-exposure prophylaxis
SRH	Sexual and reproductive health
STI	Sexually transmitted infection
TDF	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate
UCLA	University of California, Los Angeles
UNAIDS	Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS
USAID	U.S. Agency for International Development
UTI	Urinary tract infection
VCT	Voluntary counseling and testing
WHO	World Health Organization

Introduction

This report summarizes available information on male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy and the policy and prevention implications of its implementation. To this end, the report examines:

1. Summary of HIV prevention science and practice;
2. A review of the currently available data from observational studies and randomized controlled clinical trials;
3. Adult male circumcision, other health benefits, and the implications for women's health;
4. Biological mechanism responsible for reduced susceptibility to HIV infection and other medical benefits among circumcised males;
5. Medical professional group policy statements pertaining to male circumcision;
6. Challenges related to male circumcision;
7. Research priorities;
8. Ethical concerns; and
9. Potential next steps.

It is urgent that we immediately address the myriad cultural, economic, social, ethical, moral, and political challenges related to male circumcision (MC) as an HIV prevention strategy. The first randomized controlled clinical trial to report impact of MC on HIV infection, the South African "Orange Farm" trial, released results at the July 2005 International AIDS Society meeting in Rio de Janeiro that demonstrated that MC could provide up to a **60% protective benefit** in 3,274 men aged 18-24 that were enrolled in the study. On December 13, 2006, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) announced the early termination of two additional randomized controlled trials of male circumcision—in Kenya and Uganda—based on interim evidence that MC has a significant protective benefit against HIV infection. The Kenya trial reported a **53% reduction** in HIV incidence among 2,784 enrolled men; the Uganda trial reported a **48% reduction** in HIV incidence among 4,996 enrolled men. The combined results from the three trials provide sufficient evidence that MC does provide protective benefit from HIV acquisition, but many additional questions remain unanswered.

Now that results are available from these three studies, it is urgent that planning for large-scale implementation begins. Plans for implementation of this magnitude need to account not only for the medical risks and benefits, but also social, cultural, economic, sexual, and other risks and benefits. We outline these issues and the associated challenges surrounding them to stimulate discussion about policy and planning.

Background

At the time this report was produced, approximately 39.5 million people globally are infected with HIV, of which, 24.7 million live in sub-Saharan Africa(1). Currently there are no available strategies that provide complete protection from HIV infection (other than complete abstinence, which is difficult to maintain and in the case of couples trying to conceive, unrealistic). Nor is a vaccine providing either full or partial immunity likely to be developed in the short term, and fundamental questions about whether a preventive vaccine is even feasible remain unanswered.

Significant emphasis has been placed on the development of novel prevention technologies and behavioral and social approaches that are intended to work in concert with one another. Currently, there are approximately a dozen such approaches being investigated. Current trials include:

- **Pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP)** is chemoprophylaxis using tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) or a combination of TDF and emtricitabine. Both agents are existing, well-tolerated antiretrovirals licensed in the U.S. and Europe to treat HIV infection.
- **Treatment or suppression of herpes simplex virus 2 (HSV-2).** With chronic or episodic use of acyclovir Infection with HSV-2 has been associated with higher HIV prevalence rates.
- **HIV viral load suppression** uses antiretroviral medications to treat HIV infection, and also has the potential to dramatically lower transmission rates.
- **Diaphragms** might prevent HIV from reaching the cervix and endocervix where most female infections occur, as well as providing women with the potential advantage of being able to protect themselves without the need to negotiate with a partner.
- **Vaginal, rectal, and topical microbicides** are substances that could be placed inside the vagina, inside the rectum, or topically on the penis to prevent infection.
- **New strategies for treating sexually transmitted infections,** a co-factor for HIV acquisition (eg, treatment of bacterial vaginosis); and for improving vaginal health.
- **New behavioral and pharmacologic strategies** for preventing and treating abuse of substances, including opiates, stimulants, and alcohol.
- **New strategies for making voluntary counseling and testing (VCT)** uptake more attractive and available. This has the potential to challenge stigma, reduce risk behavior, and heighten community level discussion about HIV.
- **More effective strategies for reducing mother-to-child transmission,** including reducing transmission of HIV through breast milk, and strategies for women whose HIV is not diagnosed until labor.
- **Treatment of depression,** as this has been related to HIV infection in several different studies.
- **Male circumcision,** the focus of this report, which has a rapidly growing body of literature, and findings from three randomized controlled clinical trials suggest has a substantial protective benefit against HIV-1 acquisition.

Why Do We Need Additional Prevention Strategies?

One might wonder why it is necessary to develop new prevention strategies and technologies when current devices such as the male and female condom are highly effective when used correctly and consistently. There are several reasons. The first is that the prevention literature demonstrates that it can be difficult to motivate certain groups of people to use male or female condoms every time that they are in a high-risk situation (eg, when consuming alcohol or using other psychoactive substances). The second is that it requires consistent effort to ensure that individuals continue to use condoms over time. Most studies show that it might be possible to get an immediate or even short-term (eg, 12 months) increase in condom use, but that this effect wanes over a longer period of time. The third is that there is substantial evidence demonstrating that condoms use drops significantly at the initiation of emotional, intimate, or long-term relationships, as use of condoms often signifies lack of trust. Nonetheless, there is also substantial literature demonstrating that women, especially in resource poor countries, are at risk for HIV and other sexually transmitted infections from their regular, not secondary or casual partners.

The search for other prevention strategies is not intended to replace condoms, but rather to add to the armory of available HIV prevention strategies. We know that having multiple prevention strategies allows more dynamic interventions that are able to respond to locally specific resources, culturally specific issues, as well as structural and geographical limitations. It may be possible that people will choose one strategy in preference to another, or choose one strategy at one time and a second at another time.

The Prevention Science View

The Prevention Science View diagram provides one perspective on HIV prevention and the science behind it. Delaying first intercourse and reducing number of partners can reduce HIV infection. Adults have a more mature reproductive health tract, more capable of resisting infection. Adults might also be more equipped socially and emotionally to take precautions. A greater number of sexual partners increase the likelihood that one will come into contact with someone who has HIV or another sexually transmitted infection. This is especially true because those with more sexual partners are likely to be interacting across sexual networks where more disease is present, thus increasing the likelihood of infection. Stoneburner et al document the impact of partner reduction as a result of the communication about HIV/AIDS through social networks in Uganda(2). Similar effects were noted in Zimbabwe, Kenya and Haiti(3-6).

Psychoactive drugs (eg, opiates, stimulants, alcohol, etc) increase sexual risk. Barrier methods such as male and female condoms protect against infection, but they must be used consistently and correctly. Proponents of the vaginal diaphragm await the results of the efficacy trial in South Africa and Zimbabwe.

Treating bacterial and probably viral sexually transmitted infections reduces both transmission and acquisition of HIV.

Reduced viral load is associated with reduced probability of transmission. This concept has been demonstrated both for sexual transmission and in mother-to-child transmission. Suppression of viral load with antiretroviral medications reduces mother-to-child transmission and may also reduce sexual transmission. The trial to test the hypothesis that reductions in viral load achieved through medications reduces transmission (HPTN 052) is underway (7).

Several Phase III studies are underway to test various vaginal microbicide preparations; rectal microbicides are gaining traction in concept but are still only in preclinical or early human trials. Effective preventive vaccines may not be available for as many as 15 to 20 years in the future. It is possible that a therapeutic vaccine—one that reduces viral load or boosts immune response and therefore reduces infectiousness—may also prevent transmission(8).

As the “Prevention Science View” schema depicted in the figure demonstrates, social, behavioral, and biomedical interventions require work at multiple levels of society, including the individual, the couple and family, the network, the community, and at the level of policy and legal interventions. This also means that any intervention needs to address social inequities related to gender, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, occupation, age, sexual orientation, legal status, immigration status, educational status, or any other variable that drives the epidemic.

Ideally, the use of combination prevention strategies would be encouraged, as none of the available prevention strategies work perfectly all of the time. Alternatively, it might be possible for individuals to choose different prevention strategies in different situations.

The Research Evidence on Male Circumcision

Male circumcision may offer a powerful advantage over other HIV prevention strategies in that it involves a one-time surgery that does not require ongoing behavioral modification in order to work. The protection afforded by MC is temporally separate from the risk behavior. Once it is done safely, it is completed and the person does not need to exert any further actions in order to achieve the protection that circumcision affords. This may have significant implications in resource-poor settings where routine access and distribution of technologies that require ongoing use (condoms, antiretrovirals (ARVs), diaphragms, etc) may present operational hurdles that diminish efficacy.

Nonetheless, MC presents challenges. The cost associated with population-level MC may exceed a country’s financial resources and health care infrastructure capacity. Significant financial commitments would have to come from multilateral and bilateral organizations. Furthermore, people may develop the perception that circumcision provides complete protection, when in fact protection is far less than ideal (based on the recent clinical trials, approximately a 50% protective benefit under ideal circumstances at the time of vaginal intercourse).

Observational Studies

Since the mid 1980s, multiple observational studies have correlated male circumcision with reduced risk for HIV-1 infection. Based on results from these studies, it has been hypothesized that variation in HIV prevalence rates in Africa are associated with differences in circumcision practices. High HIV prevalence rates are associated with low circumcision rates.

In response to the mounting enthusiasm generated from the observational evidence of the potential protective benefits against HIV infection that male circumcision may provide, the Cochrane Collaboration published a comprehensive review of the available studies suggesting that circumcision can be used as an intervention to prevent HIV infection(9). The original findings were reported in July 2003 and were then updated in March 2005(10). The Cochrane review differs from previous reviews in that it attempts to assess the likelihood that circumcision will reduce heterosexual transmission of HIV to men. Previous reviews focused on the correlations between circumcision and HIV prevalence. No studies included in the review reported on medical complications associated with circumcision. It is important to note that the Cochrane Collaboration points out that many of the observational studies were poorly designed.

The updated review included 37 observational studies, 18 conducted among the general population and 19 among high-risk populations. Of the 18 general population studies included, 12 reported circumcision as having a beneficial effect (9 were statistically significant). All of the 19 high-risk population studies demonstrated beneficial effect.

Observational studies, unlike randomized controlled trials, might not have comparable groups of circumcised and non-circumcised participants because people were not assigned at random. Meta-analysis was not conducted because of heterogeneity in the multiple confounding factors present, including viral load, sexual behaviors, penile hygiene, religion, etc. Sigfried et al highlight that circumcision status itself may be a confounder, functioning as a proxy measure of knowledge about sexual practice, monogamy, and penile hygiene(10).

For example, a comparison of sub-Saharan Africans by religious affiliation indicates that circumcised Muslim men have lower HIV incidence than circumcised non-Muslims. Although Muslims almost universally circumcise males, there could be many specific behaviors (eg, washing before and after sex, prohibition against substance use, etc) that might account for the lower HIV acquisition risk in Muslims. It is not possible to exclude the possibility that the apparent protective effects of circumcision may reflect subtle differences in risk behaviors between Muslim and non-Muslim men or their partners. Another example occurs in the Rakai District of Uganda where married Muslim men are predominantly polygamous, and polygamous unions may provide a closed sexual network reducing the risk of HIV infection(11). Lower alcohol consumption among Muslims may also be a factor, as alcohol reduces inhibition and potentially increases high-risk behavior.

Randomized Controlled Trials

Randomized controlled trials are the only way to determine with relative confidence a causal relationship between male circumcision and HIV acquisition. Such studies need to conform to standard ethical practices, especially informed consent, counseling for risk reduction, and the promotion and provision of condoms. Using these standards, three major, African, randomized clinical trials were initiated in South Africa, Uganda, and Kenya. The French and United States governments (through ANRS and NIH, respectively) funded these studies with additional support from The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Public health officials in the United States, Europe, and Canada have been reluctant to make recommendations based on observational data alone, because one cannot rule out alternative explanations as to why the circumcised men might be less likely to become infected than the uncircumcised men. Although there is abundant, positive observational data supporting circumcision as a preventative HIV infection strategy, observational studies alone are insufficient to recommend circumcision as an intervention because extensive confounding variables exist that can mask the true reason as to why an association is found (9, 10).

The first trial to report outcomes, the South African “Orange Farm” study, showed a substantial protective benefit in the circumcised cohort: a 65% reduction in probability of HIV-1 infection(12). The trial was stopped early after interim review by the data and safety monitoring board (DSMB) determined that continuing the trial in light of such overwhelmingly positive results would be unethical. Due to the early termination of the Orange Farm study, it was not possible to continuously monitor participants and therefore will not be able to provide critical information pertaining to how circumcision may or may not change the men’s sexual practices, possible sexual disinhibition leading to riskier behavior, and the effect MC will have on condom use.

In addition to attempting to replicate the Orange Farm study to determine if male circumcision prevents infection, the Ugandan trial (which was designed to involve approximately 6,800 male and female participants) also investigated whether male circumcision will reduce transmission rates from people with HIV to those without HIV. A third randomized controlled trial, the Kenyan study, involved 2,784 previously uncircumcised HIV-negative men, half of whom were circumcised during the trial.

On December 13, 2006, the DSMB of the U.S. NIH announced the early termination of both the Ugandan and Kenyan trials based on evidence that male circumcision in these trials did provide substantial protective benefit against HIV infection. The Kenya trial reported a **53% reduction** in HIV incidence among 2,784 enrolled men, and the Uganda trial reported a **48% reduction** in HIV incidence among 4,996 enrolled men. The HIV prevention community is eagerly awaiting the detailed discussion of the interim results from the Kenyan and Ugandan trials.

South Africa (“Orange Farm”): “Randomized, Controlled Intervention Trial of Male Circumcision for Reduction of HIV Infection Risk: The ANRS 1265 Trial”

Auvert B, Taljaard D, Lagarde E, Sobngwi-Tambekou J, Sitta R, Puren A.

In November 2005, Bertran Auvert et al, reported results from the South African “Orange Farm” trial after the DSMB stopped the trial based on an interim analysis of data collected after all subjects had completed the 12-month clinic visit(12). The results that lead to the early ending of the Orange Farm trial suggested that the risk of HIV infection was reduced by 60% in circumcised men. Important findings that may have implications on future studies and interventions include:

1. The participants were all drawn from the general population with a low lost-to-follow-up rate, suggesting that large circumcision trials can be effectively conducted in resource-limited settings;
2. The study noted that subjects in the male circumcision group had significantly more sexual contacts--an important factor for policy makers to consider as there is growing concern that MC may lead to sexual disinhibition and riskier behavior;
3. Auvert et al concluded that male circumcision provides a degree of protection comparable to what a vaccine with high efficacy would achieve.

With regard to a protective benefit for women, the authors assert; “...MC will indirectly protect women and, therefore, children from HIV infection because if the men are less susceptible to HIV acquisition, women will be less exposed.” This statement needs more rigorous scrutiny, insofar as it assumes that the benefits of MC to female sexual partners will not be counteracted by increased risk behaviors. Among societies where agency over one’s body and imbalances in sexual decision making are heavily weighted towards men, decreasing the susceptibility of men to HIV acquisition without cautious consideration of existing social norms may have a significantly less beneficial impact on HIV acquisition among women.

Uganda: “Trial of Male Circumcision: HIV, STD and Behavioral Effects in Men, Women and the Community”

Serwadda D, Wawer M, Gray R.

The study is being carried out by the Rakai Health Sciences Program, a research collaboration between the Uganda Virus Research Institute/Uganda Ministry of Health, Columbia University Mailman School of Public Health, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, and researchers from Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda.

The study was conducted in Rakai District, Uganda, and was designed to enroll ~800 HIV-positive men. Following a detailed informed consent process, the men were randomized to receive either immediate (within several days or weeks) or delayed (two years) circumcision. The goals were to assess the safety and acceptability of male circumcision among HIV-positive men, and to assess potential effects of male circumcision on the acquisition of STIs such as HSV-2. The investigators hypothesize that male circumcision will be acceptable to and safe in HIV-positive men, will reduce the rate of acquisition of STIs, and will reduce the frequency of STI symptoms, such as genital ulceration.

The study design also included the enrollment of ~1,000 men who, regardless of their HIV status, decline to receive their HIV results, despite encouragement to do so. Hypotheses are that circumcision will be acceptable and safe in men who decline their HIV results, and will reduce the rate of acquisition of HIV and STIs, and the frequency of STI symptoms such as genital ulcers.

The study also planned to enroll up to ~5,000 female partners of the men in groups above, as well as 5,000 HIV-negative men enrolled in a complementary NIH-funded study of male circumcision for HIV prevention (which is being separately registered). Female partners were to be followed annually to assess the acceptability and safety of male circumcision, and potential effects of male circumcision on HIV and STI acquisition. The hypothesis is that male circumcision will be acceptable to and safe in female partners, and will reduce the acquisition of HIV and STIs such as HSV-2 and human papillomavirus (HPV), which causes cervical cancer.

Finally, the study was also designed to follow ~3,000 men and women in the ~50 communities where the circumcision trials are taking place, in order to assess community attitudes towards and knowledge of male circumcision, and to assess whether other preventive behaviors (abstinence, monogamy, numbers of partners, condom use, etc) change in the community once circumcision becomes available. The investigators hypothesize that male circumcision will be acceptable in the community and will not result in behavioral disinhibition (increased rates of high-risk behaviors).

The Gates-funded study is complementary to a separate NIH-funded trial of male circumcision in HIV-negative men who accept their HIV results and is being carried out by the Rakai Health Sciences Program study team. It is expected to report data in 2008. The latter study, which is enrolling 5,000 HIV-negative men, is designed to answer question about whether male circumcision is acceptable and safe in HIV-negative men, and whether the procedure reduces the acquisition of HIV and STIs.

The complementary Gates-funded trial is designed to answer the following question:

- Is male circumcision acceptable to and safe in HIV-infected men, and will it reduce the rates of acquisition of STDs in these men?

This question is of great importance for future circumcision programs:

- Is male circumcision acceptable and safe in men who decline their HIV results, and will it reduce rates of acquisition of HIV and STIS in these men?

Determining potential circumcision risks in these men (such as potentially delayed healing because of their higher risk behaviors) or benefits (such as potentially reduced rates of HIV and STI acquisition) is thus very important for the design of any future large-scale circumcision programs. From the public health viewpoint, it will be important to know whether such programs should include or exclude men who decline HIV results. The Rakai Program strongly recommends and encourages the receipt of HIV test results, and provides the results confidentially and free of charge. The great majority of Rakai Program research participants (85-90%) accept their HIV results, but a minority continues to decline, although the latter group is getting smaller every year. If participants decline their HIV results, the Rakai Program still provides them with detailed HIV prevention education and counseling. Enrollment of men who decline their HIV results is also congruent with Ugandan Ministry of Health Policy, which encourages but does not force individuals and study participants to receive their HIV results.

Enrollment of female partners is designed to answer important questions regarding potential effects of male circumcision on women. Should male circumcision reduce HIV and STI acquisition in women, this

would represent an additional important public health benefit and would increase the cost effectiveness of male circumcision programs. However, if the procedure is associated with increased HIV transmission (for example, due to increased transmission before a circumcision surgical wound is fully healed), it is crucial that such a potential risk be identified rapidly within a trial, in order to prevent the risk within trials and in any potential future circumcision programs.

Following enrollment, men in the circumcision arm are followed post-operatively, at 4-6 weeks, and at 6, 12, and 24 months. Men in the control arm are also followed at 4-6 weeks and at 6, 12 and 24 months. At baseline and follow up, men respond to a detailed sociodemographic, behavioral, and health questionnaire, and provide biological samples (venous blood, urine, sub-preputial swabs [prior to circumcision] and for circumcised men, foreskins are collected at time of surgery.) Samples will allow assessment of multiple infections, including HIV, HSV-2, gonorrhoea, *Chlamydia*, and syphilis.

Female partners are followed annually, through the Rakai Community Cohort Study. Following written informed consent, women are administered a detailed sociodemographic, behavioral and health status questionnaire, and provide venous blood and self-administered vaginal swabs at baseline and study follow-up visits. The samples will allow assessment of multiple infections and conditions, including HIV, syphilis, gonorrhoea, *Chlamydia*, *Trichomonas*, bacterial vaginosis, HSV-2, and HPV. Female partners of HIV-positive men receive an additional visit at 6 months post enrollment, in order to ensure expeditious assessment of potential risks.

Kenya: “Trial of Male Circumcision to Reduce HIV Incidence”

Bailey R, Moses S, Maclean I, Parker C, Ndinya-Achola JO, Agot K, Krieger J.

Uncircumcised men aged 18 to 24 were offered voluntary HIV counseling and testing. HIV-negative men were asked to enroll in the study. All study participants were interviewed to obtain sociodemographic information and assess behavioral risk factors. Participants were examined for significant medical conditions. All men were counseled in strategies to reduce their risk for HIV infection. Consenting men was randomly assigned to either the treatment (circumcised) arm or the control (uncircumcised) arm of the study. After circumcision, men were monitored for complications. They were counseled to abstain from sex until healing is complete. Follow-up visits occurred every 6 months for 2 years. Uncircumcised men were offered circumcision at the end of the follow-up period. The primary study endpoints will be HIV incidence and surgical complications. Additional outcomes will be the incidence of other sexually transmitted diseases and behavioral risks. Additional laboratory studies of foreskin tissue will evaluate the number and density of specialized cells rich in HIV receptors in order to illuminate the biological mechanisms by which presence of foreskin may increase HIV susceptibility.

Male Circumcision, HIV Viral Load, and Male-to-Female Transmission

In addition to reducing the risk of exposure to HPV, recent studies in Uganda suggest that in HIV-infected men, circumcision combined with lower viral loads reduces the risk of male-to-female transmission. The Rakai, Uganda study group recently reported that when HIV viral loads are not controlled, the overall effects of circumcision on HIV transmission from HIV-infected men to their HIV-negative partners was modest(8). However, when circumcised HIV-positive men had viral loads less than 50,000 copies/mL, no transmission occurred whereas in uncircumcised HIV-positive men with viral loads of less than 50,000 copies/mL, the transmission rate was 9.6 per 100 person years. For the Rakai group, circumcision afforded no protection from HIV transmission at viral loads greater than 50,000 copies/mL, suggesting that male circumcision may protect women from HIV transmission at lower, but not at higher, viral loads. This finding could have significant implications in Africa, as the majority of transmissions fueling the epidemic are male-to-female. Furthermore, it suggests that controlling the viral loads of HIV-positive individuals could have significant impact on lowering new infections and that this effect is amplified by

male circumcision. It is important to note that the Rakai group looked at individuals with naturally suppressed viral load; they did not look at individuals with suppressed viral loads due to antiretroviral therapy. Studies monitoring male circumcision combined with antiretroviral-suppressed viral loads in HIV-positive individuals should be conducted.

Other Health Benefits

Since the initial paper suggesting protective effective of MC against HIV infection was published in 1986 and Wiswell et al first reported reduced UTIs in circumcised males over two decades ago, there have been extensive and impassioned debates as to the impact that male circumcision used as a public health measure would have on the reduction of STIs in the adult population(13-15). Many of these arguments have highlighted that insufficient and even contradictory evidence existed. Others have cited that although many prospective cohort studies exist, a lack of longitudinal studies limited the conclusions that could be drawn(16).

Indeed, the American Academy of Pediatrics' (AAP) 1999 decision not to recommend routine neonatal circumcisions partially rested upon this assumption(17). Since the Academy's decision, there has been mounting consistent evidence suggesting reduction of STIs in circumcised males. Fergusson et al recently reported results from a 25-year longitudinal study of a cohort of more than 500 New Zealand males that confirm the considerable reduction of STIs in circumcised males(18). Uncircumcised males were 3.19 times more likely to have STIs than circumcised males. The added power of longitudinal data makes it possible to examine circumcision status and infection risk over an extended period of time rather than at a point in time. The investigators report that if the entire cohort had been circumcised, STIs would have been reduced by approximately 50%.

In addition to the potential protective benefits from HIV-1 infection and UTIs, evidence exists that suggests male circumcision is associated with a number of other health benefits, including the reduced risk of genital ulcer disease and HSV-2. Minimizing HSV-2 infection and genital ulcer disease has the dual benefit of reducing HIV-1 transmission rates, as both significantly increase the probability HIV-1 transmission. Additionally, cervical cancer occurs at a higher rate in the female partners of uncircumcised males. The mechanism thought to be responsible for the increased cervical cancer is a higher transmission rate of HPV, which is associated to a greater extent with uncircumcised males.

Biological Plausibility

The mechanism thought to be responsible for reduced risk of incident HIV-1 infection in circumcised males is the presence of a significantly higher concentration of Langerhans cells, which are target cells for HIV-1 in the mucosal layer of the foreskin(19). Additionally, keratin is believed to provide a protective barrier against HIV-1 infection(20). The penile shaft and outer foreskin surface are well keratinized, while the inner mucosal layer of the foreskin is not(21). It is also argued that the sensitive foreskin may be more susceptible to micro-abrasion during sexual intercourse, which could provides an entry for STIs and HIV(22). Initial HIV target cell concentration studies were conducted among samples from Australian, English, and North American men. Recent results from Donoval et al confirmed that samples from African males (Kisumu, Kenya) were consistent with the previous finding(23). Donoval et al report higher concentrations of Langerhans cells in the foreskin mucosal layer and little or no protective keratin layer on the inner foreskin of the Kenyan study participants.

Potential Benefits to Populations

Herd immunity is defined as the resistance of a group to attack by a disease due to the immunity achieved in a large proportion of the members. The consequences of this process lessen the likelihood that an affected individual will come into contact with a susceptible individual.

The concept of herd immunity depends on achieving a critical breaking point in the spread of disease. For each disease, there exists a percentage of the population (the critical immune threshold) that when achieved will effectively stop or slow further transmission. As with smallpox and tuberculosis, the typical threshold for stopping disease spread is high. In the context of HIV infection, it is unlikely that full herd immunity will be achieved in the short term as no single strategy or combination of strategies are currently available to achieve a high enough protection at the population level. Nevertheless, technologies like male circumcision can significantly retard incidence rates and reduce overall prevalence insofar as the protective benefit for any single circumcised individual translates to decreased risk among sexual partners. It is important to note that epidemiologists and virologists point out that when there is insufficient coverage to thwart disease spread, while overall disease spread may be slowed, unforeseen problems can occur (eg, while overall population incidence may decline, incidence in a particular subgroup may rise).

Williams et al used modeling to project that large-scale implementation of male circumcision has the potential to avert approximately 2 million new HIV infections and 0.3 million deaths over the next ten years(24). Over the subsequent 10 years an additional 3.7 million HIV infections and 2.7 million deaths could be averted, totaling almost 6 million averted infections over 20 years. The greatest impact would be in southern Africa where circumcision rates are low and HIV prevalence is high. Additionally, Williams et al report that combining male circumcision with prevention strategies known to reduce transmission rates, such as the use of antiretrovirals, would further reduce new infections.

Table from Williams, 2006(24)

Region	Time Period	Incident Cases Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Incident Cases (Percent)	Prevalent Cases Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Prevalent Cases (Percent)	Deaths Averted (Millions)	Reduction in Mortality (Percent)
Sub-Saharan	2005–2015	2.0 (1.7–3.8)	8 (4–17)	2.2 (1.2–4.3)	8 (4–17)	0.3 (0.1–0.5)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	3.7 (1.9–9.0)	14 (6–32)	4.1 (2.0–8.7)	13 (6–31)	2.7 (1.5–5.3)	9 (5–19)
	2025–2035	4.4 (2.2–9.0)	13 (6–32)	4.7 (2.4–9.7)	13 (6–30)	4.9 (2.5–9.9)	14 (7–34)
Central	2005–2015	0.7 (0.1–0.3)	8 (4–17)	0.7 (0.1–0.4)	8 (4–17)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	1 (0–2)
	2015–2025	0.4 (0.2–0.8)	15 (7–36)	0.4 (0.2–0.9)	15 (7–37)	0.2 (0.1–0.3)	9 (4–20)
	2025–2035	0.5 (0.3–1.1)	16 (7–39)	0.5 (0.2–1.2)	15 (7–39)	0.5 (0.2–1.1)	16 (7–39)
East	2005–2015	0.5 (0.3–1.0)	9 (4–18)	0.6 (0.3–1.2)	9 (4–18)	0.1 (0.0–0.1)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	14 (7–33)	1.1 (0.5–2.3)	14 (7–34)	0.8 (0.4–1.3)	10 (5–20)
	2025–2035	1.3 (0.6–2.6)	14 (7–35)	1.4 (0.7–2.9)	14 (6–34)	1.4 (0.7–2.8)	15 (7–36)
Southern	2005–2015	1.0 (0.6–1.9)	11 (6–22)	1.2 (0.7–2.1)	11 (6–23)	0.1 (0.1–0.3)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	1.9 (1.0–3.6)	18 (9–43)	1.9 (1.0–3.8)	18 (9–42)	1.4 (0.8–2.6)	12 (7–26)
	2025–2035	2.0 (1.1–4.0)	18 (9–43)	2.0 (1.1–4.1)	16 (8–39)	2.4 (1.3–4.6)	20 (10–48)
West	2005–2015	0.2 (0.1–0.5)	4 (2–9)	0.3 (0.1–0.6)	4 (2–9)	0.0 (0.0–0.1)	0 (0–1)
	2015–2025	0.5 (0.2–1.1)	6 (3–15)	0.5 (0.2–1.2)	6 (3–16)	0.3 (0.2–0.7)	4 (2–10)
	2025–2035	0.6 (0.3–1.3)	6 (3–15)	0.6 (0.3–1.5)	6 (3–15)	0.6 (0.3–1.4)	7 (3–16)
South Africa	2005–2015	0.5 (0.3–1.0)	11 (6–22)	0.6 (0.3–1.0)	11 (6–23)	0.1 (0.0–0.1)	1 (1–2)
	2015–2025	0.9 (0.5–1.8)	20 (1–48)	1.0 (0.5–1.9)	19 (9–46)	0.7 (0.4–1.3)	13 (7–27)
	2025–2035	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	19 (9–48)	1.0 (0.5–2.0)	17 (8–43)	1.2 (0.6–2.3)	22 (1–53)

Data are as defined for the countries and regions given in Table 1. Data are given separately for each region and for South Africa over the next ten, twenty, and thirty years. Full coverage of MC is reached in 2015. The table gives the reduction in incidence and deaths, over each ten-year period, and in prevalent cases at the end of each ten-year period. Reductions are relative to the baseline, which assumes no change in MC prevalence. The calculations are done using the expected reduction in female-to-male transmission from the RCT and using the lower and upper 95% confidence limits of the reduction observed in the RCT [8]. DOI: 10.1171/journal.pmed.0030022

Although these projections are promising, there are several important caveats. First, the modeling analysis was based on the results from a single clinical trial (Orange Farm) and thus additional modeling based on

data from ongoing trials, once it is available, should be conducted. Second, the impact of a circumcision intervention depends on the current prevalence of male circumcision and HIV. Comparing the Williams modeling to the current epidemic in South Africa, a recent article in the *Mail & Guardian Online* reported that fifteen-year-olds in South Africa now have a 56% chance of dying before turning 60, versus ten years ago when they had a 29% chance of not making their 60th birthday(25). The article continues, “A third of women between the ages of 25 and 29 years are infected, while 19% of the country’s working-age (age 20 to 64) population is HIV positive.”

Men Who Have Sex with Men and Penile-Anal Transmission

There is currently limited data available on the rate of HIV transmission for the receptive partner of a circumcised man in penile-anal intercourse. In a study evaluating sexual risk factors conducted among 3,257 MSM in six U.S. cities, Buchbinder et al reported that uncircumcised men were almost twice as likely to seroconvert than circumcised men (26). The effect of male circumcision on reducing the risk of HIV transmission among men who have sex with men has not been studied in a randomized controlled trial. It is also unclear what proportion of men involved in the South African, Ugandan, and Kenyan circumcision trials engaged in MSM or penile-anal intercourse. The protective benefits afforded by MC accrue primarily to the circumcised man. The rectal and vaginal epithelium do not contain traditional receptors for HIV-1 and provide a protective barrier to the underlying target cells. Because the rectal epithelium is a single layer, and mucosal trauma is often associated with anal sex, receptive anal intercourse is significantly higher risk than receptive vaginal intercourse(27, 28). The MSM population will likely not achieve the same prevalence reduction as the heterosexual population. Within the heterosexual population, it is also unclear what percent of men engage in penile-vaginal and penile-anal intercourse. The combination of penile-vaginal and penile-anal intercourse will also likely be a confounding factor in measuring prevalence reduction.

Male Circumcision, Sexual Functioning, and Post-Procedural Satisfaction

There is no current consensus on the role of foreskin on penile sensitivity(29). Limited comprehensive data on sensation loss after male circumcision currently exists. Many early studies conducted to evaluate the effect of MC on sexual function enrolled subjects with preexisting morbidities, which may be confounding factors of the results(30). Fink et al conducted a retrospective chart review of 123 men circumcised after the age of 18, of which 43 responded to a mailed survey. Although the study concluded overall satisfaction¹ rates, it also reported slightly reduced erectile function and decreased penile sensitivity (which bordered on statistical significance, $p = .08$). Senkul et al, responding to the power limitations and pre-existing morbidities of the Fink study, looked at 42 males who were circumcised between ages 19-28, none of whom had pre-existing pathologies(31). Of the participants, 39 were circumcised for religious reasons and 3 were circumcised for cosmetic reasons. Subjects were evaluated before and after using the Brief Male Sexual Function Inventory(32). The study concluded an increase in ejaculatory latency time (which the authors note could be interpreted as a benefit) and that the subjects’ sexual function was not adversely affected.

The fields of reproductive health and sexually transmitted diseases have a long history of balancing prevention technologies as public health measures with diminished sexual sensation. Consistent and correct use of condoms has proven protective benefits against unwanted pregnancies and STIs; yet even in areas where access to condoms is not a barrier and >90% coverage is feasible, condom use is not consistent. One of the major cited barriers has been the diminished sexual sensation for both men and women. Nevertheless, the global campaign for 100% condom coverage is viewed as one of the most

¹ Satisfaction was defined as a more pleasing appearance of the penis to the men and their partners, and less pain experienced with erection.

effective strategies to thwart unplanned pregnancies and STIs. Several of the emerging prevention technologies (eg, topical microbicides, diaphragms) will likely encounter similar concerns regarding diminished sensation. While condoms, microbicides, and diaphragms are not permanent physiological alterations as is MC, there are several advantages to MC: 1) the protective benefits are separate from risk behavior; 2) unlike condoms and diaphragms, the protective benefits of MC do not require behavioral adherence; 3) MC has proven reduction of UTIs, STIs, and HPV transmission; 3) MC will easily work in concert with other prevention strategies.

Official Medical Professional Statements Regarding Male Circumcision

Medical professional groups have addressed male circumcision, especially of infants, and these official positions have changed over time. It is interesting to note that the U.S., European, and Australia/New Zealand groups have interpreted recent evidence in quite different ways. Further, it is important to note the change that has taken place in Botswana.

American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) Circumcision Policy Statement

It is useful to consider U.S. circumcision policy and understand its origins, because many governmental agencies and nongovernmental organizations in the U.S. significantly influence global HIV prevention policy. This is particularly true in regards to ethical considerations of U.S.-funded international research, and interventions targeted primarily at high-prevalence areas in Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia that may result in international policy that is not consistent with that of the United States.

On March 1, 1999, the AAP issued recommendations stating that although evidence demonstrating medical benefits exists, the benefits associated with neonatal circumcision are not sufficient to warrant the recommendation of circumcision as a routine procedure(17). The policy statement, which was reaffirmed in 2005, indicates that in circumstances where a procedure has potential risks and benefits, yet is not essential to well-being of the neonate, the decision as to what is in the best interest of the child should be left to the parents. The statement continues, “To make an informed choice, parents of all male infants should be given accurate and unbiased information and be provided the opportunity to discuss this decision.”

The AAP’s focus on the immediate well being of the neonate, rather than the individual’s well being through their adult life and any public health benefits, is inconsistent with the Academy’s other recommendations. Specifically, the Academy recommends newborn immunization against hepatitis B. Unless in circumstances where a mother is hepatitis B positive, hepatitis B presents primary risk to the adult, sexually active population, not the neonate. This recommendation is clearly based on consideration of the well-being of the adolescent or adult population. It is important to note that the hepatitis B vaccine is relatively safe. This type of inconsistency may suggest that factors other than object assessment of neonatal well being are influencing policy.

Beginning in the Academy’s 1971 manual, *Standards and Recommendations of Hospital Care of Newborn Infants*, and reiterated in the 1975 and 1985 revisions, the AAP concluded that there was no absolute medical indication for routine circumcision. In 1989, in response to research exploring the links between circumcision status and both UTIs and STIs, particularly HIV, the Academy concluded that newborn male circumcision did have potential medical benefits and advantages, as well as risks. In 1997, the AAP redefined nontherapeutic circumcision of the newborn as an elective procedure. Although the current recommendations (1999; reaffirmed in 2005) acknowledge the potential medical benefits and risks, the statement asserts circumcision is an elective procedure that is not necessary for the immediate health of the neonate and as such, defers to the parents’ judgment. The National Hospital Discharge

Survey (NHDS) provides the most comprehensive data set of incidence rates of circumcision over time. The data offers limited sensitivity insofar as only 5% of U.S. hospitals participate. The NHDS divides the country into four census regions and also produces a combined average circumcision rate of all regions. For circumcision, from 1994-2001, rates fluctuate by region, but the combined national average was approximately 60% of male neonates being circumcised. Since 2002, there has been a decline in all four regions.

The British Medical Association (BMA) Position

As of June 2006, the BMA's position was:

Circumcision for medical purposes: Unnecessarily invasive procedures should not be used where alternative, less invasive techniques, are equally efficient and available. It is important that doctors keep up to date and ensure that any decisions to undertake an invasive procedure are based on the best available evidence. Therefore, to circumcise for therapeutic reasons where medical research has shown other techniques to be at least as effective and less invasive would be unethical and inappropriate. Male circumcision in cases where there is a clear clinical need is not normally controversial. Nevertheless, normal anatomical and physiological characteristics of the infant foreskin have in the past been misinterpreted as being abnormal. The British Association of Paediatric Surgeons advises that there is rarely a clinical indication for circumcision. Doctors should be aware of this and reassure parents accordingly.”

Non-therapeutic circumcision: Male circumcision that is performed for any reason other than physical clinical need is termed non-therapeutic (or sometimes “ritual”) circumcision. Some people ask for non-therapeutic circumcision for religious reasons, some to incorporate a child into a community, and some want their sons to be like their fathers. Circumcision is a defining feature of some faiths.

There is a spectrum of views within the BMA's membership about whether non-therapeutic male circumcision is a beneficial, neutral or harmful procedure or whether it is superfluous, and whether it should ever be done on a child who is not capable of deciding for himself. The medical harms or benefits have not been unequivocally proven except to the extent that there are clear risks of harm if the procedure is done inexpertly. The Association has no policy on these issues. Indeed, it would be difficult to formulate a policy in the absence of unambiguously clear and consistent medical data on the implications of the intervention. As a general rule, however, the BMA believes that parents should be entitled to make choices about how best to promote their children's interests, and it is for society to decide what limits should be imposed on parental choices.

Australia and New Zealand

Routine Circumcision of Male Infants and Boys - Summary Statement:

The Pediatrics and Child Health Division. The Royal Australian College of Physicians (RACP) has prepared this statement on routine circumcision of infants and boys to assist parents who are considering having this procedure undertaken on their male children and for doctors who are asked to advise on or undertake it. After extensive review of the literature the RACP reaffirms that there is no medical indication for routine neonatal circumcision.

Circumcision of males has been undertaken for religious and cultural reasons for many thousands of years. It remains an important ritual in some religious and cultural groups. In Australia and

New Zealand, the circumcision rate has fallen considerably in recent years and it is estimated that currently only 10%-20% of male infants are routinely circumcised. Circumcision is now generally performed with local or general anesthesia, and when the procedure is carried out for a medical indication this is usually outside the neonatal period. The best recognized medical indication for circumcision is phimosis.

In recent years there has been evidence of possible health benefits from routine male circumcision. The most important conditions where some benefit may result from circumcision are urinary tract infections, HIV and later cancer of the penis.

Urinary tract infections affect 1%-2% of boys, and may be about 5 times less frequent in circumcised boys, whilst circumcision has a complication rate of 1% to 5%. On current evidence routine neonatal circumcision cannot be supported as a public health measure on this basis.

Whilst there is some evidence, particularly from sub-Saharan Africa, that male circumcision reduces the risk of acquisition of HIV, evidence is conflicting and would not justify an argument in favour of universal neonatal circumcision in countries with a low prevalence of HIV.

Penile cancer is a rare disease with an incidence of around 1 per 100,000 in developed countries. Even though the evidence suggests neonatal circumcision may reduce the risk 10-fold, the rarity of the condition and its other recognized predispositions are such that universal circumcision is not justified on these grounds alone. The complication rate of neonatal circumcision is reported to be around 1% to 5% and includes local infection, bleeding and damage to the penis. Serious complications such as bleeding, septicaemia and meningitis may occasionally cause death. The possibility that routine circumcision may contravene human rights has been raised because circumcision is performed on a minor and is without proven medical benefit. Whether these legal concerns are valid will be known only if the matter is determined in a court of law.

If the operation is to be performed, the medical attendant should ensure this is done by a competent operator, using appropriate anesthesia and in a safe child-friendly environment.

In all cases where parents request a circumcision for their child the medical attendant is obliged to provide accurate information on the risks and benefits of the procedure. Up-to-date, unbiased written material summarizing the evidence should be widely available to parents.

Review of the literature in relation to risks and benefits shows there is no evidence of benefit outweighing harm for circumcision as a routine procedure in the neonate.

South Africa and Botswana

In July 2006, President Thabo Mbeki of South Africa signed into law the Children's Act which contains a clause that no male under the age of 16 may be circumcised except when, "performed for religious purposes in accordance with the practices of the religion concerned", or "for medical reasons on the recommendation of a medical practitioner".

The Government of Botswana also recently mandated that all mothers of newborn boys should be counseled on the potential health benefits of circumcision. The Eastern Cape Province of South Africa recently legislated against traditional circumcision. The law raises concerns regarding parents' ability to choose to circumcise their male infants for future health benefits. The law was passed in attempt to curtail the rising number of circumcisions performed as part of traditional initiation school ceremonies resulting in serious medical complications or death. The provincial department of health says that 243 deaths and

216 genital amputations from circumcisions were recorded between 1995 and 2004. Last year there were more than 20 deaths. Furthermore, traditional surgeons must now be officially registered with the department of health. Many health care practitioners and human rights advocates point out that “medical grounds” allowing circumcision should be clarified.

Challenges

While the results of the clinical trials are extremely promising and can have enormous impact on the HIV epidemic, there are numerous implementation challenges, contextual considerations, and ethical concerns that require rigorous attention. We identify here 15 such challenges, and the list could probably be expanded. Nonetheless, we present these to encourage discussion, and to ensure that these issues are considered as new medical findings get released and implementation plans are drawn up. Furthermore, we hope that these challenges will enrich and add nuance to the discussions as to how MC should be offered as an HIV prevention intervention, and what steps need to be taken to ensure it is implemented in an ethical and effective manner.

We highlight the following:

1. **Acceptability:** Price, pain, and lack of complications seem to be universal concerns and need to be attended to in rollout of male circumcision. Rollout programs will consider these and other issues as plans for scale-up and implementation are considered.
2. **Level of protection:** The benefit from male circumcision is relative, not absolute, and communications strategies will need to be devised to reinforce this point clearly. Further, any rollout must take into account the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. Ideally, discussions of these issues will reinforce the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques will receive a needed boost in attention and funding.
3. **Risk** is typically defined in terms of medical risk; how can conceptions of risk be expanded to include social, psychological, cultural, or sexual factors? Acceptability on a population level, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.
4. Interventions using male circumcision (as with other technologies) absolutely require behavior modification and educational components. It will be essential to place male circumcision within a broad prevention context in order to avoid many of the difficulties that may be associated with it. Ideally, the introduction of male circumcision will be used as impetus to gain support for the wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies. Male circumcision may help to focus attention on *combination prevention* and the need to use multiple prevention strategies in concert.
5. It will be essential to maintain funding for broader commitments in the fight against HIV, especially with regard to fighting gender inequity, stigma, and other issues related to disease spread. The implications of MC can be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.
6. **Benefit to women:** How can male circumcision benefit women? How can male circumcision not harm women?

7. Religious and cultural practices need to be taken into account. Actual risk reduction, versus that of reduction rates achieved in controlled trials, is likely to have more regional variance and is dependent on local behaviors surrounding sexual practices, local drivers of the epidemic, and current prevalence rates.
8. The questions of when to circumcise—in infancy or adulthood—are hotly debated and will continue for some time. It may be easiest in infancy, but infants will not benefit immediately and cannot make informed choices.
9. Male circumcision and female genital mutilation (FGM): Opportunity to further distinguish the two? This raises at least two questions: a) whether promoting MC will in any way undermine current efforts to eliminate FGM, and b) how to understand the social and cultural discourses about the penis, about sexuality, and about sexual maturation that may all be affected, and potentially have positive or negative impacts on, an ostensibly neutral public health intervention.
10. Assessment and surveillance of safety and complications is essential to ensure that circumcisions are performed safely, that training is adequate, and that oversight is in place.
11. The challenges to health systems are enormous. The fact that health systems in many countries with high or growing HIV incidence are very poor and can not cope with the systemic or human resource requirements of an MC program without major additional short- and long-term investments. The estimated costs per circumcision could be significant when considering a developing country's per person health budget. The global experience with prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV (PMTCT) has already demonstrated the inability of global health systems to deliver on the promise of technical advances.
12. Male circumcision also needs to be considered and evaluated in a broader context of sexual and reproductive health, beyond the constraints of HIV alone.
13. Some have asserted that the trials and the calls for widespread implementation are being fueled by a form of racism. These issues need to be addressed seriously and included in the discussion.
14. It will be essential to determine how to avoid stigma associated with male circumcision or the lack of it.
15. It will also be essential to carry on the discussion around male circumcision to deliberately avoid branding men as perpetrators of infection.

Numerous ethical challenges will emerge as researchers define and apply the ethical principles of justice, beneficence, and respect for persons to current and future MC trials and research projects.

Challenge #1: Acceptability

The effectiveness of any circumcision intervention will be dependent on male uptake and community acceptance. In a review conducted by Westercamp et al, 13 acceptability studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa among non-circumcising communities were evaluated(33). Of these studies, 8 were designed to specifically investigate acceptability of MC, of which 4 included women. The median acceptability was 65% among men: 69% of women favored their partners being circumcised, and 81% of both men and women were willing to circumcise their male children. Variance in acceptability ranged from 29% in Uganda to 87% in Swaziland, and is at least partially attributed to how the questions were

posed and in what context. Higher acceptance rates were achieved when participants received information regarding the potential health risks and benefits. One of the highest acceptance rates was achieved by Halperin et al (2006), who asked participants if they would prefer circumcision if it was proven to have protective benefits against HIV(34). While the majority of studies on acceptability of male circumcision demonstrate general favorability, meaningful evaluation of available data requires understanding of diverse ethnic and regional specificities.

The three most common barriers to circumcision are costs associated with the procedure, fear of pain, and safety concerns. This suggests that public health and other bodies responsible for considering implementation of MC will need to ensure that the procedure is affordable, especially to the most vulnerable populations. Further, great care will need to be taken to ensure that the procedure is done as painlessly as possible and that adverse events occur as infrequently as possible.

Concerns related to costs vary from study to study; with some studies reporting that subjects feel that circumcision should be free and offered by government health clinics, other studies showing that participants perceive free or inexpensive circumcisions as being of lower quality. Notably, the cost of traditional circumcisions in some areas was viewed as prohibitive due to the costs associated with ceremony or initiation schools. In one study, 34% of participants initially opting to remain uncircumcised changed their minds when the proposed cost was set at US\$3.00. Similarly, a pilot intervention in Siaya, Kenya reported that men came in large numbers when the cost was set at US\$1.45. Concern for lost salary from missed work due to the healing period was also widely expressed these costs are difficult to quantify in economic projections.

Concerns regarding safety and pain are common. Many non-circumcising groups are familiar with circumcising practices of other groups, and cite the endurance of pain as a key component in the rite of passage. Furthermore, circumcision is widely understood as a surgical procedure with inherent risks. This concern is partially shaped by either personal knowledge or periodic media reports of complications or death. In general, most studies reviewed suggest a preference for circumcision to be provided by trained medical professionals in public health clinics. Given these results, it is likely that if male circumcision proves to have a protective benefit consistent with available results from ongoing clinical trials, acceptability is high enough to have a potentially significant impact on the reduction of HIV incidence. The greatest impact will be dependent on the age of intervention and among mixed- or non-circumcising areas that have high HIV prevalence rates(24).

Westercamp et al note that local regions of ethnically homogeneous non-circumcising groups may present greater resistance to circumcision interventions than ethnically diverse populations, insofar as circumcision may be identified as a break from identifying custom(33), although this may not be a universal trend. For example, Swaziland is a predominately non-circumcising country with high acceptability of circumcision as a protective technology.

The generalizability of any acceptability result may be limited by the context in which the study took place. One of the most important contextual factors is whether the epidemic is generalized or concentrated, and whether or not there is adequate availability of ARVs. In the United States, for example, male circumcision might not be viewed as necessary for the majority of the population because they are not at high risk for HIV, and ARVs are widely available and seemingly effective. African American, Caribbean, and large immigrant populations of males might be more interested, especially if they know that they are at extremely high risk for becoming infected with HIV. The procedure might have more attraction in sub-Saharan Africa, unless ARVs become widespread, inexpensive, and easy to access. Under those conditions, HIV might start to be seen as a more manageable, less lethal disease.

If male circumcision is a common practice, or is practiced by some groups and not others in a heterogeneous society, then individuals may feel more kindly disposed to it. If it is a foreign practice, or seen as something that some other religious or cultural group practices, then it may be less acceptable. The answers people give also depend on how the questions are asked and how well people can understand the concepts. If circumcision is proposed to prevent HIV, it may have greater acceptability than if it is proposed to prevent some other sexually transmitted infection, especially if that infection is quite treatable. If circumcision is proposed to prevent HIV, have people been told that the protection is not perfect, but is perhaps only 50% effective or maybe even less? What is the breaking point? Would it be 50% or 75% or 90%? When that concept is presented, do people understand that the probabilities refer to populations and not to individuals, and that the probability for a given individual in a given act of intercourse is either 0 or 1?

We do not understand enough about what determines acceptability for men and for women. Are men interested in male circumcision because it will render them more attractive to women (who might think that they are not susceptible to HIV)? Are they interested because they think it removes the need to use condoms? Are women interested in men being circumcised because they think it is less likely that the man will have HIV? Is it ethical to promote the intervention on an individual basis when we know the greatest public health impact would require wide scale rollout?

How price sensitive will circumcision be? Would incentives work to increase acceptance in specific situations? If a popular or important leader got circumcised or endorsed it for the population, would the procedure become more acceptable?

All of these questions are raised to reinforce the point that facile interpretations of acceptability studies are hazardous. Acceptability studies may need to use more sophisticated marketing strategies, and probably need to rely heavily on qualitative methods so that we can understand and "unpack" what people might mean when they say that male circumcision might be acceptable. And, acceptability will wax and wane over time. If people are getting circumcised, and the procedure goes well, many more may want it. If it is inexpensive, or even incentivized, many more may want it. If there are reports of serious adverse events, such as occurred in the Eastern Cape of South Africa(35-37), or if there are relevant sociocultural or ethical issues that are not adequately being tended to, then people may mistrust the medical establishment or not be so eager to expose themselves to the risk.

Challenge #2: The Benefit from MC is RELATIVE Not Absolute: How Can This Be Communicated?

Ideally, what might happen is that discussion of these issues reinforces the benefits of other prevention strategies, and all prevention techniques are given a needed boost in attention and funding.

Maintaining clear and nuanced communications about male circumcision will be difficult, when passions for and against the practice are so pronounced. We know from other circumstances, such as for the rollout of ARVs, that such passions cause people either to emphasize the problems or the benefits in ways that are not helpful for public discourse.

No single prevention technology or strategy will work on its own. All currently investigated strategies will require implementation in concert with one another. A vaccine providing 100% immunity is not likely to be developed in the short term, as fundamental questions about whether a highly effective preventive vaccine is even feasible remain unanswered. In the mean time, novel biomedical prevention strategies (such as microbicides, pre-exposure prophylaxis, etc) will be needed to effectively control the epidemic. As with MC, each of these strategies has the potential to lead to increased risk behavior. Caution should be emphasized so that the actual biomedical benefits of any investigational strategy are

not conflated with variables like risk behavior. Unlike other prevention strategies that are only as effective as the individual's ability to adhere to modified behavior or an ARV regimen, the protective benefits of male circumcision are disconnected from the actual risk behavior, making it an even more powerful strategy. The relative infection risk for each coital act remains the same. Increased risk behavior resulting from perceived protection of an intervention must be addressed in any strategy for rollout.

Any rollout must take into consideration the fact that male circumcision will be introduced into a relatively complicated prevention environment. The first complicating issue has been the (some would say unnecessary; others will say harmful) debate about abstinence, partner reduction, or condom use. The "abstinence, be faithful, use condoms" (ABC) approach to prevention has sparked debate about whether or not abstinence is better than partner reduction, and whether or not condoms provide sufficient protection against HIV and other STIs. The unfortunate consequence of this debate is that all three contribute to HIV prevention. Obviously, one cannot get HIV or an STI if one is abstinent, and delaying onset of intercourse may also render people less susceptible to HIV and other STIs. Older individuals' reproductive systems have matured to be more resistant to infection, and older individuals may be more capable of taking care of themselves emotionally and behaviorally. Reducing number of partners, especially concurrent partnerships, may reduce exposure to pathogens.

Nonetheless, some have seemed to pit one strategy against another, and disparage condoms in the process. This had lead to unnecessary confusion about the real and beneficial protective effect of condoms. The problem has been exacerbated by religious objections to condoms on the grounds that they might encourage promiscuity in an environment where abstinence and/or faithfulness within marriage should be supported (such discussions do not take into account that most women in sub-Saharan Africa, and perhaps in other regions, are put at risk for HIV and other STIs within the context of a marriage or committed relationship).

The second complicating issue is that the current prevention strategies--male and female condoms, prevention of mother-to-child transmission with ARVs, access to clean syringes and needles, voluntary counseling and testing for HIV, treatment for substance abuse (including substitution and maintenance chemotherapy for opiate abuse--have not been used widely at all. One could conclude that prevention has not worked because it has not been tried. The following chart, drawn from the work of the Global HIV Prevention Working Group and funded by The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, shows that fewer than one in five--just 4% to 16%--of people at high risk for HIV infection have access to effective prevention. The report goes on to state that access is particularly limited to populations known to be at especially high risk for infection, including sex workers, men who have sex with men, and injecting drug users (IDUs).

Percentage of Individuals at Risk with Access to HIV Prevention

Sources: UNAIDS, 2006; USAID et al., 2006

The report also cites the fact that the current supply of condoms falls 50% short of the number required, and the number of condoms needed annually is expected to increase significantly as the population of reproductive-age individuals increases by nearly 25% in some countries between 2000 and 2015.

Within this context, it is entirely possible that male circumcision will be hailed as the great new intervention, compensating for the significant failures of prior strategies when in fact those strategies

were never fully implemented. The unfortunate circumstance may be that progress toward implementation of the other strategies falls to the wayside and all hopes are pinned on male circumcision. This would be ethically irresponsible because, as we have reported, the effect of male circumcision will be relative and not absolute.

Challenge #3: Defining Risk, Benefit, and Harm Reduction

Population acceptability, societal perception, and implications for gender dynamics, sexual practices and other issues should be factored into these discussions and given appropriate weight.

Beneficence is an ethical principle that entails an obligation to protect persons from harm. The principle of beneficence can be expressed in two general rules: 1) do no harm, and 2) protect from harm by maximizing anticipated benefits and minimizing possible risks of harm. Minimal risk for male circumcision is usually understood as minimal medical risk. The common risk/benefit analysis presented in discussions of male circumcision is framed typically in terms of the biological or medical well-being of the individual.

It would appear that the current studies, and those responsible for them, have limited their perspective of risk to “medical risk” and are providing limited consideration to possible negative social or gendered impacts. Placing the risk/benefit calculus in a framework that only considers, or even emphasizes, the medical harm minimizes the social, cultural, or psychological impacts that are a necessary part of any risk/benefit calculation.

Medical risk and adverse consequences require accurate and appropriate surveillance and documentation. It might be possible, for example, that a few sensational adverse consequences will attract media attention and headlines, and cause confusion, much in the way that some toxicities associated with ARVs sometimes are exaggerated both in terms of effects on individuals and the prevalence of those effects. Thus, it will be essential, if rollout occurs, that systems be set up to understand the range and prevalence of adverse effects, and the conditions associated with those effects, and that such information be used to improve the surgery for further use. If, for example, more adverse events are associated with a particular type of medical practitioner, or with traditional practitioners, then that information needs to be used to improve quality of outcomes lest individuals and populations be put at needless risk.

There are also several ethical issues that remain around the balance of expectations concerning local and international standards of care before and after trials—and who determines them. One issue is who should provide the needed treatments and services. Major ethical debates are currently circulating about whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV-infected.

Risk and risk aversion have different meanings to different groups of people. The concept of risk perception is socially constructed and culturally imbedded within groups, and individual risk perception is perceived through this sensibility(38-41). Policy statements pertaining to routine male circumcision are no exception. The social and economic factors that inform risk perception by the American Academy of Pediatrics, the British Medical Society, or any other developed country may not be congruent with those of societies within developing countries in which the risk of morbidity or mortality resulting from HIV infection (or a host of other opportunistic infections) is considerably higher. For example, the AAP may focus on the immediate health of a neonate because the adult risk of HIV is not high in the United States and access to ARV therapy is widespread. In developing countries where there is an incredibly high risk of HIV infection and access to life-saving drugs has not materialized, risk perception may dramatically differ from that of the U.S. Multilateral and bilateral organizations based in the United States and Europe should ensure that, when considering the risk/benefit calculus of interventions targeted to high prevalence

areas, harm reduction is understood in terms of regionally specific health risks. Equally important will be assurances from governments and community members that an MC intervention may have a positive impact; these assurances may play an important role in guiding policy.

Challenge #4: Placing Male Circumcision in a Combination Prevention Strategy Context

Ideally, what could happen is that the introduction of male circumcision can be used as impetus to gain support for the wider use of all prevention technologies and strategies, and that male circumcision causes us to focus on “combination prevention” and the need to evaluate the use of multiple prevention strategies in combination.

Consider the following letter published in *The New York Times* on December 19, 2006.

To the Editor:

Although I am encouraged by the discovery that circumcisions can significantly reduce the chances of transmitting the virus that causes AIDS, I am a concerned about how people living in the third world will react to this news.

We do still live in a world where men with AIDS in Cambodia have unprotected sex with virgin girls in the belief that it will “cure” them, as Nicholas D. Kristof noted in his Dec. 12 column.

I’m concerned that more men will be circumcised as a result of these studies, but that they will then live an even more promiscuous life. We ought not lose sight of the importance of condom education.

Edmund DeMarche, Brooklyn, Dec. 14, 2006

And another letter said:

How do you persuade a man to snip off a protective skin on the most sensitive part of his body? Condoms are infinitely safer than circumcision.

Marshall Guerra, Chicago, Dec. 14, 2006

One issue here is that condoms are pitted against male circumcision in a totally unnecessary contest. We need both prevention strategies. A second is the disparaging language (addressed below).

What is needed is a framework that place MC within the context of a broader framework of prevention strategies and that does not isolate the strategy, thereby reinforcing the notion that it has the potential to address the complexities of HIV prevention by itself.

Such a framework was presented by Coates in the December 1, 2006 issue of the *Mail and Guardian* (Johannesburg). This is but one example; we encourage others to be developed:

For every person given antiretrovirals (ARVs) for HIV in South Africa, seven more become infected. If that continues, the health system will be completely overwhelmed. The advances of treatment in South Africa currently are groundbreaking. This must continue, expand and reach every person who needs drugs. Every HIV-infected person should know his or her status and be monitored so that treatment starts when he or she needs it. A good starting point would be a seven-point prevention plan, to counter the seven people that become infected for every ARV treatment. Promote HIV literacy: Received wisdom is that everyone knows about HIV and its transmission. The truth and the facts are muddled for many. That is partly the government's responsibility and partly because widespread information and messaging campaigns are imperceptible.

Goal 1: By 2010, 75% of adults score 100% on Aids literacy tests.

Promote HIV counseling and testing: People cannot plan their futures, take treatment or prevent transmission (including to babies) unless they know whether they have HIV. The biggest barriers to HIV testing are logistics and cost. We have found that bringing HIV testing to people--either through mobile or door-to-door testing--massively increases uptake. Mobile testing draws youth and especially young men.

Goal 2: By 2010, 75% of people have been tested for HIV at least once.

Protect young people: They are the future of South Africa. Access to accurate information, services and condoms are fundamental human rights. Young people vitally need them.

Goal 3: Prevalence of HIV among youth is reduced by 50% by 2010.

Prevent and treat substance use and abuse: Alcohol is probably a major driver of HIV transmission in South Africa, but other drugs such as tick and cat are spreading rapidly and could further fuel the pandemic.

Goal 4: What if every alcoholic beverage sold were accompanied by a condom? It would get the message across and demonstrate commitment to HIV prevention.

Get ready to circumcise: The results from Orange Farm's male circumcision study are the most hopeful we have had in HIV prevention since we found that ARVs can prevent mother-to-child transmission.

Goal 5: Circumcise 50% of men by 2010; advise 100% of parents of baby boys about circumcision and 75% opt for it.

Integrate prevention into treatment for HIV-positives: HIV can only spread from those who have it to those who don't. Treatment for HIV is wonderful, not only because it extends people's lives and brings hope, but also because it gives us the chance to interact with HIV positive people regularly.

Goal 6: By 2008, every HIV-infected patient is advised about safer sex at every clinic visit, every patient is offered a bag of condoms along with ARVs. An annual sexually transmitted infections check is offered to all HIV-infected patients.

Tackle stigma head-on: The popular paradigm is sad: if someone has HIV, they've been sleeping around and they bring shame on themselves and their families.

Goal 7: By 2010, 75% of South Africans regard HIV like any other disease, and that 75% of people with HIV disclose their status.

Challenge #5: Maintaining Broader Funding Commitments to Social and Behavioral Research and to Fighting Gender Inequality

The implications of MC would be helpful if, as a result of the ongoing MC clinical trials, the scientific community and those who support HIV/AIDS prevention were led to increase their commitment to all solutions to the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the broader fight against social inequalities that fuel the epidemic, such as gender inequality.

There is no vaccine to solve gender inequality or change behaviors, and the potential ethical implications of this larger over-reliance on biomedical solutions at the expense of social justice and human rights missions can't be dismissed. Finally, given the cost of circumcisions, the difficulty for health systems to scale up, and the lack of current attention in the field on the clear interaction between biomedical solutions and social and behavioral effects of interventions, some consider it unethical not to further promote behavioral prevention interventions financially, and in national-level communications at the same time as results and calls for further mass MC may roll out.

Challenge #6: How Will Male Circumcision Benefit Women? How Can Male Circumcision Not Harm Women?

There are two separate issues that must be considered: (1) benefiting women; and (2) shifting the disease burden toward women is a potential problem that may occur because the critical threshold to herd immunity cannot be achieved. Groups that advocate a cautious approach to male circumcision interventions increasingly voice this concern. The issue is that interventions that do not include adequate behavioral/educational components to ensure that the protective benefits of circumcision are not interpreted as allowing increased risk behavior among men, may in fact increase the risk to women. HIV-positive men are almost twice as likely to infect a female partner as an HIV-positive woman is to infect a male partner(42, 43). As a result, reducing the male prevalence rate would indirectly benefit the susceptibility of female partners. Modeling studies by Williams et al suggest that if male circumcision were to reduce female-to-male transmission by 60% as the Orange Farm clinical trial reports, it would have a population-level impact that reduced transmission in both directions by 37%(24).

Although mathematical modeling suggests that lowering the overall incidence of female-to-male transmission will lower prevalence rates for men and women (see *Herd Immunity* discussion above), and other studies suggest that MC combined with controlled viral burden in HIV-positive men will reduce transmission to their female partners, the degree to which MC as a prevention intervention will benefit women--or potentially increase their risk of infection--is uncertain and is a growing concern among social and behavioral scientists and policymakers. Of primary concern is that the sense of protection individuals associate with MC may lead to increased risk behaviors. Such behaviors could both diminish the

protective benefits and effectively shift the disease burden further toward women by increasing their risk. This argument is often framed as comparatively gauging the effective risk reduction for men and women separately. A strategy affording infection reduction to men that is misperceived as allowing more frequent risk behaviors may exacerbate existing gender disparities and further shift the disease burden to women.

Less obvious, but equally important, is addressing the underlying issues of why so much attention is given to the potential disinhibition of sexual behavior for male circumcision as a prevention strategy? Although there is some evidence regarding sexual disinhibition, there are conflicting results in various settings. Addressing behavioral disinhibition will have to accompany all prevention technologies (PrEP; viral load suppression; microbicides; vaccines; and even condom use, as inconsistent/improper use is pervasive). Some behavioral concerns regarding male circumcision may in part be linked to existing power discourses that connote specific gender and reproductive rights issues, (ie, coercive sex). Behavioral disinhibition would not be sufficient grounds to slow a prevention strategy that has such high potential for population impact. Behavioral disinhibition should be addressed in structuring effective messaging as part of rollout; it should not be used to withhold this technology (which in itself is counter to ethical principles of beneficence). While these issues are complex and are intimately related to prevention strategies, caution should be taken in distinguishing and evaluating with equal value the absolute biomedical harm or benefits of any strategy and its social impact.

Challenge #7: MC and Religious and Cultural Practices in the African Context

Historically, circumcision appears to have been practiced at one time or another throughout most of Africa, with the exception of the central inland east extending from southern Sudan to South Africa. Myriad circumcising and non-circumcising ethnic groups exist in both North and sub-equatorial Africa with diverse social histories. The practice, even among currently circumcising groups, was by no means consistently adhered to over time.

For groups that were not circumcising at the time of Colonial contact, there are at least two explanations for abandonment of the practice. The first is a less understood abandonment of circumcision and initiation schools in areas of south Malawi, Mozambique, parts of Zambia and Zimbabwe before arrival of the Europeans(44). The second explanation is better understood and relates to the Zulu wars in southern Zimbabwe and South Africa. The Zulu king Chaka ordered his people to stop the practice due to the difficulty of conducting initiation schools during the continuous period of fighting in the early 1800s. Many other groups that were also drawn into the fighting also abandoned the practice. That some groups readopted circumcision practices after the period of warfare, Jeff Marck explains as "...the general shifting of traditions and adopting other groups' styles and formats after long periods of abandonment"(44). Although the example of abandonment during the Zulu wars can not be generalized to the entire continent of Africa, it does provide an example of how circumcision patterns shifted because of historical factors even prior to Colonial imposition.

Religious beliefs are closely linked to the acceptability of circumcision. Islamic groups universally circumcise males. Many investigators have suggested the link between lower HIV prevalence rates in North Africa and the predominance of Islam and associated circumcising practices. As previously discussed, associating male circumcision in North Africa with lower HIV prevalence rates may be more complicated as sexual behavioral patterns among Muslims may have significant impact on curbing the spread of HIV(11, 44). In Africa, predominantly Christian groups have widely varying beliefs and inconsistent practices regarding male circumcision. In mapping the context of existing practices and strategies for potential interventions, local religious institutions and leaders should be involved, particularly where Christianity is prevalent.

Challenge #8: When to Circumcise: Infants vs. Adolescents vs. Adults?

The age at which circumcision is performed poses multiple challenges. Neonatal circumcision is considerably safer and substantially less expensive than adolescent or adult circumcisions(14, 15, 18, 45-49). If male circumcision proves effective and is only rolled out to neonates, it would take at least a generation before a population-level impact occurs. An adult intervention raises significant questions regarding the capabilities of existing health systems, increased complexity of the procedure, higher complication rates, and expense. Managing complications, and the associated costs, in resource-poor settings also raises significant concerns. Age at which a circumcision intervention is introduced is highly dependent on locally available capacity and training of staff. Surgical techniques that are feasible in resource-limited settings would have to be rapidly developed, as would clear guidelines for practitioners.

Modeling studies suggest that, although male circumcision could have an immediate and dramatic impact on HIV transmission, the full impact on prevalence rates and deaths would only be apparent in 10 to 15 years(24). Complicating the issue are the official statements, such as those cited in this document, regarding the advisability of infant circumcision, especially when such surgeries do not have an immediately beneficial therapeutic effect and/or the preventive impact will not occur for years.

Challenge #9: Taking the Opportunity to Further Distinguish MC from Female Genital Mutilation

The demand for male circumcision might lead to increased demand for female circumcision², especially in places where both practices are being carried out. The human rights reversals that are implied by this situation is one in which decades of work that has been carried out on fighting the harm of FGM to girls and women could be rolled back with implications for gender equity, rights, health, sexuality, and the body. Certainly, the ethical implications of attempting to make parallels between HIV outcomes with male circumcision and female genital mutilation are numerous. We advice caution and call for: a) extreme care around definitions of practices; b) warding off inaccurate parallels between MC and FGM; c) calls for action, advocacy, and media communications that ensure that inappropriate parallels are not made that would undermine long fought battles at the intersection of gender equality, women's rights, and harmful health outcomes on the issue of FGM; and d) consideration of a possible reinvigoration of human rights violations against girls and women if inappropriate parallels are made and actions supporting FGM moved forward.

The World Health Organization (WHO) describes the different types of FGM as follows:

- Type I - excision of the prepuce, with or without excision of part or all of the clitoris;
- Type II - excision of the clitoris with partial or total excision of the labia minora;
- Type III - excision of part or all of the external genitalia and stitching/narrowing of the vaginal opening (infibulations);
- Type IV - pricking, piercing or incising of the clitoris and/or labia; stretching of the clitoris and/or labia; cauterization by burning of the clitoris and surrounding tissue;
- Scraping of tissue surrounding the vaginal orifice (angurya cuts) or cutting of the vagina (gishiri cuts);
- Introduction of corrosive substances or herbs into the vagina to cause bleeding or for the purpose of tightening or narrowing it, and any other procedure that falls under the definition given above.

² Throughout this document we refer to female circumcision as female genital mutilation in compliance with World Health Organization's standard nomenclature.

The WHO reports that up to 80% of FGMs globally involve excision of the clitoris and the labia minora(50). The practice is conducted by several different cultures and religious groups. There are dramatic differences between FGM and male circumcision. FGM is partly structured to control a woman's sexuality and reposition it to focus on the male partner's pleasure. Removal of the clitoris eliminates the woman's ability to orgasm; and stitching the vaginal canal to make it smaller is carried out, in part, to increase male sexual pleasure due to tightening. Although significant medical and psychological morbidity has been documented, the perception of FGM by women in cultures that widely practice it varies. The importance of the practice as a group identifying marker and its cultural significance should be considered thoroughly when developing interventions intended to either eradicate the practice or minimize its severity (51). Comparisons to MC do significant violence to the global movement to eliminate the most severe forms of the practice. Male circumcision as an initiation practice is most often intended to signify either group affiliation or the transition from adolescents to adult status. From a cultural perspective, the intent is not to curtail or control the practice of one's sexuality. From a medical perspective, while circumcision may affect male sexual pleasure to a limited degree, circumcision as a public health measure is, at least in part, intended to keep men's sexual ability intact while providing protective benefits from disease.

Other than an unfortunate similarity in the naming of the procedures, male circumcision and female circumcision/FGM have no common health benefits. Male circumcision has been proven to reduce the risk of several sexually transmitted diseases, penile cancer, UTIs and a host of other diseases. FGM has no medical benefits and, in fact, may promote disease. The most severe forms of FGM are associated with tetanus infection, UTIs, gangrene, uterine infections, and other complications. In regards to HIV, UNAIDS has a clear position that, "There is no evidence or observational data that (female circumcision) would reduce the risk of HIV transmission; biologically, it is more likely to increase the likelihood of HIV transmission." Several recent studies of circumcised Tanzanian women have demonstrated the increased susceptibility to bacterial vaginosis and HSV-2, which are positively linked with HIV infection(52-54). The only biological-based similarity is that both procedures modify or remove sensitive tissues of the sexual organs.

Several possible components could be added to male circumcision interventions to ensure that participants do not believe similar benefits are gained from FGM. One possibility is to introduce joint counseling services for men and their female partners during the consent process. Additionally, male circumcision could be integrated as part of reproductive health services that provide both the circumcision procedure and family planning that distinguishes FGM from MC.

Challenge #10: Assessment and Surveillance of Safety and Complications

In developed countries it is difficult to accurately report complication rates as they vary widely depending on the type of study, setting, person performing the surgery, and most importantly, how complications are defined. This problem is compounded in resource-limited settings where multiple confounding factors may be present and basic sentinel surveillance is often limited. Limited data exists on the safety of male circumcision in resource-poor regions with high HIV prevalence. The procedure, whether conducted by traditional circumcisers or in medical facilities, is often conducted under suboptimal conditions, increasing the risk of immediate and future complications. Nevertheless, there is limited data suggesting that safe procedures utilizing accessible resources could be established in resource-limited settings. In a recent article, Krieger et al working in the Kisumu district of Kenya demonstrated that standard procedures for safe and acceptable MC services could be established in developing countries(55). The study used locally trained staff to conduct the procedures, and all supplies and instruments were locally obtained. In the United States, two large retrospective studies are often cited. The first, conducted by Wiswell et al reviewed the records of 136,086 boys from 1980-1985 for complications over the first month of life and found a 0.19% rate of complications, the majority being relatively minor(49).

The second study conducted by Christakis et al retrospectively reviewed the circumcision status of 354,297 neonates, of which 37% were circumcised, over 9 years (1987-1990) (56). The study reported a 0.20% complication rate, but also advised that although the procedure is relatively safe, “modest medical benefits may be offset by its complications.” The most common complications in both these studies were post-circumcision bleeding and infection. The major limitation to both of these studies is neither monitor or report complications after the newborn is discharged from the hospital. A longitudinal study following 500 New Zealand children from birth to 8 years post-circumcision reported an 11% complication rate (vs. 18.8% for uncircumcised males)(18). Although circumcision appears to provide a lifetime of numerous medical benefits, it is not without risk. The assessment of personal and public health benefit verses relative risk may differ dramatically by regionally specific confounding factors. In regions where high HIV prevalence rates expose the population to risks that have devastating impact on entire societies, the risks associated with MC may be outweighed by the potential lives saved. There is an urgent need to conduct further research on locally specific risks in resource-limited settings and to establish country plans for surveillance of procedures and complications.

Challenge #11: Health Systems Challenges

Implementation of male circumcision will be difficult and will strain the resources of health systems in many countries, especially those that need it the most. Prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) is still accessible to only 9% of mothers who need it, rising from 5% in 2003 to the current figure in 2005. Blood safety remains an important issue in several sub-Saharan African countries, and infection via occupational exposure (because safer devices or even clean needles and syringes are not accessible) also continues to occur.

Several issues emanate from this reality. The first is the need to continue to build and develop health systems in countries that most need it. HIV/AIDS has provided the opportunity to do so, especially given the aggressive targets for getting people onto ARVs.

But the second is the need to do so without distorting or diminishing resources from other critical aspects of the medical care system. The modeling done by Williams et al projecting thousands of new infections averted and overall reduction of prevalence rates were based on the results of the Orange Farm trial(24). With the release of the recent data from the Uganda and Kenya trials confirming the protective benefits found in Orange Farm, the Williams modeling gains further strength. The implications of averted new infections and reduced prevalence rates are that resources currently committed to combating HIV would be freed. While this is true, it will take time, as Williams points out that it would take approximately 10 years to reach the initial threshold of 2 million averted new infections and 20 years to reach approximately 6 million averted new infections (see discussion above, *Potential Benefits to Populations*). Each year would increase averted infections, presumably freeing funds. This means that substantial resources would initially need to be invested from international agencies to accommodate scale up of MC interventions and that funds could be re-allocated to other health systems needs as prevalence drops.

Immediate resource allocation will require comprehensive analysis as reduction in HIV prevalence could have a potential dramatic impact on available health system resources in the future. While achieving high rates of circumcision might be beneficial, it should not be at the cost of other disease prevention strategies such as antenatal care, malaria control, nutrition, etc. Since an internationally agreed-upon public health goal is for all women to give birth in health facilities, offering male circumcision in clinics to babies would at least not divert national resources from current efforts to build systems and might be a strategy that has multiple benefits. It might mean, however, that women have to remain longer in those settings and adequate resources will be essential to ensure that the goals might be met.

A major issue has to do with the need to ensure that there are sufficient personnel available to perform circumcisions, and whether or not the procedure necessarily needs to be performed by a physician, or whether medical officers, nurses or others can perform the surgery. Basic competency levels and certification that personnel are able to meet these standards must be established. An important issue highlighted in several XVI International AIDS Conference (Toronto, 2006) venues was the paucity of skilled health care personnel and the lack of proper medical training, even to perform the current tasks. Skilled, trained health care personnel are desperately needed to accommodate treatment needs in the context of wide-scale distribution of ARVs and appropriate follow-up treatment and care, particularly given the need for more widespread HIV testing scale up. In some contexts, many health workers received their medical training prior to the emergence of HIV, and therefore have little or no knowledge of the diagnosis and treatment of HIV and HIV-related illnesses. For some who received training after the onset of the epidemic, but prior to the availability of ARVs in their region, many still believe that HIV/AIDS is an invariably terminal and unmanageable condition. Those aware of ARVs may lack the knowledge to administer them properly.

In other contexts, community-based workers who may be lacking “formal” health-care training are delivering the highest standard of care. Volunteers have played important roles in counseling and care, but investment is needed to bridge the gap and maintain consistency in quality of care for the long term, since altruism alone may be inadequate in providing sustained motivation for volunteer involvement in long-term health programs, particularly in high-burden settings where volunteers may be subject to many of the same environmental conditions contributing to disease(57).

The South African (Orange Farm), Kenyan, and Ugandan MC randomized clinical trials all employed highly trained medical staff in controlled environments to perform the surgical procedure. As would be expected, complications in these controlled settings are relatively low; Orange Farm, the only trial of the three to report results, reported a 3.8% complication rate. Low complication rates may be significantly higher outside a controlled clinical trial environment. Questions pertaining to safety, human resources, and adequate medical training in resource-poor environments remain a high concern. A recent study in Ibadan, Nigeria reported a 20.2% complication rate among a cohort of 322 circumcised male infants ranging in age from 8 days to 13 months in which circumcisions were performed by nurses (55.9%), doctors (35.1%), and traditional circumcisers (9%)(58). Over eighty percent of these circumcisions were performed in a hospital setting. Other studies in Nigeria and Kenya cite complications rates (of varying severity) ranging from 12-17.5% in hospital settings.

Returning to Williams’ modeling, any initial intervention will take time (nearly a decade) before a dramatic impact is seen on population-level prevalence. It is unlikely that a rapid response that will achieve sufficient coverage to avert millions of new infections over the next decade can be achieved without a scale up that does not solely rely on physicians or nurses.

Health Care Infrastructure. For men who undergo an important initiation into manhood when circumcision is performed by a “traditional” surgeon (as is the case for many men in South Africa), there may be important reasons to provide solid training to those outside of the medical establishment to support important cultural rites of passage and their continuation. It is unethical not to further promote behavioral prevention interventions. What if demand outstrips capacity? Where will men get this done? What are the ethical implications of putting forward a practice and suggesting it *en masse* if families have to eventually decide, due to lack of health care capacity, which person they will or will not circumcise?

Incorporating trained and certified traditional circumcisers and nurses should be considered. It is likely that traditional circumcision practices will continue, regardless of regulatory mandates limiting them(35, 36). It is also conceivable that if circumcision receives the same level of acceptability reported from studies, and health care systems are incapable of meeting demand, unregulated and unsafe circumcisions

may rise dramatically. The ability to incorporate these providers into scale up provides several advantages including the reduced strain on existing health care systems, a more rapid scale up, and the ability to regulate and monitor circumcision conducted in a cultural context. Equally important will be engaging traditional circumcisers and potentially incorporating the complex social dynamics associated with traditional ceremony into a population-level intervention that could avert millions of deaths. Finally, as discussed above (see *Acceptability*), religious and cultural leaders have substantial influence on circumcision practices and, as Westercamp recommends, should be consulted prior to any intervention. They could present significant barriers if they are not engaged in scale up (33).

Challenge #12: Placing Male Circumcision Within a Broader Context of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Beyond the Constraints of HIV Alone

The intensification of linkages between sexual and reproductive health (SRH) and HIV/AIDS is not simply a service issue but is at the core a policy and program issue as well. These linkages are complex and involve family planning, maternal and infant health, management of STIs, and management of other sexual and reproductive health (SRH)-related issues on the one hand, and HIV/AIDS prevention, treatment, care, and support on the other.

Areas where key linkages need to be made include VCT, the promotion of safer sex, STI management, tending to the SRH of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWH/A), tending to the primary health care of PLWH/A, integrating HIV/AIDS prevention and care into maternal and reproductive health, examining SRH and safer sex between discordant couples, and optimizing other connections between HIV/AIDS and SRH (eg, gender-based violence, female condoms). The challenge here is to place the discussion and advancement of male circumcision within this broader context and not restrict the discussion to HIV/AIDS alone.

Male circumcision provides the additional benefit for partners intending to have children. It provides a level of protection against HIV, STIs, and HPV while allowing for pregnancy.

Challenge #13: Perceptions of Inequitable Power Relations between the North and the South and Reinvigorations of Essentialized Notions of Male Sexuality

The power relations implied by the way in which developed countries are carrying out trials in developing countries for a practice that has finally been declared medically unnecessary for babies in the West may be tainted with unfortunate accusations of new forms of colonialism(59). While these accusations are relatively few, and have come from adamant opponents to routine MC, they have the potential to distract from important questions of scale up. Nevertheless, there are significant ethical concerns pertaining to MC randomized trials. Trials are being carried out consistently in Africa, when several other countries, including the inner-city United States, clearly have significant epidemics. While they may not be as severe as many regions in Africa experiencing generalized population-wide epidemics, they are nonetheless local epidemics. What are the ethical issues around “exporting” a rejected practice from the West (eg, AAP, BMA, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, etc) to the South, while not calling for implementation of it in the West too?

The ethical principle of justice asks questions about who ought to receive the benefits of research and bear its burdens. This is an issue of social justice, in the sense of considering fairness in distribution or what is deserved. An injustice occurs when some benefit to which a person is entitled is denied without good reason or when some burden is imposed unduly. Thus, some may argue that the principle of justice would center on whether particular racial and ethnic minorities or individuals in particular regions of the world are being systematically selected for participation in MC trials simply because of their easy availability, their compromised position, or their manipulability, rather than for reasons directly related to

the problem being studied. As the medical, prevention, public health, and advocacy communities are perched to hear the results of upcoming trials, these issues will undoubtedly and increasingly come to the fore.

Thus, the ways in which developed countries are carrying out trials in developing countries for a practice that has been declared medically unnecessary for the West may also invariably reinvigorate racist perceptions of sexuality and African masculinity in regions where the trials are not conducted. Specifically, MC trials have already likely reinvigorated perceptions that the epidemic is largely “heterosexualized”—that men’s sexual behavior is problematic and “excessive”—only to be contained by medical surgery and an essentializing notion of male sexuality. No matter how acceptable MC may be internally to communities in various regions, the gaze of external audiences might stigmatize men in regions not experiencing the severity of the sub-Saharan African generalized epidemic. Perceptions of race are fluid, and racial formation is influenced by both proximal (local) and global factors. Diasporic communities of African men, their descendants, and men whose ancestry is of the global South are influenced and shaped by the gaze of the West on Africa. That is, the assumed relationship that men of color in the Global South have to their own (and others’) bodies and sexuality under a suggested roll out of MC—that some men are more moral and can contain themselves while others need surgery on their genitals so as to not impose damage on the populace—may become part of the public perception and this stigmatizing effect has been left out of studies and commentaries on trials thus far. While individuals in other nations will not bear the ethical brunt of the implications of the science in this way, men in the Global South may not be able to avoid it, and trials might exacerbate erroneous perceptions that men are perpetrators of the disease and responsible for it. Additionally, there is a need to investigate how MC as a HIV prevention strategy may affect social and cultural meanings about the role of the penis in constructing men’s sense of themselves and their sexuality.

Challenge #14: Avoiding Stigma Associated with Male Circumcision or the Lack of It

Remarks at the XVI International AIDS Conference in Toronto in 2006 placed the importance of female-initiated methods of HIV/STI prevention (and especially microbicides) at center stage. The comments were important and useful, and it was refreshing to see major leaders talking about equity, prevention, female-controlled methods, and condoms. The choice of words revived a familiar and important discourse that was not critically examined deeply enough at the conference. The resurgence of an individualist innocence discourse brought to the fore the need to advance rights-based approaches to HIV prevention and care without falling into the trap of morality, judgment, and blame.

This innocence discourse, long used to set apart babies, hemophiliacs, faithful wives, and orphaned children as deserving of protection and health services, might be a way to make condoms (and other prevention strategies) palatable to politicians and others. However, such discourse may perpetuate stigma, minimize structural factors that affect both women’s and men’s HIV risks, and does not deal with issues of marginalized populations (eg, MSM, commercial sex workers, and IDUs).

Lurking just below the surface in many presentations is the belief or perception that people in certain countries or regions are more promiscuous, more callous, less empathic, or less moral. For numerous reasons, some are framed as more damaged from their past and present environments than others. All too quickly, this can slide into discussions of morality, “excessiveness,” or personal responsibility. The ensuing conversations about sexuality may be too individualized (or group-based) and become a justification for racism and inequitable judgments on populations from the Global South (or inner cities of the North). Also lurking below the surface is the attitude and expectation that people living with HIV should abstain or minimize sexual activity and refrain from pursuing a full sex life, including procreation.

In this context, the questions are these: Will those men who choose not to become circumcised be branded as risky? Will they be assumed to have HIV infection? Will they be stigmatized as individuals not willing to do all that they can to reduce the spread of HIV? Will parents of young women want certification of circumcision in the male partners of their daughters?

Further, the need remains to better understand sexual behaviors and sexuality in diverse populations, as well as the needs of sexual minorities, especially in places where discrimination, stigma, and legal sanctions are practiced. Any discussion of male circumcision, and its advisability for specific populations, needs to be placed in this context.

Challenge #15: Avoiding Discourse That Brands Men as Perpetrators of Infection

In the present context, the challenge is this: Will advancement of male circumcision further brand men as perpetrators? Will male circumcision be seen as “the answer” to the need to change conceptions of masculinity in society? Will efforts to modify male social norms and behaviors be given short shrift in the desire to advance male circumcision more generally?

There were new and important emphases at the Toronto AIDS conference placed on structural inequities facing women and how to adequately respond with new interventions at this level (eg, educational and economic interventions, property rights, continued legal reform). But most sessions referred to gender as a women’s issue, and there were few sessions on gender relations, men, and masculinity. Even fewer sessions examined the role of racism in the exacerbation of the epidemic. Some of the discourse and research framed “problems” related to the epidemic as the fault of individual men instead of examining a system of interlocking race, class (or caste), age, and gender relations. Overall, particularly strong vilification of African men occurred throughout the conference.

Improving gender equality will go a long way toward resolving some of the most powerful dynamics of HIV transmission. It will remain important to examine the disenfranchisement that both women and men face, and to develop programs to fight structural inequities. Vigilance will be required in order to avoid the trap of individualizing problems/solutions that pit men and women against one another. A rights-based agenda can advance women’s status and reduce their HIV/AIDS risks, and hence a women’s empowerment agenda needs to be advanced.

However, it also remains vital that discourse and research find a more accurate way to describe men and masculinities, particularly as these intersect with race, class/ caste, sexuality, and nationality, in order to take a comprehensive gender relations agenda forward. One writer for *The Toronto Globe and Mail* said, “...changing the behaviour of African men is probably hopeless.” These kinds of stereotypes of African men serve to entrench both a highly racialized perspective on African males’ sexuality, moral depravity, and common modes of thought about gender, rather than advancing these discussions. African men are being portrayed as vectors, unconcerned about others and spreading disease along with violence and neglect for families.

What Research Needs to Be Conducted?

We provide here a list of ideas, in no particular order, about research initiatives that might be undertaken to address some of the challenges articulated above. We anticipate expanding this list as people reading this and other reports consider these issues and challenges.

1. What is the effect of male circumcision on female partners—not just related to HIV, but also sexually transmitted infections (STIs), cervical cancer, female pleasure, and female perceptions of sexual viability of the male partner?
2. There are often few ethical guidelines on the social and behavioral effects of biomedical trials—only medical effects and adverse events are examined. Social and behavioral effects need to be defined, and studies need to be carried out on the positive and negative consequences related to study participation.
3. Is penile hygiene as good as MC? Clinical trials that include a penile hygiene study arm should be conducted. These studies should also conduct analyses of feasibility, required resources, and infrastructure requirements.
4. Although much cost analysis, particularly in the United States, has been conducted to project the cost savings from averted HIV infection, STIs, and urinary tract infections (UTIs), there is a lack of data projecting the costs of treating circumcision-related complications. How will complications be addressed in resource-poor settings?
5. The development of models that include cost analysis for training practitioners in resource-poor settings is urgently needed. Modeling should project the cost of equipment and its maintenance, and the treatment of complications. These projections should be comprehensive modeling strategies including PMTCT, condom provision, voluntary counseling and testing (VCT), and treatment.
6. Interventions that combine reproductive health services, HIV VCT, and male circumcision should be explored.
7. Should MC rollout begin, it is essential that surveillance systems be put into place to track who is presenting for services, incidence of adverse events, and disinhibition in circumcised populations.
8. Qualitative studies that shed light on people’s understanding of protection afforded by male circumcision—both for males and females—will be essential. It will be important to repeat these over time as events change. The perspective of parents will also need to be included.
9. Prevention models that include male circumcision, but do not focus on it exclusively, are needed to elucidate how male circumcision can be incorporated into a broader prevention framework.
10. Legal research is needed to understand barriers and facilitators of male circumcision, and the protections necessary to maximize benefits and reduce harms.
11. Stigma remains a central impediment in HIV prevention. Understanding how male circumcision reduces or enhances stigma will be essential.

Ethical Issues for Future Research

As human subjects protections committees (HSPCs) or institutional review boards (IRBs) are only beginning to define what the social and behavioral effects of participation in a biomedical trial are (with emphasis only on “adverse events”), the field should attempt to be ethically ahead of the curve on these

issues and not wait for protests that may soon follow (a letter of caution has already been written by many leading thinkers in the field to the WHO asking for immediate consideration of ethical issues such as these to be taken into account).

Ethical Issues Related to Informed Consent

There is anecdotal information that men in several areas of high HIV prevalence are eager to be circumcised. One rather large ethical implication of these trials for future research involves the question of how consent is given by men. In some instances, researchers' may have meetings with community leaders—often including traditional, tribal, and political leaders—who then lead discussions with men, who subsequently volunteer.

But the actual question remains as to whether individuals within a village can maintain the ability to individually refuse participation while the village is being strongly encouraged to participate from its leaders. Additionally, the extent to which full disclosure about the risks and benefits are being offered to men at the group or individual level (particularly given the lack of sociocultural, gendered, tribal, or other cultural factors in the definition of risk/benefit calculation). The extent to which men feel coerced or pressured into volunteering have not been evaluated.

Ethical Implications for Past, Present, and Future Trials

Circumcision does not have a strong history of being systematically and ethically examined prior to claims being made about its ability to resolve health problems. The historical record shows that it has been claimed to prevent hydrocephalitis, persistent masturbation, epilepsy, insanity, tuberculosis, spinal paralysis, hip dysplasia, STIs, penile cancer, cancer of the tongue, and more.

IRB Principles of Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice

Recognized principles that guide the ethical conduct of research are respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. To what extent are these being adequately considered in the current trials?

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that requires that individual autonomy be respected and that persons with diminished autonomy be protected. Here, it is clear that autonomy refers to requirement that subjects, to the degree that they are capable, be given the opportunity to choose what shall or shall not happen to them. This opportunity is provided when adequate standards for informed consent are satisfied.

Some ethical issues linked to respect for persons and autonomy include:

1. Prior comments we have made concerning the way in which researchers seek the consent of participants are relevant here. The process through which consent is being obtained in MC trials is not being critically examined, particularly given the differential relationship that individuals from non-Western countries can have to the medical establishment (eg, individual consent vs. group or village level decision-making processes).
2. If recommendations are made for mass MC for neonates, the medical establishment will be recommending a permanent surgical procedure for a child who does not have the right to decide something about their own body, the consequences of which would not even be relevant until they are sexually active.

3. Full evaluation of risks and benefits is needed in order to say that one responded with informed consent to voluntarily participate. Yet, risks and benefits that we have delineated throughout this document are not currently fleshed out beyond medical risk.
4. Autonomy should also be respected in terms of respecting the fact that individuals who are HIV tested in trials may not want to receive their results. At the same time, researchers should track the behaviors of such individuals, as it is known that such individuals engage in higher risk behavior.
5. Language issues—are consent forms clear? Do people understand what is being said?

Beneficence is an ethical principle that entails an obligation to protect persons from harm. The principle of beneficence can be expressed in two general rules: (1) do no harm; and (2) protect from harm by maximizing anticipated benefits and minimizing possible risks of harm. Some ethical issues related to beneficence:

1. What are the risks—medical risks and beyond—and are they worth the benefits? Furthermore, since we do not know how behavioral factors will interact with medical aspects of risk, how can we accurately ensure protection under the principle?
2. Stigma is an issue related to both beneficence and justice. After all, entire communities may be stigmatized by the mere fact that large, well-publicized HIV/AIDS research is being conducted in them. Previous issues raised in this document about perceptions of male sexuality, masculinity, racism, and beliefs that certain men are responsible for the perpetration of disease while others are not are highly relevant.
3. Are there reductions in sexual pleasure, sexual functioning, and changed self- or sexual-concept for men? Are these, on balance, worth the benefits? How shall this be decided and by whom?
4. Properly weighing risks/benefits not just to men but also to women will remain an important ethical and practice issue.
5. As has been noted, there is no consensus on how to properly balance expectations concerning local and international standards of care before and after trials—and who decides. Who should provide the needed treatments and services is a key issue. Major ethical debates are currently circulating about whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV -infected.

The principle of **justice** asks questions about who ought to receive the benefits of research and bear its burdens. As we have noted, this is an issue of social justice, in the sense of considering fairness in distribution or what is deserved. An injustice occurs when some benefit to which a person is entitled is denied without good reason, or when some burden is imposed unduly.

Some ethical issues related to justice:

1. As we have noted, are men from particular areas of the world—or particular racial and ethnic minorities—being systematically selected for participation in MC trials simply because of their easy availability, their compromised position, or their manipulability, rather than for solid reasons directly related to the problem being studied?
2. Are poor communities able to bear the burdens of research and can they truly benefit from it despite the complexities of poverty or a lack of infrastructure?
3. With the exception of adverse events, inadvertent positive and negative consequences of research participation are not generally tracked. These could be defined and tracked in order to adequately assure adherence to principles of justice—and define new ones if needed.
4. Relatively privileged researchers may feel motivated to contribute to the reduction of social inequality through health research but this may be carried out at the expense of local communities, as Western definitions can exacerbate situations on the ground. Key to the local research experience might be the way in which “risk,” “benefit,” or “acceptable” are defined for communities that may or may not be adequate for the region.
5. Some believe that researchers from rich countries contribute to sustaining poverty in poor countries (eg, through exploitation of cheap labor, unsound trade rules, requiring debt payments that are not payable, histories of colonialism) and thus they have an ethical obligation to transfer resources (and not just public health requirements or suggestions) to reduce gross injustices(60).
6. Studies have elucidated how power relations between developing and developed countries have resulted in the misperception that Western science and its interventions are perceived by study participants as definitively “working”, even when, for example, candidate microbicides may be investigated for acceptability and not efficacy(61). No matter how clear informed consent may be concerning risks/benefits, levels of protection, and the need for behavioral change, individuals might feel that an intervention that comes from Western science is one that unequivocally “works.” True dangers therefore exist that misperceptions will occur regarding the partial protection afforded by MC. Qualitative research needs to be conducted to investigate men’s and women’s perceptions of protection afforded over the long run.

Standards of Care

Determining what the standard of care should be during and after clinical trials can be complex, particularly when examining the differential resources available to resource-rich and resource-poor countries (and middle-income countries). Debates about standards of care required in placebo arms of drug trials initially emerged in 1999, and were modified and rewritten in 2000 due to ethical debates about randomized controlled trials of PMTCT. At the time, placebo-controlled study arms were being used, rather than comparing the experimental regimen to another that was either a) an acceptable standard treatment around the world or b) a local standard treatment. Debates raged about whether control arms should be constituted according to “the highest standard in the world,” “the highest standard of care practically attainable in the country in which research is being carried out,” or “placebo control.” At first, the World Medical Association proposed that placebos should be used in trials by arguing that the standard of care should not be the “highest in the world” but rather “the highest standard of care practically attainable in the country in which research is being carried out.” However, other arguments emerged to underscore that the standard of care that is “practically attainable” might mean anything from state-of-the-art to clearly substandard treatment; on the lower end, this could certainly violate the

principle of beneficence known as “do no harm.” As a result of these debates, in October 2000 in Helsinki, the World Medical Association released a new version of the Declaration to argue that placebo arms were prohibited in “situations of local scarcity” if the “best current method” existed elsewhere. Relevant issues related to standards of care in MC trials involve debates about what will constitute standard of care during and after trials, and who will decide.

Some relevant issues are:

1. There are several ethical issues that remain about local and international standards of care before and after trials and for potential rollout. Who should provide HIV and non-HIV treatment and care services for trial participants in resource-limited health systems is a major issue. Ethical debates are also focusing on whether public health interventions can or should provide treatment, and for how long, if participants are found to be HIV-positive. In countries where ARV rollout is incomplete, what if MC trial participants are among the few in their communities who receive ARV treatment?
2. The above relates to the question of how dual standards of care shall be dealt with. In short, it is not uncommon for trial participants to receive more or better access to health care than others in their communities due to their participation in research. This can result in problems within families, communities, and health systems. Some argue that this can lead to “undue inducement” to participate in research and that large payments for trial participation should not be made to participants, as this might further exacerbate undue inducement and interfere with the principle of autonomy.
3. A basic principle of standard of care is that researchers or sponsors of trials should make successful interventions available to the host country after research is completed.
4. Some believe that researchers from resource-rich countries have an ethical obligation to transfer resources to improve the overall standard of care in health systems (and not just offer public health suggestions) to reduce gross injustices in resource-poor countries(60). The argument is that sustainable improvements in health come from improvements in the health care system-- researchers from resource-rich countries are ethically obligated to improve standards of care in the health care system where research occurs. How this would actually happen is not clear.
5. Several opportunities may exist to improve standards of care in health systems. For example, there is the opportunity to integrate male circumcision within broader male sexual, reproductive health, and HIV prevention strategies. Needs assessments and capacity building assistance in various contexts is much needed on this and various other standard-of-care improvements.

Conclusions: Possible Steps Forward

Because the Kenya and Uganda MC trials replicated the results of the already completed Orange Farm study, at least in providing evidence that HIV infection is reduced for males who are circumcised vs. those who are not, immediate steps should be taken to engage stakeholders in formulating assessment of potential MC scale up. It remains an open question as to whether or not the evidence will be similarly strong to support the hypothesis that circumcising HIV-infected men reduces transmission to their partners.

Because all three trials presented similar and convincing data, the pressure will begin mounting for broad implementation of male circumcision, especially in high-prevalence areas such as sub-Saharan Africa,

parts of India, and perhaps Eastern Europe. Questions will arise regarding the benefits of male circumcision for concentrated epidemics—such as are occurring in the United States, many parts of Spanish-speaking Latin America, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, and China—and especially when these epidemics involve primarily men who have sex with men, where the main risk is from receptive anal intercourse. Questions will continue to arise about the benefits of infant vs. adolescent or adult circumcision. Controversies will continue to rage as to whether male circumcision is mutilation, or whether it is justified for health, religious, and cultural reasons.

Because there may be a disconnect between the MC lobbying forces in Europe and the United States and those voices from the areas most impacted by HIV, it is important to ensure comprehensive inclusion of all positions, and that these positions are identified by local origin and are evidence based.

We have presented challenges to ensure comprehensive coverage of medical, social, and structural issues related to MC as a prevention strategy. The challenges are not intended to discourage the use of male circumcision for HIV prevention nor are the challenges intended to slow the development of potential interventions. Indeed, if the effectiveness of male circumcision in real practice approaches the results from the three clinical trials, the practice can potentially avert thousands of new infections and dramatically reduce prevalence of infection in entire populations.

Further, we do not present these challenges as a “social science” reaction to a decidedly medical HIV prevention strategy. All advances in HIV prevention are welcome and encouraged.

Rather, we present these challenges to ensure that the discussion regarding the evolution and rollout of male circumcision reflects the full range of issues that should be considered for individuals and for populations. We believe that there are benefits to this kind of discussion that will strengthen policy and application. We think it essential that laws, policies, and programs reflect the full reality of concerns and issues, especially for a practice as radical and potentially helpful as male circumcision.

Next steps:

- We encourage broad dissemination of this and similar monographs as a way to stimulate discussion of the points made. Articles should also be prepared for the scientific literature, and for general readership, to ensure dissemination and discussion of the ideas.
- Encourage the development of national strategic plans for countries with the highest prevalence rates. These plans should include assessment of current capacity, the development of a single sentinel surveillance and reporting mechanism, clear guidelines on basic standards of care, plans for complication triage, measurable targets, cost analyses, and specific assessment of internal ethnic group practices.
- Engagement of traditional practitioners and religious groups should be paramount. The development of national plans should include them. Ongoing research on the ethnic and cultural dynamics of scale up should be encouraged.
- Additional modeling should be done. The important modeling done by Williams et al relies on only the Orange Farm data and assumes high uptake. Modeling projections that estimate varying degrees of uptake and additional factors such as combination prevention strategies (MC + ARVs or MC + condoms) should be undertaken.
- In preparation for scale up, widespread public information campaigns should be developed that describe the risks and benefits.

- The development of regionally specific “tool kits” for ministries of health that outline standards, triage, and surveillance techniques. These kits would include manuals and modules for training of practitioners as well as “training of trainers.”
- Technical support for country-level scale up should be sought from NGOs and multilaterals.
- One or more think tanks might be beneficial to flesh out ideas, test them with larger groups of people, and to modify the points made here and add to them. Such think tanks should involve key opinion leaders. It might be useful to think of global events, as well as regional or country-level meetings, that could serve as opportunities to stimulate thinking and discussion.
- From these think tanks could emerge briefings for policymakers, program planners, and implementers. Obviously, such efforts should coincide with those of the multilateral and bilateral implementing agencies (WHO, UNAIDS, World Bank, PEPFAR, USAID, DFID, etc), so that people charged with making funding and programmatic decisions are not receiving contradictory advice. Nonetheless, we would hope that briefings would allow for the full range of issues to be raised in these discussions so that programs and policies can be advanced that take into account all of the necessary information and perspectives.
- International standards for MC should be developed that are flexible enough to respond to local need.
- It would be useful to stimulate research on some of the specific topics outlined, and especially to encourage country- and regional-level research that will have applicability for local advocacy, legal and policy issues, sexual and reproductive health, and religious and cultural perspectives.
- Specific focus needs to be given to ethical discussion, studies, and guidelines, as these issues are among the most difficult in the field of HIV prevention, especially regarding male circumcision in the context of research and in practice.
- We also encourage a focus on stigma, as it is possible that male circumcision could have a beneficial effect on HIV/AIDS stigma. It is also possible that male circumcision could result in increased stigma for individuals who do or do not undergo the surgery.
- The feasibility of comprehensive reproductive services targeting both men and women that include the provision of MC and associated counseling and messaging, as well as family planning, STI counseling, the provision of condoms, contraceptive devices, and VCT services should be considered.
- We think it would be useful to track media coverage of the issue. If one searches Google for “male circumcision,” an extremely varied array of viewpoints are found. Many of these take the perspective that male circumcision is genital mutilation. Media coverage of the issue might illuminate the various ways that people are thinking about the issue, and also highlight confusions that might be generated in populations.

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Annotated Bibliography of Key Literature

(Wiswell and Geschke 1989; Moses, Bradley et al. 1990; Christakis, Harvey et al. 2000; Gray, Kiwanuka et al. 2000; Quinn, Wawer et al. 2000; Schoen, Wiswell et al. 2000; Siegfried, Muller et al. 2003; Auvert, Taljaard et al. 2005; Christoffersen-Deb 2005; Cohen 2005; Malone 2005; Schoen 2005; Siegfried, Muller et al. 2005; Wawer, Reynolds et al. 2005; CDC 2006; Donoval, Landay et al. 2006; Fergusson, Boden et al. 2006; Westercamp and Bailey 2006; Williams, Lloyd-Smith et al. 2006)

Auvert, B., D. Taljaard, et al. (2005). "Randomized, controlled intervention trial of male circumcision for reduction of HIV infection risk: the ANRS 1265 Trial." *PLoS Med* 2(11): e298.

BACKGROUND: Observational studies suggest that male circumcision may provide protection against HIV-1 infection. A randomized, controlled intervention trial was conducted in a general population of South Africa to test this hypothesis. **METHODS AND FINDINGS:** A total of 3,274 uncircumcised men, aged 18-24 y, were randomized to a control or an intervention group with follow-up visits at months 3, 12, and 21. Male circumcision was offered to the intervention group immediately after randomization and to the control group at the end of the follow-up. The grouped censored data were analyzed in intention-to-treat, univariate and multivariate, analyses, using piecewise exponential, proportional hazards models. Rate ratios (RR) of HIV incidence were determined with 95% CI. Protection against HIV infection was calculated as $1 - RR$. The trial was stopped at the interim analysis, and the mean (interquartile range) follow-up was 18.1 mo (13.0-21.0) when the data were analyzed. There were 20 HIV infections (incidence rate = 0.85 per 100 person-years) in the intervention group and 49 (2.1 per 100 person-years) in the control group, corresponding to an RR of 0.40 (95% CI: 0.24%-0.68%; $p < 0.001$). This RR corresponds to a protection of 60% (95% CI: 32%-76%). When controlling for behavioural factors, including sexual behaviour that increased slightly in the intervention group, condom use, and health-seeking behaviour, the protection was of 61% (95% CI: 34%-77%). **CONCLUSION:** Male circumcision provides a degree of protection against acquiring HIV infection, equivalent to what a vaccine of high efficacy would have achieved. Male circumcision may provide an important way of reducing the spread of HIV infection in sub-Saharan Africa. (Preliminary and partial results were presented at the International AIDS Society 2005 Conference, on 26 July 2005, in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.).

CDC (2006). Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

This fact sheet summarizes information in 4 areas of male circumcision: (1) male circumcision and risk of HIV transmission; (2) male circumcision and other health benefits; (3) risk associated with male circumcision; and (4) status of HIV infection and male circumcision in the United States

Christakis, D. A., E. Harvey, et al. (2000). "A trade-off analysis of routine newborn circumcision." *Pediatrics* 105(1 Pt 3): 246-9.

BACKGROUND. The risks associated with newborn circumcision have not been as extensively evaluated as the benefits. **OBJECTIVES.** The goals of this study were threefold: 1) to derive a population-based complication rate for newborn circumcision; 2) to calculate the number needed to harm for newborn circumcision based on this rate; and 3) to establish trade-offs based on our complication rates and published estimates of the benefits of circumcision including the prevention of urinary tract infections and penile cancer. **METHODS.** Using the Comprehensive Hospital Abstract Reporting System for Washington State, we retrospectively examined routine newborn circumcisions performed over 9 years (1987-1996). We used International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision codes to identify both circumcisions and complications and limited our analyses to children without other surgical procedures performed during their initial birth hospitalization. **RESULTS.** Of 354, 297 male infants born during the study period, 130,475 (37%) were circumcised during their newborn stay. Overall 287 (.2%) of circumcised children and 33 (.01%) of uncircumcised children had complications potentially associated with circumcision coded as a discharge diagnosis. Based on our findings, a complication can be expected in 1 out every 476 circumcisions. Six urinary tract infections can be prevented for every complication endured and almost 2 complications can be expected for every case of penile cancer prevented. **CONCLUSIONS.** Circumcision remains a relatively safe procedure.

However, for some parents, the risks we report may outweigh the potential benefits. This information may help parents seeking guidance to make an informed decision.

Christoffersen-Deb, A. (2005). "'Taming tradition': medicalized female genital practices in western Kenya." *Med Anthropol Q* 19(4): 402-18.

This article considers the question of female genital practices at the hands of health workers in western Kenya. Recent articles in *Medical Anthropology Quarterly* have critically engaged with the biomedical arguments condemning such practices. This article studies the case of medicalized circumcision in which biomedical concerns over health risks have become incorporated in their vernacular practice. Although some suggest that medicalization may provide a harm-reduction strategy to the abandonment of the practice, research in one region challenges this suggestion. It argues that changing and conflicting ideologies of gender and sexuality have led young women to seek their own meaning through medicalized practice. Moreover, attributing this practice to financial motivations of health workers overlooks the way in which these "moral agents" must be situated within their social and cultural universe. Together, these insights challenge the view that medicine can remain neutral in the mediation of tradition.

Cohen, J. (2005). "HIV/AIDS. Prevention cocktails: combining tools to Stop HIV's spread." *Science* 309(5737): 1002-5.

Donoval, B. A., A. L. Landay, et al. (2006). "HIV-1 target cells in foreskins of African men with varying histories of sexually transmitted infections." *Am J Clin Pathol* 125(3): 386-91.

Numerous epidemiologic studies have found significant associations between lack of circumcision and HIV-1 acquisition in men. To our knowledge, this is the first study of human foreskin tissue that examines biologic mechanisms that increase susceptibility of uncircumcised African men to HIV-1. Foreskin specimens from 20 men with and 19 men with no history of sexually transmitted infections were examined for HIV-1 target cells. Most Langerhans cells were found in the epithelium; most CD4+ T cells and macrophages were in the submucosa. There were no differences in HIV-1 target cells between men with and those without history of sexually transmitted infections. However Langerhans cells and macrophages were more abundant in the group with a history of infection. The densities and positions of HIV-1 target cells in the foreskin tissue of these Kenyan men indicate that the inner mucosal surface of the human foreskin contains cells that make it highly susceptible to HIV infection.

Fergusson, D. M., J. M. Boden, et al. (2006). "Circumcision status and risk of sexually transmitted infection in young adult males: an analysis of a longitudinal birth cohort." *Pediatrics* 118(5): 1971-7.

OBJECTIVES: Previous research suggests that male circumcision may be a protective factor against the acquisition of sexually transmitted infections; however, studies examining this question have produced mixed results. The aim of this study was to examine the association between circumcision status and sexually transmitted infection risk using a longitudinal birth cohort study. **METHODS:** Data were gathered as part of the Christchurch Health and Development Study, a 25-year longitudinal study of a birth cohort of New Zealand children. Information was obtained on: (1) the circumcision status of males in the cohort before 15 years old, (2) measures of self-reported sexually transmitted infection from ages 18 to 25 years, and (3) childhood, family, and related covariate factors. **RESULTS:** Being uncircumcised had a statistically significant bivariate association with self-reported sexually transmitted infection. Adjustment for potentially confounding factors, including number of sexual partners and unprotected sex, as well as background and family factors related to circumcision, did not reduce the association between circumcision status and reports of sexually transmitted infection. Estimates of the population-attributable risk suggested that universal neonatal circumcision would have reduced rates of sexually transmitted infection in this cohort by 48.2%. **CONCLUSIONS:** These findings suggest that uncircumcised males are at greater risk of acquiring sexually transmitted infection than circumcised males. Male circumcision may reduce the risk of sexually transmitted infection acquisition and transmission by up to one half, suggesting substantial benefits accruing from routine neonatal circumcision.

Gray, R. H., N. Kiwanuka, et al. (2000). "Male circumcision and HIV acquisition and transmission: cohort studies in Rakai, Uganda. Rakai Project Team." *Aids* 14(15): 2371-81.

BACKGROUND: Male circumcision is associated with reduced HIV acquisition. **METHODS:** HIV acquisition was determined in a cohort of 5507 HIV-negative Ugandan men, and in 187 HIV-negative men in discordant relationships. Transmission was determined in 223 HIV-positive men with HIV-negative partners. **HIV**

incidence per 100 person years (py) and adjusted rate ratios (RR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were estimated by Poisson regression. HIV-1 serum viral load was determined for the seropositive partners in HIV-discordant couples. RESULTS: The prevalence of circumcision was 16.5% for all men; 99.1% in Muslims and 3.7% in non-Muslims. Circumcision was significantly associated with reduced HIV acquisition in the cohort as a whole (RR 0.53, CI 0.33-0.87), but not among non-Muslim men. Prepubertal circumcision significantly reduced HIV acquisition (RR 0.49, CI 0.26-0.82), but postpubertal circumcision did not. In discordant couples with HIV-negative men, no seroconversions occurred in 50 circumcised men, whereas HIV acquisition was 16.7 per 100 py in uncircumcised men (P = 0.004). In couples with HIV-positive men, HIV transmission was significantly reduced in circumcised men with HIV viral loads less than 50000 copies/ml (P = 0.02). INTERPRETATION: Prepubertal circumcision may reduce male HIV acquisition in a general population, but the protective effects are confounded by cultural and behavioral factors in Muslims. In discordant couples, circumcision reduces HIV acquisition and transmission. The assessment of circumcision for HIV prevention is complex and requires randomized trials.

Malone, P. S. (2005). "Circumcision for preventing urinary tract infection in boys: European view." *Arch Dis Child* **90**(8): 773-4.

Moses, S., J. E. Bradley, et al. (1990). "Geographical patterns of male circumcision practices in Africa: association with HIV seroprevalence." *Int J Epidemiol* **19**(3): 693-7.

To ascertain whether male circumcision might explain some of the geographical variation in human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) seroprevalence in Africa, we investigated the association between the practice of male circumcision at a societal level and HIV seroprevalence. Male circumcision practices for over 700 African societies were identified, and HIV seroprevalence in general adult populations from 140 distinct locations in 41 countries was obtained. In locations where male circumcision is practised, HIV seroprevalence was considerably lower than in areas where it is not practised. This study supports the hypothesis that lack of circumcision in males is a risk factor for HIV transmission.

Quinn, T. C., M. J. Wawer, et al. (2000). "Viral load and heterosexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus type 1. Rakai Project Study Group." *N Engl J Med* **342**(13): 921-9.

BACKGROUND AND METHODS: We examined the influence of viral load in relation to other risk factors for the heterosexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1). In a community-based study of 15,127 persons in a rural district of Uganda, we identified 415 couples in which one partner was HIV-1-positive and one was initially HIV-1-negative and followed them prospectively for up to 30 months. The incidence of HIV-1 infection per 100 person-years among the initially seronegative partners was examined in relation to behavioral and biologic variables. RESULTS: The male partner was HIV-1-positive in 228 couples, and the female partner was HIV-1-positive in 187 couples. Ninety of the 415 initially HIV-1-negative partners seroconverted (incidence, 11.8 per 100 person-years). The rate of male-to-female transmission was not significantly different from the rate of female-to-male transmission (12.0 per 100 person-years vs. 11.6 per 100 person-years). The incidence of seroconversion was highest among the partners who were 15 to 19 years of age (15.3 per 100 person-years). The incidence was 16.7 per 100 person-years among 137 uncircumcised male partners, whereas there were no seroconversions among the 50 circumcised male partners (P<0.001). The mean serum HIV-1 RNA level was significantly higher among HIV-1-positive subjects whose partners seroconverted than among those whose partners did not seroconvert (90,254 copies per milliliter vs. 38,029 copies per milliliter, P=0.01). There were no instances of transmission among the 51 subjects with serum HIV-1 RNA levels of less than 1500 copies per milliliter; there was a significant dose-response relation of increased transmission with increasing viral load. In multivariate analyses of log-transformed HIV-1 RNA levels, each log increment in the viral load was associated with a rate ratio of 2.45 for seroconversion (95 percent confidence interval, 1.85 to 3.26). CONCLUSIONS: The viral load is the chief predictor of the risk of heterosexual transmission of HIV-1, and transmission is rare among persons with levels of less than 1500 copies of HIV-1 RNA per milliliter.

Schoen, E. J. (2005). "Circumcision for preventing urinary tract infections in boys: North American view." *Arch Dis Child* **90**(8): 772-3.

Schoen, E. J., T. E. Wiswell, et al. (2000). "New policy on circumcision--cause for concern." *Pediatrics* **105**(3 Pt 1): 620-3.

Siegfried, N., M. Muller, et al. (2005). "HIV and male circumcision--a systematic review with assessment of the quality of studies." *Lancet Infect Dis* 5(3): 165-73.

This Cochrane systematic review assesses the evidence for an interventional effect of male circumcision in preventing acquisition of HIV-1 and HIV-2 by men through heterosexual intercourse. The review includes a comprehensive assessment of the quality of all 37 included observational studies. Studies in high-risk populations consisted of four cohort studies, 12 cross-sectional studies, and three case-control studies; general population studies consisted of one cohort study, 16 cross-sectional studies, and one case-control study. There is evidence of methodological heterogeneity between studies, and statistical heterogeneity was highly significant for both general population cross-sectional studies ($\chi^2=132.34$; degrees of freedom [df]=15; $p<0.00001$) and high-risk cross-sectional studies ($\chi^2=29.70$; df=10; $p=0.001$). Study quality was very variable and no studies measured the same set of potential confounding variables. Therefore, conducting a meta-analysis was inappropriate. Detailed quality assessment of observational studies can provide a useful visual aid to interpreting findings. Although most studies show an association between male circumcision and prevention of HIV, these results may be limited by confounding, which is unlikely to be adjusted for.

Siegfried, N., M. Muller, et al. (2003). "Male circumcision for prevention of heterosexual acquisition of HIV in men." *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*(3): CD003362.

BACKGROUND: The findings from observational studies, reviews and meta-analyses, supported by biological theories, that circumcised men appear less likely to acquire human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) has contributed to the recent ground swell of support for considering male circumcision as a strategy for preventing sexually acquired infection. We sought to elucidate and appraise the global evidence from published and unpublished studies that circumcision can be used as an intervention to prevent HIV infection. **OBJECTIVES:** 1) To assess the evidence of an interventional effect of male circumcision for preventing acquisition of HIV-1 and HIV-2 by men through heterosexual intercourse 2) To examine the feasibility and value of performing individual person data (IPD) meta-analysis **SEARCH STRATEGY:** We searched online for published and unpublished studies in The Cochrane Library (issue 2, 2002), MEDLINE (April 2002), EMBASE (February 2002) and AIDSLINE (August 2001). We also searched databases listing conference abstracts, scanned reference lists of articles and contacted authors of included studies. **SELECTION CRITERIA:** We searched for randomized and quasi-randomized controlled trials of male circumcision or, in their absence, observational studies that compare acquisition rates of HIV-1 and HIV-2 infection in circumcised and uncircumcised heterosexual men. **DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS:** Independent reviewers selected studies, assessed study quality and extracted data. We stratified studies based on study design and on whether they included participants from the general population or high-risk groups (such as patients treated for sexually transmitted infections). We expressed findings as crude and adjusted odds ratios (OR) together with their 95% confidence intervals (CI) and conducted a sensitivity analysis to explore the effect of adjustment on study results. We investigated whether the method of circumcision ascertainment influenced study outcomes. **MAIN RESULTS:** We identified no completed randomized controlled trials. Three randomized controlled trials are currently underway or commencing shortly. We found 34 observational studies: 16 conducted in the general population and 18 in high-risk populations. It seems unlikely that potential confounding factors were completely accounted for in any of the included studies. In particular, important risk factors, such as religion and sexual practices, were not adequately accounted for in many of the included studies. **General population study results:** The single cohort study (N = 5516) showed a significant difference in HIV transmission rates between circumcised and uncircumcised men [OR = 0.58; 95% CI: 0.36 to 0.96]. Results for the 14 cross-sectional studies were inconsistent, with point estimates for unadjusted odds ratios varying between 0.28 and 1.73. Six studies had statistically significant results, four in the direction of benefit and two in the direction of harm. The test for heterogeneity between the cross-sectional studies was highly significant ($\chi^2 = 77.59$; df = 13; P-value < 0.00001). Nine studies reported adjusted odds ratios with eight in the direction of benefit, ranging from 0.26 to 0.80. Use of adjusted results tended to show stronger evidence of an association although they remained heterogeneous ($\chi^2 = 75.2$; df = 13; P-value < 0.00001). Only one case-control study was found (N = 51) which had a non-significant result [OR = 1.90; 95% CI: 0.50 to 7.20]. **High-risk group study results:** The four cohort studies identified found a protective effect from circumcision with point estimates for unadjusted odds ratios varying from 0.10 to 0.39. Two of these studies had statistically significant results. Two studies reported adjusted odds ratios, both protective with one being significant. The chi-square test for between-study heterogeneity was not significant ($\chi^2 = 5.21$; df = 3; P-value = 0.16). All eleven cross-sectional studies reporting unadjusted results found benefit from circumcision, eight of which had statistically significant results.

Estimates of effnal studies reporting unadjusted results found benefit from circumcision, eight of which had statistically significant results. Estimates of effect varied from an unadjusted odds ratio of 0.10 to 0.66. Between-study heterogeneity was significant with the chi-square = 29.77; df = 10; P-value = 0.0009. Four of these studies reported adjusted odds ratios ranging from 0.20 to 0.59 and all were significant. One additional cross-sectional study only reported an adjusted odds ratio in the direction of benefit which was statistically significant. All three case-control studies found a protective effect of circumcision on HIV status, two being statistically significant. Point estimates varied from unadjusted odds ratios of 0.37 to 0.88. One reported an adjusted odds ratio showing a significant protective effect. Adverse effects: No studies reported on the adverse effects of circumcision. In most studies, circumcision had taken place during childhood or adolescence before the studies commenced. REVIEWER'S CONCLUSIONS: We found insufficient evidence to support an interventional effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition in heterosexual men. The results from existing observational studies show a strong epidemiological association between male circumcision and prevention of HIV, especially among high-risk groups. However, observational studies are inherently limited by confounding which is unlikely to be fully adjusted for. In the light of forthcoming results from RCTs, the value of IPD analysis of the included studies is doubtful. The results of these trials will need to be carefully considered before circumcision is implemented as a public health intervention for prevention of sexually transmitted HIV.

Wawer, M. J., S. J. Reynolds, et al. (2005). "Might male circumcision be more protective against HIV in the highly exposed? An immunological hypothesis." *Aids* 19(18): 2181-2.

Westercamp, N. and R. C. Bailey (2006). "Acceptability of Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Review." *AIDS Behav.*

Based on epidemiological, clinical and experimental evidence, male circumcision (MC) could have a significant impact on the HIV epidemic in selected areas. We reviewed studies of the acceptability of MC in sub-Saharan Africa to assess factors that will influence uptake of circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising populations. Thirteen studies from nine countries were identified. Across studies, the median proportion of uncircumcised men willing to become circumcised was 65% (range 29-87%). Sixty nine percent (47-79%) of women favored circumcision for their partners, and 71% (50-90%) of men and 81% (70-90%) of women were willing to circumcise their sons. Because the level of acceptability across the nine countries was quite consistent, additional acceptability studies that pose hypothetical questions to participants are unnecessary. We recommend pilot interventions making safe circumcision services available in conjunction with current HIV prevention strategies and evaluating the safety and acceptability of circumcision.

Williams, B. G., J. O. Lloyd-Smith, et al. (2006). "The potential impact of male circumcision on HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa." *PLoS Med* 3(7): e262.

BACKGROUND: A randomized controlled trial (RCT) has shown that male circumcision (MC) reduces sexual transmission of HIV from women to men by 60% (32%-76%; 95% CI) offering an intervention of proven efficacy for reducing the sexual spread of HIV. We explore the implications of this finding for the promotion of MC as a public health intervention to control HIV in sub-Saharan Africa. METHODS AND FINDINGS: Using dynamical simulation models we consider the impact of MC on the relative prevalence of HIV in men and women and in circumcised and uncircumcised men. Using country level data on HIV prevalence and MC, we estimate the impact of increasing MC coverage on HIV incidence, HIV prevalence, and HIV-related deaths over the next ten, twenty, and thirty years in sub-Saharan Africa. Assuming that full coverage of MC is achieved over the next ten years, we consider three scenarios in which the reduction in transmission is given by the best estimate and the upper and lower 95% confidence limits of the reduction in transmission observed in the RCT. MC could avert 2.0 (1.1-3.8) million new HIV infections and 0.3 (0.1-0.5) million deaths over the next ten years in sub-Saharan Africa. In the ten years after that, it could avert a further 3.7 (1.9-7.5) million new HIV infections and 2.7 (1.5-5.3) million deaths, with about one quarter of all the incident cases prevented and the deaths averted occurring in South Africa. We show that a) MC will increase the proportion of infected people who are women from about 52% to 58%; b) where there is homogenous mixing but not all men are circumcised, the prevalence of infection in circumcised men is likely to be about 80% of that in uncircumcised men; c) MC is equivalent to an intervention, such as a vaccine or increased condom use, that reduces transmission in both directions by 37%. CONCLUSIONS: This analysis is based on the result of just one RCT, but if the results of that trial are confirmed we suggest that MC could substantially reduce the burden of HIV in Africa, especially in southern Africa where the prevalence of MC is low and the prevalence of HIV is high. While the protective

benefit to HIV-negative men will be immediate, the full impact of MC on HIV-related illness and death will only be apparent in ten to twenty years.

Wiswell, T. E. and D. W. Geschke (1989). "Risks from circumcision during the first month of life compared with those for uncircumcised boys." *Pediatrics* **83**(6): 1011-5.

The records of 136,086 boys born in US Army hospitals from 1980 to 1985 were reviewed for indexed complications related to circumcision status during the first month of life. For 100,157 circumcised boys, there were 193 complications (0.19%). These included 62 local infections, eight cases of bacteremia, 83 incidences of hemorrhage (31 requiring ligature and three requiring transfusion), 25 instances of surgical trauma, and 20 urinary tract infections. There were no deaths or reported losses of the glans or entire penis. By contrast, the complications in the 35,929 uncircumcised infants were all related to urinary tract infections. Of the 88 boys with such infections (0.24%), 32 had concomitant bacteremia, three had meningitis, two had renal failure, and two died. The frequencies of urinary tract infection (P less than .0001) and bacteremia (P less than .0002) were significantly higher in the uncircumcised boys. Serious complications from routine prepuce removal are rare and relatively minor. Circumcision may be beneficial in reducing the occurrence of urinary tract infections and their associated sequelae.

Maps

Circumcision Prevalence

(Caldwell, 2006) (67)

REGIONS WHERE MOST MEN ARE UNCIRCUMCISED

HIV Prevalence

UNAIDS HIV Prevalence, 2005

2005

Adult prevalence %

Consultation on Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences

Atlanta, GA
April 26-27, 2007

AGENDA

Thursday, April 26

8:30 Welcome Dr. Rob Janssen
8:45 Charge to the Consultants and recent WHO/UNAIDS guidance Dr. Tim Mastro

Why consider increasing male circumcision in the United States?

Moderator: Dr. Tim Mastro

9:00 Overview of international male circumcision and HIV Dr. Helen Weiss
9:25 Results of the South Africa Trial Dr. Bertran Auvert
9:45 Results of the Kenya Trial Dr. Robert Bailey
10:05 Results of the Rakai Trial Dr. Ron Gray
10:30 Discussion

11:00 Break

11:30 Overview of domestic male circumcision Dr. Peter Kilmarx
11:50 Evidence on male circumcision and HIV in MSM Dr. Susan Buchbinder
12:10 Evidence of adverse outcomes in male circumcision Dr. Robert S. Van Howe
12:30 Discussion

1:00 Lunch

What is the potential cost of male circumcision and impact on HIV transmission in the US?

Moderator: Dr. John Douglas

2:30 Modeling impact and cost-effectiveness Dr. Stephanie Sansom
3:00 Cost of circumcision in US newborns and adults Dr. Edgar Schoen
3:30 Discussion

4:00 Break

4:20 Risk communication and disinhibition Dr. Brad Bartholow
4:40 Ethical, religious, and cultural issues Dr. Bernard Lo
5:00 Discussion and public comment period
5:30 Adjourn

Friday, April 27

8:30 Charge to Breakout Groups

Dr. Dawn K. Smith

8:45 Concurrent Breakout Sessions

1. MSW in the US

Dr. Lee Warner, facilitator

2. MSM in the US

Dr. Gary Marks, facilitator

3. Newborns in the US

Dr. Allan Taylor, facilitator

11:30 Lunch

Moderator: Dr. Naomi Bock

1:00 Report back and discussion - MSW Rapporteur

1:30 Report back and discussion – MSM Rapporteur

2:00 Report back and discussion – newborns Rapporteur

2:30 Summary Comments

Dr. Rob Janssen

3:00 Adjourn

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 6 Apr 2007 14:21:51 +0000
To: jpalen@gwu.edu
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention
Attachments: image001.gif

Dr. Palen,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27, 2007 in Atlanta. You were recommended to us by Dr. Jeff Levi as an expert on reimbursement for HIV prevention services (see below), and we would like to invite you to attend as a consultant and presenter at this meeting. CDC will support your travel expenses and meals if you are able to attend.

We would further like to invite you to give a presentation (approx. 20 min) at this meeting regarding healthcare financing and reimbursement around HIV preventive services. We hope that you might be able to provide us and our consultants with relevant general background information about financing for preventive procedures at the state and federal levels.

Please contact me at your earliest convenience to indicate whether you might be available to attend this consultation or, if you are unavailable, to suggest other appropriate experts with experience in this area who might be able to provide our consultants with this important background. Thank you in advance for your time.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Jeff Levi [<mailto:jlevi@TEAH.ORG>]
Sent: Friday, April 06, 2007 09:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: jpalen@gwu.edu
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention

Thanks for the invitation. Unfortunately, I already have commitments on those dates. As you know, my colleagues and I at GW have done earlier work on reimbursement for HIV testing - I am assuming this is why the invitation was extended to me. Given my new duties at Trust for America's Health, I am less on top of reimbursement issues. You might contact John Palen, jpalen@gwu.edu, who was the lead on the HIV testing study for GW; he might be able to provide some insights or alternative resources.

Jeffrey Levi, Ph.D.

Executive Director

Trust for America's Health

1707 H Street, NW

Washington, DC 20006

202-223-9877

and

Associate Professor

Department of Health Policy

George Washington University School of Public Health and Health Services

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 9 Apr 2007 16:04:33 +0000
To: ddeleon@latinoaids.org
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention

Mr. de Leon,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We would like to invite you as a representative of the Latino Commission on AIDS to participate as a consultant at this meeting. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming week, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC will provide for your travel expenses and meals.

We understand that this is short notice and hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation. Please advise us regarding your availability and provide contact information (including telephone number, fax and address) as soon as possible so that our contractor can contact you to assist with your travel arrangements. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

Thank you,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
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W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 2 Feb 2007 22:56:18 +0000
To: Birx, Deborah (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CDC Male Circumcision Working Group meeting Minutes
Attachments: Minutes 20070125 CDC Male Circumcision Working Group.doc

Hello, all.

Attached are brief minutes from last week's MCWG meeting. Please let me know of any corrections or suggestions.

Action items are copied here for your reference:

Action Items

- Bob Kohmescher agreed track down the clearance status of the plain-language fact sheet.
- Naomi agreed to distribute the agenda and summary of the December Geneva meeting and to send out these draft documents for the group to review. 2/2 addendum: DONE.
- Everyone please send dates to avoid for the consultation to Allan Taylor (e.g., major conferences, holidays, etc.).
- Allan will send out a meeting invitation for a consultation planning subcommittee, to which each program should send a representative (to assist with planning content of the consultation).

Thank you.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP

Director, National Center for HIV/AIDS, Dermatology and STD Prevention
Division of Field Epidemiology
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, NE
Atlanta, Georgia 30333
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E-mail: ataylor@cdc.gov

CDC Male Circumcision Working Group
Meeting January 25, 2007 – 3:30 pm
Corp Sq Bldg 10, Room 2201/2207

In attendance:

Peter Kilmarx, Stephanie Sansom, Tom Peterman, Robert Kohmescher, Naomi Bock, Mary Kamb, Catherine McLean, Dawn Smith, Allan Taylor, Patrick Sullivan, Tim Mastro

By telephone:

Allyn Nakashima, Lee Warner

1. Overview of Kenya and Uganda clinical trial results – Peter Kilmarx

- Two randomized clinical trials of male circumcision for HIV prevention in Kenya and Uganda completed enrollment in 2005 and had an interim analysis in June, 2006. At that time it was decided to have a second interim analysis on December 12, 2006.
- The trial in Kenya (N=2784 men age 18-24) reported a 53% reduction in HIV acquisition with circumcision. In Uganda (N approx 5000 men, age 15-40), the trial showed a 48% reduction. The trials were halted at that time by their DSMB.
- The Kenya study has funding for additional followup of cohort. Uganda has Gates funding for ongoing study to look at transmission from men to their partners.

2. Revised CDC Fact sheet – Peter Kilmarx

- Fact sheet was revised and re-released Dec 14. Thanks to all who worked to get that out so quickly.
- Key differences: summary section states that CDC is undertaking additional research and consultation to evaluate the potential value, risks and feasibility of MC for HIV prevention in the US. Individual men may wish to consider MC for risk reduction in conjunction with other prevention measures (and lists caveats).
- A plain-language version of the fact sheet was in clearance at the time of this revision; a revised plain-language version is now in clearance. Bob Kohmescher agreed track down the status of this document.

Additional publications (circulated to group previously):

- Fergusson et al *Pediatrics* 2006: birth cohort from New Zealand. Universal neonatal circumcision would have reduced rates of STDs in the area around Christchurch by 48%.
- Xu et al *STD* in press: NHANES data on prevalence of circumcision in US between 1999 and 2004. This is the latest available information on circumcision in the US.
- Kahn et al. *PLoS Medicine* 2006: CE of MC in South Africa. Showed that 1000 circumcisions would avert 308 cases of HIV infection over a 20 yr period, for a cost of \$181 per HIV infection averted.
- Warner (poster at Soc for Epi Research conference in Seattle last year): Decreased HIV risk in high-risk circumcised men in US. Being drafted as manuscript.
- Kawango et al *JAIDS*. Pre-circumcision men had higher risk, decreased after circumcision, but behavioral risk was same as uncircumcised men at 1 year.
- Schoen *J Urology* 2006. Kaiser Permanente data male infants born 1996. Post-neonatal circumcision far more expensive than neonatal circumcision. If initial cost is \$200, future cost avoided was \$183.

3. Update on global MC developments - GAP, OGAC, UNAIDS, WHO, Gates/NIH trials, etc. – Naomi Bock

- This is a very busy time for the many international organizations around this issue. Not wanting to act too soon (“off-sides penalty”) but wanting to be responsive.

- [Redacted] (b)(5)
- Naomi attended a recent meeting of international organizations (including OGAC, JHPIEGO, and other partners) in Geneva on Dec 6 at which these issues were discussed. Discussed the current status of MC and reviewed documents that WHO has prepared, including their surgical manual and ethics manual. Naomi agreed to distribute the agenda and summary of this meeting as well as WHO's draft documents for the group to review.
- The next steps from that meeting were to wait for the trial results, and it was decided to issue guidance by the end of January. The guidance has now been postponed to the end of March.
- They've brought on board a certification consultant to set national standards and measure whether providers meet these standards and have a logo that they can use if they meet the standards.
- [Redacted] (b)(5)
- [Redacted]
- OGAC has committed to WHO to help them finish and pilot their situation assessment toolkit, which has just been received by GAP this week. Some PEPFAR countries will pilot this toolkit. Treatment and MC funding have both been preserved despite funding cuts due to the continuing resolution.
- Peter reports that the Clinton Foundation has put together a box of equipment (surgical prep kit, blade, sutures, etc) to distribute to promote safe MC.
- Tim reports that invitations for the follow-up meeting (March 6-8) are going out now. DHAP and GAP are expected to be invited. OGAC will likely get GAP's invitation. Tim plans to attend if travel can be arranged.

4. Update on studies of acceptability of circumcision and willingness to participate in a clinical trial of circumcision among US MSM - Patrick Sullivan

- CROI poster and manuscript are being prepared exploring acceptability of MC among MSM.
- [Redacted] (b)(5)
- [Redacted] (b)(5)

5. Invited PLoS Med commentary on MC for HIV prevention in the US - Patrick Sullivan

- The revised version of the commentary reflects the recent trial results. Comments from co-authors are coming in and are due by COB 1/26/07. We'll look for a quick clearance turnaround and hope to have it cleared and submitted in the next 3 weeks. After some discussion it was decided that the language regarding the protective effect of MC for MSM in the US should be strengthened.

6. Update on AAP activities – Allan Taylor

- Peter Havens (Chair, AAP COPA) and others (including 2 from NIH, writing in a personal capacity) have co-authored a commentary for *Pediatrics* expressing the need to revisit

their neutral recommendations on neonatal circumcision in light of the clinical trial results. They will also send some representatives to the CDC consultation.

7. Update on modeling activities - Stephanie Sansom

- Stephanie presented her group's recent modeling results in two areas.
- Infants' lifetime risk of HIV (circumcised vs. uncircumcised).
 - Surveillance has updated an analysis of lifetime risk of HIV using a double-decrement life-table method to include 33 states and more recent data. Found a 1.9% lifetime risk of HIV for men.
 - Using these data, the group has made a relatively simple model which indicates approximately 9% decreased lifetime risk of HIV for circumcised non-Hispanic white males compared to uncircumcised. For non-hispanic black males, they calculate a 16% reduction, and for Hispanic males 18%. This model takes into account only heterosexual transmission.
- Efficacy of MC among MSM in NYC.
 - Initial models indicate that MC would be a cost-saving intervention for MSM in NYC, saving approximately \$88M at an efficacy of 7.1% among MSM.

8. CDC consultation plans – Peter Kilmarx

- We're planning the MC consultation for fairly soon in order to get input from experts in the area. Members suggested late March or early April. EIS Conference begins April 16, so that week should be avoided. WG members should send other conflicting dates to Allan Taylor.
- A draft agenda for the consultation was distributed to the group for comment.
- DHAP funding has been secured to conduct the meeting.
- Volunteers are needed to help with agenda and content planning. Mary Kamb and Lee Warner have graciously agreed to assist. Representatives from other programs are welcome.
- The SBU will coordinate the conference venue and logistics.

Action Items

- Bob Kohmescher agreed track down the clearance status of the plain-language fact sheet.
- Naomi agreed to distribute the agenda and summary of the December Geneva meeting and to send out these draft documents for the group to review.
- Send dates to avoid for the consultation to Allan Taylor (e.g., major conferences, holidays, etc.).
- Allan will send out a meeting invitation for a consultation planning subcommittee, to which each program should send a representative (to assist with planning content of the consultation).

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 16 Mar 2007 20:34:43 +0000
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CMS participation at the MC Consultation

Raul,

I wanted to touch base with you about finding someone from CMS to participate in our male circumcision consultation. I think you've discussed this with Patrick and others? Who would you think we should invite who might also be able to speak about the process/requirements/possibility for getting CMS to pay for MC for HIV prevention (and/or for newborns)?

Thanks, Raul!
-Allan

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP

Chief, Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Dermatology and STD
Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, NE
Atlanta, GA 30333
Phone: 404/616-1300
Fax: 404/616-1300
E-mail: ataylor@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 23 Apr 2007 11:04:14 +0000
To: Dominguez, Ken (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Millett, Greg (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Birx, Deborah (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Shaffer, Nathan (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Aral, Sevgi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Douglas, John (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Gift, Thomas L. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Johnson, David (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Xu, Fujie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Dalal, Shona (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR); Singh, Sonia (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR); Lasry, Arielle (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chideya, Sekai (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grant, Linda Ahdieh (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR); 'jkakiet@LearnLink.Emory.Edu'; Begley, Elin (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); 'sglowak@sph.emory.edu'; 'nmurali@sph.emory.edu'
Subject: Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
Attachments: MC Consultation Invitation Letter 2.pdf

CDC Colleagues,

We are looking forward to your participation in the upcoming consultation on male circumcision and HIV prevention occurring this week (Thursday 4/26 and Friday 4/27) at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park here in Atlanta. Attached is an invitation letter with further details regarding the venue and the objectives for this conference, for anyone who has not yet received this information. Please contact me if you have any questions or concerns.

Thank you.
-Allan

April 12, 2007

Dear Colleague,

The CDC Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

Meeting Objectives

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

Space will be available for presentation of posters if participants have data or activities they wish to share. Please contact us in advance if you plan to prepare a poster so that we may ensure adequate space.

CDC is unable to provide for your travel expenses; however we have reserved a block of rooms at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park for our participants at the US Government rate of USD\$124/night. The hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313. Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925). The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter.

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation. Please contact Allan Taylor, MD, MPH at ataylor2@cdc.gov or at (404) 639-6120 if you have any questions or comments. We are looking forward to your participation and to a productive consultation.

Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 5 Apr 2007 12:38:57 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: A state legislation question

Here's the very interesting response from a family member who's a prior state legislator in SD, now a management consultant who works mostly with hospitals and physicians.

From: Wagner, Mike [<mailto:WagnerM@advisory.com>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 8:25 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: mpwagner@itetel.com
Subject: RE: A state legislation question

The prohibition (or forced inclusion) of services in a Medicaid program -- as you suspect -- is normally a regulatory function between the State Department of Social Services and the Governor's office of any state.

However, legislators get involved in specific mandates when an individual legislator (and/or their constituency) has a morale conviction that they want to champion. The "morale convictions" could be as widespread as your imagination will allow. I have attached an article about the North Dakota situation, which clearly states that the issue in North Dakota was the opinion that circumcision is a barbaric mutilation and should be clearly stopped for that reason.

However, if CDC or any other agency for that matter were to confront these state-by-state bans, be aware that you could encounter such issues as...

- 1) It's a religious activity and the state should not pay for it.
- 2) It's a voluntary sexual procedure that should not be paid for by tax dollars (notice in the N.D. article that reduced sexual stimulation is given as a reason against circumcision.)
- 3) It's cosmetic surgery (notice the statement about 'looking like Dad')
- 4) It's not life and death and so tax dollars should not be used.

I can only imagine how the discussion must have been conducted in the legislatures where the Medicaid ban was passed, but there are two other political "factors" that would come to play here. I actually doubt that the majority of legislators who voted for the ban felt strongly about it. However...

a) ...to get up in front of 1000's of constituents and TV cameras and argue that low income boys and men should have the right to be circumcised would not be a popular position to champion. The proponents of the ban would have just made impassioned pleas about the barbaric and horrific nature of the procedure. Opponents of the ban would then have to argue FOR the procedure as being very important and worthy of scarce tax dollars. Without conclusive public health arguments -- again, notice the conflicting nature of the information reported below -- the only solid argument AGAINST the BAN would be "everyone should decide for themselves". The "let Medicaid Recipients choose their own care" argument is NOT strong, because of the second political factor below...

b) Medicaid recipients are not viewed in a particularly favorable light. Any procedure or medical intervention that is seen as elective AND for which a non-Medicaid recipient would have to pay out of their own pocket (either in cash or through their insurance premiums) would be viewed as taxing the middle class to support the poor. Most Medicaid recipients are seen as partly responsible for their own situation -- pregnant Mom's sometimes more than any other group. Plus, since the health argument might be about AIDS and STD's -- both also seen as preventable

through abstinence -- the argument to require tax dollars for the procedure becomes hard to defend.

So, with Medicaid dollars restricted, state budgets tight, and no "automatic" argument to fight the ban, it is unlikely that a lot of legislators would strictly oppose an impassioned plea to stop using the middle class' tax dollars to give Medicaid recipients "Cadillac level health care" that the average person would not get.

(Don't shoot me the messenger -- I'm just relating how the arguments start to unfold at the state level.)

One last consideration. If CDC were to advocate for Medicaid reimbursement, it would be based on the argument of reducing the public health risk. Obviously, that is both a worthy and solid objective to champion. However, if the argument is made that this is a "critical" component of public health policy AND that Medicaid should pay for MC for the poor...then watch for the attached proposal that is likely to surface: REQUIRED MC for all baby boys unless religious convictions exist. In other words, people who become convinced of the merits would want every baby boy to be protected and the debate would become highly public about parental rights, government intrusion, etc., etc.

Again, mixing tax-supported Medicaid with VOLUNTARY procedures is a volatile issue.

As said, please don't shoot the messenger. Below is the North Dakota story.

Take care...

MIKE

Circumcision Opponents Use the Legal System and Legislatures

By ADAM LIPTAK

FARGO, N.D., Jan. 16 - Josiah Flatt, like about 60 percent of other newborn American boys, was circumcised soon after he was born here, in the spring of 1997. Two years later, his parents sued the doctor and the hospital.

They did not contend that the circumcision was botched or deny that Josiah's mother, Anita Flatt <<http://www.zbaer.com/anita.htm>> , had consented to the procedure in writing. They said, instead, that the doctor had failed to tell them enough about the pain, complications and consequences of circumcision, removing the foreskin of the penis.

The suit will be heard by a jury next month. In declining to dismiss the case here before trial, Judge Cynthia Rothe-Seeger <<http://www.court.state.nd.us/court/bios/Rothe-Seeger.htm>> acknowledged that the case was unusual in that nothing "went `wrong' during the procedure." The main harm Josiah seeks compensation for, Judge Rothe-Seeger noted, is "diminished sexual sensation injury."

The suit is but one effort by a small but energetic group of loosely affiliated advocates and lawyers to use the legal system to combat the practice - most American newborn boys undergo the operation when they are days old - which they liken to genital cutting in girls.

The advocates have been active in state legislatures, too. Ten states no longer allow Medicaid to pay for circumcision.

"They have reached the ears of legislators and insurance companies," Dr. Thomas Wiswell, a professor of pediatrics at the State University of New York at Stony Brook and a proponent of the procedure, said about the opponents. "They are far more vocal than proponents of circumcision."

J. Steven Svoboda, director of Attorneys for the Rights of the Child <<http://www.arclaw.org/>> , a group devoted to the issue, contends that circumcision is wrong as a matter of law, medicine and philosophy. Children of both sexes, Mr. Svoboda said, should be entitled to "bodily integrity."

Josiah Flatt's case appears to be the first to go to trial based on the theory that the absence of an exhaustive medical briefing about the risks and benefits of circumcision is tantamount to a lack of informed consent.

Among the possible complications in the operation are excess bleeding, infection and ulceration and occasional permanent damage to the penis.

"This could be a very important test case," said Geoffrey P. Miller, a professor of law at New York University <<http://www.nyu.edu/>> who has written about legal and cultural issues <<http://www.cirp.org/library/legal/miller1/>> of circumcision.

Josiah's father, James, died in 2001 in an automobile accident, but the boy's mother, Anita, 33, decided to proceed with the suit. The family's lawyer, Zenas Baer <<http://www.zbaer.com/zenas.htm>> , said no sensible parent would willingly subject a child to circumcision knowing what it entailed.

"The practice is absolutely barbaric," Mr. Baer said.

The doctor who performed the circumcision, Sunita Kantak <<http://www.meritcare.com/guidebook/directories/info.asp?id=734>> , and representatives of the hospital, the MeritCare Medical Center <<http://www.meritcare.com/>> , issued this statement:

"Anita Flatt was given information about circumcision, and she asked to have her son circumcised. The circumcision was done because she requested it."

A hospital spokeswoman, Carrie Johnson, declined to elaborate.

In court papers, the hospital said the suit was part of a crusade.

"This lawsuit is an attempt to abolish circumcision in North Dakota of newborn males with healthy foreskin," the hospital's lawyers wrote. "Plaintiffs want to change public policy so that only a competent male once he reaches adulthood, and not his parent, should be able to consent to circumcision."

Only 3 in 1,000 men not circumcised at birth choose to have the procedure, experts say.

David J. Llewellyn <<http://firms.findlaw.com//llewellynlaw/practices.htm>> , a Georgia lawyer who represents plaintiffs in circumcision malpractice cases, said the hospital was correct in identifying what would be the next step for opponents of the practice.

"The question of whether or not a parent can consent at all will come rather quickly," Mr. Llewellyn said.

Judge Rothe-Seeger, who will preside over the trial in Cass County <<http://www.co.cass.nd.us/>> District Court <<http://www.court.state.nd.us/COURT/DISTRICTS/EC.HTM>> , seemed to agree in a pretrial decision. She suggested that Josiah could sue his parents some day if he could show that they failed to act in his best interests.

About 1.2 million newborns are circumcised in the United States every year, at a cost of \$150 million to \$270 million, the American Academy of Pediatrics <<http://www.aap.org/>> says.

Circumcision for other than religious reasons is a relatively recent phenomenon in the United States. It began in the late 19th century and peaked in the 1960's at 90 percent of newborns. Circumcision rates vary widely. They are highest in the Midwest, about 80 percent, and lowest in the West, under 40 percent.

The procedure is not common elsewhere. In Canada <<http://www.cirp.org/library/statistics/Canada/>> , the rate is 17

percent and in Britain <http://www.cirp.org/library/statistics/UK/> 5 percent. Elsewhere in Europe, in South America and in non-Muslim Asia, the procedure is rare.

There is powerful evidence, Dr. Wiswell said, that circumcision helps prevent urinary tract infections <http://www.cirp.org/library/disease/UTI/mueller/> , penile cancer <http://www.cirp.org/library/disease/cancer/vanhowe/> and sexually transmitted diseases <http://www.cirp.org/library/disease/STD/vanhowe6/> , including H.I.V. <http://www.cirp.org/library/disease/HIV/vanhowe4/>

The American Academy of Pediatrics, in a policy statement <http://www.cirp.org/library/statements/aap1999/> in 1999, said that the risks of infection and cancer were low even without the procedure and that evidence on sexually transmitted diseases was "complex and conflicting."

The academy noted that the procedure could involve complications, as could any surgery. If performed without adequate anesthesia, it is very painful.

The academy concluded that "existing scientific evidence demonstrates potential medical benefits of newborn male circumcision."

"However," it added, "these data are not sufficient to recommend routine neonatal circumcision."

It added that it was "legitimate for parents to take into account cultural, religious and ethnic traditions, in addition to the medical factors, when making this decision."

Judge Rothe-Seeger wrote, "One of the earliest purposes of circumcision was to limit sexual intercourse and to curb sexual excitement."

It has also been prescribed through the years as a remedy for alcoholism, epilepsy, asthma, gout, hysteria, malnutrition, night terrors, clubfoot, eczema and promiscuity.

"Circumcision is a medical procedure in search of something to cure," said Mr. Baer, the Flatts' lawyer.

In the last year, Arizona <http://www.cirp.org/news/thetribune06-14-02/> , Missouri <http://www.cirp.org/news/columbiainmissourian07-25-02/> , Montana <http://www.cirp.org/news/themissoulian12-21-02/> and North Carolina <http://www.cirp.org/news/charlotteobserver09-21-02/> joined six other states - California, Mississippi, Nevada, North Dakota, Oregon and Washington - that do not offer Medicaid reimbursement for circumcision for any reason, including religious beliefs.

David L. Gollaher, who wrote "Circumcision: A History of the World's Most Controversial Surgery" (Basic Books, 2000), said that trend would "be the bullet that kills this thing."

"If people have to pony up a couple of hundred bucks, at the margin, they won't do it," Mr. Gollaher said. "And insurance coverage signals a certain attitude about medical appropriateness or necessity."

There is little legal scholarship <http://www.cirp.org/library/legal/conundrum/> in the area. That is partly attributable, Professor Miller said, to efforts intended to prevent genital cutting in girls, a practice prevalent in Africa that reduces sexual pleasure.

"It's all tied up in the politics of feminism," he said. "Some feminists take offense at the idea that there is any comparison between a highly damaging assault committed by a patriarchal society and male circumcision. It's a dangerous topic to get into."

In an interview, Ms. Flatt, who is a lawyer, said she was told next to nothing about circumcision before she consented to it. Asked what she wished she had been told, she grew animated and her voice rose.

"It's healthy tissue <http://www.cirp.org/library/disease/STD/fleiss3/> ," she said of the foreskin. "It's useful. There's

bleeding <<http://www.cirp.org/news/theprovince08-29-02/>> risk. There's pain
<<http://www.cirp.org/library/pain/howard/>> . There's infection
<<http://www.cirp.org/library/complications#infection>> risk. There's death
<<http://www.cirp.org/library/death/>> risk. There's no medical benefit.

"You'd better give me a very good reason why, and it's got to be more than he'll look like dad."

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIHISTP) [<mailto:dks0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 3:35 PM
To: Wagner, Mike
Subject: A state legislation question

Mike,

We're planning an expert consultation later this month to decide on national policy about the use of male circumcision in the US to reduce HIV transmission. 3 trials in Africa showed that circumcising young adults reduced their risk of becoming HIV infected by about 65%.

In the process, we discovered that several states passed laws in the last few years (including ND) refusing medicaid reimbursement for MC unless it was to treat an existing disease or condition that couldn't be treated by a less invasive means. Us docs are a bit surprised that laws are passed about such a specific issue. Can you enlighten me about how/why this happens instead of leaving it up to the medicaid office?

Thanks.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DIIAP, NCIISTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 18 Apr 2007 20:30:00 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: An Apology

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, April 18, 2007 4:27 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); James, Kathy
Subject: An Apology

Hi Peter and Bob and Dawn,

As you know, I had planned to go to CDC next thursday PM, but unfortunately I have some unexpected UNC obligations that simply will NOT allow me to be out of town on Friday.

I'm really sorry as I was looking forward to this meeting and the attendant discussion.

Please accept my apologies.

Thanks,

Mike

Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

>
> Thanks Mike. Will be great to have you.
>
> PK
> -----
> Sent from my wireless handheld
>
>
> ----- Original Message -----
> From: Myron Cohen <myron_cohen@med.unc.edu>
> To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N.
> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Sent: Fri Apr 06 09:34:01 2007
> Subject: Re: Fw: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>
> Ok. Ill get there as early as possible on thursday. I assume Bob
> will hook me up with the travel agency. I was amazed to see nyc
> moving ahead of your meeting. I am also concerned about reality
> testing of some assumptions about transmission probabilities, safety
> of circumcision if it becomes a profit center for surgeons, sexual behaviors, etc.

>
> see you soon.
>
> mike
>
> i
>
> Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>>
>> Hi Mike,
>> I think you should come. The first day will be largely presentations
>> of info you already know and limited new information you could get
>> up to speed on pretty quickly. Sounds like you have some views that
>> would be a valuable contribution for the second day of breakout discussions.
>>
>> I'm on leave this week. Can f/u next week.
>>
>> Cheers,
>> PK
>> -----
>> Sent from my wireless handheld
>>
>>
>> ----- Original Message -----
>> From: [REDACTED] (b)(6)
>> To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>> Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>> Sent: Fri Apr 06 08:09:38 2007
>> Subject: FW: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>>
>> Peter - Mike Cohen won't be able to arrive at the consultation until
>> afternoon. Is it worth it for him to come? Could you give him a
>> call? I don't have his number readily available, but Cathy
>> Burckhardt of my branch has his number.
>> Thanks
>> Bob Kohmescher
>>
>>
>> -----Original Message-----
>> From: Myron Cohen <myron_cohen@med.unc.edu>
>> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>> Sent: Thu Apr 05 08:07:51 2007
>> Subject: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>>
>> Hi Bob,
>>
>> I might be able to get there by early afternoon of April 26th but
>> this might not be so helpful to you, especially if there is a clamor
>> for attendance. Where are you actually meeting?
>>
>> I have actually spent a lot of time this week talking about
>> circumcision for MSM. To expose my bias I cannot see how clinical
>> trials would be ethical based on the biology of protection and the
>> risk behaviors of the study population. But this leads to interesting debates.
>>
>> Please advise.

>>
>> THX
>>
>> Mike
>>
>> Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>>> Mike - We're in the process of ensuring that we have adequate
>>> space at the hotel for the consultation on circumcision. Have you
>>> had a chance to review your calendar to see if you are available April 26-27?
>>>
>>> We'll be sending out more information about the consultation very
>>> shortly.
>>>
>>> Thanks,
>>>
>>> Bob Kohmescher
>>> Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch
>>> Centers for Disease Control & Prevention Division of HIV/AIDS
>>> Prevention (A43) 1600 Clifton Rd NE Atlanta, GA 30333
>>> -----
>>> (404) 639-1914
>>> (404) 639-5260 (fax)
>>> Corp 8/Rm 5057
>>> -----Original Message-----
>>> From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
>>> Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 5:49 PM
>>> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>>> Subject: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>>>
>>> THx, Il let you know ASAP. Did I ignore an earlier invitation??
> This was
>>>
>>> much discussed at NUH this week and Ken Mayer asked me why I had
>>> not responded., Sorry if that was the case.
>>>
>>> Mike
>>>
>>> Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>>>
>>>> Mike - CDC is sponsoring a meeting to discuss the research data
> on the
>>>>
>>>>
>>>>
>>>> value of circumcision in HIV prevention. The meeting will be held
>>>> in Atlanta on April 26 and 27.
>>>>
>>>> By the conclusion of the meeting, participants will:
>>>>
>>>> * Review science regarding circumcision efficacy in preventing
> HIV and
>>>>
>>>>
>>>>
>>>> other adverse health consequences
>>>>

>>> * Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant
> (general) and
>>>
>>>
>>> adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
>>>
>>> * Discuss potential next programmatic steps or recommendations
>>> that should be made by CDC
>>>
>>> *
>>>
>>> Please let me know whether you'll be able to attend. CDC will
>>> cover all travel costs. If you are interested and able to attend,
>>> we'll
> send
>>>
>>>
>>> a formal letter of invitation.
>>>
>>> And also, thanks for your willingness to speak at our 2007
>>> National HIV Prevention Conference in December!
>>>
>>> Bob Kohmescher
>>>
>>> Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch
>>>
>>> Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
>>>
>>> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (A43)
>>>
>>> 1600 Clifton Rd NE
>>>
>>> Atlanta, GA 30333
>>>
>>> ----->>
>>> (404) 639-1914
>>>
>>> (404) 639-5260 (fax)
>>>
>>> Corp 8/Rm 5057
>>>
>>> -----Original Message-----
>>> From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
>>> Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 6:57 PM
>>> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); James, Kathy
>>> Subject: Re: FW: 2007 National HIV Prevention Conference
>>>
>>> oops. maybe my signature is not working.
>>>
>>> my phone is 919-966-2536
>>>
>>> address ID Center
>>>
>>> UNC

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 14 Mar 2007 13:13:44 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Article on USPSTF methodology

Add the following to our confirmed invitee list.

Thanks.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 8:49 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Dawn: The USPSTF staff member we'd like to send to your meeting:

Tracy Wolff, MD, MPH
Center for Primary Care, Prevention and Clinical Partnerships
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality
540 Gaither Road
Rockville, MD 20850
(301) 427-1616
Tracy.Wolff@ahrq.hhs.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Sunday, March 11, 2007 10:16 PM
To: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

David,

We'll pay travel for someone from your office (a gov employee) to attend the circumcision consultation. Just let me know the name and contact info.

From: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Sent: Friday, March 09, 2007 11:37 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Article on USPSTF methodology

Dawn: Here's the methods paper from the Task Force that I mentioned. Nice speaking with you
– I'll get back to you about the AHRQ/USPSTF representative for your consultation meeting.

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 18 Apr 2007 19:09:43 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in t he US

Another one lost... Ouch. I was looking forward to hearing from him. Anyone know him who could convince him to change his mind?

-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Coates, Thomas [<mailto:TCoates@mednet.ucla.edu>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 18, 2007 15:05
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in t he US

My regrets, but I will not be able to attend this meeting as I have a very important grant going in May 7 and need to be home to finish it.

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Thu 4/12/2007 3:44 PM
To:
Cc:
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Colleagues,

We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this conference as detailed in the letter.
- 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.

Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB
Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 17 Apr 2007 18:01:22 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Well, we've struck out with Kaiser Family Foundation (Too bad, too: it sounds like they would have been great, but we got to them too late.) I'm thinking it is probably too late to ask Edgar Schoen to add this stuff in at this point, too. Peter? Would you like to try to cover this? Or shall we ask Raul if he could do it? Would a call with Jennifer Kates be helpful?

-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [mailto:jkates@kff.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 13:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Unfortunately, no one is available to participate on such short notice. However, as I mentioned earlier, I would be happy to have a phone briefing in advance with you or others involved, and/or send along some materials that could be helpful.

Jen

JENNIFER KATES
Vice President and Director, HIV Policy
Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

www.kff.org www.kaisernet.org www.statehealthfacts.org www.kaiserEDU.org
www.GlobalHealthFacts.org www.GlobalHealthReporting.org

www.kff.org/register

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:58 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for checking. It would be wonderful if you could identify someone.

-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [mailto:jkates@kff.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 09:42
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Not sure about someone else, since I am the person who focuses on this area and the notice is quite short. I will explore today and let you know, but doubt it.

JENNIFER KATES

Vice President and Director, HIV Policy

Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

www.kff.org www.kaisernetwork.org www.statehealthfacts.org www.kaiserEDU.org
www.GlobalHealthFacts.org www.GlobalHealthReporting.org

www.kff.org/register

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:42 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for your prompt reply. We regret the extremely short timeline; might it be possible to recommend someone else from your organization who might be available to give a short presentation at this consultation?

Thank you again.
-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [mailto:jkates@kff.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 09:24
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for the invitation. I really would like to attend and can provide information on Medicaid and financing, but I cannot make those dates next week. I did not realize the consultation was that soon.

If it is helpful, perhaps we can have a call in advance and I can share some information that way?

JENNIFER KATES

Vice President and Director, HIV Policy

Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

www.kff.org www.kaisernetwork.org www.statehealthfacts.org www.kaiserEDU.org
www.GlobalHealthFacts.org www.GlobalHealthReporting.org

www.kff.org/register

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:22 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Ms. Kates,

We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

We would also like to invite you to give a brief general presentation at this meeting regarding healthcare financing and reimbursement around HIV preventive services. We hope that you might be able to provide us and our consultants with relevant general background information about financing for preventive procedures at the state and national levels (e.g., how “medical necessity” is defined, what types of outside recommendations may have influence on this decision, etc.). We would be happy to provide more information if you will be available.

We understand that this consultation is occurring on very short notice; CDC is working quickly to respond appropriately to this emerging issue. We hope that your schedule will allow you to attend. Please contact me at your earliest convenience to indicate whether you might be available to attend this consultation or, if you are unavailable, to suggest other appropriate experts with experience in this area who might be able to provide our consultants with this important background information. Thank you in advance for your time.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this conference as detailed in the letter.
- 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.

Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting and hope that you will be able to participate.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Director, Center for Global Health
University of Michigan
1010 Tappan Street
Ann Arbor, MI 48106
734-763-2822
ataylor@umich.edu

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 13 Apr 2007 16:05:19 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US
Attachments: Zohar Male Circ April 2007.pdf

Paper from SF on prevalence of MC in their clinics and Jeff Klausner's thoughts. (Paper under review: not for distribution).

-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Klausner, Jeff (CDC sfdph.org)
Sent: Friday, April 13, 2007 11:55
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Susan Buchbinder
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Here is that paper under review.

Usual cautions, caveats, concerns with papers under review.

Thanks for that invite but currently our epi staff is stretched to thin and there are too many other competing priorities. I will get feedback from Susan. She and I are on the same page on this---ie, role of MC in MSM HIV likely to be very small.

I do think, however, for heterosexuals when you include all the other health benefits, the evidence for a strong US MC policy is quite good, so would favor that perspective and would support policy encouraging routine neonatal MC in the U.S.

Best,

Jeff

(See attached file: Zohar Male Circ April 2007.pdf)

Jeffrey D. Klausner, MD, MPH
Deputy Health Officer
Director, STD Prevention and Control Services
San Francisco Department of Public Health

Associate Clinical Professor of Medicine
University of California, San Francisco
Jeff.Klausner@sfdph.org

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attachments. Thank you.

"Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV> wrote on 04/13/2007 05:54:37 AM:

> Yes, Dr. Buchbinder is planning to attend. If you would like another
> representative there as well, we'd be supportive. We'll also watch with
> interest for your upcoming paper. Would it be possible to have a
> preview?

>
> Thanks. I hope all is well with your family.
> -Allan

> -----Original Message-----

> From: Klausner, Jeff (CDC sfdph.org)
> Sent: Thursday, April 12, 2007 21:37
> To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in
> the US

> Yes, I had planned to attend but family obligations came up.

> Have you invited Dr. Buchbinder? Susan Buchbinder?

> We also have a paper coming out on the epidemiology of male circumcision
> that would inform the proceedings.

> Best,

> Jeff

> *****

> Jeffrey D. Klausner, MD, MPH
> Deputy Health Officer
> Director, STD Prevention and Control Services
> San Francisco Department of Public Health

> Associate Clinical Professor of Medicine
> University of California, San Francisco
> Jeff.Klausner@sfdph.org

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> you have received this communication in error, please notify me by reply
> e-mail and immediately and permanently delete this message and any
> attachments. Thank you.

> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV> wrote on 04/12/2007
> 03:57:04 PM:

>> Dr. Klausner,
>>
>> We are disappointed that you will not be able to attend. If you would
>> like to recommend an alternate representative from SFDPH, we would
>> welcome their input and would support their travel expenses.
>>
>> Thank you.
>> -Allan
>>
>>
>>
>> -----Original Message-----
>> From: Klausner, Jeff (CDC sfdph.org)
>> Sent: Thursday, April 12, 2007 18:53
>> To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>> Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
> in
>> the US
>>
>> I cannot attend.
>>
>> Thank you.
>>
>>
> *****
>> Jeffrey D. Klausner, MD, MPH
>> Deputy Health Officer
>> Director, STD Prevention and Control Services
>> San Francisco Department of Public Health
>>
>> Associate Clinical Professor of Medicine
>> University of California, San Francisco
>> Jeff.Klausner@sfdph.org
>>
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>> information included in this message and any attachments is
> prohibited.
>> If
>> you have received this communication in error, please notify me by
> reply
>> e-mail and immediately and permanently delete this message and any
>> attachments. Thank you.
>>
>>
>> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avi0@CDC.GOV> wrote on
> 04/12/2007
>> 03:44:07 PM:
>>
>>> Colleagues,
>>>
>>> We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming Consultation

>>> on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other
>>> Health Consequences in the United States to be held on April 26-27,
>>> 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in
>> Atlanta,
>> GA.

>>>

>>> Attached are the following:

>>> 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference

>>> 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Scamon containing instructions
>>> for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your
>>> travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this
>>> conference as detailed in the letter.

>>> 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this
>>> form to BL Scamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they
>>> may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel
>> arrangements.

>>>

>>> Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should
>> arise.

>>>

>>> Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting.

>>>

>>> Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

>>> LCDR, US Public Health Service

>>> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch

>>> National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB

>>> Prevention (proposed)

>>> Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

>>> 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333

>>> W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

>>> [attachment "Circumcision Consultation Conference Registration

>>> Form.doc" deleted by Jeff Klausner/DPII/SFGOV] [attachment "MC

>>> Consultation ConferenceLogistics Letter 1.doc" deleted by Jeff

>>> Klausner/DPII/SFGOV] [attachment "MC Consultation Invitation Letter.

>>> pdf" deleted by Jeff Klausner/DPII/SFGOV]

>>

>>

>>

>>

>

>

>

>

**Declining Rates in Male Circumcision amidst Increasing Evidence of Its Public
Health Benefit**

Zohar Mor, MD, MHA, MPH¹

Charlotte K. Kent, PhD²

Robert P. Kohn, MPH²

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Abstract

Background: Recent experimental evidence has demonstrated the benefits of male circumcision for the prevention of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection. Studies have also shown that male circumcision is cost-effective and protects against other ulcerative sexually transmitted diseases (STDs). The epidemiology of male circumcision in the United States is poorly studied and most prior reports were limited by self-reported measures.

Objective: To describe male circumcision trends among men attending the San Francisco municipal STD clinic, and to correlate the findings with HIV, syphilis and sexual orientation.

Methodology: A cross sectional study was performed by reviewing all electronic records of males attending the San Francisco municipal STD clinic between 1996 and 2005. The prevalence of circumcision over time and by subpopulation such as different races and sexual orientation were measured. The findings were further correlated with the presence of syphilis and HIV infection.

Main Outcome Measures: Circumcision status was determined by physical examination and disease status by clinical evaluation with laboratory confirmation.

Principle findings: Among 58,598 male patients, 32,613 (55.7%, 95% Confidence Interval (CI) 55.2-56.1) were circumcised. Male circumcision varied significantly by decade of birth (increasing between 1920 and 1950 and declining overall since the 1960's), race/ethnicity (Black: 62.2%, 95% CI 61.2-63.2, White: 60.0%, 95% CI 59.46-60.5, Asian Pacific Islander: 48.2%, 46.9-49.5 95% CI, and Hispanic: 42.2%, 95% CI 41.3-43.1), and sexual orientation (gay/bisexual: 73.0%, 95% CI 72.6-73.4; heterosexual:

66.0%, 65.5-66.5). Male circumcision may have been modestly protective against syphilis in HIV-uninfected heterosexual men (PR 0.92, 95% C.I. 0.83-1.02, P=0.06).

Conclusions: Male circumcision was common among men seeking STD services in San Francisco but has declined substantially in recent decades. Male circumcision rates differed by race/ethnicity and sexual orientation. Given recent studies suggesting the public health benefits of male circumcision, a reconsideration of national male circumcision policy is needed to respond to current trends.

Key words: male circumcision, epidemiology, HIV, STD, syphilis

Introduction

In North America, male circumcision has been promoted for more than a century by the medical community and is an accepted social norm [1]. Based on a small U.S. probability sample (n=1410) using self-report of circumcision status conducted in 1992, it was estimated that 77% of males born in the United States (U.S.) are circumcised [2]. Even though male circumcision is one of the most common operations performed in the U.S. [3] it has become highly controversial. Advocates who oppose male circumcision have challenged its medical benefits, questioned its ethical underpinnings, and highlighted its potential associated risks [1,4].

The first report suggesting male circumcision was protective against HIV infection was published in 1986 [5]. Many subsequent studies have demonstrated that male circumcision reduces susceptibility to HIV infection with a protective effect ranging between 23% and 88% [6,7]. Three recently completed randomized-controlled trials—considered the ‘gold standard’ of scientific evidence—have confirmed the protective effect of male circumcision demonstrating a reduced risk of HIV acquisition between 48-60%. All trials were discontinued by the ethical boards, as significant results in HIV reduction were achieved in the interim analyses [8-10]. Following those encouraging findings, male circumcision was recently recommended by the WHO and the UNAIDS [11]. Other studies have suggested that male circumcision was associated with lower risk of genital ulcerative disease, such as chancroid and syphilis [12,13], as well as it being a cost-effective procedure [14,15].

Given the recent interest in male circumcision and its demonstrated benefits, further understanding of the trends and distribution of male circumcision in the U.S. is critical. We describe the epidemiology of male circumcision based on physical examination among male patients visiting the San Francisco municipal STD clinic during the recent decade.

Methods:

We reviewed electronic medical records among male patients visiting the San Francisco municipal STD clinic between January 1, 1996 and December 31, 2005.

Following clinic face-to-face registration to collect self-reported demographic (including race/ethnicity) and behavioral information, clinicians performed physical examination of the genitalia among all male patients. Clinicians recorded penile circumcision status in the medical records as “Yes” or “No.” The remainder of the examination, diagnostic testing and treatment was performed according to standard clinic protocols.

In order to examine the relationship between circumcision status, HIV and ulcerative infection, such as syphilis, prevalence ratios (PR) were computed by comparing infection status in visits of circumcised and non-circumcised men. Each of the infections was counted only once, e.g, patient-visits in HIV-infected patients were restricted to one count, even if multiple visits were made. For birth cohort trend analyses of circumcision we compared unique patient records excluding those of persons with repeat visits. Using standard methods, 95% Exact Confidence Intervals (CI) were calculated (Stata 5.0, StataCorp, LP, Texas, U.S.A.) Proportions were compared by Chi-square analysis. As these were de-identified medical records undergoing retrospective analyses, no human subjects review was required in accordance with the Code of Federal Regulations, Title 45.

Results:

Between January 1, 1996 and December 31, 2005, 58,598 male patients were examined at the San Francisco municipal STD clinic. During that period, these men made 154,177 clinic visits, with an average of 2.6 visits per patient. The majority of male patients were white (54.1%), born before 1970 (52.3%), and 35.5% identified as gay/bisexual (Table 1). Fifty-one percent of patient visits were by gay or bisexual men. Among patients, 32,613 (55.7%, 95% CI 55.2-56.1) were circumcised. Circumcision status varied by race/ethnicity (Table 1): the highest proportion was 62.2% among Blacks to the lowest proportion of 42.2% among Hispanics ($P<.001$); and by sexual orientation 66.0% (95% CI 65.5-66.5) among heterosexual men and 73.0% (95% CI 72.6-73.4) among gay/bisexual men ($P<.001$).

By decade of birth, we observed increasing rates of circumcision among men born between 1920 and 1950, and then an average 33.4% decline in rates of circumcision among those born after the 1960's (Figure). Those trends were similar across all racial/ethnic groups.

Table 2 shows the proportion of visits by circumcised men at the San Francisco municipal STD clinic from 1996 through 2005 by sexual orientation, syphilis and HIV infection status. There was a trend towards a protective effect of circumcision for syphilis infection in heterosexual men regardless of HIV status. Among gay/bisexual men, no such protective effect was seen and also no association was found between circumcision status and HIV infection (71.1% circumcised *versus* 72.2%, $PR=0.97$, 95% CI 0.90-1.0,

P=0.52). Among HIV-infected heterosexual men 73.7% were circumcised *versus* 72.3% circumcised in HIV-uninfected heterosexual men (PR = 1.02, 95% CI .92-1.08).

Discussion

A majority (55.6%) of male patients attending the San Francisco municipal STD clinic between 1996 and 2005 were circumcised. Afro-American and White men were more commonly circumcised than Hispanic men and men of Asian/ Pacific Islander descent. A steady and substantial decline in circumcision rates was observed beginning in men born after 1960 across all racial/ethnic groups. There was a trend towards a protective effect of male circumcision in heterosexual men for syphilis infection.

The strengths of this study include a very large sample population that visited the clinic within a decade and could be representative of current male residents throughout the U.S. At least 85% of men seen at the San Francisco municipal STD Clinic during the study period were San Francisco residents. Census data in San Francisco suggest that most county residents were born in the U.S. (63%) but only 35% were born in California suggesting that most STD clinic patients were born outside of California [16]. Therefore, the characteristics of this study population by race/ethnicity might be similar to those of men currently living in the U.S.

In addition, circumcision status was determined by physical examination by trained clinicians and both syphilis and HIV status were determined by clinical testing with laboratory confirmation.

Male circumcision is an accepted procedure in Jewish and Muslim dominated countries and also in other areas, like North America and Korea [17]. The decision to circumcise is usually made by parents, and stems from religious practices, cultural factors, social

pressures and health beliefs. While we observed declines in circumcision among younger men across all racial/ethnic groups, we found that both Black and White men were circumcised more often in comparison with other racial/ethnic groups, suggesting important differences by culture.

Previous studies correlating male circumcision and the prevalence of HIV were ecological or cross sectional and performed in Africa, where HIV epidemic is generalized and the mode of transmission is mainly heterosexual. However, the relationship between circumcision status and STDs or HIV infection in gay or bisexual men has been poorly studied. A cross-sectional study in the early 1990's conducted in the U.S. [18] found that uncircumcised gay men were two-fold more likely to be infected with HIV. A recent study [19] found similar elevated risk of HIV acquisition among uncircumcised gay men, but did not correlate sexual practices and circumcision status with HIV acquisition. Our study included a very large number of visits made by gay or bisexual men (nearly 80,000 visits), and to our knowledge, consists of the largest sample of gay men ever studied. Our findings, showing no significant differences between circumcision status and risk of HIV or syphilis infection, are consistent with the non-penile, primarily rectal acquisition of those infections among gay men in the U.S. [20], rather than heterosexual practices, during which the foreskin may be exposed to HIV by insertive intercourse. Because large proportions of gay men practice both insertive and receptive anal intercourse [21], the ability to differentiate between different risks for HIV infection associated with sexual practices *versus* circumcision status is limited. Consequently, gay men and other men who have sex with men might not gain the same level of protection from circumcision as

heterosexual men.

In this study, male circumcision was found to be consistent with protection against syphilis infection in heterosexual men, similar to prior reports [12,13]. That finding in our study supports our measurement of circumcision status as it corroborates prior epidemiologic evidence and the current biological understanding of the foreskin. That tissue, which is exposed upon erection, provides a warm, moist and supportive environment for infectious agents between the gland penis and the intact foreskin, thus prolonging those pathogens' survival [22]; it also may cover ulcers or sores, which consequently may be responsible for late diagnosis and treatment [23]. In addition, the visceral aspect of the foreskin is poorly keratinized and contains a high density of Langerhans cells, which are suspected to facilitate the delivery of pathogens into regional lymph nodes and further to the blood stream [24].

Nevertheless, health promoters should be aware that as circumcision is perceived by the public to be protective against HIV acquisition, it may encourage behavioral disinhibition. Involvement in high risk behavior by circumcised men may compensate for the relative benefit of circumcision.

Limitations of our study should be addressed. Firstly, the study design was a retrospective cross-sectional analysis, for which it is usually difficult to ascertain the temporal sequence of exposure and outcome. Because most males are circumcised during infancy, it is unlikely that men in our study acquired STDs or HIV infection prior to their circumcision. While a very large sample, the true generalizability of our findings outside of men attending that clinic is unknown. The large sample size, however, may allow our

results to be compared to other studies in the U.S, and findings from subpopulations in our clinic might be similar to comparable subpopulations in the U.S. Secondly, behavioral attributes for the study participants were not available, therefore only a univariate analysis is presented at this stage.

An important strength of our study was that circumcision status was determined by clinical examination reducing the likelihood of misclassification. Several studies have found that objective penile physical examination yield more accurate results regarding circumcision status than self-report [2,6,25].

In conclusion, while a majority of men attending the San Francisco STD clinic were circumcised, there were large and steady declines in circumcision across all racial/ethnic groups since 1960. There were significant differences by racial/ethnic groups suggesting important socio-cultural factors related to decisions to circumcise newborn males. Given the recent evidence demonstrating the substantial potential public health benefit of male circumcision and our observed declines in circumcision rates, national organizations that promote circumcision policy should review current practice guidelines in responding to those trends.

Figure: Trends in circumcision proportion of male patients by birth decade and race/ethnicity San Francisco municipal STD clinic, 1920-1980.

Table 1. Selected demographic characteristics of male patients: San Francisco municipal STD clinic, 1996 –2005.

Characteristic	Patients		Circumcised
	N	% of the total	N (%) [95% CI]
Race/ethnicity			
Black	9,214	15.8	5,731 (62.2) [61.2-63.2]
White	31,685	54.1	18,996 (60.0) [59.4-60.5]
Asian/Pacific Islander	5,876	10.0	2,834 (48.2) [46.9-49.5]
Hispanic	10,980	18.7	4,634 (42.2) [41.3-43.1]
Missing, unknown	843	1.4	397 (47.1) [43.7-50.5]
Birth Decade			
1900-1920	178	0.3	28 (15.7) [10.7-21.9]
1930	557	1.0	262 (47.0) [42.8-51.3]
1940	2,696	4.6	1,421 (52.7) [50.8-54.6]
1950	8,281	14.1	4,844 (58.5) [57.4-59.6]
1960	18,981	32.4	11,275 (59.4) [58.7-60.1]
1970	21,837	37.3	12,098 (55.4) [54.7-56.1]
1980-1990	5,606	9.6	2,418 (43.1) [41.8-44.5]
Missing, unknown	462	0.7	255 (55.2) [50.5-59.8]
Sexual Orientation			
Gay, bisexual	20,832	35.5	12,577 (60.4) [59.7-61.0]
Heterosexual	33,867	57.8	18,352 (54.2) [53.7-54.7]
Missing, unknown	3,899	6.7	2,253 (57.8) [56.2-59.3]
Total	58,598		32,613 (55.7) [55.2-56.1]

Table 2. Percent circumcised in those with and without syphilis infection by HIV status and sexual orientation, as determined during male patient visits, San Francisco municipal STD clinic, 1996–2005.

Sexual orientation	Syphilis infection	HIV-infected		HIV -uninfected	
		Circumcised % (n/N)	PR* (95% CI)	Circumcised % (n/N)	PR (95% CI)
Heterosexual	Yes	62.5 (10/16)	0.85 (0.40-1.56)	66.7 (384/576)	0.92 (0.83-1.02)
	No	73.8 (1,050/1,423)	Ref.	72.4 (36,290/50,128)	Ref.
Gay/ bisexual	Yes	75.8 (214/282)	1.0 (0.87-1.15)	72.7 (384/528)	0.98 (0.88-1.08)
	No	75.4 (15,910/21,090)	Ref.	74.6 (34,210/45,869)	Ref.

*PR = Prevalence ratio of circumcision status by syphilis infection (Yes/No)

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 12 Apr 2007 22:57:35 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Darn! I was afraid this would happen...
-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Klausner, Jeff (CDC sfdph.org)
Sent: Thursday, April 12, 2007 18:53
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

I cannot attend.

Thank you.

Jeffrey D. Klausner, MD, MPH
Deputy Health Officer
Director, STD Prevention and Control Services
San Francisco Department of Public Health

Associate Clinical Professor of Medicine
University of California, San Francisco
Jeff.Klausner@sfdph.org

This message and any attachments are solely for the intended recipient and may contain confidential or privileged information. If you are not the intended recipient, any disclosure, copying, use or distribution of the information included in this message and any attachments is prohibited. If you have received this communication in error, please notify me by reply e-mail and immediately and permanently delete this message and any attachments. Thank you.

"Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV> wrote on 04/12/2007 03:44:07 PM:

- > Colleagues,
- >
- > We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming Consultation
- > on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other
- > Health Consequences in the United States to be held on April 26-27,
- > 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta,
- > GA.
- >
- > Attached are the following:
- > 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- > 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions
- > for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your
- > travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this
- > conference as detailed in the letter.

- > 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this
- > form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they
- > may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.
- >
- > Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.
- >
- > Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting.
- >
- > Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
- > LCDR, US Public Health Service
- > Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
- > National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB
- > Prevention (proposed)
- > Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
- > 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
- > W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov
- > [attachment "Circumcision Consultation Conference Registration
- > Form.doc" deleted by Jeff Klausner/DPH/SFGOV] [attachment "MC
- > Consultation ConferenceLogistics Letter 1.doc" deleted by Jeff
- > Klausner/DPH/SFGOV] [attachment "MC Consultation Invitation Letter.
- > pdf" deleted by Jeff Klausner/DPH/SFGOV]

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 10 Apr 2007 13:25:04 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention
Attachments: image001.gif

Another dead end. I'll start trying state Medicaid medical directors. Other ideas?
-A

-----Original Message-----

From: John Palen [mailto:jpalen@gwu.edu]
Sent: Monday, April 09, 2007 16:47
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention

Allan

Unfortunately I will need to decline the invitation. Dr Romaguera at CDC may be able to providenames of other potential presenters.

John GII Palen
jpalen@gwu.edu
202-994-1000

---- Original Message ----

From: "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV>
Date: 4/6/07 10:22 am
To: "jpalen@gwu.edu" <jpalen@gwu.edu>
Cc: "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@CDC.GOV>
Subj: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention
Dr. Palen,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27, 2007 in Atlanta. You were recommended to us by Dr. Jeff Levi as an expert on reimbursement for HIV prevention services (see below), and we would like to invite you to attend as a consultant and presenter at this meeting. CDC will support your travel expenses and meals if you are able to attend.

We would further like to invite you to give a presentation (approx. 20 min) at this meeting regarding healthcare financing and reimbursement around HIV preventive services. We hope that you might be able to provide us and our consultants with relevant general background information about financing for preventive procedures at the state and federal levels.

Please contact me at your earliest convenience to indicate whether you

might be available to attend this consultation or, if you are unavailable, to suggest other appropriate experts with experience in this area who might be able to provide our consultants with this important background. Thank you in advance for your time.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
(proposed)
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From: Jeff Levi [<mailto:jlevi@TEAH.ORG>]
Sent: Friday, April 06, 2007 09:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: jpalen@gwu.edu
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention

Thanks for the invitation. Unfortunately, I already have commitments on those dates. As you know, my colleagues and I at GW have done earlier work on reimbursement for HIV testing - I am assuming this is why the invitation was extended to me. Given my new duties at Trust for America's Health, I am less on top of reimbursement issues. You might contact John Palen, jpalen@gwu.edu, who was the lead on the HIV testing study for GW; he might be able to provide some insights or alternative resources.

Jeffrey Levi, Ph.D.

Executive Director

Trust for America's Health

1707 H Street, NW

Washington, DC 20006

202-223-9877

and

Associate Professor

Department of Health Policy

George Washington University School of Public Health and Health Services

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 15:53:58 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation
Attachments: JC1320_MaleCircumcision_Final_240407_5_.pdf

OK to distribute by email?
-A

From: Hankins, Catherine [mailto:hankinsc@unaids.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 10:50
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

Hi Alan,

Helen and I would like to have the attached draft document on determinants and prevalence of male circumcision sent or provided to participants if possible.

Thanks,
Cate

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, 24 April, 2007 03:18
Subject: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

Colleagues,

We are planning to distribute contact information for all participants at the upcoming consultation. While we have previously requested your contact information for travel arrangements, we are aware that at times the information we have is not that which participants would like to have published. Therefore, we would like to ask you to complete the following with the information you would wish to have distributed to participants at this consultation. Also please indicate if you would prefer to have any of this information withheld. Thank you for your assistance.

Full Name (with degrees):
Title
Organization
Address
Telephone Number
Email

In addition, we have corrected a typographical error that was discovered in the agenda. A revised copy is attached for your reference.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
CDC

07

Male circumcision: Global trends and determinants of prevalence, safety and acceptability

Male circumcision:
Global trends and determinants
of prevalence, safety and acceptability

February 2007

DRAFT DOCUMENT

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report is the result of collaborative work between the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, the World Health Organization and the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS). The report was written by Helen Weiss and Jonny Polonsky, with detailed input from Robert Bailey, Catherine Hankins, Daniel Halperin, and George Schmid. We also thank the following for their written comments: David Alwick, Chiweni Chimbwete, Kim Dickson, Inon Schenker, Charles Shey Wiysonge and Isabelle de Zoysa.

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SUMMARY

Male circumcision is one of the oldest and most common surgical procedures worldwide, undertaken for many reasons: religious, cultural, social and medical. There is conclusive evidence from observational data and three randomised controlled trials that circumcised men have a significantly lower risk of becoming infected with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Demand for safe, affordable, male circumcision is expected to increase rapidly, and country-level decision makers need information about the socio-cultural and medical determinants of circumcision, as well as risks of the procedure, in the context of comprehensive HIV prevention programming.

Scope of the review

The aim of this report is to review the determinants, prevalence, safety and acceptability of male circumcision, focusing on sub-Saharan Africa. In the first section, we review the religious, cultural and social determinants of male circumcision and estimate the global and regional prevalences. In the second section, we summarise medical aspects of the procedure, including medical indications for circumcision, surgical methods used and the complications of circumcision carried out in clinical and non-clinical settings. The third section focuses on the public health implications of the fact that male circumcision reduces risk of HIV infection, including a summary of the acceptability of adult male circumcision in currently non-circumcising populations in sub-Saharan Africa with high incidence of HIV.

Results

Approximately 30% of males are estimated to be circumcised globally, of whom an estimated two-thirds are Muslim. Other common determinants of male circumcision are ethnicity, perceived health and sexual benefits, and the desire to conform to social norms. Neonatal circumcision is common in Israel, the United States of America, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, and in much of the Middle East, Central Asia and West Africa, but is uncommon in East and southern Africa where median age at circumcision varies from boyhood to the late teens or twenties. In several countries, prevalence of non-religious circumcision has undergone rapid increases and decreases, reflecting cultural mixing and changing perceptions of health and sexual benefits.

There is substantial evidence that male circumcision protects against several disease, including urinary tract infections, syphilis, chancroid, invasive penile cancer as well as HIV. However, as with any surgical procedure, there are risks involved. Neonatal circumcision is a simpler procedure than adolescent or adult circumcision and has a very low rate of adverse events, which are usually minor (0.2%-0.4%). Adolescent or adult circumcision can be associated with bleeding, haematoma or sepsis but these are treatable and there is little evidence of long-term sequelae when undertaken in a clinical setting with experienced providers. In contrast, circumcision undertaken by inexperienced providers with inadequate instruments, or with poor after-care can result in serious complications.

Recent studies of acceptability among non-circumcising communities with high prevalence of HIV in southern Africa were fairly consistent in finding that a majority of men would be willing to be circumcised, if it were done safely and at minimal cost. The primary concerns were around safety, pain and the cost of the procedure. Facilitators of acceptability of circumcision were perceived protection from sexually transmitted infections (STI), including HIV; improved genital hygiene; and improved sexual pleasure of both the male and his female partner. Public health concerns about increased uptake of male circumcision services focus on safety, acceptability, and risk compensation. To date, there is modest evidence of risk compensation following adult male circumcision, and care must be taken to embed any male circumcision provision within existing HIV prevention packages that include intensive counselling on safer sex, particularly regarding reduction in number of concurrent sexual partners and correct and consistent use of male and female condoms.

Conclusions

There is increasing demand for male circumcision in southern Africa and future expansion of circumcision services must be embedded within comprehensive HIV prevention programming, including informed consent and risk reduction counselling. Male circumcision can have serious sequelae if carried out in unhygienic settings or by inexperienced providers, and it is therefore essential that existing and future demand for circumcision is matched by provision of adequate equipment and training of personnel to conduct safe, voluntary and affordable male circumcision. If correctly planned, increased provision of accessible safe adult male circumcision services could also increase opportunities to educate men in areas of high HIV prevalence about a variety of reproductive and sexual health topics, including hygiene, sexuality, gender relations and the need for ongoing combination prevention strategies to further decrease risk of HIV acquisition and transmission.

SECTION 1 :Determinants of male circumcision & global prevalence

1.1 Introduction

Male circumcision is one of the oldest surgical procedures known, traditionally undertaken as a mark of cultural identity or religious importance. With advances in surgery in the 19th century, and increased mobility in the 20th century, the procedure was introduced into some previously non-circumcising cultures for both health-related and social reasons. In this section, we review the main determinants of male circumcision, and describe the global and regional prevalences of male circumcision today.

1.2 Determinants of male circumcision

Historically, male circumcision has been associated with religious practice and ethnic identity. Circumcision was practised among ancient Semitic peoples including Egyptians and Jews ¹, with the earliest records depicting the practice coming from Egyptian tomb work and wall paintings dating from around 2300 BC, (Figure 1)

Figure 1 : An ancient Egyptian relief from Ankhmahor, Saqqara, Egypt (2345-2182 BCE) representing the adult circumcision ceremony (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Image:Egypt_circ.jpg#filehistory)

1.2.1 Religion

1.2.1.1 Judaism

In the Jewish religion, male infants are traditionally circumcised on their eighth day of life, providing there is no medical contraindication. The justification, in the Jewish holy book (the Torah), is that a covenant was made between Abraham and God, the outward sign of which is circumcision for all Jewish males: *"This is my covenant, which ye shall keep, between me and you and thy seed after thee: every male among you shall be circumcised"* (Genesis 17:10).

Male circumcision continues to be almost universally practiced among Jewish people. For example, almost all newborn Jewish males in Israel ², an estimated 99% Jewish men in United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland ³ and 98% of Jewish men in the United States, are circumcised ⁴.

1.2.1.2 Islam

Muslims are the largest religious group to practice male circumcision. As an Abrahamic faith, Muslims practice circumcision as a confirmation of their relationship with God, and the practice is also known as *tahera*, meaning purification. There is no specific mention of circumcision in the Qur'an⁵, and it is only obligatory (*wajib*) among one of the six Islamic schools of law (the Shafite school). The other schools regard the practice as traditional (*sunnah*) and strongly encourage it. It is also essential for a man to be circumcised to lawfully make the Hajj to Mecca, one of the five pillars of Islamic belief⁶.

With the global spread of Islam from the 7th century AD, male circumcision was widely adopted among previously non-circumcising peoples. In some regions, male circumcision was already a cultural tradition prior to the arrival of Islam (for example among the Poro in West Africa, and in Timor in SE Asia⁷⁻⁹). In other regions, Islam became a major determinant of circumcision. For example, in Rakai District, Uganda, 99% of Muslim men are circumcised, compared with just 4% of non-Muslim men¹⁰. However, this is not always the case, and in nearby Mwanza region of the northwest of the United Republic of Tanzania which has no traditionally circumcising ethnic group, circumcision is not universal among Muslim men (estimated prevalence 74% among the Sukuma ethnic group) suggesting a continuing influence of the non-circumcising culture among Muslims in this setting¹¹.

There is no clearly prescribed age for circumcision in Islam, although the prophet Muhammad recommended it be carried out at an early age and reportedly circumcised his sons on the seventh day after birth⁶. Many Muslims perform the rite on this day, although a Muslim may be circumcised at any age between birth and puberty. For example, in Pakistan, the general practice is to circumcise boys born in hospital a few days before discharge, whereas those born outside hospital are circumcised between the ages of 3 and 7 years⁶. Similarly, in Turkey, Muslim boys are circumcised between the 8th day after birth and puberty¹², and in Indonesia, typically between the ages of 5 and 18 years⁸.

1.2.1.3 Other religions

With the major exceptions of Islam and Judaism, religion tends not to be a major determinant of male circumcision and many religions, including Hinduism and Buddhism appear to have a neutral stance towards it.

The Coptic Christians in Egypt and the Ethiopian Orthodox Christians are two of the oldest surviving forms of Christianity⁵, and they retain many of the features of early Christianity, including male circumcision (e.g. 97% of Orthodox men in Ethiopia are circumcised¹³). Circumcision is not prescribed in other forms of Christianity – for example, St. Paul wrote: "in Christ Jesus neither circumcision nor uncircumcision count for anything" (Galatians 5:6) and a Papal Bull issued in 1442 by the Roman Catholic Church stated that male circumcision was unnecessary *Therefore it strictly orders all who glory in the name of Christian, not to practise circumcision either before or after baptism, since whether or not they place their hope in it, it cannot possibly be observed without loss of eternal salvation.*¹⁴ Focus group discussions on male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa found no clear consensus on compatibility of male circumcision with Christian beliefs¹⁵. Some Christian churches in South Africa oppose the practice, viewing it as a pagan ritual¹⁶, while others, including the Nomiya church in Kenya, require circumcision for membership¹⁷ and participants in focus group discussions in Zambia and Malawi mentioned similar beliefs that Christians should practice circumcision since Jesus was circumcised and the Bible teaches the practice^{18, 19}.

In some West African countries, circumcision prevalence tends to be lower among those of traditional religion than among Christians (66% vs. 93% in Burkina Faso, 68% vs. 95% in Ghana¹³). Although religion and ethnicity can be closely correlated, religion can be a strong determinant within an ethnic group. For example among the Mole-Dagbani in Ghana, 97% of Muslims are circumcised, 78% of Christians, 43% of those with traditional religion, and 52% of those with no religion¹³. In Cameroon, circumcision is almost universal among all religions except the Animists (79% prevalence) among whom there is one particular

ethnic group, the Mboom, who tend not to circumcise (40%), compared with a circumcision prevalence of 89% among non-Mboom Animists.

1.2.2 Ethnicity

Circumcision has been practiced for non-religious reasons for many thousands of years in sub-Saharan Africa, and in many ethnic groups around the world, including aboriginal Australasians^{20,21}, the Aztecs and Mayans in the Americas^{5,22,23}, inhabitants of the Philippines and Eastern Indonesia⁸ and of various Pacific Islands, including Fiji²⁴ and the Polynesian islands⁷.

Prevalence of circumcision within a country can vary dramatically by ethnicity. For example, although an estimated 84% of all Kenyan men are circumcised, it is much lower among the Luo and Turkana ethnic groups (17% and 40% respectively)¹³ and focus group discussions among adult Luo men and women found no knowledge of any history of male circumcision among the Luo in Kenya. Instead, children traditionally had their six lower front teeth carefully removed at initiation. Similarly, male circumcision is not practiced among the Jopadhola, Acholi and other Luo-speaking River-Lake Nilotic groups in Uganda and southern

Figure 2: Traditional circumcision in Uganda (photo permission pending)

Sudan from where the Luo migrated²⁵. In the majority of these cultures, circumcision is an integral part of a rite-of-passage to manhood, although originally it may have been a test of bravery and endurance (Figure 2)²⁶. Circumcision is also associated with factors such as masculinity, social cohesion with boys of the same age who become circumcised at the same time, self-identity and spirituality²⁷. The association with initiation to manhood is not universal however, with some ethnic groups, such as the Yoruba and Igbo in Nigeria, circumcising in infancy²¹. The ethnographer Arnold Van Gennep in his 1909 work 'The Rites of Passage'²⁸, describes various initiation rites which are present in many circumcision rituals. These include a three stage process: separation from normal society; a period during which the neophyte undergoes transformation; and finally reintegration into society in a new social role. A psychological explanation for this process is that ambiguity in social roles creates tension, and a symbolic reclassification is necessary as individuals approach the transition from being defined as a child to being defined as an adult. This is supported by the fact that many rituals attach specific meaning to circumcision which justify its purpose within this context. For example, certain ethnic groups including the Dogon and Dowayo of West Africa, and the Xhosa of South Africa view the foreskin as the feminine element of the penis, the removal of which (along with passing certain tests) makes a man of the child^{29,30}.

Ethnicity is thus a major determinant of circumcision worldwide – for example, in ethnic groups of Bendel State in southern Nigeria, 43% of men stated that their motivation for circumcision was to maintain their tradition³¹. In some settings where circumcision is the norm there is discrimination against non-circumcised men. In some cultures such as the Yao in Malawi, or the Lunda and Luvale tribes in Zambia, or the Bagisu in Uganda^{11,18,32}, it is unacceptable to remain uncircumcised, to the extent that forced circumcisions of older boys are not uncommon¹⁵. Among the Xhosa in South Africa, men who have not

been circumcised can suffer extreme forms of punishment, including bullying and beatings²⁹. This discrimination may extend to entire ethnic groups, as in the case of the Luo in Kenya, who do not traditionally practice circumcision and report that they are often discriminated against by other Kenyans because of this²⁵.

1.2.3 Social determinants

1.2.3.1 Social desirability

Today, male circumcision is performed for a range of reasons, mainly social or health-related, in addition to religion and ethnicity. The desire to conform is an important motivation for circumcision in places where the majority of boys are circumcised. A survey in Denver, United States where circumcision occurs shortly after birth, found that parents, especially fathers, of newborn boys cited social reasons as the main determinant for choosing circumcision (e.g. not wanting him to look different). The main correlate of circumcision status was circumcision status of the father, with 90% of circumcised fathers choosing to circumcise their son, compared with 23% of non-circumcised fathers³³.

In the Philippines, where circumcision is almost universal and typically occurs at age 10-14, a survey of boys found stronger evidence of social determinants, with two-thirds of boys choosing to be circumcised simply 'to avoid being uncircumcised', and 41% stating that it was 'part of the tradition'³⁴. Social concerns were also the primary reason for circumcision in the Republic of Korea³⁵ with 61% of respondents believing they would be ridiculed by their peer group unless they were circumcised in one study³⁶.

Social desirability may also contribute to the relatively recent uptake of circumcision among the Akan ethnic group in Ghana which traditionally did not elect circumcised men as chiefs. However, in the past century male circumcision has become more common^{37,38} and the most recent Demographic & Health Survey (DHS) shows that 99% of Akan men were circumcised and 83% of Akan men reported that circumcision was practiced in their community¹³. The reasons given for the uptake of male circumcision include social, hygiene, disease prevention, female preference, enhanced sexual enjoyment³⁹. A further example of recent changing practice comes from the Sukuma ethnic group in the northwest of the United Republic of Tanzania which is also traditionally non-circumcising. The word for circumcision in the Sukuma language is derogatory (njilwa); however, now that boys mix with other ethnic groups at school, the practice is more acceptable, with an estimated prevalence of 21%¹¹.

The desire to 'belong' is also likely to be the main factor behind the high rate of adult male circumcisions among immigrants to Israel from non-circumcising countries (predominantly the former Soviet Union)⁴⁰.

1.2.3.2 Socio-economic status

Socio-economic factors also influence circumcision prevalence, especially in countries with more recent uptake of the practice such as English-speaking industrialised countries. When male circumcision was first practised in the United Kingdom in the late 19th and early 20th century, it was most prevalent among the upper classes⁴¹. A study published in 1953 found that 74% of private hospital patients in New York City were circumcised, compared to 57% of non-private patients⁴². A similar association was seen in a recent nationwide survey in Australia, which found that the proportion of men circumcised was significantly associated with higher levels of education and income⁴³. In the United States, a review of 4.7 million newborn male circumcisions nationwide between 1988 and 2000 also found a significant association with private insurance and higher socioeconomic status⁴⁴, which is likely to reflect the low circumcision prevalence among recent immigrants many of whom, in addition to coming from non-circumcising countries such as Mexico and China, are more likely to be of lower socio-economic status. Although circumcision is uncommon in Thailand, it tends to be associated with higher educational and socioeconomic status. In order to make male circumcision more accessible, it was recently added to the procedures covered under a flat rate payment scheme for a medical visit or procedure of any type⁴⁵.

In contrast, the DHS surveys in sub-Saharan African countries show no consistent association with socio-economic status (Figure 3). For example, in the United Republic of Tanzania, higher rates of circumcision are seen among men with higher levels of education, and higher socio-economic status, and those living in urban areas, whereas in Lesotho, circumcision is most common among men with no education, in the lowest wealth quintile and in rural areas¹³. Circumcision prevalence in Ethiopia is universally high (93%) but men are most likely to be circumcised if they are in a higher wealth quintile, have at least secondary education and live in an urban area.

Figure 3: Prevalence of male circumcision by education & wealth quintiles: Source:¹³

1.2.3.3 Perceived health and sexual benefits

One of the driving determinants in the spread of circumcision practices in the English-speaking industrialised world has been the perception that it results in improved penile hygiene and lower risk of infections. These were also the main determinants found in recent studies of factors determining acceptability of male circumcision in sub-Saharan African communities which do not traditionally circumcise (see Section 3.3)¹⁵. A male circumcision service was established at the University Teaching Hospital in Lusaka, Zambia in August 2004, and of the 895 circumcisions that have been undertaken there, 91% of clients requested the procedure because they considered it protective against STI/HIV⁴⁶.

In a study of United States newborns in 1983³³, mothers cited hygiene as the most important determinant of choosing to circumcise their sons, and in Ghana, male circumcision is seen as cleansing the boy after birth^{27, 47}. Improved hygiene was also cited by 23% of 110 boys circumcised in the Philippines³⁴ and in the Republic of Korea, the principal reasons given for circumcision were 'to improve penile hygiene' (71% and 78% respectively³⁶) and to prevent conditions such as penile cancer, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV⁴⁸. In Nyanza Province, Kenya, 96% of uncircumcised men and 97% of women irrespective of their preference for male circumcision stated their opinion that it was easier for circumcised men to maintain cleanliness¹⁷. Men participating in focus group discussions in Botswana, Kenya, Malawi, the United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe also believed that it was easier to keep the circumcised penis clean^{11, 17-19, 25, 49-51}.

Perceived improvement of sexual attraction and performance can also motivate circumcision. In a survey of boys in the Philippines, 11% stated that a determinant of becoming circumcised was that women like to have sexual intercourse with a circumcised man³⁴, and 18% of men in the study in the Republic of Korea

stated that circumcision could enhance sexual pleasure⁴⁸. In Nyanza Province, Kenya, 55% of uncircumcised men believed that women enjoyed sex more with circumcised men, and this belief was a strong predictor of preference to be circumcised even after controlling for education, employment and beliefs about whether circumcision is associated with disease. Similarly, the majority of women believe that women enjoyed sex more with circumcised men, even though it is likely that most women in Nyanza have never experienced sexual relations with a circumcised man¹⁷. In the northwest of the United Republic of Tanzania, younger men associated circumcision with enhanced sexual pleasure for both men and women¹¹, and in Westonia district, South Africa about half of men said that women preferred circumcised partners⁵². In Southern Nigeria, the enhancement of sexual performance and reproductive ability was also an important reason given for male circumcision³¹.

1.3 Global prevalence of male circumcision

We have estimated the global prevalence of circumcision among males aged 15 or over by first assuming that all Muslim and Jewish males in this age group are circumcised. Then, using published data from the DHS and other sources^{13, 53, 54}, we estimated the number of non-Muslim and non-Jewish men circumcised in countries with substantial prevalence of non-religious circumcision (Angola, Australia, Canada, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Indonesia, Kenya, Madagascar, Nigeria, Philippines, the Republic of Korea, Uganda, United Kingdom, the United Republic of Tanzania, United States).

Table 1: Estimation of number of males aged 15 years or older circumcised for non-religious reasons, by country

Country	Male population aged 15 years or older (millions)	Percent non-Muslim or non-Jewish ⁵⁵	Non-Muslim, non-Jewish adult male population (millions)	Percent of non-Muslim, non-Jewish adult men circumcised ^{13, 53, 54}	Number of non-Muslim, non-Jewish adult men circumcised (millions)
United States	115.56	98.0%	113.2	75%	84.9
Philippines	28.75	95.0%	27.3	90%	24.6
Nigeria	35.225	50.0%	17.6	90%	15.9
Democratic Republic of Congo	16.23	90.0%	14.6	90%	13.1
Ethiopia	20.92	55.0%	11.5	92%	10.6
Republic of Korea	19.71	100.0%	19.7	60%	11.8
Kenya	9.99	93.0%	9.3	83%	7.7
Indonesia	84.98	12.0%	10.2	85%	8.7
South Africa	14.87	98.5%	14.6	35%	5.1
Ghana	5.61	84.4%	4.7	85%	4.0
Madagascar	4.24	90.0%	3.8	98%	3.7
United Republic of Tanzania	9.84	65.0%	6.4	58%	3.7
Angola	3.44	99.0%	3.4	90%	3.1
Canada	11.79	96.9%	11.4	30%	3.4
Australia	8.05	98.5%	7.9	20%	1.6
United Kingdom	24.22	97.3%	23.6	6%	1.4
Uganda	6.94	85.0%	5.9	14%	0.8

Using these assumptions, we estimate that approximately 30% of the world's males aged 15 or older are circumcised (Table 2). Of these, around two-thirds (68%) are Muslim (living mainly in the Asia, the Middle East and North Africa), 0.8% are Jewish, and 13% are non-Muslims, non-Jews living in the United States (Table 2).

Table 2: Proportion of males aged 15 or older circumcised globally

	Prevalence of circumcision	Number circumcised	Proportion of those circumcised globally
Muslim men	100.0%	455.0	68.5%
Jewish men	100.0%	5.3	0.8%
Non-religious circumcision			
United States of America	75%	84.9	12.8%
Other countries ¹	62%	119.3	18%
Global total	30%	664.5	100%

This method is likely to under-estimate the true prevalence of male circumcision, as we have excluded circumcision among non-Muslim and non-Jewish men in heavily populated countries such as China, Brazil, India and Japan where a small proportion of men are also circumcised, for medical, cultural or social reasons. If we assume that 5% of men aged 15 or above who are not included in the countries or religions above are circumcised, then our estimate rises to 34%.

Further limitations are that the country-level estimates rely on self-reported circumcision status which may be unreliable in some ^{11, 56}, though not all ⁴³ settings. A Kenyan study concluded that asking men 'Are you circumcised' is misleading, not only because of unreliability of self-report, but also because different styles of circumcision in this population result in varying amounts of residual foreskin ⁵⁶. However, the impact of misclassification of self-reported circumcision status is not clear. A study in the northwest of the United Republic of Tanzania found that the self-reported prevalence of circumcised was higher than the actual rate upon genital examination (34% vs. 28%) ⁵⁷ whereas in a study of adolescents in Texas, United States, the self-reported prevalence was lower than that found by clinical examination (36% vs. 49%) ⁵⁸. Further, in this study, a substantial proportion of respondents (27%) stated that they did not know their circumcision status.

1.4 Regional prevalence of male circumcision

Figure 4: Global Map of male circumcision prevalence at country-level

National prevalence of male circumcision was estimated using DHS data where available. For other countries, estimates were made from other published sources. Countries with no published data on male circumcision prevalence are labelled "no data."

¹ Includes countries listed in Table 1. If 5% of men in other countries are assumed to be circumcised for non-religious reasons, the global prevalence of circumcision is 34%

Figure 4 shows estimated country-level prevalence of male circumcision. However, these estimates do not reflect the substantial within-country variation in prevalence due to the social, cultural and religious determinants discussed in Section 1.2. For example, the estimated prevalence in Uganda is 25%, but 97% of Muslims are circumcised compared with 14% of non-Muslims, and regional prevalence varies from 2% in North Central Region to 55% in Eastern Region¹³.

1.4.1 Africa

Male circumcision is common in many African countries, and is almost universal in North Africa and most of West Africa. In contrast, it is less common in southern Africa, where self-reported prevalence is around 15% in several countries (Botswana⁵⁹, Namibia, Swaziland, Zambia, Zimbabwe^{13, 53, 60}) although higher in others (Malawi 21%, South Africa 35%, Lesotho 48%², Mozambique 60%, and Angola and Madagascar >80%)^{13, 53, 60}. Prevalence in Central and Eastern Africa varies from approximately 15% in Burundi and Rwanda to 70% in the United Republic of Tanzania, 84% in Kenya and 93% in Ethiopia¹³.

This variation is partly due to some groups (mainly Nilotic or Sudanic speakers) who are traditionally non-circumcising, and also to different ethnic traditions among Bantu speaking populations (which include over 400 different ethnic groups in Africa, from Cameroon to South Africa), some of whom gradually stopped the practice, sometimes many centuries ago⁶¹. The reasons for this cessation are unclear, but in more recent history it is known that in Botswana, southern Zimbabwe and parts of South Africa and Malawi, circumcision was stopped by European missionaries and colonial administrators. In Zululand, King Shaka ordered that circumcision schools be abolished during the Zulu wars in the early 19th century, presumably because of the difficulty in holding the schools during the continual fighting⁶¹. For similar reasons, many other groups in southern Africa are thought to have abandoned male circumcision at that time, including the Swazi when King Mswati II banned the practice as it incapacitated men at times of war⁶¹.

Another smaller region where circumcision was not traditionally practiced is in a contiguous area in central/eastern Côte d'Ivoire, northwestern/central Ghana, and southwest Burkina Faso⁶¹. However, the procedure has become more widespread in this region over the past century^{37, 39}; prevalence has increased to 68% in northwestern/central Ghana (still much lower than the national Ghanaian prevalence of 96%) but remains much less common (28%) among the Lobi in southwest Burkina Faso (national prevalence 90%)¹³.

Age at circumcision varies by country. Neonatal circumcision is common in Ghana⁴⁷, but in other countries median age at circumcision varies from boyhood (median age 5-7 years in Burkina Faso)¹³, age 7-10 in Zambia⁶², age 8-16 in Kenya⁶³ to the late teens or twenties, for example in parts of the United Republic of Tanzania and South Africa^{11, 61}. Age at circumcision can also vary considerably within a country. For example in Burkina Faso, families of higher socio-economic status and education level, or living in urban areas are more likely to circumcise their sons at a young age¹³.

1.4.2 Asia and the Middle East

Male circumcision is almost universal in the Middle East and Central Asia, and in Muslim Asian countries such as Indonesia⁸, Pakistan and Bangladesh⁵³. In addition, there is a large circumcised Muslim population (estimated 120 million) in India⁵⁵.

There is generally little non-religious circumcision in Asia, with the exceptions of the Republic of Korea and the Philippines, where circumcision is routine. In Republic of Korea, circumcision patterns changed dramatically during the 20th century, increasing from virtual non-existence in 1945 to over 90% currently. This is thought to be largely the influence of the United States, which established a trusteeship in the Republic of Korea in 1945. The very rapid uptake of this practice is seen clearly in prevalence of male circumcision among 20-year olds from 1950 to 2000 (Figure 5a), rising from virtually zero in 1950 to 90% in 2000 with the sharpest increase in the 1980s. The overall prevalence among men is about 60%.⁶⁵

² The self-reported prevalence of male circumcision in Lesotho is 48%, but this figure may refer to attendance at a circumcision school or ceremony. In many cases, only a small proportion of these men are actually circumcised. In addition, there is wide prevalence of 'incomplete' circumcision, for example, an incision only.

Fig. 5a: The circumcision rate of then-20-year olds among the respondents as a function of calendar year; 5b: The estimated circumcision rate over the whole population as a function of calendar year (Permission granted): ⁶⁶

In the Republic of Korea, male circumcision tends to occur in adolescence or later, rather than as neonates ⁶⁶ and the median age of circumcision among 1500 young men interviewed in South Province was 10-15 years, with only 1% of boys circumcised in their first year ³⁵. Another survey of 1124 men found that 80% were circumcised, and the median age of circumcision was 12-14 ⁶⁷.

The reason for the near universal prevalence of male circumcision in the Philippines is less clear, but is long-standing and thought to be unrelated to religious influence ³⁴. There are few data on age at circumcision but one study found that 42% of boys were circumcised aged under 10, 52% aged 10-14, and 5% aged 15-18 years ³⁴.

In Malaysia, male circumcision is also very common, likely influenced by its majority Muslim population of 60% ⁶⁸. In contrast, the practice is rare in neighbouring Thailand ^{69, 70} apart from among predominantly Muslim communities in South Thailand.

1.4.3 North America, Europe, Australia & New Zealand

During the 19th century, male circumcision became increasingly popular in English-speaking industrialised countries following the advent of anaesthesia in surgery and the first epidemiological studies such as that of venereal patients in 1855, which found that 61% of non-Jewish patients (who were uncircumcised) had syphilis compared with 19% of Jewish patients ⁷¹. The Victorian establishment, including the medical profession, was concerned with issues surrounding the relationship between sexuality and disease, and there was a widespread belief that circumcision was beneficial, leading to statements such as 'the prepuce is a frequent source of disease, often requiring its removal' ⁷².

By the end of the 19th century, male circumcision was advocated in these countries as a preventive measure against a range of conditions and behaviours including masturbation, syphilis and nocturnal incontinence ⁷². As a result, neonatal and child circumcision rates in the United States increased to about 55% by 1938, and subsequently increased further to about 80% in the 1960s, possibly influenced by men returning from the Second World War when circumcision was reportedly common to prevent penile infections while serving in North Africa and the Pacific ⁷³. The American Academy of Pediatrics has issued several statements on neonatal circumcision since 1971, with the most recent (issued in 1999; reaffirmed in May 2005), stating that there are insufficient data to recommend routine neonatal circumcision ⁷⁴. Despite this, there appears to be little decline in prevalence of neonatal circumcision in the United States. An estimated 61% of male newborns were recorded as being circumcised on hospital discharge sheets in 2000 ⁴⁴, but the true figure will be higher than this because circumcision is not routinely documented on the hospital discharge sheet used to collate the data and furthermore, post neonatal circumcisions for religious or medical reasons are not captured. Community surveys have found higher neonatal male circumcision prevalence of 76%-92% ⁷⁵. There is also substantial

regional variability, with lowest prevalence in the West, likely due to the high proportion of Hispanics who have lower rates of male circumcision⁷³.

Most data from Canada are also hospital-based and therefore again exclude a substantial proportion of procedures. However, in contrast to the United States, there is clear evidence of a gradual decline in circumcision prevalence. Data from 1970-71 found that neonatal circumcision rates varied from 42% in Nova Scotia to 67% in Alberta, and prevalence generally declined during the 1970s, with the lowest rate of 13% in Quebec, and 22% in Nova Scotia in 1978⁷⁶. This decline may have been partly due to the American Academy and Canadian Pediatric Society statements in the 1970s that there were no medical indications for neonatal circumcision^{77,78}. A more recent study of 69,100 boys born in Ontario in 1993-1994 found a prevalence of 44%⁷⁹, and there is evidence of declining circumcision rates among male infants aged under 28 days in Ontario during the 1990s (inpatient circumcision prevalence of 39% in 1989/92 and 30% in 1994/95)⁸⁰.

The rate of neonatal circumcision in Australia has also declined. A recent nationwide survey of 10,173 men found that 59% of men are circumcised, decreasing from 66% of those aged 50-59 to 32% of those aged 16-19 years⁴³. Other data confirm this, with reported neonatal circumcision rates of 50% in 1974, 24% in 1983⁸¹, and 8% in 1999^{82,83}. There are few studies from New Zealand. A study of 435 men born in 1972-73 in Dunedin found a prevalence of circumcision of 40%⁸⁴, substantially higher than that of 26% found among 1265 children born in the Christchurch urban region in 1977⁸⁵, and just 7% in a 1991 survey in the Waikato region on North Island⁸⁶.

In the United Kingdom, circumcision prevalence is likely to have been 20-30% in the 1940s, with large variations due to socio-economic status⁸⁷. Since then, prevalence has declined sharply, probably both for financial reasons when National Health Service was established and did not pay for the procedure, and also due to a 1949 British Medical Journal article which concluded that there was no medical justification for neonatal circumcision⁸⁷. A recent probability-based nationwide survey in 2000 found that 15.8% of men aged 16-44 are circumcised, and this is lowest among those born more recently (e.g. 11.7% among boys born in 1980-84 compared with 19.6% among those born in 1955-1959)³. This reflects the decreasing prevalence over time, and currently, as in the rest of Europe, neonatal circumcision predominantly related to Muslim or Jewish religion, medical indications or immigration from circumcising countries.

1.4.4 Central and South America

There is little information on determinants of male circumcision in Central and South America, where the practice is uncommon. Circumcision was traditionally practiced among the Aztec and Mayan civilizations but largely disappeared following the European conquests^{5, 22, 23}. Reports from the 17th-19th century suggest that male circumcision in the Caribbean was practiced not only among Jews but also among local Africans working for them⁸⁸.

A study of male partners of cervical cancer controls in Panama, Costa Rica, Colombia and Mexico found that 11% of men were circumcised on genital examination (although 25% of men reported being circumcised)⁸⁹. A more recent study, also among partners of female controls in a cervical cancer study, found a prevalence of 7% in both Colombia and Brazil⁹⁰. A random sample of 300 men requesting pre-employment or routine annual worker health certification in low socioeconomic neighbourhoods of Lima, Peru, found that 6% were circumcised⁹¹. A recent multi-country survey found no countries in Central or South America with circumcision prevalence greater than 20%⁵³.

1.5 Summary

Male circumcision is a common surgical procedure in many parts of the world, undertaken for religious, cultural, and secular reasons. The most common determinant of circumcision globally is Muslim religion, and there are many regions of the world where non-religious circumcision is largely unknown. The age at which circumcision is undertaken is determined by socio-cultural and religious traditions, and it may occur from the neonatal period to the early twenties. There have been rapid increases and decreases of prevalence in several settings among non-Muslims and non-Jews, which may result from increased mixing between different cultures, religions and socio-economic groups, or from changes in perceptions of health or sexual benefits associated with the practice.

SECTION 2 Medical indications, clinical procedures and safety of male circumcision

2.1 Introduction

In this section, we review the physiology of the foreskin, current therapeutic and preventive medical indications for circumcision, the common methods of neonatal and adult circumcision, and the safety of these procedures when carried out both traditionally and medically.

2.2 The foreskin

The foreskin is a continuation of skin from the shaft of the penis which covers the glans penis and the urethral meatus (Figure 6a). The foreskin is attached to the glans by the frenulum, a highly vascularised tissue of the penis. The frenulum forms the interface between the outer and inner foreskin layers, and when the penis is not erect, it tightens to narrow the foreskin opening. Circumcision removes some, or all, of the foreskin from the penis. The word "circumcision" comes from Latin *circum* (meaning "around") and *caedere* (meaning "to cut").

There is debate about the role of the foreskin, with possible functions including keeping the glans moist⁹², protecting the developing penis *in utero*⁷³, or to enhance sexual pleasure due to the presence of nerve receptors⁹³. The foreskin is part of our phylogenetic heritage; non-human primates, including our closest living relatives, chimpanzees, have prepuces that partially or completely cover the glans penis⁹⁴.

2.2.1 Mechanisms of penile infection

Epidemiological studies have shown circumcised men have a lower risk of several reproductive tract infections than uncircumcised men (see Section 2.3.2). There are several likely biological mechanisms for this. The area under the foreskin is a warm, moist environment which may enable some pathogens to persist and replicate, especially when penile hygiene is poor⁹³. For example, it has been shown that uncircumcised infants are more likely to harbour a reservoir of uropathogenic organisms (e.g. *Escherichia coli*) in the urethral meatus and periurethral area⁹⁵ and that these uropathogenic bacteria adhere especially well to the inner mucosal surface of the foreskin as opposed to the keratinized external surface⁹⁶. These very adherent, more abundant uropathogenic organisms may then ascend to the bladder and kidneys causing urinary tract infections and pyelonephritis⁹⁷.

In addition, the inner mucosal surface of the foreskin is thinly keratinized⁹⁸, unlike the penile shaft and the outer surface of the foreskin⁹⁹ and may be more susceptible to minor trauma and abrasions which facilitate entry of pathogens⁹⁹.

There are several mechanisms by which the foreskin may specifically increase risk of HIV acquisition. Firstly, there is an increased risk of genital ulcer diseases in uncircumcised men¹⁰⁰, which in turn, increases risk of HIV as the disrupted mucosal surface of the ulcer increases risk of HIV acquisition¹⁰¹. Secondly, the foreskin may increase risk of HIV infection directly as tissue from the inner surface of the foreskin mucosa contains accessible HIV-1 target cells (CD4+ T cells, macrophages and Langerhans cells)¹⁰². The density of these HIV-1 target cells is similar in the inner foreskin as the glans penis and outer foreskin, but those in the inner foreskin are closer to the epithelial surface than those situated elsewhere in the penis, due to the lack of keratin⁹⁸. Within the inner foreskin the Langerhans cells are more likely to be found near the epithelial surface than other cells, and are likely to be the first to be infected by HIV-1¹⁰³. More direct evidence of the susceptibility of the foreskin to HIV-1 infection comes from Patterson *et al*¹⁰² who found that infectivity of the inner mucosal surface (assessed by quantity of HIV-1 DNA one day after *ex vivo* infection with explant culture) was greater than that of cervical tissue, which is a known primary site of HIV-1 acquisition in women.

Figure 6: (a) Schematic diagram of a flaccid uncircumcised penis. (b) Erect uncircumcised penis with the foreskin retracted showing the likely sites of HIV-1 entry. Permission pending from: McCoombe & Short. AIDS 2006 20:1491-1495.

In an uncircumcised man, the cells in the inner foreskin and frenulum are directly exposed to vaginal secretions during heterosexual intercourse, and this superficial location of the HIV-1 target cells presumably increases risk of infection (Figure 6b). In contrast, in a circumcised man the penile shaft is covered with a thickly keratinized epithelium, providing some protection from infection⁹⁸.

2.2.2 Penile hygiene and circumcision status

The perception of improved penile hygiene is one of the main determinants of circumcision. The inner foreskin and glans require regular cleaning to ensure adequate penile hygiene as there is the potential for secretions to accumulate in the space between foreskin and glans, potentially leading to proliferation of pathogens⁹³. This substance, known as smegma, is a combination of exfoliated epithelial cells, transudated skin oils, moisture and bacteria. However, few studies have assessed the degree of penile hygiene among uncircumcised men. In a recent study, 49% of men attending an STI clinic in Durban, South Africa had detectable wetness under the foreskin (thought to reflect poor genital hygiene)¹⁰⁴, similar to the proportion found in a study of men in India¹⁰⁵ but hygiene appeared to be better (9.5% wetness) among men attending an STI clinic in London¹⁰⁶.

Difficulty in maintaining good penile hygiene may contribute to the risk of infections among uncircumcised men. One cross-sectional study of men in Durban found a significantly higher prevalence of HIV among men with penile wetness fourteen days after treatment for STI after adjusting for potential confounding factors (OR=2.38, CI 1.4-4.0), and the circumcised men in the study had a similar prevalence of HIV as the uncircumcised men without penile wetness (43% vs. 46%)¹⁰⁴. Another cross-sectional study, of 150 male partners of women with lower genital tract symptoms from a family planning clinic and an STI clinic in Nairobi, Kenya also found that increased post-coital washing was associated with lower HIV infection¹⁰⁷.

Male circumcision was independently associated with lower risk of HIV in this study (OR=0.12, CI 0.02-0.91) independently of being associated with superior genital hygiene.

Interventions to improve penile hygiene may help reduce risk of HIV/STI, irrespective of circumcision status. Two studies of a topical microbicide (BZK 0.4%) wipes for penile cleaning among both circumcised and uncircumcised men in Malawi concluded that this wipe was safe and acceptable, and could decrease the frequency of penile colonization with micro-organisms¹⁰⁸. However, it is also possible that frequent penile cleaning could cause inflammation and micro-abrasions leading to increased risk of HIV acquisition.

2.3 Medical determinants of male circumcision

2.3.1 Therapeutic indications for male circumcision

The most frequent medical reason for male circumcision is phimosis - a stricture of the foreskin that narrows the opening and prevents it from being retracted to uncover the glans. Ninety percent of medically indicated circumcisions in the United Kingdom from 1997 to 2003 were for phimosis¹⁰⁹. Phimosis may be currently over-diagnosed¹¹⁰ and there was a 23% reduction in the number of circumcisions performed for phimosis during this period (from 11501 in 1997 to 8866 in 2003), possibly due to greater awareness of over-diagnosis and/or to availability of alternative treatment by corticosteroids^{111,112}.

Other, less common, medical indications for circumcision are otherwise untreatable paraphimosis (in which the foreskin is trapped behind the corona and forms a tight band of constricting tissue, causing swelling of the glans and foreskin), balanoposthitis (an acute or chronic inflammation of the mucosal surface of the foreskin), and balanitis xerotica obliterans (a chronic sclerosis and atrophic process of the glans penis and foreskin – a risk factor for penile cancer and the only absolute indication for circumcision). In addition, preputial neoplasms, excessive skin, and tears in the frenulum are also rare medical indications for adult circumcision^{113,114}.

2.3.2 Preventative indications for male circumcision

Table 3 summarises the systematic reviews and randomised controlled trials (RCT) of the association of male circumcision with penile infections. These show that circumcised men are at significantly lower risk of urinary tract infections (UTI), HIV, syphilis and chancroid^{100, 115, 116}.

In addition, there is consistent evidence from studies in the United States that circumcised men are at significantly lower risk of invasive penile cancer¹¹⁷⁻¹²⁰. Most^{4, 121-128}, but not all^{3 Taylor, 1975 #229-129} have found a reduced risk of gonorrhoea among circumcised men, and a significantly reduced risk of Chlamydia trachomatis infection has been found in female partners of circumcised men (OR=0.18, CI 0.05-0.58 compared with partners of uncircumcised men)⁹⁰.

Table 3: Association of infections with male circumcision

Infection	Type of study/review	No. of studies ³	Relative risk (RR) or odds ratio (OR) (95% CI)	Strength of evidence
Urinary tract infections 115	RCT	1	OR=0.13 (0.01-2.63)	+++
	Systematic review and meta-analysis	12	OR=0.13 (0.08-0.20)	
Chancroid 100	Systematic review	7	RRs from 0.12-1.11 ⁴	++
Syphilis 100	Systematic review and meta-analysis	14	RR=0.67 (0.54-0.83)	++
HIV 130-134)	RCT	3	RRs from 0.40 to 0.52	+++
	Systematic review & meta-analysis of observational data	15	RR=0.52 (0.40-0.68)	
	Systematic review of observational data	19	RRs from 0.12 to 1.25 ⁵	
HSV2 100	Systematic review & meta-analysis of observational data	7	RR=0.88 (0.77-1.01)	+
HPV 135	Systematic review and meta-analysis of observational data	8	OR=0.80 (0.60-1.05)	+

In addition to these viral and bacterial infections, a recent study found a significantly higher prevalence of yeast in samples from the prepuce and glans penis of uncircumcised (62.5%) compared to circumcised boys (37.5%) in Turkey ¹³⁶, although an earlier study found no association of yeast in 66 circumcised and 69 uncircumcised men ¹³⁷.

In the industrialized world, routine neonatal circumcision is not recommended by national Paediatric Societies including those of Australia, Canada, Finland, New Zealand and the United States for the prevention of these conditions ^{74, 138-141} because the risks are judged to outweigh the benefits.

There have been several cost-benefit analyses of impact of neonatal circumcision. Their conclusions depend on the assumed surgical complication rate of neonatal circumcision – for example, a decision-tree analysis found that circumcision would be preferred if the rate of surgical complications was below 0.6% ¹⁴². There have been several cost-benefit analyses. One study, using data from 350,000 neonatal circumcisions in Washington State observed a complication rate of 0.2%, and concluded that six UTI would be prevented for every complication ¹⁴³. Conversely, two complications could be expected for each case of penile cancer expected in later life. In contrast, in a recent meta-analysis, a complication rate of 2% was assumed (which is typical of the rate in adult circumcision, but much higher than that found in neonates), and concluded that circumcision would only have a favourable cost-benefit ratio for boys at high risk of UTI ¹⁴⁵.

The complication rates cited in some medical society statements also tend to be higher than observed for neonatal circumcision (for example 0.2%-2% in the Canadian statement, 1%-5% in the Australasian statement), and the Australasian and American statements have been criticized for being unduly negative towards circumcision and down-playing the benefits of circumcision on infections including UTIs, penile and cervical cancer, and HIV ^{144, 145}.

³ For meta-analyses of HIV infections in adults, only studies with adjusted RRs are included, as crude RRs are likely to be misleading due to potential confounding with behaviour and other factors. The meta-analyses of chancroid, syphilis and HSV-2 include 'best estimates' of effect which are the adjusted RR if it was available, otherwise the crude RR.

⁴ Protective effect in 6 out of 7 studies, of which 4 had a significant protective effect.

⁵ Protective effect in 18/19 studies, of which 14 were significantly protective

There is increasing evidence that male circumcision protects men from acquiring HIV (Table 2)^{130, 133, 134}. The public health issues surrounding possible uptake of adult male circumcision to prevent HIV infections in settings with high incidence are discussed in Section 3.

2.3.3 Sexual function

The impact of circumcision on sexual function has not been systematically reviewed, and remains unclear due to substantial biases in many studies. For example, reporting of post-surgical performance may be related to whether circumcision was carried out for elective or therapeutic reasons. Although it has been argued that sexual function may diminish following circumcision due to the removal of the nerve endings in the foreskin and subsequent thickening of the epithelia of the glans⁹³, there is little evidence for this and studies are inconsistent^{4, 43, 146-148}. The randomised trials and increased provision of male circumcision services will thus provide important information on sexual function post-circumcision. So far 4 out of 1131 HIV-1 negative men reported mild or moderate erectile dysfunction 21 months after the surgery in the Orange Farm Intervention Trial but it is unclear whether this was a pre-existing problem for any of them¹³⁰.

2.4 Male circumcision in clinical settings

A recent manual has been prepared by WHO, UNAIDS and JHPIEGO which provides full details of methods of male circumcision in clinical settings¹⁴⁹. In this paper we summarise the main points only.

2.4.1 Methods of neonatal circumcision

Neonatal circumcision should only be undertaken if the baby is a normal full-term delivery with no significant medical problems after birth. There are four techniques for neonatal circumcision: the dorsal slit method, the Plastibell method, the Mogen clamp method and the Gomco clamp method.

The use of clamps reduces pain, minimizes or eliminates bleeding, promotes haemostasis, protects the glans. The Plastibell method is widely used around the world and has been shown to be acceptable and practical in developing country situations but incorrect technique can lead to complications and this method is recommended in the context of regular circumcision practice but not for occasional use. The Mogen clamp is used widely in North America and complications are less frequent than other methods when used in neonates. Comparative studies have shown that it is quicker and causes less pain than the Gomco clamp¹⁵⁰⁻¹⁵². Unlike the Plastibell, the clamp is re-usable and precautions are needed to ensure sterility. The Gomco clamp has different bell sizes and so can be used in infants and older children.

Circumcision is a simpler operation in infants and young children and healing is usually complete within a week. Bleeding is rare because the clamp crushes the foreskin edge. The use of local anaesthesia and/or analgesics is recommended for neonates, and is necessary for older children⁷⁴. A pacifier soaked in a sucrose solution has been found to be effective in reducing fussiness in infants and oral doses of acetaminophen every 6 to 8 hours, for 24 hours provide additional analgesia¹⁵³.

2.4.2 Methods of adult and adolescent circumcision

Adult and adolescent circumcision is carried out using one of three methods: the forceps guided method, the dorsal slit method and the sleeve method. Details are given in the WHO/UNAIDS/JHPIEGO manual¹⁴⁹. The procedure is more complex than in neonates or children, requiring local or general anaesthesia. Local anaesthesia is the preferred method because it is less risky and more economical. The nerve supply of the penis consists of the twin dorsal penile nerves and anaesthesia blocks the dorsal penile nerve and its branches.

The sleeve method produces the tidiest result but requires a higher level of surgical skill than the other method. The forceps guided method (Figure 7a) can be performed without an assistant and is suitable for resource-limited settings. The disadvantage is that it leaves between 0.5 and 1.0 cm of mucosal skin proximal to the corona. The dorsal slit method is widely used by general and urological surgeons throughout the world and, whilst requiring

Figure 7a: Male circumcision using the forceps guided method in the Orange Farm, South African trial
 [Permission granted B Auvert]

more skill than the forceps guided method, can be done without an assistant. The South African and Kenyan trials employed the forceps guide method, whilst the Ugandan trial used the sleeve method.

All methods of adult and adolescent circumcision require suturing and dressing. Minor bleeding should stop with a few minutes of pressure with a gauze. Once bleeding has ceased, the wound is dressed and left in place for 24-48 hours. A follow-up visit should occur within 7 days of surgery to assess the progress of healing and to look for signs of infection.

2.4.3 Adverse events associated with male circumcision in clinical settings

Surgical complications of male circumcision can include excessive bleeding, haematoma formation, sepsis, unsatisfactory cosmetic effect, lacerations of the penile or scrotal skin and injury to the glans.

Neonatal circumcision is a simpler procedure than adult circumcision and very low rates of complications (0.2%-0.4%) have been consistently reported in large series of neonatal circumcisions in the United States and Israel^{143, 154-157}. Most of these are relatively minor (bleeding and excess skin) but definition of 'complication' varies - for example in one of these studies¹⁵⁷, the rate of 'significant' complications (systemic infections, haemorrhage in a patient with factor VII deficiency, circumcisions of infants with hypospadias, denudation of the penile shaft) was 0.2%, but 2% of patients had some complication (mainly bleeding or infection). A higher rate was reported among 100 neonates circumcised in Canada in 1962 with the Plastibell or Gomco clamp, where moderate or severe complications (bleeding, ulcer and infection) were seen in 7 infants¹⁵⁸. However, this paper provides an example of how reported rates can vary depending on definition - complication rates were reported as 55%, mainly due to the classification of any bleeding (including oozing) as 'haemorrhage'¹⁵⁸.

There is relatively little data on complication rates following circumcision in developing countries. One study of 205 Jamaican neonates, using the Plastibell device, found minor complications in 2.4% of circumcisions¹⁵⁹, a study from Nigeria reported that of 1563 boys circumcised at the hospital, 5 (0.3%) developed minor complications¹⁶⁰ and a report from Anjouan Island in the Comoros found 7 cases of haemorrhage (0.6%) and 18 cases of infection (1.8%) among 1019 boys circumcised at ages 3-8 years¹⁶¹. Only 5% of these circumcisions were performed by doctors and the remaining by teams of 2-3 surgical aids and nurses who were trained to perform circumcisions, which were carried out in the home under local anaesthesia with full asepsis. In contrast, a recent study of 270 neonates in Nigeria found that two neonates sustained amputation of the glans penis, and one had a buried penis (a penis that lacks an appropriate sheath of skin and is located beneath the integument of the abdomen, thigh, or scrotum)¹⁶². The overall complication rate was 20.2%, with the most common complication redundant foreskin (53.8% of all adverse events) and excessive loss of foreskin (24.6%). There were no reports of bleeding, swelling or infection. The method of circumcision in this study was not reported, but most circumcisions (80%) were carried out in hospitals, often by nurses, among whom complication rates were higher than among doctors or among traditional practitioners.

Turning to older children, a recent large study of 66,519 boys circumcised in the United Kingdom between 1997 and 2003 found a complication rate of 1.2%¹⁰⁹. Interestingly, complication rates were significantly lower among boys age 5-9 (0.7% with haemorrhage) compared with those aged 0-4 years (1.0% with haemorrhage). Of 200 boys circumcised in Australia (mean age 2 years 4 months), the overall complication rate was much higher at 15.5% (31/200). The main complication was bleeding (9 mild, 4 moderate, 1 unknown degree), and meatal ulcer (7 cases)¹⁶³. Again, rates were highest among the less experienced doctors. Among 600 boys circumcised in Turkey, the complication rate was 3.8%. Most of these (13/23) were bleeding, mostly simple oozing¹². In a series of 249 consecutive circumcisions in Nigeria and Kenya¹⁶⁴, of

whom most (61%) were adolescents or young adults, there were 28 (11.2%) complications, predominantly wound infection (2.8%), but also severe haemorrhage (1.2%), retention of urine (1.2%) and swelling (1.2%).

The current trials of elective male circumcision among men in Africa will provide essential information on risks of surgery in adults. In the South African study, the overall risk of adverse events during surgery or in the first month post-surgery was 3.6% among the 1495 HIV seronegative men and 8.2% among the 73 HIV seropositive men¹³⁰. Pain was the most common adverse event, reported by 13/1568 men (0.8%), and problems with appearance were reported by 9 men (0.6%). Excessive bleeding, infection, swelling or other complications were reported for 38 men (2.4%). By 21 months after circumcision, 11 (1%) adverse events were reported (problem with urinating, dissatisfaction with appearance, mild or moderate erectile dysfunction). The rate of clinical adverse events was slightly lower among the HIV seronegative men recruited into the Kenyan trial (1.8%), and all of these were resolved within hours or days¹⁶⁵. Again, the complication rate was substantially lower when performed by experienced surgeons (<1% for those who had performed at least 200 circumcisions compared with 3.8% among those who had performed fewer than 100). The duration of the procedure also decreased as the trial progressed, from a median of 38 minutes for the first 100 procedures to a median of 21.5 minutes for the final 75 procedures¹⁶⁵. A complication rate of 3% (27/895) has been seen at the University Teaching Hospital in Lusaka, Zambia, where a dedicated public sector male circumcision service has been available since August 2004. Circumcision is performed under local anaesthesia, predominantly by clinical officers using the dorsal slit method⁶².

2.4.4 Summary

To summarize, neonatal male circumcision is a relatively simple, quick and safe procedure when performed in a clinical setting under antiseptic conditions by trained professionals. Complication rates are between 1 in 500 and 2 in 100 and are usually minor. In adults, the operation is more complex and under optimal conditions, complication rates of about 2-4% are seen (Box 1). However, these optimal conditions are not always met. Reported rates of complications vary dramatically, due mainly to different definitions of adverse events, and also because complication rates are likely to depend on age at circumcision, experience of the surgeon, reason for circumcision (therapeutic versus elective), and the method used. For example, the potential for complications is greater in adults, as the procedure is more complex, requiring suturing of skin edges.

Potential complications of male circumcision in clinical settings

Pain

Bleeding

Haematoma

Swelling

Wound infection

Anaesthesia-related events

Delayed wound healing

Excessive skin removed

Insufficient skin removed

Problems with urination

Problems with appearance

2.5 Male circumcision in non-clinical settings

2.5.1 Methods of male circumcision in non-clinical settings

Male circumcision for religious or traditional reasons frequently takes place in a non-clinical setting, although in some cultures, an increasing proportion now takes place in clinics^{36,166}. The usual procedure, of which almost all ritual circumcisions are variants, involves pulling the foreskin forward and cutting through the prepuce above the level of the glans, sometimes using a shield to protect the glans.

Traditionally, Jewish males are circumcised neonatally by a specially trained 'Mohel', or traditional circumciser, in a ceremony called a 'Bris Milah' (Figure 8). The surgical training undertaken by a Mohel may include anatomy, surgical technique, minimizing complications, treating complications and pre- and post-operative care routines. The technique employed by some Mohels is similar to the Mogen clamp, the

Figure 8: Jewish bris (photo from http://www.305651bris.com/fenster_bris.htm - Permission pending)

foreskin being passed through a slit in a metal shield that protects the glans, while a scalpel is run across the face of the shield, removing the foreskin. The highly vascularised frenulum is not excised in this method, and so bleeding is minimised. The remaining inner foreskin is subsequently pulled back off the glans and excised, and the wound is bandaged without the use of stitches. As this is a neonatal procedure, this method is safer than many other non-clinical procedures.

Methods of non-clinical circumcision among Muslims vary and may be undertaken neonatally, which will generally be a safe procedure. However, it is often performed at older ages with increased risks. In Turkey, circumcision is traditionally undertaken by non-medically trained individuals including barbers and traditional drummers¹². The usual technique involves pulling the foreskin in front of the glans, placing some kind of shield to protect the glans, and excising the skin. In northern Sudan, where boys must be circumcised before entering school at age eight, the traditional circumciser inserts a straw made from savannah grass into the foreskin opening, and pushes the glans down while pulling the foreskin as far forward as possible. A cord is then tied around the foreskin above the glans, and the foreskin excised with a knife immediately in front of the cord. The inner epithelium is then folded back over the glans and the wound is dressed, but not stitched.

Among the Xhosa of South Africa, circumcision is carried out using a razor blade or penknife²⁶, without anaesthesia¹⁶⁷. The wound is covered with eucalyptus leaves²⁶, or maize¹⁶⁸, and left in place for four weeks while the boys are in seclusion. Among the Australian Aboriginals and Polynesians, the foreskin is reportedly removed using seashells, and boys then squat or stand for several hours over the smoke from a fire covered with eucalyptus leaves to promote haemostasis²⁶. Eucalyptus oil is used due to its antiseptic, analgesic and possibly anticoagulant properties when used topically^{26, 169}.

The degree of foreskin removed also varies in traditional circumcision. A study among the Meru people in central Kenya revealed distinct differences between medical and traditional circumcision⁵⁶. In this culture, boys are typically circumcised between the ages of 13-17. Three types of circumcision were identified, including the clinic-based forceps guided method (see Section 2.4.2), but also freehand methods in which a smaller part of the foreskin is removed (1-2 cm, in contrast to the 4cm removed in the forceps-guided method), and part of the outer layer of the foreskin is retained. The local 'buttonhole' form, which is also used among the Masai, Samburu and Dorobo (all in East Africa), results in the retention of part of the outer foreskin as an appendage below the glans. A study among the Babukusu in Kenya found that traditional circumcisions were highly variable, with some resulting in insufficient skin removal and flaps of foreskin partially covering the glans, and others with excessive skin removed including non-foreskin tissue from the penile shaft.¹⁶⁶ This can lead to problems, as the Babukusu are culturally expected to be completely circumcised, and having residual foreskin may lead to further surgery to complete the procedure.

Adult and adolescent Ethiopian Jews immigrating to Israel undergo "correctional" male circumcision to further remove (small or large) foreskin portions not cut by the traditional circumcisers in their home villages. This is required as the Jewish definition of circumcision is the complete removal of the foreskin¹⁷⁰

2.5.2 Adverse events associated with male circumcision in non-clinical settings

Circumcisions undertaken in non-clinical settings can have significant risks of serious adverse events, including death. Among 50 patients admitted to hospital with post-circumcision complications in Nigeria and Kenya between 1981 and 1998, 80% had been circumcised by medically untrained traditional surgeons. One of these patients died from septicaemia, two lost their penis from gangrene, and five others had permanent disability from complete or partial amputation of the glans or shaft¹⁶⁴. Similar findings are reported from Turkey, where, of 200 boys admitted to hospital with circumcision complications over a ten-year period, 85% of the circumcisions were performed by traditional circumcisers, 10% by health technicians, and 5% by doctors¹². One of these, a 2-year old boy, died from haemorrhage. Although the proportion of circumcisions undertaken by traditional circumcisers in these two populations is not known, these data illustrate the risks associated with some traditional procedures. A further study of 48 boys presenting to hospital with post-circumcision complications in Nigeria found that the commonest complication was haemorrhage (52% patients) and infection (21%)¹⁶⁰. One child had amputation of the penis with subsequent stricture of the external urethral meatus.

A sobering report of circumcision among the Babukusu ethnic group in western Kenya has recently been published¹⁶⁶. Among the Babukusu, circumcision is part of the initiation rite for youth aged 8-20, and circumcision may be carried out traditionally or medically by a doctor, clinician or health professional. Twenty-four circumcisions were directly observed (12 traditional and 12 medical). The results were alarming – 21 of the 24 men suffered adverse events, and none had fully healed by 30 days post-operation. Further, seven men (29%) were judged to have permanent adverse sequelae. Among the 1007 youth undergoing circumcision who were interviewed, complication rates were lower, and reported adverse events were twice as common among those circumcised traditionally (35%) compared with medically (18%). The most common complications were excessive bleeding, infections and excessive pain. More detailed examination of 298 of the boys at 45-96 days post-operation showed that traditional circumcision was also associated with slower healing, more swelling, laceration and keloid scarring. The rate of adverse events depended on the provider, with rates being higher in private clinics where providers may have little or no health care education, compared to public clinics. Although all providers stated they had been adequately trained for circumcision, about half were willing to have more training. Finally, as the mean healing time was long (47 days), some of the men had resumed sexual activity before wound healing, potentially increasing risk of HIV infection through the open wound¹⁶⁶.

Mass circumcisions are also common in some settings and can increase complication rates. Among the Xhosa in South Africa, an unsterilized unwashed blade may be used on a dozen or more initiates in a single session^{167, 168}. Initiates are also significantly dehydrated during their 2 week period of seclusion in the belief that this reduces weeping of the wound, and after-care may be in the hands of a traditional attendant with no basic medical training¹⁶⁷. The combination of dehydration and septicaemia can result in acute renal failure, gangrene, tetanus or even death^{167, 168}. An estimated 40-50 young men die annually following ritual circumcision in South Africa¹⁶⁸, predominantly from infection and haemorrhage¹⁶⁷. The Eastern Cape provincial Department of Health recorded 243 deaths and 214 genital amputations for circumcisions between 1995 and 2004. To address this, traditional surgeons are now required by law to be officially recognized and registered with the provincial Department of Health¹⁷¹.

Aside from complications, traditional circumcision can also be more painful than clinical circumcision, as use of anaesthetics is rare¹², probably due to the origins of circumcision as a marker of bravery and endurance²⁶. The rite of skin-stripping, whereby much of the skin of the penile shaft is progressively flayed, is used to prove 'bravery' and therefore marriage suitability, among various ethnic groups, including the Dowayo of Cameroon and formerly among Arabian tribes^{7, 172}.

2.6 Summary

Male circumcision is medically indicated for only a few conditions. There is substantial evidence that circumcised men have a lower risk of some reproductive tract infections, as well as penile cancer, but some of these conditions are rare while others are uncommon or treatable, and routine neonatal circumcision is not currently recommended on medical grounds.

The safety of male circumcision depends crucially on the setting, equipment and expertise of the provider. Neonatal circumcision is a simpler procedure than adult circumcision, and has very low rates of adverse events. Adolescent or adult circumcision in clinical settings can cause bleeding, haematoma or sepsis, but with no long-term sequelae when undertaken in a clinical setting by experienced, well-trained providers. In contrast, circumcisions undertaken in unhygienic conditions, by inexperienced providers with inadequate instruments, or with poor after-care, can result in serious complications and even death.

Reported demand for male circumcision is increasing in some countries with high rates of HIV¹⁷³. Consultations, training programmes, health personnel mobilization and provision of appropriate equipment and supplies are urgently needed to meet this demand, provide skilled and safe surgery, and avoid unnecessary complications. WHO, UNAIDS and JPIEGO have recently developed a manual to train practitioners in safe medical circumcision¹⁴⁹. This manual is targeted at trained health care providers circumcising adult men, and is accompanied by guidance on training, instrumentation, regulatory, licensing and ethical issues (including counselling on sexual behaviour)¹⁷⁴.

SECTION 3 : Male circumcision and HIV - public health issues concerning increased uptake of male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa

3.1 Introduction

In this section, we focus on changing patterns of male circumcision in the face of the expanding HIV epidemic in southern Africa. Three randomised controlled trials, in Kenya, Uganda and South Africa, have found that circumcised men are at 48-60% reduced risk of becoming infected with HIV. Male circumcision is likely to be integrated into the current package of HIV prevention measures, and a rapidly increased demand for safe, affordable male circumcision services is anticipated. There are many challenges associated with expanding provision of male circumcision services. We have discussed safety issues in Section 2, and in this Section we focus on acceptability of male circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising communities, and some of the potential problems associated with increased uptake.

3.2 HIV prevention in southern Africa

An estimated four million adults were newly infected with HIV in 2005, of whom two-thirds live in sub-Saharan Africa¹⁷⁵. The prevalence is highest in southern Africa where around 20% of adults are living with HIV. Notably, each country in this region with high prevalence of HIV (South Africa, Lesotho, Swaziland, Malawi, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia, Mozambique, Zambia) has a relatively low circumcision prevalence⁵³, whereas over 80% of males are circumcised in the two southern African countries with low HIV prevalence (Angola 3.7%; Madagascar 0.5%).

HIV in sub-Saharan Africa is predominantly transmitted by unprotected heterosexual intercourse, and effective prevention strategies include behavioural change programmes to promote abstinence and delayed sexual debut in young people, fidelity within partnerships where both people know they are seronegative, reduction in the number of partners, and correct and consistent condom use¹⁷⁵. Reduced incidence and prevalence in several African countries, including Zambia and Zimbabwe in southern Africa, show that these prevention messages can work, but the alarming number of new infections every day in the region means that not only do we need to intensify and expand current prevention programs, but also to identify new methods to add to the existing ones, while undertaking essential structural interventions in the social and economic spheres to reduce gender inequities in education, employment, property inheritance and other key areas.

Male circumcision is one of these new potential methods, along with vaginal microbicides, pre-exposure prophylaxis with antiretroviral medication, herpes suppressive therapy, cervical barrier methods and HIV vaccines¹⁷⁶. So far, it is the only new prevention method to have shown consistent efficacy through randomised controlled trials¹³⁰. An additional trial, in Rakai, Uganda, is evaluating the impact of male circumcision on male to female transmission of HIV.

There are reports that demand for safe, affordable male circumcision is already increasing in southern Africa^{173, 177}. Urgent consideration must be given to the need to provide increased access to safe, affordable male circumcision services on a large scale, embedded within a comprehensive package of proven HIV prevention measures. The current randomized controlled trials of circumcision also indicate that demand for male circumcision in non-circumcising communities is substantial when the procedure is offered at no cost in a safe setting. In Kisumu, Kenya, over 6686 of the 34,200 (19.5%) uncircumcised men in the city aged 18-24 years came to the study clinic for enrolment when they knew that willingness to be circumcised was a requirement for enrolment in the trial¹⁵. Similarly, the Rakai trial has recruited 5000 men,

representing approximately 45% of all the HIV uninfected eligible men in the study population (personal communication, R Gray). Data from Lusaka, Zambia show current demand for male circumcision exceeds capacity, with a shortage of skilled providers to meet demand¹⁷⁷, and the same situation exists in Swaziland. In light of the recent trial results, demand for male circumcision for HIV prevention is likely to increase rapidly.

3.3 Acceptability of male circumcision in east and southern Africa

One concern around the potential for male circumcision as an HIV prevention measure is that it may not be acceptable in communities which do not traditionally circumcise. A recent comprehensive review¹⁵ addresses this issue by summarising 13 studies assessing the acceptability of offering male circumcision services among traditionally non-circumcising groups in east and southern Africa (Table 4). The studies were carried out between 1991 and 2003 in Botswana, Kenya, Malawi, South Africa, the United Republic of Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe. Women as well as men were included in ten of the studies, enabling assessment of female perspectives on the acceptability of male circumcision.

The median proportion of uncircumcised men willing to become circumcised was 65% (range 29% in Uganda to 87% in Swaziland¹⁵). Similarly, 69% of women (range 47-79%) favoured circumcision for their partners and 71% (50-90%) of men and 81% (70-90%) of women were willing to circumcise their sons (Figure 9). The response varied with how the questions were posed and the context of the study. For example, one of the highest acceptability levels was recorded in Botswana after an informational session in which participants were told about the health benefits and risks associated with the procedure⁵¹.

Figure 9: Acceptability of male circumcision from eight quantitative studies in six sub-Saharan African Countries (adapted from Westercamp & Bailey; AIDS Behaviour 2006 – Permission pending from Springer Science & Business Media)

3.3.1 Barriers to acceptability

The three most salient barriers to the acceptability of male circumcision were fear of pain, concerns for safety, and the cost of the procedure. In areas where traditional circumcision is uncommon, the preference was overwhelmingly for a medical practitioner to be the provider, as this was perceived to be safer. All studies reported fear of infection, bleeding, excessive pain, and possible mutilation at the hands of traditional circumcisers.

Fear of pain was the main reported barrier towards male circumcision acceptability in most studies. This fear was based largely on knowledge of traditional circumcisions in which pain is often viewed as an integral part of the rite of passage to manhood.

Concerns for safety were also very common, especially among mothers when asked about infant and early childhood circumcision. Overall, there was greater trust in medical practitioners and a strong preference for circumcision services to be made available in public health facilities by trained health professionals. For example, fears about the risk of excessive bleeding or infection were heightened if the procedure was performed by a traditional circumciser outside the clinical setting^{16, 19, 25, 50, 52}.

Cost was mentioned as a significant barrier to male circumcision acceptability in many studies. Some participants would prefer circumcision to be provided at health clinics and hospitals for free or at reduced cost^{19, 25} whilst others recognised the need to pay for the service as free services are perceived as being of poor quality¹⁹. During a pilot study of provision of male circumcision services in Siaya, Kenya, demand for circumcision rapidly increased when the cost was reduced from US\$3.62 to US\$1.45, and half of all circumcisions carried out during the 25 month study occurred during the two month period in which lower fees were charged²⁵.

The determinants of male circumcision in traditionally circumcising populations, such as cultural identity, did not appear to be major barriers to circumcision in non-circumcising communities. Sanctions against circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising communities tend to be much less severe than the converse (i.e. not being circumcised in a circumcising community). In ethnically diverse areas, male circumcision status is likely to be less integral to cultural identity. For example, only 2% of the participants in the Botswana survey (which included 29 different ethnic groups) stated that circumcision would lead to disapproval by their community, although 22% cited "cultural reasons" as a factor in their decision not to circumcise their male child⁵¹. Similarly, in South Africa, 38% of circumcised and 32% of uncircumcised study participants described circumcision as "forbidden" by their religion⁵². In general, culture and religion tended to be more of a concern of older participants and less so among younger respondents, and several studies concluded that circumcision was increasingly an issue of personal choice rather than ethnic identity.

One factor which was discussed in focus group discussions but was not consistently found to be either a facilitator of or barrier to acceptability was sexual function. For example in one study in South Africa 30% of uncircumcised men believed that circumcision would improve their sexual performance and 14% believed it would decrease sexual pleasure⁵².

Table 4: Summary of studies assessing acceptability of male circumcision in non-circumcising communities in sub-Saharan Africa

Country	Time of the study	Participants interviewed	Ethnicity	Primary barriers	Primary facilitators
Botswana Kebabetswe et al, 2003 ⁵¹	March-June 2001	316 male and 289 female participants of 29 ethnicities, age 18 to 74, in urban and rural settings	Ethnically heterogeneous (29 ethnicities)	Pain Safety concerns Not culturally acceptable Religion	Protection from STI/HIV Culture/tradition Improved hygiene
Kenya Bailey et al, 2002 ²⁵	April-May 1998	30 focus groups, urban and rural population, farmers, business people, teachers, sex workers, barmaids, and touts.	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	Pain Cost Safety concerns Not culturally acceptable Difficulty of access to health facilities	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Enhanced sexual pleasure
Kenya Mattson et al, 2005 ¹⁷	April-May 1999	107 men and 110 women, of Luo ethnicity, in urban and rural settings	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	Pain Cost	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Enhanced sexual pleasure
Kenya Agot et al, 2007 ^{17,8}	2002-2004	628 men enrolling in study offering circumcision to assess behaviour change post surgery	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	(not reported)	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Avoiding injuries during sex Social influence
Malawi Ngalande et al., 2006 ¹⁹	July-August 2003	318 participants, 32 focus groups with men and women 16 to 80 years old	Ethnically diverse (Chewa, Tonga, Yao, Ngoni, Lomwe, and Nyanja)	Pain Surgical complications	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Social acceptability Enhanced sexual pleasure
South Africa Lagarde et al, 2003 ⁵²	August-September 2001	482 men aged 19-29 years and 302 women aged 14-25 years	Ethically heterogeneous (Sotho, Tswana, Xhosa and other ethnicities)	Cost Surgical complications 'Old fashioned'	Enhanced sexual pleasure Increased sexual desirability
South Africa Scott et al, 2005 ¹⁷⁹	July 2002	100 adult men and 44 adult women in rural Zulu land and 4 service providers	Ethnically homogenous (Zulu)	Pain	Enhanced sexual pleasure
South Africa Rain-Taljaard et al, 2003 ¹⁶	1999-2000	606 13-59 year old males interviewed in August 2000 and 723 14-24 year old males interviewed in August 1999	Ethnically diverse (Sotho, Xhosa, Zulu, Tswana, Shangaan, and Venda)	Surgical complications 'Old fashioned' Culture/tradition Religion	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Enhanced sexual performance Increased sexual desirability Greater respect Good fortune
Swaziland Tsela & Halperin, 2006 ⁸⁹	2006	409 men aged 15-19 in urban & rural settings	Ethnically homogenous (Swazi)		Protection from STI/HIV
United Republic of Tanzania Nnko et al, 2003 ¹¹	1991-1997	998 Sukuma men from a cohort of factory workers in Mwanza town, 13 focus groups from mostly rural area, and population based surveys	Ethnically homogenous (Sukuma)		Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Enhanced sexual performance
Zambia Lukobo & Bailey, 2007 ¹⁸	August-September 2003	160 men and 162 women in the 34 focus groups in rural and urban settings	Ethnically diverse (Lunda, Luvale, Chewa, Tonga)	Pain Cost Surgical complications Not culturally acceptable	Protection from STI/HIV Improved hygiene Enhanced sexual performance Increased social acceptability Increased sexual desirability
Zimbabwe Halperin et al, 2005 ⁵⁰	2000	200 men attending beer halls in Harare	Not reported, likely to be mainly Shona	Risk of infection through traditional circumcision if single blade used	Protection from STI Improved hygiene

3.3.2 Facilitators of acceptability

The main factors associated with willingness to be circumcised were improved penile hygiene, and a reduced risk of sexually transmitted infections (Table 2). Penile hygiene was widely recognized as being extremely important and was perceived as a major benefit of circumcision by both men and women. Participants also thought that it was easier for a circumcised man to maintain cleanliness and was thus a major factor in women's acceptability of male circumcision as in many parts of Africa, cleaning of the penis following intercourse is viewed as the woman's role, for example in Zambia, Malawi and Uganda^{18, 19, 32}

Similarly, circumcision was widely perceived to protect against infections, and to allow for easier identification of sores and ulcers, permitting earlier treatment. For example, in Nyanza Province, Kenya, 79% of uncircumcised men and 81% of women believed that it was easier for uncircumcised men to acquire STIs compared with circumcised men¹⁷, and in Swaziland, 81% of participants stated that circumcision reduced risk of STI, and 18% that it reduced risk of HIV⁵⁰. In a study in Kwa-Zulu Natal, South Africa, the majority of men (65%) stated that uncircumcised men were more likely to acquire STIs, but this was not associated with willingness to become circumcised among men¹⁷⁹. Conversely, a minority of respondents in the acceptability study in Zambia reported that the circumcised penis was "always dry", "susceptible to cracking", and that this state provided a portal of entry for bacteria and viruses¹⁸.

Beliefs about the impact of male circumcision on sexual performance and pleasure for the man or his partner were mentioned by men in most studies as a reason to become circumcised (Table 2)¹⁵. In addition, many younger men from traditionally non-circumcising communities cited being accepted as a sexual or marriage partner by women from other ethnic groups as an important reason to be circumcised^{11, 18, 19, 25}.

3.4 Behaviour change following circumcision

A major concern about the increased uptake of male circumcision in areas with high HIV incidence is that circumcision does not provide complete protection against infection. The public health message is that the procedure may reduce, but not eliminate, risk of infection, and safer sex practices must still be followed. However, this message may be difficult to communicate, and there is potential for risk compensation⁶ (i.e. increases in risky behaviour sparked by decreases in perceived risk)¹⁸¹.

Gray et al used stochastic simulation models to estimate HIV transmission probabilities under various assumptions¹⁸², including modelling the impact of male circumcision on HIV transmission¹⁸³. The model, using empirical data from the Rakai STI treatment trial, estimated that if newly circumcised men were to increase the number of sexual partners by an average of more than 25%, this would offset any beneficial effect of circumcision, even assuming a high efficacy of 60%.

To date, there are data on sexual behaviour following adult circumcision in two of the three randomized controlled trials. In the South African trial, men were asked about factors associated with numbers of sexual partners and contacts. Circumcised men reported higher risk behaviour for the five reported factors (being married or living as married; at least one sexual contact not protected by a condom; at least one non-spousal partner; at least one sexual partnership with only one sexual contact; at least 5 sexual contacts) during the period 4-12 months post randomization, and four out of five during the period 13-21 months after randomization. However, only the mean number of sexual contacts was statistically different between circumcised and uncircumcised men (5.9 vs. 5.0 in the period 4-12 months after randomization, $p < 0.001$; 7.5 vs. 6.4 in the period 13-21 months after randomisation, $p = 0.002$)¹³⁰. The numbers of new partners reported was not significantly higher among circumcised and uncircumcised men suggesting that, although sexual activity increased following circumcision, it was not with new partners. Notably, despite the increased reported sexual activity during follow-up, the risk of HIV acquisition in the circumcised men was

⁶ Risk compensation is also called 'behavioural disinhibition' in some circles.

the same whether behavioural variables were controlled for or not (unadjusted rate ratio=0.40; adjusted rate ratio=0.39). No risk compensation has been seen in either the Kisumu or Rakai trials^{133, 134}.

Behaviour change following circumcision within trials may differ from that in the 'real world', where less intensive counselling may be given to men undergoing circumcision. The first study to examine sexual behaviour following circumcision outside of a clinical trial setting was recently published¹⁷⁸. This cohort study offered circumcision to adult men at Siaya and Bondo District Hospitals in western Kenya. The 324 men who chose to be circumcised were matched with eligible men who chose to remain uncircumcised, on the basis of age, marital status and residential location. The circumcised men reported more risky behaviour in the three months before study entry compared with men who chose to remain uncircumcised (for example 34% vs 26% reported risk sex acts in the past 3 months; $p=0.03$) but during the 12 month follow-up period there were no significant difference in risky behaviour (number of unprotected sex acts, number of non-spousal partners, condom use). This was similar excluding the 3 months post-circumcision when circumcised men were less sexually active due to the operation. The study provides reassurance that, within the context of adequate counselling on risk reduction, circumcised men did not increase their risky behaviour but further studies are needed in other settings.

3.5 Cost-effectiveness of male circumcision for HIV prevention

The cost of clinic-based male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa depends on the setting and resources available. For example, at the University Teaching Hospital in Lusaka, the cost to the patient is \$3, whereas the cost in the private sector is \$343⁶². Similarly, in Kisumu Kenya, the cost is \$3-15 in public facilities and \$10-95 in private clinics⁶³, and costs of \$10-100 are typical in Senegal²⁷.

Two studies have estimated the cost-effectiveness of male circumcision for HIV prevention in Africa. The cost-effectiveness of expanding male circumcision services will depend on many factors including the costs of the surgery and of averted HIV treatment. The first study to be published assumes full coverage of male circumcision in Gauteng Province, South Africa (location of the randomised controlled trial), and an adult male HIV incidence of 3.8%. Based on the cost per circumcision in the trial of \$47, the authors estimated that 1000 circumcisions would avert an estimated 308 (95% CI 189-428) infections over 20 years. The cost was \$181 (80% CI \$117-306) per HIV infection averted, and net savings would be \$2.4 million (80% CI \$1.3-\$3.6 million). With a lower HIV incidence of 1%, the cost per HIA was \$551 (80% CI \$344-\$1 071)¹⁸⁴.

Higher estimates of the cost per HIV infection averted have been presented based on data from the randomised controlled trial in Rakai, Uganda. In this trial, which used physicians and fully equipped theatres, the cost per circumcision was \$69, and assuming HIV incidence of 1.25%, the estimated cost per HIV infection averted would be \$3136 if the efficacy of male circumcision is 50%, or \$1485 if circumcision also protects against acquisition in women¹⁸³. Given the 'gold standard' settings of this trial, it can be assumed that actual program costs would be lower.

Further work on cost-effectiveness using different assumptions is needed to compare usefully with other intervention methods in sub-Saharan Africa, such as treatment of sexually transmitted infections, voluntary counselling and testing and school-based educational interventions^{185, 186}. Suggested ranges of cost per HIV infection averted are \$11 - \$2,188 for condom distribution, \$18 - \$950 for blood safety, \$20 - \$2,198 for antiretroviral drugs to prevent mother-to-child transmission, \$393 - \$482 for voluntary counselling and testing, \$58 for mass media-based education, \$304 - \$512 for treatment of STIs, and \$6,704 - \$9,448 for school-based HIV prevention programs. Compared with these, data from the Orange Farm trial suggest male circumcision to be a highly cost-effective intervention, whereas those from Rakai suggest it would be less cost-effective than other HIV prevention methods.

3.6 Male circumcision and female genital mutilation

While both male circumcision and female genital mutilation or cutting (FGM/C) are steeped in culture and tradition, the health consequences of each are drastically different¹⁸⁷. Male circumcision may seem similar as far as definition is concerned – “partial ... removal of the external genitalia” – but in practice is substantially different. FGM/C, often referred to as ‘female circumcision’ comprises surgical procedures involving partial or total removal of the external female genitalia. It is the manifestation of deep-rooted gender inequality that assigns women an inferior position in societies, and is unambiguously linked to a reduction in women’s sexual desire and an irreversible loss of capability for a type of sexual functioning that many women value highly¹⁸⁸.

FGM frequently involves complete removal of the clitoris, as well additional cutting and stitching of the labia resulting in a constricted vaginal opening. The procedures are linked to extensive and in some cases lifelong health problem¹⁸⁹. The immediate complications include severe pain, shock, hemorrhage, tetanus or sepsis, urine retention, ulceration of the genital region and injury to adjacent tissue. Hemorrhage and infection can be of such magnitude as to cause death¹⁸⁹. Moreover the WHO collaborative prospective study in six African Countries on Female Genital Mutilation and Obstetric Outcomes published in June 2006¹⁹⁰ showed that deliveries to women who underwent FGM/C (all types considered) were significantly more likely to be complicated by Cesarean section, postpartum hemorrhage, episiotomy, extended maternal hospital stay, resuscitation of the infant and hospital inpatient perinatal death than deliveries to women who have not had FGM/C. FGM/C is estimated to lead to an extra one to two perinatal deaths per 100 deliveries.

There are no known health benefits associated with FGM and no research evidence to suggest that such procedures could reduce the risk of HIV transmission. For these reasons, bodies including WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, the International Council of Nurses, the American Academy of Pediatrics and the Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists consider FGM/C to be universally unacceptable because it is an infringement on the physical and psychosexual integrity of women and girls and is a form of violence against them¹⁸⁹.

3.7 Human rights, ethical and legal implications

The protection and promotion of human rights is integral to all aspects of HIV prevention, treatment, care and support. Expansion and initiation of male circumcision services must ensure that the procedure is carried out safely, under conditions of informed consent and without discrimination. With the exception of South Africa, where the 2005 Children’s Act prohibits male circumcision for males aged under 16 except for medical or religious reasons, most countries do not currently have laws dealing specifically with male circumcision. One exception is Israel, where several regulations of the Ministry of Health are in place to regulate and supervise male circumcision¹⁷⁰.

Any future expansion of male circumcision services needs to be considered within a legal, regulatory and policy framework to ensure accessibility, acceptability and quality of service provision. Guidelines on these issues have been published separately¹⁹¹.

3.8 Summary

There is already some evidence of increased demand for male circumcision in southern Africa, and this is likely to increase further now that results from the Kenyan and Uganda trials have confirmed those of the South African trial. Major concerns about increased uptake of male circumcision services are safety, acceptability, and risk compensation. Recent studies of acceptability among non-circumcising communities with high incidence of HIV in southern Africa were fairly consistent in finding that a majority of men would be willing to be circumcised, if it were done safely and at minimal cost. In addition, the large numbers of men recruited into the trials in non-circumcising communities in South Africa, Uganda and Kenya, and the increased demand in male circumcision in Swaziland and Zambia, suggest that uptake of circumcision could be rapid if there was confidence in provision of safe and affordable surgery. To date, there is modest evidence of risk compensation following adult male circumcision, and care must be taken to embed any male circumcision provision with existing HIV prevention packages that include intensive counselling on safer sex, particularly regarding reduction of number of concurrent sexual partners and correct and consistent use of male and female condoms. Further data, both from the recently completed trials, but also from observational studies of men pre- and post- elective circumcision are needed.

SECTION 4 : Conclusions

Male circumcision has been carried out for many thousands of years, and is likely to be the most common surgical procedure globally, with an estimated 30% of men circumcised. Promotion of male circumcision for medical benefit has always been controversial, largely due to the lack of evidence for a strong protective effect of male circumcision against common diseases. However, there is now conclusive evidence that male circumcision significantly reduces risk of HIV infection in men.

Demand for male circumcision has already increased in east and southern Africa, the region of the world with highest HIV incidence among the general population. When the procedure is carried out under correct conditions, the risk of adverse events among adult men (mainly bleeding, infection and swelling) are about 2%, and these are readily treatable. However, in this review we have highlighted the dangers associated with male circumcision when undertaken in unhygienic, ill-equipped settings by inexperienced providers. There is an urgent need to establish national policies to maximise safety of male circumcision provision.

The demand for circumcision is likely to increase further given the results of the trials. Ensuring an adequate supply of trained providers adequately equipped to meet this demand will be challenging, but will also provide an opportunity. Sexually active young men in areas of high HIV prevalence are usually a population that is hard-to-reach. Provision of circumcision services, with the necessary repeated visits, counselling, and focus on sexuality and hygiene, will provide a much-needed opportunity to engage these men in comprehensive HIV prevention counselling as well as other reproductive health matters.

SECTION 5 : References

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Uniting the world against AIDS

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 17:10:31 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address
Attachments: Board Circumcision Statement.doc

This just in from the front lines. FYI.
-Allan

From: Dennis deLeon [mailto:DdeLeon@latinoaids.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 13:04
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

Mr. Taylor, the Latino Commission on AIDS has just issued the attached statement: Latino Commission on AIDS Recommends Health Providers Consider Offering Education and Services on Male Circumcision to Latino Men that Regularly Engage in High Risk Sexual Practices. I don't know if this will be of any use for the consultation.

	24 WEST 25TH STREET 9TH FLOOR NEW YORK, NY 10010-2704 TEL (212) 675-3288 FAX (212) 675-3466
Dennis deLeon President	Direct Line (212) 594-9300 Direct Fax (212) 202-3620 Cell Phone (917) 697-8040 ddeleon@latinoaids.org www.latinoaids.org

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 7:23 PM
To: Dennis deLeon
Subject: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

Mr. de Leon

We are putting together a list of consultation participants with contact information for distribution to all participants. Below is the contact information we have listed for you. Please complete and confirm that this is the information that you would like distributed to participants or provide an alternate. Please also inform us if you prefer to have any or all of this information withheld.

ddeleon@latinoaids.org

-
Title: President
Organization: Latino Commission on AIDS
Contact Address:
24 West, 25th Street, 9th Floor
New York, NY 10010
Contact Phone: 212-675-3288

We have also identified a typographical error on the agenda and have attached a corrected version.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

24 W. 25TH STREET, 9TH FLOOR, NEW YORK, NY 10010-2704 • TEL: 212-675-3288 • FAX: 212-675-3466

THE LATINO COMMISSION ON AIDS RECOMMENDS HEALTH PROVIDERS CONSIDER OFFERING EDUCATION AND SERVICES ON MALE CIRCUMCISION TO LATINO MEN THAT REGULARLY ENGAGE IN HIGH RISK SEXUAL PRACTICES

Three recently reported studies conducted in Kenya and Uganda have demonstrated that heterosexual men who were circumcised as adults experienced dramatically lower rates of HIV infection when compared to a control group of men who were uncircumcised. The results showed 60% to 51% fewer infections in the circumcised males. All groups in each study had the same access to HIV prevention counseling and free condoms. An effective circumcision strategy could save thousands of lives in Africa and other countries where heterosexual transmission is the primary cause of HIV infection. In addition, male circumcision has also been associated with lower rates of HPV among men and lower rates of HPV and cervical cancer rates among women. Thus, circumcision not only helps reduce rates of heterosexual HIV transmission, but it also is associated with lower rates of other sexually transmitted diseases.

What is the importance of these studies for Latin America/Caribbean countries and for Latino immigrants to the United States from those countries? This is no trivial question. The question of circumcision as a public health strategy bears special relevance to the Latino community in Mexico, Central American, the Spanish Caribbean, and South America where men have circumcision rates below 20%.¹ It is more than likely that men from these countries who are immigrants to the United States share the circumcision profile of their home countries. The three studies raise hopes of reduced heterosexual infections and constitute one of the most potentially important public sexual health interventions in recent history.

What are the public health implications for Latinos in Latin America and the United States? To understand the risk for heterosexual males for HIV infection in the Latin

¹ Drain, P, Halperin D, Hughes J, Male circumcision, religion and infectious diseases: an ecologic analysis of 118 developing countries. BMC Infectious Diseases 2006 6:172 Table !

America and the United States, it is important to understand the prevalence of HIV among women and the rates of AIDS in Africa and Latin America and the United States. We are talking about female to male transmission of HIV so the incidence of infections among women is important because that is one way heterosexual men become infected. The epidemic among women in Latin America and the United States looks very different than that in Sub Saharan Africa where the three controlled studies were done. In Latin American about 26% of all persons living with HIV/AIDS are women compared to 61% of all persons living with AIDS in Africa.² Latinas in the United States have similar proportions to Latin America with 17% of women living with HIV/AIDS.³ Further the rates of AIDS in South America are less than 1% with only slightly higher rates in Central America and the Dominican Republic as compared to 6.2% for Sub Saharan Africa.

All this data tells us that there is less opportunity for HIV transmission from women to men to take place in Latin America and the United States compared to Africa because of the lower numbers of infected women and the lower prevalence in the general population. The low rates of heterosexual transmission among men in the United States bears this out. Fourteen percent of Latino men living with AIDS in the United States in 2005 were identified as being infected by “high risk” heterosexual contact compared to the overwhelming percentage of infections among men in Africa. Put another way, the sexual ecology of risk is different in the Americas as compared to Africa.

Should uncircumcised Latino heterosexual men in Latin America or the United States who are sexually active with numerous sexual partners consider circumcision?

If Latino men insist on not using condoms for vaginal or anal sex, they should consult with their doctors on the advisability of becoming circumcised. Even though the risk is lower in Latin America, infection is still a risk for uncircumcised heterosexual men. Heterosexual Latino men report only 14% condom use.⁴ While the high rates of HIV infection among heterosexual men in the Africa may not be present in the United States and Latin America, there is now evidence that such surgery will almost

² UNAIDS/WHO 2006 Report on the global AIDS epidemic, Annex 2: HIV and AIDS estimates and data, 2005 and 2003.

³ CDC 2005 Surveillance Report Table 9

⁴ Fernandez-Esquer M, Atkinson J, Diamond P Condom use self-efficacy among U.S.- and foreign-born Latinos in Texas j Sex Research Nov 2004

certainly have a dramatic effect in lessening the number of heterosexual Latino men becoming infected, especially among Latino men who are sexually active with numerous sexual partners. However there are issues that may deter some Latino heterosexual men from considering the surgery.

- There is a real problem in access to the surgery among men who might most need it – the unacculturated immigrant heterosexual men who have the lowest rates of circumcision. The surgery is estimated to cost \$3,000 and must be performed by a specialist. At a time when Latino men and women are being excluded from the nation's health care system, it is unlikely that a poor man is going to get access to such surgery even if he were recommended as an appropriate candidate by his doctor?
- Another problem is the requirement after surgery that the man abstains from sex for up to six weeks or possibly longer. For some men this may be extremely difficult.
- There are very low risks such as bleeding, pain, damage to the penis and infections which could deter some men.

Should uncircumcised Latino homosexual men who are sexually active with numerous sexual partners and do not use condoms consider circumcision? For Latin America and the United States this is a very important question because the epidemic among men is primarily among men who have sex with men. The sexual ecology for Latino gay men is like that for men and women in Africa. While condom use may be higher among Latino gay men (44%), the background incidence of those who are infected is high presenting a higher risk of infection. In some areas of the country there are very high rates of HIV infection among Latino gay men. If Latino gay men have concluded that they are unable to use condoms for anal sex or desire to engage in unprotected sex, circumcision is something that should be discussed with their doctors. The scientific data available on circumcision and gay men is based on surveys and observational studies. There has been no controlled study as was done in Africa. On one hand, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention points out two observational studies in which the lack of circumcision is associated with a two-fold increased risk for

seroconversion.⁵ On the other hand, there is demographic research which shows that while male circumcision was independently associated with HIV infection among countries with primarily heterosexual HIV transmission, and not among countries with primarily homosexual HIV transmission.⁶

Despite this lack of a controlled study, there may be some gay men who will be persuaded by the observational data described above and wish to consult their doctors. These Latino men will face the challenge of accessing an expensive surgery, immigration fears, and the requirement of a period of abstinence.

Will circumcision eliminate the risk of HIV infection for heterosexual or homosexual Latino men? The answer is no. Depending on the sexual ecology of one's environment, there will always be at some level of risk of HIV infection. Circumcision may reduce the likelihood of infection but it will never eliminate it. A circumcised male should always use a condom despite the lower risk of HIV infection.

For those Latino gay and heterosexual men who refuse to use condoms but still engage in vaginal and/or anal sex with multiple partners, are there other steps that can be taken to reduce the risk of infection? There is a lot that gay or straight men that care about staying sexually healthy can do to lessen the likelihood of infection.

- **Sero-sorting:** This is the practice of having sex without condoms in which both men or a man and a woman are HIV infected or HIV negative. There still is a risk with sero-sorting for other sexually transmitted infections and some argue you may become "reinfected" with different varieties of HIV.⁷
- **Oral Sex:** The practice of giving or receiving fellatio carries a very low risk of HIV transmission. The level of risk may vary with whether there is ejaculation in the mouth but there is still some risk even without ejaculation.⁸
- **Monogamy:** If two men or a man and a woman who are HIV negative and in a committed monogamous relationship, the risk for HIV infection is sharply reduced.

⁵ CDC HIV/AIDS Science Facts: Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States (March 2007)

⁶ Drain, P, Halperin D, etc. at Table 4

⁷ <http://aids.about.com/cs/safesex/a/reinfection.htm>.

⁸ <http://hivinsite.ucsf.edu/InSite?page=pr-rr-05>.

Although gay and straight men in monogamous relationships are more likely to have unprotected sex (without use of a condom), the data indicates lower rates of HIV for such men.⁹

- **Psychological help:** There is a growing body of literature that connects the mental health of gay men and engaging in unsafe sex. Gay men with long-term, low-grade depression are almost twice as likely to have had unsafe casual sex.¹⁰ Mental health assistance could play a role in reducing unsafe casual sex.
- **PREP:** Pre-exposure prophylaxis (taking an anti-retroviral HIV drugs before unprotected sex) shows promise in guarding against the likelihood of HIV infection. There are many questions that must be answered before this strategy should be followed. The Federal Government needs to support such research.

All of these steps toward sexual health are similar to circumcision. They are all forms of harm reduction that reduce the spread of HIV that are not 100% guaranteed to prevent HIV infection. Even condoms are a form of harm reduction because they fail 2% of the time even with correct usage.¹¹

What research is needed? There must be a controlled study of uncircumcised gay men before solid health recommendations can be made for gay men. Such a study might prove important in helping gay men to navigate a difficult sexual environment. In the interim we must expand the discussion of harm reduction steps that can be taken to reduce the risk of HIV infection now and how to increase condom use. In addition studies need to be done on the cultural barriers that may prevent gay or heterosexual men from considering circumcision even when the behavioral profile may make the discussion appropriate.

⁹ L McKusick, T J Coates, S F Morin, L Pollack, and C Hoff Longitudinal predictors of reductions in unprotected anal intercourse among gay men in San Francisco: the AIDS Behavioral Research Project. *Am J Public Health*. 1990 August; 80(8): 978–983.

¹⁰ Science Day: Unsafe Sex Among Gay Men Linked To Depression, Oct 13, 2000

¹¹ MMWR Weekly August 06, 1993 / 42(30);589-591,597

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 4 Apr 2007 18:35:51 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

FYI

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 2:34 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Barry Dickinson
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

It would be me, and I'd fly in the morning of the 26th arriving at about 9 AM and then leaving at the end of the day. So no hotel room would be needed.

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:dks0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 11:16 AM
To: Litjen Tan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Dr. Tan,

If that is the time available for you, it will be ok. But I would then ask the attendee to be vocal during the discussion periods on Thursday so that we have good input from AMA before he/she leaves.

Does that work for you? We need the name of your representative urgently for the hotel to hold a spot.

Thanks for your efforts in this.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 12:14 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hi Dr. Smith!

We are having trouble getting someone to be there both days. If I can only fly in on Thursday AM and fly out Thursday PM, will that be OK?

L.J

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>]
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 2:41 PM
To: Litjen Tan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hi there.

This meeting is being convened on April 26-27 in Atlanta in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be high risk populations something missing in this sentence??? in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

We will pay for travel for an AMA representative as we feel it is important to hear your perspective on possible changes in recommendations about this medical practice as it affects HIV prevention clinical activities.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Friday, March 23, 2007 8:56 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Barry Dickinson
Subject: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hello Dr. Smith!

I have been forwarded a request for AMA representation at your consultation on the role of male circumcision in preventing HIV transmission.

Can you email me some details about the meeting? When is it, and will the CDC be paying for travel?

Thanks!

L.J

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 29 Mar 2007 17:14:37 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

From: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 12:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cagle, Chris (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Allan,
In a rush this morning I forwarded several e-mails. I missed one of them.
Here is the "cut and paste" of all three below.
Please contact Sean Barry directly but please cc me so I am in the loop.
If you have any questions as you move through the process, please let me or Chris Cagle know.
Thanks much.
Sean

From: Sean Barry [mailto:sean@champnetwork.org]
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 8:20 PM
To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Circumcision consultation - recommendations for participants

We would like Walt Senterfitt to be our CHAMP representative. Contact info:
(b)(6) (cell).

Bio: Dr. Walt Senterfitt, a gay man living with AIDS, is the Chair of the Community HIV/AIDS Mobilization Project (CHAMP) Board. He is an epidemiologist who served as a Visiting Scientist at the CDC's Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, coordinating demonstration projects of HIV prevention interventions with HIV positive people. His special focus as a public health official has been to increase the active collaboration of researchers and policy makers with the community constituencies that are the targets and intended beneficiaries of the research and policy. Walt is also involved with Being Alive/Los Angeles and the Southern California HIV/AIDS Coalition.

===

Additional recommendations [none have a formal affiliation with CHAMP beyond our regular collaboration] --

Edd Lee, Director of Education & Outreach, AIDS Vaccine Advocacy Coalition (AVAC).

Edd is active within the domestic HIV prevention research trials networks and has been one of the only people I'm aware of who's been asking questions about what the MC trial results mean for the US. He was formerly the Assoc Director of Prevention Services at API Wellness Center before going to AVAC. Fyi, in case you haven't see it, AVAC has a great webpage on MC

at www.aidsvaccineclearinghouse.org/MC/index.html

I just thought of some more knowledgeable and thoughtful folks we'd recommend and that the branch is probably more familiar with. Let me know if I can pass along additional information about any of them.

Judy Auerbach, Assistant Director for Science and Public Policy, San Francisco AIDS Foundation (SFAF). jauerbach@sfaf.org

Monica Ruiz, Acting Director for Public Policy, American Foundation for AIDS Research (amFAR). monica.ruiz@amfar.org

Cornelius Baker, Policy Advisor, National Black Gay Men's Advocacy Coalition (NBGMAC). acorneliusbaker@hotmail.com

Diana Bruce, Policy Director, AIDS Alliance for Children, Youth, and Families & steering committee member of the National Black Women's HIV/AIDS Network. dbruce@aidsalliance.org

I think it's important to also invite someone from a leading Latino AIDS organization like Bienestar or LCOA given the comparatively lower rates of circumcision within that population.

Two more recommendations that just came to mind:

- Jim Pickett, Policy Director, AIDS Foundation of Chicag. Jim's HIV-positive and a very active gay men's health advocate. He's also with lifelube.org and is a main convener of the International Rectal Microbicides WG, which has been having conversations about how to respond to the MC trials.
- Someone from NAPWA – probably Frank Oldham, Sean Dwyer (policy person), or David Munar (a Board member).

PS – promise last email from me on this thread!

Edd is also a good person to touch base with about anecdotal reports of ASOs dealing with questions around circumcision. He has an extensive network through HVTN recruitment and has been hearing from providers who don't know what to say when people walk in their door and ask what the African trial results mean for them.

Sean Barry
Community HIV/AIDS Mobilization Project (CHAMP)
www.champnetwork.org

office: 212.937.7955, ext. 5
cell: 646.373.3344
email: sean@champnetwork.org

[Faint, illegible text, possibly a signature or header]

[Faint, illegible text]

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 6:13 PM

To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Great. Thanks. I'll add Walt Senterfit to the list.

-Allan

From: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 18:11
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Hi Allan,

I will be getting an e-mail from CHAMP recommending Walt Senterfit later today. I will forward it on as soon as I receive it.

Sean Berry will also be recommending another person and will include that in the e-mail as well.

SDG

[Faint, illegible text, possibly a signature or a very light email body]

[Faint, illegible text]

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 4:58 PM
To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Hi, Sean.

Just wanted to check in with you about this: Any word on whether CHAMP would like to send someone? We're pulling together our final invitation list and are holding a spot for them if they would like to attend. Thanks for your help.

-Allan

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 22, 2007 14:38
To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Hi, Sean.

Thank you for inviting us for this call. I am coordinating the male circumcision consultation in late April, and we would welcome participation from CHAMP. We're finalizing the invitee list in the next day or so; would you be able to contact them to see if they would like to send a representative? CDC would support the participant's travel, hotel, meals.

Thanks!
-Allan

From: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Sent: Wednesday, March 21, 2007 17:17

To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Purcell, David (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lyles, Cynthia (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cleveland, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Studer, Craig (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cagle, Chris (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Dooley, Samuel (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Branson, Bernard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Hello all,
The CHAMP call went well today.

Both Cindy and David did great. There were lots of questions. They made several comments about the interventions.

The other issues were:

(b)(5)

Peter also did a great job representing the Division on circumcision. The group was very interested in the issue and offered a number of challenging and interesting comments/questions. They also raised the issue that rates of circumcision in the US may have changed in the recent years from the reported 70-80% and that 16 states have recently dropped Medicaid coverage for circumcision. Also, shared that lower rates of circumcision in the US may differ based on regions in the US and populations (i.e., Latinos, AA, etc.).

Peter, David/Cindy, please feel free to add.
Sean

From: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 21, 2007 11:09 AM
To: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Purcell, David (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lyles, Cynthia (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cleveland, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Studer, Craig (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cagle, Chris (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Dooley, Samuel (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Branson, Bernard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

All,
Here is the final agenda for today's call:

CHAMP STRATEGY LAB CALL

TODAY, March 21st

3:30 – 5:15 EDT / 2:30 – 4:15 CDT / 1:30 – 3:15 MDT / 12:30 – 2:15 PDT

866-438-5720, passcode 3528

NOTE - updated agenda for today's call.

ATTACHED - Dr. Lyles' presentation for the call + CDC fact sheet on circumcision in the United States.

3:30 – 4:15 SPOTLIGHT DISCUSSION: Behavioral Prevention

Updating what works in behavioral prevention - discussion of "Best-Evidence Interventions: Findings From a Systematic Review of HIV Behavioral Interventions for US Populations at High Risk, 2000–2004."

PRESENTED BY:

* Cindy Lyles, PhD, Leader, Synthesis and Analytical Support Team, Prevention Research Branch, DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC | www.cdc.gov/hiv/topics/research/prs/index.htm

* David W. Purcell, JD, PhD, Acting Branch Chief, Prevention Research Branch (PRB), DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC

4:15 – 4:30 HIV PREVENTION RESEARCH: Microbicides & PrEP at CROI

Highlights from the Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections (CROI).

PRESENTED BY:

* Monica Ruiz, PhD, MPH, Acting Director for Public Policy, American Foundation for AIDS Research (amFAR) | www.amfar.org

4:30 – 5:00 RESEARCH INTO ACTION: Circumcision in the United States

CDC has a new fact sheet "Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States" available at www.cdc.gov/hiv/resources/factsheets/circumcision.htm

PRESENTED BY:

- * Peter H. Kilmarx, MD, Chief, Epidemiology Branch, DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC
- * Deborah Baron, MPH, CHAMP.

5:00 – 5:15 ANNOUNCEMENTS

Dear all,
I hope you are all well.
I am looking forward to seeing you all tomorrow.
I will be in the room from 5:00 to 5:15 PM.

Thank you,
Sean Griffiths

From: Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 12:21 PM

To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Purcell, David (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lyles, Cynthia (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cleveland, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Studer, Craig (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cagle, Chris (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Griffiths, Sean (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Subject: CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

Hello All,

Below is the DRAFT agenda for the CHAMP Strategy Lab call tomorrow.

The call-in number is: 866-438-5720, pass code 3528

There will be questions from call-in participants for each of the agenda items. CHAMP forwarded sample questions for the PRS agenda item. They are:

(b)(5)

For the Microbicides/Circumcision section CHAMP is asking the following:

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Please let me know if you have any other questions.
Sean

CHAMP Strategy Lab Call- Behavioral Prevention/Microbicides/Circumcision

STRATEGY LAB CALL

WEDNESDAY, March 21st

3:30 – 5:30 EDT / 2:30 – 4:30 CDT / 1:30 – 3:30 MDT / 12:30 – 2:30 PDT

CALL AGENDA – *please note agenda times may not match up exactly with presentations.*

3:30 – 4:15 SPOTLIGHT DISCUSSION: Behavioral Prevention

Evolving and updating behavioral prevention programs that work. Discussion of “*Best-Evidence Interventions: Findings From a Systematic Review of HIV Behavioral Interventions for US Populations at High Risk, 2000–2004.*” by Dr. Cindy Lyles and colleagues. A systematic review of behavioral interventions in the 90s led to the *Compendium of HIV Prevention Interventions With Evidence of Effectiveness* (www.cdc.gov/hiv/pubs/hivcompendium/hivcompendium.htm), which was last revised in 2000. Dr. Lyles and her colleagues in the CDC’s HIV/AIDS Prevention Research Synthesis (PRS) Team set out to review newer interventions for HIV-positive and HIV-negative persons and concluded that 18 interventions fit their criteria for best evidence, although they recognized gaps in interventions for some high-risk populations.

ATTACHED: Dry. Lyles’ article and presentation for the call.

PRESENTED BY:

- **Cindy Lyles, PhD**, Leader, Synthesis and Analytical Support Team, Prevention Research Branch, DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC | www.cdc.gov/hiv/topics/research/prs/index.htm
- **David W. Purcell, JD, PhD**, Prevention Research Branch, DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC

4:15 – 4:45 HIV PREVENTION RESEARCH: Microbicides, PrEP, & Vaccines at CROI

Highlights from the Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections (CROI). Hear from the experts about microbicides, PrEP, and vaccine research presented at the preeminent HIV science conference. And if you haven’t already, check out our picks in our “Prevention Takes the Red Carpet” article from the latest issue of *HHS Watch*, available at www.champnetwork.org/index.php?name=news.

PRESENTED BY:

- **Monica Ruiz, PhD, MPH**, Acting Director for Public Policy, American Foundation for AIDS Research (amFAR) | www.amfar.org
- **AIDS Vaccine Advocacy Coalition (AVAC) rep [invited]** | www.avac.org

4:45 – 5:15 RESEARCH INTO ACTION: Circumcision in the United States

Asking the questions – what do we tell people in the United States about the potential benefit of circumcision? Research from trials in Africa suggest that male circumcision (MC) can reduce the risk of an HIV-negative male partner acquiring HIV through vaginal sex by an average of 50-60%. What does that mean for the United States, where circumcision rates are relatively high but uneven among ethnic groups, and where there is comparably less heterosexual transmission of HIV? What do we tell people who are hearing news reports from the trials overseas? What additional research needs to be done? These questions and more will be explored...

CDC has a new fact sheet “Male Circumcision and Risk for HIV Transmission: Implications for the United States” available at www.cdc.gov/hiv/resources/factsheets/circumcision.htm

PRESENTED BY:

- **Tim Mastro, MD**, Deputy Director for Science, DHAP/NCHHSTP/CDC. (from 4:45p – 5p)
- **Deborah Baron, MPH, CHAMP**.

5:15 – 5:30 ANNOUNCEMENTS

1. The first meeting of the National HIV/AIDS Conference will be held on November 14-15, 2008 in Washington, DC. The meeting will focus on the theme of “HIV Prevention: A New Paradigm.” The meeting will be held at the Marriott Marquis Hotel. For more information, please visit www.hivconference.org.

2. The second meeting of the National HIV/AIDS Conference will be held on November 16-17, 2008 in Washington, DC. The meeting will focus on the theme of “HIV Treatment: A New Paradigm.” The meeting will be held at the Marriott Marquis Hotel. For more information, please visit www.hivconference.org.

3. The National HIV/AIDS Conference will be held on November 14-17, 2008 in Washington, DC. The meeting will focus on the theme of “HIV Prevention, Treatment, and Care: A New Paradigm.” The meeting will be held at the Marriott Marquis Hotel. For more information, please visit www.hivconference.org.

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 16 Apr 2007 13:34:31 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision & MSM
Attachments: circumcision.jpg

FYI. Craig Neiderberger, our participant from AUA, speaks clearly in this NYT piece.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Millett, Greg (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 16, 2007 7:50 AM
To: CDC NCHSTP/DHAP Prevention Research Branch
Cc: Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision & MSM

From Sunday's NY Times...

Tough Sell: Preventing H.I.V., but at What Price?

By DONALD G. McNEIL Jr.

Published: April 15, 2007

READ the next sentence aloud, and watch all the men around you involuntarily cross their legs:
How do you persuade a grown man to get circumcised?

Answer: it's not easy, even in America, where most men are circumcised at birth.

Now that three clinical trials in Africa have shown that circumcision helps protect men against AIDS and the World Health Organization has endorsed it, public health doctors elsewhere — including in New York City — are contemplating whether to recommend it. Then comes the difficult part — how to sell the idea.

Unfortunately, the data from Africa does not translate well. Those trials were of heterosexual men in countries where the virus is everywhere, education about safe sex is practically nonexistent, and condoms get in the way of the need to father children.

In the United States, the AIDS epidemic is very different. The highest risk groups are men having sex with men (whether openly or covertly or even forcibly — in prison rapes, for example), people who share needles and women who, often unknowingly, have sex with high-risk men. Although it has been killing people here for 25 years, AIDS has not turned into a

generalized epidemic like it has in Africa. Sex education, condoms, abstinence, antiretroviral drugs and the fear of death have concentrated it mostly in small pockets of the population.

And for most of those people, circumcision probably won't do much good. It might help protect gay men who are exclusively "tops" — that is, they have only penetrative anal sex, never receptive. It presumably would protect men having sex with infected women. It might protect women who choose circumcised men — but even that wasn't proved in the African studies, which had to be stopped early because the benefit for men was so glaring.

Because of these unknowables, no domestic medical authority, from the New York City Health Department to the American Urological Association, has a policy on adult circumcision yet.

And, besides, there hasn't been a groundswell of demand.

"We haven't gotten a lot of calls," said Noel Alicea, a spokesman for Gay Men's Health Crisis, which runs a hotline.

"Not a one," said Tokes Osubu, executive director of Gay Men of African Descent.

"A few," said Mark McLaurin, executive director of the New York State Black Gay Network. "The first ones wanted to make sure that it wasn't going to be mandatory. And then there were others who said 'Tell me more — how much does this reduce my risk?'"

Mr. McLaurin said he would advise most gay men to "hold off until we have more data."

But, he added, "for someone who was predominantly or exclusively a top, and said he was really having a hard time reducing his risk by practicing safe sex — I'd have a hard time recommending against it."

But, he quickly added, he was certain that few men in his network would want it.

"We've had a hard time recruiting black and Latino men even for vaccine trials," he said.

"Because of everything from Tuskegee on up," he explained — referring to the notorious medical experiment in which black men with syphilis were left untreated for decades — many black Americans mistrust the medical establishment.

In Africa, it is relatively easy to talk men into getting circumcised, said Daniel Halperin, an AIDS researcher at the Harvard School of Public Health who has interviewed hundreds of African men about sex, AIDS and local customs.

Some tribes circumcise teenagers to welcome them to full manhood. Many men who can't get enough water to bathe regularly think foreskins are unhygienic. And some, he said, "say circumcised men get all the women" because of a widespread belief that, with slightly lessened sensation, they can make love longer.

(Circumcision's effect on sex is a white-hot issue in the United States for the small but vocal anticircumcision lobby. The lobby's main focus is on advice to parents of baby boys, but it has offshoot groups, like the "uncuts" who insist that sex with uncircumcised men is superior, and the "foreskin restoration movement" which utilizes tape, small weights and parental resentment.)

For adult men, circumcision takes about 30 minutes, said Dr. Craig Niederberger, chief of male reproductive surgery at the University of Illinois at Chicago. It is an outpatient procedure and, like dental work, can be done with local injections of Novocain.

“But with many men,” he added, “if you use the words ‘scalpel’ and ‘penis’ in the same sentence, they say ‘put me to sleep!’ So then we do it under general anesthesia.”

There is no official national estimate of how many adults have the operation each year.

Most of his patients have phimosis or balanitis — a painfully tight foreskin or swollen glans, which can become a crisis if urination is blocked.

But, because he practices in a black Chicago neighborhood, some of his young, healthy patients are volunteers — perhaps the only demographic group of African-American men currently lining up for the operation.

They are converts to Islam, which requires circumcision.

“They come in very committed,” he said. “It’s a personal choice that’s very strong.”

A spokeswoman for the Nation of Islam, the Black Muslim group also based in south Chicago, said she presumed most adherents were circumcised at birth, “but I’m the wrong person to ask,” she added. A male official she suggested for comment did not return a phone call.

In any case, that appears to be the answer: Until more trials are done, it’s going to take a medical emergency. Or divine intervention.

CIRCUM(DE)CISION

CIRCUM(DE)CISION

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 5 Apr 2007 12:41:10 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

From: Millett, Greg (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 8:01 AM
To: CDC NCHSTP/DHAP Prevention Research Branch
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

In today's New York Times....

New York City Plans to Promote Circumcision

By DONALD G. McNEIL Jr.

Published: April 5, 2007

New York City's Department of Health and Mental Hygiene is planning a campaign to encourage men at high risk of AIDS to get circumcised in light of the World Health Organization's endorsement of the procedure as an effective way to prevent the disease.

While the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention in Atlanta is just beginning to convene meetings and design studies to help it formulate a national policy, New York City is moving ahead on its own.

In the United States, "New York City remains the epicenter of the AIDS epidemic," Dr. Thomas R. Frieden, the city's health commissioner, said in an interview. Referring to H.I.V., he said, "In some subpopulations, you have 10 to 20 percent prevalence rates, just as they do in parts of Africa."

His department has started asking some community groups and gay rights organizations to discuss circumcision with their members, and has asked the Health and Hospitals Corporation, which runs city hospitals and clinics, to perform the procedure at no charge for men without health insurance.

A spokeswoman for the corporation said it was "having conversations" with the health department but had not reached a decision.

“As you know, the research on this is pretty recent,” the spokeswoman, Ana Marengo, said.

In three recent clinical trials in Africa, circumcision was shown to lower a man’s risk of contracting the virus from heterosexual sex by about 60 percent. On March 28, the World Health Organization officially recommended that countries adopt the procedure as part of their AIDS prevention plans.

No spontaneous outcry for circumcision has arisen in New York, Dr. Frieden conceded.

“This is not something that has a lot of buzz,” he said.

But he added that even 1,000 circumcisions in the right subgroups might slow the spread of AIDS.

For example, in Manhattan, 20 percent of all black men between 40 and 50 are infected with the virus that causes AIDS. About 10 percent of all gay men in the city are infected, and the rate rises to as high as 25 percent in the Chelsea neighborhood.

Dr. Frieden said black, Hispanic and foreign-born men were less likely to be circumcised than white Americans, and the percentage is smaller among men with lower incomes.

(About 65 percent of all male babies in the United States are circumcised, according to the National Center for Health Statistics, compared with about 30 percent of men worldwide, by W.H.O. estimates.)

Among men seeking treatment at the city’s clinics for sexually transmitted diseases — another risk group for AIDS infection because of genital sores — a large proportion are uncircumcised, Dr. Frieden said.

There are clear limitations, however, on extrapolating data from Africa to New York.

The studies, done in Uganda, Kenya and South Africa, enrolled men who said they had sex with women, while New York’s highest-risk groups are men who have sex with men, men who inject drugs and people who have sex with those men.

Nonetheless, Dr. Frieden said, it is logical to assume that circumcision would offer protection in some types of gay sex.

A man’s risk from performing penetrative anal sex is about the same as his risk from vaginal sex, Dr. Frieden said, so circumcision would presumably confer the same protection as it did in the African trials.

The risk from receptive anal sex is five times higher, he said, and circumcision would obviously not protect those men. Oral sex is much less risky.

Also, cutting down infections among bisexual men — some of whom do not admit to female partners that they participate in gay sex — would protect women, he said.

Dr. Frieden said he thought health insurance companies might agree to pay for preventive circumcisions since they already covered them for infections and urinary blockage. City hospitals also offer the operation in those cases, Ms. Marengo said.

Peter Staley, a longtime AIDS activist and co-founder of ACT-UP New York, the Treatment Action Group and AIDSmeds.com, said he was “intrigued” by the idea of offering circumcisions but worried because those in the studies supporting it bore little relation to New York’s risk groups.

“Should we proceed when we don’t have hard data yet on the population here?” he asked. “On the other hand, if we wait the three years it would take to answer that question, how many will be infected in the meantime?”

Also, after reading many postings on gay Web sites about the Africa trials, he said he feared a backlash among black and Hispanic men to endorsements of circumcision from white public health officials or gay activists.

“I’m white, Frieden’s white,” he said. “It’s going to sound like white guys telling black and Hispanic guys to do something that would affect their manhood.”

Tokes Osubu, executive director of Gay Men of African Descent, a 21-year-old gay rights organization, agreed.

“There will always be conspiracy theorists,” he said. “That’s par for the course.”

He also said he thought circumcision was “not the answer to our problems” and doubted that it would lower infection rates.

Many black men who have sex with men, he said, already face discrimination, stigma and an inability to talk about their sex lives with family members and sometimes even with doctors.

“No amount of circumcision is going to change that,” he said.

Bric Bernas, manager of information and counseling for the Asian and Pacific Islander Coalition on H.I.V./AIDS, said his organization wanted to see studies done in the United States and among gay men before taking a position on the issue.

Circumcision is not common among Asian men, except those from Muslim countries and the Philippines, Mr. Bernas said, “and there might be cultural sensitivities around it.”

[Next Article in New York Region \(2 of 28\) »](#)

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 14:56:42 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi, Dawn. Looks like Helen Weiss is willing to do whatever we need her to do. I was going to ask her to cover just 1, 2 and 4. Make sense?
-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Helen Weiss [<mailto:Helen.Weiss@lshtm.ac.uk>]
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 14:42
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi Allan,

Yes, that would be OK.

Can I just check whether you wanted me to cover the results of 3 MC/HIV RCTs or whether someone else is doing this, and also whether someone else is going to touch on the public health issues we are now faced with (internationally)? No prob to do this - then i would do something like the following:

1. MC - global prevalence & determinants (religion, ethnicity, culture, medical)
2. Ecological, biological & observational evidence for association of MC & HIV
3. Summary of results of 3 RCTs of MC & HIV, including data on safety and risk compensation
4. Evidence that MC protects against other diseases, including GUD, cervical cancer, penile cancer
5. Evidence for MC & HIV transmission among MSM
6. Outline of public health issues for expanding MC services in Africa.

Could (just about) cover this in 35 minutes but it would be a bit rushed and I assume others might be covering some of this? Let me know what you think.

best wishes
helen

>>> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@cdc.gov> 02/04/2007 08:50 >>>

Dr. Weiss,

Thank you for agreeing to speak at the upcoming consultation. Our planning committee met on Friday to discuss the content of each

presentation, and we are in need of someone who would be able to present a review of the evidence for other (non-HIV) health effects of MC (e.g., reduction in other STDs, penile cancer, etc.). In our search for the appropriate person, Dr. Hayes suggested that you might be able to include such a discussion in your talk. We would of course increase the length of time allotted to 35 minutes to allow adequate time to cover this new material. This is clearly quite short notice, but might you be able to include such a discussion in your presentation?

Thank you for your assistance. We look forward to working with you.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 17:17
To: 'Helen Weiss'
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Excellent. Thank you. More details soon.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Helen Weiss [<mailto:Helen.Weiss@lshtm.ac.uk>]
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 17:16
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi Allan,

Yes, I would be happy to do this. Tim Mastro had mentioned this when I met him in Montreux.

best wishes
helen

>>> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@cdc.gov> 29/03/2007 14:12:30 >>>
Dr. Weiss,

I am coordinating preparations for CDC's upcoming consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US. We are pleased that you will be able to attend, and we would like to invite you to present an overview and background of MC and HIV prevention (Approx. 20 min, similar to the excellent presentation you gave at the recent WHIO meeting). We will send further details in the coming weeks if you

will
be able to present, but we wanted to contact you as early as possible
to
assess your availability.

Please contact me at your convenience to indicate whether you will be
able to present. We look forward to hearing from you and to your
participation in this consultation.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
(proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 13 Mar 2007 17:44:17 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Impact of male circumcision

The 2006 paper is at the top of the web page and the 2007 one down below.

Dawn K. Smith

Nagelkerke NJD, Moses S, de Vlas SJ and Bailey RC. Modeling the public health impact of male circumcision for HIV prevention in high prevalence areas in Africa. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 2007, 7:16, 13 march, 2007.

This paper is now available with open access at:

<http://www.biomedcentral.com/bmcinfectdis/>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 14:34:27 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: male circumcision consultation, Atlanta, April 26-27

FYI – we can't keep this agenda static for more than a few hours...
-A

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 09:07
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: male circumcision consultation, Atlanta, April 26-27

Since Kevin F won't be able to make it, let's have Rob do the welcome, and I will deliver the charge to the consultants. I'd like to moderate the Thursday morning session, noting that Peter is presenting in that session.

Thanks for your good work on this.

It's great that Ron Gray will attend.

Tim

From: Burgess, Elizabeth (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 8:57 AM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Burgess, Elizabeth (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: male circumcision consultation, Atlanta, April 26-27

Tim, unfortunately, Dr. Fenton will be in Houston on April 26th.

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 8:40 AM
To: Burgess, Elizabeth (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Fenton, Kevin (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Fenton, Kevin (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Cagle, Chris (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: male circumcision consultation, Atlanta, April 26-27

Liz,

DHAP would like to invite Dr. Fenton to deliver the welcoming comments at our consultation on male circumcision and HIV prevention to be held April 26-27 at a downtown Atlanta hotel. Dr. Fenton would be on the agenda, Thursday, April 26, at 8:30am for about 10 minutes. We would prepare talking points.

Could you please advise if Dr. Fenton's schedule would allow for this?

Thanks in advance.

Tim

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
CAPT, USPHS
Acting Chief, HIV Incidence and Case Surveillance Branch
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
1600 Clifton Road, Mailstop D-21
Atlanta, GA 30333

Tel: 404-639-0900
Fax: 404-639-0897
E-mail: TMastro@cdc.gov

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Tim

Timothy D. Mastro, MD

CAPT, USPHS

Acting Chief, HIV Incidence and Case Surveillance Branch

Deputy Director for Science

Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

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1600 Clifton Road, Mailstop D-21

Atlanta, GA 30333

Tel: 404-639-0900

Fax: 404-639-0897

E-mail: TMastro@cdc.gov <<mailto:TMastro@cdc.gov>>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 4 Apr 2007 20:43:55 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Male Circumcision Meeting

FYI
-A

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 16:42
To: Haban, Nancy (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Mast, Gerri E. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Larkin, Theresa (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Studer, Craig (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Workman, Deborah (CDC/OCOO/PGO)
Subject: RE: Male Circumcision Meeting

Thank you all for your extra efforts to make this happen. This will be an important, high-profile meeting for CDC and important for HIV prevention.

Best,
Tim

From: Haban, Nancy (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 4:36 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Mast, Gerri E. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Larkin, Theresa (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Studer, Craig (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Workman, Deborah (CDC/OCOO/PGO)
Subject: Male Circumcision Meeting

Tim and Peter - I have just concluded a conversation with PGO regarding the contract for the above meeting. There is one pending issue related to security that PGO is still working to finalize. Deborah Workman will not be in the office until next Monday - but according to her conversation with the vendor, they may go ahead and secure the rooms with the hotel and as soon as the vendor lets her know about the security, she will cut the award on Monday. Also, the contractor indicated to Deborah that if the award was cut on Monday, they would not have a problem getting the required activities done in time for the meeting. So - it sounds like everything is a go for the meeting. I want to thank Deborah and Gerri for really going the extra mile to get this accomplished. Your willingness to get the job done is sincerely appreciated. It is great to be able to work with folks like you!!!! EPMO will continue to try to minimize these kinds of circumstances where we and PGO have to handle the seemingly impossible - but when they do occur - it is really good to have people like Deborah and Gerri that are able to make things happen. Thank you.....

ndh

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 25 Apr 2007 15:46:18 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Tracey, Angie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC Consultation Messages
Attachments: Circumcision CONSULTATION messages 4 20 2007.doc, Draft Messages Post Consultation 4 20 2007.doc, Circumcision Q&A 070418.doc

Hi, all.

I checked in with Bob and Angie about the status of the message boards, etc. They were waiting for feedback from us on these documents. If we can provide them with comments ASAP today, they will revise so that we can distribute to appropriate staff. Who do we think should get them?

Thanks.
-Allan

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 17:56
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Tracey, Angie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC Consultation Messages

Peter and Dawn,

Bob and Angie have been working hard on the messaging documents. Attached are the most recent iterations. Pay particular attention if you can to the Q&A document: It's a good start but I think still could benefit from some refinement. Comments welcome to me or directly to Angie Tracey.

-Allan

From: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 14:18
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC Consultation Messages

FYI...

Bob Kohmescher
Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (A43)
1600 Clifton Rd NE
Atlanta, GA 30333

(404) 639-1914
(404) 639-5260 (fax)
Corp 8/Rm 5057

From: Smith, Jill (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 2:17 PM
To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Tracey, Angie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC Consultation Messages

Bob/Angie/Peter:

We have updated our circumcision message box to incorporate information about the upcoming consultation (specifically, see 6:00 message). I also have attached some Q&A responses that may be helpful, especially immediately after the consultation if we are to get media questions.

From a media standpoint, we feel like these documents will answer most of the media questions. I wanted to share these with you as you guys put together your Q&A for partners or others. Please let us know if you have any corrections or suggestions.

As additional background, we pulled some information on advocate positions on circumcision. I will send those in a separate e-mail, fyi.

Thank you,
Jill Smith
Office of Communication
404-639-2863

There Are Significant Differences in U.S. to Be Considered Before Recommendations Can Be Made

- Africa & U.S. experiencing very different HIV epidemics
 - Africa – generalized epidemic (e.g., prev. over 20% in S. Africa), w/ most transmission through heterosexual sex
 - U.S. – epidemic primarily among MSM w/ a general prevalence < 0.1%; only 15% of male HIV dx due to male-female sex (2005)
- African trials do not provide data on how circumcision impacts most common routes of transmission in U.S. – male to male & male to female
- Circumcision rates vary among U.S. men, but are generally high
 - 77% of men overall in a 1992 nat'l survey (Recent data show 82% of MSM at 7 gay pride events, 2006)
 - Since 1999, AAP no longer recommended infant circumc. (neutral stance); Reaffirmed position in 2005
- Degree to which circumc. can help reduce trans. in U.S. will depend on % of heterosexual men at high risk who are not circumcised (& ultimately whether proves to reduce MSM transmission), willingness to be circumcised & whether approach can be effectively integrated w/ other prevention strategies
 - Recent CDC data suggest some high-risk MSM – especially black MSM - in U.S. would consider integrating circum into HIV prevention strategy if proven effective for this population.

Circumcision Can Play Important Role in Helping to Reduce Heterosexual HIV Transmission in Some Areas of the World (if Combined w/Other Effective Prevention Strategies)

- 3 large, randomized trials indicate roughly 50-60% reduction in female-to-male HIV transmission
 - Still do not know if circumc. has protective effect for men's female partners or MSM
- New WHO/UNAIDS recs (supporting MC as part of comprehensive HIV prevention programs for men at het risk) are critical step forward
- But they also highlight important challenges that remain as individual countries consider incorporating circumcision into HIV prevention efforts:
 - How to best integrate with other prevention methods
 - Cultural and safety concerns
 - Need for training, equipment, monitoring of circumcision programs
 - *OGAC can best address questions about how M.C. will be incorporated into USG programs internationally*

CDC Circumcision CONSULTATION Messages DRAFT 4/20/2007

CDC Consultation is an Important First Step in Evaluating Potential Role of Circumcision in U.S.

- We are working with our public health partners to evaluate the potential value, risks and feasibility of circumcision to prevent HIV in the U.S.
- As a key first step, we are holding a consultation that will explore the role of circumcision - at a public health level - in preventing HIV transmission in the U.S.
 - Bringing together broad range of experts – including public health practitioners, major medical associations [insert other examples] and community representatives...
 - To analyze the existing research and its application to the United States
 - Consultation will begin to explore
 - best scientific evidence & how translates or not to U.S. pops at risk
 - examination of multiple factors that would play a role (can't consider in a vacuum): potential cost-effectiveness, cultural and safety concerns, integration with prevention methods
 - additional research needed to guide policy
 - Circumcision guidance on a public health level in the U.S. is a complex issue (9:00 message) and there are challenges to be considered (12:00 message)
- Outcome: This consultation will assimilate the best available science to guide CDC and other partners as we determine what public health guidance is appropriate regarding circumcision—and what research is needed.
 - CDC plans to publish a report from this consultation in a peer-reviewed journal in the coming months.
 - Other organizations and policy makers will be able to use this information as a basis for decisions moving forward.
- While premature to discuss exact next steps, CDC will work to outline add. research needs in this area and provide public health guidance on MC within the coming year (under what circumstances MC should be considered as an HIV prevention strategy based on current data).

CDC Continues to Support Combination of Evidence-Based Prevention Strategies

- Because no HIV prevention strategy is 100% effective – any potential use of MC must be coupled w/other proven strategies (to ensure benefits are not outweighed by increased risk)
- As CDC moves forward in determining what role circumcision may play from a public health perspective, individual men may wish to consider circumcision as an add'l HIV prevention measure, but must recognize that circumcision:
 - Has only proven effective in reducing HIV risk of infection through insertive vaginal sex
 - Confers only partial protection and should be considered only in conjunction with other proven prevention measures
 - Does carry risks and costs that must be considered in addition to potential benefits
- (For questions about prev. trial design) As CDC's research on other prevention methods (e.g., PrEP) proceeds, will work closely w/ host countries to ensure trial services are consistent with both the WHO/UNAIDS guidance and country-specific recommendations, which are yet to be determined
 - Where circumcision is recommended, will ensure participants have access to safe and effective services

Supplemental Messages AFTER THE CONSULTATION
DRAFT April 20, 2007

What next? What was accomplished?

- **As we move forward, CDC and other policymakers will draw upon the evidence presented at this consultation to determine what public health guidance is appropriate regarding circumcision in U.S. and what additional research is needed.**
 - This was a critical step in examining the body of scientific evidence on circumcision as an HIV prevention strategy and how these data may or may not be applicable for high risk populations in the U.S
 - Also allowed us to explore with community partners and scientific and medical colleagues the multiple factors that would play a role in any use of circumcision—from cost-effectiveness to cultural and safety concerns and integration of this strategy with other prevention methods.
 - Consultation report will provide critical information to guide decision-making:
 - Important that we were able to capture this broad range of information from the consultation
 - CDC plans to publish a report from this consultation in a peer-reviewed journal in the coming months.
 - CDC and other policy makers will be able to use this information as a basis for decisions moving forward.
 - We also came out of this consultation direction from experts on future research needs
 - [examples of research need]
- **(As we work to fill these gaps, CDC will continue to support a combination of approaches to reduce HIV infection, supported by the best available science. (3:00)**

Based on what you heard today, what would you anticipate recommendations will be and what will the process be moving forward?

- Because of the complexity of these issues, it's important to move forward with caution:
 - From individual perspective, data are obviously most clear for uncircumcised men at high risk from heterosexual sex. For these men (go to 3:00 recommendation)
 - Heard varying opinions—and interpretations-- as to how data apply to women or MSM that will have to be carefully considered

- And on a population level, number of factors must be considered in outlining appropriate guidance:
 - Given impact on epidemic will be less in U.S., cost-effectiveness must be considered
 - How to ensure MC works in combination with other proven strategies
 - Acceptability to populations at risk
- While premature to speculate on exact next steps, CDC will work to outline additional research needs in this area and provide public health guidance on male circumcision within the coming year (under what circumstances MC should be considered as an HIV prevention strategy based on current data).
- Additionally, we will continue and expand key CDC research on:
 - List a few key areas:
 -

(As we work to fill these gaps, CDC will continue to support a combination of approaches to reduce HIV infection, supported by the best available science. (3:00))

If asked about specific mutilation or religious concerns –

- CDC's role is to provide best possible public health guidance, based on science available.
- We of course recognize that HIV prevention does not occur in a vacuum—and that range of cultural, social, and religious beliefs will impact the acceptability of circumcision for disease prevention.
- That's why we included a wide range of perspectives in consultation today.
- Available data and perspectives from communities at risk on all of these issues will be considered as we move forward.

[Premature to speculate on what guidance will be—but our role will be to provide guidance from a public health perspective on documented risks and benefits]

Other Statement:

We now have credible, scientific evidence about circumcision's proven ability to help prevent this devastating disease for some populations. When we know there are prevention strategies that work, we certainly want to get that information into the hands of providers and public health practitioners; we do this through public health guidance.

[back to: CDC will draw upon the evidence presented at this consultation to determine what public health guidance is needed regarding circumcision.]

Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Issues Brief/ Questions and Answers

April 18, 2007

Background

The results from three research trials in Africa have revealed compelling data about the effectiveness of male circumcision in female to male transmission of HIV. Numerous international consultations have been held to analyze the findings and to determine policy recommendations as a result. On March 28th, the World Health Organization, WHO, and UNAIDS announced their summary of these findings and their subsequent policy and programmatic recommendations. They conclude that the effectiveness of circumcision in HIV prevention associated with female to male transmission has been proven and that policies and programs should be put into effect that consider circumcision as a part of comprehensive HIV prevention efforts. It is important to note that the trials in Africa were conducted in populations where HIV transmission is predominantly heterosexual, with very high HIV prevalence, and low prevalence of circumcision. This population profile differs significantly from the US population where transmission also occurs among men who have sex with men who were not included in the original trials and for whom it remains unknown whether there is any HIV prevention benefit from circumcision. Additionally, in contrast, the US has low HIV prevalence and high circumcision rates.

Their recommendations include: identifying countries with high, HIV prevalence, high heterosexual transmission rates, and low circumcision rates to promote this intervention for maximum impact. . *(Note: Circumcision has been performed for thousands of years as part of the culture of indigenous people in such countries as Australia, the Pacific Islands, the Middle East, Africa. The US is one of the few countries in the world that practices routine circumcision of infant boys.)*

Applying the results of these studies and the WHO recommendations to the US raises significant policy issues around limitations of the studies to heterosexual transmission, application to men who have sex with men, implication to women who have sex with men, access to safe medical procedures, subsidies for the procedures, and wound healing. Additionally, implementation of such policies would have significant communications implications causing WHO/UNAIDS to recommend additional funds and consideration of producing and disseminating clearly articulated information to the public and target audiences

Circumcision is not an issue without controversy. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) for instance, agrees that while circumcision has some medical benefit, the benefits are not sufficient to make any further recommendations. Organizations like, "Mothers Against Circumcision" consider it to be child abuse.

On April 26-27, 2007, CDC will be holding a consultation (Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infections and Other Health Consequences in the

United States) to review the science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences, review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention and to gain expert advice on potential programmatic steps.

Recent Announcements

3/28/07

“UN Recommends Male Circumcision to Prevent HIV”

The World Health Organization, WHO, and UNAIDS endorsed male circumcision as an additional method of preventing the heterosexual transmission of HIV. The decision was based upon data from three recent studies that indicated a 50-60% reduction in HIV infection of circumcised men who have sex with women. WHO and UNAIDS further indicated that countries, such as Africa, where heterosexual transmission is the predominant mode of transmission, should increase access to circumcision and particularly target young, sexually active men. Condoms and regular HIV testing are still recommended as well. They indicated that 5.7 million sub-Saharan African men could avoid HIV infection and 3 million people would be spared death over the next two decades. They further recommended that countries consider ways to subsidize the cost associated with the procedure. (summarized from Reuters (3/28/07: Laura MacInnis)

Research Background and Summary of Findings

Two of the three research trials on HIV transmission and risk reduction associated with circumcised males were conducted in Kisumu, Kenya and Rakai District, Uganda. The results revealed a 53% reduction in HIV transmission from circumcised men in Kisumu and 51% reduction in transmission of HIV in the Rakai District. “These results support findings published in 2005 from the South Africa Orange Farm Intervention Trial, sponsored by the French National Agency for Research on AIDS, which demonstrated at least a 60% reduction in HIV infection among men who were circumcised.” (WHO/UNAIDS)

On December 13, 2006, the National Institutes of Health, NIH, announced that the two trials in Kenya and Rakai District would be stopped based upon recommendations of the Data Safety and Monitoring Board.

On March 6-8, 2007, an international consultation was conducted by WHO and UNAIDS to review these findings and to make subsequent recommendations.. (*“New Data on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention: Policy and Programme Implications”*- WHO/UNAIDS, March 28, 2007)

Conclusion: The research findings indicate that male circumcision does reduce the sexual transmission of HIV from women to men. Three randomized, controlled studies, indicate that circumcision reduced the risk to men of acquiring HIV by approximately 60% and has been proven beyond doubt according to WHO/UNAIDS. It should also be noted that circumcision does not provide complete protection against HIV transmission and is considered an additional strategy to “reduce” transmission rather than a

replacement for other interventions such as abstinence and condom use. “In all three randomized controlled trials, HIV incidence was considerably lower in the intervention (circumcised men) than in the control group (uncircumcised men), but nevertheless remained high overall (0.7 to 1.0 per 100 person-years in circumcised men). This high incidence persisted in spite of intensive safer sex counseling, condom provision and the management of sexually transmitted infections. This underlines the need to strengthen comprehensive HIV prevention programmes even further.” (WHO/UNAIDS). It is also not known whether circumcision has any affect on transmission from circumcised men to women or between men who have sex with men.

Meetings and Consultations

Regional Consultation on male circumcision and HIV prevention (Nairobi, November 20-21, 2006)

Strategies and approaches to male circumcision programming (Geneva, December 5-6, 2006)

Perspectives from social science on male circumcision for HIV prevention (Durban, January 18-19, 2007)

WHO/UNAIDS Consultation on new data on male circumcision and HIV prevention: Policy and Programme implications (March 6-7, 2007)

CDC Consultation- Public Health issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns (April, 2007- On April 26-27, 2007)

Policy Issues

Conclusions and Recommendations from WHO/UNAIDS Consultation

1. The research is compelling
2. Male circumcision does not provide complete protection against HIV

3. Correct communication and messages on male circumcision are critical (men, newborns, false sense of security with high-risk behavior, access to proper care, healing periods, different from female mutilation)
4. The socio-cultural context should inform male circumcision programming (religions)
5. Human rights, legal and ethical principles must guide service delivery (safety, informed consent, etc.)
6. The gender implications of male circumcision as an HIV prevention method must be addressed
7. Programmes should be targeted to maximize the public health benefit (areas where male circumcision is low, heterosexual transmission high and populations at risk)
8. Health services need to be strengthened to increase access to safe male circumcision services (skilled professionals, access, etc.)
9. Additional resources should be mobilized to finance the expansion of safe male circumcision services (subsidies for circumcision, communications, etc.)
10. Promoting circumcision for HIV-positive men is not recommended
11. Research is needed to guide programme implementation

WHO/UNAIDS Communications Recommendations

1. Strategies need to be clear and consistent as part of comprehensive HIV prevention
2. Messages developed to ensure proper counseling about limitations and effective prevention
3. Messages should include info on wound healing (abstinence for at least 6 weeks)
4. Messages should be culturally sensitive, draw on local languages, etc.

CDC Consultation

On April 26-27, 2007, CDC will be holding a consultation (Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infections and Other Health Consequences in the United States) to review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences, review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention and to gain expert advice on potential programmatic steps.

Questions and Answers

Previous Research

1. What were the findings of the three research trials?

Two research trials on HIV transmission and risk reduction associated with circumcised males were conducted in Kisumu, Kenya and Rakai District, Uganda. The results revealed a 53% reduction in HIV transmission from circumcised men in Kisumu and 51% reduction in transmission of HIV in the Rakai District. "These results support findings published in 2005 from the South Africa Orange Farm Intervention Trial, sponsored by the French National Agency for Research on AIDS, which demonstrated at least a 60% reduction in HIV infection among men who were circumcised." (WHO/UNAIDS)

On December 13, 2006, the National Institutes of Health, NIH, announced that the two trials in Kenya and Rakai District would be stopped based upon recommendations of the Data Safety and Monitoring Board.

Conclusion: The research findings indicate that male circumcision does reduce the sexual transmission of HIV from women to men. These three randomized, controlled studies indicate that circumcision reduced the risk to men of acquiring HIV by approximately 60% and has been proven beyond doubt according to WHO/UNAIDS. It should also be noted that circumcision does not provide complete protection to HIV transmission and is yet a strategy to “reduce” transmission rather than a replacement for other interventions such as abstinence and condom use. “In all three randomized controlled trials, HIV incidence was considerably lower in the intervention (circumcised men) than in the control group (uncircumcised men), but nevertheless remained high overall (0.7 to 1.0 per 100 person-years in circumcised men). This high incidence persisted in spite of intensive safer sex counseling, condom provision and the management of sexually transmitted infections. This underlines the need to strengthen comprehensive HIV prevention programmes even further.” (WHO/UNAIDS). It is also not known whether circumcision has any affect on transmission from circumcised men to women or between men who have sex with men.

2. What are the statistics on circumcision in the US? Around the world in high prevalence countries?

In a national probability sample of adults in 1992, the National Health and Social Life Survey found that 77% of men reported being circumcised including 81% of white men, 65% of black men, and 54% of Hispanic men [19]. It is important to note that reported circumcision status may be subject to misclassification. In a study of adolescents, only 69% of circumcised and 65% of uncircumcised young men correctly identified their circumcision status as verified by physical exam [20].

According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999 and the overall proportion of newborns circumcised was stable from 1979 to 1999 [21]. Notably, the proportion of black newborns circumcised rose over this reporting period (58% to 64%), while the proportion of white infants circumcised remained stable (66%). In addition, the proportion of newborns who were circumcised in the Midwest increased over the 20-year period from 74% in 1979 to 81% in 1999, while the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased from 64% in 1979 to 37% in 1999. In another survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), circumcision rates increased from 48% during 1988-1991 to 61% during 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black (CDC Fact Sheet)

3. Do these studies indicate that HIV transmission risk is reduced for women having sex with men who are circumcised?

No. It is also not known whether circumcision has any affect on transmission from circumcised men to women or between men who have sex with men.

4. Studies were conducted in Africa and not the US. Given the high rates of circumcision in the US, will these findings be applicable to the US?

The conclusions drawn by the studies that circumcision reduces the risk of transmission of HIV from a woman to a circumcised man are relevant to the US. The purpose of CDC's upcoming consultation is to evaluate the results of the three studies and to discuss their policy relevance and develop recommendations that are specific to the US. These studies were relevant to heterosexual transmission of HIV between men and women.

5. How does this apply to men who have sex with men?

At this time, no conclusions related to this population can be determined from these studies.

6. Is there any difference between circumcision at birth versus circumcision as an adult male? Any additional issues related to adult male circumcision?

All three studies performed circumcision of adult males. No man who had been circumcised as an infant was included. The studies, therefore, did not draw a conclusion between the effectiveness of circumcision at birth versus as an adult. There are concerns raised that adult male circumcision would require further data and study on healing timeframes from the surgery prior to sexual activity without the added risk of lesions and skin perforations. These studies do not address the risk to women or between men who have sex with men.

7. Is circumcision considered complete protection from HIV transmission?

No. It should be noted that circumcision does not provide complete protection to HIV transmission and is a strategy to "reduce" transmission rather than a replacement for other interventions such as abstinence and condom use. According to WHO/UNAIDS, "In all three randomized controlled trials, HIV incidence was considerably lower in the intervention (circumcised men) than in the control group (uncircumcised men), but nevertheless remained high overall (0.7 to 1.0 per 100 person-years in circumcised men). This high incidence persisted in spite of intensive safer sex counseling, condom provision and the management of sexually transmitted infections. This underlines the need to strengthen comprehensive HIV prevention programmes even further." (WHO/UNAIDS). It is also not known whether circumcision has any affect on transmission from circumcised men to women or between men who have sex with men. According to WHO, studies are ongoing to determine whether male circumcision affects women but they indicate that the reduction in male transmission would ultimately impact women. Thus far, the studies have indicated minimal impact on men who have sex with men and are circumcised.

8. *What is the position of WHO/UNAIDS on these findings?*

On March 28, 2007, WHO and UNAIDS endorsed male circumcision as way to prevent heterosexually acquired HIV. WHO estimates that 5.7 million sub-Saharan African men could avoid HIV transmission with 3 million being spared death over the next two decades if circumcision was implemented. WHO recommends that countries provide the surgery free of charge or at minimal cost to assure access to care.

9. *How are other US medical groups implementing these findings? (i.e., American Medical Association, Pediatricians)*

According the American Academy for Pediatrics, “After analysis of almost 40 years of available medical research on circumcision, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) issued new recommendations today stating that the benefits are not significant enough for the AAP to recommend circumcision as a routine procedure. The new policy statement was published in this month's issue of Pediatrics, the journal of the AAP.

Circumcision is not essential to a child’s well-being at birth, even though it does have some potential medical benefits. These benefits are not compelling enough to warrant the AAP to recommend routine newborn circumcision. Instead, we encourage parents to discuss the benefits and risks of circumcision with their pediatrician, and then make an informed decision about what is in the best interest of their child,” says Carole Lannon, M.D., MPH, FAAP, chair of the AAP’s Task Force on Circumcision.

The policy concluded, however, that it is legitimate for parents to take into account cultural, religious and ethnic traditions, in addition to medical factors, when making this decision. It states that to make an informed choice, parents of all male infants should be given accurate information and be provided the opportunity to discuss this decision with their pediatrician.

For the first time in AAP circumcision policy history, the new recommendations also indicate that if parents decide to circumcise their infant, it is essential that pain relief be provided.” (AAP Website)

There are also advocacy groups on both sides of the issue and it has economic, religious and access to care policy issues associated with it. There are organizations that consider the practice “barbaric” while others associate it with female mutilation practices.

Consultation

1. What is the position of CDC on the research findings?

“Male circumcision has been associated with a lower risk for HIV infection in international observational studies and in three randomized, controlled clinical trials. Male circumcision could also reduce male-to-female transmission of HIV to a lesser extent. It has also been associated with a number of other health benefits. While there are risks to male circumcision, serious complications are rare. Accordingly, male circumcision, together with other prevention interventions, may play an important role in HIV prevention in settings similar to the clinical trials.

Male circumcision may also have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. With the results of three clinical trials showing that male circumcision decreases the risk for HIV infection, CDC is undertaking additional research and consultation to evaluate the potential value, risks, and feasibility of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention in the U.S.

As CDC proceeds with the development of public health recommendations for the U.S., individual men may wish to consider circumcision as an additional HIV prevention measure, but must recognize that circumcision 1) does carry risks and costs that must be considered in addition to potential benefits; 2) has only proven effective in reducing the risk of infection through insertive vaginal sex; and 3) confers only partial protection and should be considered only in conjunction with other proven prevention measures (abstinence, mutual monogamy, reducing number of sex partners, and correct and consistent condom use).” (CDC Fact Sheet)

2. What is the purpose of the consultation? How does this consultation differ from international consultations on this topic?

Previous consultations focused on the international impact of the data and results with a focus on Africa. Strategic recommendations from WHO/UNAIDS included identifying countries with high rates of HIV transmission, low rates of male circumcision and mostly heterosexual transmission as opportunities for impact on transmission rates.

The purpose of the CDC consultation is to analyze the results of the three studies, how they can be applied or adapted to the US and the policy implications of these recommendations. During the consultation, participants will review the science, review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention, and provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC.

3. Will CDC be making policy recommendations for change as a result of these findings?

One of the purposes of the consultation is to determine whether, in the opinion of experts, there is sufficient data to make recommendations. [NEED MORE TEXT]

General Questions

- 1. Are men who undergo circumcision to reduce their risk of HIV more likely to practice unsafe sex?***

The answer to this question cannot be determined from the three studies; however, this is an issue that may need further study. [NEED A BETTER ANSWER]

- 2. Are there any groups that oppose male circumcision? Why?***

Yes. There are groups that believe that the practice is “barbaric” and has little medical value while others associate it with female mutilation practices. Mothers Against Circumcision associated it with child abuse. Circumcision has been conducted for a variety of reasons: religious (Islam, Judaism), cosmetic, and medical. (prevention of penile inflammation and problems such as meatitis, balanitis and inflammation of the foreskin, UTIs))

- 3. What are the religious implications/ barriers to policies related to circumcision?***

Circumcision has long been a recommended practice by both Islam and Judaism. The majority of Americans are Christian and the major denominations (Catholic, Southern Baptist) see it as an option and not a requirement based upon the scriptures of the New Testament. Unrelated to religious implications, there are individuals and organizations that consider the practice, “child abuse” and some that associate it with female mutilation practices. (still working on this)

- 4. Should research be conducted in men who have sex with men related to circumcision?***

One of the purposes of the consultation is to suggest needed research and the advisability of conducting this research.

- 5. Will there be any further studies conducted?***

One purpose of the consultation is to determine the need for additional research.

- 7. Does Medicaid cover male circumcision in the US?***

In a 1995 review, 61% of circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant. Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary (CDC Fact Sheet)

- 7. If there is inadequate funding for adult circumcision, will this only be a strategy for those who can afford the procedure?***

The cost-benefits and access to care policy issues will be discussed at the upcoming CDC consultation.

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 8 Mar 2007 00:31:50 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC
Attachments: 1471-2490-7-4.pdf

New MC article.

Lead author is a urologist at UNC

BMC Urol. 2007 Mar 2;7(1):4 [Epub ahead of print]

Prevalence of complications of male circumcision in Anglophone Africa: a systematic review.

Muula AS, Prozesky IIW, Mataya RH, Ikechebelu JI.

Free full text <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2490/7/4>

ABSTRACT: BACKGROUND: There is growing evidence that male circumcision (MC) prevents heterosexual acquisition of HIV by males in sub-Saharan Africa, the region of the world heavily affected by the HIV pandemic. While there is growing support for wide-spread availability and accessibility of MC in Africa, there is limited discussion about the prevalence of physical complications of male circumcision on the continent. **METHODS:** A systematic literature search and review of articles in indexed journals and conference abstracts was conducted to collect and analyze prevalence of complications of MC in Anglophone sub-Saharan Africa. Information extracted included: indications for MC, complications reported, age of patients and category of circumcisers. **RESULTS:** There were 8 articles and 2 abstracts that were suitable for the analysis. The studies were not strictly comparable as some reported on a wide range of complications while others reported just a limited list of possible complications. Prevalence of reported complications of MC ranged from 0% to 50.1%. Excluding the study with 50.1%, which was on a series of haemophilia patients, the next highest prevalence of complications was 24.1%. Most of the complications were minor. There was no firm evidence to suggest that MCs performed by physician surgeons were associated with lower prevalence of complications when compared with non-physician health professionals. **CONCLUSIONS:** The available data are inadequate to obtain a reasonable assessment of the prevalence of complications of MC in sub-Saharan Africa. Some of the available studies however report potentially significant prevalence of complications, though of minor clinical significance. This should be considered as public health policy makers consider whether to scale-up MC as an HIV preventative measure. Decision for the scale-up will depend on a careful cost-benefit assessment of which physical complications are certainly an important aspect. There is need for standardized reporting of complications of male circumcision.

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Prevalence of complications of male circumcision in Anglophone Africa: a systematic review

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Prevalence of complications of male circumcision in Anglophone Africa: a systematic review

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Abstract

Background

There is growing evidence that male circumcision (MC) prevents heterosexual acquisition of HIV by males in sub-Saharan Africa, the region of the world heavily affected by the HIV pandemic. While there is growing support for wide-spread availability and accessibility of MC in Africa, there is limited discussion about the prevalence of physical complications of male circumcision on the continent.

Methods

A systematic literature search and review of articles in indexed journals and conference abstracts was conducted to collect and analyze prevalence of complications of MC in Anglophone sub-Saharan Africa. Information extracted included: indications for MC, complications reported, age of patients and category of circumcisers.

Results

There were 8 articles and 2 abstracts that were suitable for the analysis. The studies were not strictly comparable as some reported on a wide range of complications while others reported just a limited list of possible complications. Prevalence of reported complications of MC ranged from 0% to 50.1%. Excluding the study with 50.1%, which was on a series of haemophilia patients, the next highest prevalence of complications was 24.1%. Most of the complications were minor. There was no firm evidence to suggest that MCs performed by physician surgeons were associated with lower prevalence of complications when compared with non-physician health professionals.

Conclusions

The available data are inadequate to obtain a reasonable assessment of the prevalence of complications of MC in sub-Saharan Africa. Some of the available studies however report potentially significant prevalence of complications, though of minor clinical significance. This should be considered as public health policy makers consider whether to scale-up MC as an HIV preventative measure. Decision for the scale-up will depend on a careful cost-benefit assessment of which physical complications are certainly an important aspect. There is need for standardized reporting of complications of male circumcision.

Background

The HIV pandemic is among the most critical public health challenges facing the African continent. Observational studies and three randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have reported that male circumcision can prevent HIV acquisition heterosexually by men [1-3]. Williams et al [4] have conducted mathematical models showing that wide-scale implementation of MC has the potential of reducing 2.0 million (1.1-3.8 million) new HIV infections in the first ten years of implementation in sub-Saharan Africa. Several studies have reported on the acceptability of male circumcision for the prevention of HIV in sub-Saharan Africa [5-7]. In a review, Westercamp and Bailey report that there is sufficient research evidence to suggest that male circumcision is acceptable in sub-Saharan Africa for the prevention of HIV transmission [8]. However, Mills and Siegfried have suggested a "cautious optimism" approach towards male circumcision [9]. There is on-going debate as to whether male circumcision should be routinely performed for the purpose of preventing heterosexual transmission of HIV in sub-Saharan Africa [10-15]. While the literature has focused on the role of MC in the prevention of transmission of HIV in sub-Saharan Africa, we argue that there has not been commensurate interest in the estimation of safety and complications potentially associated with any scale-up in MC in Africa. In conducting this review, we were motivated to find out the available evidence regarding the reported prevalence of complications of MC in Africa. We therefore conducted a review of the published literature to attempt to answer the question: What has been the reported prevalence of complications of MC in sub-Saharan Africa? A secondary question is: Who is conducting MC in Africa?

Methods

Search strategy and selection criteria

We searched for all reports in peer-reviewed journals that reported on complications of male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa and abstracts from the International Conference on AIDS (2004 and 2006). Journal databases searched included: African Journals Online (AJOL), MEDLINE, OVID, Google Scholar and Web of Science. The search period was limited to 1980 and August 2006. We used the key word: "circumcision". Studies were included for analysis if they reported on any series of patients in Anglophone Africa on

whom male circumcision had been conducted and complications reported. ASM, RM and JII participated in the data collection. Data abstracted included: author details, location of study, number of patients circumcised in the reported series, ages of patients, inclusion criteria for procedure, prevalence of complications, nature of complications reported, period of follow-up for reporting of complications, indications for circumcision and who performed the circumcisions. Only studies published in English were included, irrespective of study design. Our method used applicable recommendations from the Meta-Analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (MOOSE) guidelines as reported by Stroup et al [16].

Results

Clinical characteristics of cases

Eight articles and two conference abstracts were considered suitable for the review. The papers reported on studies conducted in Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Tanzania. Table 1 reports on indications reported for MC, exclusion criteria of cases, length of period of follow-up and the range of complications reported, which included zero reporting. Zero reporting means type of complication was reported as having never occurred.

Studies included randomized controlled clinical trials and reports of routine clinical work. The inclusion and exclusion criteria in the series of cases were diverse with the RCTs reporting stringent inclusion criteria of cases while the routine series of patients were generally less restrictive. The lists of complications reported in studies were different. The period of follow-up to document complications were variable ranging from just immediate post-operative up to a year. 4 of the 10 studies did not report follow-up time.

Complications of male circumcision

Table 2 reports on the total number of cases in a series group, age of patients, categories of circumciser and prevalence of complications reported. The prevalence of complication reported ranged from 0% to 50.1% in a series of hemophiliacs. Different professional categories performed circumcision. There were equivocal reports on the comparison of complications between circumcisions performed by nurses versus those performed by physicians.

Association between category of circumciser and complications

Several studies reported high prevalence of complications when circumcision was conducted by untrained personnel. Osuigwe et al [23] reported that midwives were associated with 30.6% complications compared to physicians at 14.5%. However, physicians at a university teaching hospital were associated with fewer complications compared to private and mission hospital physicians. The series of cases by Magoha [26] and Manji [25] were operated on by one physician in each case and no comparisons could

be made about the skill of the circumciser. Auvert et al study [20] used general physicians for all their subjects. Okeke et al [19] reported more complications with nurses compared to physicians. However, the difference was not statistically significant.

Discussion

There is limited published literature on the complications of male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa. The available evidence regarding the prevalence of complications in male circumcision is conflicting, with some studies reporting significantly high complications prevalence and at least one study reporting no complications. It is plausible to consider that a study that may not have reported a single complication may indeed have none to report or that complications may have been considered so minor as to be 'worth' reporting. In case of complications that may be experienced at home and there are significant barriers to access medical care, it is conceivable to expect that many patients will not present to health facilities for care following minor to moderate complications. Another explanation for no report of complications may be that the patients may have presented for management of complications at a different facility from where they obtained circumcision.

In virtually all the studies reviewed, the majority of complications reported were of minor clinical consequence. The exception was the study by Shittu and Shokunbi [24] which reported on a special group of patients i.e. hemophiliacs, with extremely high risk of bleeding from minimal trauma. The interpretation of prevalence of complications in this study must be made within these special circumstances. Other than the report of bleeding, no other complication was reported. It is unlikely though that bleeding was the only complication experienced; rather it would seem that this was the main focus of the study.

Reports on complications of male circumcision also differ in so far as the time after the circumcision that complications were reported i.e. early versus late complications. Yegane et al [27] for instance have reported on possible late complications of MC which include granuloma formation, penile rotation and secondary chordee [27]. In some of the studies that were reviewed in our study like that of Bailey et al [17] where patients were followed up for complications for 8 days, long term complications such as keloid formation may have been missed. Bailey et al's randomized controlled study however was of much longer duration and the assessment of long term complications was possible, but not reported. In general, most of the studies we reviewed reported on bleeding and infections only. Auvert's et al study however had reported an extensive list of possible complications and included zero reporting. Of the complications reported by Auvert et al, 13 (31.7%) reported pain, excessive bleeding (15%), infection (5%), damage to penis (5%), 1 anesthetic complications and 9 complaints of problems with appearance.

The prevalence of complications of MC in North America has been reported in the range of 0.2% to 0.5% [28]. However, the true prevalence of complications is not known as ways of ascertaining these will always underestimate the true prevalence [28]. Ben Chaim et al [29] have reported on series of 19,478 male infant circumcision conducted in Israel, of which only 66 (1.3%) recorded complications. This study reported fewer

complications than most of the studies we reviewed but prevalence was higher than the single study that reported no complications.

The study by Okafor et al [22] which reported no complications, had potentially 119 neonates but 17 were excluded for a variety of reasons. This could suggest that proper selection of MC candidates will be necessary to minimize complications. However, such conclusion may not be justified in the absence of data on the criteria for exclusion i.e. the selection may have or may have not influenced the prevalence of complications.

There are always concerns about the safety of MC in sub-Saharan African health systems. Mattson et al reported on the feasibility of performing MC in health facilities in Kenya. The lack of basic instruments and inadequate supplies were identified as crucial limitations in facilitating provision of safe MC in that country [30]. Ahmed [31] studied circumcision practices in Anjouan, Comoros and reported that circumcisions by trained lay people were as safe as those carried out by physicians in hospitals. Training and supervision was emphasized in this series.

The special cases of complications in haemophiliacs deserve special mention. It has been reported that the use of fibrin glue or the “diathermic knife” may prevent bleeding and transfusion with blood factors [32,33]. These supplies will need to be considered if MC is to be scaled-up, but will increase the cost of the procedure.

It is reasonable to expect that prevalence of complications from MC in Africa is likely to be higher than in countries with well-resourced health systems. While that expectation is reasonable and perhaps will be realized, a recent publication by Archibald et al is also informative [34]. Archibald et al compared contamination of blood culture specimens at Duke Medical Center (Durham, North Carolina, United States), Kamuzu Central Hospital (Malawi) and Muhimbili National Hospital (Tanzania). Contamination of specimens at both African centers was less than 2% while it was 28% at Duke Medical Center. The expectation that developing country health systems will always perform poorly when compared to developed nation health systems may therefore not be justified.

Conclusions

The literature on prevalence of complications following male circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa is limited. Most of the complications reported have been of minor clinical consequence. Reporting practices also have been varied such that comparisons among studies with regard to age of patients, indications for circumcision, duration of follow-up of complications and categories of circumcisers are difficult. There is need to develop and encourage standardized reporting of complications of male circumcisions. We believe that the finding that there is not enough data to suggest that MC is associated with more than the ‘average’ risk in Africa is important as public policy discussions gain momentum as whether to scale-up provision and accessibility of the procedure to prevent HIV transmission.

Competing Interests

The author(s) declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' Contributions

ASM conceived the idea of the study, participated in identifying papers for review and drafting of manuscript. ASM is guarantor of manuscript.

HWP participated in identifying papers for review, analysis and drafting of manuscript.

RM participated in identifying papers for review and drafting of manuscript.

JII participated in identifying papers for review, analysis and drafting of manuscript. All authors approved the manuscript submitted.

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Table 1: Socio-clinical characteristics of male circumcision cases included in the review

Author(s)	Reasons for circumcision	Exclusion Criteria	Period of follow-up	Complications reported
Bailey et al [17]	Randomized controlled trial	HIV infection	8 days	bleeding, infection
Kiwanuka et al [18]	Randomized controlled trial	Not reported	6 weeks	Not reported
Okeke et al [19]	Non medical reasons	Not reported	Not reported	redundant foreskin, excessive skin, skin bridges, amputation of glans, buried penis, hemorrhage
Auvert et al [20]	Randomized controlled trial	Any contraindication to MC and HIV infection	1 month	pain, excessive bleeding, infection, damage to penis, anesthetic complications, excessive skin removal, insufficient skin removal, delayed healing, cosmetic concerns, problems with urination
Krieger et al [21]	Randomized controlled trial	Any medical contraindications to MC e.g. paraphimosis, Significant phimosis, recurrent balanitis, history of bleeding, keloid formation	30 days	infections, bleeding, delayed healing, disrupted wound, swelling, anesthetic, erectile dysfunction
Okafor et al [22]	Feasibility study of MC	Lack of parental consent, preterm birth, congenital anomalies, low APGAR score, history of neonatal jaundice in a sibling, jaundice at birth	1 year	None
Osuigwe et al [23]	Parental request	None reported	6 weeks	bleeding, incomplete circumcision, meatal

					stenosis, urethral laceration
Shittu and Shokunbi [24]	socio-cultural	None		not reported	bleeding
Manji [25]	socio-cultural, religious	none		not specified	infection, bleeding, haematoma
Magoha [26]	cultural, religious, phimosis, paraphimosis, urinary infection, acute infection, hygienic reasons, enhanced sexual sensation, preputial cyst	None reported		Not reported	wound infection, hemorrhage, retention of urine, penile edema, haematoma, scrotal laceration, wound dehiscence, glans injury, meatal stenosis

Table 2: Prevalence of Complications of Male Circumcision Reported From sub-Saharan Africa

Author	Location	Total number of patients	Ages of Patients	Circumcisers	Number of complications	Prevalence of Complications
Bailey et al [17]	Kisumu, Kenya	1334	18-24 yrs	Not indicated	23	1.7%
Kiwanuka et al [18]	Rakai, Uganda	136	15-49 years	Not indicated	5	3.7%
Okeke et al [19]	Ibadan, Nigeria	322	< 1 yr	Nurses, physicians and traditional circumcisers	65	20.2%

	Orange Farm, South Africa				60	
Auvert et al [20]	South Africa	1568	18-24 yrs	Generalist physicians		3.8%
Krieger et al [21]	Kisumu, Kenya	479	18-24yrs	Physicians and clinical officers	17	3.5%
Okafor et al [22]	Nigeria	102	<1 yr	Physicians	0	0
Osugwe et al [23]	Nigeria	138	neonates	Physicians and nurses	33	24.1%
				Nurses, physicians, community health workers and traditional circumcisers	35	
Shittu and Shokunbi [24]]	Ibadan, Nigeria	70	birth to 35 yrs	hemophilia cs		50.1%
Manji [25]]	Tanzania	386	< 1 yr	Pediatricians	11	2.8%
	Lagos, Nigeria and Nairobi, Kenya				28	
Magoha [26]]	Nairobi, Kenya	249	birth to 54 years	Specialist Surgeon physicians		11.2%

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 21:49:54 +0000
To: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: PLoS
Attachments: Circumcision_commentary_revised_per_reviewers_for submission.doc

For inclusion in the binders.
-A

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 10, 2007 15:36
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: PLoS

Hi Allan,

I did get it resubmitted – the final version is attached. Thanks so much for your help while I was out.

I think it is OK to include in the conference materials – when is the deadline for getting materials into the binder? I am expecting to hear back from PLOS quickly, and would feel better about putting it out as in press after we have the final acceptance.

Patrick

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Divisions of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 10, 2007 2:46 PM
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: PLoS

Patrick,

I hope all is well with the PLoS commentary, and I was wondering if I can help in any way. Also, we are getting the binders together for the consultation. May we include an “in press” copy of this paper?

Thanks, Patrick. Let me know if there's anything I can do.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

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Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV Transmission: What the New Data Mean for HIV Prevention in the United States

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Required Disclaimer: The findings and conclusions in this commentary are those of the authors, and do not necessarily represent the views of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

Word Count: 2969

Three randomized, controlled clinical trials in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda were recently unblinded early because interim analyses concluded that circumcision of HIV-negative adult males reduced their risk for acquiring HIV infection through penile-vaginal sex.¹⁻³ In each trial, men who had been randomly assigned to an intervention group receiving circumcision had a lower incidence of HIV infection in up to 2 years of follow-up, compared to men who were assigned to a control group not receiving circumcision. The estimated reduction in the risk of HIV infection ranged from 51% to 60%; per-protocol estimates of risk reduction ranged from 55% to 76%.

It is now clear that male circumcision can be efficacious for men in reducing their risk of HIV acquisition through sex with women.⁴ Some experts predict that the impact of male circumcision as a biomedical intervention for HIV prevention in Africa may be large^{5,6}, and preparatory work for male circumcision programs in Africa has been taking place. The implications of African trials of circumcision for HIV prevention programs in the United States are less clear despite interest of the popular press in the idea.⁷ Here, we consider the differences between the HIV epidemics in Africa and the United States, the current status of male circumcision in the United States, and the knowledge gaps in the United States that will need to be addressed as we consider whether male circumcision should be evaluated or implemented as a biomedical intervention to reduce sexually acquired HIV infection domestically.

Epidemiologic Differences

The results of any trial must be interpreted with the caution that inference not be extended to populations differing from the study participants in important ways. The

HIV epidemics in Africa are substantially different from the US epidemic. In many areas of Africa, generalized HIV epidemics exist, and the population prevalence of HIV among adult Kenyans, Ugandans and South Africans ranges from 6-19%.⁸ The predominant mode of HIV transmission in Africa is through male-female sex. In contrast, the United States has a concentrated epidemic, with most sexual transmission occurring among men who have sex with men (MSM). The general population prevalence of HIV is about 0.4%⁹, and only 17% of men diagnosed with HIV infection during 2005 were reported to have acquired HIV through male-female sex.¹⁰

Biologic Plausibility of Circumcision to Prevent HIV Acquisition

The association between circumcision and reduced risk for HIV acquisition is biologically plausible: the foreskin contains high concentrations of superficial Langerhans cells, CD4+ T cells, and macrophages¹¹ target cells for HIV infection some of which may also be close to the skin surface^{12,13}; the preputial sac may serve as a reservoir for HIV-containing secretions, resulting in prolonged contact time after exposure to secretions; and the foreskin may present less of a physical barrier to HIV entry because of lower keratinization¹² and, potentially, more frequent epithelial disruption. There are also potential indirect mechanisms of association of lack of circumcision and HIV risk; for example, lack of circumcision is associated with increased risk of genital ulcer diseases, which are associated with increased risk of HIV transmission and acquisition.¹⁴

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Vaginal-Penile Sex

Epidemic differences are important because, on a population basis, the impact of circumcision as an intervention to prevent HIV infection among men who have sex with

women will depend on the likelihood of exposure to HIV among US men who have sex with women and, therefore, on the prevalence of HIV among their female sex partners. A recent analysis of data from sexually transmitted disease clinics in Baltimore evaluated the association of male circumcision and risk of prevalent HIV infection in two ways first, among all male attendees at the clinics, and second, restricting the analysis to males who were known to have been exposed to HIV heterosexually (e.g., sexual contacts to partners known to be infected with HIV).¹⁵ The results indicated that, while circumcision was not associated with prevalent HIV infection in the whole population of male STD clinic attendees where HIV prevalence was 3%, circumcision was associated with significantly lower HIV prevalence among men with a known infected female sex partner -- where the prevalence of infection was markedly higher at 12% (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 0.46; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.22-0.97). In effect, this analysis illustrated the impact of partner prevalence of HIV on the association of circumcision and HIV infection status and concluded that it was difficult to detect a protective effect from circumcision on HIV infection in the setting of a partner pool with lower HIV prevalence.

Considerations for Prevention of HIV Transmission by Male-Male Sex

Most sexual transmission of HIV in the United States is by male-male sex¹⁰, and most transmission by male-male sex is to the *receptive* partner in penile-anal intercourse.¹⁶ The fact that the results from the African trials that circumcision was protective for men who were the *insertive* partner in vaginal intercourse suggests that the utility of male circumcision in prevention of HIV transmission among MSM may be limited. Because reducing the concentration of target cells for HIV infection on the penis is a proposed protective mechanism, understanding the relative viral challenge presented

by vaginal versus anal-rectal secretions is relevant to evaluating the plausibility of a protective effect of circumcision for the insertive male partner during anal intercourse. The concentration of HIV-RNA in rectal secretions may be higher than in blood or semen, regardless of use of antiretroviral therapy¹⁷, and may be orders of magnitude higher than the concentrations in vaginal or cervical secretions.^{17,18} Circumcision may change the balance of virus and target cells, but if rectal mucosal secretions contain a higher concentration of infectious virus than vaginal secretions, any potential protective effect of circumcision for the insertive partner may be overwhelmed by excess virus. Also, new data suggest that, for limited periods of time before wound healing is complete, female sex partners of newly circumcised men may be at increased risk of acquiring HIV.⁴ Possible transient increased risk of transmission (before complete wound healing) from recently circumcised MSM to their receptive anal intercourse partners is also of concern.

Few studies provide evidence as to whether circumcision may protect against HIV infection among MSM. In a vaccine-preparedness cohort of MSM followed from 1995 to 1997, circumcision was significantly associated with a decreased risk for HIV seroconversion (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.3-0.9), controlling for number of male sex partners and unprotected sex with an HIV-positive partner.¹⁹ In a cross-sectional survey of gay men in the early 1990s, circumcision was associated with decreased odds of prevalent HIV infection (aOR 0.5; CI, 0.25-1.0).²⁰ While falling short of the quality of data from a randomized intervention trial, these limited data suggest that circumcised MSM in the United States may have decreased risk of HIV infection. However, it is possible that the noted associations in these two observational studies may have been related to

uncontrolled bias. A small cross-sectional study of Australian MSM found no association of circumcision status and risk of HIV infection, when stratifying by insertive and receptive roles.²¹

Virologic Issues

In the African countries where circumcision has been demonstrated to be efficacious, the predominant HIV subtypes are A, C, and D; it is likely that some recombinant strains were also represented in the Kenya and Uganda trials. In the United States, subtype B predominates. Despite the theoretical possibility that subtype differences in either vaginal shedding of HIV or affinity to HIV receptors (especially those natively expressed on the foreskin) could modify the effectiveness of circumcision as an HIV prevention intervention, the consistent findings of the African trials argue that this is unlikely. For example, despite differences in vaginal shedding between subtype C and subtypes A and D¹⁸, the efficacy of circumcision in trials where subtypes A, C, or D were prevalent was comparable. One potentially relevant biological difference relates to binding avidity of HIV subtypes for CCR5 receptors, which are important mechanisms for entry into Langerhans cells, and present in high concentrations in the foreskin.¹¹ Subtype C is reported to have lower binding avidity than subtype B for CCR5 receptors²²; it is unclear whether the greater binding avidity of subtype B for CCR5 could represent an escape mechanism to overcome the decreased availability of target cells that results from circumcision.

Status of Circumcision in the United States

Public health recommendations will likely have the largest impact in populations where circumcision has been rare. Non-religious male circumcision was introduced to

the United States in the late 1800s²³, and by the 1940s, an increasing proportion of male children in the United States were born in hospitals, and were circumcised.²⁴ The proportion of newborns that were circumcised annually reached 80% after World War II and peaked in the mid-1960s. The proportion of male babies circumcised subsequently decreased. According to the National Hospital Discharge Survey (NHDS), which documents circumcisions performed in hospitals but would not ascertain circumcisions performed outside of the hospital for religious reasons, 65% of newborns were circumcised in 1999. Although the overall proportion of newborns circumcised has been stable from 1979 to 1999²⁵, the proportion of black newborns who were circumcised rose over the period to approximately 65%. Significant discrepancies also exist by region. While the proportion of newborns born in the Midwest who were circumcised increased over the 20-year period to 81% in 1999, the proportion of infants born in the West who were circumcised decreased over the same period, to 37% in 1999.²⁵

Data from another hospital discharge survey, the National Inpatient Sample (NIS), present a slightly different picture.²⁶ In that survey, newborn circumcision rates increased from 48% in 1988-1991, to 61% in 1997-2000. Circumcision was more common among newborns born to families of higher socioeconomic status, in the Northeast or Midwest, and who were black.²⁶

Data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES) from 1999 to 2004 indicated that the overall prevalence of circumcision among adult males in the United States was 79% and varied by race/ethnicity (88% in non-Hispanic whites, 73% in non-Hispanic blacks, 42% in Mexican Americans, and 50% in others). The prevalence of circumcision decreased among US-born men from the 1970s to the

1980s.²⁷ Although causality cannot be implied by these data and many other factors are likely operative, the rates of HIV and AIDS among non-Hispanic blacks and Hispanic men are considerably higher than in non-Hispanic whites in the United States.²⁸

Willingness of adult males to be circumcised

The ability of investigators to fully enroll three trials of adult circumcision¹⁻³ in Africa speaks to the acceptability of circumcision among adult males in South Africa, Kenya, and Uganda. A recent systematic review of published literature suggests that adult male circumcision may be acceptable as an HIV prevention intervention in many countries in sub-Saharan Africa.²⁹ In the United States, the overwhelming majority of circumcisions are performed on newborns; adult circumcisions are commonly only done for medical reasons, such as preputial cancer or phimosis. It is not clear whether adult circumcision, were it to be recommended in the United States, would be acceptable as a prevention intervention. Preliminary evidence from interviews with uncircumcised men surveyed at Gay Pride festivals in the United States suggests that the majority of men would consider circumcision as an adult, if circumcision were shown to reduce risk of HIV infection by male-male sex³⁰ although respondents were not told in the survey that protection would be partial, and condom use would still be recommended after circumcision.

Policy Issues Related to Circumcision of Newborn Boys

In 1999, the American Academy of Pediatrics changed from routinely recommending circumcision (primarily based on benefits with respect to risk for urinary tract infections and sexually transmitted infections) to a neutral stance on circumcision³¹; this position was re-affirmed in 2005 by the Academy after publication of the results of

the South Africa trial.³² In a 1995 US review, 61% of infant circumcisions were paid by private insurance, 36% were paid for by Medicaid, and 3% were self-paid by the parents of the infant.³³ Since 1999, 16 states have eliminated Medicaid payments for circumcisions that were not deemed medically necessary.³⁴

Should Adult Male Circumcision be Recommended for HIV Prevention in the United States?

Circumcision may have a role for the prevention of HIV transmission in the United States. However, because of the many differences in the underlying HIV epidemics between Africa and the United States, differences in the prevalence of male circumcision in Africa and the United States, and the considerable gaps in knowledge that exist regarding the potential impact of circumcision on HIV transmission by male-male sex, the extent of this role on a population basis is unknown. Further, the already high prevalence of circumcision among US men suggests some limitations in the potential impact of circumcision at a population level.

Based on the data from the three African clinical trials, it is likely that circumcision will decrease the probability of a man acquiring HIV via penile-vaginal sex with an HIV-infected woman in the United States. Until public health recommendations are available for the United States, some sexually active men may consider circumcision as an additional HIV-prevention measure, but should do so only in consultation with their physician or health care provider, and with a clear understanding of the costs and risks of circumcision and the need to continue use of other, proven prevention measures (e.g., reducing the numbers of sex partners and consistent and correct condom use). Men who

choose to be circumcised should also be counseled about the importance of refraining from sexual intercourse following circumcision, until wound healing is complete.⁴

To consider the possible impact of public health recommendations for male circumcision, we must also take into account HIV incidence in high-risk groups, as well as adoption of other protective behaviors, such as condom use. For example, HIV incidence among US MSM recruited in community- and venue-based samples was, on average, about 1.9% annually,³⁵ and 36% of MSM in the US National HIV Behavioral Surveillance System reported having unprotected anal sex with a casual partner in the 12 months before interview.³⁶ There are few data on HIV incidence among high-risk heterosexuals in the United States, but there are limited data on condom use: in 2002, 16% of high-risk heterosexual men and 24% of high-risk heterosexual women never used condoms during penile-vaginal sex with a non-primary partner.³⁷ Currently available data on disparities in rates of prevalent HIV infection and AIDS^{28,38} and the prevalence of circumcision among US men²⁷ suggest that Black and Hispanic men may have particular opportunities for reduction of risk of HIV acquisition through circumcision.

Future research and consultation

In order to understand the potential for male circumcision as an HIV-prevention approach in the United States, we believe that there are important questions that should be answered. These include questions that can be answered by basic science, by modeling, by surveys of acceptability, by considering ethical issues, and, perhaps, by clinical trials in the United States. For example, it is important to understand more fully the differences in shedding of HIV by rectal versus vaginal mucosa. Modeling may provide important information on (1) the impact on the US epidemic from increasing

male circumcision rates, and (2) the cost-benefit of circumcision among newborns, or among adult men with high risk of exposure to HIV through sex. Cost benefit models may be limited by lack of definitive transmission parameters in US populations and should therefore be conducted with appropriate sensitivity analyses. Surveys may increase our understanding of the acceptability of adult male circumcision among groups of uncircumcised adult males in the United States for whom circumcision might be recommended (e.g., men at high risk of acquiring HIV heterosexually and who do not use condoms consistently, and high-risk MSM), and of barriers and facilitators to acceptance of adult male circumcision, were it recommended as an HIV-prevention strategy. In light of recent trial results and international consensus that male circumcision is efficacious, ethical questions about whether equipoise exists for a US MSM trial, and about how to implement trials or programs of male circumcision in light of complex cultural and religious views about circumcision are important to consider.³⁹ Evaluating data from basic science, modeling, and acceptability surveys and addressing ethics questions will be important in deciding whether a clinical trial to determine the efficacy of male circumcision among MSM may be feasible and appropriate in the United States.

Further, recommendations about circumcision in newborns or high-risk adults for the prevention of HIV infection cannot be made without a more comprehensive discussion of other, documented prevention benefits and risks of circumcision. Benefits include reduction in acquisition of sexually transmitted genital ulcer disease, infant urinary tract infections, penile cancer, and cervical cancer in female sex partners.^{14,40-43} Although less clear, circumcision may also be associated with reduced risk of herpes simplex-virus-2 infection.¹⁴ Risks include post-operative infection, damage to the penis,

excessive bleeding, problems with post-operative appearance of the penis, and anesthesia-related problems.^{1-3,40} If it is determined that circumcision has a role in preventing HIV transmission and other adverse health outcomes in the United States, it will be important to consider the extent to which circumcision is included in public and private medical insurance benefits. The cost, medical risks, and potential benefits of circumcision for HIV prevention will need to be considered separately for infants, high-risk heterosexuals and high-risk MSM. Relatively high rates of circumcision have prevailed in the United States, where rates of HIV infection are currently relatively low. To the extent that a high prevalence of circumcision may have hypothetically led to lower HIV rates in the United States, reducing reimbursement and declining rates of the procedure could reverse this beneficial effect.

To address these scientific and policy questions with a broad group of stakeholders, CDC plans to convene a consultation in 2007 to gain diverse input about the public health research agenda and to develop public health recommendations about the role of male circumcision for prevention of HIV in the United States.

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- (29) Westercamp N, Bailey RC. Acceptability of Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Review. *AIDS Behav*. 2006.
- (30) Begley E, Jafa K, Voetsch A, Heffelfinger J, Sullivan PS. Willingness of men who have sex with men (MSM) in the U.S. to be circumcised as adults to

- reduce risk of HIV infection. Presented at 14th Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections, February 2007. Abstract 983.**
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- (32) American Academy of Pediatrics. AAP Publications Retired and Reaffirmed [Policy Statement]. *Pediatrics* 2005; 116: 796.**
- (33) Mansfield CJ, Hueston WJ, Rudy M. Neonatal circumcision: associated factors and length of hospital stay. *J Fam Pract.* 1995;41:370-376.**
- (34) National Conference of State Legislatures. State Health Notes: Circumcision and Infection. Available from:
<http://www.ncsl.org/programs/hhealth/shn/2006/hl475.htm#circumcision>. Last Accessed December 12, 2006.**
- (35) Stall RD. Re-emerging HIV epidemics among MSM in the United States and other industrialized nations: Evidence and insight. XVI International AIDS Conference, Toronto Canada, August 13-18, 2006: Abstract THBS0202.**
- (36) Sanchez T, Finlayson T, Drake A, et al. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) risk, prevention, and testing behaviors--United States, National HIV**

- Behavioral Surveillance System: men who have sex with men, November 2003-April 2005. *MMWR Surveill Summ.* 2006;55:1-16.**
- (37) **Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. *HIV Testing Survey, 2002.* Atlanta: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; 2004: 1-28. HIV/AIDS Special Surveillance Report 5. Also available at <http://www.cdc.gov/hiv/stats/hasrsupp.htm>.**
- (38) **Espinoza L, Hall HI, Hardnett F, et al. Characteristics of persons with heterosexually acquired HIV infection, United States 1999-2004. *Am J Public Health.* 2007;97:144-149.**
- (39) **Lie RK, Emanuel EJ, Grady C. Circumcision and HIV prevention research: an ethical analysis. *Lancet.* 2006;368:522-525.**
- (40) **Moses S, Bailey RC, Ronald AR. Male circumcision: assessment of health benefits and risks. *Sex Transm Infect.* 1998;74:368-373.**
- (41) **Alanis MC, Lucidi RS. Neonatal circumcision: a review of the world's oldest and most controversial operation. *Obstet Gynecol Surv.* 2004;59:379-395.**
- (42) **Fergusson DM, Boden JM, Horwood LJ. Circumcision status and risk of sexually transmitted infection in young adult males: an analysis of a longitudinal birth cohort. *Pediatrics.* 2006;118:1971-1977.**

- (43) **Diseker RA, III, Peterman TA, Kamb ML, et al. Circumcision and STD in the United States: cross sectional and cohort analyses. *Sex Transm Infect.* 2000;76:474-479.**

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 7 Mar 2007 22:45:49 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

I've asked Peter Havens to check on skeptics within AAP; he said he'd look into it but that nobody was coming to mind. He recommended considering a pediatric urologist (though from Dawn's and my conversation with Dr. Niederburger yesterday, it seems likely that most urologists are pretty well in favor of circumcision these days).

If AAP doesn't pan out and if van Howe is, as Bailey indicates, 'THE anti-circ "expert,"' I wonder if he might turn out to be the right person after all. We might even be faulted in some quarters for not inviting him. I'd trust the other attendees to be able to critically evaluate the evidence he presents, and we would at least be certain that he would represent the views of those opposed to circumcision (if that's our objective). If he makes a well-supported, scientific presentation, that's great; if the best they've got is distorted fact and emotion, then that is also useful to know. (I'm by no means convinced that this is a good idea; I just wanted to get your thoughts about it).

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Bailey [mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 12:46
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Well, THE anti-circumcision "expert" is Robert van Howe, but he distorts the evidence badly and his a member of the anti-circ fringe. I think you might contact the AAP. Their recent guidelines have been quite, well, if not anti-circumcision, at least not pro. Get one of the members of their panel that reviewed the AAP policy on MC. Sorry that I don't have any names.

I think you need an American and would advise against a Brit. You need someone thoroughly familiar with practice in the U.S..

I don't know Dr. Neiderberger. It sounds like I should meet him.

Bob

----- Original Message -----

From: "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@cdc.gov>
To: "Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pbk4@cdc.gov>; <rcbailey@uic.edu>; "Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pss0@cdc.gov>
Cc: "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@cdc.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 11:17 AM

Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the JS, April 26-27

Glad we finally reached Bob!

Allan and I had a great talk with one of his UofI colleagues, Dr. Neiderberger, the rep from the American Urologic Association. Learned a bunch of cool stuff about urology and andrology. Dr. Neiderberger is looking for what he termed a "sentient dissenter" among his andrology listserve colleagues and will try to get us a name in the next few days. In the meanwhile, Allan is also following up on a european urologist who has written quite a lot about the complications of urology. So hopefully one of these several routes will identify a good the counterpoint speaker.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 6:30 PM
To: 'rcbailey@uic.edu'; Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the JS, April 26-27

Thanks Bob this is very helpful. Can I also ask, is there a "credible sceptic" who can summarize arguments against MC as an HIV prevention intervention in the JS? It will be a controversial issue and we want to provide a balance of views or at least a counterpoint.

Thanks!
Peter K

Sent from my wireless handheld

----- Original Message -----

From: Bailey <rcbailey@uic.edu>
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Mar 06 17:40:16 2007
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the JS, April 26-27

I highly recommend that you invite Dr. Thomas Wiswell, probably the foremost authority on infant circumcision in the U.S., famous for his research on infant circumcision and UTI infections. His e-mail address is: (b)(6).

Also, an important consideration with circumcision is protection from penile and cervical cancer. The authority on this is Dr. Xavier Castellsague. His e-mail address is: xcastellsague@iconcologia.net

While the perspectives of myself and Bertran Auvert and others who have worked on male circumcision and HIV in Africa will be helpful, you

should invite a few more experts on INFANT circumcision in general and infant circumcision in the U.S. in particular. I highly recommend Dr. Wiswell, and there should probably be a few more with extensive experience in infant circumcision in the U.S. Another name I can think of is Dr. Ed Schoen, of Kaiser Permanente.

Bob Bailey

----- Original Message -----

From: Sullivan, Patrick <mailto:pss0@cdc.gov> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Wakefield, Steven (CDC and infant circumcision in
<mailto:[REDACTED]@the J.S..com>); bozzette@smmail1.rand.org ;
carl.dieffenbach@nih.hhs.gov ; duffuswa@dnec.sc.gov ; G.Garnett@ic.ac.uk
; ahoward@fhcrc.org ; kenneth_mayer@brown.edu ;
melanie.bacon@nih.hhs.gov ; phavens@mcw.edu ; phavens@mcw.wsu ;
rcbailey@uic.edu ; spb@itsa.ucsf.edu ; TCoates@mednet.ucla.edu ;
tquinn2@jhmi.edu ; victoria.cargill@nih.hhs.gov ; Cates, Willard (CDC
<mailto:wcates@fhi.org> fhi.org) ; Klausner, Jeffrey (CDC
<mailto:jeff_klausner@dph.sf.ca.us> dph.sf.ca.us) ; Weisfuse, Issac (CDC
health.nyc.gov) <mailto:iweisfus@health.nyc.gov> ; aeg1@gwu.edu ;
Curran, Jim <mailto:jcurran@sph.emory.edu> (CDC sph.emory.edu) ;
mitchell@avac.org ; Ciesielski, Carol (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
<mailto:cac2@cdc.gov> ; Douglas, John <mailto:jyd3@cdc.gov>
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Valdiserri, Ronald
<mailto:Ronald.Valdiserri@va.gov> ; Dominguez, Ken
<mailto:kld0@cdc.gov> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; mperez@dhs.co.la.ca.us ;
Romaguera, Raul A. <mailto:rar2@cdc.gov> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Wood, Bob
<mailto:Bob.Wood@METROKCC.GOV> ; bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) <mailto:pbk4@cdc.gov> ; Taylor,
Allan W. <mailto:avt0@cdc.gov> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Smith, Dawn
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) <mailto:dks0@cdc.gov> ; Warner, Lee
<mailto:dlw7@cdc.gov> (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 10:06 AM
Subject: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV
prevention in the US, April 26-27

Colleagues,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. For non-federal employees, we will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

Non-CDC participants will receive a second email shortly with a link to indicate your interest and availability to participate in this consultation. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions,

please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Patrick Sullivan

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Road NE, MS E46
Atlanta, GA 30333
404-639-2090
Fax: 404-639-8640
email: <<mailto:pss0@cdc.gov>> pss0@cdc.gov (note: 4th digit is the
number zero, not the letter "O")
Courier address: 8 Corporate Blvd, Atlanta GA 30329

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 20 Mar 2007 00:13:01 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

FYI - Schoen is confirmed.
-A

From: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org [mailto:Edgar.Schoen@kp.org]
Sent: Monday, March 19, 2007 6:00 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr Taylor - I will be happy to attend the meeting on HIV prevention on April 26-27. Thank you for your invitation. I'll look forward to receiving more information.

E. Schoen

NOTICE TO RECIPIENT: If you are not the intended recipient of this e-mail, you are prohibited from sharing, copying, or otherwise using or disclosing its contents. If you have received this e-mail in error, please notify the sender immediately by reply e-mail and permanently delete this e-mail and any attachments without reading, forwarding or saving them. Thank you.

"Taylor, Allan W.
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)"
<avt0@cdc.gov>
03/16/2007 01:10 PM

To: Edgar Schoen/CA/KAIPERM@KAIPERM
cc: "Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pss0@cdc.gov>
Subject: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr. Schoen,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

You will receive a second email shortly with a link to indicate your interest and availability to participate in this consultation. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thank you,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP

Assistant Professor of Pediatrics
University of Michigan
Department of Pediatrics
1500 East River Road
Ann Arbor, MI 48106-0616
734-763-2100
ataylor@umich.edu

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 11:47:58 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Save the Date: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

I haven't asked him to speak yet, but it looks like Van Howe will be there.
-A

-----Original Message-----

From: rsvanhowe@mgh.org [mailto:rsvanhowe@mgh.org]
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 1:04 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the Date: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Dear Dr. Taylor,

I have been able to set aside these dates, so I should be able to attend. I look forward to hearing from you.

Sincerely,

Robert S. Van Howe, MD, MS, FAAP

"Taylor, Allan W.
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <(b)(6)> <avt0@cdc.gov>
<pss0@cdc.gov> To: Robert S Van Howe/PESP/MGHS@mghs.
cc: "Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)"
Department Not Found Subject: Save the Date: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision
03/26/2007 10:57 AM

Dr. Van Howe,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC will support your transportation, lodging and per diem for the conference.

You will receive a second email shortly with details regarding travel arrangements. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thank you,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and
TB Prevention
(proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333 W:404.639.6120 /
F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 13 Apr 2007 21:10:49 +0000
To: Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McElroy, Laura (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Subject: Letters for SUPPORTED participants
Attachments: Circumcision Consultation Conference Registration Form.doc, MC Consultation ConferenceLogistics Letter 1.doc, MC Consultation Invitation Letter.pdf

And these are the letters to use for invitations to SUPPORTED travelers, as we discussed in our meeting today. Thank you for your assistance with these additional invitations.

-Allan

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 12, 2007 18:44
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Colleagues,

We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this conference as detailed in the letter.
- 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.

Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Centers For Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the
United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns
April 26-27, 2007

RETURN BY: April 21, 2007 TO: Leris
Bernard
B L Seamon Corporation
4221 Forbes Boulevard, Suite 245, Lanham,
MD 20706

Registration Information Form

Please check as appropriate:

Mr. Ms. M.D. Ph.D. Other _____

Name: _____ Title: _____

Organization/Affiliation: _____

Department: _____

Address: _____

City: _____ State: _____ ZIP Code: _____

Phone: _____ Fax: _____ E-mail: _____

Assistant Name: _____ Phone: _____ E-mail: _____

Emergency Contact Name: _____ Phone: _____

PLEASE CONFIRM ATTENDANCE:

_____ YES, I will attend.

_____ NO, I will be unable to attend.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

Room Type: Single Double
 Smoking Nonsmoking Handicap No Hotel Needed

Arrival Date: _____ Departure Date: _____

Comments: _____

Your room **MUST** be guaranteed with a credit card.

Type of Card: VISA MC AMEX Other: _____ Expiration Date: _____

Name of Cardholder: _____

Credit Card #: _____

Signature

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS: Please make your travel arrangements through our travel agency, Travel-On, at (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between the hours of 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.) and reference project # **H1248**. **Please indicate your method for arranging your travel:**

_____ I will call Travel-On to arrange my travel.

_____ I will make my own travel arrangements.

_____ Other: _____

Special Requirements

*Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)*

Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

April 26–27, 2007

Atlanta, GA

FROM: Leris Bernard, Conference Planner
B L Seamon Corporation
Phone: (301) 577-0244, ext. 32
Fax: (301) 577-5261

MEETING DATES: **Thursday April 26, 2007 – 8:30 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.**
Tuesday March 27, 2007 – 9:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m.

MEETING AND LODGING SITE: **Embassy Suites Hotel**
Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park
267 Marietta Street
Atlanta, GA 30313
Phone: (404) 223-2300
Fax: (404) 223-0925

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns, sponsored by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). B L Seamon Corporation (BLS), under contract to DHHS, is providing administrative and logistical support for the meeting. Please take a few minutes to review the information below.

REGISTRATION

Please confirm your intent to attend the meeting by filling out the enclosed Registration Form. This form will also be used to reserve your hotel room. If you do not plan to attend, please let us know by returning the registration form.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

A guestroom has been reserved in your name at the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for your arrival on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007. Your confirmation number will be provided under separate cover. **Do not call the hotel directly.**

BLS will cover the cost of your guestroom for a maximum of 2 (two) nights. You will be responsible for settling all incidental charges and additional nights before checking out of the hotel. If you need to cancel your reservation, please do so 72 hours before your scheduled arrival date to avoid a direct credit card charge of 1 night's lodging. If you cancel your reservation, be sure to obtain a cancellation number from the reservationist for your records.

Your reservation must be guaranteed with a major credit card submitted on the attached Registration Information Form. Although the cost of your accommodations will be covered, a major credit card is required to guarantee your room reservation. Your card will be charged if you do not attend the meeting and do not cancel your room reservation by 3:00 p.m., 24 hours prior to the day of arrival. Please provide this information on the attached Travel and Hotel Information Form.

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS

CDC will sponsor travel and lodging support for you to attend the meeting. Please make your travel arrangements as soon as possible through our travel agency, Travel-On, 9000 Virginia Manor Road, Suite 201, Beltsville, MD. Call 1 (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.) and **reference the meeting name and project code #H1248.** Your travel authorization will cover the most economical, round-trip, coach fare between the city listed in your address and the meeting site for arrival in Atlanta, GA, on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007 (unless otherwise authorized).

Federal Travel Regulations require BLS to purchase the most economical airfare for sponsored participants. In most cases, a nonrefundable ticket will be purchased for you. Therefore, it is important that you carefully consider your schedule when requesting travel reservations.

In addition, if you need to fly from an airport other than the one serving your city, notify BLS as soon as possible. Use of an alternate airport requires special authorization if it increases the cost of your ticket, and approval for a rental car must be obtained **prior to the meeting.** If a rental car is approved, reimbursement may be restricted to the cost of a round-trip taxi from the airport.

After your travel arrangements are confirmed, Travel-On will forward a copy of your itinerary to you for approval (most often via e-mail). Upon receipt, please review, approve, and return to Travel-On. Upon receipt of your approved itinerary, a prepaid ticket will be issued.

Ticketing

An electronic ticket (e-ticket) will be issued unless you request a printed ticket. However, please note that in some cases printed tickets cannot be issued. Please discuss your preference with the travel agent, and he/she will advise you of available ticketing methods.

If you request a printed ticket and it is an available option, please confirm your mailing address when speaking with the travel agent. Your ticket will be sent to you via express mail within a few days after confirming your arrangements.

If an e-ticket is issued, please note that your itinerary should be used as confirmation of your arrangements. Upon arrival at the airport, please present your itinerary and photo identification. After you check in, the airline will provide you with a printed boarding pass for your reserved seat.

Making Your Own Travel Arrangements

If you would like to make (or have already made) your own travel arrangements, please check the appropriate box on the attached Travel and Hotel Information Form. **You will be reimbursed for the cost of your ticket if you use an American carrier, reserve coach-class seating, and have your ticket cost approved by BLS *BEFORE* you purchase your ticket.** Submit your travel receipts for reimbursement after the meeting.

Travel by Automobile

If you are traveling by automobile, you will be reimbursed 48.5¢ per mile, not to exceed the cost of air travel. The Federal Government does not authorize BLS to reimburse you for lodging or meals between your departure city and the meeting site or for mileage not related to attending the meeting.

Ground Transportation

From Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport, participants may use the MARTA, Atlanta's subway system to travel to the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for \$1.75 each way. Take any northbound train to Five Points Station. Transfer to the Westbound train. Go one stop to W1/Omni/Dome/GWCC Station. Take the small escalator to the big escalator. Turn left and go to Philips Drive. Turn right and go to International Blvd. Turn right and go to Marietta Street. Embassy Suites Hotel is one block on the left. (Approximately a 5-minute walk from the train station)

In addition, participants can utilize the Atlanta Link, a traditional van service that offers round-trip airport transfer for \$28.00 per person. The *DOWNTOWN* Shuttle is preferred because it handles downtown properties only. Advance reservations can be secured by calling 1 (866) 545-9633.

A taxicab from the Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport should run \$24.00 one way plus \$2 for each additional passenger.

REIMBURSEMENT OF EXPENSES

BLS will reimburse you for ground transportation as well as meals and incidental expenses (M&IE) after the meeting. Ground transportation expense reimbursement covers taxis to/from your home, the airports, and the hotel, as well as parking and tolls. Mileage is reimbursed at 48.5¢ per mile for the use of your personally owned vehicle. The M&IE reimbursement covers meals, tips, telephone calls, and other miscellaneous expenses and is applicable to the geographical location of the site visit. The M&IE allowance for Atlanta, GA is \$49.00 per full day. You will receive three-fourths of the M&IE allowance or \$36.75 for each travel day on

April 25 and April 27.

To claim your expenses following the conference, please submit the Travel Reimbursement Form by May 11, 2007. You will receive this form at the meeting. When submitting your expenses, attach all applicable receipts including your travel ticket stub. All receipts and your travel ticket stub must be submitted in original form. Receipts are not required for meal expenses.

QUESTIONS

Please contact Leris Bernard at lbernard@blscamon.com or (301) 577-0244, ext. 32, if you have questions regarding logistics or if your attendance plans should change.

Questions concerning program content should be directed to Dr. Allan Taylor at (404) 639-6120 e-mail: avt0@cdc.gov.

April 12, 2007

Dear Colleague,

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

Meeting Objectives

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

Space will be available for presentation of posters if participants have data or activities they wish to share. Please contact us in advance if you plan to prepare a poster so that we may ensure adequate space.

CDC will cover the cost of your travel and lodging and will provide a per diem of \$49 per full day for meals and incidentals. The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. The Embassy Suites Hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313, Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925. We have reserved a block of rooms for our participants at the US Government rate. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation. Please contact Allan Taylor, MD, MPH at ataylor2@cdc.gov or at (404) 639-6120 if you have any questions or comments. We are looking forward to your participation and to a productive consultation.

Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 13 Apr 2007 21:09:47 +0000
To: Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McElroy, Laura (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Subject: Letters for UNSupported participants
Attachments: MC Consultation Invitation Letter 2.pdf, MC Consultation Conference Logistics 2.doc

These are the letter and attachments sent to the UNSUPPORTED participants, for your reference.

-A

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 12, 2007 19:08
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Colleagues,

We would like to extend our formal invitation to the upcoming **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon, with instructions regarding travel arrangements and logistics. Please send the first page of this form back to the contractor to confirm your attendance.

NOTE: Hotel reservations must be made between 4/13/07 and 4/18/07 to receive the group rate.

Please do not hesitate to contact me at any time if questions should arise. We look forward to a productive meeting.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

April 12, 2007

Dear Colleague,

The CDC Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

Meeting Objectives

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

Space will be available for presentation of posters if participants have data or activities they wish to share. Please contact us in advance if you plan to prepare a poster so that we may ensure adequate space.

CDC is unable to provide for your travel expenses; however we have reserved a block of rooms at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park for our participants at the US Government rate of USD\$124/night. The hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313. Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925). The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter.

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation. Please contact Allan Taylor, MD, MPH at ataylor2@cdc.gov or at (404) 639-6120 if you have any questions or comments. We are looking forward to your participation and to a productive consultation.

Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

*Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)*

Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

**April 26–27, 2007
Atlanta, GA**

FROM: Leris Bernard, Conference Planner
B L Seamon Corporation
Phone: (301) 577-0244, ext. 32
Fax: (301) 577-5261

MEETING DATES: **Thursday April 26, 2007 – 8:30 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.**
Tuesday March 27, 2007 – 9:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m.

MEETING AND LODGING SITE: **Embassy Suites Hotel**
Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park
267 Marietta Street
Atlanta, GA 30313
Phone: (404) 223-2300
Fax: (404) 223-0925

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns, sponsored by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). B L Seamon Corporation (BLS), under contract to DHHS, is providing administrative and logistical support for the meeting. Please take a few minutes to review the information below.

REGISTRATION

Please confirm your intent to attend the meeting by marking the appropriate line and faxing back this page to Leris Bernard, B L Seamon at (301) 577-5261:

Please Confirm Attendance:

YES, I will attend.
 NO, I will be unable to attend.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

The Conference will be held at the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park, 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, GA 30313. Please call the hotel at 1-800-EMBASSY to reserve a room for arrival on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007. Your reservation must be guaranteed with a major credit card. Please reference meeting name: “*CDC Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the US*” to receive the conference rate of \$124.00. **The Hotel Reservation deadline is April 18, 2007.**

The Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park offers the following amenities:

- ❖ This is an all suite hotel. All suites include a living room with one convertible sofa, refrigerator, and microwave.
- ❖ A complimentary full American cooked-to-order breakfast at Ruth’s Chris Steak House
- ❖ Complimentary evening hors d’oeuvres served in the hotel’s atrium lobby
- ❖ Rooftop heated pool and Jacuzzi. Indoor fitness center and sauna.

If you need to cancel your reservation, please do so 72 hours before your scheduled arrival date to avoid a direct credit card charge of 1 night’s lodging. If you cancel your reservation, be sure to obtain a cancellation number from the reservationist for your records.

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS

You are responsible for making your own travel arrangements. Please do so as soon as possible. You may use your own travel agent or the B L Seamon’s travel management company Travel-On. Travel-On can be reached at 1 (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.).

Ground Transportation

From Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport, participants may use the MARTA, Atlanta’s subway system to travel to the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for \$1.75 each way. Take any northbound train to Five Points Station. Transfer to the Westbound train. Go one stop to W1/Omni/Dome/GWCC Station. Take the small escalator to the big escalator. Turn left and go to Philips Drive. Turn right and go to International Blvd. Turn right and go to Marietta Street. Embassy Suites Hotel is one block on the left. (Approximately a 5-minute walk from the train station)

In addition, participants can utilize the Atlanta Link, a traditional van service that offers round-trip airport transfer for \$28.00 per person. The *DOWNTOWN* Shuttle is preferred because it handles downtown properties only. Advance reservations can be secured by calling 1 (866) 545-9633.

A taxicab from the Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport should run \$24.00 one way plus \$2 for each additional passenger.

In addition, participants can utilize the Atlanta Link, a traditional van service that offers round-trip airport transfer for \$38.00 per person. Advance reservations can be secured by calling 1 (866) 545-9633.

QUESTIONS

Please contact Leris Bernard at lbernard@blseamon.com or (301) 577-0244, ext. 32, if you have questions regarding logistics or if your attendance plans should change.

Questions concerning program content should be directed to Dr. Allan Taylor at (404) 639-6120 e-mail: ataylor2@cdc.gov.

**Directions to Embassy Suites Hotel
Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park
267 Marietta Street
Atlanta, GA 30313**

From South: (I-75/I-85)

Take interstate highway into Atlanta where I-75 & I-85 are connected to exit #248C (International Blvd.). Take left on International Blvd. Turn left on Centennial Olympic Park Drive. Turn right onto Marietta Street. The hotel is on the right one block.

From North: (I-75/I-85)

Take interstate highway to exit #249C (Williams Street). Proceed on Williams Street to International Blvd. Turn right on International Blvd. and continue through Centennial Olympic Park. Turn right onto Marietta Street. The hotel is one block down on the right.

From West: (I-20)

Take interstate highway I-20 East to exit #56B (Windsor Street/Spring Street/Stadium). Turn left onto Windsor Street. Turn left onto Marietta Street. Hotel is 3 blocks down on the right.

From East: (I-20)

From I-20 exit onto I-75/I-85 North to exit #248C (International Blvd.). Turn left on International Blvd, and continue through Centennial Olympic Park. Turn right onto Marietta Street. The hotel is one block down on the right.

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Sat, 14 Apr 2007 22:55:53 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: MC CD
Attachments: US Circumcision reference list.rtf, Policy statements reference list.rtf, Table of contents.doc, Transmission reference list.rtf, Ethics Acceptability reference list.rtf, CD Table of contents.doc

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Section 1 Policy Statements

Section 2 Ethics and Acceptability of Circumcision

Section 3 Circumcision in the United States

Section 4 Transmission of HIV and STDs

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Ref Type: Electronic Citation

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- Section 1 Meeting Agenda**
- Section 2 HIV Clinical Trials and Studies**
- Section 3 Circumcision in the United States**
- Section 4 Non-HIV Health Effects of Circumcision**
- Section 5 Ethics and Acceptability of Circumcision**
- Section 6 Policy Statements**

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 12 Apr 2007 23:18:59 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Subject: More new circ papers
Attachments: Westercamp07.pdf, Muula_AidsBeh07.pdf, Krieger07.pdf

Three brand new circumcision papers from Bailey et al!

Westercamp - review of acceptability in subSaharan Africa

Krieger - safety outcomes in the trial

Muula (Aids and Behavior) - next research questions (prominant citation to Crepaz and Marks work)

Keeping up is getting to be a full-time job :)

Acceptability of Male Circumcision for Prevention of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Review

N. Westercamp · R. C. Bailey

Published online: 20 October 2006
© Springer Science + Business Media, LLC 2006

Abstract Based on epidemiological, clinical and experimental evidence, male circumcision (MC) could have a significant impact on the HIV epidemic in selected areas. We reviewed studies of the acceptability of MC in sub-Saharan Africa to assess factors that will influence uptake of circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising populations. Thirteen studies from nine countries were identified. Across studies, the median proportion of uncircumcised men willing to become circumcised was 65% (range 29–87%). Sixty nine percent (47–79%) of women favored circumcision for their partners, and 71% (50–90%) of men and 81% (70–90%) of women were willing to circumcise their sons. Because the level of acceptability across the nine countries was quite consistent, additional acceptability studies that pose hypothetical questions to participants are unnecessary. We recommend pilot interventions making safe circumcision services available in conjunction with current HIV prevention strategies and evaluating the safety and acceptability of circumcision.

Keywords Male circumcision · Acceptability · HIV-1 · Africa

Introduction

Numerous observational studies have reported a significant protective effect of male circumcision (MC)

against HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in men (Bailey, Plummer, & Moses, 2001; Cameron et al., 1989; Gray et al., 2000; Lavreys et al., 1999; Siegfried et al., 2003; Urassa, Todd, Boerma, Hayes, & Isingo, 1997; Weiss, Quigley, & Hayes, 2000). Recently, a randomized controlled trial (RCT) of MC to reduce HIV incidence in Orange Farm, South Africa was stopped prematurely due to an observed protective effect of MC of 60% in intention to treat analysis and 76% in a per protocol analysis. This effect was consistent with the protective effect found in cohort studies (Auvert et al., 2005).

Ecological studies have shown that the countries in sub-Saharan Africa with the highest HIV prevalence are those in which MC is little practiced (Halperin & Bailey, 1999; Moses et al., 1990). Based on the epidemiological and experimental evidence to date, MC could have a significant impact on the HIV epidemic in these most highly affected countries. However, the effectiveness of the intervention will depend on many factors, not the least of which is the extent to which MC is accepted and taken up by males in these populations. If sufficient numbers of males are circumcised, there could be an effect similar to herd immunity since preventing men from becoming infected will also protect their sex partners. At more moderate levels of uptake, the effect is less clear.

In addition to the proportion of males who will become circumcised, the age at circumcision will also be a determinant of how rapidly the intervention results in reduction of HIV prevalence in the population. If infant circumcision is preferred over, say, pubertal circumcision, then the time lag from introduction of a large scale intervention until observable reductions in HIV prevalence could be decades. Because acceptance of MC

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by men and by parents of males in traditionally non-circumcising communities will be crucial to the success of a MC intervention for reducing HIV prevalence, we provide a review of the extant literature on acceptability of MC in sub-Saharan Africa.

Study Collection and Search Strategies

Criteria for inclusion in this review were established before the literature searches were carried out and included studies researching acceptability of MC as an HIV prevention method formally or as a part of a larger study, conducted in sub-Saharan Africa and published in a peer-reviewed journal or presented at an international conference. Electronic searches were conducted in MEDLINE using the following strategy: term “circumcision” in the title, abstract or keywords was combined with “acceptability”, “attitudes” or “beliefs” in the title, abstract or keywords generating 920 articles, subset by “HIV” or “STIs/STD” in the title, abstract or keywords producing 244 articles, and finally limited to English language articles published from 1980 through 2006 resulting in 229 publications. Electronic search conducted in Google Scholar using phrase “acceptability of male circumcision in Africa as HIV prevention” resulted in 142 publications. Nine articles were directly related to the acceptability of circumcision in sub-Saharan Africa. Four additional studies were identified through personal communication with authors. A map of study sites in nine countries is presented in Fig. 1. Key characteristics of the 13 studies included in this review are shown in Table 1.

Diversity of the Study Sample

All studies employed some variation of a convenience sample. Out of 13 studies reviewed, eight were designed specifically to study acceptability of MC (Bailey, Muga, Poulussen, & Abicht, 2002; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde, Dirk, Puren, Reathe, & Bertran, 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson, Bailey, Muga, Poulussen, & Onyango, 2005; Ngalande, Levy, Kapondo, & Bailey, 2006; Scott, Weiss, & Viljoen, 2005; Tsela & Halperin, 2006), two included questions on MC acceptability in the context of a larger study (Bailey, Neema, & Othieno, 1999; Halperin, Fritz, McFarland, & Woelk, 2005), and three included formal MC acceptability data collection as well as previously collected data as part of a larger scope of research (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Nnko, Washija, Urassa, & Boerma, 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Seven of the studies were performed

in largely ethnically homogenous populations (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Halperin et al., 2005; Mattson et al., 2005; Nnko et al., 2001; Scott et al., 2005; Tsela & Halperin, 2006), while the remaining studies implemented specific strategies to ensure an ethnically mixed sample (Bailey et al., 1999; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Ten of 13 studies included both male and female participants (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). The remaining three studies were restricted to males (Bailey et al., 1999; Halperin et al., 2005; Tsela & Halperin, 2006). Only two studies addressed acceptability in adolescent populations separately from adults (Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Three studies purposely included the participation of female sex workers (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006), and four studies included the opinions of MC providers in the assessment of circumcision acceptability/promotion (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). Nine studies included both rural and urban populations (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Tsela & Halperin, 2006); one study limited participation to rural groups only (Scott et al., 2005); and three studies were restricted to urban groups (Bailey et al., 1999; Halperin et al., 2005; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). All the studies were conducted in areas where circumcision is not traditionally practiced. Two purposely also included at least one area where most men are circumcised (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Ten studies assessed the circumcision status of male participants (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 1999; Halperin et al., 2005; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde et al., 2003; Mattson et al., 2005; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005; Tsela & Halperin, 2006) and all studies allowed participation regardless of circumcision status.

Summary of Quantitative Results of Acceptability

Eight of the 13 studies reviewed included quantitative assessments of the acceptability of MC in six countries

Fig. 1 Locations (by level 3 administrative unit) where male circumcision (MC) acceptability studies were conducted

using interview questionnaires. Results are summarized in Fig. 2 and Table 2. Four of the eight studies included women respondents. Willingness of uncircumcised men to become circumcised varied from 29% in Uganda to 87% in Swaziland. The variation depended in part on how the question was posed and the context of the study. For example, one of the highest acceptability levels (81%) was recorded in Botswana after an informational session in which participants were told about the health benefits and risks associated with the procedure (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). In some studies, adults were

asked if they would be circumcised or prefer their partner to be circumcised “if MC were proven to be protective against HIV and STIs” (Halperin et al., 2005; Lagarde et al., 2003; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Tsela & Halperin, 2006). In others, participants were asked if they would accept MC “if it were safe and affordable” (Bailey et al., 1999; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Mattson et al., 2005; Scott et al., 2005).

In general, approximately the same proportion of women would prefer circumcision for their partners or their sons as men would prefer circumcision for

Table 1 Characteristics of male circumcision (MC) acceptability studies ($N = 13$), 1999–2006

Country/Authors/Year	Time of the study	Study population	Ethnic composition	Circumcision status of participants	Data collection methods
Botswana/ Kebaabetswe et al. (2003)	2001	316 Male and 289 female participants, age 18–74, in urban and rural settings	Ethnically heterogeneous (over 15 ethnicities)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Interviews, pre- and post-educational session
Kenya/Bailey et al. (2002)	1998	Residents of Nyanza Province, age 16–80, men and women, 30 focus groups, each 6–14 people, urban and rural population, farmers, business people, teachers, sex workers, barmaids, and touts.	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	Not recorded; nearly all likely uncircumcised	Focus groups; interviews with healthcare providers
Kenya/Bailey (Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002)	1999	32 Clinicians were interviewed to assess their knowledge and practice of MC, records of MC performed in the area were reviewed, 7 circumcised men and their wives were interviewed	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised	Interviews, KAB questionnaires, record review
Kenya/Mattson et al. (2005)	1999	107 Men and 110 women, 16 years of age and older of Luo ethnicity, in urban and rural settings	Ethnically homogenous (Luo)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Structured interviews
Malawi/Ngalande et al. (2006)	2003	318 Participants, 32 focus groups with men and women 16–80 years old	Ethnically diverse (Chewa, Tonga, Yao, Ngoni, Lomwe, and Nyanja)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Focus groups
South Africa/Lagarde et al. (2003)	2001	482 Men aged 19–29 years and 302 women aged 14–25 years	Ethnically heterogeneous (Sotho, Tswana, Xhosa and other ethnicities)	22% of men 19–29 years old were circumcised	Interviews using standardized questionnaire
South Africa/Scott et al. (2005)	2002	100 Adult men and 44 adult women in rural Zulu land and 4 service providers	Ethnically homogenous (Zulu)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Interviews, focus groups
South Africa/Rain-Taljaard et al. (2003)	1999–2000	Sample of 606 13–59 year old males interviewed in August 2000 and 723 14–24 year old males interviewed in August 1999	Ethnically diverse (Sotho, Xhosa, Zulu, Tswana, Shangaan, and Venda)	36% of men 25–59 years old were circumcised	Interviews and focus groups
Swaziland/Tsela and Halperin (2006)	2006	409 Men aged 15–49 were interviewed in urban and rural setting	Not reported, but likely majority were Swazi	14% of men were circumcised	Interviews
Tanzania/Nnko et al. (2001)	1991–1997	998 Sukuma men from a cohort of factory workers in Mwanza town, 13 focus groups from mostly rural area, and population based surveys	Ethnically homogenous (Sukuma)	21% of men in the sample were circumcised	Interviews and cohort data analysis
Uganda/Bailey et al. (1999)	1997	188 Circumcised and 177 uncircumcised men 18 to 67 years old from the Industrial Borough, Mbale.	Ethnically diverse (17 tribal groups, including Gisu)	52% of men were circumcised	Structured interviews
Zambia/Lukobo and Bailey (submitted)	2003	160 Men and 162 women in the 34 focus groups in rural and urban settings	Ethnically diverse (Lunda, Luvale, Chewa, Tonga)	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Focus groups
Zimbabwe/Halperin et al. (2005)	2000	200 Men attending beer halls in Harare	Not reported, but likely majority were Shona	Both circumcised and uncircumcised men	Interviews, focus group

Fig. 2 Levels of male circumcision (MC) acceptability from eight quantitative studies in six sub-Saharan African countries

themselves or their sons. In Botswana, Kenya, South Africa and Swaziland, where men or women were asked about circumcision for their sons, more adults would agree to the procedure for their child than for their spouse or themselves. Approximately 75% of parents would seek circumcision for their son if it was safe, affordable and shown to be protective against HIV and STIs.

Across studies, the median proportion of uncircumcised men willing to become circumcised was 65% (range 29–87%). Sixty nine percent (range 47–79%) of women favored circumcision for their partners, and 71% (50–90%) of men and 81% (70–90%) of women were willing to circumcise their sons. The study restricted to rural population found that 51% of men were willing to become circumcised, while median proportion in the same category was 45% (range 29–59%) in three urban studies and 77% (70–87%) in studies that included both rural and urban population.

Barriers to the Acceptability of MC

Pain

Apprehension about pain during and after the procedure was reported to be the major barrier to MC acceptability in most studies (Bailey et al., 2002; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Scott et al., 2005). Participants belonging to non-circumcising ethnic groups were familiar with the circumcision practices in neighboring circumcising tribes where pain

was a key characteristic of the procedure. As a rite of passage to becoming a man, the endurance of the pain from circumcision is often an integral aspect of the ceremony. For example, of 108 circumcised participants in South Africa, 42.6% described the traditional procedure as “very painful”, 34.4% as “mildly painful”, and 18.5% as “not painful” (Lagarde et al., 2003).

Culture and Religion

Lack of circumcision was mentioned as an element of the ethnic identity of those who do not circumcise traditionally. However, remaining with one’s foreskin is not considered crucial to one’s own ethnic identity. It serves as an ethnic marker primarily used by others. In both Botswana and Swaziland studies, only 2% of participants, for example, felt that circumcision would lead to disapproval by their community (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Tsela & Halperin, 2006), although in Botswana 22% cited “cultural reasons” as a factor in their decision not to circumcise their male child (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). It is fundamentally different from belonging to an ethnic group that does practice traditional circumcision. For the Yao in Malawi, for example, or the Lunda and Luvale tribes in Zambia, or the Bagisu in Uganda (Bailey et al., 1999; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Nnko et al., 2001), it is unacceptable to remain uncircumcised, to the extent that forced circumcisions of older boys are not uncommon.

In some ethnic groups in which circumcision is not commonly practiced, disapproval of circumcision is

Table 2 Circumcision preference and conditions for acceptability reported in eight studies from six sub-Saharan African countries

Authors/year/country	% Of uncircumcised men willing to be circumcised	% Of women favoring circumcision of their partners	% Of men willing to circumcise their sons	% Of women willing to circumcise their sons
Kebaabetswe et al. (2003)/Botswana	61% Before and 81% after information session, if procedure is done in safe hospital settings and is free	50% Before and 79% after information session	67% Before and 90% after information session, if procedure is done in safe hospital settings and is free	62% Before and 90% after information session, if procedure is done in safe hospital settings and is free
Mattson et al. (2005)/Kenya	70%, If procedure involved minimal cost and little pain	69%	74%, If procedure was safe and affordable (Bailey, Muga, & Poulussen, 2000)	89%, If little pain was involved
Lagarde et al. (2003)/South Africa	73%, If MC protected from STIs/HIV	47% Thought most women preferred circumcised men	71% Of non-circumcised men and 82% of circumcised men, if MC protected from STIs/HIV	70%, If MC protected from STIs/HIV
Scott et al. (2005)/South Africa	51%, If performed safely and at low cost	68%	50%	73%
Rain-Taljaard et al. (2003)/South Africa	59%, If MC reduced chances of STIs and HIV	N/a	N/a	N/a
Tsela and Halperin (2006)/Swaziland	54%: 87%, If MC protected against HIV/STIs	N/a	71%	N/a
Bailey et al. (1999)/Uganda	29%, If cost was minimal	N/a	N/a	N/a
Halperin et al. (2005)/Zimbabwe	45% If MC protected against HIV/STIs, and was safe and affordable	N/a	N/a	N/a

evident in the existence of a derogatory term for a circumcised man or a man with a congenitally shortened prepuce. These terms include “*rayuom*” in DhoLuo (Bailey et al., 2002) and “*njilwa*” in the Sukuma language (Nnko et al., 2001). In ethnically homogenous areas, circumcision could lead to rejection by local women and serve as a barrier to marriage (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). In more ethnically diverse areas, however, circumcision among traditionally non-circumcising peoples could be held as a positive, increasing a man’s chances of being accepted by the women of the surrounding circumcising groups.

Religion is a major determinant of circumcision acceptability. MC is universally associated with Islam. It is also considered fundamental to some minority Christian and animist sects. There was no clear consensus on compatibility of MC with Christian beliefs (Bailey et al., 1999; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). Great variability in perceptions of Christian churches’ positions on MC was described by different study populations, ranging from condemning MC as a pagan practice (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003) to viewing MC as consistent with Christian tradition according to the Bible and Jesus’ circumcision status (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). In South Africa 38% of circumcised and 32% of uncircumcised study participants described circumcision as “forbidden” by their religion (Lagarde et al., 2003). Sukuma study participants in Tanzania felt that the Christian religion did not theologically promote MC, while circumcision services were known to be available in church-run hospitals (Nnko et al., 2001). Lukobo and Bailey describe the prevalent Zambian perception of circumcision being linked with Muslim or animist Chawa heritage, with several participants also reporting the belief that Christians should practice MC since Jesus was circumcised and the Bible teaches the practice (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). Similar findings were reported by Ngalande et al. in Malawi (Ngalande et al., 2006). In Kenya the Nomiya Church and a few other small Christian sects require circumcision for church membership (Mattson et al., 2005).

Rain-Taljaard and colleagues report the South African belief that circumcision is fundamentally an African tradition and that Western ideas concerning the practice should not be taken seriously. Further, participants stated that many Christian churches opposed circumcision as a pagan tradition (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). However, it was unclear whether this opposition was directed at circumcision itself or at rites and ceremonies with which it was associated.

Before MC is promoted in a country, it would be prudent to consult and collaborate with religious leaders to learn the stance of the various churches regarding MC. In many cases, churches can act as helpful advocates or obstructive opponents and may have significant influence on acceptability of MC.

Cost

The cost of the procedure was a significant barrier to MC acceptability by participants in many studies (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005). Some participants expressed the opinion that if circumcision were promoted by the government, it should be provided at health clinics and hospitals for free or at reduced cost (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Others recognized the need to pay for services because a free circumcision was viewed as being of potentially poor quality (Ngalande et al., 2006). Male and female participants in Zambia believed that, if the MC procedure were free or extremely inexpensive, more men would be willing to get circumcised (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). In one study as many as 34% of participants who initially stated that their preference was to remain uncircumcised changed their minds when the proposed cost of the procedure was set at US\$3.00 (Mattson et al., 2005). Cost of traditional circumcision was considered to be high in many areas and there is a gradual shift from traditional to medical circumcision in part for this reason (Bailey & Egesah, 2006; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Traditional circumcision is often expensive due to the costs of food, drink, special clothing and other items required during a sometimes prolonged celebration.

Complications and Adverse Effects

If men and parents believe that circumcision leads to high rates of complications, then uptake of MC is likely to be slow. Concerns for safety were universal in the studies examined. Mothers were vocal in their concerns, especially in cases of infant and early childhood circumcision. Excessive bleeding was a major concern and this fear was heightened if the procedure was to be performed by a traditional circumciser outside the hospital setting (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Infection and difficulty in healing were expressed as concerns as well, but were generally believed to be minimized in clinical settings (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey,

Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Using the same knife for several boys was believed to be common in traditional settings and a source of infections, including HIV (Bailey et al., 2002; Halperin et al., 2005; Lagarde et al., 2003; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Women were especially opposed to circumcision at the traditional initiation schools, as they feared that their children may be injured or die during the process (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Overall, there seemed to be a great deal of trust in medical practitioners and a strong preference for circumcision services to be made available in public health facilities by trained health professionals.

Potential for Behavioral Disinhibition

If men and their partners believe that circumcision offers protection from HIV infection, they may be less inhibited (“disinhibited”) in their sexual activities and engage in higher HIV risk behaviors, thereby mitigating a partially protective effect of MC. Fortunately, the perception that MC provides full protection against HIV and STIs was found to be generally rare, but it was expressed by a few study participants in South Africa and in Nyanza Province, Kenya (Bailey et al., 2002; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). In focus groups in Kenya, Malawi and Zambia a concern about the possibility of behavioral disinhibition was inevitably expressed. Most participants did seem to appreciate the concept of risk reduction opposed to risk elimination (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Similarly in Swaziland 87% of study participants advocated having only one partner and 94% promoted condom use for circumcised men (Tsela & Halperin, 2006).

There is some evidence of behavioral disinhibition among circumcised men. A study in South Africa found a significant association between circumcision status and the higher reported number of non-spousal lifetime partners (Lagarde et al., 2003). Circumcised men in Uganda were found to engage in more HIV risk behaviors than uncircumcised men (Bailey et al., 1999). In addition to reporting more extramarital partners in the previous year (1.13 vs. 0.62, $P < 0.01$), circumcised men had an overall higher “risk profile”. A few respondents in another South African study expressed the belief that MC potentially encouraged adultery as newly circumcised men were curious to test the new shape of the penis (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

One study in Botswana found that participants felt that circumcision before the age of six years may help to avoid a change in sexual behavior associated with sense of increased protection due to circumcision

(Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). Men attending beer halls in Harare, Zimbabwe were aware of the partial protection against HIV provided by MC, and had a good understanding of the limitations and the concept of risk reduction (Halperin et al., 2005).

Other Reasons Not to Circumcise

Other barriers to circumcision, mentioned by participants, were lack of access to health care, required time away from work, the loss of penile sensitivity, reduction in penis size, decreased ability to satisfy women, excessive sexual desire, increased promiscuity (Bailey et al., 2002; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003), and the perception of circumcision as old-fashioned (Lagarde et al., 2003; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Facilitators of MC Acceptability

Hygiene

Penile hygiene was universally recognized as being extremely important and was viewed as a major benefit of circumcision (Bailey et al., 2002; Halperin et al., 2005; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001). A great majority of participants, both male and female from multiple studies, agreed that it was much easier for a circumcised man to maintain cleanliness (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

The majority of participants, including women, believed that it was worrisome that men do not maintain proper hygiene. Because women were the primary providers of water, poor penile hygiene was often seen as a woman’s failing (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). In both Zambia and Malawi women were considered responsible for cleaning their partners’ penises after sexual intercourse. Additionally, women in these populations linked their own risk of STIs to their partners’ genital hygiene (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Ease of maintaining proper penile hygiene proved a major factor in women’s acceptability of circumcision (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006).

Protection from STIs and HIV

Hygiene as a mechanism of protection from STIs was mentioned by a great number of participants (Bailey

et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). It was held that germs, dirt, bacteria, and viruses had a greater opportunity to proliferate in the warm moist environment beneath the foreskin (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Participants also expressed a belief that it would be easier to detect rashes and/or ulcerations with the foreskin removed allowing for earlier treatment (Bailey et al., 2002; Ngalande et al., 2006). The foreskin was also perceived as a portal of entry for sexually transmitted infection as the tissue is considered prone to traumatic injury during sexual intercourse (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). MC was recognized as a medical procedure to reduce or eliminate penile ulcerations and diseases of the penis (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001). Conversely, a minority of respondents in Zambia reported that the circumcised penis was “always dry”, “susceptible to cracking”, and that this state provided a portal of entry for bacteria and viruses (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted).

Seventy percent of Botswana study participants willing to circumcise their male child listed protection from STIs or HIV among their reasons for doing so (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). In Nyanza Province, Kenya, 79% of uncircumcised men and 81% of women believed that it was easier for uncircumcised men to acquire STIs compared to circumcised men. This belief dropped to 43% and 60%, respectively, concerning the acquisition of AIDS (Mattson et al., 2005). In Swaziland, 81% of participants stated that MC reduced risk of STIs and 18% believed that MC reduced risk of HIV (Tsela & Halperin, 2006). In Tanzania STIs were considered more severe and more infective in uncircumcised men, with ulcers healing faster in those who are circumcised (Nnko et al., 2001). Nearly all commercial sex workers believed that there exists a strong association between lack of circumcision and STIs, including HIV (Ngalande et al., 2006). In South Africa (Scott et al., 2005), no association was found between willingness to be circumcised and perceived health benefits. It was belief about sexual pleasure that was the strongest predictor of being willing to undergo circumcision.

Acceptability by Other Ethnic Groups

Common reasons given for favoring MC were the social, political, and sexual benefits that could accrue when interacting with those in predominantly

circumcising groups (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). The Luo believed that they were often discriminated against by other Kenyans due to their circumcision status which led to political exclusion and even security concerns in times of social upheaval (Bailey et al., 2002). Many younger men from traditionally non-circumcising groups cited being accepted as a sexual or marriage partner by women from other ethnic groups as an important reason to be circumcised (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001).

Sexual Pleasure Among Circumcised versus Uncircumcised

How circumcision is perceived to influence sexual drive, sexual performance, and sexual pleasure for the man himself or for his partner is likely to influence decision making around MC. Participants in many studies believed that circumcision enhances sexual pleasure (Bailey, Unpublished; Bailey et al., 2002; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Most studies assessed three factors associated with sexual activity based on circumcision status: sexual performance, sexual pleasure for men, and sexual pleasure for women. Fifty percent of circumcised and 30% of uncircumcised participants in South Africa believed that MC increased sexual performance, while only 21% and 14%, respectively, believed that MC decreased sexual pleasure (Lagarde et al., 2003). Other studies found that a high proportion of men and a majority of women believed that circumcised men enjoyed sex more than uncircumcised men (Mattson et al., 2005; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). About half of female participants reported preference for circumcised men (Lagarde et al., 2003; Mattson et al., 2005). Many had no preference. A study in South Africa found that men were 8 times more likely to prefer circumcision if they believed that circumcised men enjoyed sex more, and 6 times more likely to prefer circumcision if they believed that women enjoy sex more with circumcised men (Scott et al., 2005). Other studies did not find a consensus about circumcision status and sexual pleasure on the part of the man or the woman (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). For some, circumcision was irrelevant to pleasure, as pleasure was more related to emotional attachment and past sexual experience (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006). Attitudes about circumcision and pleasure may

be different in areas where dry sex is practiced (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted).

Other Reasons to Circumcise

Other reasons to be circumcised reported by participants included the belief that it was easier for circumcised men to use condoms (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002; Bailey et al., 2002; Kebaabetswe et al., 2003), that MC proved manhood, that aim during urination was improved, and that not being circumcised brought bad luck (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Time and Setting of Circumcision Procedure

Preferred Age at Circumcision

The ages at which males become circumcised will have an effect on how rapidly MC interventions may impact the HIV epidemic in any given area. Preferred age at circumcision varied both between and within studies. There appeared to be two leading directions exhibited by many studies: either circumcise males as babies due to a simpler procedure, less fear, easier care, and faster healing, or circumcise males around puberty and adolescence when boys can decide and take care of the wound for themselves (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005).

Among the nine countries where acceptability studies have been undertaken, only in Botswana were most participants in favor of circumcision in infancy and early childhood. Fifty-five percent of respondents were in favor of circumcising children under 6 years old with half of those preferring neonatal circumcision (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). In all other areas a significant minority were in favor of infant or early childhood MC, but most favored circumcision between ages 8–16 years with very few saying that over 18 years was best. Those who advocated for infant circumcision did so for reasons relating to decreased pain during the procedure and faster healing times (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted), although babies under 1 year of age were thought to experience excessive pain, leading to crying and fevers (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). Participants from Malawi viewed infants especially vulnerable to potential complications of MC due to “lack of maturity” and difficulty of timely detection of bleeding due to babies being carried on the mothers’ backs (Ngalande et al., 2006).

Many studies reported strong beliefs among participants that circumcision should take place before the onset of sexual activity (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Ages 7–13 years were thought to be best since the boy could make the decision for himself, understand the significance of the event, take care of the wound himself, heal faster than if done post-pubertally, and has likely not begun sexual activity (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Circumcision as an adult or post-pubertally was reported by many to be undesirable due to higher risk of complications, pain during the procedure (Ngalande et al., 2006; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003), and painful erections after MC, leading to complications and delays in healing (Bailey et al., 2002; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006).

Many people from traditionally non-circumcising communities felt that they had insufficient knowledge to make a decision about when best to circumcise. They preferred to consult clinical professionals to get their advice (Bailey et al., 2002; Ngalande et al., 2006). Practitioners interviewed in Kenya and Malawi preferred not to perform neonatal circumcision due to the small size of the penis and foreskin, potentially leading to higher rates of errors and complications. These providers preferred to perform the operation at ages 8–12 years (Bailey et al., 2002).

Preferred Circumcisers

In areas where traditional circumcision is uncommon, the preference is overwhelmingly for a medical practitioner to be the provider. All studies reported fear of infection, bleeding, excessive pain, and possible mutilation at the hands of traditional circumcisers (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Lagarde et al., 2003; Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted). In Zambia (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted), even in the traditionally circumcising area of Zambezi District, the majority believed medical doctors to be experienced, more apt to use sterile equipment, able to minimize pain through anesthesia, and capable of dealing with complications. The few participants who preferred traditional surgeons viewed these practitioners as more experienced and more willing to maintain confidentiality (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted).

Scott et al. found that 77% of male Zulu preferred MC by a doctor or medical surgeon, 8% by a nurse, 11% by traditional circumciser, and 3% by other providers (Scott et al., 2005). Another study based in South Africa observed that MC was commonly

performed in both “initiation schools” and by clinical providers. The more common circumcision was in an ethnic group, the less likely it was done in medical settings (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003).

Acceptability in Certain Populations

Women's Beliefs and their Influence

The influence of women on the decision to circumcise is likely to be highly variable across cultures and across families within communities. However, in many settings, women, as mothers and as partners, are likely to have considerable influence, even if it is not overt. Any effort to promote MC will be more successful if it appeals to women as well as men.

Bailey et al. (2002) found that women's beliefs may have a strong influence on male acceptability of circumcision in western Kenya. This influence may stem from women's strong emphasis on penile hygiene for their partners, and the wish to protect their young sons from acquisition of infections as they become sexually active. Scott et al. (2005), on the other hand, suggested that in South Africa women are likely to have only an indirect influence through the male perception that women enjoy sex more with circumcised men. A different study from South Africa found that women had a strong influence on men's decision to circumcise, often scheduling the appointment for their boyfriends or husbands. Single mothers, however, were believed to have no influence over their teenage sons' decisions to circumcise (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Thirteen percent of circumcised participants in yet another South African study (Lagarde et al., 2003) reported undergoing circumcision because their partner expressly requested it.

Acceptability in Youth

Two out of thirteen studies assessed acceptability of MC among adolescents. In Tanzania, school aged boys and girls believed that it was easier for an uncircumcised man to acquire STIs, that it was easier for a circumcised man to maintain proper genital hygiene, and that circumcision enhanced sexual pleasure for both partners (Nnko et al., 2001). As in most areas, adolescent boys linked circumcision with modernity and good hygiene. Overall, adolescent males and females proved to be knowledgeable about potential benefits of MC (Nnko et al., 2001; Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003). Nnko et al. (2001) observed that knowledge and a positive attitude about MC became most obvious in secondary schools due to the effects of increased ethnic mixing.

Many studies found that younger participants were more likely to view circumcision favorably than their elders (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Mattson et al., 2005; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001). In Botswana, only 43% of men ages 45–59 years were willing to be circumcised, compared to 65% of 25–34 year-olds (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003). In Kenya, younger men were more likely to accept circumcision. Among those 16–21 years old, 71% said that they would prefer to be circumcised; whereas only 56% of those over 21 years preferred to be circumcised (Bailey, 2001). Results from more qualitative studies entailing focus group discussions were consistent with these quantitative results. Younger men in Zambia, Malawi and Tanzania were more likely to express a desire to be circumcised (Lukobo & Bailey, Submitted; Ngalande et al., 2006; Nnko et al., 2001).

Hypothetical versus Actual Acceptability

Asking people whether they might prefer to be circumcised under various hypothetical scenarios (e.g., if it is found to reduce risk of HIV acquisition; or if it is at minimal cost and safe) is one means of assessing acceptability. A more realistic means is to discover where MC services are available and see who takes advantage of the services. Alternatively, one can offer the services in non-circumcising communities and see the response. This approach permits assessment of not just numbers seeking the services, but also the ages and population segments that respond as well as factors that inhibit or facilitate uptake of the services.

A trial intervention in Siaya District, Kenya—an area where circumcision is not traditionally practiced—was introduced in 1999 (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002). During a 25 month period, 433 circumcisions were performed in health facilities where only 6 procedures had been done in the previous year. In a comparison district, where no intervention was available, just 24 circumcisions were performed over the same period. Demand for MC services was judged to be high but was highly dependent on cost. When the price charged for a circumcision was reduced from \$3.62US to \$1.45US, demand surged, and 50% of all circumcisions occurred during the 2 months when the price was reduced. The median age of those circumcised was 18 years; 25% were below age 12 years, and an estimated 35% were circumcised before their sexual debut. The researchers felt that a greater number of younger males would have been circumcised had parental permission not been required for those under age 18 years and if the cost were reduced permanently, since older

males tended to have more financial support (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002). The results from this trial intervention are consistent with results from studies of hypothetical acceptability indicating that cost is consistently found to be a major barrier to uptake of circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising communities.

Further evidence of acceptability comes from the one RCT completed in Orange Farm, South Africa and the two ongoing trials in Kisumu, Kenya and Rakai, Uganda, both of which have completed enrollment. Because every participant in these three trials stands a 50% chance of being circumcised immediately upon randomization, all of them must prefer to be circumcised in order to enroll in the study. The Orange Farm trial screened 3,483 young men, ages 18–24 years. We do not know what proportion of the total population of 18–24 year olds these men represent. However, that all but 203 (5.8%) of the men consented to enroll indicates that acceptability was high (Auvert et al., 2005). In Kisumu, Kenya, a community in which 90% of adult men are uncircumcised, 6,686 of the 34,200 (19.5%) uncircumcised men in the population ages 18–24 years came to the study clinic seeking to enroll in the study. Of these, 4,489 (67.1%) were eligible to enroll, and of those eligible, 68.5% accepted to be randomized (Bailey, 2006). This acceptability rate agrees very closely with the 70% figure found in the sample by Mattson et al. (2005) from the same area. In Rakai, Uganda, a rural community in which 83% of adult men are uncircumcised, approximately 45% of all eligible HIV uninfected men in the community enrolled in the trial before enrollment was closed (R. Gray, personal communication). That such large numbers of men are willing to join these trials suggests that circumcision acceptability is high and that uptake of MC in these communities could be rapid, if sufficient resources are available to accommodate large numbers of procedures.

Discussion

Through searching electronic databases and contacting authors, we identified 13 studies from nine countries that include investigation of the acceptability of MC in traditionally non-circumcising regions in sub-Saharan Africa. We found one additional report of a pilot intervention introducing MC services into health facilities where circumcision was little practiced. The level of acceptability across the nine countries appears greater than might be expected, considering that all thirteen communities where the studies were per-

formed were all traditionally non-circumcising. The lowest level of acceptability by uncircumcised men (29%) was reported from eastern Uganda in a study conducted in 1997, before MC became well recognized as possibly being associated with STIs and HIV (Bailey et al., 1999). More than half of men in the regions studied appear to be receptive, if not eager, to become circumcised.

Cost, fear of pain, and concern for safety were the three most consistent barriers to acceptability of MC. In communities where circumcision is the norm families expect to incur the obligatory circumcision expenses negating the importance of cost. In non-circumcising communities circumcision is regarded as a voluntary procedure that may be unlikely to take precedence over competing needs. Cost is viewed as including not only the payment for the procedure, but also the opportunity costs of time away from work and other income generating activities. Cost as a primary consideration was shown dramatically by the pilot intervention in Siaya, Kenya, where men came in large numbers when the charges were lowered to \$1.45US (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002). These results indicate that the true cost of the procedure will have to be supplemented to achieve significant uptake of MC.

The concerns for safety and pain are based partially on the perception of circumcision as a surgical procedure with inherent risks and partially on the occasional press releases publicizing mutilations and deaths. Personal knowledge of neighboring communities where traditional initiates withstand excruciating pain also likely plays a role. Sustained uptake of MC will require performance of the procedure with minimal adverse events. This can be achieved through proper training and supervision of practitioners, proper instrumentation and sterilization, complete instructions to patients, follow-up with patients, and over all attention to quality control (Krieger et al., 2005).

The studies we reviewed revealed that it is virtually universal that Africans equate circumcision with improved hygiene. Also widespread is the belief that circumcision leads to reduced incidence of STIs achieved through improved hygiene, reduction in the number and severity of scratches, tears and abrasions to which the foreskin is susceptible and through earlier detection of ulcers, leading to earlier treatment. Although not as frequent, a significant proportion of participants in the studies also saw circumcision leading to reduced risk of HIV acquisition through the same route. If MC is proven in the remaining two clinical trials to reduce incidence of HIV and some STIs (e.g., HPV, HSV-2, chancroid and gonorrhea),

this information will be consistent with the already existing beliefs of most sub-Saharan Africans.

Cultural norms, ethnic identity, and religious affiliation were viewed as central factors in acceptability of circumcision. Circumcision was associated with specific traditionally circumcising communities and with Muslims and members of a few minority Christian and animist sects. It will likely be important that confidentiality is maintained by circumcision practitioners, since stigmatization for being circumcised is a possibility in non-circumcising communities. An important conclusion reached by several studies was that circumcision was increasingly an issue of personal choice rather than ethnic identity (Rain-Taljaard et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). Urbanization, ethnic mixing, and exposure to other cultures and religions are conducive to higher acceptability of circumcision in traditionally non-circumcising ethnic groups.

In East and Southern Africa most MCs are done between ages 8 and 21 and the preferences for age at circumcision found in studies are consistent with these practices. However, a large enough proportion of people, especially mothers, preferred infant circumcision to consider making infant circumcision an available option. This should be an important consideration in designing MC interventions.

Information campaigns may be effective in increasing acceptability of MC. This was found to be true in Botswana and South Africa (Kebaabetswe et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). However, many studies demonstrated that both knowledge and acceptability of MC varies considerably by region within the same country. Therefore, informational campaigns may be more effective if targeted to particular communities.

Just as the international health community is concerned about the possibility that promotion of circumcision could lead to increases in risky sexual behavior (World Health Organization, 2005), participants in many of the studies reviewed were similarly concerned. Higher risk behaviors have been found to be associated with circumcision status previously in Uganda, Rwanda and Kenya (Bailey et al., 1999; Seed et al., 1995; Tyndall et al., 1996), as well as in the Orange Farm RCT (Auvert et al., 2005). This underlines the importance of the counseling and education that must be provided to men who undergo circumcision, reinforcing the idea of MC reducing, not eliminating, the risk of HIV and other STIs.

There are several limitations to the studies that we reviewed. All used convenience sampling to recruit participants. The results could be biased if recruits were more likely to participate if they had a favorable view of MC. This may not be a concern, since most

studies had nearly 100% participation by those who were asked to participate. Only two studies verified the circumcision status of the participants (Lagarde et al., 2003; Nnko et al., 2001) and none of the studies verified MC status of partners of interviewed women. The direction in which this may have biased results is not clear. There were differences across studies in design: some were more qualitative with open ended questions asked in a group discussion setting, others were more quantitative using closed-ended questions during a one-on-one interview. There was variation in the wording of questions to participants about the conditions under which they would accept circumcision. Some studies were geographically restricted and, as a result, may have limited generalizability and lack of representativeness of populations. Geographical coverage was spotty within study countries, and some high HIV prevalence countries where MC is little practiced (e.g., Mozambique, Lesotho, Namibia) were not included. Lastly, there was variation in the time when the studies were conducted (range 1991–2006). Attitudes toward circumcision assessed by early studies (Bailey et al., 1999; Nnko et al., 2001) may have changed since the time of the study.

All studies attempted to assess peoples' beliefs and attitudes toward circumcision and their willingness to be circumcised under some hypothetical conditions sometime in the future. We cannot know from these studies what the actual uptake of circumcision would be if it were found to be protective in three clinical trials and was actively promoted. We have only one example of an introduction of MC services in a traditionally non-circumcising community (Bailey, Unpublished report to AIDSMARK, 2002), and this was at a time when circumcision could not be actively promoted, but could only be made available. Results from that intervention were instructive in that demand for safe circumcision was robust, but depended very much upon price.

The results from the thirteen available studies of acceptability of MC in nine countries in sub-Saharan Africa where circumcision is little practiced are very consistent. Acceptability of MC is likely to be high enough to have a significant impact on HIV prevalence in these communities, if MC is proven to have a protective effect similar to that found in observational studies and in the Orange Farm RCT. It is doubtful, given the consistency of results to date, that we will learn a great deal more by additional acceptability studies that pose hypothetical questions to participants. Instead, we recommend pilot interventions making circumcision services available in health facilities after training of clinicians and provision of proper

instruments and supplies. There are reports that demand for MC services is already high in many traditionally non-circumcising communities in East and southern Africa (Bangre, 2006; Nnko et al., 2001; PlusNews, 2006; Timberg, 2005). There is a danger that this increasing demand will be filled by unqualified practitioners causing unnecessary adverse events. Pilot interventions will serve simultaneously to test whether there truly is a growing niche and, if so, to gain experience in filling the niche with safe, affordable services. At the same time, much will be learned about the operational requirements for training, instrumentation, safety, counseling and follow-up of patients, supervision of staff, monitoring of behavioral disinhibition, and about how MC services can be integrated with HIV/STIs prevention services, including VCT, STIs diagnosis and treatment, behavioral counseling, condom promotion and anti-retroviral therapies.

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Male Circumcision to Prevent HIV Transmission and Acquisition: What Else do We Need to Know?

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Abstract There is growing interest and controversy regarding the promotion of male circumcision (MC) for the prevention of HIV transmission in Africa. Three randomized controlled studies has so far been stopped prematurely as evidence accumulated that showed that circumcision was superior to no circumcision in preventing HIV acquisition among sexually active men in Africa. To some people, the evidence is overwhelming and MC should be promoted aggressively. Others suggest cautious decision making. This paper attempts to review a continuum of perceptions and suggest that the decision to scale-up male circumcision cannot just be based on randomized controlled trial results.

Keywords Male Circumcision · HIV Prevention · AIDS in Africa

‘The findings suggest that circumcision should be advocated, just as we advocate condoms...We’ve got to do everything we can to decrease the rate of transmission of this disease.’ (Marx, 1989).

In this journal, Westercamp and Bailey (2006) report on a review of studies aimed to describe the

acceptability of male circumcision (MC) for the prevention of HIV transmission in Africa. One message that comes out clear from their review is that the authors believe that further acceptability studies will add very little to what is already known about acceptability of MC especially in Eastern and Southern Africa. This is the region of the world heaviest hit by HIV and also likely to benefit most from any intervention aimed at reducing the spread of HIV, including MC. Here I offer my perspective on MC for HIV prevention.

The Benefits of Male Circumcision

Historically, male circumcision was once considered a ‘cure’ for masturbation, gout, epilepsy, and insanity (Alanis & Lucidi, 2004). Lack of male circumcision has been reported as a risk factor for penile cancer and cervical cancer for women whose male sexual partners are not circumcised (Micali, Nasca, Innocenzi, & Schwartz, 2006). Interest in MC was rekindled when the link between male circumcision and HIV transmission was reported in observational studies. With the exception of a few studies that have reported equivocal results, meta-analyses have concluded that all in all, male circumcision (MC) is protective against HIV acquisition. However, observational studies, because of how they are designed, are not considered the ‘gold standard’ of evidence on the protective effect of any disease protective intervention. It was therefore of note that Auvert et al. (2005) reported the first randomized-controlled study from Orange Farm, South Africa, which confirmed that MC is protective of HIV acquisition. The reason is simple. Medical decision making is a conservative endeavor and change is most

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often taken when previous research results are corroborated.

The benefits of MC are diverse ranging from prevention of urinary tract infection in boys (Singh-Grewal, Macdessi, & Craig, 2005); and as a treatment for Phimosis, balanitis, condyloma (Fink, Carson, & Davellis, 2002). Circumcision can also be performed for cultural and religious reasons. Westercamp and Bailey (2006) report on a study from Malawi by Ngalande et al (2006). In this study, women especially reported the absence or reduction of smegma (*madeya* or *gaga* in Chichewa, literally husks) on the circumcised penis as desirable. Chichewa or Nyanja is spoken by in Malawi, Mozambique, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

Of all the characteristics that humans share with apes, that the need for penile cleaning after sex is common is interesting. O'hara and Lee (2006) have reported on subspecies of chimpanzee (*Pan troglodytes schweinfurthii*), from Budongo Forest, Uganda, which as a custom clean their penises with leaves or bare hands after sexual intercourse. There is no doubt therefore that these chimpanzees detest *madeya/gaga*.

While Westercamp and Bailey (2006) have reported on the hygienic benefits of MC, it is obvious that their main concern is the link between lack of circumcision and HIV. There can be other, non-invasive ways of ensuring that penises are clean other than suggesting MC. The Ugandan chimpanzees' way, but with water, is an option!

How Might Male Circumcision Work to Prevent HIV Infection?

There have been various explanations as to how MC works in preventing transmission of HIV. The larger surface area of the mucosa of the uncircumcised man has been suggested as increasing the potential portal of entry of HIV. The underside of the foreskin has been identified as replete with immunological cells including Langerhans cells which are primary targets for HIV. A removed or reduced foreskin therefore means less immunological cells and consequently less target cells that HIV can use in order to enter the body. The foreskin has also been suggested as prone to tears during sexual intercourse; with these tears acting as entry and exit points of HIV during the current and subsequent sexual intercourse. The association between MC and prevention of (other) sexually transmitted infection is well known. As STIs are an important risk factor in the transmission and acquisition of HIV, with MC preventing STIs, HIV is also prevented.

It has also been postulated that the keratinization (hardening) of the surface of the penile glans that is associated with MC could contribute to its protective effect. Keratinization takes time to develop, which suggests that if the maximal effect is to be obtained, it will occur several months to years after MC is performed. In the Auvert et al. trial (2005) it was possible that we missed out from witnessing the protective effect of MC several years after the procedure, as the study was conducted for about 18 months. This is important, because in real life settings, it is the long term protective effect, which can be enhanced or wear off with time, that will matter most.

Which Circumcision?

Male circumcision is defined as the surgical removal of *all or part* of the penile foreskin. If MC is to be adopted as a recommended HIV preventing measure, the question as to how much to remove of the foreskin will certainly arise. Is it that the more foreskin removed the better or is there a point where further removal will not change the transmission dynamics? For now, we could say we don't know, although it may appear that the less foreskin remains, the more protection there is.

How do We Interpret Acceptability of Male Circumcision?

Westercamp and Bailey's (2006) study was a review of acceptability studies conducted in Eastern and southern Africa. Study participants in the reports reviewed were diverse including women, men, the old and the young. Of note was that women's high acceptability for the circumcision of sexual partners and their sons. Women may be instrumental in some cases of MC but may also not matter much in many other cases if they are not key decision makers or their influence of decisions is limited. There are many reports about situations where women cannot decide matters regarding their own bodies in terms of reproductive health much less the bodies of men. The urgency to identify effective microbicides for the prevention of HIV acquisition partly stems from the fact that women are unable to determine when and whether to have sex and whether a condom is to be used. A covert method of HIV prevention is therefore urgently needed. The high total fertility rate among many developing nation women also is explained in terms of women not having cultural space to determine their destiny and exercise their own wishes. This therefore suggests that it is

especially important to interpret with caution the ‘acceptability’ of MC among women, who may not have much cultural space as to whether MC eventually occurs or not.

It is encouraging that in most of the acceptability studies (however the term acceptability was defined) high prevalence of approval was reported. Over 50% of men in Kenya, 29% Uganda, and over 50% in Botswana (Kabaabetswe et al., 2003), South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania have been reported as accepting circumcision if the procedure would reduce the risk of acquisition of HIV. As Westercamp and Bailey (2006) suggest in this Journal, it will not be until the procedure is offered realistically (not in a hypothetical sense) that we will be able to know if these ‘acceptability’ figures can be realized in practice. Mantell et al. (2005) in a review of the literature on the acceptability of microbicides for the prevention of HIV suggested the need for standardization of the term ‘acceptability’. The same can be said about acceptability studies on male circumcision.

Almost all the MC acceptability studies fail to represent reality in one major way; in that the choice of the intervention is presented as if in real life the study participants only have that intervention to choose from. In real life however, a study participant in a MC acceptability study also has the male condom, has ARVs to think about, abstinence and other measures to consider; and yet the study question is usually posed as if the current proposed intervention were the only one. If my reasoning is true, then an MC only acceptability misrepresents reality. One study that has moved a step closer to reality is that reported by Kulczycki, Kim, Duerr, Jamieson, and Macaluso (2004). In this study, 108 women in stable sexual relationships recruited from reproductive health clinic were randomly assigned to use 10 male or female condoms, followed by use of 10 of the other type. After having experience of both methods (male and female condoms), they were allowed to indicate their preferences. Male circumcision as HIV prevention arena should be like that. There should not just one method on the table to choose from as is the case in most hypothetical MC acceptability studies.

Circumcision acceptability studies also fail to represent reality in that rarely are the potential adverse effects of MC, which include physical, psychological and social effects are not present for the study participants to make an informed decision. Emphasis is placed on the protective effect on HIV, little information is provided in risk of bleeding, infection, amputation and pain. In trained hands, the risks of adverse events are extremely rare but they exist.

Lessons from Condom Acceptability Studies

Several studies have reported high knowledge and acceptability of condom use to prevent HIV transmission. Coffey et al. (2006) have reported on a study aimed to evaluate acceptability of the PATH Woman’s Condom among user populations in Mexico, South Africa and Thailand. In this non-randomized, non-blinded study conducted among 20 couples per site. It was reported that women from all sites reported that the PATH woman’s condom was easy and comfortable to insert, and the pouch and ring were very stable during use. Both women and men reported that the comfort and sensation of sex while using the condom was acceptable. This is certainly encouraging, especially if one did not have prior knowledge of previous female condom acceptability studies conducted several decades ago and yet currently the intervention is yet to be accessible to or preferred by a significant proportion of women.

Contrast the often reported high acceptability of condoms among the general population with the report by Kiragu et al. (2005) in a study of 692 health workers from five hospitals in Zambia. Only 60% of health professionals in Zambia believed that condoms were effective in preventing HIV transmission. One wonders what proportion of non-health professionals will believe condoms are effective when even 40% of health workers doubt condoms are effective.

Lessons from Antenatal Clinics

In the maternal and reproductive health spheres, it is well known that many women in developing countries express desire to limit the number of children they have but fail to achieve their desires. Similarly, when asked about the desire to deliver at a health facility where supervision by a trained midwife is assured, many women indicate such desire but fail to eventually deliver at a health facility (Lule & Ssembatya, 2003). This is not a particularly new finding in human behavior dynamics.

Age at Circumcision

If MC must be effective against sexual transmission of HIV, then it must be performed way before exposure. Many issues determine sexual debut but age is normally one common determinant. Circumcising at birth or at least within a few months of birth can be a reasonable thing to do as there normally remain many

years before sexual exposure. However, like many other interventions that adults assent for children such as vaccinations, there is no longer room for choice for the recipient of the procedure. There is therefore divided opinion on whether it is humane or not to subject neonates to MC. The consideration is that a permanent procedure is being conducted on an individual unable to consent (Fox & Thomson, 2005).

Another option is to circumcise just before sexual debut. In many communities, the ages between 10 and 14 years may be suitable. The challenge at this stage may be that the minor's assent may be required. Doing so may also mean that the minor understands the reason for the procedure. In communities where there is concern about sexual education to young children, this may be an important issue.

If MC is to be offered after sexual debut, there will be concerns as to whether the individual is already infected. Otherwise there is potential for some people to seek MC after already being exposed to and being infected with HIV. It is therefore important that if circumcision becomes policy, we will also have to address the needs of people already infected with HIV. The potential individual benefits of a person already infected include protection from STIs and acquiring new strains of HIV. Because HIV infection is currently a lifelong condition, there may not be sufficient incentives for MC to an individual who is already HIV infected.

The Socio-Cultural Meaning of Male Circumcision

Male circumcision is not an alien practice in sub-Saharan Africa. In fact many African communities were circumcising males before European colonialization (Ahlberg, 1994). In some countries, the rituals surrounding the practice were deemed heathen by the westerners so that new converts were discouraged from these rituals. Among the Kikuyu in Kenya, circumcision was a rite of passage as a boy transitioned into adulthood. Not only was the boy transformed into a man, but also the boy's parents attained status as their child had been circumcised. In many cases, the initiate was expected to endure pain.

Traditional male circumcision has been associated with factors that can be considered as risk factors for the transmission of HIV, while in some communities, preventative factors can be identified. Among the Lomwe in Malawi and Mozambique, male circumcision is associated with the practice of *kuchotsa fumbi* (removing the dust). What happens in *kuchotsa fumbi* is that initiates are advised by their peers (*aphungu*)

that in order for them to be duly considered as adults, they must have sex with a female. Among the Kikuyu in Kenya, traditional customs advocated for sexual abstinence in the small rooms (*thingira*) where the initiates reside for healing and counseling after the circumcision. However, the boy's peers (*aturi*) may pressure the initiate into having sex upon release from the *thingira*, a process called *kukurwo mbiro*. There is some evidence that the initiation process amongst the Kikuyu had established taboos, which made premarital sexual intercourse punishable (Ahlberg, 1994).

If MC is to become policy in an effort to prevent the spread of HIV, there will obviously be a need to score the potential environments where the procedure is to be carried out. Will traditional circumcisers be the major players or will the procedure have to be conducted in health facilities? Will the traditional rituals associated with MC be promoted, discouraged or modified? Will initiates attain the same social recognition they did, partly because they endured pain? Will MC have the same social meaning among *aphungu* if there will be no removing of the dust? These are some of the outstanding issues that Westercamp and Bailey (2006) ignored when they presented that no further acceptability studies will add new information to the literature.

What are we Waiting for?

Lie, Emmanuel, and Grady (2006) suggest that if the two on-going randomized controlled trials on male circumcision from Uganda and Kenya confirm Auvert et al. (2005) findings, there would be sufficient grounds to advocate for MC in high HIV prevalence areas. It is interesting that Marx as early as 1989 had advocated the same. What will be the message? Will it be to impress the governments to fund free access? Will it be the governments encouraging people to come forward for the procedure? As is generally known, epidemiological information may not necessarily translate into policy (Ashford, Smith, De Souza, Fikree, & Yinger, 2006); It is unlikely that any amount of published research studies will necessarily result in adoption of MC as a prime HIV preventive tool. Also unlike ARVs which in some countries needed drug approvals, MC is not in that category as willing men are even now, not prevented from accessing the procedure. On the other hand, for a drug, the relevant drug licensing boards needed to approve before the drug is made available.

Having the necessary in-country policy on MC is just the first step in ensuring wider access of MC. Will it be rationed as has been the case with many other public

health interventions when in short supply (McGough, Reynolds, Quinn, & Zenilman, 2005) for example? The lack of or the availability of vaccines, post exposure drug prophylaxis, condoms, and vaginal microbicides will all influence decisions regarding MC.

Human Resources for Scaling-Up

Almost all of the eastern and southern African countries that have a high burden of HIV also suffer from shortage of adequate numbers of human resources for health services. This problem has a multi-factorial origin, which includes the low production from training institutions as a result of constraints in investments towards training and migration (Loewenson & McCoy, 2004). Countries like Malawi and Zambia for instance, have never relied on physicians for the delivery of clinical services. Paramedics are in general the largest group of health professionals responsible for providing clinical and surgical care (Dovlo, 2004).

There has also been significant out-migration of nurses from many eastern and southern African countries to the developed world. Just as when scaling-up for ARVs was being planned, the question as to which amongst the different cadres of health professionals would provide the main or leading clinical services was considered. Although MC is a relatively simple and straight forward surgical procedure in trained hands, complications are more likely to occur when poorly or non-trained person perform the operation.

There are just not enough surgeons in many African countries (Evans, 2005). Steinlechner, Tindall, Mkandawire, & Chimangeni (2006) reported that in 2003, all the 21 district hospitals in Malawi had no surgeon. Surgical procedures were thus mainly done by clinical officers. Fenton, Whitty, and Reynolds (2003) reported that clinical officers conducted 65% of all caesarean section deliveries in Malawi while physicians did only 35% and 8.7% of caesarean sections had anesthetics provided by a non-trained staff.

Behavioral Dis-Inhibition

A meta-analysis by Crepaz, Hart, and Marks (2004) reported that the likelihood on unprotected sex was higher among individuals who believed that HAART reduced HIV transmission. Will knowledge that MC was protective result in increased exposure to HIV as was the case in the Auvert et al (2005) study? It is interesting that Westercamp and Bailey (2006)

reported that belief about sexual pleasure was 'the strongest predictor of being willing to undergo circumcision'. This may also suggest if it were known that MC interfered negatively with sexual pleasure, the acceptability of the procedure may decline. There are controversies about the effect of MC on sexual pleasure and this area needs more research.

Male and not Female Circumcision

It is important that as we advocate for the 'scaling-up' of MC, the 'male before circumcision is not lost and is never replaced by 'female'. There should not be any doubt that female circumcision is a totally different matter altogether and it generally no longer acceptable by the global public health community.

Surgery is Usually the Last Resort

Traditionally in medical practice and disease prevention, lifestyle changes to prevent disease are thought about first before medical treatment. Surgery, even when disease has occurred is considered a last resort. Obviously, in some exceptional situations where there are no known effective lifestyle changes and/or drugs, surgery may be the first option. Although it is tempting to consider MC as first among equals with all the other HIV interventions, that mindset will be difficult to obtain for some policy makers and health practitioners. Unlike abstinence and consistent condom use, which when practiced are nearly 100% effective against sexual transmission, MC is not that effective.

Is there Need for Further Acceptability Studies?

The question as to whether any more studies aimed to describe hypothetical acceptability of MC to prevent HIV transmission and acquisition are needed can be asked. The answer depends on what else do we need to know that is not known as yet. Westercamp and Bailey's review (2006) reports on studies that are relatively recent. The passage of time can sometimes result in changes in acceptability of an intervention. How much time should elapse before another acceptability study is carried out? Time in essence is an indirect measure of what other changes are going on in a community. In case of HIV, education, poverty issues, availability of antiretroviral therapy will all have a bearing on MC acceptability.

While MC acceptability studies have been conducted among women, men and adolescents, it may also be important to study the acceptability of the interventions amongst community leaders and other key stakeholders such religious leaders and government officials. Male circumcision can be acceptable among general community members, but ultimately policy makers' decisions will make the procedure a national policy or at least formulate guidelines to ensure wider coverage.

In many African societies it is not just ordinary men and women or adolescents whose acceptability may have to be sought. There exist custodians of culture, those people who are entrusted to make decisions on behalf of the community. The Zulu proverb as quoted by Tambulasi and Kayuni (2005) can be quite instructive to public health officials, especially those coming from outside Africa. The proverb; '*Umuntu ngamuntu ngabantu abanye*' is translated as a person is a person through others. In many African cultures, in which MC may have to be focused, this concept that an individual exists and has meaning because of others is deep-rooted. Individualistic thinking is despised, in favor of collective thinking and decision making. Therefore, instead of only researching on the acceptability of MC by individuals, we will also have to attempt to study the acceptability of the procedure by key societal figures. None acceptance of MC by one traditional chief may have far reaching societal consequences beyond the acceptance of the procedure by a hundred.

The Language of Effect and Risk

The language that epidemiologists use to describe various concepts may not only be confusing to the general public but also among epidemiologists themselves. Terms like 'risk' are debated even among epidemiologists and have diverse meanings (Tam, 2006). Taking the language of epidemiology and applying it to an individual is extremely problematic. The protective effects of condoms and MC have been described for population groups.

What of the individual? What is the risk of acquiring HIV for an individual who has been circumcised? The answer is; we don't know. An individual's risk can either be 1 or 0 (stochasticists of course believe the risk can be anything from 0 to 1). But we cannot know about the risk a priori. Unfortunately, there have been people in the past and will be people in the future who will be circumcised but go on to contract HIV. The message therefore that the public will get from such experiences will be difficult to deal with. It will be

something like: 'male circumcision does protect against contracting HIV, but the protective effect is not perfect.' This situation is reminiscent to that of condoms where opponents have criticized the lack of perfect protection of condoms as suggesting that condoms should not be promoted. It is interesting to note that some people want perfect protection from HIV preventative tools but do not seek similar performance from other public health interventions such as vehicle seat belts, lipid lowering drugs and crash helmets.

Complications of Circumcision

Opponents of MC, opposing for whatever reasons (cultural, moral, ethical, religious), will likely want to highlight the adverse events and limitations associated with MC. People who oppose condom use have used the less than 100% protective capacity, the allergic reactions that may occur in some individuals, instances of slippage and bursting as reasons condoms ought not to be promoted. Interestingly or rather sadly, especially in South Africa, the fact that antiretroviral drugs (ARVs) are associated with side effects, which is a feature of essentially all drugs, is sometimes flagged as a reason not to promote ARVs. It is therefore incumbent upon the public health fraternity and policy makers to be forthcoming and active, rather than being reactive. All effort should be made to ensure MC is provided in as safe an environment as possible by trained personnel. It is also good public health practice to inform society that MC is not 100% effective just like most other public health interventions.

Final Remarks

Consider the Aristotelian idea of the 'ideal' universe, an utopia, which is perfect and we know that we have a clear idea of what causes what and what does not cause what. The epidemiological field however is the 'real' universe and things are not perfect. The imperfections however vary depending on the tools one has at his or her disposal. With the available evidence that we have however, there are certainly sufficient grounds, more grounds than was the case in 1989 when Marx called for advocacy to promote access to MC, for us to believe that MC is protective of HIV acquisition.

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responsible for the content of the paper or the decision to publish this article.

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Adult Male Circumcision Outcomes: Experience in a Developing Country Setting

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(b)(4)

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 20 Feb 2007 23:25:33 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Revised draft agenda and background document
Attachments: Male Circumcision Meeting)_BAckground.doc, MC Consultation Agenda (3).xls

Allan,

Here's a cleaned up version incorporating changes from the discussion at last week's meeting

Still some polishing needed but should be sent to the wider group with the minutes to get input from those unable to attend last week.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

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Public Health Issues regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for the prevention of HIV and other Health Consequences

Date: TBD during last 2 weeks of April

Issue:

- Review the evidence for and against male circumcision for prevention of HIV and other health consequences as it pertains to the United States
- Based on the science, clarify next programmatic steps and who should take them
- (As an aside, we discussed potential recommendations regarding health education by providers, funding, further research --- ??? should recommendations be made on circumcision itself)

Background and Rationale:

- For most people, individuals decisions to circumcise are generally not based on scientific grounds; however, science may influence decisions and it certainly influences availability of funding and how strongly health providers promote the procedure.
- Results of recent randomized trials...
- But unclear how these results pertain for HIV/STD/cancer prevention outside of settings with high HIV prevalence, or where heterosexual transmission is not the predominant mode of spread
- (Possibly take some wording out of PLoS article)

Objectives and Specific Outcomes

- Review science regarding circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Discuss potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made, and who should make them
- ? Other

Consultation: Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences

DAY 1		
Time	Subject	Possible Speaker(s)
9:00 AM	Welcome/Opening Moderator	Kevin Fenton, Rob Jansson (either P Sullivan or Peter, whomever does not do the Background talk)
9:15 AM	Background Point: What is the evidence arguing for MC for HIV prevention	Patrick Sullivan? Peter Kilmarx?
9:30 AM	Circumcision and HIV risk	Bob Bailey
10:00 AM	Other health effects of male circumcision	Stephen Moses
10:30 AM	Discussion	
11:00 AM	Break	
11:15 AM	Counterpoint: What is the evidence arguing against MC for HIV prevention?	TBD
11:45 AM	Discussion	
12:00 PM	Lunch Moderator:	John Douglas or Sevgi Aral (DSTDP)
	How great is the potential impact of MC on HIV transmission in US?	
1:00 PM	MC among MSM: modeling of impacts and CE and data needs	Sansom et al
1:15 PM	MC among MSW: how much of a contribution in US? (and data needs)	Sansom/Hutchinson et al
1:45 PM	Newborn MC: lifetime risk of HIV (and other conditions) (and data needs)	Schoen?
2:00 PM	Discussion	
2:30 PM	Break	
	What are the potential challenges to address in employing MC as an HIV prevention strategy in the US?	
	Moderator	Tom Coates
3:00 PM	Who would pay for MC?	Panel: HRSA, Kaiser, ? Blue Cross
3:30 PM	Who will perform procedures in adults?	Panel: urologist? Family practitioner Pediatrician?
4:00 PM	Risk communication re: MC (incomplete protection, disinhibition)	Brad Bartholow
4:30 PM	Ethical, religious, cultural concerns	? Vanessa Northington Gamble
5:00 PM	Adjourn Day 1	
DAY 2		
9:00 AM	Opening session	Dawn Smith (DHAP) (charge to working groups)
9:15 AM	Breakout sessions (concurrent)	
	1. Given the scientific data regarding risks and benefits for MSW in the U.S.: - What, if any, additional steps/recommendations are needed? - If needed, who should take the lead?	Lee Warner (DRH) Facilitator for working group
	2. Given the scientific data regarding risks and benefits for MSM in the US: - What, if any, additional steps/recommendations are needed? - If needed, who should take the lead?	Gary Marks (DHAP) Facilitator for working group
	3. Given the scientific data regarding risks and benefits for newborns in the US: - What, if any, additional steps/recommendations are needed? - If needed, who should take the lead?	Allan Taylor (DHAP) Facilitator for working group
12:00 PM	Lunch Moderator	Naomi Bock (GAP)
1:00 PM	Report back and summary	
3:00 PM	Adjourn	Rob Janssen (DHAP)

Stakeholder	Organization	N	Examples
HIV/STD prevention	Universities Health departments (NASTAD, NACCHO)	20	Coates, Auvert, Baily, Gray, Kreiss, Buchbinder, Klausner, Ken Mayer
Policy	AMA, NMA, NHMA, AAP, etc.	5	Chair of latest AAP recs committee, etc.
Pediatrics	AAP, other providers	3	Havens, Schoen
Urology	American Urological Assn?	2	
Community		5	MSM groups, HIV-related orgs, minority groups, STD clinic providers, anti-
Subtotal non-federal		35	
CDC		20	
Other Fed	Medicaid, NIH	20	
Grand Total		75	

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 30 Mar 2007 20:53:05 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: 07-PLME-PF-0140 Decision -- Quick response please
Attachments: Male Circ revision redline.dkscomments.doc

A very few comments in the attached version

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 7:14 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: 07-PLME-PF-0140 Decision -- Quick response please

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 3:58 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: 07-PLME-PF-0140 Decision -- Quick response please

I am attaching a revision for your review based on these comments. At the moment, our L drive is down, so I can't add the last few references indicated with highlights. However, the major changes in content should be included in this version. Please look especially at the new paragraph on page 10.

Because I would like to get this back asap in hopes that publication can occur before the consultation, I would like to request your comments/approval in COB on Wednesday, March 28. In the meantime, I will work on the reply to the reviewers.

Thanks,

Patrick

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Divisions of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: gyamey@plos.org [mailto:gyamey@plos.org]
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 7:10 PM
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: pssinatl@gmail.com
Subject: 07-PLME-PF-0140 Decision

Dear Patrick,

(b)(4)

(b)(4)

Sincerely,

Gavin Yamey
Senior Editor
PLoS Medicine

(b)(4)

(b)(4)

(b)(6)

(b)(4)

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 30 Mar 2007 15:45:49 +0000
To: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: 2007-Q-09451BLS - Assessment Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences

Jennifer,

I assume we have to wait for the other proposal to come in? Or could we just pick these guys and start negotiating to get their price down?

-A

From: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 10:55
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: 2007-Q-09451BLS - Assessment Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences

Please review the attached proposal from BL Seamon for the MC Consultation.

PGO is waiting on one more proposal.

From: Workman, Deborah (CDC/OCOO/PGO)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 10:46 AM
To: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Mast, Gerri E. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: 2007-Q-09451BLS - Assessment Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences

For your review

Deborah T. Workman
Contract Specialist
Center for Disease Control and Prevention
Acquisition and Assistance
Branch I
Procurement and Grants Office
Phone: 404-639-8893
Fax: 404-639-8095/8155
Email: at17@cdc.gov

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This survey is for internal CDC use only and the results will be used to improve business services.

Anyone working for CDC in any capacity is invited to participate in our survey.

From: Duane Howard [mailto:dhoward@blseamon.com]

Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 6:00 PM

To: Workman, Deborah (CDC/OCOO/PGO)

Cc: Sandra Selha; Brad Seamon

Subject: 2007-Q-09451BLS - Assessment Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences

Ms. Workman,

Attached are the Cost Proposal, Past Performance Matrix and Technical Proposal for the "Assessment Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Consequences." We appreciate this opportunity. Thank you for your consideration. Please call me or Brad Seamon if there are any questions. My phone number is (301) 577-0244 ext 15.

Thank you,

<<2007-Q-09451BLS.xls>> <<Experience Past Performance Matrix.doc>> <<2007-Q-09451BL.doc>>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 9 Apr 2007 20:15:03 +0000
To: 'Bellinda Schoof'
Cc: Herb Young; Pam Carter; Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: AAFP policy on HIV and Circumcision

Sorry to hear that but then we invited you (and everyone else) pretty late in the day.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Bellinda Schoof [<mailto:bschoof@aafp.org>]
Sent: Monday, April 09, 2007 2:25 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Herb Young; Pam Carter
Subject: RE: AAFP policy on HIV and Circumcision

Hi Dawn:

Unfortunately, both of the representatives we identified have conflicting meetings so we will have to take a pass at this meeting.

Thanks for inviting us to the meeting and hope all goes well. Thanks, Bellinda

>>> "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@CDC.GOV> 4/4/2007 5:50 PM
>>>

Great news!

-----Original Message-----

From: Bellinda Schoof [<mailto:bschoof@aafp.org>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 4:50 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Pam Carter
Subject: RE: AAFP policy on HIV and Circumcision

Yes, we will have someone there. I am confirming our rep's availability right now. I should have a name to you by tomorrow morning. Thanks, Bellinda

>>> "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@CDC.GOV> 4/4/2007 11:17 AM
>>>

Belinda,

Hi. The hotel is pushing us for the names of attendees in order to block the rooms. Will you know soon?

Thanks for your help with this.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Bellinda Schoof [<mailto:bschoof@aafp.org>]
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 4:48 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: AAFP policy on HIV and Circumcision

Hello Dr. Smith:

I'm following up to our discussion regarding the new WHO guidelines on circumcision. Following are the AAFP's policies on HIV Screening and Treatment and Circumcision.

[http://www.aafp.org/online/en/home/clinical/clinicalrecs/circumcision.ht](http://www.aafp.org/online/en/home/clinical/clinicalrecs/circumcision.html)

ml

<http://www.aafp.org/online/en/home/clinical/clinicalrecs/hiv.html>

Please let me know the specifics of the meeting on April 26-27 including what outcome is expected. Thanks so much, Bellinda

Bellinda K. Schoof, MHA, CPHQ
Scientific Affairs Manager
American Academy of Family Physicians
11400 Tomahawk Creek Parkway
Leawood, KS 66211-2672
Tel: (913) 906-6000 ext. 3160
(800) 274-2237 ext. 3160
Fax: (913) 906-6099
email: bschoof@aafp.org

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 29 Mar 2007 16:51:46 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Agenda question

I agree, but I was hesitant to change the focus of the second plenary away from HIV prevention, since that's the focus of our consultation. What do you think?

-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 10:57
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Agenda question

Or we could change the header on the session title. modeling impact and cost-effectiveness do seem be belong in the same session.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 10:46 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Agenda question

Hi, all.

I was just about to invite Edgar Schoen to give the talk on cost-effectiveness of neonatal MC, when I realized that the title of that session is *What is the potential impact of male circumcision on HIV transmission in the US?* The data I've seen from Schoen does not relate directly to HIV transmission, so I'm not sure he would fit well in that session. What we're really talking about for that presentation is Stephanie and Angela's lifetime risk study.

Would Schoen perhaps fit better in the slot we've got labeled *Evidence of other health effects of male circumcision?* I imagine he'd be willing to talk more generally about potential "other" benefits of MC, rather than the cost-effectiveness part, per se. Attached is his paper on costs/benefits of neonatal circ from Kaiser Permanente (JUrol 2006), to give you a flavor of what he might be able to discuss.

What are your thoughts?
-Allan

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 13 Apr 2007 20:25:02 +0000
To: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Cc: Lanier, David (AHRQ); Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Tracy,

My apologies. You inadvertently received the wrong letter. We will, indeed, be picking up your travel expenses.

Put your travel in GovTrip in the usual way and use CAN number 9211042. The hotel info, etc. should be the same. Let me know if you have any other questions.

-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 13, 2007 13:44
To: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Cc: Lanier, David (AHRQ); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Tracy,

No, you are correct. While we are not paying for most HHS participants, we agreed to pay for you and will do so. I've cc'd Allan Taylor who will let the contractor know.

From: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Sent: Friday, April 13, 2007 10:37 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Dear Dawn,

I received the materials for the meeting on circumcision. It looks like it will be a very interesting and informative meeting. I noticed in the logistics memo from the contractor that it stated that travel expenses will not be paid. I believe David and you had spoken earlier about the CDC paying to travel the AHRQ representative. Am I mistaken?

Thanks for any clarification on this.

Regards,

Tracy

Tracy Wolff, M.D., M.P.H.

Medical Officer

U.S. Preventive Services Task Force Program

Center for Primary Care, Prevention, and Clinical Partnerships

Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality

540 Gaither Road, Rockville, MD 20850

301-427-1616

Tracy.Wolff@ahrq.hhs.gov <<mailto:Tracy.Wolff@ahrq.hhs.gov>>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIHISTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 9:13 AM
To: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Cc: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Thanks!

Dawn K. Smith

From: Lanier, David (AHRQ)

Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 8:49 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Wolff, Tracy (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

Dawn: The USPSTF staff member we'd like to send to your meeting:

Tracy Wolff, MD, MPH

Center for Primary Care, Prevention and Clinical Partnerships

Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality

540 Gaither Road

Rockville, MD 20850

(301) 427-1616

Tracy.Wolff@ahrq.hhs.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Sunday, March 11, 2007 10:16 PM
To: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Subject: RE: Article on USPSTF methodology

David,

We'll pay travel for someone from your office (a gov employee) to attend the circumcision consultation. Just let me know the name and contact info.

From: Lanier, David (AHRQ)
Sent: Friday, March 09, 2007 11:37 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Article on USPSTF methodology

Dawn: Here's the methods paper from the Task Force that I mentioned. Nice speaking with you - I'll get back to you about the AHRQ/USPSTF representative for your consultation meeting.

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 1 Mar 2007 21:22:09 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll (comments from DRH)

I agree as well. I just got email from Peter Havens's office: they're checking on availability for Peter H. and for another individual (unnamed at this point). Shall we set up a call with them to encourage greater involvement as well?

-Allan

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 01, 2007 15:30
To: Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll (comments from DRH)

Thanks Lee. I do think we want robust involvement with AAP and not simply a few members as consultants. Can discuss tomorrow.

PK

From: Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)
Sent: Thursday, March 01, 2007 2:43 PM
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll (comments from DRH)

Wanda Barfield and Kay Tomashek from DRH provided the following suggestions to me regarding possible attendees from AAP:

1. Jim Couto (JCouto@aap.org) may know what AAP committee was/is involved with writing this statement.
2. A pediatrician/neonatologist leader in this area is Dr. Thomas Wiswell. He did the early studies on neonatal circumcision and outcomes in military populations. He would be an excellent resource and has some views that may differ from AAP. Here is his contact info:

Dr. Thomas Wiswell, M.D.

Cell (b)(6) (best way to reach him)

(b)(6)

Lee

From: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 10:45 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll

That sounds great Dawn, good idea. M

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 10:42 AM
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll

An update.

I have calls in to the American Urologic Association, their Patient Advocacy Council, and the American Association of Clinical Urologists. Hoping that will turn up some interested urologists to invite :)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 10:12 AM
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Attendee list/poll

Hi Patrick,

Very sorry for delayed feedback, was out of office and couldn't get back to my handwritten notes. List looks good. Also have some official feedback from DSTDP (as I wasn't so clear on previous email, sorry about that):

If possible, DSTDP would like to include some vs. others suggested here on the new list. I have actually run this through senior staff here and gotten their feedback, so this official recommendation. For technical the strong recs are for Stephen Moses and Judy Wasserheit as you have listed. Also recommended are **Tom Quinn (JHU) and Mike Cohen (UNC)** with the thought they they each bring unique contributions to this particular discussion. (Holmes and Golden are great, of course, very knowledgeable in many areas but the group here discussed this at length and came up with the ones above, if possible)

On modeling, **Geoff Garnett** from Imperial College in UK has been working on this area for Africa, and the word is he'd be very useful at this meeting if funds available (he would need to be covered, however, which may not be an option).

In policy area, the group here felt Rev. **Edmund Sanders** from Nashville, is excellent. He has been very helpful in the congenital syphilis elimination programmatic work, and particularly knowledgeable about HIV/STD issues among the African-American community. The feedback is that he is hard to reach by email, telephone works great.

On other news, Austin Hayes went ahead and checked through the CC lists in Atlanta, and we have **no urologist on staff here** -- so this had drawn a blank. I'm also going to check with John Douglas later today, but will guess up front he may not have a name. Another possibility is **I could write Bob Bailey or Stephen Moses and see if they have anyone they suggest -- shall I go ahead with that?** (Lee, do you have any thoughts for urologist?)

Mary

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Saturday, February 24, 2007 2:37 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Amanda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Attendee list/poll

All,

I am attaching a revised list of possible attendees for the circ consultation. Thanks to those who have provided email contracts for some of these folks.

I am planning on sending out an email poll over the weekend to try to see what dates might maximize participation. Peter, I need to get some guidance from you on a couple issues:

Inviting David Satcher – is there some protocol for inviting a former CDC director? I think it would seem odd for me to email him along with 40 others – I'm OK with doing it, but it feels like there should be some notification up the line before we send the poll.

International – would like to get your approval for the idea of inviting some international reps from (non-GAP) countries with similar prevention issues at their own expense as observers. Idea is that they will likely be having the same kind of discussions in their own countries, and this could give them a leg up.

I also wanted you to have a chance to identify any people on the list that you have questions about – once we ask someone about possible dates, it would be awkward if we didn't invite them. So if there is anyone you are not sure of, just flag them for me and I will not poll them; we can always add names to the poll later once we solidify our thinking.

Thanks,

Patrick

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch

Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Road NE, MS E46
Atlanta, GA 30333
404-639-2090
Fax: 404-639-8640
email: pss0@cdc.gov (note: 4th digit is the number zero, not the letter "O")
Courier address: 8 Corporate Blvd, Atlanta GA 30329

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 23 Apr 2007 22:53:13 +0000
To: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org
Cc: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

Dr. Schoen,

We would like to arrange a conference call prior to the consultation to discuss the concerns you outline below. We would be available at the following times (NOTE: all times Eastern Daylight):

Tuesday 12:00, 1:00, or 4:00 pm

Wednesday 3:30 pm

Would any of those times be convenient for you?

I will set up a conference line at:

866 836 1410 Passcode 585990

We look forward to speaking with you.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org [mailto:Edgar.Schoen@kp.org]

Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 4:52 PM

To: avtO@CDC.GOV

Cc: bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu; bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr; Bartholow, Brad (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); helen.weiss@lshtm.ac.uk; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCIHSTP); rebailey@uic.edu; RGray@jhsph.edu; spb@itsa.ucsf.edu

Subject: Castellsague et al 'IIPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

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"Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV>----- Forwarded by Edgar Schoen/CA/KAIPERM on 04/23/2007 01:10 PM -----

Dear Dr Taylor,

I cant believe that in a scientific meeting like this you have chosen Dr Robert Van Howe to be a speaker. I have known of his work for years as previous Chair of the AAP 1989 Task Force on Circumcision and as a reviewer for Pediatrics. His credibility is dubious and I and other who have worked in the field do not feel that his "studies" should be taken seriously. I am forwarding you this commentary on one of Dr Van Howe's "metanalysis"of HPV demonstrating the failing of his analysis of the evidence linking HPV to circumcision. As you can see he uses his own brand of creative statistics - invalid methodology to arrive at erroneous conclusions. Previously he used similar invalid statistical methodology to arrive at the conclusion that circumcision actually made it MORE LIKELY to get HIV(Int J STD AIDS 1999;10:8-16). These results were discredited in a future issue by Dr Stephen Moses a leading researcher on ! HIV and one of the authors of a recent RCT which is being reported at the meeting (see Moses S et al Int J STD AIDS 1999;10:626-628.). Recently I pointed out the major failings of a Van Howe publication on circumcision and urethral stenosis (attached to this letter). It goes on and on.Including Van Howe as a speaker pulls down the entire level of the conference in my opinion. I am disappointed - shocked might be a better word.

Ed Schoen

*

Brian Morris <brianm@medsci.usyd.edu.au>

04/18/2007 03:11 PM

To: brianm@medsci.usyd.edu.au

cc:

Subject: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

*

From Xavier Castellsague and co-workers

... this is a very good critical analysis of Van Howe's dubious meta-analysis in the same journal.

>J Infect. 2007 Apr 10; [Epub ahead of print]

>

>HPV and circumcision: A biased, inaccurate and misleading meta-analysis.

>

>Castellsague X, Albero G, Cleries R, Bosch FX.

>

>Servei d'Epidemiologia i Registre del Cancer, Institut Catala

>d'Oncologia, Gran via s/n, km 2.7, 08907 L'Hospitalet de Llobregat,

>Spain.

>

>Publication Types:

>LETTER

>

>PMID: 17433445 [PubMed - as supplied by publisher]

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 23 Apr 2007 22:25:24 +0000
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

I would be happy to join and/or organize the call if this sounds like a good plan.

-A

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 17:59
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

I think it's appropriate for Peter to call ES and explain the situation (CDC consultations and diversity of input) to him.

Tim

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 5:27 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

And here we go :(

Does anyone want to reply to calm the waters?

Dawn K. Smith

From: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org [mailto:Edgar.Schoen@kp.org]

Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 4:52 PM

To: avt0@CDC.GOV

Cc: bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu; bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr; Bartholow, Brad (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); helen.weiss@lshtm.ac.uk; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); rebailey@uic.edu; RGray@jhsph.edu; spb@itsa.ucsf.edu

Subject: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

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"Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV>----- Forwarded by Edgar Schoen/CA/KAIPERM on 04/23/2007 01:10 PM -----

Dear Dr Taylor,

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Ed Schoen

*

Brian Morris <brianm@medsci.usyd.edu.au>

04/18/2007 03:11 PM

To: brianm@medsci.usyd.edu.au

cc:

Subject: Castellsague et al 'HPV and circumcision ... critique of VanHowe's meta-analysis

*

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>

>Servei d'Epidemiologia i Registre del Cancer, Institut Catala

>d'Oncologia, Gran via s/n, km 2.7, 08907 L'Hospitalet de Llobregat,

>Spain.

>

>Publication Types:

>LETTER

>

>PMID: 17433445 [PubMed - as supplied by publisher]

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 23:15:03 +0000
To: Robert Bailey
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Dr. Bailey,

Indeed, thank you. We noticed that the error had not been corrected and distributed a corrected version of the agenda last night. Our deepest apologies for the typo.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Robert Bailey [mailto:rebailey@uic.edu]
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 18:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Per the agenda, as I pointed out to you previously, I will be talking about the results of the Kisumu, Kenya trial, NOT the Uganda trial. Rakai is in Uganda; thus the Uganda trial would be the same as the Rakai trial, which will be covered by Ron Gray.

Bob Bailey

At 08:46 PM 4/22/2007, you wrote:

>Colleagues,
>
>We are looking forward to your participation at the upcoming Consultation
>on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the United States. Attached
>are several documents for your reference:
>
>1. Consultation Agenda
>2. CDC Factsheet on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention
>3. Two overview papers that review many of the issues to be discussed at
>the consultation
>
>Thank you, and see you next week.
>
>
>
>Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
>
>LCDR, US Public Health Service
>Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
>National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
>(proposed)
>Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
>1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
>W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov
>
>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 17 Apr 2007 19:09:32 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

You know, another way to get at this would be to "plant" a question. We have several folks attending who would probably have a thing or two to say in response without having to develop a formal talk.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 2:01 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Well, we've struck out with Kaiser Family Foundation (Too bad, too: it sounds like they would have been great, but we got to them too late.) I'm thinking it is probably too late to ask Edgar Schoen to add this stuff in at this point, too. Peter? Would you like to try to cover this? Or shall we ask Raul if he could do it? Would a call with Jennifer Kates be helpful?

-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [mailto:jkates@kff.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 13:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Unfortunately, no one is available to participate on such short notice. However, as I mentioned earlier, I would be happy to have a phone briefing in advance with you or others involved, and/or send along some materials that could be helpful.

Jen

JENNIFER KATES
Vice President and Director, HIV Policy
Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org | +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

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www.kaiserEDU.org <<http://www.kaiseredu.org/>>
www.GlobalHealthFacts.org <<http://www.globalhealthfacts.org/>> www.GlobalHealthReporting.org
<<http://www.globalhealthreporting.org/>>

SIGN UP FOR E-MAIL ALERTS AT: www.kff.org/register <<http://www.kff.org/register>>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:58 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for checking. It would be wonderful if you could identify someone.

-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [<mailto:jkates@kff.org>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 09:42
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Not sure about someone else, since I am the person who focuses on this area and the notice is quite short. I will explore today and let you know, but doubt it.

JENNIFER KATES
Vice President and Director, HIV Policy
Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org | +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

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<<http://www.globalhealthreporting.org/>>

SIGN UP FOR E-MAIL ALERTS AT: www.kff.org/register <<http://www.kff.org/register>>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:av10@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:42 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for your prompt reply. We regret the extremely short timeline; might it be possible to recommend someone else from your organization who might be available to give a short presentation at this consultation?

Thank you again.

-Allan

From: Jennifer Kates [<mailto:jkates@kff.org>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 09:24
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Thank you for the invitation. I really would like to attend and can provide information on Medicaid and financing, but I cannot make those dates next week. I did not realize the consultation was that soon.

If it is helpful, perhaps we can have a call in advance and I can share some information that way?

JENNIFER KATES
Vice President and Director, HIV Policy
Kaiser Family Foundation
1330 G Street, NW Washington, DC 20005
jkates@kff.org | +1 202.347.5270 +1 202.654.1423 Direct

www.kff.org <<http://www.kff.org/>> www.kaisernetwork.org
<<http://www.kaisernetwork.org/>> www.statehealthfacts.org <<http://www.statehealthfacts.org/>> |
www.kaiserEDU.org <<http://www.kaiseredu.org/>>
www.GlobalHealthFacts.org <<http://www.globalhealthfacts.org/>> www.GlobalHealthReporting.org

<http://www.globalhealthreporting.org/>

SIGN UP FOR E-MAIL ALERTS AT: www.kff.org/register <<http://www.kff.org/register>>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCIIIISTP) [<mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 9:22 AM
To: Jennifer Kates
Cc: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCIIIISTP)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention in the US

Ms. Kates,

We would like to extend our invitation to the upcoming Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

We would also like to invite you to give a brief general presentation at this meeting regarding healthcare financing and reimbursement around HIV preventive services. We hope that you might be able to provide us and our consultants with relevant general background information about financing for preventive procedures at the state and national levels (e.g., how "medical necessity" is defined, what types of outside recommendations may have influence on this decision, etc.). We would be happy to provide more information if you will be available.

We understand that this consultation is occurring on very short notice; CDC is working quickly to respond appropriately to this emerging issue. We hope that your schedule will allow you to attend. Please contact me at your earliest convenience to indicate whether you might be available to attend this consultation or, if you are unavailable, to suggest other appropriate experts with experience in this area who might be able to provide our consultants with this important background information. Thank you in advance for your time.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon containing instructions for arranging your travel. The contractor will assist with your travel arrangements and will cover your travel expenses for this conference as detailed in the letter.
- 3) A registration form to confirm your attendance. Please send this form to BL Seamon as indicated on the top of the form so that they may confirm your attendance and assist you with your travel arrangements.

Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you. We look forward to a fascinating and productive meeting and hope that you will be able to participate.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 2 Apr 2007 15:16:01 +0000
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

It is essential that we have someone who can explain that situation to our consultants. This is a very important issue about which there is much confusion. Do you have a relationship with Dr. Smith that would allow you to clarify that for him? Or can you think of someone who might be willing to perform this function if Dr. Smith is not?

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 11:10
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Actually Dennis is correct. From their perspective, CMS allows reimbursement for circumcision as long as it meets the state definition of medical necessity. CMS doesn't question how that states define medical necessity as in most cases it is defined by the state legislature.

I am following up with some of my contacts at CMS, but Dennis is a Center Director (at Kevin Fenton's level) and I doubt that anyone CMS will question his decision.

Raul

-----Original Message-----

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 7:44 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Wow that's pretty weak in addition to being incorrect. Is he just talking about Georgia?

Raul?

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 7:41 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

This isn't good... Ideas?

-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dennis G. (CMS/OA/CMSO)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 6:58 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Cc: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/OA/CMSO); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)

Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

We believe medicaid coverage is well established as has been paying for procedure for 35+ years so respectfully decline invitation. Thanks. Dennis

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Device

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

To: Smith, Dennis G. (CMS/CMSO)

CC: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/CMSO); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)

Sent: Fri Mar 30 17:55:45 2007

Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Dear Dr. Smith,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We would like to invite the participation of a representative from CMS at this consultation. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible.

In addition, we would like to invite your representative to present (approx. 20 min) at this meeting an overview of the processes by which the decision is made whether a given service becomes covered by CMS and its state affiliates.

Please reply if possible by close of business on Wednesday 4/4 with the name and contact information for an appropriate representative so that we may facilitate travel arrangements. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We look forward to your participation in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

LCDR, US Public Health Service

Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA

30333 W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 30 Mar 2007 22:06:44 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Thank you. That's great. See you Monday.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 18:05
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Allan,

FYI, I sent of e-mails to Cate Hankins (UNAIDS), Kevin De Cock (WHO), and John Kaldor (Australia).

I'll follow-up with them and contact Jacob Gayle on Monday.

Have a good weekend!

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 5:56 PM
To: Smith, Dennis G. (CMS/OA/CMSO)
Cc: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/OA/CMSO); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Dear Dr. Smith,

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In addition, we would like to invite your representative to present (approx. 20 min) at this meeting an overview of the processes by which the decision is made whether a given service becomes covered by CMS and its state affiliates.

Please reply if possible by close of business on Wednesday 4/4 with the name and contact information for an appropriate representative so that we may facilitate travel arrangements. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We look forward to your participation in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Director, Center for Disease Prevention and Control
U.S. Department of Health and Human Services
1600 Clarendon Boulevard, Room 220
Alexandria, VA 22304
Phone: 703/298-7447
Fax: 703/298-7448
E-mail: ataylor@hhs.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 12 Apr 2007 13:09:29 +0000
To: Bailey, Robert C.
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Apologies for the typo. We will correct it ASAP.

See you soon.
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Bailey, Robert C. [<mailto:rebailey@uic.edu>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 23:21
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: rebailey@uic.edu
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Thank you. I was wondering when I might be hearing from you. One correction to the agenda: I would be speaking about the "Kisumu, Kenya trial," not the "Uganda trial." The Uganda trial is the same as the Rakai trial, which Ron Gray will cover.

I look forward to the conference.

Bob Bailey

On Wed, April 11, 2007 5:00 pm, Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

> Dr. Bailey,
>
>
>
> We wanted to provide you with an update regarding the CDC Consultation
> on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention. Our contractor, BL Seamon,
> will contact you in the next couple of days to arrange your travel. You
> may contact Leris Bernard directly at lbernard@blscamon.com or
> +1-301-577-0244, ext. 32 if you have urgent questions. Thank you for
> your patience.
>
>
>
> I've also attached a draft of the conference agenda for your reference.
> This is incomplete and not for general distribution at this time.
>
>
>
> Please feel free to contact me at any time if any question should arise.
>
>
>
> Sincerely,
>
>

- >
- > Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
- > LCDR, US Public Health Service
- > Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
- > National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
- > (proposed)
- > Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
- > 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
- > W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov
- >
- >
- >
- >

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 14:35:16 +0000
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Excellent. When's good for you?
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 13:17
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Allan -- I have a list of State Medicaid Medical Directors. Let's go over the list to identify a couple of people that you could consider inviting, maybe one from a state that covers circumcision and one from a state that doesn't.

Raul

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 12:55 PM
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Thanks for checking on this, Raul. I'm in clinic this afternoon but will check email again this evening. Let me know if you get any good leads.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 12:46
To: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/OA/CMSO)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Thanks Jerry. A list of State Medicaid Medical Directors would be great, my fax number is (404) 639-0897.

raul

-----Original Message-----

From: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/OA/CMSO)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 11:44 AM
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

You might try to invite one or more State Medicaid Directors or State Medicaid Medical Directors. Currently there are about 20 States that have Medicaid Medical Directors and they are often in charge of the medical necessity/coverage decisions made by States. I have a list of these folks if you want me to fax it.

-----Original Message-----

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 10:59 AM
To: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/CMSO)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Jerry -

Any thoughts about how we should proceed? If CMS is not attending our consultation, who should we invite to describe the process by which states make their decision on what is medical necessity?

Thanks,
Raul

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dennis G. (CMS/OA/CMSO)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 6:58 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/OA/CMSO); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

We believe medicaid coverage is well established as has been paying for procedure for 35+ years so respectfully decline invitation. Thanks. Dennis

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Device

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Smith, Dennis G. (CMS/CMSO)
CC: Zelinger, Gerald D. (CMS/CMSO); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Sent: Fri Mar 30 17:55:45 2007
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Dear Dr. Smith,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We would like to invite the participation of a representative from CMS at this consultation. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible.

In addition, we would like to invite your representative to present (approx. 20 min) at this meeting an overview of the processes by which the decision is made whether a given service becomes covered by CMS and its state affiliates.

Please reply if possible by close of business on Wednesday 4/4 with the name and contact information for an appropriate representative so that we may facilitate travel arrangements. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We look forward to your participation in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333 W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 18 Apr 2007 14:06:18 +0000
To: Gayle, Jacob
Cc: McGovern, Terry; Leris Bernard; Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Dr. Gayle,

We regret that you will not be able to attend in person but will certainly welcome participation by Ms. McGovern. Note that her hotel reservations should be made today to assure that you receive the group rate. Do not hesitate to contact me at any time if any question should arise.

Thank you.

-Allan

From: Gayle, Jacob [mailto:J.Gayle@fordfound.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 17, 2007 22:09
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); undisclosed-recipients
Cc: McGovern, Terry
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Dear Allan:

While it is with personal regret that I must decline the gracious invitation, it is with great pleasure that I inform you that Ms. Theresa McGovern, Program Officer, will participate on behalf of CDC, pending final clearance at Ford. Terry McGovern is well-known by CDC over many years of engagement on HIV matters. She can forward directly any details you might need of her.

I look forward to being updated by Terry upon her return. Please share my thanks to Dawn for keeping Ford Foundation in mind.

Sincerely,

Jacob Gayle (CDC alum)

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Thu 4/12/2007 7:07 PM
To: undisclosed-recipients
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision and HIV Prevention

Colleagues,

We would like to extend our formal invitation to the upcoming Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

Attached are the following:

- 1) An invitation letter with details regarding the conference
- 2) A letter from our contractor, BL Seamon, with instructions regarding travel arrangements and logistics. Please send the first page of this form back to the contractor to confirm your attendance.

NOTE: Hotel reservations must be made between 4/13/07 and 4/18/07 to receive the group rate.

Please do not hesitate to contact me at any time if questions should arise. We look forward to a productive meeting.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 18:49:04 +0000
To: dkern@nastad.org
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Thank you. Let us know as soon as you can so we can arrange travel.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: dkern@nastad.org [mailto:dkern@nastad.org]
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 14:29
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Allan,

We have a call with our Prevention Advisory Committee next Tuesday. I'll get back to you after the call.

Best,

Dave
Sent from my Verizon Wireless BlackBerry

-----Original Message-----

From: "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@CDC.GOV>
Date: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 09:26:08
To: "David Kern" <dkern@nastad.org>
Cc: "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@CDC.GOV>, "Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pss0@CDC.GOV>
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

David,

We are sorry you will be unable to attend. Yes, please pass along our invitation to another representative from NASTAD and let me know ASAP who your representative will be so that we may assist with travel arrangements.

Thank you.

-Allan

From: David Kern [<mailto:dkern@nastad.org>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 10, 2007 16:39
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Allan,

Unfortunately, I won't be able to attend the consultation. Our annual meeting coincides. I'm trying to identify someone from one of our advisory committees to attend in my absence. If I'm able to, I'll you know. Is it alright if I pass along this message?

Best,

Dave

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Monday, April 09, 2007 9:18 AM
To: David Kern
Cc: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Dr. Kern,

We are looking forward to your participation in CDC's upcoming consultation regarding male circumcision and HIV prevention, scheduled for April 26-27, 2007 in Atlanta. We wanted to provide you an update regarding travel arrangements and to ensure that we have correct contact information for all participants.

A contractor is being identified who will assist you with travel arrangements. The contractor will contact you in the next couple of days to assist with your travel arrangements. We are in final negotiations with the hotel where the conference will be held and have reserved a block of sleeping rooms for participants. Further information will be forthcoming in the coming week.

Please reply to Therese Teague at FPL6@cdc.gov with an email address, telephone number, fax number, and

physical address where official letters of invitation can be sent and where the contractor will be able to reach you quickly to make travel arrangements. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 5 Apr 2007 22:52:48 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Indeed!

-A

(Though I still haven't heard from Van Howe whether he'll be able to speak... And of course we don't have a contract yet... Details.)

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 18:50
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

It's all coming together :)

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 6:24 PM
To: Mazin, Dr. Rafael (WDC)
Cc: Alonso Gonzalez, Dr. Monica (WDC); Rojas, Dr. Patricio (WDC); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Drs. Mazin, Alonso Gonzales, and Rojas,

We are pleased that you will be able to participate in this consultation. Our contractor will contact you early next week with further information regarding travel arrangements and conference location. We look forward to meeting Dr. Alonso Gonzales and to working with you in the future on this issue. Please do not hesitate to contact us if any question should arise.

Que les vaya bien.

-Allan

From: Mazin, Dr. Rafael (WDC) [mailto:mazinraf@paho.org]
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 17:48
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Alonso Gonzalez, Dr. Monica (WDC); Rojas, Dr. Patricio (WDC)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Dr. Taylor,

Thank you very much for your kind invitation. It is a great idea to have a consultation to review and reframe the recommendations issued at the WHO Montreaux meeting. This event you are putting together is of utmost importance and there is no doubt it will serve as a reference to have a similar meeting in the near future (perhaps end of August) to review and reframe the recommendations for Latin America and the Caribbean. I have discussed your kind invitation with our unit chief, Dr. Patricio Rojas, and he has agreed on the importance of the consultation and the convenience of PAHO being present as observers. Since I will be away attending a conference in Buenos Aires on the same dates of the consultation, Dr. Rojas has appointed our colleague, Dr. Monica Alonso to attend. PAHO will cover her travel expenses.

As soon as we start preparing the regional consultation on the same topic we will be contacting you to have you as a co-organizer and speaker at that event. In the meanwhile you may send to us any relevant documents and to Dr. Alonso anything that may be of use for her attending the Atlanta meeting on April 26th & 27th.

Best regards,

Rafael Mazin

Rafael Mazin, MD; MPH

Regional Advisor on HIV Prevention and Care

PAHO/WHO

(202) 974-3489

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 5:11 PM

To: Mazin, Dr. Rafael (WDC)
Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Dr. Mazin,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. As many of the relevant issues will likely be quite similar in the PAHO region, we would like to invite you to observe the consultation. Unfortunately, our budget will not allow us to sponsor your travel, but we hope that you or a representative will be able to attend. A draft agenda is appended (not for further distribution) so you can get a sense of whether this would be of interest to you.

Please contact me at your earliest convenience to let us know if you are interested and available to attend this consultation. If you or a representative would be able to attend, we will send further information about the location and logistics for the meeting in the coming days.

Thank you,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 15:20:16 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC consultation on MC

Cool. Thanks.

-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 11:18
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC consultation on MC

Allan,

Here is the name of the WHO rep for the MC meeting. Following their e-mail address structure, his e-mail should be

(b)(6)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Decoek, Kevin [mailto:(b)(6)]
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 2:30 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Guerma, Teguest; Simonds, R. J. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Farmer, Lynette (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR); Anagbo, Victoria
Subject: RE: CDC consultation on MC

Dawn -

WHO will be represented by Dr Teguest Guerma, Associate Director, Department of HIV/AIDS (aka Deputy Director).

RJ - It would be very helpful if Teguest could meet briefly with you and some other key people in the Global AIDS Program, to gain familiarity with GAP's work and to see the collaboration with WHO from the CDC perspective. [redacted] (b)(5)

[redacted] (b)(5)
[redacted] (b)(5) I would be grateful if you would think on this, and perhaps we could follow up on it when I am in Atlanta next week.

best regards

Kevin

(vicki, please put in my file for Atlanta)

: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:dks0@cdc.gov]
Sent: 02 April 2007 02:27
To: Decock, Kevin
Subject: RE: CDC consultation on MC

Kevin,

We haven't invited anyone else from WHO. Please do nominate a replacement.

Thanks for responding quickly.

From: Decock, Kevin [mailto:[\[redacted\]](mailto:[redacted])] (b)(6)
Sent: Sunday, April 01, 2007 4:13 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC consultation on MC

Dawn

I regret that I will not be able to attend this meeting because of other prior commitments. I would very much have liked to participate. Has anyone else from WHO been invited? Could I nominate someone to replace me?

thanks

Kevin

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>]
Sent: 30 March 2007 23:49
To: Decock, Kevin
Subject: CDC consultation on MC

Kevin,

It is my pleasure to invite you to the consultation CDC is holding on MC in the US. Unfortunately, we have no funding to cover your travel but would love to have you participate. We have also invited Cate Hankins.

The Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention is convening a Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States to be held in Atlanta on April 26-27, 2007.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- * Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- * Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- * Discuss potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation

Let me know if you will be attending.

All the best,

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166

dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 14 Mar 2007 21:13:06 +0000
To: 'Bernard Lo'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC consultation

Great news! We're soon to send out letters with this information.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Bernard Lo [mailto:bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 4:13 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC consultation

Dear Dawn,

I will be able to attend the consultation. Whom should I contact regarding travel arrangements -- the issue is whether I should make my own plane reservations or whether I need to go through a government travel agency.

Thanks,

Bernie

Bernard Lo, M.D.
Professor of Medicine
Director, Program in Medical Ethics
University of California San Francisco
521 Parnassus Avenue
Room C-126, Box 0903
San Francisco, CA 94143-0903
bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu

Phone 415-476-5370
Fax 415-476-5020

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On Mar 7, 2007, at 9:46 AM, Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

Bernie,

Hi there :) CDC is planning an external consultation about what role male circumcision might/should play in HIV prevention in the US. We were wondering if you might be available and interested to participate? We'd especially like to hear your thoughts about some of the public health ethics questions that are being raised.

For example, should parents be allowed/encouraged to consent to an elective surgical procedure (with attendant pain and risks) in order to reduce the child's risk of acquiring HIV many years later, when the child would be of age to make their own decision. Is it ethical to recommend only for heterosexual men (where we have trial data on efficacy) and hold off for gay men (where we have no efficacy trial data, and can't even reasonably extrapolate it for the receptive partner).

The consultation is April 26-27 in Atlanta. Hope you can come

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 17:16:23 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

Again, I'd suggest printing out and having available for pickup at registration.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 11:54 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

OK to distribute by email?
-A

From: Hankins, Catherine [mailto:hankinsc@unaids.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 10:50
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

Hi Alan,

Helen and I would like to have the attached draft document on determinants and prevalence of male circumcision sent or provided to participants if possible.

Thanks,
Cate

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Tuesday, 24 April, 2007 03:18
Subject: CDC Consultation: Address confirmation

Colleagues,

We are planning to distribute contact information for all participants at the upcoming consultation. While we have previously requested your contact information for travel arrangements, we are aware that at times the information we have is not that which participants would like to have published. Therefore, we would like to ask you to complete the following with the information you

would wish to have distributed to participants at this consultation. Also please indicate if you would prefer to have any of this information withheld. Thank you for your assistance.

Full Name (with degrees):

Title

Organization

Address

Telephone Number

Email

In addition, we have corrected a typographical error that was discovered in the agenda. A revised copy is attached for your reference.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
CDC

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 17:14:35 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

We should make copies and place on the table for folks to pick up.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 1:11 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

This just in from the front lines. FYI.
-Allan

From: Dennis deLeon [mailto:DdeLeon@latinoaids.org]
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 13:04
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

Mr. Taylor, the Latino Commission on AIDS has just issued the attached statement: Latino Commission on AIDS Recommends Health Providers Consider Offering Education and Services on Male Circumcision to Latino Men that Regularly Engage in High Risk Sexual Practices. I don't know if this will be of any use for the consultation.

	24 WEST 25TH STREET 9TH FLOOR NEW YORK, NY 10010-2704 TEL (212) 675-3288 FAX (212) 675-3466
Dennis deLeon President	Direct Line (212) 584-9300 Direct Fax (212) 202-3620 Cell Phone (917) 697-8040 ddeleon@latinoaids.org www.latinoaids.org

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:avt0@CDC.GOV]
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 7:23 PM
To: Dennis deLeon
Subject: CDC Consultation: Confirm Address

Mr. de Leon

We are putting together a list of consultation participants with contact information for distribution to all participants. Below is the contact information we have listed for you. Please complete and confirm that this is the information that you would like distributed to participants or provide an alternate. Please also inform us if you prefer to have any or all of this information withheld.

ddeleon@latinoaids.org

Title: President
Organization: Latino Commission on AIDS
Contact Address:
24 West, 25th Street, 9th Floor
New York, NY 10010
Contact Phone: 212-675-3288

We have also identified a typographical error on the agenda and have attached a corrected version.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

Assistant Director for HIV Prevention
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Dermatology and STD
1600 Clifton Road, NE
Atlanta, Georgia 30333
Phone: 404/616-1400
Fax: 404/616-1401
E-mail: ataylor@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 16 Mar 2007 18:29:21 +0000
To: 'Bernard Lo'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC consultation

Bernie,

Would you be willing to give a 20 minute talk at the end of the first day on ethical/religious/cultural issues (in the US) that may impact male circumcision for HIV prevention? It would follow a series of talks about the African trial data, impact modelling data, and a discussion about risk communication and disinhibition.

Talk to you soon.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Bernard Lo [mailto:bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 4:13 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC consultation

Dear Dawn,

I will be able to attend the consultation. Whom should I contact regarding travel arrangements -- the issue is whether I should make my own plane reservations or whether I need to go through a government travel agency.

Thanks,

Bernie

Bernard Lo, M.D.
Professor of Medicine
Director, Program in Medical Ethics
University of California San Francisco
521 Parnassus Avenue
Room C-126, Box 0903
San Francisco, CA 94143-0903
bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu

Phone 415-476-5370
Fax 415-476-5020

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On Mar 7, 2007, at 9:46 AM, Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

Bernie,

Hi there :) CDC is planning an external consultation about what role male circumcision might/should play in HIV prevention in the US. We were wondering if you might be available and interested to participate? We'd especially like to hear your thoughts about some of the public health ethics questions that are being raised.

For example, should parents be allowed/encouraged to consent to an elective surgical procedure (with attendant pain and risks) in order to reduce the child's risk of acquiring HIV many years later, when the child would be of age to make their own decision. Is it ethical to recommend only for heterosexual men (where we have trial data on efficacy) and hold off for gay men (where we have no efficacy trial data, and can't even reasonably extrapolate it for the receptive partner).

The consultation is April 26-27 in Atlanta. Hope you can come

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 16 Apr 2007 13:36:28 +0000
To: 'Litjen Tan'
Cc: Barry Dickinson; Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nancy Nolan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Thanks, Litjen. We are very excited to have you represented. Dr. Taylor will see to it that Dr. Levin is contacted.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org]
Sent: Monday, April 16, 2007 9:34 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Barry Dickinson; Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nancy Nolan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision
Importance: High

Hi Dawn!

We have managed to identify a person from the AMA's Council on Science and Public Health to represent the AMA at this meeting. She will be able to provide a report back to the AMA staff in order to maintain continuity of the efforts on this issue.

I think that your consultation is timely in light of the planned New York campaign.

The person who will be representing the AMA is:

Ilse Levin, DO, MPH & TM
Resident Member, Council on Science and Public Health
Cell: (b)(6)
e-mail: ilevin@westernu.edu

Can you have someone contact her directly, with a cc to me, to arrange her travel?

Thanks!

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

Director, Infectious Disease, Immunology, and Molecular Medicine

American Medical Association

515 N. State Street

Chicago, IL 60610

Tel: (312) 464-4147

Fax: (312) 464-5841

Email: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 2:11 PM
To: Litjen Tan
Cc: Barry Dickinson; Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

I'm not sure. We'll have to ask our travel unit. thanks for the heads up.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 2:57 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Barry Dickinson
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision
Importance: High

Hi Dr. Smith!

Either Barry Dickinson, Secretary of the AMA's Council on Science and Public Health, or myself will be there. However, due to how other meeting obligation may pan out, we cannot know for sure until April the 23rd which one of us will be there.

Since you had kindly offered to pay travel costs, this may cost more in terms of airfare. Is this going to be a problem for you? If so, let us know and we will try and adjust here.

Thanks!

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

Director, Infectious Disease, Immunology, and Molecular Medicine

American Medical Association

515 N. State Street

Chicago, IL 60610

Tel: (312) 464-4147

Fax: (312) 464-5841

Email: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@CDC.GOV>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 11:16 AM
To: Litjen Tan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Dr. Tan,

If that is the time available for you, it will be ok. But I would then ask the attendee to be vocal during the discussion periods on Thursday so that we have good input from AMA before he/she leaves.

Does that work for you? We need the name of your representative urgently for the hotel to hold a spot.

Thanks for your efforts in this.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Wednesday, April 04, 2007 12:14 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hi Dr. Smith!

We are having trouble getting someone to be there both days. If I can only fly in on Thursday AM and fly out Thursday PM, will that be OK?

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

Director, Infectious Disease, Immunology, and Molecular Medicine

American Medical Association

515 N. State Street

Chicago, IL 60610

Tel: (312) 464-4147

Fax: (312) 464-5841

Email: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org

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From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>]
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 2:41 PM
To: Litjen Tan
Subject: RE: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hi there.

This meeting is being convened on April 26-27 in Atlanta in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to

have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be high risk populations something missing in this sentence??? in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

We will pay for travel for an AMA representative as we feel it is important to hear your perspective on possible changes in recommendations about this medical practice as it affects HIV prevention clinical activities.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Friday, March 23, 2007 8:56 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Barry Dickinson
Subject: CDC external consultation on male circumcision

Hello Dr. Smith!

I have been forwarded a request for AMA representation at your consultation on the role of male circumcision in preventing HIV transmission.

Can you email me some details about the meeting? When is it, and will the CDC be paying for travel?

Thanks!

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

Director, Infectious Disease, Immunology, and Molecular Medicine

American Medical Association

515 N. State Street

Chicago, IL 60610

Tel: (312) 464-4147

Fax: (312) 464-5841

Email: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 29 Mar 2007 19:57:04 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC request

Perfect. Thanks.
-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 15:54
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: CDC request

Allen,

Here's the contact info for Isaac's replacement

Dawn K. Smith

From: Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 3:50 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC request

sblank@health.nyc.gov
Phone: 212 788-4406

>>> Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) 03/29/07 3:48 PM >>>
Thanks, Isaac. Can we have contact information for her?

See you next time :)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 3:47 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CDC request

Dawn:
Sue Blank, Assistant Commissioner of our Bureau of Sexually Transmitted

Diseases will be able to attend.
Isaac

>>> Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) 03/27/07 2:14 PM >>>
Hi Isaac,

do you know yet if you'll be able to join us?

thanks.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Weisfuse, Isaac (CDC health.nyc.gov)
Sent: Friday, March 23, 2007 3:32 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC request

Dawn: I do remember you! I need to check out the dates, and I'll give you an answer on Monday. Isaac

>>> Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) 03/23/07 2:53 PM >>>
Isaac,

I don't know if you remember me (the EISO for ICL in 1992?), but I do remember

you and all the good advice you gave me.

I'm writing because you should have received an invitation to participate in a

consultation on the potential role of male circumcision in HIV prevention efforts in the US. We had not heard back from you and I volunteered to check in and see if you will be able to attend.

We are very unsure about if/how to translate the African trial findings (and impending WHO recommendation) to the US epidemic; both because of the role of RAI where no direct protective effect can be assumed, and because of our relatively high rate of circumcision. However, for insertive MSM events and for MSW, it may offer some protection. So what's an agency to do??

Please let me know if you will be able to join us.

Best always.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science

Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

The New York City Department of Health & Mental Hygiene is now offering information important for the health of all New Yorkers. To sign up for these new and valuable updates, log-on to our website at <http://www.nyc.gov/health/email> and select the NYC DOHMH updates you'd like to receive.

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The New York City Department of Health & Mental Hygiene is now offering information important for the health of all New Yorkers. To sign up for these new and valuable updates, log-on to our website at <http://www.nyc.gov/health/email> and select the NYC DOHMH updates you'd like to receive.

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replying to this message and please delete it from your computer. Thank you for your cooperation.

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 22:27:54 +0000
To: Gleaton, Tonica (CDC/CCID/OD)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision binder cover.doc

Looks good to me :)

From: Gleaton, Tonica (CDC/CCID/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 10:16 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision binder cover.doc
Importance: High

Hi Dawn,

I'm not sure if Allan is around and I'd like to get started with what I can. Would you please review the attachment and let me know your thoughts?

Thanks!

From: Gleaton, Tonica (CDC/CCID/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 10:15 AM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision binder cover.doc

<< File: Circumcision binder cover.doc >>

Your thoughts...

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 5 Apr 2007 13:53:10 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

FYI,

We had invited the Deputy Commissioner for HIV/STD and he was unable to come so nominated Sue Blank.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 9:11 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

Sue Blank from NYC STD will be at the consultation. It will be interesting to hear their plans: if they do some good surveillance/data collection around this effort, it might be able to answer some of the outstanding questions about potential effects in US populations.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 08:50
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

Agree, fascinating.

PK

Sent from my wireless handheld

----- Original Message -----

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu Apr 05 08:46:28 2007
Subject: RE: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

Thanks.

Would be worthwhile to have a voice from NYC at our consultation.

Tim

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 8:41 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

From: Millett, Greg (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 8:01 AM
To: CDC NCHSTP/DHAP Prevention Research Branch
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Wolitski, Richard (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision campaign planned by NYC Dept of Health

In today's New York Times....

New York City Plans to Promote Circumcision

Top of Form 1

By DONALD G. McNEIL Jr.

http://topics.nytimes.com/top/reference/timestopics/people/m/donald_g_jr_meneil/index.html?inline=nyt-per

Published: April 5, 2007

New York City's Department of Health and Mental Hygiene is planning a campaign to encourage men at high risk of AIDS <http://topics.nytimes.com/top/news/health/diseasesconditionsandhealthtopics/aids/index.html?inline=nyt-classifier> to get circumcised in light of the World Health Organization

http://topics.nytimes.com/top/reference/timestopics/organizations/w/world_health_organization/index.html?inline=nyt-org's endorsement of the procedure as an effective way to prevent the disease.

While the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

http://topics.nytimes.com/top/reference/timestopics/organizations/c/centers_for_disease_control_and_prevention/index.html?inline=nyt-org in Atlanta is just beginning to convene meetings and design studies to help it formulate a national policy, New York City is moving ahead on its own.

In the United States, "New York City remains the epicenter of the AIDS epidemic," Dr. Thomas R. Frieden, the city's health commissioner, said in an interview. Referring to H.I.V., he said, "In some subpopulations, you have 10 to 20 percent prevalence rates, just as they do in parts of Africa."

His department has started asking some community groups and gay rights organizations to discuss circumcision with their members, and has asked the Health and Hospitals Corporation, which runs city hospitals and clinics, to perform the procedure at no charge for men without health insurance.

A spokeswoman for the corporation said it was "having conversations" with the health department but had not reached a decision.

"As you know, the research on this is pretty recent," the spokeswoman, Ana Marengo, said.

In three recent clinical trials in Africa, circumcision was shown to lower a man's risk of contracting the virus from heterosexual sex by about 60 percent. On March 28, the World Health Organization officially recommended that countries adopt the procedure as part of their AIDS prevention plans.

No spontaneous outcry for circumcision has arisen in New York, Dr. Frieden conceded.

"This is not something that has a lot of buzz," he said.

But he added that even 1,000 circumcisions in the right subgroups might slow the spread of AIDS.

For example, in Manhattan, 20 percent of all black men between 40 and 50 are infected with the virus that causes AIDS. About 10 percent of all gay men in the city are infected, and the rate rises to as high as 25 percent in the Chelsea neighborhood.

Dr. Frieden said black, Hispanic and foreign-born men were less likely to be circumcised than white Americans, and the percentage is smaller among men with lower incomes.

(About 65 percent of all male babies in the United States are circumcised, according to the National Center for Health Statistics, compared with about 30 percent of men worldwide, by W.H.O. estimates.)

Among men seeking treatment at the city's clinics for sexually transmitted diseases

<http://topics.nytimes.com/top/news/health/diseasesconditionsandhealthtopics/veneraldiseases/index.html?inline=nyt-classifier> — another risk group for AIDS infection because of genital sores — a large proportion are uncircumcised, Dr. Frieden said.

There are clear limitations, however, on extrapolating data from Africa to New York.

The studies, done in Uganda, Kenya and South Africa, enrolled men who said they had sex with women, while New York's highest-risk groups are men who have sex with men, men who inject drugs and people who have sex with those men.

Nonetheless, Dr. Frieden said, it is logical to assume that circumcision would offer protection in some types of gay sex.

A man's risk from performing penetrative anal sex is about the same as his risk from vaginal sex, Dr. Frieden said, so circumcision would presumably confer the same protection as it did in the African trials.

The risk from receptive anal sex is five times higher, he said, and circumcision would obviously not protect those men. Oral sex is much less risky.

Also, cutting down infections among bisexual men — some of whom do not admit to female partners that they participate in gay sex — would protect women, he said.

Dr. Frieden said he thought health insurance companies might agree to pay for preventive circumcisions since they already covered them for infections and urinary blockage. City hospitals also offer the operation in those cases, Ms. Marengo said.

Peter Staley, a longtime AIDS activist and co-founder of ACT-UP New York, the Treatment Action Group and AIDSmeds.com, said he was "intrigued" by the idea of offering circumcisions but worried because those in the studies supporting it bore little relation to New York's risk groups.

"Should we proceed when we don't have hard data yet on the population here?" he asked. "On the other hand, if we wait the three years it would take to answer that question, how many will be infected in the meantime?"

Also, after reading many postings on gay Web sites about the Africa trials, he said he feared a backlash among black and Hispanic men to endorsements of circumcision from white public health officials or gay activists.

"I'm white, Frieden's white," he said. "It's going to sound like white guys telling black and Hispanic guys to do something that would affect their manhood."

Tokes Osubu, executive director of Gay Men of African Descent, a 21-year-old gay rights organization, agreed.

"There will always be conspiracy theorists," he said. "That's par for the course."

He also said he thought circumcision was "not the answer to our problems" and doubted that it would lower infection rates.

Many black men who have sex with men, he said, already face discrimination, stigma and an inability to talk about their sex lives with family members and sometimes even with doctors.

"No amount of circumcision is going to change that," he said.

Bric Bernas, manager of information and counseling for the Asian and Pacific Islander Coalition on H.I.V./AIDS, said his organization wanted to see studies done in the United States and among gay men before taking a position on the issue.

Circumcision

<http://topics.nytimes.com/top/news/health/diseasesconditionsandhealthtopics/circumcision/index.html?inline=nyt-classifier> is not common among Asian men, except those from Muslim countries and the Philippines, Mr. Bernas said, "and there might be cultural sensitivities around it."

Next Article in New York Region (2 of 28) » <http://www.nytimes.com/2007/04/05/nyregion/05terror.html>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 20:03:55 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision Consultation Award

Partially. Last I'd heard the contractor still hadn't signed the contract with the hotel. I'll breathe after that.

-A

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 16:02
To: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision Consultation Award

Can we breath a sigh of relief now, or not yet?

PK

From: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 2:44 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision Consultation Award

Award document.....

From: Mast, Gerri E. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 2:42 PM
To: Brannon, Jennifer S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision Consultation Award

Here 'tis.

<< File: NoticeofAward.pdf >>

Gerri E. Mast
Funding Resource Specialist
Centers for Disease Control
NCHISTP/DHAP/OPS/EPMO
gem5@cdc.gov
404.639.4592

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 9 Apr 2007 15:29:34 +0000
To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision Consultation

Great news! Thanks.
-Allan

From: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 09, 2007 11:11
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Circumcision Consultation

Edwin Sanders will be able to attend. I'll be sending you his address shortly. His e-mail address is: (b)(6)
He needs to be back in Nashville by Friday evening, April 27.

Bob Kohmescher
Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (A43)
1600 Clifton Rd NE
Atlanta, GA 30333

(404) 639-1914
(404) 639-5260 (fax)
Corp 8/Rm 5057

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 22:02:21 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision consultations

Agreed. Thanks.
-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 18:01
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Circumcision consultations

Sorry not to have seen it earlier but not sure we can take either suggestion. We have several 30 minute discussion breaks on day 1 and I'm sure we'll get early feedback then. Let's proceed with the agenda as decided by the group.

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 5:46 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Circumcision consultations

Eek, I hadn't realized that he hadn't actually cc'd you on this. For our consideration. (not sure we can take the first suggestion...) -A

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 16:21
To: Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Circumcision consultations

Thanks -- am copying Allan Taylor and Dawn Smith, who are working on the agenda, so they can see your suggestions.

Patrick

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov)
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon Apr 02 14:27:00 2007
Subject: Re: Circumcision consultations

Patrick:

this looks like a valuable meeting. 2 suggestions: on the pediatric issue may want to devote some time to discussion of the anti circ movement as a potential barrier to any pediatric recommendation. Also not clear if you have any data on circ rates presently in US, as this would be valuable.

As with any consultation, the degree to which you can begin to get feedback on day 1 would be valuable, because there is a lot to talk about, and may not be able to get to everything on day 2.

Unfortunately, I need to be back in NYC on Friday about 5, which would mean having to leave earlier than the 3 pm

conclusion. Sue Blank of our STD program will attend. Sue is up to date on our NYC plans regarding circs. Isaac

>>> Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) 03/30/07 11:43 AM >>>
Hi,

I wanted to follow up and see if you had any questions or comments about the draft agenda for the male circumcision consultation that I sent earlier, and to ask if you think you will be able to attend.

Thanks,

Patrick

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Road NE, MS E46
Atlanta, GA 30333
404-639-2090
Fax: 404-639-8640
email: pss0@cdc.gov (note: 4th digit is the number zero, not the letter "O")
Courier address: 8 Corporate Blvd, Atlanta GA 30329

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From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 23 Mar 2007 15:16:27 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Thanks, Patrick: if you're able, that would be very helpful.
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 23, 2007 10:27
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CMS

Thanks Raul.

Allan, do you want me to invite or will you?

P

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
CC: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri Mar 23 10:26:30 2007
Subject: RE: CMS

Allan and Peter --

I spoke with one of the medical consultants in the Center for Medicaid State Operations and he suggested we send the letter of invitation to:

Dennis Smith
Director, Center for Medicaid and State Operations
7500 Security Blvd.
Baltimore, MD 21244-1850

If your budget allows, you can offer to cover their travel costs (he told me that they have limited travel funds). They may also decide to designate someone from the CMS Regional Office in Atlanta.

The presenter can describe how CMS designates mandatory vs. optional services and the states' role in defining medical necessity. CMS allows states to define medical necessity and the services that would be covered under that definition. Because Medicaid is a federal-state partnership, State legislatures can define what would be covered by Medicaid in their states. CMS typically won't challenge or question states' decisions. The best strategy to cover increase coverage for circumcision may be to work with the American Academy of Pediatrics to change their recommendations.

Raul

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 22, 2007 11:13 AM
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Raul,

Thank you. That's very helpful. I think it would be important for the consultants to hear about that process. Thanks for your help.

-Allan

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 22, 2007 11:00
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Allan -- I am trying to get someone, but I should clarify one of the points you make here.

They only way CMS can influence coverage of a medical procedure is by making it a required service (an example of a service required of those states that decide to participate on the Medicaid program is prenatal care). Some procedures are classified as optional based on recommendations from national medical organizations (they typically follow AAP recommendations to determine what services should be required for children under age 18). If the service is elective or optional, then the final decision is made by the state legislatures (for an example you can check the language approved by the General Assembly of Missouri regarding male circumcision at <http://www.senate.state.mo.us/02info/billtext/intro/SB751.htm>

The CMS speaker can probably discuss what is the current coverage of circumcision by state and how they determine if a procedure is considered optional or required. He/she can also discuss how it is address under the 1115 Medicaid waivers for people who enroll in managed care.

Raul

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 22, 2007 8:49 AM
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Hi, Raul,

We would like someone who can give a presentation (about 10-15 min) on the mechanisms by which CMS decides to pay for various procedures (or, rather, how they influence state affiliates to pay or not pay) and who can detail the current CMS policy/stance on male circumcision (for newborns and for adult males).

Peter, Patrick and Dawn: what would you add?

-Allan

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 21, 2007 17:26
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Peter and Allan --

Can you send me a short summary of what role you expect CMS to play at the consultation? I talked to an old colleague at the CMS Regional Office in Atlanta and she agreed to talk to the director of the office to see if he would agree to send someone from their office. The Regional office covers 8 states in the Southeast US.

Raul

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 5:56 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Margolies-Seiler, Eva Z. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Hi Raul,

Indeed, payment for services is really a critical piece. Thanks for your guidance in getting the right consultant(s) for this meeting.

PK

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 5:51 PM
To: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Margolies-Seiler, Eva Z. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: CMS

Raul,

Thank you for looking into this. It will be important to have someone there at the consultation (preferably from CMS) who can talk about this (and related) issue. Do you know anyone else we could convince to come down for the consultation?

Thanks.

-Allan

From: Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 14:18
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Margolies-Seiler, Eva Z. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: CMS

Patrick and Allan -

I have tried to contact Joe Razes at CMS but he has not returned my phone call or e-mails. I suspect that that the new rule proposed by CMS to restrict Federal Medicaid payments for publicly supported healthcare services may have to do with their lack of interest. Last January CMS published a proposed regulation entitled "Medicaid Program; Cost Limit for Providers Operated by Units of Government and Provisions to Ensure the Integrity of Federal State-Financial Partnership". This rule would change public provider payment and financing arrangements with State Medicaid programs. The Rule would: (1) impose a cost limit on Medicaid payments to public providers; (2) impose a new federal definition of public provider status; (3) greatly restrict the sources of non-federal share funding through intergovernmental transfers (IGTs) and certified public expenditures (CPEs); and (4) require providers to receive and retain the full amount of Medicaid payments received.

The Proposed Rule would cut \$3.87 billion from the Medicaid program over the next five years beginning on September 1, 2007..

A copy of the Proposed Rule is available at:

<http://a257.g.akamaitech.net/7/257/2422/01jan20071800/edocket.access.gpo.gov/2007/pdf/07-195.pdf> <<http://a257.g.akamaitech.net/7/257/2422/01jan20071800/edocket.access.gpo.gov/2007/pdf/07-195.pdf>> .

Here is Joe's contact information:

Joseph Razes
HIV/AIDS Program Coordinator
Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services
S2-14-26
7500 Security Boulevard
Baltimore, MD 21244

Phone: (410) 786-6126
Fax: (410) 786-9004

Raul << File: Raul A. (DIIAP) Romaguera (rar2@cdc.gov).vcf >>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 6 Apr 2007 14:25:48 +0000
To: 'Gayle, Jacob'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Consultation at CDC

Thanks, Jacob.

We need a name to hold the hotel room, so I'll use yours for now. Let's us know when you know :)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Gayle, Jacob [<mailto:J.Gayle@fordfound.org>]
Sent: Thursday, April 05, 2007 9:17 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Consultation at CDC

Dawn,

I apologize: every time I get close to calling, something comes up. Expect to see someone from Ford. Either I or a colleague will contact in advance.

Fond regards.

Jacob

via Blackberry

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Gayle, Jacob
Sent: Mon Apr 02 14:06:02 2007
Subject: Consultation at CDC

Jacob, See invitation below....

The Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States to be held in Atlanta on April 26-27, 2007.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- * Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- * Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- * Discuss potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 30 Apr 2007 17:21:24 +0000
To: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Draft content of MC peer review article

Thanks, Tom, for the rapid read and concrete suggestions.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 30, 2007 1:12 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Draft content of MC peer review article

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Thanks. Tom

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Sent: Sunday, April 29, 2007 8:36 PM

To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Subject: Draft content of MC peer review article

Dear all,

Last week we contacted JAMA to see if they would be interested in this submission. We were told they might be but would need to see an outline of the proposed paper.

For that reason, and because I wanted to keep the momentum up, I have used the report back templates and review of similar consultation reports to begin the paper while the discussions are fresh in our minds. Clearly we will need to fill in a lot of blanks, come to some internal decisions about next steps at CDC, and review the meeting report in detail before completing a full draft of the paper.

But if you would take a look at this preliminary outline and send your comments, it would help in responding to JAMA and in being sure that the writing is on the right track so far.

Thanks for looking at it so early.

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 23 Apr 2007 21:04:50 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Thanks!
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon 4/23/2007 4:00 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

that's ok. I was just trying to finish the CD. So I edited the word version I had with the timing changes/dropped session from the pdf you sent out, changed the Uganda to Kenya, and reordered the title of Brad's talk as he requested at the run-through.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 3:53 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Oh, no! I think I sent out the wrong one to all the participants, then, too! Ack! How embarrassing... I'm not in the office now. I'll send you the correct one when I get out of clinic. Ugh... I guess I should send to all the other participants, too. Oy vey.
-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon 4/23/2007 2:30 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Allan,

Where is the current version of the meeting agenda? PS. the one you handed out today still had Bob talking about the Uganda trial (vs Kenya) :)

I need to include it on the CD.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCIIIHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 2:23 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIIIHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

The contractor was copied: she'll handle. Thanks.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon 4/23/2007 1:33 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Allan,

Can you check for her?

Dawn K. Smith

From: Litjen Tan [<mailto:Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org>]
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 1:29 PM
To: Paul Brown
Cc: Leris Bernard; Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Can I confirm that this reservation is for Ilse Levin, who will be the AMA representative?

Thanks!

L.J

Litjen (L.J) Tan, MS, PhD

Director, Infectious Disease, Immunology, and Molecular Medicine

American Medical Association

515 N. State Street

Chicago, IL 60610

Tel: (312) 464-4147

Fax: (312) 464-5841

Email: Litjen.Tan@ama-assn.org

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From: Paul Brown [<mailto:Pbrown@blseamon.com>]

Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 12:18 PM

To: Litjen Tan

Cc: Leris Bernard

Subject: FINAL CONFIRMATION - Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

Importance: High

Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS)

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)

Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns

April 26-27, 2007

Atlanta, GA

FINAL CONFIRMATION

FROM: Leris Bernard, Conference Planner
B L Scamon Corporation
Phone: (301) 577-0244, ext. 32
Fax: (301) 577-5261

MEETING DATES: Thursday April 26, 2007 - 8:30 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.
Friday, April 27, 2007 - 9:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m.

MEETING AND LODGING SITE: Embassy Suites Hotel

Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park
267 Marietta Street

Atlanta, GA 30313

Phone: (404) 223-2300
Fax: (404) 223-0925

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for Prevention of HIV and Other Health Concerns, sponsored by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). B L Seamon Corporation (BLS), under contract to DHHS, is providing administrative and logistical support for the meeting. Please take a few minutes to review the information below.

LODGING ARRANGEMENTS

A guestroom has been reserved in your name at the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for your arrival on Wednesday, April 25, 2007, and departure on Friday, April 27, 2007. Your hotel confirmation number is 83861044.

BLS will cover the cost of your guestroom for a maximum of 2 (two) nights. You will be responsible for settling all incidental charges and additional nights before checking out of the hotel. If you need to cancel your reservation, please do so 72 hours before your scheduled arrival date to avoid a direct credit card charge of 1 night's lodging. If you cancel your reservation, be sure to obtain a cancellation number from the reservationist for your records.

Your reservation has been guaranteed with your major credit card. Although the cost of your accommodations will be covered, your credit card was required to guarantee your room reservation. Your card will be charged if you do not attend the meeting and do not cancel your room reservation by 3:00 p.m., 24 hours prior to the day of arrival.

TRAVEL ARRANGEMENTS

If you made your travel arrangements through our travel agency, Travel-On, and encounter an emergency situation, they can be reached at 1 (888) 495-7770 or (240) 387-4188 between 8:30 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. (e.t.). The address is 9000 Virginia Manor Road, Suite 201, Beltsville, MD. If you encounter any problems after 5:00 p.m., please contact Travel-On by dialing

1 (800) 366-2100.

Ground Transportation

From Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport, participants may use MARTA, Atlanta's subway system to travel to the Embassy Suites Hotel Atlanta-Centennial Olympic Park for \$1.75 each way. Take any northbound train to Five Points Station. Transfer to the westbound train. Travel one stop to W1/Omni/Dome/GWCC Station. Take the small escalator to the big escalator. Turn left and go to Philips Drive. Turn right and go to International Boulevard. Turn right and go to Marietta Street. Embassy Suites Hotel is 1 block on the left (approximately a 5-minute walk from the train station).

In addition, participants can utilize the Atlanta Link, a traditional van service that offers round-trip airport transfer for \$28.00 per person. The DOWNTOWN Shuttle is preferred because it handles downtown properties only. Advance reservations can be secured by calling

1 (866) 545-9633.

A taxicab from the Hartsfield-Jackson International Airport should cost \$24.00 one-way plus \$2 for each additional passenger.

REIMBURSEMENT OF EXPENSES

BLS will reimburse you for ground transportation as well as meals and incidental expenses (M&IE) after the meeting. Ground transportation expense reimbursement covers taxis to/from your home, the airports, and the hotel, as well as parking and tolls. Mileage is reimbursed at 48.5¢ per mile for the use of your personally owned vehicle. The M&IE reimbursement covers meals, tips, telephone calls, and other miscellaneous expenses and is applicable to the geographical location of the site visit. The M&IE allowance for Atlanta, GA, is \$49.00 per full day. You will receive three-fourths of the M&IE allowance or \$36.75 for each travel day on

April 25 and April 27.

To claim your expenses following the conference, please submit the Travel Reimbursement Form by May 11, 2007. This form will be e-mailed to you after the meeting. When submitting your expenses, attach all applicable receipts including your travel ticket stub. All receipts and your travel ticket stub must be submitted in original form. Receipts are not required for meal expenses.

QUESTIONS

Please contact Leris Bernard at lbernard@blseamon.com <<mailto:pbrown@blseamon.com>> or (301) 577-0244, ext. 32, if you have questions regarding logistics or if your attendance plans should change.

Questions concerning program content should be directed to Dr. Allan Taylor at (404) 639-6120 or avt0@cdc.gov <<mailto:avt0@cdc.gov>> .

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 11 Apr 2007 15:21:22 +0000
To: (b)(6)
Bcc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Great news! Thank you. Our contractor will be in touch in the next couple of days to assist with your travel arrangements. I will send a draft agenda later today so you can see the context for your talk. Let me know if you have questions regarding the presentation. We look forward to your participation.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

-----Original Message-----

From: (b)(6)
Sent: Wednesday, April 11, 2007 10:30
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Dear Dr. Taylor,

Yes, I will be able to present. I apologize for any delay in responding, as I am in Chicago visiting relatives.

Today, Wednesday, I can be reached at (b)(6)
On Thursday, I will be travelling and be on my cell phone (b)(6)
On Friday, I will be in Wisconsin at (b)(6) or on my cell phone.

Saturday I will be at (b)(6)

E-mail contact is best at (b)(6) I will not be able to check my e-mail on Thursday or Friday.

Fax number at my office is 906-225-4838.

I look forward to meeting you. Please respond that you have received this e-mail. If not, I will call this afternoon.

Sincerely,

Robert S. Van Howe, MD, MS, FAAP

- > Dr. Van Howe,
- >
- > We must finalize our agenda today and remain hopeful that you will be
- > able to present regarding potential adverse effects of MC at this
- > conference. Please respond by close of business today (4/11) to indicate
- > whether you will be able to present. If we have not heard from you
- > before tomorrow morning, it will unfortunately be necessary for us to
- > identify another speaker for this presentation. We would value your

> insight and participation and hope to hear from you soon.
>
> Also, regardless of whether you will be able to present, if you are
> still able to attend the meeting, please provide an address, phone
> number and fax number where you can be reached so that the contractor
> can assist with your travel arrangements.
>
> Thank you.
>
> Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
> LCDR, US Public Health Service
> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
> National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
> (proposed)
>
>
> -----Original Message-----
> From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Sent: Monday, April 09, 2007 09:25
> To: 'rsvanhowe@mgh.org'
> Cc: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
> Subject: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision
>
> Dr. Van Howe,
>
> We are finalizing the agenda for this consultation and have not yet
> heard from you regarding the presentation below. Please reply by
> tomorrow (4/10) 6:00 pm EDT to indicate whether you will be able to
> present.
>
> In addition, please provide a telephone number, fax number and physical
> address where you may be reached so that the contractor can assist you
> with your travel arrangements.
>
> We look forward to your participation. Thank you.
>
> Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
> LCDR, US Public Health Service
> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
> National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
> (proposed)
> Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
> 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
> W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov
>
> -----Original Message-----
> From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 18:12
> To: 'rsvanhowe@mgh.org'
> Subject: RE: Save the Date: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision
>
> Dr. Van Howe,
>
> We are pleased that you will be able to attend. We are striving for a
> rational and open discussion of the relevant issues at this meeting. We
> would like to invite you to present evidence regarding potential adverse

> effects associated with male circumcision (evidence of altered
> sensation, surgical or other complications, etc.). Your presentation
> would be approximately 20 minutes in length, with a discussion period to
> follow. Please contact me to let me know if you would be able to give
> such a presentation.

> Thank you for your consideration.

> Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH

> -----Original Message-----

> From: rsvanhowe@mgh.org [mailto:rsvanhowe@mgh.org]

> Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 13:04

> To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

> Subject: Re: Save the Date: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

> Dear Dr. Taylor,

> I have been able to set aside these dates, so I should be able to

> attend. I

> look forward to hearing from you.

> Sincerely,

> Robert S. Van Howe, MD, MS, FAAP

> "Taylor, Allan W.

> \CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP\ To: Robert S Van

> Howe/PESP/MGHS@mghs, <(b)(6)>

>)" <avt0@cdc.gov> cc: "Sullivan,

> Patrick \CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP\)" <pss0@cdc.gov>

> Department Not Subject: Save the Date:

> CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

> Found

> 03/26/2007 10:57 AM

> Dr. Van Howe,

> CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for

> male

> circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007

> in
> Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the
> consultation
> (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming
> weeks,
> but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC
> will
> support your transportation, lodging and per diem for the conference.
>
> You will receive a second email shortly with details regarding travel
> arrangements. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as
> possible
> will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please
> feel
> free to contact me using the contact information below.
>
> We hope that you will be able to participate in this important
> consultation.
>
> Thank you,
>
>
> Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
> LCDR, US Public Health Service
> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
> National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
> (proposed)
> Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
>
>
>
>
>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 15:59:26 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Allan, I agree with just asking her to do 1,2,4. Comments below.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 10:57 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi, Dawn. Looks like Helen Weiss is willing to do whatever we need her to do. I was going to ask her to cover just 1, 2 and 4. Make sense?

-A

-----Original Message-----

From: Helen Weiss [<mailto:Helen.Weiss@lshtm.ac.uk>]
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 14:42
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi Allan,

Yes, that would be OK.

Can I just check whether you wanted me to cover the results of 3 MC/HIV RCTs or whether someone else is doing this, and also whether someone else is going to touch on the public health issues we are now faced with (internationally)? No prob to do this - then i would do something like the following:

1. MC - global prevalence & determinants (religion, ethnicity, culture, medical) YES
2. Ecological, biological & observational evidence for association of MC & HIV YES.
3. Summary of results of 3 RCTs of MC & HIV, including data on safety and risk compensation Since all three investigators are now attending, I will split this slot allowing Auvert and Bailey to present their own studies briefly (as PK said, you can do it in 10 minutes), and allowing a bit longer time for Ron to present the Rakai data including whatever they have about transmission from circumcised men to partners
4. Evidence that MC protects against other diseases, including GUD, cervical cancer, penile cancer YES
5. Evidence for MC & HIV transmission among MSM NO, Susan Buchbinder is doing this
6. Outline of public health issues for expanding MC services in Africa.NO, not the topic of this agenda. Since they raised this, you might want to reinforce that this meeting is about the role of MC in the US epidemic.

Could (just about) cover this in 35 minutes but it would be a bit rushed and I assume others might be covering some of this? Let me know what you think.

best wishes

helen

>>> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@cdc.gov> 02/04/2007
08:50 >>>

Dr. Weiss,

Thank you for agreeing to speak at the upcoming consultation. Our planning committee met on Friday to discuss the content of each presentation, and we are in need of someone who would be able to present a review of the evidence for other (non-HIV) health effects of MC (e.g., reduction in other STDs, penile cancer, etc.). In our search for the appropriate person, Dr. Hayes suggested that you might be able to include such a discussion in your talk. We would of course increase the length of time allotted to 35 minutes to allow adequate time to cover this new material. This is clearly quite short notice, but might you be able to include such a discussion in your presentation?

Thank you for your assistance. We look forward to working with you.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 17:17
To: 'Helen Weiss'
Subject: RE: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Excellent. Thank you. More details soon.

-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Helen Weiss [<mailto:Helen.Weiss@lshtm.ac.uk>]
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 17:16
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision

Hi Allan,

Yes, I would be happy to do this. Tim Mastro had mentioned this when I met him in Montreux.

best wishes
helen

>>> "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avt0@cdc.gov> 29/03/2007
14:12:30 >>>
Dr. Weiss,

I am coordinating preparations for CDC's upcoming consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US. We are pleased that you will be able to attend, and we would like to invite you to present an overview and background of MC and HIV prevention (Approx. 20 min, similar to the excellent presentation you gave at the recent WHO meeting). We will send further details in the coming weeks if you will

be able to present, but we wanted to contact you as early as possible to assess your availability.

Please contact me at your convenience to indicate whether you will be able to present. We look forward to hearing from you and to your participation in this consultation.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis,
STD, and TB Prevention
(proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 23 Apr 2007 22:42:17 +0000
To: rsvanhowe@mgh.org
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FW: MC Consultation: Speaker Bios

Thank you. You can call in at the following number:

(b)(6) Passcode (b)(6)

We will talk to you tomorrow at 11:00 AM EDT.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: rsvanhowe@mgh.org [mailto:rsvanhowe@mgh.org]
Sent: Monday, April 23, 2007 11:04
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: MC Consultation: Speaker Bios

Sorry, I haven't had a chance to respond. I had board meeting in Milwaukee for the past couple of days. Tuesday at 11 a.m. would be fine.

Bob Van Howe

"Taylor, Allan W.
(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" To: Robert S Van Howe/PESP/MGHS@mghs,
(b)(6)
<avt0@CDC.GOV> cc:
Department Not Subject: FW: MC Consultation: Speaker Bios
Found

04/23/2007 10:40 AM

Greetings. We wanted to follow up with you regarding the call suggested below. Let us know what might be a good time for a short call.

Thank you.
-Allan

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 17:28
To: 'Robert Van Howe'
Subject: RE: MC Consultation: Speaker Bios

Dr. Van Howe,

Thank you for this bio. We also are interested in setting up a brief call to discuss your talk to minimize duplication with other presentations. Would you be available early next week for a short call? Tuesday 4/24 at 11:00 EDT would be convenient for us, if that would work for you. If that time would not be convenient, please feel free to suggest alternate times. I will set up a conference line once we have decided on a mutually convenient time.

Thank you. Talk to you soon.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
(proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Robert Van Howe [redacted] (b)(6)
Sent: Thursday, April 19, 2007 12:07
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: MC Consultation: Speaker Bios

Dear Dr. Taylor,

Here is my brief bio.

Bob Van Howe

Robert S. Van Howe, M.D., M.S. received his B.A. from Saint Olaf College with majors in chemistry and philosophy and his M.D. from Loyola University Stritch School of Medicine. He completed his pediatric training at Children's Hospital of Wisconsin in Milwaukee. He has been in general pediatric practice since then. In 2003 he completed a M.S. in Clinical Research Design and Statistical Analysis at the University of Michigan School of Public Health. He currently holds a Clinical Assistant Professor position with the Michigan State University College of Human Medicine Department of Pediatrics. His areas of interest include cost-utility analysis, meta-analysis, neonatal hypoglycemia, and neonatal circumcision. His current research includes a prospective, longitudinal study of gastroesophageal reflux in infants, a Markov model of Cesarean section rates, monitoring post-natal depression and anxiety, estimating injury rates in an off-road bicycle race, bladder dysfunction, and estimating the health system costs of formulary changes.

On Apr 18, 2007, at 2:43 PM, Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

Dear Colleagues,

Thank you once again for speaking at the upcoming consultation on male circumcision and HIV prevention in the US. We would like to obtain short biographical sketches of each of you to use for your introductions and to include in the materials distributed to participants.

Please send a short (~1 paragraph) bio if possible by close of business (US Eastern time) Friday 4/20. In addition, please send the contact details that you would like included in materials distributed to conference participants (or indicate if you would like your contact information withheld).

Thank you. We look forward to an interesting and productive meeting.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention
(proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 5 Mar 2007 15:28:55 +0000
To: 'Craig Niederberger'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FW: Request from CDC

40-639-5166 will be best.

Looking forward to it!

Dawn K. Smith

From: Craig Niederberger [mailto:(b)(6)]
Sent: Friday, March 02, 2007 5:28 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: Request from CDC

Sounds great--which of the numbers is best for you?

On 3/2/07, **Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)** <dks0@cdc.gov> wrote:
Hi. It's been a busy week for both of us.

How about Tuesday at 10 AM our time (9 AM CST)? Will you call me?

Dawn K. Smith

From: Craig Niederberger [mailto:(b)(6)]
Sent: Friday, March 02, 2007 3:42 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: FW: Request from CDC

Hi Dawn,

I left a couple of messages on the numbers you left with Yan. How about anytime Monday Mar 5 between 1p and 2:30p, Tues Mar 6 between 9 and 11 am, Wed Mar 7 after 1:30 pm all CST?

Craig

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [mailto:dks0@cdc.gov]
Sent: Wednesday, February 28, 2007 8:49 AM
To: Craig Niederberger; Chisolm, Stephanie; [redacted] (b)(6)
Subject: RE: Request from CDC

Dr. Niederberger,

Thank you very much for getting back to me and for the attached article. I would very much like to talk with you. Is it possible to have your phone number and make an appointment for time to talk?

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: Craig Niederberger [mailto:[\[redacted\]](mailto:[redacted])] (b)(6)
Sent: Wednesday, February 28, 2007 8:24 AM
To: 'Chisolm, Stephanie'; [redacted] (b)(6)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Request from CDC

Hi Stephanie, here's a recent article that we wrote based on an Androlog thread concerning circumcision. It has some of what you might be interested in it, and is relatively current. Happy to talk to Dawn--just have her email me directly at [redacted] (b)(6) or [redacted] (b)(6) if she'd like.

Craig

-----Original Message-----

From: Chisolm, Stephanie [mailto:schisolm@auanet.org]
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 6:35 PM
To: Craig Niederberger; [redacted] (b)(6)
Subject: FW: Request from CDC

Hi Craig & Allen! I've got something interesting for you. This request (see below) came from the CDC and I thought you might like to weigh in on this. I would be happy to contact Dr. Smith if you are interested, or could recommend someone who would be a good fit if this is not something you can be involved with at this time. I would like to make the connection so that she can see the Foundation is involved. Please let me know. Thanks.

Stephanie Chisolm, Ph.D.

Director of Patient Education
American Urological Association Foundation
Phone: 410-689-4038
www.AUAFoundation.org
www.urologyhealth.org

From: Reuwer, Brian on behalf of z~IM - govaffairs
Sent: Tue 2/27/2007 12:41 PM
To: # - AUA Foundation
Subject: FW: Request from CDC

We got this request on the government affairs email. I have not responded but this sounds like it is right up your alley.

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>]
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 10:41 AM
To: z~IM - govaffairs
Subject: Request from CDC

Dear colleague,

CDC is planning an external consultation on male circumcision for the prevention of HIV acquisition in the US. We want to discuss whether and how the recent international clinical trials showing a 50-60% reduction for males at heterosexual risk following circumcision as young adults should be incorporated into HIV prevention activities in the US.

We would like to discuss participation by a clinical representative from AUA and perhaps someone from the Foundation Patient Advocacy Council as well.

You can reach me at the number below or at 404-386-9301. Thank you for your consideration of this request.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 6 Apr 2007 14:28:07 +0000
To: 'Myron Cohen'; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Fw: Re: Circumcision Consultation

Hi Mike,

Glad you can come. We'll have our travel contractor contact you, probably next week.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
Sent: Friday, April 06, 2007 9:34 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Fw: Re: Circumcision Consultation

Ok. Ill get there as early as possible on thursday. I assume Bob will hook me up with the travel agency. I was amazed to see nyc moving ahead of your meeting. I am also concerned about reality testing of some assumptions about transmission probabilities, safety of circumcision if it becomes a profit center for surgeons, sexual behaviors, etc.

see you soon.

mike

i

Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

>
> Hi Mike,
> I think you should come. The first day will be largely presdenations
> of info you already know and limited new information you could get up
> to speed on pretty quickly. Sounds like you have some views that would
> be a valuable contribution for the second day of breakout discussions.
>
> I'm on leave this week. Can f/u next week.
>
> Cheers,
> PK
> -----
> Sent from my wireless handheld

> ----- Original Message -----

> From: [redacted] (b)(6) <[redacted] (b)(6)>
> To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Cc: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Sent: Fri Apr 06 08:09:38 2007

> Subject: FW: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>
> Peter - Mike Cohen won't be able to arrive at the consultation until
> afternoon. Is it worth it for him to come? Could you give him a
> call? I don't have his number readily available, but Cathy Burckhardt
> of my branch has his number.
> Thanks
> Bob Kohmescher
>
>
> -----Original Message-----
> From: Myron Cohen <myron_cohen@med.unc.edu>
> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
> Sent: Thu Apr 05 08:07:51 2007
> Subject: Re: Circumcision Consultation
>
> Hi Bob,
>
> I might be able to get there by early afternoon of April 26th but
> this might not be so helpful to you, especially if there is a clamor
> for attendance. Where are you actually meeting?
>
> I have actually spent a lot of time this week talking about
> circumcision for MSM. To expose my bias I cannot see how clinical
> trials would be ethical based on the biology of protection and the
> risk behaviors of the study population. But this leads to interesting debates.
>
> Please advise.
>
> THX
>
> Mike
>
> Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>> Mike - We're in the process of ensuring that we have adequate space
>> at the hotel for the consultation on circumcision. Have you had a
>> chance to review your calendar to see if you are available April 26-27?
>>
>> We'll be sending out more information about the consultation very
>> shortly.
>>
>> Thanks,
>>
>> Bob Kohmescher
>> Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch Centers
>> for Disease Control & Prevention Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
>> (A43) 1600 Clifton Rd NE Atlanta, GA 30333
>> -----
>> (404) 639-1914
>> (404) 639-5260 (fax)
>> Corp 8/Rm 5057
>> -----Original Message-----
>> From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
>> Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 5:49 PM
>> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
>> Subject: Re: Circumcision Consultation

>>
>> THx. Il let you know ASAP. Did I ignore an earlier invitation?? This
>> was
>>
>> much discu ssed at NUH this week and Ken Mayer asked me why I had
>> not responded., Sorry if that was the case.
>>
>> Mike
>>
>> Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>>
>>> Mike - CDC is sponsoring a meeting to discuss the research data on
>>> the
>>>
>>>
>>> value of circumcision in HIV prevention. The meeting will be held
>>> in Atlanta on April 26 and 27.
>>>
>>> By the conclusion of the meeting, participants will:
>>>
>>> * Review science regarding circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV
>>> and
>>>
>>>
>>> other adverse health consequences
>>>
>>> * Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general)
>>> and
>>>
>>>
>>> adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
>>>
>>> * Discuss potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that
>>> should be made by CDC
>>>
>>> *
>>>
>>> Please let me know whether you'll be able to attend. CDC will cover
>>> all travel costs. If you are interested and able to attend, we'll
>>> send
>>>
>>>
>>> a formal letter of invitation.
>>>
>>> And also, thanks for your willingness to speak at our 2007 National
>>> HIV Prevention Conference in December!
>>>
>>> Bob Kohmescher
>>>
>>> Acting Chief, Technical Information & Communications Branch
>>>
>>> Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

>>>
>>> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (A43)
>>>
>>> 1600 Clifton Rd NE
>>>
>>> Atlanta, GA 30333
>>>
>>> ----->>
>>> (404) 639-1914
>>>
>>> (404) 639-5260 (fax)
>>>
>>> Corp 8/Rm 5057
>>>
>>> -----Original Message-----
>>> From: Myron Cohen [mailto:myron_cohen@med.unc.edu]
>>> Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 6:57 PM
>>> To: Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); James, Kathy
>>> Subject: Re: FW: 2007 National HIV Prevention Conference
>>>
>>> oops. maybe my signature is not working.
>>>
>>> my phone is 919-966-2536
>>>
>>> address ID Center
>>>
>>> UNC
>>>
>>> Bioinformatics Building
>>>
>>> Second Floor
>>>
>>> 130 Mason Farm Road
>>>
>>> Chapel Hill, NC 27599-7030
>>>
>>> Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:
>>>
>>>
>>>> Mike - Thanks for agreeing to serve as a plenary speaker at our
>>>> 2007
>>>>
>>>> National HIV Prevention Conference in December. We'll be sending
>>>> you
>>>>
>>> a
>>>
>>>> formal letter acknowledging this very shortly. Could you please
>>>> send
>>>>
>>>> me your mailing address and phone number?
>>>>
>>>> Thanks,
>>>>
>>>> Bob Kohmescher
>>>>

>>>> Conference Coordinator, 2007 NHPC
>>>>
>>>> Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
>>>>
>>>> Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention (A43)
>>>>
>>>> 1600 Clifton Rd NE
>>>>
>>>> Atlanta, GA 30333
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>>>> (404) 639-1914
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>>>> (404) 639-5260 (fax)
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>>>> Corp 8/Rm 5057
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>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 23 Feb 2007 20:59:15 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FYI Museveni response to circumcision trial results

(b)(5)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, February 23, 2007 3:56 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: FYI Museveni response to circumcision trial results

(b)(5)

-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, February 23, 2007 14:28
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FYI Museveni response to circumcision trial results

"Uganda: Museveni scoffs at circumcision for HIV-AIDS"

Author(s): Agness Nandutu

Date: 18 February 2007

Source: *The Monitor*

<http://allafrica.com/stories/200702170370.html>

President Yoweri Museveni has trashed claims that circumcised men are less prone to HIV/Aids infection. Mr Museveni was on Thursday speaking to over 350 NRM district leaders and MPs from the central region at Vice President Gilbert Bukenya's Garuga home, off the Kampala-Entebbe highway.

In a press statement from Prof. Bukenya's office, Mr Museveni warned that immorality was leading to increased infection rates. "The only way to avoid getting infected is to avoid having illicit sexual affairs. Why are Muslims and Bagisu dying? Who beats the Bagisu when it comes to circumcising men?" Mr Museveni asked. Among the Bagisu, a tribe in eastern Uganda, every male, between adolescence and manhood, must be circumcised. The circumcision is done in the open during daytime, in the presence of witnesses.

Mr Museveni also scoffed at claims that the **microbicide** gels that have been on trial in various countries can be an effective prevention against HIV/Aids. "People know how and where they can catch Aids. Unless they fight irresponsible sexual relationships, they cannot stop it," he said.

United States researchers last month halted clinical trials of cellulose sulphate, a topical **microbicide** gel being tested for prevention of HIV/Aids infection in women. Preliminary data indicated that cellulose sulphate could lead to an increased risk of HIV infections in women who use the compound. The trial was being conducted in South Africa, Benin and India.

Mr Museveni said part of the NRM strategy was to keep Ugandans alive and in good health. He said his government had implemented immunisation programmes among children and sensitised the entire country about the HIV/Aids pandemic. The approach, he said, had helped reduce the rate of infection.

The other approach, he said, was the doling out of ARV drugs to infected Ugandans in a bid to prolong their lives.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 20 Apr 2007 20:36:15 +0000
To: jpeterson@gsu.edu
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Go Blue at CDC!
Attachments: MC Consultation Invitation Letter 2.pdf

Dr. Peterson,

Attached is an invitation letter with details about the venue and timing of the meeting. We look forward to your participation.

Thank you.
-Allan

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 16:30
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Go Blue at CDC!

Great news! John Peter can come. Please help him get registered. :)

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: John Peterson [mailto:jpeterson@gsu.edu]
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 4:26 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Go Blue at CDC!

Dawn,

I have followed the recent evidence with much concern, especially after the NYT article provoked some controversy. No problem with the late notice, if you will excuse my absence at the reception since I will be out of town for our new CDC study in Texas and on Thursday morning due to my class. I can attend Thursday afternoon following the lunch break and return all day Friday. Thank you for the invitation and understand your need to convene this important consultation. I look forward to the discussion with the breakout groups and seeing you again to get caught up.

John

John L. Peterson, Ph.D.

Professor
Department of Psychology
Georgia State University
P. O. Box 5010
Atlanta, Georgia 30303-5010

(404) 651-1148 (phone)
(404) 651-1391 (fax)
jpeterson@gsu.edu (email)

>>> "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIHISTP)" <dks0@cdc.gov> 04/20/07 11:17 AM

>>> >>>

John,

I've recently returned to Atlanta and am working with the group planning a consultation on what role male circumcision could play in US HIV prevention efforts. Since the trial data shows impressive protection for heterosexual African men (i.e., the insertive partner) and our epidemic is driven by MSM partnerships where few men are tops-only, there's a lot to consider. And our early read is that concerns are already apparent among AA MSM about surgically altering their genitalia, even though it would be a voluntary procedure.

I'm sorry for the late notice but wonder if you could possibly attend the consultation. I've attached the agenda FYI. Let me know if it's possible and/or you're interested. <<MCAgenda10.doc>>

For this and other reasons, I hope to see you sometime soon and catch up a bit :)

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

April 12, 2007

Dear Colleague,

The CDC Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention would like to request your participation in the **Consultation on Male Circumcision for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences in the United States** to be held on April 26-27, 2007 at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park in Atlanta, GA.

This meeting is being convened in response to the three African clinical trials showing a protective effect of male circumcision on HIV acquisition by adolescent and adult men. While we are excited to have another prevention tool available in the global fight against HIV, these trials were done with heterosexual men in countries with high-incidence, generalized epidemics in Africa. It is not clear how to incorporate male circumcision into prevention efforts in the US where the epidemic profile is quite different from that in Africa, and where neonatal circumcision is very common. During this consultation, we will discuss what can reasonably be adapted from the African trials, what the cost-effectiveness and potential protective impact may be in high risk populations in the US, and what additional information is needed to decide on possible domestic implementation strategies.

Meeting Objectives

By the conclusion of the consultation, participants will:

- Review science regarding male circumcision efficacy in preventing HIV and other adverse health consequences
- Review existing data regarding cost-benefits of infant (general) and adult male (MSM, other men) circumcision for disease prevention
- Provide expert advice to CDC regarding potential next programmatic steps or recommendations that should be made by CDC

Space will be available for presentation of posters if participants have data or activities they wish to share. Please contact us in advance if you plan to prepare a poster so that we may ensure adequate space.

CDC is unable to provide for your travel expenses; however we have reserved a block of rooms at the Embassy Suites Hotel at Centennial Olympic Park for our participants at the US Government rate of USD\$124/night. The hotel is located at 267 Marietta Street, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313. Tel: +1-404-223-2300 Fax: +1-404-223-0925). The meeting will begin at 08:30 AM on April 26 and will adjourn at 3:00 PM on April 27. For logistical and travel-related questions, please refer to the logistical memo from Leris Bernard, B L Seamon, which accompanies this letter.

We hope you can join us to lend your expertise to the consultation. Please contact Allan Taylor, MD, MPH at ataylor2@cdc.gov or at (404) 639-6120 if you have any questions or comments. We are looking forward to your participation and to a productive consultation.

Sincerely,

Timothy D. Mastro, MD
Deputy Director for Science
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 16 Mar 2007 20:46:33 +0000
To: 'Bailey'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Impact of male circumcision

Bob,

Right now, we only have one (long) talk about the 3 trials. Our consultation is only 1-3/4 days and most of the second day is spent in workgroups.

Let me discuss with the planning group and get back to you soon (next week).

Dawn K. Smith

From: Bailey [mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu]
Sent: Friday, March 16, 2007 3:57 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Impact of male circumcision

Dawn,

I really can't commit to that now. I am familiar with those issues, but it would entail a lot of time to put together all the evidence in a systematic way. I'm happy to present our trial data on safety. I am also happy to present the study that I did comparing medical and traditional circumcision in Bungoma District, Kenya. I could also add some analyses of perceptions about sensation/pleasure that we included in our trial but have not yet analysed. But I'm sorry, I just don't have the time now to put together all the evidence worldwide, or even U.S.-based about safety, and I assume that is what you really want. What goes on in east and southern Africa, while of great interest and importance, is not particularly relevant to the situation here in the U.S.

You might ask Ed Schoen. He is very pro-circumcision, but he is also very well versed in the U.S. clinical data, which is really what is relevant for this discussion.

Will you be asking me to present a summary of our trial results?

Bob

----- Original Message -----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Bailey
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 16, 2007 12:32 PM
Subject: RE: Impact of male circumcision

Bob,

Would you be willing to give a talk called something like "evidence of adverse outcomes in male circumcision" It would follow the talks on the trials data and the STI benefits of circumcision. We'd also like to raise awareness about safety, sensation change, etc.issues that lead to an appropriate level of caution.

Talk to you soon.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Bailey [mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu]

Sent: Tuesday, March 13, 2007 12:05 PM

To: Thomas Wiswell; David Wilson; Carolyn Masters Williams; Williams, Brian G (WHO); Amy Welton; Helen Weiss; Gerald Weiss; Maria Wawer (E-mail); tcoates@mednet.ucla.edu; Stover, John; Stirling, Mark; Markus Steiner; Stanton, David (CDC usaid.gov); Michael Stalker; smoses@cc.umanitoba.ca; Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nandi Siegfried; Shelton, Jim(GH/PRH); Schmid, George Philip (WHO); Russell, Sabin; Thomas von Riess; Renee Ridzon; rhughes@jhpiego.net; Adrian Puren; pperchal@engenderhealth.org; Malcolm Potts; Dr. Jeremy Penner; Roger Pearson; Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Parker, Corette B.; Christopher Ouma; eolorin@jhpiego.net; O'Reilly, Kevin Richards; nweste1; Nolan, Monica (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nolan, Monica (Abidjan) (CDC gapcdcci.org); Phil Nieburg; Rebecca Ngalande; nico nagelkerke; Daniel Halperin

Subject: Impact of male circumcision

Nagelkerke NJD, Moses S, de Vlas SJ and Bailey RC. Modeling the public health impact of male circumcision for HIV prevention in high prevalence areas in Africa. BMC Infectious Diseases 2007, 7:16, 13 march, 2007.

This paper is now available with open access at:

<http://www.biomedcentral.com/bmcinfectdis/>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 20 Feb 2007 23:12:35 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: male circumcision in the US

Yep. At the meeting last week, we came to the same conclusion about presenters. I'm trying to contact Bob Bailey for that. But also wanted to check on Bertran's availability. Hence the e-mail respons.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 20, 2007 6:08 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: male circumcision in the US

Hi - sorry I have been remiss in leading on the agenda. I'd like to be in the loop but would like to bow out of lead role if possible.

I think it would be preferable to have an American presenting the data - Bob Bailey, Ron Gray, etc. They would be more appropriate as a participant in bridging to our US issues. And we would save on travel costs. Would be nice of us to include Bertran as an observer if they are also planning something like this for France, but would rather hold off on that decision until we have a better sense of the size/numbers.

PK

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 20, 2007 2:26 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: male circumcision in the US

Allan,

Bertran Auvert is interested - see below. Haven't heard yet from Bob Bailey so I'll try and reach him again. Interesting to see that a European nation is about the tackle the same questions.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Bertran Auvert [<mailto:bertran.auvert@uvsq.fr>]
Sent: Saturday, February 17, 2007 11:50 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Jean-François Delfraissy
Subject: Re: male circumcision in the US

Hi dawn,
Thanks for this email.
Of course. I will be glad to attempt/present.

I suppose you know that I don't know anything to our question: "the public health implications of MC trial results for the US"!

Nevertheless, I am very interested to take part of this meeting because the same question is going to be discussed for France in the next months!

Best

Bertran.

Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) a écrit :

>

> Dr. Auvert,

>

> CDC is planning a consultation on the public health implications of MC

> trial results for the US and we wondered if you might be available to

> attend/present. Our target dates are either the second or fourth week

> in April.

>

> Thank you for considering this request

>

> *Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH*

> Acting Associate Chief for Science

> Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP

> CDC

>

> 404.639.5166

> dsmith1@cdc.gov

>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 20 Feb 2007 21:38:32 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: male circumcision in the US

Great news. Thanks, Dawn, for contacting him.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 20, 2007 14:26
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: male circumcision in the US

Allan,

Bertran Auvert is interested - see below. Haven't heard yet from Bob Bailey so I'll try and reach him again. Interesting to see that a European nation is about to tackle the same questions.

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> Thank you for considering this request
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> *Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH*
> Acting Associate Chief for Science
> Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
> CDC
>
> 404.639.5166
> dsmith1@cdc.gov
>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 14 Feb 2007 17:01:31 +0000
To: 'Kebaabetswe, Poloko'
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chen, Robert (Bob) (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chillag, Kata (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Thigpen, Michael C. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Brooks, John T. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Male circumcision offered by HIV prevention trials

(b)(5)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kebaabetswe, Poloko [<mailto:KebaabetsweP@bw.cdc.gov>]
Sent: Wednesday, February 14, 2007 10:09 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chen, Robert (Bob) (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chillag, Kata (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Thigpen, Michael C. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Brooks, John T. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Male circumcision offered by HIV prevention trials

Thanks. Wao hope the circumcision issue don't spill over to affect our trial

Please note that my email has changed to kebaabetswep@bw.cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) [<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>]
Sent: Wednesday, February 14, 2007 3:09 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter; Paxton, Lynn; Chen, Robert (Bob); Mastro, Tim
Cc: Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D.; Chillag, Kata; Taylor, Allan W.; Thigpen, Michael C.; Brooks, John T.; Kebaabetswe, Poloko
Subject: Male circumcision offered by HIV prevention trials

**SOUTH AFRICA: "HIV-Vaccine Trial to Involve Thousands in South Africa"
Business Day (Johannesburg) (02.09.07):: Tamar Kahn**

Scientists are recruiting South African volunteers of different races, sexual orientations, and economic strata to take part in a trial of Merck's HIV vaccine candidate MRKAd5 HIV-1...

The \$35 million experiment, dubbed Phambill, is run by the international HIV Trials Network and the South African AIDS Vaccine Initiative, with backing from Eskom and the South African government. It has been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration, the South African Medicines Control Council, and the agriculture department, and it will be overseen by an independent monitoring board.

The trial will run parallel with studies in the United States and Latin America to determine whether the vaccine works against different strains of HIV, including the clade C strain common to South Africa. At least 5.5 million South Africans (11 percent) have HIV/AIDS.

The vaccine, based on a modified version of the common cold virus combined with three HIV genes, has already been tested for safety in Phase I and IIa trials. Researchers must now determine whether the candidate stimulates the body to recognize and kill HIV. Developed against the clade B virus, scientists hope the vaccine will also be effective against clade C.

Scientists intend to enroll 3,000 participants from Gauteng, North West, Western Cape and KwaZulu-Natal. Participants will receive free male and female condoms and safe-sex advice. Men will be offered circumcision to reduce the risk of HIV transmission.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

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dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 30 Mar 2007 16:43:26 +0000
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Excellent. Thanks. I'll be ready.
-Allan

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:14
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Heads up - we'll meet with OD week after next as to prepare for MC consultation. Would be best if you both can be there, and let me ask one of you to be prepared to present the latest updates on agenda, invitees, etc.

Thanks,
PK

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:07 PM
To: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: FW: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

TT,
Please set up a 1 hour meeting with:
Rob Janssen
Tim Mastro
Rich Wolitski
Invite both Dawn Smith and Allan Taylor. One of the two of them is required, both are welcome

These are to be invited, but if they are not available the meeting should go ahead anyway:
Janet Cleveland (not required)
Craig Studer (not required)
Patrick Sullivan (not required)

Should be able to use conf room 5A. Will not need any special phone, computer, etc.

Should be the week of April 9, after I am back from leave.

Subject - "Planning for CDC Male Circumcision Consultation - (April 26, 27)"

Thanks!
PK

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 10:00 AM

To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

And yes – please plan on a briefing of Rob, me, Rich W, Janet C (not required), & Craig S (not required) the week of April 9.

Tim

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 9:46 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Peter – thank you, glad this is on track. I will try to get with Rob on this – we are both eager to participate and will sort out our roles. We can ask Kevin about this at our 2:2 on 4/2.

It looks like some key people are not yet confirmed. I had earlier suggested that Richard Hayes not be invited (from London) is Helen Weiss can attend. Need to lock in Maria Wawer.

Tim

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 2:05 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Hi Tim and Rob,

Here is latest version of MC consultation agenda. It looks like we will have a hotel identified very soon and are on track for April 26-27. The planning team is meeting again tomorrow. We are also planning a pre-meeting of the broader CDC MC WG before the consultation.

1. Please confirm your own availability/agreement for the designated roles.
2. Please advise on inviting Kevin. He is currently slated to provide welcoming remarks. We can draft a formal invitation letter if desired.
3. Please provide any other comments on the agenda.
4. Please let me know if you want me to also schedule a DHAP pre-meeting and whom to include.

Thanks,
PK

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 12:01 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Revised agenda and speaker status

Dear all,

I've amended the draft agenda based on comments I received since last Friday and added notation of whether speakers/facilitators are confirmed or invited (but not yet confirmed). Any other changes before tomorrow's meeting?

<< File: MCAgenda6.doc >>

Thanks.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Fri, 30 Mar 2007 16:43:01 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Exactly: we need to discuss at our meeting today. I think we could ask Weiss to fold it into her talk or ask Maria Wawer to do it (if she's coming), or maybe Tom Coates, now that he's confirmed?

-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:35
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

That's fine but then who is giving that talk?

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:33 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

I got email from her Wednesday about this. My understanding is that she was holding off on inviting him while we checked on finances and Weiss's attendance. (Sorry about that: I forgot to cc you on that chain.)

-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:26
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Allan,

That was for the "repeat presentations" from the WHO meeting and you're right that once we got Helen Weiss, we weren't considering him for that role.

But for the talk on the other health consequences of circumcision, Mary Kamb discussed with STD folk (because we had suggested Tom Peterman) and they suggested him for that talk (along with Bob who had previously said he was too busy to prepare a new talk). So I think she's inviting him for that but you should check with her.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:22 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Hi, guys.

I actually don't think Richard ended up being invited after all, because we wanted to wait to see if we had Weiss (which we do). We'll need to discuss who can do that presentation at our meeting.

-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:20
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Peter,

Richard is being invited for a different talk than our original discussion with Tim.

Both Patrick and I are attempting to contact Maria Wawer daily. Only so much we can do.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:16 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

FYI

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 12:16 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation draft agenda and speaker status

Thanks. We are meeting this afternoon to nail down speakers/invitees.

PK

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Friday, March 30, 2007 9:46 AM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
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It looks like some key people are not yet confirmed. I had earlier suggested that Richard Hayes not be invited (from London) is Helen Weiss can attend. Need to lock in Maria Wawer.

Tim

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Thanks.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

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dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 7 Mar 2007 22:14:20 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MC consultation ethicist

Great. Thanks for doing that.

Still waiting on the German articles.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 15:36
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Chillag, Kata (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: MC consultation ethicist

Hi all,

Didn't hear from nancy Kass as expected and she's now out the office for a while. So I went ahead and contacted Bernie Lo. As you'll see below, he's accepted tentatively.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Bernard Lo [mailto:bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 3:17 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: CDC consultation

Dear Dawn,

Yes, I would like to come.
Let me check my calendar to move some things around and get back to you.
Hope all is well

Bernie

Bernard Lo, M.D.
Professor of Medicine
Director, Program in Medical Ethics
University of California San Francisco
521 Parnassus Avenue
Room C-126, Box 0903
San Francisco, CA 94143-0903
bernie@medicine.ucsf.edu

Phone 415-476-5370
Fax 415-476-5020

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On Mar 7, 2007, at 9:46 AM, Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) wrote:

Bernie,

Hi there :) CDC is planning an external consultation about what role male circumcision might/should play in HIV prevention in the US. We were wondering if you might be available and interested to participate? We'd especially like to hear your thoughts about some of the public health ethics questions that are being raised.

For example, should parents be allowed/encouraged to consent to an elective surgical procedure (with attendant pain and risks) in order to reduce the child's risk of acquiring HIV many years later, when the child would be of age to make their own decision. Is it ethical to recommend only for heterosexual men (where we have trial data on efficacy) and hold off for gay men (where we have no efficacy trial data, and can't even reasonably extrapolate it for the receptive partner).

The consultation is April 26-27 in Atlanta. Hope you can come

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 2 Apr 2007 16:03:15 +0000
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Meeting about MC in the US

I emailed Dr. Weiss to assess her willingness to include this added material. Thanks, all.

-Allan

From: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 09:42
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Meeting about MC in the US

Just got note back from Richard Hayes, who is unfortunately unable to attend. He suggests contacting Helen Weiss, whom I believe has already agreed to come (is that right?)

I propose we should ask Helen to include in her global review data on STDs and other outcomes, and increase her time slot by 15 minutes or so. She has reviewed the observational studies in the past, but the really interesting thing will be new data coming out of the African trials (that also looked at other STD outcomes, in addition to HIV).

Mary

From: Richard Hayes [mailto:Richard.Hayes@lshtm.ac.uk]
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 6:10 AM
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Meeting about MC in the US

Dear Mary: Many thanks for the invitation to this important meeting. Unfortunately I can't come at that time because of teaching commitments here at the School (the next few weeks are my main teaching period). May I suggest that you could invite my colleague Helen Weiss - we work very closely on this topic, and Helen is now an acknowledged expert on male circumcision - also, she is now on sabbatical in Seattle, and so may be able to travel to Atlanta quite easily. She has an email address there: hweiss@fhcrc.org

With all good wishes. Richard.

Richard Hayes
Professor of Epidemiology & International Health,

Infectious Disease Epidemiology Unit,
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine,
Keppel Street, London WC1E 7HT, UK.

Tel: 020 7927 2243
Fax: 020 7637 4314
Email: Richard.Hayes@lshtm.ac.uk

>>> "Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <mlk5@cdc.gov> 31/03/2007 01:14 >>>
Hi Richard,

I'm a member of CDC's Working Group on male circumcision and am contacting you to see if you might be willing/able to participate in a consultation that CDC's Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention is holding on "Public Health issues around male circumcision in the US for prevention of HIV infection and other health consequences."

This is very short notice: The consultation will be taking place in Atlanta April 26-27 (Th/Fr). It's intended to bring together a small group of experts in the area to review the existing data considering US epidemiology and discuss whether/how the African trial results may play a role here, and whether (and if so what types of) any additional information are needed to make any type of public health recommendations. It is a small meeting, and will have about 10 invited speakers as well as several invited attendees.

One of the topics on the agenda the first morning is a review of the data on **the current evidence around male circumcision as a prevention intervention for other, non-HIV, outcomes including STIs and preventable cancers**. *** We're wondering, is there a possibility that you would be able to speak on this topic? *** There is an ~ 30 minute time slot available during the morning session (April 26th). CDC will be able to support travel costs

I realize time is short and you are very busy, but appreciate your consideration. You would be an enormous support to this meeting.

Warm regards, Mary

Mary L. Kamb, MD, MPH
International Coordinator
Division of STD Prevention
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC)
(404) 639-8632

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Mon, 2 Apr 2007 14:43:32 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Meeting about MC in the US

Fine by me.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 10:25 AM
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Meeting about MC in the US

In the interest of time, that seems like a good solution, if she's willing. Thoughts?

-Allan

From: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, April 02, 2007 09:42
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
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With all good wishes. Richard.

Richard Hayes
Professor of Epidemiology & International Health,
Infectious Disease Epidemiology Unit,
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine,
Keppel Street, London WC1E 7HT, UK.

Tel: 020 7927 2243
Fax: 020 7637 4314
Email: Richard.Hayes@lshtm.ac.uk

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I'm a member of CDC's Working Group on male circumcision and am contacting you to see if you might be willing/able to participate in a consultation that CDC's Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention is holding on "Public Health issues around male circumcision in the US for prevention of HIV infection and other health consequences."

This is very short notice: The consultation will be taking place in Atlanta April 26-27 (Th/Fr). It's intended to bring together a small group of experts in the area to review the existing data considering US epidemiology and discuss whether/how the African trial results may play a role here, and whether (and if so what types of) any additional information are needed to make any type of public health recommendations. It is a small meeting, and will have about 10 invited speakers as well as several invited attendees.

One of the topics on the agenda the first morning is a review of the data on **the current evidence around male circumcision as a prevention intervention for other, non-HIV, outcomes including STIs and preventable cancers**. *** We're wondering, is there a possibility that you would be able to speak on this topic? *** There is an ~ 30 minute time slot available during the morning session (April 26th). CDC will be able to support travel costs

I realize time is short and you are very busy, but appreciate your consideration. You would be an enormous support to this meeting.

Warm regards, Mary

Mary L. Kamb, MD, MPH
International Coordinator

*Division of STD Prevention
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC)
(404) 639-8632*

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 28 Feb 2007 14:33:23 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Right,

My confusion is that we talked about others who are not on the list and I don't remember making the choices where there were several discussed, e.g., Ruth Faden or Ron Bayer or Kata's suggested ethicist, Marie Wawer or Ron Grey. It's probably just my memory failing me.

No biggie. We can regroup at the next meeting :)

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 10:19 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Sounds like a plan to have kata talk to them -- I was just thinking that we should only poll those we definitely want to invite -- that's why I held off on polling the list of folks below.

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Feb 27 22:03:22 2007
Subject: RE: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Since Kata knows them, we should probably let her try first. I didn't understand that all the folk we discussed were actually being invited but if that's where we are now, that's cool.

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 7:10 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Hi Dawn,

I can add Bernie and Nancy to the online poll if you want. I think it is better to only poll those who we definitely want to invite -- it would be awkward to ask them for availability, and then not invite them. If we could determine a first choice when there are 2 possibles to fill a particular niche, then we could add the second if the first is not available.

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Feb 27 19:00:38 2007
Subject: RE: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Thanks, Patrick for the follow-up. Did Allan, Kata and I discussed ethics input and she is checking the availability of two others, Nancy Kass and Bernie Lo.

Peter, the group decided to find out availability for all without committing to inviting each person on the list.

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 27, 2007 6:32 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Fw: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Hi,

I have polled the following about availability. There are others whose names have come up that I felt I didn't have 100% clarity on; I can add them to the poll at any time. Let me know if you want me to add any of these now; otherwise, we can discuss at our meeting on friday.

Patrick

Need final determination:

Mario Perez (LAC)
Maria Wawer
Ron Bayer
Isaac Weisfuse (NYC)
Alan Greenberg
David Allen
Marcia Martin (DC)
Ron Valdisseri (VA)
Kreiss
Klausner
Schoen
John Douglas
Carol Ciesielski
Ken Dominguez
Fritz vonGriesven
Connie Cclum
King Holmes

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: MeetingWizard
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Feb 27 18:05:11 2007
Subject: MeetingWizard - confirmation of meeting request

Confirmation of Meeting Request: CDC Consultation on Male Circumcision for HIV Prevention in the US

Hi Patrick,

This message confirms that invitations were sent to the following:

bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr Bertran Auvert (b)(6) Steve Wakefield bozzette@smaill.rand.org Sam Bozzette carl.dieffenbach@nih.hhs.gov Carl Dieffenbach duffuswa@dhcc.sc.gov Wayne Duffus G.Garnett@ic.ac.uk Geoff Garnett jwasserh@fhcrc.org jwasserh@fhcrc.org Judy Wasserheit kenneth_mayer@brown.edu Ken Mayer melanie.bacon@nih.hhs.gov Melanie Bacon phavens@mcw.wsu Peter Havens rbailey@uic.edu Bob Bailey rgray@jhsp.edu Ron Gray smoses@cc.umanitoba.ca Stephen Moses spb@itsa.ucsf.edu Susan Buchbinder TCoates@mednet.ucla.edu Tom Coates tquinn2@jhmi.edu Tom Quinn victoria.cargill@nih.hhs.gov victoria.cargill@nih.hhs.gov Cargill-Swiren Victoria wcates@fhi.org Ward Cates

You can review complete information about this meeting event by the clicking the following link:

<http://www.meetingwizard.com/mwiz/m/check2.cfm?u=1170&m=85154&mtag=824381986>

Or...cut & paste it into the address bar of your browser.

The following is how your contact information appears, you can change it at any time: (if nothing appears, you have not yet entered your contact information)

Patrick Sullivan
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
tel: 404-639-2090
fax: 404-639-8640

MeetingWizard - great meetings begin here!

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 20 Mar 2007 13:55:36 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP);
Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Patrick, thank you for the clarification. I agree that it will be important to have someone there who can talk about the data on potentially increased risk of transmission from HIV+ men who have sex too soon after their procedure. It looks like we're doing okay on our travel budget so far. Would you be able to invite Maria Wawer?

Thanks.
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 09:13
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Fyi, we invited gray and he declined. The working group discussed 2 weeks ago and the conclusion was not to invite wawer as we had auvert and bailey confirmed. I'm fine with whatever decision, but wanted to make sure everyone knew that gray already declined for those dates.

Patrick

Sent from my BlackBerry Wireless Handheld

-----Original Message-----

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
CC: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Mar 20 09:03:40 2007
Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Allan -- I'm happy for you to do this. I'd suggest writing to Gray and Wawer together, indicating we have one slot for their study group. As you may know know, they are a husband/wife team.

Tim

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 19, 2007 8:24 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Tim,

No, I do not believe we have invited Ron Gray or Wawer yet. Below is the text of the "save-the-date" email that we've used for other invitees. If you'd like to send something of this sort in conjunction with your email to him, you can use this; otherwise, I would be happy to send it, if you prefer.

Dr. Gray,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

You will receive a second email shortly with a link to indicate your interest and availability to participate in this consultation. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thank you,

Thank you,
-Allan

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 19, 2007 5:53 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIHSTP)
Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Thanks Allan,

Have we invited the Rakai investigators (Marie Wawer or Ron Gray) yet? I got an e-mail from Ron Gray on a related matter.

Tim

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 12, 2007 5:26 PM
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCIHSTP)

Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Tim,

Thank you for these helpful comments.

- i. Definitely makes sense. We'll discuss at our meeting on Friday.
- ii. Excellent. We're planning to invite Helen Weiss. It sounds like she'll be a great addition.
- iii. Thank you for the presentations: they'll be very helpful.
- iv. We'll discuss PAHO at our meeting on Friday.
- v. No problem: we'll change the spreadsheet format.

Thanks again.

-Allan

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Saturday, March 10, 2007 11:13 AM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Janssen, Robert (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Allan,

Thanks for your work on this. A few comments:

- i. We definitely need to have the Rakai/Uganda study presented at our consultation, so we need to invite Gray or Wawer – they have the only data on MC of HIV+ men and the potential risk of increased transmission (from the Gate-funded study of HIV+ men). This was the big new news from the WHO consultation. It is essential we address this issue – a thorny issue is how to handle HIV+ men who want to be circumcised. and, I would much rather have Gray or Wawer travel here from Baltimore, than Auvert from Paris!). If we have people from all three, so be it.

ii. At the WHO meeting, Richard Hayes (LSHTM) did a wonderful job comparing the data across the three trials – Richard is in the same group as Helen Weiss: I discussed this with them the other day, and Richard would be happy to have Helen present this analysis at our consultation. So, Helen can give the global MC overview and then after hearing of the three trials, present the “meta-analysis”.

iii. I’ll send you some key presentations from the consultation. Note, we were not given permission to share these widely, so please don’t send to all. (I have attached here the presentations from Weiss and Hayes – again, these are not for general distribution).

iv. Consider inviting someone from PAHO – they relate more to the US than WHO on this issue. Rafael Mazin (mazinraf@paho.org) was at the meeting last week. However, if our meeting is getting too big, this is optional. The rep at the meeting from Brazil was frustrated that the meeting last week did not address their issues.

v. Can I request not using a color-coded spreadsheet to update invitees? It’s easier to have info in B/W.

Best,

Tim

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Sent: Friday, March 09, 2007 4:15 PM

To: Birx, Deborah (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)

Subject: Minutes: MC Consultation Planning meeting 3/9/07

Colleagues,

Attached are minutes from today’s MC Consultation Planning subcommittee meeting and the most recent invitee list (will be updated with the results of this meeting). I’ve reproduced action items below for your convenience:

Action Items

- * Patrick: invite Helen Weiss, Edgar Schoen, Thomas Wiswell and confer with Raul re: CMS representation. Update the invitee list on the shared drive at M:\SHARE\MC Consultation\Consultation Planning Subcommittee Minutes
<file:///C:/CDC/Project/NCHSTP_DHAP_Store1/SHARE/MC%20Consultation/Consultation%20Planning%20Subcommittee%20Minutes>
- * Dawn agreed to look into inviting someone from Kaiser and to contact Peggy Johnston from NIII.
- * Dawn/Mary: Consider adding Helen Weiss to the agenda to do an overview

Let me know if there are any changes or suggestions. Thanks, all.

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thu, 29 Mar 2007 16:49:24 +0000
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: RE: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

Only cause Bob sent me a copy directly :)

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 12:48 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: RE: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

Ah, way ahead of me as usual. ☺ Thanks.
-A

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Thursday, March 29, 2007 10:53
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: RE: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

It's already in the "new articles" folder.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 28, 2007 6:42 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Teague, Therese (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) (CTR)
Subject: FW: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

Add to the CD?
-A

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 20, 2007 19:54
To: Birx, Deborah (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary

(CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)

Subject: FW: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

A paper of interest. More updates will be forthcoming, including on the planned CDC consultation on MC/HIV in the US.

Conclusion: "Male circumcision was significantly associated with lower cervical cancer incidence and lower HIV prevalence in sub-Saharan Africa, independent of Muslim and Christian religion. As predicted, male circumcision was also strongly associated with lower HIV prevalence among countries with primarily heterosexual HIV transmission, but not among countries with primarily homosexual or injection drug use HIV transmission. These findings strengthen the reported biological link between MC and some sexually transmitted infectious diseases, including HIV and cervical cancer."

PK

From: Bailey [mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu]

Sent: Tuesday, March 13, 2007 11:54 AM

To: mwelsh@fhi.org; mothia2@uic.edu; Stephen Moses; Brian Morris; Supriya Mehta; (b)(6) Mbori-Ngacha, Dorothy; Klausner, Jeff (CDC sfdph.org); Doug Kirby; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Godfrey Kigozi; judlevy@uic.edu; helen.jackson; Ndinya-Achola J.; imaclea@Ms.UManitoba.CA; Richard Hayes; De Zoysa, Isabelle F. (WHO); Decock, Kevin; King K. Holmes; Amy Herman-Roloff; Hankins, Catherine; Gray, Ronald; Gavin, Lorrie (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP); Garnett, Geoffrey P; Fuchs, Nomi; Ted Fitzgerald; Farley, Timothy M.M.; egreen; Edgar.Schoen@kp.org; (U) Carter, Marion; abuve@itg.be; Kawango Agot; Michel Alary; David Alnwick; aronald@Ms.UManitoba.CA; Bertran Auvert; Bertran Auvert; Bacon, Melanie (NIH/NIAID); Stefan A. Bailis; Mark Barone; John Berman; Kasonde Bowa; Brito, Maximo; Alan Brody; Bunnell, Rebecca (Kenya) (CDC); Cassell, Michael(GH/OHA/TLR); Cates, Willard (CDC fhi.org); Chimbwete, Chiweni; cmatts1

Subject: Modeling the impact of male circumcision

Nagelkerke NJD, Moses S, de Vlas SJ and Bailey RC. Modeling the public health impact of male circumcision for HIV prevention in high prevalence areas in Africa. BMC Infectious Diseases 2007, 7:16, 13 march, 2007.

This paper is now available with open access at:

<http://www.biomedcentral.com/bmcinfectdis/>

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 6 Mar 2007 16:45:33 +0000
To: 'Craig Niederberger'
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: msg to Androlog

thanks, Craig. It was a great conversation this morning and we're looking forward to a lively discussion at the consultation in Atlanta.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Craig Niederberger [mailto:(b)(6)]
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 11:23 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: msg to Androlog

Hi Dawn, this is the message I sent to Androlog. I'll cull the responses, looking for a sentient dissenter...
Craig

Date: Tue, 6 Mar 2007 10:14:04 -0600 (CST)
From: androlog@godot.urol.uic.edu
To: craign@godot.urol.uic.edu
Subject: Risk/benefit analysis of circumcision and HIV

Androlog Mail

Dear Androlog participants,

Concerning the recent prospective trials investigating the effect of adult circumcision on HIV transmission:

Auvert B, Taljaard D, Lagarde E, Sobngwi-Tambekou J, Sitta R, Puren A.
Randomized, controlled intervention trial of male circumcision for reduction of HIV infection risk: the ANRS 1265 Trial. PLoS Med. 2005 Nov;2(11):e298.
Epub 2005 Oct 25. Erratum in: PLoS Med. 2006 May;3(5):e298. PMID: 16231970

Bailey RC, Moses S, Parker CB, Agot K, Maclean I, Krieger JN, Williams CF, Campbell RT, Ndinya-Achola JO. Male circumcision for HIV prevention in young men in Kisumu, Kenya: a randomised controlled trial. Lancet. 2007 Feb 24;369(9562):643-56. PMID: 17321310

in which circumcision was consistently statistically associated with a reduction of approximately half in HIV transmission, I was very curious about your sense of the risk side of the equation: does the surgical risk of circumcision balance the potential benefit in HIV reduction in developed and/or third world populations?

Thank you for your thoughts,
Craig Niederberger
craign@uic.edu

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 22:14:06 +0000
To: 'Robert Bailey'; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: potential urologists for CDC meeting later this month

Thanks, Bob.

We've been trying hard and appreciate your sending these additional recommendations. In addition to discussing with Tom Wiswell, we approached both the American Urologic Society and the American Association of Clinical Urologists and they jointly nominated Dr. Craig Neiderberger, who is attending. And since most neonatal cirs are not done by urologists, we also invited reps from AAP, AAFP, and ACOG.

We'll take a look and see how many slots we have open for some of the people Tom suggests. Please thank him for these references and thank you for passing them on to us.

We're finalizing the agenda in a day or two and then I will send you a copy.

See you soon!

-----Original Message-----

From: Robert Bailey [<mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 03, 2007 6:08 PM
To: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Fwd: potential urologists for CDC meeting later this month

>Peter and Dawn,

I'm not sure who is organizing the meeting on circumcision for later this month, but I spoke with Tom Wiswell and he was concerned that you may not have any urologists with extensive experience with MC in the U.S.. He forwarded me the below names and contacts.

Look forward to seeing you.

Bob

>
>Two Pediatric urologists, who may be able to address some "adult
>issues",
>too:
>
>1. Steve Skoog, University of Oregon Health Science Center, phone:
>(503)
>494-4779
>
>2. Gil Rushton, Children's National Medical Center (Washington, D.C.),
>phone: (202) 884-5000.
>
>Two adult urologists are:
>

>1. Ian Thompson, University of Texas at San
>Antonio: E-mail: <<mailto:ThompsonI@UTHSCSA.edu>>ThompsonI@UTHSCSA.edu
>
>2. Craig Peters, University of
>Virginia: E-mail: <<mailto:cap9b@virginia.edu>>cap9b@virginia.edu
>
>If these individuals fall through, they may be able to suggest others.
>I would appreciate it if you could forward this information on to the
>powers that be at the CDC.
>
>Thanks,
>
>Tom
>
>
>Thomas E. Wiswell, M.D.
>

(b)(6)

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 24 Apr 2007 23:58:34 +0000
To: Burgess, Rashad (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: questions.....
Attachments: MC Consultation Agenda Final.pdf

Hi, Rashad,

Here is the consultation agenda. It will be at the Embassy Suites Hotel - Centennial Olympic Park on April 26-27 (this Thurs-Fri). It begins at 8:30 on Thursday and ends at 3:00 PM on Friday. If you could, please send me the names of anyone who would like to attend from Atlanta so that I can ensure that we have enough space.

Let me know if you have any questions.
-Allan

-----Original Message-----

From: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, April 24, 2007 19:53
To: Burgess, Rashad (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (Botswana) (CDC)
Subject: Re: questions.....

Hi Rashad,

Just landed at ATL. Yes, we are holding a CDC Consultation on male circumcision (MC) and HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27, at the Embassy Suites Centennial Olympic Park. While it is too late to add to the invitation list, this is not a closed meeting. We have a good group of consultants, including community reps. Peter K or Allan T could send you the consultation agenda.

As you may know, we have a MC fact sheet on the DHAP website.

We'd be happy to be engaged with Matt and his group.

Best,
Tim

-----Original Message-----

From: Burgess, Rashad (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Apr 24 11:07:12 2007
Subject: FW: questions.....

Hi Tim,

I got a question from a colleague, Matt Hamilton, Director of HIV/AIDS Policy at the LA Gay and Lesbian Center, regarding some of our work in Circumcision and HIV Prevention with MSM. I am not able to respond to his question because none of our grantees are doing work in this area. Also, if my memory serves me correct, you are the lead of the Circumcision workgroup so I thought you may be able to provide me with some information that would help me respond to Matt Hamilton.

Thanks for your help.

Best,
Rashad

Rashad Burgess, MA

Team Leader

National Center for HIV, STD and TB Prevention

Division of HIV Prevention Program Branch

1600 Clifton Road, NE, MS-E-58

Atlanta, GA 30333

404-639-0907

404-639-5258 fax

From: Hamilton, Matt [<mailto:mhamilton@lagaycenter.org>]
Sent: Friday, April 20, 2007 3:13 PM
To: Burgess, Rashad (CDC/CCID/NCIIISTP)
Subject: questions.....

Hi rashad,

I hope that this note finds you well and not working too hard. Do you know what if anything is happening with the CDC looking at circumcision among gay and bi men here in the states? As you know there has been much discussion about implications for gay and bi men here in the states, since the African trials were ended. I read somewhere (if I get the details wrong forgive me) that the CDC would be pulling together a community and scientific advisory group to look at this issue and possible research related to it here in the states. The center would be very interested in being part of this as it is right up our alley so to speak, in regards to community involvement.

if you do know who's heading this up could you send me their contact info so that I can reach out to them? I'd appreciate your doing so. Any update on the gay group meeting with dr. fenton, I wasn't sure if you guys still planned to hold that meeting?

Take good care, many thanks in advance for your help.

matt

Matt Hamilton

Director of HIV/AIDS Policy

L.A. Gay & Lesbian Center

1625 N. Schrader Blvd.

Los Angeles, CA 90028

voice 323-993-7583

fax 323-308-4058

email mhamilton@lagaycenter.org

Consultation on Public Health Issues Regarding Male Circumcision in the United States for the Prevention of HIV Infection and Other Health Consequences

Atlanta, GA
April 26-27, 2007

AGENDA

Thursday, April 26

8:30 Welcome Dr. Rob Janssen
8:45 Charge to the Consultants and recent WHO/UNAIDS guidance Dr. Tim Mastro

Why consider increasing male circumcision in the United States?

Moderator: Dr. Tim Mastro

9:00 Overview of international male circumcision and HIV Dr. Helen Weiss
9:25 Results of the South Africa Trial Dr. Bertran Auvert
9:45 Results of the Kenya Trial Dr. Robert Bailey
10:05 Results of the Rakai Trial Dr. Ron Gray
10:30 Discussion

11:00 Break

11:30 Overview of domestic male circumcision Dr. Peter Kilmarx
11:50 Evidence on male circumcision and HIV in MSM Dr. Susan Buchbinder
12:10 Evidence of adverse outcomes in male circumcision Dr. Robert S. Van Howe
12:30 Discussion

1:00 Lunch

What is the potential cost of male circumcision and impact on HIV transmission in the US?

Moderator: Dr. John Douglas

2:30 Modeling impact and cost-effectiveness Dr. Stephanie Sansom
3:00 Cost of circumcision in US newborns and adults Dr. Edgar Schoen
3:30 Discussion

4:00 Break

4:20 Risk communication and disinhibition Dr. Brad Bartholow
4:40 Ethical, religious, and cultural issues Dr. Bernard Lo
5:00 Discussion and public comment period
5:30 Adjourn

Friday, April 27

8:30 Charge to Breakout Groups

Dr. Dawn K. Smith

8:45 Concurrent Breakout Sessions

1. MSW in the US

Dr. Lee Warner, facilitator

2. MSM in the US

Dr. Gary Marks, facilitator

3. Newborns in the US

Dr. Allan Taylor, facilitator

11:30 Lunch

Moderator:Dr. Naomi Bock

1:00 Report back and discussion - MSW Rapporteur

1:30 Report back and discussion – MSM Rapporteur

2:00 Report back and discussion – newborns Rapporteur

2:30 Summary Comments

Dr. Rob Janssen

3:00 Adjourn

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 21 Feb 2007 15:36:08 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Revised draft agenda and background document

Thanks, Dawn! I'll send it out today.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, February 20, 2007 18:26
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Revised draft agenda and background document

Allan,

Here's a cleaned up version incorporating changes from the discussion at last week's meeting

<< File: Male Circumcision Meeting)_BBackground.doc >> << File: MC Consultation Agenda (3).xls >>

Still some polishing needed but should be sent to the wider group with the minutes to get input from those unable to attend last week.

Dawn K. Smith, MD MS MPH
Acting Associate Chief for Science
Epidemiology Branch, DHAP, NCHSTP
CDC

404.639.5166
dsmith1@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 7 Mar 2007 17:53:17 +0000
To: 'Bailey'; Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Hi Bob,

Allan is talking to AAP to try and identify who on their advisory group was advocating against routine infant circ resulting in their softening their guidelines.

We're searching hard for an American but several of the issues raised against routine circ are not nation-specific (e.g., complication rates, loss of sensation, removing normal tissue for "minimal" personal benefit, etc). It would be better to have a rational detractor from europe than a non-scientific rant. We'll keep trying :)

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Bailey [<mailto:rcbailey@uic.edu>]
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 12:46 PM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Well, THE anti-circumcision "expert" is Robert van Howe, but he distorts the evidence badly and his a member of the anti-circ fringe. I think you might contact the AAP. Their recent guidelines have been quite, well, if not anti-circumcision, at least not pro. Get one of the members of their panel that reviewed the AAP policy on MC. Sorry that I don't have any names.

I think you need an American and would advise against a Brit. You need someone thoroughly familiar with practice in the U.S..

I don't know Dr. Neiderberger. It sounds like I should meet him.

Bob

----- Original Message -----

From: "Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <dks0@cdc.gov>
To: "Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pbk4@cdc.gov>; <rcbailey@uic.edu>; "Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <pss0@cdc.gov>
Cc: "Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)" <avi0@cdc.gov>
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 11:17 AM
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Glad we finally reached Bob!

Allan and I had a great talk with one of his UofI colleagues, Dr. Neiderberger, the rep from the American Urologic Association. Learned a bunch of cool stuff about urology and

andrology. Dr. Neiderberger is looking for what he termed a "sentient dissenter" among his andrology listserv colleagues and will try to get us a name in the next few days. In the meanwhile, Allan is also following up on a european urologist who has written quite a lot about the complications of urology. So hopefully one of these several routes will identify a good the counterpoint speaker.

Dawn K. Smith

-----Original Message-----

From: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 6:30 PM
To: 'rebailey@uic.edu'; Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Thanks Bob this is very helpful. Can I also ask, is there a "credible sceptic" who can summarize arguments against MC as an HIV prevention intervention in the US? It will be a controversial issue and we want to provide a balance of views or at least a counterpoint.

Thanks!
Peter K

Sent from my wireless handheld

----- Original Message -----

From: Bailey <rebailey@uic.edu>
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue Mar 06 17:40:16 2007
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

I highly recommend that you invite Dr. Thomas Wiswell, probably the foremost authority on infant circumcision in the U.S., famous for his research on infant circumcision and UTI infections. His e-mail address

is: (b)(6)

Also, an important consideration with circumcision is protection from penile and cervical cancer. The authority on this is Dr. Xavier Castellsague. His e-mail address is: xcastellsague@iconcologia.net

While the perspectives of myself and Bertran Auvert and others who have worked on male circumcision and HIV in Africa will be helpful, you should invite a few more experts on INFANT circumcision in general and infant circumcision in the U.S. in particular. I highly recommend Dr. Wiswell, and there should probably be a few more with extensive experience in infant circumcision in the U.S. Another name I can think of is Dr. Ed Schoen, of Kaiser Permanente.

Bob Bailey

----- Original Message -----

From: Sullivan, Patrick <<mailto:pss0@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
To: Wakefield, Steven (CDC and infant circumcision in <(b)(6)> the U.S..com) ;
bozzette@smmail1.rand.org ; carl.dieffenbach@nih.hhs.gov ; duffuswa@dhcc.sc.gov ; G.Garnett@ic.ac.uk ;
ahoward@fhrc.org ; kenneth_mayer@brown.edu ; melanie.bacon@nih.hhs.gov ; phavens@mew.edu ;
phavens@mew.wsu ; rebailey@uic.edu ; spb@itsa.ucsf.edu ; TCoates@mednet.ucla.edu ; tquinn2@jhmi.edu ;
victoria.cargill@nih.hhs.gov ; Cates, Willard (CDC <<mailto:wccates@fhi.org>> fhi.org) ; Klausner, Jeffrey (CDC

<mailto:jeff_klausner@dph.sf.ca.us> dph.sf.ca.us); Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov) <<mailto:iweisfus@health.nyc.gov>> ; aegl@gwu.edu ; Curran, Jim <<mailto:jcurran@sph.emory.edu>> (CDC sph.emory.edu) ; mitchell@avac.org ; Ciesielski, Carol (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) <<mailto:cae2@cdc.gov>> ; Douglas, John <<mailto:jyd3@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Valdiserri, Ronald <<mailto:Ronald.Valdiserri@va.gov>> ; Dominguez, Ken <<mailto:kld0@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; mperez@dhs.co.la.ca.us ; Romaguera, Raul A. <<mailto:rar2@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Wood, Bob <<mailto:Bob.Wood@METROK.COV>> ; bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) <<mailto:pbk4@cdc.gov>> ; Taylor, Allan W. <<mailto:avt0@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) ; Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP) <<mailto:dks0@cdc.gov>> ; Warner, Lee <<mailto:dlw7@cdc.gov>> (CDC/CCIP/NCCDPIIP)
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 10:06 AM
Subject: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Colleagues,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. For non-federal employees, we will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

Non-CDC participants will receive a second email shortly with a link to indicate your interest and availability to participate in this consultation. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Patrick Sullivan

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 1600 Clifton Road NE, MS E46 Atlanta, GA 30333 404-639-2090
Fax: 404-639-8640
email: <<mailto:pss0@cdc.gov>> pss0@cdc.gov (note: 4th digit is the number zero, not the letter "O")
Courier address: 8 Corporate Blvd, Atlanta GA 30329

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 14 Mar 2007 13:43:32 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

I'd be supportive if we have funds available still. Can we discuss at our meeting on Friday?
-Allan

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 09:20
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

I think an AMFAR person would be a good addition to the non-governmental side – what do you think about inviting Dr. Ruiz?

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Divisions of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Dieffenbach, Carl (NIH/NIAID) [E] [mailto:CDieffenba@niaid.nih.gov]
Sent: Monday, March 12, 2007 6:05 PM
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Dear Patrick:

I appreciate the efforts you are putting into this meeting. One additional person you may wish to invite is Dr. Monica Ruiz. She was in the Division of AIDS until recently and had a role in the prevention efforts in the Division. She is now at amfAR and her email is monica.ruiz@amfar.org. I applaud the breath of people you have already included and the attendees from the Division of AIDS are looking forward to participating.

Best Regards,

Carl

Carl W. Dieffenbach, Ph.D.
Acting Director
Division of AIDS, NIAID
6700-B Rockledge Drive MSC 7620
Bethesda, Maryland 20892-7620
Phone: (301) 496-0545
Fax: (301) 402-1505

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From: Sullivan, Patrick S. (CDC)
Sent: Tuesday, March 06, 2007 11:07 AM
To: Wakefield, Steven (CDC aol.com); bozzette@smmail1.rand.org; Dieffenbach, Carl (NIH/NIAID) [E]; duffuswa@dhec.sc.gov; G.Garnett@ic.ac.uk; ahoward@fhcrc.org; kenneth_mayer@brown.edu; Bacon, Melanie (NIH/NIAID) [C]; phavens@mcw.edu; phavens@mcw.wsu; rcbailey@uic.edu; spb@itsa.ucsf.edu; TCoates@mednet.ucla.edu; tqinn2@jhmi.edu; Cargill-Swiren, Victoria (NIH/OD) [E]; Cates, Ward; Klausner, Jeffrey (CDC dph.sf.ca.us); Weisfuse, Issac (CDC health.nyc.gov); aeg1@gwu.edu; Curran, M.D., M.P.H., James; mitchell@avac.org; Ciesielski, Carol A. (CDC); Douglas, John (CDC); Valdiserri, Ronald; Dominguez, Kenneth L. (CDC); mperez@dhs.co.la.ca.us; Romaguera, Raul A. (CDC); Wood, Bob; bertran.auvert@apr.aphp.fr
Cc: Kilmarx, Peter (CDC); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC); Smith, Dawn K. (CDC); Warner, Lee (CDC)
Subject: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Colleagues,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. For non-federal employees, we will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

Non-CDC participants will receive a second email shortly with a link to indicate your interest and availability to participate in this consultation. Knowing whether you plan to participate as soon as possible will help us plan for your travel. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me using the contact information below.

We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thanks,

Patrick Sullivan

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch

Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Road NE, MS E46
Atlanta, GA 30333
404-639-2090
Fax: 404-639-8640
email: pss0@cdc.gov (note: 4th digit is the number zero, not the letter "O")
Courier address: 8 Corporate Blvd, Atlanta GA 30329

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 3 Apr 2007 22:23:49 +0000
To: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision forHIVprevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr. Schoen,

Thank you for agreeing to give this presentation. It will be a very valuable addition to this meeting.

I would like to propose a conference call at your earliest convenience to coordinate the content of your presentation with some of our other presenters (to prevent duplication of effort). We have availability on Wednesday 4/11 at 2:00 PM EDT (11:00 AM PDT) or Thursday 4/12 between 2:00 pm and 5:00 pm EDT (11:00 to 2:00 pm PDT), if either would be convenient for you. If neither of these timeframes is convenient, please feel free to suggest others. Please advise us of your availability, and we will arrange a conference line for the call.

Thank you again. We look forward to working with you.

-Allan

From: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org [mailto:Edgar.Schoen@kp.org]
Sent: Sunday, April 01, 2007 16:17
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision forHIVprevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr Taylor - I will be able to present a 20-30 minute paper on costs and effects of neonatal circumcision in the US at the April 26-27 meetings. Please send me details as soon as you can. Thanks, Ed Schoen

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"Taylor, Allan W. \CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP\" <avt0@cdc.gov>

03/29/2007 01:46 PM

To: Edgar Schoen/CA/KAIPERM@KAIPERM
cc:
Subject: RE: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIVprevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr. Schoen,

We are pleased that you will be able to attend the consultation on April 26-27, and we would like to invite you to give a presentation at this meeting regarding the costs and effects of neonatal circumcision. This presentation would be approximately 20-30 minutes in length and would be one of three presentations in a plenary session regarding the potential costs and impacts of male circumcision in the US. We will send further details in the coming weeks if you will be able to present, but we wanted to contact you as early as possible to assess your availability.

Please contact me at your convenience to indicate whether you will be able to present. We look forward to hearing from you and to your participation in this consultation.

Sincerely,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Edgar.Schoen@kp.org [mailto:Edgar.Schoen@kp.org]
Sent: Monday, March 19, 2007 18:00
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Re: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIVprevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr Taylor - I will be happy to attend the meeting on HIV prevention on April 26-27. Thank you for your invitation. I'll look forward to receiving more information.

E. Schoen

NOTICE TO RECIPIENT: If you are not the intended recipient of this e-mail, you are prohibited from sharing, copying, or otherwise using or disclosing its contents. If you have received this e-mail in error, please notify the sender immediately by reply e-mail and permanently delete this e-mail and any attachments without reading, forwarding or saving them. Thank you.

"Taylor, Allan W. \(\CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP\)" <avt0@cdc.gov>

03/16/2007 01:10 PM

To: Edgar Schoen/CA/KAIPERM@KAIPERM
cc: "Sullivan, Patrick \(\CDC/CCID/NCIHSTP\)" <pss0@cdc.gov>
Subject: Save the dates -- CDC consultation on male circumcision for HIV prevention in the US, April 26-27

Dr. Schoen,

CDC will be hosting a consultation to discuss the potential role for male circumcision in HIV prevention in the United States on April 26-27 2007 in Atlanta. We will be providing a more formal invitation to the consultation (including the purposes and charge to the consultants) in the coming weeks, but we wanted to make you aware of the dates as soon as possible. CDC will be providing for your travel expenses and meals.

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We hope that you will be able to participate in this important consultation.

Thank you,

Allan W. Taylor, MD, MPH, FAAP
LCDR, US Public Health Service
Division of HIV/AIDS Prevention, Epidemiology Branch
National Center for HIV/AIDS, Viral Hepatitis, STD, and TB Prevention (proposed)
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
1600 Clifton Rd, NE, MS E-45, Atlanta, GA 30333
W:404.639.6120 / F:404.639.6127 / ataylor2@cdc.gov

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wed, 14 Mar 2007 13:42:37 +0000
To: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Upcoming consultation: Circumcision & US HIV prevention

Both my contacts are out of the office on travel (Ellen Stover, Director of the AIDS program and Willo Pequenat, head of the international AIDS program).

So I opted to google scholar him. By his title and his publications, I'd say he's the right person. I've asked him to call me for a brief chat to confirm. Back at you after that.

Dawn K. Smith

From: Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Wednesday, March 14, 2007 9:21 AM
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: FW: Upcoming consultation: Circumcision & US HIV prevention

Dawn,

Did I remember correctly that you had a contact to check out whether this was the right person to invite from NIMH?

Thanks

Patrick Sullivan, DVM, PhD
Chief, Behavioral and Clinical Surveillance Branch
Divisions of HIV/AIDS Prevention

From: Forsyth, Andrew (NIH/NIMH) [E]
Sent: Wednesday, March 07, 2007 10:39 PM
To: Sullivan, Patrick S. (CDC)
Subject: Upcoming consultation: Circumcision & US HIV prevention

Greetings, Patrick:

I learned today of the CDC consultation in tentatively scheduled for late April to explore the potential role of circumcision in a domestic HIV prevention strategy. I wonder if there's any possibility of other Feds attending as observers. We at NIMH are interested to explore future directions in this area, especially in collaboration with our partners at NIAID and elsewhere.

Would you let me know if there's any chance of attending as an observer? We might also explore the opportunities to collaborate on future initiatives in the area.

Thanks for considering it.

Andrew

Andrew D. Forsyth, Ph.D.

Chief, Primary HIV Prevention & Behavior Change Program

Center for Mental Health Research on AIDS

National Institute of Mental Health

6001 Executive Boulevard, RM 6201, MSC 9619

Bethesda, MD USA 20892-9619

Voice: 301/443-8403

Fax: 301/443-9719

Email: aforsyth@mail.nih.gov

URL: <http://www.nimh.nih.gov> <<http://www.nimh.nih.gov/>>

For Visitors and Federal Express/UPS mailings use:

Rockville, Maryland 20852

Change in Standing Receipt Dates for AIDS and AIDS-related applications for NIH/AHRQ Beginning in May 2007

<http://grants1.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-07-053.html>

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Tue, 27 Mar 2007 15:27:33 +0000
To: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Update: Talk on MC and other health outcomes

That sounds good. Let me check the budget, though. I need to see how many internationals we've got. I'll get back to you.
-Allan

From: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 3:10 PM
To: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: RE: Update: Talk on MC and other health outcomes

Mary,

We asked Bob to do the talk about adverse outcomes and declined because he says he doesn't have time to develop a new talk, particularly given the need to review and include non-African data. I think the same would apply even more so to a talk about other health effects. Ron Gray has already told us he is not available.

So, how about you invite Richard Hayes?

Dawn K. Smith

From: Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2007 3:05 PM
To: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Cc: Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)
Subject: Update: Talk on MC and other health outcomes

Regarding that "Evidence of other health effects of male circumcision talk" (11:30 on the schedule) -- I've pow-wowed with Tom, and we are thinking that even though there are several of us here in DSTDP that could do this talk, for a consultancy of this type it would be much preferable to have an outside "expert" do this. This is especially true for this particular topic, given that so little of the data comes from US federal government (unlike NHANES) and so would need to be distilled from the existing literature (already nicely summarized) and new trials (not yet so nicely summarized, so would essentially be presenting the new data from others at the meeting). We had our own ideas who the best outside folks to do an STD/other outcomes talk would be. But considering all this, wanted to make sure we weren't missing someone additional ... so I re-contacted Stephen Moses to ask him, given he is not available, who he would recommend to give this talk. It turned out that he came back with about the same list of folks as we'd recommend -- most of whom we've invited (see below in black).

If I understand correctly, at the last meeting we thought Bob Bailey (who was going to do that 12 noon slot) may not be the best person for adverse outcomes and was taken off agenda. So **I'm going to recommend we ask Bob to do the talk on other health effects. What do you think about this? and, if it sounds reasonable, would you like me to contact him? (I'd be happy to)** Alternatively we could have Helen add STDs/cancers to her overview and free of some time later on, as there was concern at last meeting about time

You'll see that in addition to the usual suspects, Stephen suggested Xavier Castellsague -- an OK suggestion, but he is primarily a cancer epidemiologist whose group has done secondary analyses that have led to some interesting hypotheses -- I think he has a possibility of taking us off on some tangents. Thus I'd personally put him further down the list and recommend Bob Bailey (or Ron Gray, but he's already talking I think), followed by Helen Weiss or Richard Hayes. I don't think Richard is invited to the meeting -- but he would do about the same type of talk as Helen.

Let me know what you think, and if you agree if you'd like me to contact Bob.

Also, I'm going to be out of the office this coming Friday and won't be able to attend MC meeting - - let me know if you'd like me to send a proxy. Thanks, Mary

Hi Mary,

Not sure if you have tried by colleague Bob Bailey at UIC, who is not an STD expert, but could speak to the STD issue. Another possibility would be Ron Gray, but I expect that he would have already been contacted. Bob's email address is rcbailey@uic.edu. Ron's is rgray@jhsph.edu. Another good choice would be Helen Weiss (or Richard Hayes) from the London School, who has published quite a bit on STIs and HIV. Their addresses are: richard.hayes@lshtm.ac.uk and helen.weiss@lshtm.ac.uk. A good person to talk about male circumcision and HPV and chlamydia would be Xavier Castellsague from Barcelona (xcastellsague@ico.scs.es). Hope that this is helpful. All the best.

Stephen

From: Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP)

Sent: Thursday, March 22, 2007 9:10 AM

To: Birx, Deborah (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Bock, Naomi (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Grohskopf, Lisa A., M.D. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Hutchinson, Angela (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kamb, Mary (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kilmarx, Peter (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Kohmescher, Robert N. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Lee, Chung-Won (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Marks, Gary S. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Mastro, Tim (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); McLean, Catherine (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Moore, Janet (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Nakashima, Allyn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Paxton, Lynn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Peterman, Thomas (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sansom, Stephanie (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Smith, Dawn (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Sullivan, Patrick (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Taylor, Allan W. (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Valleroy, Linda (CDC/CCID/NCHHSTP); Warner, Lee (CDC/CCHP/NCCDPHP)

Subject: Consultation subcommittee meeting 3/16/07 Minutes

Workgroup members:

Attached are brief minutes from last week's consultation planning subcommittee (3/16). Past minutes as well as the most recent invitee list are available here: <M:\SHARE\MC Consultation>

Our next meeting will be at the usual time and place (1:00 Friday 3/23 in Corp Sq Bldg 8, Rm 4A).

Any suggestions or comments are welcome.

Thanks.

-Allan

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